

The Prose Contexts of Eddic Poetry

Primarily in the Fornaldarsögur

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Introduction

The purpose of this thesis is to investigate the following questions:

1. What is the role of eddic verse in its prose contexts, primarily in the *fornaldarsögur*?¹
2. What is the probable status of the long prosimetric form in oral and written Old Norse literature, primarily in the *fornaldarsögur*?

And thirdly, what the above can tell us about the evolutionary relationship of verse and prose in the Old Norse literature. The texts that are the focus of this study are prosimetra – prose texts that include verse:

The...epic form, where prose and verse interact in this manner, has been called prosimetrum by some scholars. In relation to heroic tales, in particular, it is no doubt an important question, whether this form is to be regarded as a development of tales entirely in verse, or whether stories entirely in prose as well as stories composed partly in prose and partly in verse were in existence in addition to the known tales told entirely in verse... Whatever way we look at it, this form, whether we call it prosimetrum or something else, is fundamental to the development of saga literature.²

This is an important topic of study because the origins of the *fornaldarsögur* subgenre are thought to lie in oral prosimetra, and thus such a study of the interaction of prose and verse in the written texts is interesting, since it may suggest oral features that have carried over into the written sagas and may help to clarify the construction of texts in the *fornaldarsögur* subgenre. To this end, examination of the extant sagas can help, to see whether their forms suggest what role verse may have played in their assembly.

In order to provide a more precise sense of the role verses play in the *fornaldarsögur*, I examine the role of verse in the *fornaldarsögur* and, as comparative material, *Gylfaginning*, selected poems from the *Poetic Edda*, and selected texts that are pre-*Snorra Edda*, such as *Íslendingabók*, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, *Sverris saga*, and *Fagrskinna*. I ask whether the way the stanzas are used in these texts (or groups of

¹ The subgenre designation '*fornaldarsaga*' is translated variously in English as 'legendary saga,' 'heroic saga,' 'legendary-heroic saga,' 'mythical-heroic saga,' and 'saga of ancient times' (the most literal translation), the variation reflecting the fact that the sagas contain legendary, heroic, mythical and ancient material, albeit rather mixed together.

² Davíð Erlingsson, "Prose and Verse in Icelandic Legendary Fiction," *The Heroic Process: Form, Function and Fantasy in Folk Epic. The Proceedings of the International Folk Epic Conference University College Dublin 2 – 6 September 1985*, ed. Bo Almqvist, Séamas Ó Catháin and Pádraig Ó Héalaí (Dun Laoghaire: Glendale, 1987) pp. 371-394, at 382.

texts) are similar; if so, how; and what this might tell us. I have picked these types of texts to investigate because they all, with the exception of the pre-*Edda* material, include eddic rather than skaldic verse in their narratives, and it is thus tempting to look for links between them. Material that is pre-*Edda* has been included because this kind of history writing is amongst the earliest writing in Old Norse and it seems likely that it would have influenced subsequent literary production, not least that of Snorri Sturluson, who, as far as can be judged, was responsible for the *Prose Edda*.

Stephen Mitchell has emphasised that the *fornaldarsögur* are “a cultural hybrid, a constellation of (primarily) folkloric and traditional materials and of (secondarily) literary materials, the interpretation of which must depend on the methodological tools of both fields.”³ I examine the relationship between prose and eddic poetry in the *Poetic Edda*, the *Gylfaginning* section of the *Edda* by Snorri Sturluson and in the *fornaldarsögur* [‘sagas of ancient times’] as the written products of a lengthy Old Norse-Icelandic oral tradition. I look at major interpretive and aesthetic differences of the above contexts of eddic verse (defined further below) in order assess whether or not preliterate narration of both the verse and its prose contexts is conceivable, building upon work done by scholars such as Heather O’Donoghue in the use of verse to generate meaning in the prosimetric narratives found in Old Icelandic literature.⁴ I have chosen to compare the prosimetry of the legendary sagas and *Gylfaginning* because *Gylfaginning* was written by an author who likely used oral verses in a written prosimetry. Both the prose and verse of the legendary sagas, on the other hand, can be understood as anonymous, ‘traditional’ narratives, collectively composed and transmitted in oral tradition before they were written down, and the content of which still circulated orally after versions has been committed to writing.

³ Stephen A. Mitchell, *Heroic Sagas and Ballads*, Myth and Poetics (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1991), p. 43. See also Jesse L. Byock, “The *Fornaldarsögur*: Stephen Mitchell’s Contribution,” *Oral Tradition* 10.2 (1995): 451-457.

⁴ See her books *The Genesis of a Saga Narrative: Verse and Prose in Kormaks saga*, Oxford English Monographs (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1991) and *Skaldic Verse and the Poetics of Saga Narrative* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005). Cf. Theodore M. Andersson, “Verse and Prose in Old Norse-Icelandic,” *Medievalia et Humanistica* 19 (1992): 197-210.

In order to answer my overarching questions of the role of eddic verse in prose contexts, the status of the long prose form and what this might suggest about the evolutionary relationship between prose and verse, I will use the following questions to formulate my investigation:

- How does the prosimetrum of the *Poetic Edda* function?
- How is eddic verse used in the compositional strategies of *Gylfaginning* and the *fornaldarsögur*?
- How does the citation of eddic verse generate meaning in these prose narratives and what can it tell us?
- What role does poetry play in the structuring of the *fornaldarsögur* narratives?

The thesis falls into four parts. What constitutes eddic poetry is discussed in the first part, “Approaches to Old Norse Eddic Prosimetrum,” and the oral background of eddic poetry and the sagas is explored, and a review of the earlier scholarship surrounding the origin of the saga genre in general is included, paying particular attention to the role of stanzas, since many of the perspectives common in modern philological practices, such as the rise of Oral Theory, can be shown to have their roots in the early studies of the discipline. Part One continues with a discussion of the roles the prose plays in the two medieval manuscripts of the eddic poetry collection. Part One concludes with an examination of early Nordic prosimetra, texts selected from material that is likely to be pre- *Snorra Edda*, in order frame the examination of the prosimetra in *Gylfaginning* and in the *fornaldarsögur* in Parts Two and Three. A discussion of the relationship of Saxo Grammaticus’ *Gesta Danorum* to the works that some of the work covered in the thesis is included, focusing mainly on his direct prosimetric links with the Icelandic material.⁵ The section on “Approaches” is

⁵ During the thesis itself I make only minimal reference to Saxo Grammaticus, whose work the *Gesta Danorum* often includes stories that are clearly related to those found in some of the *fornaldarsögur*. Equally versed in the Latin and Old Norse poetic traditions, part of Saxo’s achievement was to translate simple, alliterative, vernacular poetry into Latin hexameter, whilst using Old Norse material as a source in other ways besides. Much of this source material seems to have been both prosaic and poetic material very much akin to that preserved in the legendary sagas. Since the point of my project is to explore the prosimetra of the narratives as extant, I have not made substantial reference to Saxo in the course of my analysis of the individual legendary sagas, also his work is of course pertinent to the substance of the stories in the *fornaldarsögur* were one to undertake a study of narrative transformations of vernacular Nordic literature.

concluded with an analysis of how previous scholars have classified the roles that verse can take within prose and how this is built upon in the present project.

The second part of the thesis, “Generating Meaning and the Eddic Poetry of *Gylfaginning*,” is an analysis of the first part of the 13th century *Snorra Edda* as a written Old Norse prosimetrum and an examination of how the quotation of stanzas from poems now found collected in the *Poetic Edda* into the text *Gylfaginning* generates the structure of the text, within the broader framework of analysing the rhetorical strategy of *Gylfaginning*. Theoretically, the section draws on intertextuality. *Gylfaginning*’s place in the *Edda* as a whole is discussed, and suggests that the existing theory on the significance of each part of the *Edda* and the order of composition of the parts ought perhaps to be reexamined. An analysis of the prosimetric structure of *Gylfaginning* as whole is presented, beginning from the text’s construction of a question-and-answer sequence and demonstrating ways in which Snorri’s contact with a Latin education may have influenced its structure.

The consideration of compositional strategies in narrative continues in Part Three, which focuses on the legendary sagas containing verse.⁶ Each saga is considered separately, and readings from different manuscripts are introduced from the apparatus of critical editions, occasionally supplemented by referring to the manuscripts themselves. It is beyond the scope of the project to delve deeply into the manuscript tradition of each *fornaldarsaga* or to leave the confines of critical editions, but a general presentation of the major manuscripts of each saga is included. Sagas with particularly complex textual traditions are treated in more detail, notably *Qrvar-Odds saga*.

The methodology behind the thesis is broadly New Philological, and the method can be summarised as close reading of the context of a stanza in the prose. In

⁶ This thesis is about eddic style poetry in its prose contexts. Although some of these prose contexts are rather short and terse, the majority of the prose contexts are extended fictional narratives, mythological, in the case of *Gylfaginning*, or from the *fornaldarsögur*. Since this thesis explores the interaction of verse and prose in these narrative contexts, in order to control the boundaries of the dissertation I have maintained a focus on those sagas actually only containing eddic verse, and thus have left out of the analysis formally related sagas such as *Ynglinga saga* (for more on this, see below), and whilst primacy in terms of narrative importance is assumed for neither prose nor verse, *fornaldarsögur* that do not include eddic material have also been excluded.

terms of verse quotation, I analyse how, when, why and by whom the stanzas are quoted in the prose. The idea of “ethnopoetics” put forward by John Miles Foley, that we should aim to read “according to the poet’s and tradition’s “way of speaking” rather than our own”⁷ has been influential in my way of thinking, as has much else in Foley’s other writings. My orientation in Oral Theory and its application to Old Norse texts is shaped by the work of Else Mundal and Gísli Sigurðsson in particular;⁸ nevertheless, I do not adhere strictly to any particular strand of theory and remain wary of the limitations of Oral Theory, particularly the temptation to promote comparisons between unrelated oral cultures.

The references in the thesis are formatted in accordance with the MLA handbook (6th edition), using a slightly modified footnote and works cited system, with a short footnote.⁹ The full reference can be found in the bibliography. The font used is AndronScriptorHB51. The term “audience” ought to be taken to mean both the spectators and auditors at recitations of poems or sagas, and readers of the text in the manuscript or auditors of these readings.¹⁰ I use the term “text” in a comprehensive manner, to include not only the idea of the “work” as well as each example of the work’s singular physical manifestation in manuscript form and also to represent an oral performance of the work.¹¹ A saga “author,” “writer” or “compiler” should likewise be understood in a wide sense. I use these terms out of necessity to name the force behind the existence of a manuscript copy of a work, or of a version of

⁷ John Miles Foley, *How To Read an Oral Poem* (Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 2002) 33. See especially pp. 95-108.

⁸ See, for example, Else Mundal, “Oral or Scribal Variation in *Völuspá*: A Case Study in Old Norse Poetry.” *Oral Art Forms and their Passage into Writing*, ed. Else Mundal and Jonas Wellendorf (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanum Press, 2008) pp. 209-227; “Snorri og *Völuspá*,” *Snorrastefna, 25.–27. júlí 1990*, ed. Úlfar Bragason, Rit Stofnunar Sigurðar Nordals 1 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Sigurðar Nordals, 1992) pp. 180-192; Gísli Sigurðsson, *The Medieval Icelandic Saga and Oral Tradition: A Discourse on Method*, Publications of the Milman Parry Collection of Oral Literature 2 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard UP, 2004); “Orality Harnessed: How to Read Written Sagas from an Oral Culture?” *Oral Art Forms and their Passage into Writing*, ed. Else Mundal and Jonas Wellendorf (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanum Press, 2008) pp. 19-28.

⁹ Joseph Gibaldi, *MLA Handbook for Writers of Research Papers*, 6th ed. (New York: The Modern Language Association of America, 2003).

¹⁰ Cf. Carolyne Larrington, *A Store of Common Sense: Gnomie Theme and Style in Old Icelandic and Old English Wisdom Poetry* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1998) 19.

¹¹ Cf. Robert Kellogg, “What is a Saga?” *Sagnaþing: helgað Jónasi Kristjánssyni sjötugum 10. apríl 1994*, vol. 2 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska bókmenntafélag, 1994) pp. 497-503, esp. p. 503.

a work, without committing myself to the modern connotations of ownership and copyright conveyed by the word “author.”

I have assumed the reader has a reading knowledge of Old Norse. I provide a translation of the Old Norse into English when it aids in making my point clearer. Published translations I have used are cited in a footnote. Translations without a citation I have translated myself.

Part One: Approaches to Old Norse Eddic Prosimetrum

Prose texts that contain eddic poetry can be described as ‘eddic prosimetra.’ The borderline for the inclusion of material considered in this thesis lies between eddic and skaldic poetry: eddic material is included, skaldic is not.¹² The question of what constitutes eddic poetry is thus a foundational consideration.

Poems that are found outside the manuscript GkS 2364 4to, the Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda*, are termed ‘eddic’ by virtue of their similarity with the poems contained in this anthology. Almost all of the eddic poems are preserved in a prosimetric context, but the poems that make up the corpus of eddic poetry can be more precisely divided into three groups depending on what type of context they are preserved in. The first group is the poems of the *Poetic Edda*, found in GkS 2365 4to (the Codex Regius of the *Poetic Edda*) and the fragment AM 748 4to of the *Poetic Edda*. These are both poetic manuscripts with some prose framing and occasional prose inserts between the stanzas. The second group of eddic poetry is the poetry preserved in the *fornaldarsögur* (known as the *eddic minora*), which are prose narratives containing eddic verse.¹³ The third group, called the “eddic appendix” by Joseph Harris,¹⁴ is a mixed group made up of eddic poems preserved singularly in manuscripts (for example in *Flateyjarbók*), and the other snippets of eddic poems we find preserved.¹⁵ The poetry in the second and third groups is deemed ‘eddic’ because it is similar to the poetry in the first group both in metre and in content.

¹² With the exception of the few skaldic stanzas found in the *fornaldarsögur*.

¹³ This is often called the *eddic minora* after an edition that published most of it: *Eddica minora. Dichtungen eddischer Art aus den Fornaldarsögur und anderen Prosawerken*, ed. Andreas Heusler and Wilhelm Ranisch (Dortmund: Ruhfus, 1903).

¹⁴ “Eddic Poetry,” *Old Norse-Icelandic Literature: A Critical Guide*, ed. Carol J. Clover and John Lindow, *Islandica* 45 (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1985) pp. 68-156, at 68.

¹⁵ Counted among the eddic appendix by Harris are *Hyndluljóð* (some of which at least was known to Snorri as *Völuspá in skamma*), *Hljóðskviða*, *Grottasöngur*, *Svipdagsmál* and *Hildibrand's Death-Song*. I would extract *Hljóðskviða* from this group, since it is preserved only in a *fornaldarsaga* (*Hervarar saga*), and thus should be considered to be in that category.

The three groups of eddic poetry can be thought of as different styles of eddic poetry. Prior studies have noted the likelihood that the eddic poetry in the Poetic Edda, the eddic poetry in the *fornaldarsögur* and the eddic quotations in *Gylfaginning* are linked. Often, this is expressed as a developmental relationship, for example Torfi H. Tulinius states: “The legendary sagas arise out of a narrative tradition that is older than they are and is to some extent common to all the Scandinavian peoples, namely the heroic poems of the Elder Edda.”¹⁶ Otherwise, stylistic similarities have been highlighted in the method of presentation, Lars Lönnroth commenting that “several Eddic lays are also presented within the framework of a *fornaldarsaga*,”¹⁷ a statement that also indicates a possible genetic relationship. The eddic poetry found in three prose contexts then likely forms a continuum rather than each type existing separately in distinct types of context, and the differences between the types of poetry can be explained in terms of style shifting due to differing contexts of the verse.

¹⁶ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North: The Rise of Literary Fiction in Thirteenth-Century Iceland*, trans. Randi C. Eldevik, The Viking Collection 13 ([Odense]: Odense University Press, 2002) 19.

¹⁷ Lars Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga,” *Religion, Myth, and Folklore in the World’s Epics: The Kalevala and its Predecessors*, ed. Lauri Honko, Religion and Society 30 (Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 1990) pp. 73-92, at p. 75.

Eddic Verse

An examination of the nature of eddic verse is relevant to my discussion of the prosimetra in the *fornaldarsögur* because this saga subgenre is aligned with eddic verse rather than skaldic, and so the character of eddic verse itself is a foundational consideration. Eddic verse can be thought of as a suitable metre to include in the *fornaldarsögur* since both the prose and often the verse are used to tell of events in the far past. However, eddic metres are also used in a range of situations unrelated to the *fornaldarsögur*. Likewise, some *fornaldarsögur* contain verse in skaldic metre, and this section demonstrates why neither of these alternative uses should not be thought of as either surprising or problematic. This indicates that in oral and written prosimetra, which metre of verse is used is dictated to large extent by the traditional connotations associated with the verse, tempered by the demands of the prose context.

The verse contained within the Old Norse prosimetra is traditionally separated into two types: eddic and skaldic. ‘Eddic’ denotes both a metre and a style of poetry and as such is a “literary label”;¹⁸ the other type of poetic metre and style found in Old Norse is termed ‘skaldic,’ and these two poetic types can often be described in dichotomous terms, for example the eddic author is anonymous, the skaldic author is named; the eddic metre is simple, the skaldic complex; if we accept this construction of what Hermann Pálsson censures as a “simplistic dichotomy,”¹⁹ this suggests that eddic metres should, to some extent, be defined against the skaldic metres, both formally and functionally, and indeed, this has been the standard manner by which to divide the two types of poetry in an analytical manner in scholarship. Such a division was eloquently attempted by Andreas Heusler in 1937, when he lists the characteristics of eddic poetry:

¹⁸ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda: MS No. 2365 4to in the old Royal Collection in the Royal Library of Copenhagen*, intro. Andreas Heusler, trans. Leonard Forster, *Corpus Codicum Islandicorum Medii Aevi* 10 (Copenhagen: Einar Munksgaard, 1937) 13.

¹⁹ Hermann Pálsson, “Towards a Classification of Early Icelandic Poetry,” *Atti del 12^o Congresso Internazionale di Studi sull’alto medioevo: Poetry in the Scandinavian Middle Ages, The Seventh International Saga Conference* (Spoleto: Centro Italiano di Studi sull’alto medioevo, 1990) pp. 59-65, at 59.

- 1) “The genres are objective; there is no personal work, no occasional or topical poetry.
- 2) The tradition is anonymous; borrowings from predecessors can thus be made with impunity and there is no demand for originality.
- 3) The old Teutonic metrical forms and poetic ornaments hold the field. The filling of the verse may develop from this stage, but progress only a short way towards separate verse forms.
- 4) The language differs from prose less than that of the skalds as regards choice of words, use of kennings and word transpositions.”²⁰

This separation seems to be confirmed by the fact that certain metres are associated with certain saga subgenres. The metre of the verse is not bound to a particular poetic genre, and *fornyrðislag* could be used for court poetry, epic, riddles and spell verses. However, this is only of the content that the verse itself expresses. The meter of the verse is linked to the type of narrative in which the verse is bound – the prose context. The prosimetric *fornaldarsögur* tend to contain verse in the eddic metre, while the *Íslendingasögur* and *konungasögur* tend to contain verse in the skaldic metre (or at least verse in the skaldic style).

There are similarities and differences between eddic and skaldic metres. Skaldic metres are more complex and particular than eddic, and are by a named poet as opposed to the anonymity of the extant eddic poetry.²¹ Although Kristján Árnason concludes in his study of the Old Norse poetic metres that “Eddic and skaldic poetry coexisted in a tradition which made use of essentially the same rhymical means,”²² metre is one dividing mechanism between the different types of poetry: the skaldic form is the stricter of the two, the eddic form being far more relaxed in terms of rhythm and variation in the number of syllables, although still with regular

²⁰ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Heusler, pp. 12-13.

²¹ Clive Tolley, “Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse,” *The Kalevala and the World's Traditional Epics*, ed. Lauri Honko, *Studia Fennica Folkloristica* 12 (Helsinki: Finnish Literature Society, 2002) pp. 128-35, at p. 131.

²² Kristján Árnason, *The Rhythms of Dróttkvætt and Other Old Icelandic Metres* (Reykjavík: Institute of Linguistics, University of Iceland, 1991) 172.

alliteration.²³ The standard metre of skaldic poetry is *dróttkvætt* [‘court metre’], which has a six syllable line.²⁴ Like skaldic poetry, eddic poetry is stanzaic, although the stanzas can be of irregular length. Eddic poetry is also characterised by alliteration and formulaicity.²⁵

It is common to use a number of formal and functional criteria to distinguish between eddic and skaldic poetry,²⁶ a typical description might run thus: on the whole, verse in eddic metre and eddic style is anonymous, whereas verse in the skaldic style is rarely anonymous. Eddic poetry is often not set in a particular period of time, or focuses on events from the past, whereas skaldic-style verse focuses on contemporary events. Eddic poetry tends to treat heroic, gnomic and mythological themes, whereas skaldic-style verse frequently praises, honours or eulogises a chieftain or a ruler. The content of eddic poetry is “common property, rooted in oral tradition,”²⁷ whereas skalds were conscious of the creative process and tried to leave their mark on the stanzas.²⁸ Eddic poetry relates the heroic and mythological themes in a fairly straight-

²³ Kristján Árnason, *The Rhythms of Dróttkvætt*, p. 45. For a full overview of the metrics of eddic and skaldic verse, see Else Mundal, “Edda- og skaldediktning,” *Handbok i norrøn filologi*, ed. Odd Einar Haugen (Bergen: Fagbokforlaget, 2004) 215-266, at 224-231 and 246-247 and Eduard Sievers, *Altgermanische Metrik*, Kurzer Grammatiken Germanischer Dialekte 2 (Halle: Max Niemeyer, 1893) pp. 62-91 for eddic verse and pp. 91-118 for skaldic.

²⁴ There are also variants of the metre. Margaret Clunies Ross, *A History of Old Norse Poetry and Poetics* (Cambridge: Brewer, 2005) 21-22. For the metrics of *dróttkvætt*, see Sievers, *Altgermanische Metrik*, pp. 98-105, and for variations on *dróttkvætt* and other skaldic metres, see pp. 105-118.

²⁵ For more on the terminology and structure of skaldic poetry, see Sievers, *Altgermanische Metrik*, pp. 91-98; Nitalu Sroka, *The Syllable – Evidence from Icelandic Skaldic Poetry*, unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Hawaii, 1990: pp. 6-10, 21-24; Kari Ellen Gade, *The Structure of Old Norse Dróttkvætt Poetry*, *Islandica* 49 (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1995). For a recent study of the eddic metre see Kristján Árnason, “The Rise of the Quatrain in Germanic: Musicality and Word Based Rhythm in Eddic Meters,” *Formal Approaches to Poetry: Recent Developments in Metrics*, ed. B. Elan Dresher and Nila Friedberg, *Phonology and Phonetics* 11 (Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 2006) pp. 151-169. For the cultural aspects of skaldic poetry, see Kevin J. Wanner, *Snorri Sturluson and the Edda: The Conversion of Cultural Capital in Medieval Scandinavia*, *Toronto Old Norse and Icelandic Studies* (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2008) pp. 6, 57-65. For overviews of Old Germanic versification as a whole, see Sievers, *Altgermanische Metrik* which laid the groundwork for later discussions, e.g. Geoffrey Russom, *Beowulf and Old Germanic Metre*, *Cambridge Studies in Anglo-Saxon England* 23 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998).

²⁶ Gade, *The Structure of Old Norse Dróttkvætt Poetry*, p. 1.

²⁷ Gade, *The Structure of Old Norse Dróttkvætt Poetry*, p. 2.

²⁸ One early approach in this vein is by Axel Olrik in 1917, in which he discusses the status of mythology in eddic and skaldic poetry and these forms’ use as sources. His discussion runs counter to the standard account of the differences between the forms, which is that eddic poetry is anonymous and traditional in source, whereas skaldic poetry is individualistic and by a named author. Olrik argues that it is eddic poetry that is individualistic and personal, and that skaldic poetry is impersonal and traditional in its “mythological expression.” See Axel Olrik, “Eddamytologien,” *Nordisk tidskrift för vetenskap, konst och industri* (1917): 81-93. While overall Olrik’s assessment does not hold, John Lindow and suggest that his characterisation in

forward style, whereas skaldic-style poetry uses the same mythological and heroic themes as the basis for complex kennings. While skaldic metre counts syllables, the eddic form tends to be in freer measures; stresses and not syllables or line-endings are counted. The eddic metres *fornyrðislag* and *málaháttr* developed so that syllables did begin to be counted; this was probably under the influence of the skalds.²⁹ Both eddic and skaldic poems are around the same length and are stanzaic, although the older eddic poetry can be in loose strophe form with strophes of varying lengths. This developed into an eight line strophe with a deep caesura after the fourth line, also probably under the influence of the skalds,³⁰ since skaldic metre is in strict strophe form.³¹

Nevertheless, there are a number of factors that militate against the appositeness of this two part division of the Old Norse verse structure. The difficulty of drawing a sharp lines between the eddic and skaldic has most eloquently been recognised in recent scholarship by the acknowledgement of Dan Ben-Amos's formulization of ethnic genres and analytic categories.³² These two categories, which distinguish between the genre system as experienced by members of the culture (ethnic categories) and the categories established by scholars (analytic categories), was first used in an Old Norse context by Joseph Harris in the mid-1970s,³³ and given a fresh perspective by Bernt Øyvind Thorvaldsen in his 2006 analysis of the formulaic

terms of religious expression of skaldic poetry being traditional and formal and eddic poetry being the form in which individual religious expression might more readily have found a home as likely to be correct. See John Lindow, "Myth and Mythography," *Old Norse-Icelandic Literature: A Critical Guide*, ed. Carol J. Clover and John Lindow, *Islandica* 45 (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1985) 21-67, at 32; Marius Kristensen, "Skjaldenes mytologi," *Acta Philologica Scandinavica* 5 (1930-1931): 67-92, at 67.

²⁹ E. O. G. Turville-Petre, *Scaldic Poetry* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1976) xiii.

³⁰ Turville-Petre, *Scaldic Poetry*, pp. xiii; for an alternative view see Kristján Árnason, "The Rise of the Quatrain in Germanic Musicality."

³¹ Lee Hollander, *The Skalds: A Selection of the Poems, with Introductions and Notes* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1945) pp. 1-2, 18; Turville-Petre, *Scaldic Poetry*, pp. xii-xvii; Gade, *The Structure of Old Norse Dróttkvætt Poetry*, pp. 1-2.

³² Dan Ben-Amos, "Analytical categories and ethnic genres" *Folklore genres*, ed. Dan Ben-Amos (Austin and London: University of Texas Press, 1976) pp. 215-242. [Originally published in *Genre* 1 (1969): 273-301.]

³³ Joseph Harris, "Genre in the Saga Literature: A Squib," *Scandinavian Studies* 47 (1975): 427-436.

aspect of eddic poems in Old Norse poetic tradition.³⁴ Despite the obvious attractions for modern scholars of attempting to adopt a genre system and a terminological vocabulary based on ethnic genres, it is not always easy to separate ethnic genres from analytical categories,³⁵ nor is it possible to extract an ethnic genre system that we can be sure was “experienced by members of the culture,” as described by Joseph Harris.³⁶

The first objection to the analytical method of dividing eddic and skaldic verse based on metre is that a large amount of what is conventionally thought of as skaldic verse is found in eddic metre. The most common eddic metre is *fornyrðislag* [‘ancient story metre’] which is the common Germanic form; other derivative eddic metres are *málaháttur* [‘speech metre’], *ljóðaháttur* [‘song metre’] and *galdralag* [‘spell metre’].³⁷ Despite it being an eddic metre, Margaret Clunies Ross,³⁸ following Anthony Faulkes,³⁹ has pointed out that *fornyrðislag* is the second most common metre in the corpus of skaldic poetry published by Finnur Jónsson.⁴⁰ Consequently the metre cannot be the sole determining factor for whether a stanza is eddic or skaldic, but, as Thorvaldsen notes, the choice of metre for the verse and what kind of poetic language (e.g. kennings) is used is obviously part of the ethnic process of literary composition,⁴¹

³⁴ Bernt Øyvind Thorvaldsen, “Svá er sagt í fornum vísindum: Tekstualiseringin av de mytologiske eddadikt,” Doctoral thesis, 30th June 2006, University of Bergen. Esp. pp. 35-48.

³⁵ Thorvaldsen, “Svá er sagt,” p. 36.

³⁶ Harris, “Genre in the Saga Literature,” p. 427. Ruth Finnegan also notes that ethnic genre categories do not always match ethnic terminology and attempts at taxonomy, *Oral Traditions and the Verbal Arts: A Guide to Research Practices*, ASA Research Methods in Social Anthropology (London: Routledge, 1992) 138. Guðrún Nordal makes the important point that “medieval scholars of vernacular metrics, such as the authors of *Háttalykill* and *Háttatal*, did not distinguish between skaldic and eddic meters in their analysis of the metrical system.” “Metrical Learning and the *First Grammatical Treatise*,” *Versatility in Versification: Multidisciplinary Approaches to Metrics*, ed. Frog & Tonya Kim Dewey, Berkeley Insights in Linguistics and Semiotics 74 (New York: Peter Lang, 2009) pp. 23-37, at p. 26, fn. 7.

³⁷ For a discussion of the metrics of each of these eddic metres, see Sievers, *Altgermanische Metrik*, pp. 62-70 for *fornyrðislag*, 70-79 for *málaháttur*, 79-90 for *ljóðsháttur* and *galdralag*.

³⁸ Clunies Ross, *A History of Old Norse Poetry and Poetics*, p. 22.

³⁹ Clunies Ross, *A History of Old Norse Poetry and Poetics*, p. 22; Snorri Sturluson, *Edda: Háttatal*, ed. Anthony Faulkes (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1999) p. 83.

⁴⁰ *Den norsk-islandske skjaldedigtning, A: Tekst efter håndskrifterne; B: Rettet tekst*, ed. Finnur Jónsson (Copenhagen: Villadsen & Christensen, 1912-1915).

⁴¹ Thorvaldsen, “Svá er sagt,” pp. 39-40.

even though these categories are also used in constructing analytical classifications.⁴² In terms of prosimetrum, this indicates that the preference for eddic verse in the *fornaldarsögur* is an ethnic one, even though the division of *fornaldarsögur* from other kinds of saga subgenre can largely be considered an analytic one. This might suggest that the division of the prosimetric *fornaldarsögur* from non-prosimetric *fornaldarsögur* could be an ethnic one.

The use of skaldic or eddic metre is to an extent dictated by subject matter and narrative use, but, as Judy Quinn has noted,⁴³ there are many stanzas that occupy a

⁴² See further Clunies Ross, *A History of Old Norse Poetry and Poetics*, pp. 21-28. It should be noted that it is impossible in some instances to draw a hard and fast line between whether a poem is skaldic or eddic. A mixed skaldic-eddic style sometimes appears. This is found, for example, in the poems *Eiríksmál* (anonymous), Eyvindr Skáldspillir's *Hákonarmál* and Þorbjörn Hornklofi's *Haraldskvæði* (also known as *Hrafnsmál*), as they are composed in eddic metres but have skaldic content. *Haraldskvæði* has the typical skaldic trait of being by a named poet and celebrates a contemporary prince yet mixes the straight-forward expressions of eddic poetry and the complex diction of the skalds. Furthermore, the poem is in the eddic metres *málabáttur* and *ljóðabáttur* and its frame-setting resembles some eddic poems, as it is a dialogue between a raven and a valkyrie; see G. Turville-Petre, *Origins of Icelandic Literature*, (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1953) 38-39. *Eiríksmál* is similar. It is also in dialogue form and uses mainly the *ljóðabáttur* metre. Although it is a commemorative poem and has been described as "solemn and serious," it uses eddic diction and syntax rather than a turgid and dense skaldic style; see Turville-Petre, *Origins of Icelandic Literature*, p. 39. Eyvindr's *Hákonarmál* has been influenced by *Eiríksmál* and several other eddic poems. It too is a commemorative poem, and remembers Hákon the Good who was killed in 962 in the eddic metres *málabáttur* and *ljóðabáttur*. Opinion is thus divided as to whether these should be classified as skaldic or eddic poems: Kari Ellen Gade notes these poems are the exception rather than the rule and describes them as "panegyric poems" in the eddic corpus; see Gade, *The Structure of Old Norse Dróttkvætt Poetry*, p. 1. Hollander, however, considers that the poems wholly disqualify themselves from the skaldic category by virtue of their content and partially by their sometimes dialogic form: "Skaldic poetry is not elegiac-epic, i.e. it does not tell a story or dwell on mournful reflections, as does so much of West Germanic poetry; nor is it dramatic-dialogue like the Old High German *Hiltibrantsliet* and so many Eddic Lays – in fact, this difference is the very touchstone of Skaldic poetry." Hollander, *The Skalds*, pp. 18-19. According to Hollander, *Eiríksmál*, *Hákonarmál* and *Haraldskvæði* thus "by definition ... emphatically are not skaldic"; see Hollander, *The Skalds*, p. 19 fn. 25. See also Bernt Øyvind Thorvaldsen, "The Generic Aspect of the Eddic Style," *Old Norse Religion in Long-Term Perspectives: Origins, Changes and Interactions, An International Conference in Lund, Sweden, June 3-7, 2004*, Väger till Midgård 8 (Lund: Nordic Academic Press, 2006) pp. 276-279.

Caught at a similarly troubling intersection of the eddic and skaldic forms is *Darraðljóð*, whose metre and subject matter are eddic but given a precise historical context typical of the skaldic form; see Karsten Friis-Jensen, *Saxo Grammaticus as Latin Poet: Studies in the Verse Passages of the Gesta Danorum*, *Analecta Romana Instituti Danici*, Supplementum 14 (Rome: L'Erma di Bretschneider, 1987) 45. The metre *kviðubáttur* causes similar problems, resembling eddic *fornyrðislag* in its stricter forms more closely than the *dróttkvætt*, since it alternates between three and four syllables per line rather than four; see Turville-Petre, *Origins of Icelandic Literature*, p. 34, and in contrast to the six strict syllables per half-line found in *dróttkvætt*; see Hollander, *The Skalds*, p. 9. In *Ynglinga saga*, the *kviðubáttur* poem *Ynglingatal* appears as split up into units serving as evidence for its accompanying section of prose. The content too is similar to that of the *fornaldarsögur*, and the saga occasionally makes appearances in discussions of the *fornaldarsögur* corpus. Mitchell, for example, considers *Ynglinga saga* one of the earlier examples of a *fornaldarsögur* type narrative; see Mitchell, *Heroic Sagas and Ballads*, pp. 18, 104. *Ynglingatal*, *Eiríksmál*, *Hákonarmál*, *Haraldskvæði* and *Darraðljóð* thus exemplify the impossibility of drawing absolute distinctions between the eddic and skaldic genres and corpuses. For several recent discussions about the relationship of *Ynglinga saga* to the *fornaldarsögur*, see Jon Gunnar Jørgensen, "Ynglinga saga mellom fornaldersaga og kongesaga," *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighet. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, eds. Agnete Ney, Ármann Jakobsson & Annette Lassen (København: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 49-59 and Else Mundal, "Ynglinga saga ok genreproblematikken," *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighet. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, eds. Agnete Ney, Ármann Jakobsson & Annette Lassen (København: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 61-65.

⁴³ Judy Quinn, "The Use of Eddic Poetry in Contemporary Sagas" *Frá suðlegri strönd (From a Southern Shore)* 3 (1987): 54-72. This grey area has led Hermann Pálsson to call for a rejection of the modern scholarly division between eddic and skaldic and instead classify verse "on the subject matter and purpose of each individual poem," in "Towards a Classification of Early

grey area in between: skaldic metre can occur, for example, where we might expect eddic, and eddic metres might be found in contexts that usually employ skaldic metres. In her study on the eddic stanzas of the prosimetric Contemporary sagas, Quinn shows that while men actively engaged in the drama of the sagas speak *lausavísur* in *dróttkvætt* measure, the verses spoken in dreams and by supernatural figures (valkyries and ravens, for example), are in eddic metre.⁴⁴ However, a number of stanzas cross these lines, and she finds stanzas in dreams in *dróttkvætt*, and anonymous *dróttkvætt* stanzas in the narrative that function in the same manner as *lausavísur* composed by saga characters.⁴⁵ Likewise, we find in the *fornaldarsögur* predominantly eddic stanzas included in the narrative, but a number of skaldic stanzas appear when we might expect eddic metre, for example in *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*. Formal criteria, author self-identification and genre norms are not then sole determining features of whether a skaldic or eddic stanza is employed at a certain moment. Quinn suggests that in order to gain an extra dimension to our classification of stanzas as eddic or skaldic we must also take into consideration the “functional definition of each type of poetry” rather than the formal features.⁴⁶ This functional definition is “based on the voice of the verse,”⁴⁷ and in Quinn’s breakdown, takes into account the following factors: “its identity,” “the conventions surrounding it,” “the authority it lends the content of the verse,” and “the function of the verse in the text,”⁴⁸ that is to say, the prosimetric context of a stanza is all-important.

Thorvaldsen notes that both the anonymity of the eddic poetry and the difference in the use of poetic language in skaldic and eddic poetry also cannot be used

Icelandic Poetry,” p. 61. But, to a large extent this coincides with the use of either skaldic or eddic metre and has no advantages over recognising that formal and functional aspects of verse must be considered in tandem. Medieval poets must have preferred either skaldic or eddic metre for their compositions for a reason.

⁴⁴ Quinn, “The Use of Eddic Poetry in Contemporary Sagas,” p. 54.

⁴⁵ Quinn, “The Use of Eddic Poetry in Contemporary Sagas” p. 54.

⁴⁶ Quinn, “The Use of Eddic Poetry in Contemporary Sagas” p. 54.

⁴⁷ Quinn, “The Use of Eddic Poetry in Contemporary Sagas” p. 55.

⁴⁸ Quinn, “The Use of Eddic Poetry in Contemporary Sagas” p. 55.

to divide eddic and skaldic poetry in a satisfactory way as ethnic categories. It is possible to find anonymous skaldic poetry.⁴⁹ Although there is a chance that the association of the name of the author with the verse may have been lost over time, this should not be assumed. In terms of poetic language, skaldic verse is identified as having complex, unnatural syntax and using kennings, and eddic poetry simple, prose-like syntax. Thorvaldsen provides the examples of *Ynglingatal* and *Háleygjatal* as skaldic poems in relatively simple poetic language, while *Alvíssmál* and *Hymiskviða* contain kennings.⁵⁰

Another way of distinguishing eddic poetry from skaldic is to view eddic poems as those stylistically analogous with those poems preserved in the *Poetic Edda*,⁵¹ and from this, Joseph Harris ascertains that the poems of the Poetic Edda, the so-called eddic appendix and the *eddic minora* all belong to the same field of study.⁵² However, Rudolf Simek and Hermann Pálsson instead view the *eddic minora* of the *fornaldarsögur* as a group inbetween eddic and skaldic poetry.⁵³ This is likely because of the preponderance of situational stanzas in the sagas, which are of a more ‘skaldic’ style:

The situational verse portrayed in saga literature appears to be a natural extension of genres of skaldic poetry as characterized by reflecting the perspective of the poet, his relationships and personal experiences – the same features which appear to underlie attributions of authorship and the persistence of verses in relation to anecdotes and/or contextualizing information, distinguishing ‘skaldic’ poetry from anonymous ‘eddic’ genres of established narratives, riddles, proverbs, etc.⁵⁴

⁴⁹ Diana Whaley comments on the special difficulty of determining the role of verse in saga prose for an anonymous skaldic stanza; see Diana Whaley, “Skalds and Situational Verses in Heimskringla,” *Snorri Sturluson. Kolloquium anlässlich der 750. Wiederkehr seines Todestages*, ed. Alois Wolf (Tübingen: Narr, 1993) pp. 245-266, at p. 253, fn. 16.

⁵⁰ Thorvaldsen, “Svá er sagt,” p. 38.

⁵¹ Harris, “Eddic Poetry,” p. 69.

⁵² Harris, “Eddic Poetry,” p. 68.

⁵³ Rudolf Simek and Hermann Pálsson, *Lexikon der altnordischen Literatur*, Kröners Taschenausgabe 490 (Stuttgart: Alfred Kröner Verlag, 1987) p. 64.

⁵⁴ Frog, “Speech-Acts in Skaldic Verse: Genre, Compositional Strategies and Improvisation,” *Versatility in Versification: Multidisciplinary Approaches to Metrics*, ed. Frog & Tonya Kim Dewey, Berkeley Insights in Linguistics and Semiotics 74 (New York: Peter Lang, 2009) pp. 223-246 at pp. 227-228.

The *eddic minora* is thus viewed as between eddic and skaldic style poetry because it contains stanzas in the eddic metre used in a manner which is associated more closely with the way in which skaldic verse is used. However, it must be noted that it is the prose context, as the carrier of the anecdote to which the stanza is related and conveying the name of the poet is crucial here in determining that the eddic verses are indeed used in a ‘skaldic’ context of named attribution and embedded in the personal experiences of the speaker. This suggests to me that the so-called ‘skaldic’ style of using an eddic stanza might be better reframed as the ‘prosimetric style’ of using such a verse. By using a verse in a *fornaldarsaga* as a situational verse and having it spoken by a named speaker in a particular context, the stanza is not being used in a skaldic style but in a way that it is simply suitable for a prose narrative.

The *fornaldarsögur* have been described as eddic poetry’s “prose equivalent,”⁵⁵ but the relation of eddic and skaldic metres to narrative prose has frequently been considered very different. Vésteinn Ólason considers skaldic poetry specially to stand in relief to its surrounding prose:

The concentration and complexity of verse distinguishes it from prose, as becomes especially clear when we compare the straight-forward prose to be found in the *Íslendingasögur* with skaldic verse which is as far removed from prose as can be imagined.⁵⁶

As Lee Hollander also points out, part of “the glaring contrast” between skaldic poetry and its prose context in sagas is because of the “unaffectedness of saga style.”⁵⁷ Bjarne Fidjestøl extends the dichotomy of prose and verse to the narrative functions of skaldic and eddic metres:

...eddic metre relates to *dróttkvætt* in much the same way as prose relates to verse. In the metrical world the eddic measures stand in practical terms at the prosaic pole. They are not particularly close to prose in form, but the two chief metres, *fornyrðislag* and *ljóðabáttr*, were developed as vehicles for the same basic kinds of information as ordinary prose, the one for narrative, the other for speech and reflective

⁵⁵ Robert Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” *Vox intexta: Orality and Textuality in the Middle Ages*, ed. A. N. Doane & Carol Braun Pasternack (Madison, WI: University of Wisconsin Press, 1991) pp. 89-101, at 96.

⁵⁶ Vésteinn Ólason, *Dialogues with the Viking Age: Narration and Representation in the Sagas of the Icelanders*, trans. Andrew Wawn (Reykjavík: Heimskringla, 1998) 128-129.

⁵⁷ Hollander, *The Skalds*, p. 1.

thought. In contrast, *dróttkvætt* and other distinctively skaldic metres were designed to serve a particular performative purpose.⁵⁸

From this perspective, eddic verse serves a role similar to prose as a potential carrier of narrative since “the narrative element in skaldic poems is often minimal,”⁵⁹ which supports Thorvaldsen’s construction of a continuum between eddic and skaldic verse based on their complexity,⁶⁰ which seems relevant in determining whether or not a particular verse form can be considered close to prose.

It must be acknowledged that skaldic verse can also be used in a more narrative, mythological context, one which is usually attributed to eddic-style verse. Nevertheless, Lindow makes the good point that eddic verse on the whole also does not tell stories, but rather allude to a story that is already known by their audience.⁶¹ Eddic verse is used in a mythic or heroic context and little used in historical contexts (which tends to be the preserve of the skaldic-style verse), but it is powerfully demonstrated in *Sneglu-Halla þáttr* that mythological subjects were a fitting subject for skaldic verse. King Haraldr harðráði and the Icelandic poet Þjóðólfr Arnórson hear a blacksmith and a tanner arguing whilst walking down the street one day, and the king demands that the skald compose a poem about the incident, but Þjóðólfr is reluctant to because he considers the subject matter (two craftsmen) beneath him. The king (himself an accomplished poet), has the idea that Þjóðólfr ought to recast the craftsmen as figures from Old Norse mythology, and he does so, first with the blacksmith as Þórr and the tanner as Geirrøðr, using the myth of Þórr’s visit to Geirrøðr, which appears as a narrative in *Skáldskaparmál*,⁶² and also, under the king’s

⁵⁸ Bjarne Fidjestøl, “Skaldic Stanzas in Saga-Prose. Observations on the Relationship between Prose and Verse in Snorri’s *Heimskringla*,” *Selected Papers*, ed. Odd Einar Haugen & Else Mundal, The Viking Collection 9 (Odense: Odense University Press, 1997) pp. 255-276, at 260.

⁵⁹ Clive Tolley, “Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse,” p. 131. John Lindow counters the notion that *dróttkvætt* was unsuitable for narrative. See “Myth and Mythography,” p. 24, and “Narrative and the Nature of Skaldic Poetry,” *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 97 (1982): 94-121.

⁶⁰ Thorvaldsen, “Svá er sagt,” pp. 42-48.

⁶¹ Lindow, “Narrative and the Nature of Skaldic Poetry,” p. 106.

⁶² Snorri Sturluson, *Edda: Skáldskaparmál*, ed. Anthony Faulkes, vol. 1 (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1998) 24 ff.

direction, with one as Sigurður Fáfnisbani and one as Fáfnir.⁶³ The poet is praised and rewarded by the king for his performance. Certain subjects are thus felt to be appropriate for court poetry, the mythological content, otherwise cast in eddic verse, amongst them.⁶⁴

The use of eddic or skaldic metre is socially determined by convention and by the status of the respective metres or verseforms.⁶⁵ Although *fornyrðislag* could be used for skaldic poetry, *dróttkvætt* seems to have had a superior social status than the eddic metre, as demonstrated by two stanzas from King Haraldr harðráði, who, having realised he has left his armour aboard his ship before the Battle of Stamford Bridge in 1066, composes an eddic verse saying so and then says, “þetta er illa kveðit ok mun verða at gera aðra vísu betri” [‘that is badly composed and I will now make another, better verse’].⁶⁶ The king then composes a rather obscure skaldic stanza, which can be taken to mean that skaldic verse was more highly esteemed than eddic (at least in that context).⁶⁷ In *Gunnlaugs saga*, it is clear that there is a level of expectation about which verseform to use when Gunnlaugr criticises Hrafn for having composed a *flokkr* rather than *drápa* about a king: “hví ortir þú flokk um konunginn?” segir hann; ‘eða þótti þér hann eigi drápunnar verður?’ [“why do you compose a *flokkr* about the king,” he says, “or doesn’t he seem to you worthy of a *drápa*?”].⁶⁸ This comment should be read against the background of Gunnlaugr composing a very well-received *flokkr* himself

⁶³ *Sneglu-Halla þátr, Eyfirðinga sögur*, ed. Jónas Kristjánsson, Íslenzk fornrit 9 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska fornritafélag, 1956) pp. 263-95, at 267-268.

⁶⁴ Clunies Ross, *History of Old Norse Poetry*, pp. 115-117; Frog, “Speech-Acts in Skaldic Verse,” p. 227,

⁶⁵ Thorvaldsen, “Svá er sagt,” p. 41.

⁶⁶ *Haralds saga Sigurðarsonar, Heimskringla*, ed. Bjarni Aðalbjarnarson, Íslenzk fornrit 28 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska fornritafélag, 1951) pp. 68-202, at p. 188.

⁶⁷ Anthony Faulkes, “Poetical Inspiration in Old Norse and Old English Poetry,” The Dorothea Coke Memorial Lecture in Northern Studies delivered at University College London 28 November 1997 (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1997) <<http://www.vsnrweb-publications.org.uk/Faulkes.pdf>> 8; Frog, “Speech-Acts in Skaldic Verse,” p. 227; Joseph Harris & Karl Reichl, “Performance and Performers,” *Medieval Oral Literature*, ed. Karl Reichl (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2012) pp. 141-202, at p. 155.

⁶⁸ *Gunnlaugs saga Ormstungu: The Story of Gunnlaug Serpent-Tongue*, ed. P. G. Foote, trans. R. Quirk, Icelandic Texts (London: Thomas Nelson, 1957) p. 22.

on several occasions in the saga, but for jarls rather than kings.⁶⁹ The difference between a *drápa* and a *flokkr* is that a *flokkr* lacks the embellishment of a series of refrains (each called a *stef*) found in a *drápa*. A similar example can be found in *Óláfs saga helga* in *Heimskringla*, in which Þórarinn loftunga offends King Knút by offering him a *flokkr*, scathingly described by Knút as a *dræplingr*, and has to recompose it into a *drápa* to make amends.⁷⁰ Note that these verseforms in the *drápa* and *flokkr* are in the same metre (*dróttkvætt*), it is the verseform that is here dictated by social custom and it is noticed when genre-norms are broken, even if the difference to us might seem minimal.⁷¹

The above seems to demonstrate that to think in terms of eddic and skaldic verse as a dichotomy is misleading, but to use the two separate terms is not invalid, since the categories overlap rather than negate each other. Thorvaldsen comments that the difficulties in separating eddic and skaldic verse “could just as well indicate that categories involved do not confirm [sic] to categorization exclusively based in common and differentiating properties.”⁷² This makes a functional and a performative consideration of the stanzas found in prosimetrum all the more important.

⁶⁹ For example, for Sigurðr jarl and Sigurðr jarl Hloðvisson, *Gunnlaugs saga Ormstungu*, ed. Foote, p. 19.

⁷⁰ See *Óláfs saga helga*. *Heimskringla*. Ed. Bjarni Aðalbarnarson. Vol. 2. 3rd ed. Íslensk fornrit 27. Reykjavík: Hið Íslenska fornritafélag, 2002. ch. 172, pp. 307-310.

⁷¹ *Gunnlaugs saga Ormstungu*, ed. Foote, p. 41; Thorvaldsen, “Svá er sagt,” p. 41.

⁷² Thorvaldsen, “The Generic Aspect of the Eddic Style,” p. 277.

The Oral Background of Eddic Poetry and the Sagas

Many of the Old Icelandic genres extant in written form appear to have been preceded by an equally rich vernacular tradition that in many cases continued to supplement and complement the traditions after they were written down;⁷³ Judy Quinn notes this is likely to be the case with skaldic panegyrics, mythological and heroic eddic poetry, lists (mnemonic) and genealogies, *prosimetra* of the types examined in this thesis (apart from perhaps *Gylfaginning*), and oral sagas.⁷⁴ The extant eddic poetry, it seems reasonable to conclude, is the product of a lengthy oral tradition that is largely untraceable; nevertheless, they are also a product of the 13th century and the literature milieu that wrote them down in what Kellogg has described as “a collaboration between two contemporaneous cultures, one essentially oral and the other essentially literate.”⁷⁵ Tom DuBois has described the Old Norse texts with this background as “valuable hybrid works, combining earlier oral tradition (evidenced in content, diction, style, and structure) with the literate concerns and perceptions of a later writer, age or situation,”⁷⁶ and comments that “in order to appreciate the nature of such a hybrid, however, the testimony of undeniably non-literary oral tradition is essential.”⁷⁷ The two most notable recent contributors in this vein are Ruth Finnegan and, building upon Finnegan, Slavica Ranković, although only Ranković’s work takes the Old Norse literature as an example. Both have demonstrated the need and the usefulness to see these “two contemporaneous cultures” standing not in a dichotomy but rather as

⁷³ There is also evidence that some genres were never written down. See Judy Quinn, “From Orality to Literacy in Medieval Iceland,” *Old Icelandic Literature and Society*, ed. Margaret Clunies Ross, Cambridge Studies in Medieval Literature 42 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000) pp. 30-60, at pp. 36-41. Quinn also suggests (p. 42), that some verses by women that did not suit the predominant prosimetric form were not preserved, suggesting an important role for such *prosimetra* in transmitting Iceland’s poetic heritage.

⁷⁴ Quinn, “From Orality to Literacy in Medieval Iceland,” p. 31.

⁷⁵ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 90.

⁷⁶ Tom DuBois, “Dynamics and Continuities of Tradition: What a Finnish Epic Song Can Teach Us About Two Old Norse Poems,” *Dynamics of Tradition: Perspectives on Oral Poetry and Folk Belief. Essays in Honour of Anna-Leena Siikala on her 60th Birthday 1st January 2003*, ed. Lotte Tarkka, Studia Fennica, Folkloristica 13 (Helsinki: Finnish Literature Society, 2003) pp. 233-247, at p. 234.

⁷⁷ DuBois, “Dynamics and Continuities of Tradition,” p. 234.

part of a spectrum of orality-literacy, or on a continuum, which they term the “oral-literate continuum.” Ranković refines and builds upon Finnegan’s theory to account for genre differences, and constructs a method by which one may visualise this continuum in terms of the different Old Norse genres.⁷⁸

In contrast to the earlier instance of formularity as a marker of orality, in the most recent scholarship the oral background of much Old Norse literature has been demonstrated by its variance. It is commonplace to state variability as one defining characteristic between oral and literate texts: the oral being fluid and variable, and the literate as stable and fixed. In Old Norse, however, we can find variable reflexes of the same narrative in a written context. An approach that has proved fruitful is that of exploring the variants in obviously related or similar content, and determining whether it could conceivably be a result of oral tradition or whether it is simply a literary borrowing (often indicated by word-for-word similarity), a method first seriously pioneered by Gísli Sigurðsson in his book *The Medieval Icelandic Saga and Oral Tradition: A Discourse on Method*.⁷⁹ This is not to equate variation with the historical development of the tale, since, as Lauri Honko has demonstrated, “variation is neither stable nor hierarchic” and any given manifestation of a tale is likely to a mixture of both temporary and permanent changes,⁸⁰ that many times will be possible to acknowledge but ultimately impossible to untangle.

Whilst oral elements will have been transformed during their textualisation into written sagas as Quinn notes,⁸¹ scholars such as Jan de Vries, Theodore Andersson and Clive Tolley suggest a continuation between the preliterate and

⁷⁸ Ruth Finnegan, “The How of Literature,” *Oral Tradition* 20 (2005): 164-187; Slavica Ranković, “The Oral-Written Continuum as a Space,” *Along the Oral-Written Continuum: Types of Texts, Relations and their Implications*, ed. Slavica Ranković, Leidulf Melve and Else Mundal, *Utrecht Studies in Literacy* 20 (Turnhout: Brepols, 2010) pp. 39-71. The latter volume represents the latest thinking on the subject.

⁷⁹ Gísli Sigurðsson, *The Medieval Icelandic Saga and Oral Tradition: A Discourse on Method*, Publications of the Milman Parry Collection of Oral Literature 2 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard UP, 2004).

⁸⁰ Lauri Honko, “Thick Corpus and Organic Variation: an Introduction,” *Thick Corpus, Organic Variation and Textuality in Oral Tradition*, *Studia Fennica, Folkloristica* 7 (Helsinki: Finnish Literature Society, 2000) pp. 3-28, at p. 7.

⁸¹ Judy Quinn, “From Orality to Literacy in Medieval Iceland,” *Old Icelandic Literature and Society*, ed. Margaret Clunies Ross, *Cambridge Studies in Medieval Literature* 42 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press) pp. 30-60, at p. 31.

literary periods in Iceland and that the Icelandic oral tradition was one that had artistic expectations commonly found in literate rather than oral societies.⁸² The written sagas deriving much of their form and narrative technique from their oral predecessors may explain why the earliest written saga texts show evidence of a fully-developed saga form, rather than a long prose form that had to be worked upon to reach its literary zenith – there exists no evidence of practice period in which Icelanders came to terms with long prose forms normally associated only with written cultures.⁸³ There also appears to have been a vibrant oral poetic tradition in medieval Scandinavia.

Documentary evidence that points towards this include verses written in runic script, references given in prose narratives to oral poetic activity, and the recording of stanzas in works such as Snorri Sturluson's *Edda* that have the intention of recording poetical forms.⁸⁴

Eddic Poetry and Oral Tradition

The majority of the stanzas examined in this thesis are in the eddic metres.⁸⁵ The Old Norse eddic metres are from a written record that preserves the Old Norse version of the Germanic alliterative metres also found in Old English, Old High German and Old Saxon that were once used in a purely oral form.⁸⁶ The Germanic metres differ

⁸² Jan de Vries, *Heroic Song and Heroic Legend*, trans. B. J. Timmer, Oxford Paperbacks 69 (London: Oxford University Press, 1963) 98; Theodore Andersson, *The Family Saga: An Analytic Reading* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1967) p. 306; Tolley, "Oral Assumptions," p. 134. Nevertheless, Haraldur Bessason cautions against Andersson's suggestion of continuity between the oral and written periods in Iceland, particularly with regards to the *fornaldarsögur*, about which he points out that although the *fornaldarsögur* may be based for the best part on oral tradition, the *Íslendingasögur* were written down first and could have sometimes served as models for the *fornaldarsögur*. Haraldur Bessason, "Mythological Overlays," *Sjötiú Ritgerðir: Helgaðar Jakobi Benediktssyni 20. júlí 1977*, ed. Einar G. Pétursson and Jónas Kristjánsson, vol. 1, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar á Íslandi Rit 12 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1977) pp. 273-292, at p. 272. Bjarne Fidjestøl conceives of the situation (in the neutral statement) as "the literary culture naturally presupposes the existence of an oral culture," in "Skaldic Stanzas in Saga-Prose," p. 255.

⁸³ Orality and literacy likely merged in the Old Norse culture in which the sagas and eddic poems were written down; nevertheless, I have found useful David Barton's chapter "The Social Basis of Literacy" in his book *Literacy: An Introduction to the Ecology of the Written Language* (Oxford: Blackwell, 1994) pp. 33-52 helpful for formulating my thoughts on the social aspects of literacy, and Walter J. Ong's book *Orality and Literacy, New Accents* (New York: Routledge, 2002 [1982]) useful for his exploration of oral and literate mindsets; nevertheless, I think he holds too firm a distinction between the two.

⁸⁴ Quinn, "From Orality to Literacy in Medieval Iceland," p. 41

⁸⁵ However, some stanzas encountered in the *fornaldarsögur*, for example in *Ragnars saga loðbrókar* and *Áns saga bogsveigis*, are skaldic. They will be considered here because the sagas are mixed in their use of eddic and skaldic metres, and it makes no sense to examine just parts of a whole saga when I am discussing narrative construction using verse.

⁸⁶ Tolley, "Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse," p. 128.

slightly between language and people, and it is clear that the metres underwent a continuous process of development from the earliest times; the first recordings of alliterative metres are in runic inscriptions from c. the 2nd century CE.⁸⁷ The skaldic metres likely developed from the eddic metres in the 8th to 9th centuries, likely deriving from *fornyrðislag*, the basic eddic metre, although they probably also later influenced eddic verse.⁸⁸ The oldest skaldic poems that we have preserved were composed in the 9th century and were preserved and transmitted orally to around the 12th century.

How Do We Know Eddic Poetry Has an Oral Background?

The claim that eddic poetry has an oral background (that it was conceived, performed and transmitted orally),⁸⁹ is made on the basis of the elements discussed directly above: literary and social factors in medieval Iceland and from such hints as we can gather from literature, although the reliability of these sources must always be contested.⁹⁰ The oral background of written eddic poetry is suggested by the stanzas content, metre and diction drawn from a common preliterate of Germanic heroic tradition about people and events from as long ago as the fifth and sixth centuries;⁹¹ only by oral tradition could this content have reached, for example, the heroic eddic

⁸⁷ Tolley, "Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse," p. 128 fn. 1.

⁸⁸ Joseph Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," *Prosimetrum: Crosscultural Perspectives on Narrative in Prose and Verse*, ed. Joseph Harris & Karl Reichl (Cambridge: D. S. Brewer, 1997) pp. 131-163, at 133. Roberta Frank questions the assumption that the eddic metres are older than the skaldic, in "Skaldic Poetry," *Old Norse-Icelandic Literature: A Critical Guide*, ed. Carol J. Clover and John Lindow, *Islandica* 45 (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1985) pp. 157-196, at p. 160.

⁸⁹ To borrow the definition of 'oral' from Bengt R. Jonsson, "Oral Literature, Written Literature: The Ballad and Old Norse Genres," *The Ballad and Oral Studies*, ed. Joseph Harris, *Harvard English Studies* 17 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1991) pp. 139-170, at p. 141.

⁹⁰ It is thought that *Gripissþá* may be the only eddic poetry composed entirely in a written context; Einar Ólafur Sveinsson, *Íslenzkar bókmenntir í fornöld* (n.p.: Almenna bókafélagið, 1962) p. 195.

⁹¹ Joseph Harris, for example, when discussing the Heroic group of *fornaldarsögur* which he says contain older eddic verse and narrative material, comments that their "tone is the tragic one of Germanic heroic legend, with its core ultimately from the Migration Age." See Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 145. Clive Tolley points out that even in the oral period, influences from literate cultures must have reached the Germanic societies (from, for example, the Roman and Byzantine cultures), but that this was unlikely to have influenced the verse tradition; see "Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse," 128, fn. 2. See also Robert Kellogg, "The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry," *Atti del 12^o Congresso Internazionale di Studi sull'alto medioevo: Poetry in the Scandinavian Middle Ages, The Seventh International Saga Conference* (Spoleto: Centro Italiano di Studi sull'alto medioevo, 1990) pp. 187-199, at 187.

poems in their first written forms, from which our extant poems seem to be recent descendants, and older than the circumstances of their manuscript preservation might suggest.⁹²

Bengt R. Jonsson has emphasised that “*the natural state for oral poetry is to remain oral* and ...such poetry is rarely written down without a real incitement and ... a proper vehicle, that is, a suitable form of written language” (his emphasis).⁹³ What then, might have been the incitement to record the poems of the *Poetic Edda*? The appearance of the *Poetic Edda* manuscripts and *Snorra Edda* in the 13th century has been explained by the emergence of an antiquarian movement⁹⁴ that likely continued into the early 14th century and that also accounts for the appearance of compilations such as *Hauksbók*. Sigurður Nordal moots the possibility that the collection and writing down of the *Poetic Edda* collection was prompted by *Snorra Edda*, since Snorri is not thought to have had access to an extensive collection of poems.⁹⁵

From a 13th century perspective, Snorri in *Heimskringla* offers several glimpses of his conception of the oral life of poetry. In *Ólafs saga helga* we hear:

Þat var meirr en tvau hundruð vetra tólfraeð, er Ísland var byggt, áðr menn tœki hér sǫgur at rita, ok var þat lǫng ævi ok vant, at sǫgur hefði eigi gengizk í munni, ef eigi væri kvæði, bæði ný ok forn, þau er menn tœki þar af sannendi fræðinnar.⁹⁶

It was more than two hundred and forty winters since Iceland was settled before men here took to writing sagas, and that was a long period a risk that the stories had been altered in oral tradition, if there had not been poems, both new and old, those from which men might take historical truth.

The eddic poetry preserved in manuscripts from the 13th century onwards in some way “represents – or even presents – much older oral poetry.”⁹⁷ Anne Holtmark has

⁹² Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” pp. 89-90.

⁹³ Jonsson, “Oral Literature, Written Literature,” p. 145.

⁹⁴ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 93.

⁹⁵ *Codex Wormianus: Ms. no. 242 fol. in the Arnemagnean collection in the University library of Copenhagen*, intro. Sigurður Nordal, *Corpus codicum Islandicorum medii aevi* 2 (Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1931) p. 12.

⁹⁶ *Ólafs saga helga, Heimskringla*, ed. Bjarni Aðalbjarnarson, vol. 2, 3rd ed, Íslensk fornrit 27 (Reykjavík: Hið Íslenska fornritafélag, 2002) p. 422.

⁹⁷ Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 131.

described the *Poetic Edda* “as close to oral tradition as we can get,” and suggests the poems began to find written form just before 1200.⁹⁸

There is also evidence, however, to suggest that eddic poetry was still also an oral tradition in the 13th century, when new compositions, as Judy Quinn notes, “assume their audience’s familiarity with heroic figures...and mythological phenomena,” indicating the audience was aware of conventions present in the *Poetic Edda* material which they likely knew from an oral tradition that was alive and productive.⁹⁹ Clive Tolley argues that the living oral tradition in which the eddic poems of the *Poetic Edda* must once have been transmitted was no longer to be found around a century after the eddic poems being written down. This can be surmised because the Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda* (from c. 1270) contains lapses that the scribe was unable to correct by using his own knowledge of an oral tradition, and he gives the example of leaving a gap for an absent or indecipherable word in his exemplar in the poem of *Helgakviða Hundingsbana I*, 7:4.¹⁰⁰ Some of the poems contained in the *Poetic Edda* collection are found quoted or paraphrased in *Gylfaginning* and other *fornaldarsögur* (for example *Völsunga saga* and *Norna-Gests þáttur*). It is impossible to make detailed links on the basis of manuscripts between these sources,¹⁰¹ and it seems that the versions of the poems we can deduce from the above contexts must ultimately derive from independent recordings from oral tradition.

⁹⁸ Anne Holtmark, “Heroic Poetry and Legendary Sagas,” *Bibliography of Old Norse-Icelandic Studies 1965*, trans. Peter Foote (Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1966) pp. 9-21, at 12. For a wideranging survey of this and related issues, see Vésteinn Ólason, “The Poetic Edda: Literature or Folklore?,” *Along the Oral-Written Continuum: Types of Texts, Relations and their Implications*, ed. Slavica Ranković, Leidulf Melve and Else Mundal, *Utrecht Studies in Medieval Literacy* 20 (Turnhout: Brepols, 2010) pp. 227-252.

⁹⁹ Quinn, “From Orality to Literacy in Medieval Iceland,” p. 45. See also Joseph Harris, “Romancing the Rune: Aspects of Literacy in Early Scandinavian Orality,” “*Speak Useful Words or Say Nothing:*” *Old Norse Studies by Joseph Harris*, ed. Susan E. Deskis and Thomas D. Hill, *Islandica* 53 (Ithaca: Cornell University Library: 2008) pp. 319-347, at p. 329 [Originally published as *Atti Accademia Peloritana dei Pericolanti*, 70 (1996), pp. 109–140.]

¹⁰⁰ Clive Tolley, “Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse,” p. 130 and fn. 4 on the same page.

¹⁰¹ Rellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 91.

The Formula and the Eddic Poems

The possible oral improvisation of eddic poetry has been mooted in connection with the Oral-Formulaic theory articulated by Milman Parry and his student Albert Lord, which they formed after the observation of the compositional practices of oral Serbo-Croatian poets and used to explain the recurrent phrases and epithets found in Homeric poetry.¹⁰² Parry argued that these formulas were chosen in accordance with demands of the metrics; this argument was expressed by Lord as a definition of the formula: “a group of words which is regularly employed under the same metrical conditions to express a given essential idea.”¹⁰³ Although developed by studying Balkan field material, the spread of the theory to vernacular genres gave rise to the suggestion that verse was composed and transmitted in the medieval Icelandic oral period by the use of formulas.¹⁰⁴ By the use of these formulas, poets could compose as they went along, and the text would be recreated with each performance, and the formulas surviving in the written texts would thus be “traces of the compositional habits of performers who composed orally.”¹⁰⁵ As Clive Tolley points out, this means that some features, words and motifs, were retained, while others were not.¹⁰⁶ While both eddic and skaldic poems were transmitted and composed orally, the oral-formulaic mode is likely to have applied to only some degree to eddic poetry, and does not really appear in skaldic poetry in a manner in which we are familiar with it from studies of other Germanic literatures. Tolley suggests that the recurrent phrases in

¹⁰² Albert B. Lord, *The Singer of Tales*, ed. Stephen Mitchell and Gregory Nagy, 2nd ed., Harvard Studies in Comparative Literature 24 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard UP, 1988). The scholarship on oral formulaic theory and eddic poetry has been surveyed by Paul Acker, *Revising Oral Theory: Formulaic Composition in Old English and Old Icelandic Verse*, Garland Studies in Medieval Literature 16, Garland Reference Library of the Humanities 2104 (New York: Garland, 1998) pp. 85-110.

¹⁰³ Lord, *The Singer of Tales*, p. 30.

¹⁰⁴ See for example Francis P. Magoun, Jr., “The Oral-Formulaic Character of Anglo-Saxon Narrative Poetry,” *Speculum* 28 (1952): 446-67; Robert Kellogg, *A Concordance to Eddic Poetry*, Medieval Texts and Studies 2 (East Lansing: Michigan State University Press, 1988); Robert Scholes and Robert Kellogg, *The Nature of Narrative* (New York: Oxford UP, 1966) the chapter “The Oral Heritage of Written Narrative”; Elena A. Gurevič, “The Formulaic Pair in Eddic Poetry: An Experimental Analysis,” *Structure and Meaning in Old Norse Literature: New Approaches to Textual Analysis and Literary Criticism*, ed. John Lindow, Lars Lönnroth and Gerd Wolfgang Weber, The Viking Collection 3 (Odense: Odense University Press, 1986) pp. 32-55.

¹⁰⁵ Kellogg, “The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry,” p. 190.

¹⁰⁶ Tolley, “Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse,” p. 130.

skaldic poetry are borrowings and allusions rather than part of the oral-formulaic tradition, although he suggests that the oral formulaic aspect of oral societies might be located in the skaldic tradition by the use of mythological motifs and in the use of kennings to present these motifs.¹⁰⁷ This separation of borrowings and allusions as a form of intertextuality separate from that at play in oral-formulaic composition is by no means certain, however.

In the earlier phase of applying the Parry-Lord theory on formulae and their relation to oral composition to vernacular literature, it was taken for granted that if a text were “formulaic and traditional” it pointed to “oral-formulaic techniques of composition,”¹⁰⁸ and thus the formulae in written texts were used as a means of proving an oral background for a text. Similarly, the application of the Parry-Lord theory was used to justify the idea that the eddic poems were composed in the pre-Christian period and were transmitted uncorrupted until they were recorded in the 13th century, and were thus entirely reliable sources for Scandinavian mythology and Germanic pagan religion.¹⁰⁹ These repeated blocks had to fit both metrically and content wise into the gap in the line, although the metrical dimension originally proposed by Parry and Lord seems to have been relaxed in recent years.

The presence of formulaic phrases in a written text can no longer be considered an indication that a text has roots in a preliterate society, a criterion that was once used as evidence that Old Norse eddic poems were indeed oral and thus ancient.¹¹⁰ This is for the simple reason that those who write texts can also employ these formulae in their putting together of a text that is manifestly literate. Authors might choose to do this for a number of reasons that were likely largely aesthetic or traditional, giving the

¹⁰⁷ Tolley, “Oral Assumptions: A Warning from Old Norse,” p. 131.

¹⁰⁸ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 90.

¹⁰⁹ “Myth and Mythography,” p. 29.

¹¹⁰ By, for example, Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 89; “The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry,” p. 190. Curiously, in 1979, Kellogg recognises that formulaic texts that were patently not oral used formulas to sound traditional and to be considered art; he does not allow this admission to nuance his later views on eddic poetry. See Robert Kellogg, “Varieties of Tradition in Medieval Narrative,” *Medieval Narrative: A Symposium*, ed. Hans Bekker-Nielsen, Peter Foote, Andreas Haarder and Preben Meulengracht Sørensen (Odense: Odense University Press, 1979) pp. 120-129, at 125.

literate text an air of orality, for example, since they do not need the formula for compositional reasons. In addition, although they cannot indicate an oral background, formulaic content and syntax remained an important compositional resource in the literary period.¹¹¹ Scott Mellor argues that some syntactic and content units are so frequent in the *Poetic Edda* that there is likely to be a system beneath,¹¹² one that Tom DuBois has described as giving even the late eddic poems, such as *Grógaldr* and *Fjölvinnsmál* found in 17th century paper manuscripts, the means to “sound eddic.”¹¹³ Old Norse speakers in the late medieval times had access to the eddic tradition through the use of formulaic syntax or content, regardless of whether it was gained by reading or orally, rather than mere literary borrowings.¹¹⁴ Direct recordings of poetic texts from oral tradition would indeed presumably include formula, but the fact that formula can also be found in the output of literate authors means that it cannot be a criterion in itself in determining the absolute oral roots of a text, only that it rests on the oral-literate continuum and that to the literate society that produces such texts, oral reflexes serve a positive purpose. On the basis of this, other criteria once used to demonstrate a text’s preliterate background, criteria in early vernacular works like “stereotyped elements of diction, narrative style, and structure that are typical of poetry composed orally in performance,”¹¹⁵ must likewise be discredited as absolute indicators of an oral background.

¹¹¹ I make this point more fully in “Younger Icelandic Manuscripts and Old Norse Studies,” *Approaching Methodology*, ed. Frog and Pauliina Latvala, *RMN Newsletter* (special issue) 5 (2012): 148-161, at 153-155, where I also discuss Matthew J. Driscoll’s formulation of the concept in “Traditionality and Antiquarianism in the Post-Reformation *Lygisaga*,” *Northern Antiquity: The Post-Medieval Reception of Edda and Saga*, ed. Andrew Wawn (Enfield Lock: Hisarlik Press, 1994) pp. 83-99.

¹¹² Scott A. Mellor, *Analyzing Ten Poems from the Poetic Edda: Oral Formula and Mythic Patterns* (Lewiston, N. Y.: Edwin Mellon Press, 2008).

¹¹³ Cf. Eleazar M. Meletinsky, “Commonplaces and Other Elements of Folkloric Style in Eddic Poetry,” *Structure and Meaning in Old Norse Literature: New Approaches to Textual Analysis and Literary Criticism*, ed. John Lindow, Lars Lönnroth and Gerd Wolfgang Weber, *The Viking Collection* 3 (Odense: Odense University Press, 1986) pp. 15-31.

¹¹⁴ Tom DuBois, “Dynamics and Continuities of Tradition: What a Finnish Epic Song Can Teach Us About Two Old Norse Poems,” *Dynamics of Tradition: Perspectives on Oral Poetry and Folk Belief. Essays in Honour of Anna-Leena Siikala on her 60th Birthday 1st January 2003*, ed. Lotte Tarkka, *Studia Fennica, Folkloristica* 13 (Helsinki: Finnish Literature Society, 2003) pp. 233-247, at pp. 243-244.

¹¹⁵ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 89. See also Kellogg, *A Concordance to Eddic Poetry*; Scholes and Kellogg, *The Nature of Narrative*, pp. 17-57.

The Question of a Fixed, Oral Text for the Eddic Poems

Andreas Heusler is perhaps typical of his time when he states that:

Alle diese Skope und Skalden, Spielleute, Ritter und Ritterfräulein haben vorbedachte, auswendig gelernte Lieder vorgetragen, eigene sowohl wie fremde: das eigene Schaffen vertrug sich durchaus mit dem Nichtimprovisieren und mit der bedingten Festigkeit des Liedkörpers...¹¹⁶

Thanks to the work of Parry and Lord onwards this view was nuanced, but if the eddic poems were born purely of an oral-formulaic tradition, they cannot have been fixed texts: “Oral-formulaic ‘singers’ did not memorize a set text or a lexicon of poetic expressions but rather intuited systems for producing metrical utterances, generating them anew with each performance.”¹¹⁷ Although, as discussed above, eddic poetry certainly has formulaic aspects, whether or not the eddic poems were indeed fixed rather than fluid texts before they were recorded as extant is an open question; Lars Lönnroth suggests that if the eddic poems were indeed born out of oral-formulaic improvisation, then they later became fixed and were transmitted verbatim, possibly due to the adoption of prose for the narrative form and the lyrical verse lines remaining becoming shorter and thus more conducive to memorisation.¹¹⁸ It is possible there were (at least in theory) multiple recordings of an eddic text from oral tradition, and these would give rise to multiple versions being recorded. In the case of the three recordings of *Völuspá* (in the Codex Regius manuscript, Hauksbók, and quotations in *Snorra Edda*), for example, this seems to be the case, as demonstrated most recently by Else Mundal.¹¹⁹ In other cases where there are one or more versions of the same eddic poem in existence, it seems that they come from the same written exemplar, for example in the case of *Grímnismál*.

¹¹⁶ Andreas Heusler, “Das Nibelungenlied und die Epenfrage,” *Kleine Schriften*, ed. Helga Reuschel, vol. 1, *Kleinere Schriften zur Literatur- und Geistesgeschichte* (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1969) pp. 132-169, at p. 134.

¹¹⁷ Paul Acker, *Revising Oral Theory: Formulaic Composition in Old English and Old Icelandic Verse*, *Garland Studies in Medieval Literature* 16, *Garland Reference Library of the Humanities* 2104 (New York: Garland Publishing, 1998) xv.

¹¹⁸ Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga,” pp. 78-79, 83-84.

¹¹⁹ Else Mundal, “Oral or Scribal Variation in *Völuspá*: A Case Study in Old Norse Poetry,” *Oral Art Forms and their Passage into Writing*, ed. Else Mundal and Jonas Wellendorf (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanum Press, 2008) pp. 209-227.

One possibility is that the eddic poems were not of a very fluid nature in oral tradition and did not change much between their existence in oral tradition and their initial recording; John Lindow and Lars Lönnroth both suggest that the eddic poems are akin to the ballads in that they were likely reasonably fixed in their oral form.¹²⁰ Lönnroth comments in 1981 that “Like ballads and unlike Yugoslav epics, Eddic poems are comparatively short, tightly structured and only *in part* formulaic; they were obviously meant to be memorized and recited (or sung) from memory.”¹²¹ Lindow points out that of the different types of texts, those with sacred content for example are strong contenders to remain relatively static in content, but nuances his view with the point that texts are open to change along with a culture, and that a changing text can also be a sacred text.¹²² There is no evidence, however, that the eddic poems were ever used in a ritual or religious context,¹²³ and the fact that the eddic poems were also apparently preserved in oral culture for c. 250 years after the conversion also makes it questionable as to whether they were not changed during this period.¹²⁴ Typically, oral transmission means that material is changed gradually to keep it relevant to the present:

Traditional art amalgamates the present and past, preserving elements it no longer clearly understands because they have been passed down, comfortable with archaism and anachronism, and yet continuously avoiding a debilitating decadence by gradually filling old images with new significance when intelligibility and relevance require it.¹²⁵

Robert Kellogg, who supports the application of the Parry-Lord model to eddic material, poses the question of whether the eddic poems existed in a fixed form but rejects an affirmative answer. If, he argues, the texts were fixed, there would have been little reciprocal interaction between a performer and audience, and since it is this

¹²⁰ “Myth and Mythography,” p. 30; Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga,” p. 84.

¹²¹ Lars Lönnroth, “*Íorð eða né upphiminn: A Formula Analysis*,” *The Academy of Odin: Select Papers on Old Norse Literature*, The Viking Collection 19 (Odense: University Press of Southern Denmark, 2011) pp. 219-241, at p. 221.

¹²² “Myth and Mythography,” p. 30.

¹²³ “Myth and Mythography,” p. 32.

¹²⁴ “Myth and Mythography,” p. 30.

¹²⁵ Kellogg, “Varieties of Tradition in Medieval Narrative,” p. 122.

that keeps the poetry relevant and the eddic poems seem to have existed orally in one form or another for several hundred years before they were recorded, the texts are unlikely to have been fixed.¹²⁶ Although Kellogg's arguments are rejected by Lönnroth, Lönnroth acknowledges the important point that Kellogg's contribution at least demonstrates that the eddic poems ought to be considered as orally derived texts.

Both Lönnroth and Tolley have sought middle ground in the discussion of whether the eddic poems were fixed, and have identified it as a literary-historical development. According to Lönnroth, the eddic poems were improvised at an early stage in their oral transmission, at which point the eddic poems could have been more loosely structured with less rigid metrical demands, less concern for a 'correct' poetic diction and more formulaic. All these factors are conducive to improvisation rather than memorization.¹²⁷ Clive Tolley suggests that the Scandinavian poetry is literary in character, despite its oral background, and strikes a middle ground by linking the fixity of the eddic tradition as it appears in the 13th century to the influence of the skaldic poetry; the eddic poetry became gradually more fixed, and oral-formulaic recreation at each performance was ostensibly replaced with memorisation (to varying degrees in the eddic corpus), a shift entrenched by the arrival of the technology of writing.¹²⁸

Much of the extant eddic poetry in the *Poetic Edda* is preserved with prose in its written form, and it is possible that this too was transmitted orally in a form resembling what is extant in the written record in those poems that have a prose frame or prose inserts in between their stanzas. Customarily it has been assumed that the prose was added to the *Poetic Edda* by a compiler, likely in a manuscript previous to the two surviving: this is discussed further below. The assumption is born out of the acceptance of poetry as the primary oral form, although in the case of the sagas, the

¹²⁶ Kellogg, "The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry," pp. 188-189.

¹²⁷ Lönnroth, "Ígrð fannz æva né upphiminn: A Formula Analysis," p. 221.

¹²⁸ Clive Tolley, *Oral Assumptions*, p. 134.

notion of fluid prose accompanying stanzas has been allowed. Nevertheless, prose is the natural medium of story telling, and the recitation of poems, whether or not they were also dramatically enacted, would, as far as can be judged from what is found in the written poems of the *Poetic Edda*, have benefitted from explanation, even if the audience were familiar with the story.¹²⁹ Further, the existence of prose descriptive titles for some of the poems and the prose story *Dauði Sinfjötla* indicates that the prose in some places is simply summing up tradition associated with the poems that was once narrated orally. It is unlikely that the prose was fixed in the same way as the eddic poems are thought to have been, although they could have maintained consistency in content and general expression, and indeed this is likely if they provide context to the same, unchanging poem. Were units of the poem to be switched, as can be seen for example in the difference in versions between the Hauksbók and Codex Regius versions of the *Poetic Edda*, the prose associated with the poem would perhaps have to transform in order to suit the order of the poetic content.

The Performance of Eddic Poetry

If we accept as a general premise that much of Old Norse literature has an oral background or is orally-derived, texts thus ought to be thought of not only as written works, but also as artistic events – as performances.¹³⁰ Above I argued that variation ought to be considered as an indicator of orality in some texts (which we would then think of as being orally-derived), in the light of Gísli Sigurðsson and Tom DuBois’s research;¹³¹ here I would like to turn to the idea that variation and performance go hand-in-hand in orally-derived literature, beginning with Richard Bauman’s observation that:

¹²⁹ The fact that these prose inserts seem necessary in the 13th century is perhaps indicative of varying levels of knowledge of the audience. Whilst all were likely familiar with the tradition, it could have been that some participants in performance or, later, readings of the poems may not have been conversant in the details of the poems to the point where they were able to identify participants without guidance, for example.

¹³⁰ See Joseph Harris, “Eddic Poetry as Oral Poetry: The Evidence of Parallel Passages in the Helgi Poems for Questions of Composition and Performance,” *“Speak Useful Words or Say Nothing:” Old Norse Studies by Joseph Harris*, ed. Susan E. Deskis and Thomas D. Hill, *Islandica* 53 (Ithaca: Cornell University Library: 2008) pp. 189-225.

¹³¹ Honko, “Thick Corpus and Organic Variation: an Introduction.”

A performance-centered conception of verbal art calls for an approach through performance itself. In such an approach, the formal manipulation of linguistic features is secondary to the nature of the performance, per se, conceived of and defined as a mode of communication.¹³²

This theory is particularly pertinent to texts that are preserved in manuscript form. At its most basic level, performance theory indicates that performance is part of the meaning, which in Bauman's terms means that a performer enunciates and puts forth a certain interpretation of the text.¹³³ John Miles Foley points out that this in turn demands that the audience decode the performance using what Bauman terms "keys to performance" that vary from community to community, but can include, for example, opening and closing formulae and appeals to tradition.¹³⁴

Performance becomes important in three areas of this thesis: the first are the descriptions of actual performances, such as that of the wedding in Reykjahólar or as found in *Norna-Gests þáttur*. The second area of performance considered is the capture of a performance on a page, which can be thought of as an extended text of a performance. An extended text is one that contains "several notations concerning the verbal and non-verbal interaction between the performer and the audience, paralinguistic expressions such as gesture and body movement (kinesics), the utilisation of space (proxemics) and artifacts (instruments, ritual objects) and different forms of integral or collateral action (dance, pantomime, ritual, song, orchestra)."¹³⁵ Perception of these elements in a text demands individual readers to reconstruct the performance event captured. This area of performance is considered in my analysis of the mythological eddic poems below, in conjunction with the prose that is found with this poems.¹³⁶ The third aspect of performance I pick out is the performance on the

¹³² Richard Bauman, "Verbal Art as Performance," *American Anthropologist* n.s. 77 (1975): 290-311, at 292.

¹³³ "...in artistic performance of this kind, there is something going on in the communicative interchange which says to the auditor, 'interpret what I say in some special sense; do not take it to mean what the words alone, taken literally, would convey.' This may lead to the further suggestion that performance sets up, or represents, an interpretative frame within which the messages being communicated are to be understood, and that this frame contrasts with at least one other frame, the literal." Bauman, "Verbal Art as Performance," p. 292. Cf. Foley, *How To Read an Oral Poem*, pp. 83-84.

¹³⁴ Foley, *How to Read an Oral Poem* pp. 84-93; Bauman, "Verbal Art as Performance," p. 295 ff.

¹³⁵ Honko, "Thick Corpus" p. 13.

¹³⁶ See Terry Gunnell, *The Origins of Drama in Scandinavia* (Cambridge: Brewer, 1995). The best recent articles on the performance of eddic poetry, are Kari Ellen Gade, "On the Recitation of Old Norse Skaldic Poetry," *Studien zum*

manuscript page. Each manuscript is unique by nature, and the inscription of each saga narrative can be likened to a unique performance of the text by the scribe, with individual quirks and variations – differences that can nevertheless only be noted when multiple versions of the “same” text are compared. This is relevant for my discussion of *Gylfaginning*, which quotes versions of eddic poems found elsewhere, and for some of the *fornaldarsögur* that I will discuss, where I consider the saga(s) in multiple manuscripts. The concept of performance is thus useful to the study of written texts in a variety of ways.

In the oral stage of the eddic poems, the texts would have existed “only at the moment of performance.”¹³⁷ Outside of these performances the texts were not, and there was only a *competence* to produce the poems in a performance.¹³⁸ The oral performer was also in some sense part of the audience, since he and the audience have similar levels of competence.¹³⁹ Nevertheless, as Robert Kellogg points out, the record does not divulge “the mental text of the performer nor the intertexts resorted to by the audience.”¹⁴⁰ There is not a great deal of anecdotal evidence for the performance of eddic poetry, which has no word for its poet akin to the ‘skald’ of the skaldic tradition,¹⁴¹ but there are several scenes recorded that provide some evidence for eddic prosimetrum and the functional as well as entertainment role for eddic verse.

Altgermanischen: Festschrift für Heinrich Beck, ed. Heiko Uecker, Ergänzungsbände zum Reallexikon der Germanischen Altertumskunde 11 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1994) pp. 126-151, which considers the evidence for the actual performance of Old Norse poetry and its depiction in the sagas, and Terry Gunnell, “The Performance of the Poetic Edda,” *The Viking World*, ed. Stefan Brink and Neil Price (London: Routledge, 2008) pp. 299-303; Joseph C. Harris, “The Performance of Old Norse Eddic Poetry: A Retrospective,” *The Oral Epic: Performance and Music*, ed. Karl Reichl (Berlin: Verlag für Wissenschaft und Bildung, 2000) pp. 225-32.

¹³⁷ Kellogg, “The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry,” p. 188.

¹³⁸ Kellogg, “The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry,” p. 188.

¹³⁹ Kellogg, “The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry,” p. 190.

¹⁴⁰ Honko, “Thick Corpus,” p. 25.

¹⁴¹ What does exist is traced by Joseph Harris in Harris and Reichl. “Performance and Performers,” p. 155 ff.

In *Norna-Gests þátr*, an Odinnic guest performs eddic poetry and prose to the king and his men, in a format distinctly reminiscent of a *fornaldarsaga*. Stanzas from extant eddic poems leave the mouth of the performer, leaving open the intriguing question of whether this is a likely format in which such eddic poems could have been performed in the oral tradition. Lars Lönnroth locates the origin of the prose and verse *fornaldarsaga* in an oral performance akin to that found in *Norna-Gests þátr*. Although written around 1300, the tale is clearly much older, as can be seen by its parallels with earlier sagas and with the Old English poem *Widsith*.¹⁴² In this *þátr*, a mysterious old man called Norna-Gest visits King Oláfr Tryggvason, and entertains him by telling stories from the past about the great heroes he has met, since he is several hundred years old, and his characters speak several verses that are direct quotations from *Reginsmál* and *Helreið Brynhildar* from the Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda*.¹⁴³ Lönnroth contends that “his performance and its social context are probably in several important respects typical of mythical-heroic entertainment in Iceland and Norway during the 13th century,” and he lists the entertainment at big feasts while people are drinking, the story-telling and poetic recitation that happened there, its acceptability in Christian circles, the existence of heroic relics (which Norna-Gest produces to show his hosts), and the allure of the figure of the skald as shared characteristics between the *þátr* and the real-life performance context of legendary sagas.¹⁴⁴

The second suggestion of the performance of eddic poetry, also in a prosimetric context, is to be found in the depiction of saga entertainment at a wedding at Reykjahólar in 1119 (discussed further below). Here, verses are said to accompany saga prose, and the episode suggests that eddic verses were performed outside the contexts of the Royal courts (as *Norna-Gests þátr* suggests they were also performed in a court context), and that the prosimetric form of saga narration familiar from the

¹⁴² Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga,” p. 76. See also Margaret Schlauch, “Widsith, Vidföruull and Some Other Analogues,” *Publications of the Modern Language Association of America* 46 (1931) 969-987.

¹⁴³ Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga,” p. 76.

¹⁴⁴ Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga,” p. 77.

written *fornaldarsögur* can be traced relatively far back in performance in oral tradition.¹⁴⁵

Joseph Harris suggests that two episodes from Saxo Grammaticus in his *Gesta Danorum* of around 1200 provide early written evidence for the use of eddic poetry in a functional role in addition to the examples elsewhere of it being used for entertainment.¹⁴⁶ In the first scene, a Saxon attempts to warn the Danish king of an ambush by reciting a poem given the descriptive title in the *Gesta* of “the very famous perfidy of Grimhild against her brothers,” whilst at the same time not breaking his allegiance to the attackers. In a second scene in the same text, a singer, *cantor*, rides amongst troops “rehearsing Sveno’s murderous treachery in a famous song” and exciting the warriors to revenge. Although there is no way to tell whether the latter is eddic, Harris notes that the former, the *perfidia Svenonis*, seems to correspond to a poem that is lost in Old Norse.¹⁴⁷

The performance of *Bjarkamál* before the battle of Stiklastaðir as related in *Heimskringla* (and discussed further below), is perhaps not historical,¹⁴⁸ but nevertheless Harris suggests we take from the scene the fact that a skald is responsible for the re-performance of an eddic poem, and, like in Saxo, this happens before a battle and outside. He also argues that the recitation of *Bjarkamál* at this point was done so by Þórmóðr for its effect of the double-scene, since *Bjarkamál* relates the last stand of *Hrólfs saga kraka* and the historical battle of Stiklastaðir likewise saw the

¹⁴⁵ Harris and Reichl, “Performance and Performers,” p. 156.

¹⁴⁶ Harris and Reichl, “Performance and Performers,” p. 156.

¹⁴⁷ Harris and Reichl, “Performance and Performers,” p. 156; Joseph Harris, “*Guðrúnarbrögð* and the Saxon Lay of Grimhild’s Perfidy,” “*Speak Useful Words or Say Nothing:*” *Old Norse Studies by Joseph Harris*, ed. Susan E. Deskis and Thomas D. Hill, *Islandica* 53 (Ithaca: Cornell University Library: 2008) pp. 127-136 [Originally published in *Mediaeval Scandinavia* 9 (1976): 173-180].

¹⁴⁸ See Klaus von See, “Hastings, Stiklastaðir und Langemarck: Zur Überlieferung vom Vortrag heroischer Lieder auf dem Schlachtfeld,” *Edda, Saga, Skaldendichtung: Aufsätze zur skandinavischen Literatur des Mittelalters* (Heidelberg: Winter, 1981) pp. 259-271, and “*Húskarla hvot*: Nochmals zum Alter der *Bjarkamal*,” *Edda, Saga, Skaldendichtung: Aufsätze zur skandinavischen Literatur des Mittelalters* (Heidelberg: Winter, 1981) pp. 272-282; Heinz Klingenberg, “Altnordisch *húskarl*, *Bjarkamal*=*Húskarlahvot* und stiklastad,” *Festskrift til Ottar Grønvik på 75-årsdagen den 21. oktober 1991*, ed. John Ole Askedal et al. (Oslo: Universitetsforlaget, 1991), pp. 183-211.

death of St. Óláfr, but the reason behind the recitation of the poem was to motivate the warriors to battle.¹⁴⁹

Eddic verse was thus likely used for both entertainment and in functional settings. The first two of the examples given above, *Norna-Gests þáttr* and the wedding at Reykjahólar, suggest that the eddic prosimetric form has deep roots in the performance history of Old Norse narrative as entertainment. The three scenes, from Saxo and the recitation of Bjarkamál, suggest the alternative uses to which eddic verse could be put apart from entertainment contexts. Indeed, both the use of eddic verse as a warning and as motivation for fight/vengeance are found in the *fornaldarsögur*. In *Hrólfs saga kráka*, Reginn recites an eddic verse to King Fróði as a warning. Even though Reginn is party to the actions that will lead to Fróði's death, he must issue a warning about what is happening in order to fulfill his oaths to him.¹⁵⁰ In *Ragnars saga*, we hear of Áslaug's despair and irritation when she is unable at first to convince her sons to avenge their step-brothers by the power of her poetry, and her son Ívarr comments that "Eigi er vist, segir Ivar, 'hvart þat stodar nackvat, þottu kvedir aþra visu at annari'" ["it is not certain," Ívarr says, "whether that helps anything, even if you speak one verse after another"].¹⁵¹ The characters in the saga thus seem aware of and attuned to the potential of verse to persuade and motivate.¹⁵²

The second aspect of performance I noted above is performance on a page, the text of a performance. The possibility of this has been analysed in detail by Terry Gunnell, who argues that the actual performance of the dialogue poems in the *Poetic Edda* is likely, although not in a ritual sense. Gunnell reads the layout of the poems in the

¹⁴⁹ Harris and Reichl, "Performance and Performers," pp. 156-157.

¹⁵⁰ *Hrólfs saga kraka ok Bjarkarímur*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur 32 (København: S. L. Møller, 1904) p. 15, ll. 17-18.

¹⁵¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar, Volsunga saga ok Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Magnus Olsen, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur 36 (København: S. L. Møller, 1906-1908) pp. 111-175, at p. 143, ll. 23-24.

¹⁵² Note that in fact many of the stanzas in *Ragnars saga* are skaldic, but used in the context of a *fornaldarsaga* as the dialogue of ancient characters, play an eddic role in the proceedings of the saga.

Codex Regius manuscript, particularly the marginal “V” markings, as indicative that the pages could have been marked up as documents approaching scripts, and provides examples of this from contemporaneous European tradition. Medieval readers and writers, used to oral (aural) performances, might thus negotiate a written text with reference to an oral performer (not author),¹⁵³ one with which they were rather close to:

...manuscripts, with their glosses or marginal comments (which often got worked into the text in subsequent copies) were in dialogue with the world outside their own borders. They remained closer to the give-and-take of oral expression. The readers of manuscripts are less closed off from the author, less absent, than are the readers of those writing for print.¹⁵⁴

Ursula Schaefer argues that the divorce of the verse from a physical poet’s gestures and intonations, used by aural receivers of texts as interpretative aids, prompted the poet to supply in his narrative a substitute voice by employing a speaker,¹⁵⁵ and in skaldic poetry we might suppose that the lack of performer is compensated for by naming the person responsible for the composition of the stanza. In eddic prosimetra, we might consider the function of putting verses directly into the mouths of characters a similar reflex.

The third aspect of performance I noted is performance on the manuscript page, linked to variation and the uniqueness of each manuscript presentation of a text. In this sense, each manuscript is a ‘performance’ of a work, although the ‘performer’ responsible for the manuscript is one linked directly to tradition:

The most striking fact about traditional literature...is the absence of authors. The performer is not an author. He transmits the work out of the past and into the present. Through him, the tradition is made manifest. In this sense his performance is analogous not to authorship – that belongs to the tradition – but to the presentation of an author’s work through a book or other text. The performer is more nearly

¹⁵³ Cf. Carol Braun Pasternack’s discussion in *The Textuality of Old English Poetry*, Cambridge Studies in Anglo-Saxon England 13 (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1995) 4-5.

¹⁵⁴ Ong, *Orality and Literacy*, p. 130.

¹⁵⁵ Ursula Schaefer, “Hearing from Books,” *Vox Intexta: Orality and Textuality in the Middle Ages*, ed. A. N. Doane and Carol Braun Pasternack (Madison, WI: Wisconsin University Press) pp. 117-128, at p. 124. Cf. Pasternack, *The Textuality of Old English Poetry*, p. 13.

akin to a reader than to the author of a book. His performance is one “reading”, one “interpretation” of the tradition.¹⁵⁶

The mediation of the manuscript compiler and scribe in the transmission of poetry can be seen in those cases where more than one version has survived.¹⁵⁷ In the Old Norse corpus, we are fortunate in having poetry preserved in saga prose that is preserved in tens of copies; for poetic works, fewer exist. Pasternack understands the reshaping of a text through its written transmission through an oral paradigm, something that Tim William Machan argues continues in to the later middle ages: “a variety of the conscious alterations effected by scribes as they “copied” texts are similar to the changes made by oral poets as they re-create songs – that a model of improvisation can describe the performance qualities of both oral poets and scribes.”¹⁵⁸ In a manuscript tradition, this can be seen in both the general shape of the text and the specific manuscripts. Stemmatic studies usually reveal groups of texts related to each other, each group either a related or independent transformation. On the specific level, each individual manuscript is an individual manifestation of the text, and no two will be exactly alike. Both levels of textual transformation are due in part to the process of recomposition in the transmission of the text, and perhaps in part due to more minor differences in the copying process: errors, emendations, omissions and additions (neither of which are necessarily erroneous), and minor interpolations. In such a way can prosimetric (and non prosimetric) texts be considered usefully as performances in their manuscript versions.

The oral background of eddic poetry as found both in the *Poetic Edda* compilations and the *prosimetra* proper can be explored via a number of routes, several of which have been traced above. I have argued that eddic poetry should, as conventionally

¹⁵⁶ Kellogg, “Varieties of Tradition in Medieval Narrative,” p. 122.

¹⁵⁷ Pasternack, *The Textuality of Old English Poetry*, p. 15; see fn. 58, p. 15 for Old English poems surviving in more than one or related versions.

¹⁵⁸ T. W. Machan, “Editing, Orality and Late Middle English Texts,” *Vox Intexta: Orality and Textuality in the Middle Ages*, ed. A. N. Doane and Carol Braun Pasternack (Madison, WI: Wisconsin University Press) pp. 229-245, at p. 237.

done, be read as having an oral background, although its formularity should not be considered to be evidence of this, but an indication that even as written texts they are in an oral mode. This in turn makes it difficult to say whether the eddic poems in the oral period were transmitted in the more fluid manner associated with oral poetry, or were memorised and transmitted in fixed texts. Either way, the performance of the eddic poems is suggested by a number of factors: references in extant literature to the performance of eddic poetry, traces left as they were written and copied by scribes, and as evidenced by their variation as unique performances of poetry in each manuscript context. The discussion above also suggests that prosimetra were likely present in the oral period, although this cannot be absolutely proven. The question of whether the extant written sagas reflect the form of narrative that existed in the preliterate period has been under debate for many years, and it is this question of the origin of the saga form itself to which I will now turn.

The Debate Surrounding the Orality of the Sagas

The purpose of this section is to summarise the scholarly debate that surround the origins of the Icelandic sagas in order to frame my discussion of learned literature as a background to the written prosimetrum of *Gylfaginning* in Part Two, and the development of the *fornaldarsögur* in Part Three. The question of saga origins has shifted in recent years from the Book Prose and Free Prose debate to an emphasis on socio-historical considerations on the *ursprung* of the Icelandic vernacular literature, although the discussion is still characterised by a focus on the *Íslendingasögur*.

A consideration of how the saga genre developed as a whole has, from the beginning of critical thought towards the sagas, been based in a discussion of whether the sagas have oral or written origins. This culminated in the 19th and 20th centuries in the so-called Free prose and Book prose theories, which I will discuss below, a debate that is, as such, no longer on-going but which undoubtedly underpins contemporary commentary, since its concern was whether the saga form as we know it from written texts was a reflection of a long prose form that was found in oral tradition. The discussion of saga origins is a vast field, so here I have limited myself firstly to major scholars in the discipline, and secondly to those who have commented explicitly on the development of the sagas in relationship to verse. I do not attempt to provide a complete map of the discussion, but rather to pick out the points relating most directly to the role of stanzas in saga origins (I refer you to Theodore M. Andersson's 1964 book *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins: A Historical Survey* for such a map, and his survey has been invaluable in preparing mine and I treat the pre-19th century authors in the same order).¹⁵⁹

Surveys of the debate as to whether or not the sagas have oral origins usually begin in Free-Prose/Book-Prose era of the 19th century, but the beginning of analytical approaches to prose and verse, however credulous, must be sought slightly

¹⁵⁹ Theodore M. Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins: A Historical Survey*, Yale Germanic Studies 1 (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1964). Else Mundal's *Sagadebatt* (Oslo: Universitetsforlaget, 1977) also contains invaluable commentary on selected pieces of criticism relevant to the Book Prose – Free Prose debate.

further back in 17th century with the first generation of those working in Denmark on Icelandic sources, for example Ole Worm. Such scholars, who were not Icelandic, were unable to read the manuscripts themselves and needed Icelandic assistants as amanuenses. For our purposes, Thormod Torfaeus (1636-1719) is particularly important,¹⁶⁰ since he hypothesises that oral tradition was extremely important in explaining the foundations of the written saga genre, and explicitly comments on the importance of prose in the transmission of verse. In his *Series Dynastarum et Regum Daniae*,¹⁶¹ composed following a trip to Iceland in 1662 to collect parchment manuscripts but not published until 1702,¹⁶² he reasons that in order for an audience to interpret them, (skaldic) stanzas must have been accompanied by what Andersson calls “a stock of tradition,”¹⁶³: “Hactenus de Carminibus egimus egregiis illis memoriae subsidiis, quæ tamen vetustarum historiarum non nisi breviarum fuere; nec raro tam obscura, ut sine interprete parum ab auditoribus intelligerentur.”¹⁶⁴ Without interpretation, Torfaeus reasons, the stanzas are too obscure to make sense. He buttresses this by emphasising the role of oral tradition in supplying the traditional context necessary:

Sed plenior adhuc rerum gestarum notitia ad perfectam historiam rite concinnandam requireretur. Hanc scripturientibus suppeditarunt relationes, non scriptæ, quas ex parentum avorumque ore auditu exceptas, filii nepotesque memoriâ conservarunt, atque suis posteris eadem ratione tradiderunt, donec tandem ad eos pervenirent, qui literarum beneficio illas ab interitu vindicarunt. Quod Verelius agnoscit, ubi in limine Notarum ad Gothrici Rolphi historiam scribit: majores nostras in Principum suorum, virorumque fortium laudibus celebrandis parcos non fuisse, nec in conventibus publicis, ubicumque genio indulgebant, alia magis ablectatione quam eorum facinoribus decantandis animum paviffere; additque: narrationes hujusmodi, à majoribus per manus traditas, literis postea consignatas fuisse.¹⁶⁵

¹⁶⁰ See Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* pp. 5-8 for his discussion of Torfaeus. See also Halldór Hermannsson, “Þormóður Torfason,” *Skírnir* 128 (1954): 65-94; Jon Gunnar Jørgensen, “Tormod Torfæus og det fantastiske i sagalitteraturen” *Historisk tidsskrift* 3 (2008): 475-490; Lars Boje Mortensen, “Before Historical ‘Sources’ and Literary ‘Texts’: The Presentation of Saga Literature in Tormod Torfæus’ *Historia rerum Norvegicarum*,” *Renaissanceforum* 5 (2008): 1-14. <http://www.renaissanceforum.dk/5_2008/lbm.pdf.>

¹⁶¹ Thormod Torfaeus, *Series Dynastarum et Regum Daniae: à primo eorum Skioldo Odini filio, ad Gormum Grandaevum, Haraldi Caerulidentis patrem, antea anno Christi MDCLXIV* (Hafniae: Sumptibus Joh. Melchioris Lieben, 1702).

¹⁶² Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins*, p. 5.

¹⁶³ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins*, p. 7.

¹⁶⁴ Torfaeus, *Series Dynastarum et Regum Daniae* ch. 6, Book 1, p. 56. For a discussion of this see also Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 7.

¹⁶⁵ Torfaeus, *Series Dynastarum et Regum Daniae*, ch. 6, Book 1, pp. 56-57.

But a fuller knowledge of events was necessary for the proper exposition of history. This was provided to the writers by accounts not written but transmitted orally from parents and grandparents; sons and grandsons retained them by memory and passed them on in the same way to their descendants, until finally they reached those who rescued them from oblivion with the aid of letters. Verelius is also of this opinion when he writes in his notes to *Gautreks saga ok Hrólfs* that our ancestors were not sparing in their praise of their heroes or kings and that neither at their assemblies nor on any other occasion for recreation did they cultivate other pastimes more eagerly than the reciting of their deeds; and he adds that these stories were handed down from their ancestors and were later consigned to writing.¹⁶⁶

From this it can be seen that the suggestion of oral transmission of saga material goes back to Olof Verelius (1618-1682), a Swedish scholar responsible for the earliest printed editions of sagas in Uppsala, who rationalises the oral tradition behind the sagas.¹⁶⁷ Another Swede, Olof Rudbeck (1630-1702), sought to establish Sweden as the cradle of civilisation and, in his magnum opus *Atlantica* (1679-1702)¹⁶⁸ used Icelandic, classical and biblical material in an argument that equated Sweden with Plato's Atlantis.¹⁶⁹ However unlikely sounding his conclusions to modern scholarship, he is at least clear in his belief that oral tradition must be responsible for even the earliest history writings, an argument he takes back to the sources of Moses' material.¹⁷⁰ The saga material and discussion of its origins at this time belonged to the historians, and were part of the evolution of historical thinking of the 18th century, and in the middle of the century, the mood had evolved to scepticism.¹⁷¹

¹⁶⁶ Trans. Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins*, p. 7.

¹⁶⁷ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins*, p. 12.

¹⁶⁸ Olof Rudbeck, *Olof Rudbecks Atland eller Manheim: Olaus Rudbecks Atlantica*, ed. Axel Nelson (Uppsala: 1937-1950).

¹⁶⁹ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 12. For more on Rudbeck's project, see David King, *Finding Atlantis: A True Story of Genius, Madness, and an Extraordinary Quest for a Lost World* (New York: Harmony Books, 2005). For an exploration of the framework that Rudbeck uses in the work, and how he uses Old Norse sources, see Mats Malm, "Olaus Rudbeck's *Atlantica* and Old Norse Poetics," *Northern Antiquity: The Post-Medieval Reception of Edda and Saga*, ed. Andrew Wawn (Enfield Lock: Hisarlik Press, 1994) pp. 1-25.

¹⁷⁰ Olof Rudbeck, *Olof Rudbecks Atland eller Manheim: Olaus Rudbecks Atlantica*, ed. Axel Nelson, vol. 1 (Uppsala: 1937) pp. 7-14. For a summary, see Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 12. See also Gunnar Eriksson, "Olof Rudbeck ock Atlantan," *Kungl. Vitterhets Historie och Antikvitets Akademiens Årsbok 1981*, 151-159.

¹⁷¹ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* pp. 13-15. For more on this period, see Jan Ragnar Hagland, "The Reception of Old Norse Literature in Late Eighteenth-Century Norway," *Northern Antiquity: The Post-Medieval Reception of Edda and Saga*, ed. Andrew Wawn (Enfield Lock: Hisarlik Press, 1994) pp. 27-40; C. Paludan-Müller, "Dansk Historiografi i det 18 de Aarhundrede" *Historisk Tidsskrift* 5.4 (1883): 1-188, <http://img.kb.dk/tidsskriftdk/pdf/hto/hto_5rk_0004-PDF/hto_5rk_0004_81232.pdf>.

One comment that indicates this shift is from Paul Henri Mallet in Denmark in his *Introduction á l'histoire de Dannemarc* (first edition 1755),¹⁷² in which he questions whether poetry could be maintained accurately for seven, eight or nine centuries:¹⁷³

Endelig, hvad Skialdre-Sangene angaar, som man lærde uden ad, da kand det ikke nægtes, at jo Skribenterne, som vi tale om, have kundet uddrage deraf megen Oplysning udi Historien af de Tider, der vare ikke for langt borte fra deres; Men er det vel troeligt, at man har med Omhyggelighed forvaret mange Skialdre-Vers, der vare giorte syv, otte eller ni hundrede Aar tilforn? Skulde man vel finde derudi megen Rigtighed og Tydelighed? Vare Skialdrene i de Tider saa nöye regnende, og fulgte de den Orden, som Historien udkræver?¹⁷⁴

Sven Lagerbring issued a defence of the sagas to answer Mallet as a contributor to Johan Adolph Steachau's *Dissertatio gradualis de fide historica monumentorum Islandicorum*,¹⁷⁵ published in 1763.¹⁷⁶ As part of this, he argues that since the ancient poems were "the only order of annals and erudition,"¹⁷⁷ and carried the most important aspects of religious and secular material, we should be assured of their longevity. Lagerbring is also of the opinion that whilst most poetry was undoubtedly part of a memorial tradition, some may have been written, and uses in this connection the example of Þorgerðr inscribing Egill's verses in *Egils saga*,¹⁷⁸ and furthermore cites Snorri as an authority that learned men thought the poems to be true.¹⁷⁹ P. F. Suhm, a

¹⁷² Régis Boyer sets Mallet in context in his treatment of the development of the image of the Vikings in Frances, see "Vikings, Sagas and Wasa Bread," *Northern Antiquity: The Post-Medieval Reception of Edda and Saga*, ed. Andrew Wawn (Enfield Lock: Hisarlik Press, 1994) pp. 69-81.

¹⁷³ See Margaret Clunies Ross, "Percy and Mallet: The Genesis of *Northern Antiquities*," *Sagnaþing: helgað Jónasi Kristjánssyni sjötugum 10. apríl 1994*, vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska bókmenntafélag, 1994) pp. 107-117, for a discussion of the translation of Mallet's work into English and it starting up interest in Old Norse in the UK, as well as its translator's career. See also Lars Lönnroth, "Mallet och det nordiska subluma," *Sagnaþing: helgað Jónasi Kristjánssyni sjötugum 10. apríl 1994*, vol. 2 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska bókmenntafélag, 1994) pp. 527-537.

¹⁷⁴ P. H. Mallet, *Indledning udi Danmarks Riges Historie: hvorudi handles om de gamle Danskes Guds-Dyrkelse, Love, Sæder og Skikke*, (Kiöbenhavn, 1756) p. 31. This is a Danish translation of Paul Henri Mallet, *Introduction a l'histoire de Dannemarc, ou l'on traite de la religion, des loix, des moeurs & usages des anciens Danois* (Copenhagen, 1755).

¹⁷⁵ Sven's surname is given as 'Bring' in the title, but Lagerbring later. For the answer to Mallet, see p. 5 ff. For an answer to the part of Mallet that I have cited above, see p. 20 ff.

¹⁷⁶ Sven Lagerbring and Johan Adolf Stechau, *Dissertatio gradualis de fide historica monumentorum Islandicorum* (London: 1763).

¹⁷⁷ To cite Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins*, p. 17.

¹⁷⁸ Lagerbring & Stechau, *Dissertatio gradualis*, pp. 15, 22.

¹⁷⁹ Lagerbring & Stechau, *Dissertatio gradualis*, p. 23 ff. Cf. Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins*, p. 17.

historian,¹⁸⁰ also attributed much of the material found in the *fornaldar-* and *riddarasögur* type material to have come from the people's "uvisse Tradition, og deres egen stærke Indbildningskraft" ["uncertain tradition, and their own vigorous imagination,'] and cites the "de herligste vers bevarede" in *Völsunga saga* as one reason not to be entirely dismissive of their historical value.¹⁸¹ At the beginning of the 19th century, Friedrich Rühls in Germany, did not, like Lagerbring, hedge his bets, and simply dismissed material prior to Haraldr Fairhair's time as fiction,¹⁸² and was very cautious of the poetry in more recent material. The unquestioning belief characteristic of Torfaeus and many of his near contemporaries was replaced by the critical attitudes towards their historicity characterised by Mallet and Rühls. The next step in the discussion of the origins of the saga was to set the problem of saga origins in its historical context, and Peter Erasmus Müller (1776-1834) was the first scholar to do just this.

Müller's 1813 *Ueber den Ursprung und Verfall der Isländischen Historiographie*¹⁸³ proposed that the Icelandic storytelling tradition had undergone a development from mythical interests, to historiography to fiction (*fornaldarsögur*),¹⁸⁴ and in doing so founded the so-called *Verfall* theory of saga development, in that saga literature peaked and then declined with the flourishing of such ridiculous and light fiction as the legendary sagas. Müller maintains a fairly standard account of the transmission of poetry (memorised or carved in runes), and the normal arguments for the historical knowledge of the poets and Snorri believing in their accuracy are deployed.¹⁸⁵

¹⁸⁰ For more on Suhm's other approaches see Hagland, "Norse Literature in 18th-century Norway," pp. 35, 37.

¹⁸¹ P. F. Suhm, "Tanker om de Vanskeligheder som Møde ved at Skrive den Gamle Danske og Norske Historie," *Kammerherre og kongelig histographus Peter Friderich Suhms Samlede Skrifter*, vol. 9 (Kjøbenhavn: S. Poulsens Forlag, 1792) pp. 5-112, at p. 77. See also Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 18.

¹⁸² Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 19; see also Ludvig Stavenow, "Friedrich Rühls' Betydelse för Svensk Historieskrivning," *Nordisk Tidskrift* (1918).

¹⁸³ P. E. Müller, *Ueber den Ursprung und Verfall der Isländischen Historiographie nebst einem Anhang über die Nationalität der altnordischen Gedichte* (Copenhagen, 1813).

¹⁸⁴ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 26.

¹⁸⁵ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* pp. 24-25.

Müller argues that the prosimetric saga tradition has its beginnings in stanzas composed in the feuding period, mainly on historical topics,¹⁸⁶ and the social context of the poets (long winter evenings and assemblies) provided plenty of times for the art form to be displayed and developed.¹⁸⁷ An aptitude for narrative and a lively interest in contemporary events gave rise to stories; initially these were eye witness reports but developed into an artistic story form (sagas), although essentially they were still historical.¹⁸⁸ The subsequent popularity of these sagas meant that their subject matter became distorted, and eventually the taste of the audience had shifted as far as *fornaldarsögur* with their basis in the fictional and the fabulous.¹⁸⁹ As such, this is a theory based on an aesthetic judgement.

The next clear statement on the origin of the prosimetric sagas can be found in the literature of the Norwegian national romanticists, notably Rudolf Keyser.¹⁹⁰ He argues that in the oral period, traditional material was given verse form, and then was accompanied by prose accounts, and both forms became set, and comments that the basis of *fornaldarsögur* is often old “folkedigte.”¹⁹¹ Andersson comments Keyser presents standard Romantic formulations of literary origins, adapted to Norwegian concerns (held to be identical to Icelandic concerns).¹⁹² While Keyser believed in the authority and authorial power of tradition and less in the role of the individual author in the saga composition process, N. M. Peterson believed in a set, oral background for the sagas, but one in which the written saga was an imitation and not direct recording of oral stories, and that the written sagas became longer and longer as authors got used

¹⁸⁶ Müller, *Ueber den Ursprung* p. 33; cf. Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 25.

¹⁸⁷ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 25. See Hermann Pálsson, *Sagnaskemmtun Íslendinga* (Reykjavík: Mál og Menning, 1962).

¹⁸⁸ Müller, *Ueber den Ursprung* p. 39 ff.; Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 25.

¹⁸⁹ Müller, *Ueber den Ursprung* pp. 42, 44; Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 26.

¹⁹⁰ Rudolf Keyser, *Nordmændenes Videnskabelighed og Literatur i Middelalderen, Efterladte skrifter*, vol. 1 (Christiania, 1866), published posthumously.

¹⁹¹ Keyser, *Nordmændenes Videnskabelighed*, pp. 10 ff. and 345.

¹⁹² Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* pp. 32-33.

to making written compositions and eventually were able to produce texts in line with the old oral stories.¹⁹³

Around the same time, the German C. F. Köppen argues for the derivation of saga narrative from poetry in a similar vein to Keyser and for the sagas and poetry's set form.¹⁹⁴ He sees the *fornaldarsögur* as a prose tradition emerging from the disintegration of the poetic pre-Christian heroic tradition, the adaptation of the poetic tradition to prose made possible because the poetic lines were short.¹⁹⁵ Köppen's explanation was rejected by Theodor Möbius on the grounds that the existence of oral epic poems was not provable, assigning the sagas' similarity to the power of stereotype.¹⁹⁶ Svend Grundtvig too was unconvinced by Keyser and Petersen's support of set oral pieces, particularly in prose, arguing that it was clear that:

...lange omhyggelig udarbejdede prosa værker aldrig kunne tænkes gennem århundreder at forplantes uforandrede fra mund til mund, således som korte, bestemt formede og rimbundne kvad...¹⁹⁷

He also asserts Icelandic tenure of the material and promoted the term *oldnordisk*, in part to include Denmark and Sweden in the Norse *fornöld* in which Norse mythological poetry was thought to have flourished,¹⁹⁸ a position rejected by Gustav

¹⁹³ Niels M. Petersen, "Indledning," *Historiske Fortællinger om Islandernes Færd Hjemme og Ude*, vol. 1 (Kjøbenhavn, 1839) pp. 55-56. Cf. Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* pp. 35-36.

¹⁹⁴ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* pp. 34-35.

¹⁹⁵ "Uebrigens lag in der Form der altnordischen Gedichte selbst der Grund, warum neben der Liedsprache sich schon früh die prosaische Erzählung- oder Sagensprache entwickeln musste, ein Grund, der bei den Griechen nicht obwaltete, nämlich die unverhältnismässige Kürze der Verszeilen und der Stabreim." C. F. Koeppen, *Literarische Einleitung in die Nordische Mythologie* (Berlin, 1837) p. 92, and "Ehre aber ernährt die Künste, und so dürfen wir uns nicht wundern, dass manche Isländer es zu lernen und öffentlich vorzutragen, also dass im Sagmann dem Skalden sein prosaisches Abbild gegenüber trat. So ward der Stoff, welcher anfangs nur in einzelnen Momenten und unverbunden im Gesange lebte, in verständige, stätige, prosaische Form gegossen." Koeppen, *Literarische Einleitung in die Nordische Mythologie*, p. 93.

¹⁹⁶ Theodor Möbius, *Über die Ältere Isländische Saga* (Leipzig, 1852) 7.

¹⁹⁷ Svend Grundtvig, "Om Nordens gamle literatur: en anmeldelse og en indsigelse," *Historisk Tidsskrift* 3.5 (1867): 1-120 at p. 54.

¹⁹⁸ Svend Grundtvig, "Om Nordens gamle literatur," p. 2 ff.. See Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 38. For more on Grundtvig and his father, N. F. S. Grundtvig, particularly the attempt to create a national mythological imagery, see Flemming Lundgreen-Nielsen, "Grundtvig's Norse Mythological Imagery – An Experiment that Failed," *Northern Antiquity: The Post-Medieval Reception of Edda and Saga*, ed. Andrew Wawn (Enfield Lock: Hisarlik Press, 1994) pp. 41-67 and Lars Lönnroth, "The Academy of Odin: Grundtvig's Political Instrumentalization of Old Norse Mythology," *The Academy of Odin: Selected Papers on Old Norse Literature*, The Viking Collection 19 (Odense: University Press of Southern Denmark: 2011) pp. 357-378.

Storm.¹⁹⁹ The work of Konrad Maurer, who accepted with Keyser that the saga originated in oral story telling but differed in assigning a fluid character to the oral material,²⁰⁰ heralds the movement into modern methods of saga analysis, listed by Anderson as the comparison of saga with other written sources, testing a saga's internal logic, that an author or redactor can innovate, and relative dating.²⁰¹

These older theories that centred around the written sagas as something like transcriptions of oral sagas and varieties of this argument, outlined above, gave rise in the 19th century to the Book-Prose and Free-Prose debate, as it has come to be known; a name not only for the two schools of thought of the origins of medieval Icelandic literature, but also shorthand for their associated methodological approaches.²⁰² The terms were introduced into scholarship by Andreas Heusler in his 1914 book *Die Anfänge der isländischen Saga*,²⁰³ and whilst the debate is no longer current as such, it still underpins most approaches to the origins and formation of the sagas. Much of the discussion centred on the *Íslendingasögur*, although it is relevant to the *fornaldarsögur* and the *konungasögur*. The position of a scholar in this debate was important because adherence to one methodological approach or another determines the kinds of research questions posed to the material, and influences, for example, the methods one might select in making an edition of a text. Whilst Book-Prose adherents broadly approached the saga material as only written and Free-Prose adherents

¹⁹⁹ Gustav Storm, *Om den gamle norrøne Literatur: Et Indlæg i Striden mellem Docent Grundtvig og den norske historiske Skole* (Christiana: 1869).

²⁰⁰ Konrad Maurer, "Die Norwegische Auffassung der Nordischen Literaturgeschichte," *Zeitschrift für deutsche Philologie* 1 (1869): 25-88, at 53. See Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 37.

²⁰¹ Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins* p. 40.

²⁰² A clear overview along these terms is given by Else Mundal, "Bookprose/Freeprose Theory," *Medieval Scandinavia: An Encyclopedia*, ed. Phillip Pulsiano, Garland Encyclopedias of the Middle Ages 1, Garland Reference Library of the Humanities 934 (New York: Garland Publishing, 1993) pp. 52-53. See also the overview by Andersson, *The Problems of Icelandic Saga Origins* pp. 65-81.

²⁰³ Andreas Heusler, *Die Anfänge der isländischen Saga*, *Kleine Schriften*, vol. 2 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1969) pp. 388-459, at p. 432. [Originally published: *Abhandlungen der königlich preussischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, Jahrgang 1913, phil.-hist. Classe, 9. Berlin: Reimer, 1914.]

approached saga origins as oral and traditional, at the same time, the positions are united by underlying Romantic motivations: the Book-Prose proponents desired the Icelandic Commonwealth receive the acknowledgement it deserved for its rich, educated literary culture, while the Free-Prose proponents initially sought to reduce the specifically Icelandic element and thought of the traditions as of the stock of the people; later this developed into wanting the sagas to be an unsullied record of an heroic past that had the potential to define Scandinavians, particularly Icelanders.²⁰⁴

The Book-Prose enthusiasts emphasised the book learning of the medieval Icelanders, and held the opinion that the Icelanders moulded the European clerical culture of the time to their own forms. This view was founded in the work of, for example, Björn M. Ólsen (a major spokesman), and the other notable proponents of this view were Sigurður Nordal, Einar Ólafur Sveinsson and Jónas Kristjánsson.²⁰⁵ Sometimes known as the Icelandic School, their preferred method was to uncover in the medieval Icelandic texts all that common to traditions of medieval European learning. In addition, the Book-Prose supporters propagated the notion of fiction in the sagas (applied to most saga subgenres except some *konungasögur* and the *samtíðarsögur*).²⁰⁶ The realism that these scholars observed in the sagas they attributed to literary skill of authors, and the major sagas were thus entirely literary works from the late 12th to early 14th centuries and were not based (for the most part), on pre-existing (i.e. oral) material.²⁰⁷

The Free Prose supporters, on the other hand, the most notable of which are Knut Liestøl and Andreas Heusler and Finnur Jónsson,²⁰⁸ emphasised an exceptional

²⁰⁴ Cf. Paul Bibire, "On Reading the Icelandic Sagas: Approaches to Old Icelandic Texts," *West Over Sea: Studies in Scandinavian Sea-Borne Expansion and Settlement Before 1300. A Festschrift in Honour of Dr Barbara E. Crawford*, ed. Beverley Ballin Smith, Simon Taylor & Gareth Williams., *The Northern World* 31 (Leiden: Brill, 2007) pp. 3-18, at 11.

²⁰⁵ Bibire, "On Reading the Icelandic Sagas," p. 10.

²⁰⁶ Bibire, "On Reading the Icelandic Sagas," p. 10.

²⁰⁷ Bibire, "On Reading the Icelandic Sagas," p. 11.

²⁰⁸ Bibire, "On Reading the Icelandic Sagas," p. 11. Heusler did in fact call Finnur Jónsson a Book-Prose supporter, against which Finnur objected strongly; see Mundal, *Sagadebatt*, p. 159. Finnur Jónsson is difficult to classify as Free-Prose or Book-Prose supporter either way.

oral tradition as the primary means of understanding the origins of the medieval Icelandic sagas, and their methods thus tended to be retrospective and involved scouring texts for references to pre-Christian Nordic culture, for example, although Heusler originally used the term “Free-Prose” for the theory that written sagas were copies of oral sagas. These scholars mooted that the *Íslendingasögur* and *Konungasögur* were composed orally at the times they depict, and transmitted orally (verbatim), until they found their written form in the 12th to 14th centuries.²⁰⁹ Heusler assumed that the majority of the *fornaldarsögur* were based on an oral saga, except for cases in which they were obviously based on written sources, such as *Völsunga saga*.²¹⁰

In practical terms, adherents of either school of thought rarely insisted on their preferred methodology in every instance, and instead used it as a guideline while working with texts on individual bases. Although a Free-Prose proponent, Heusler happily considered individual sagas as part of the Book-Prose tradition, and considered the majority of sagas to have originated “between the typical freeprose saga based on an oral saga and the typical bookprose saga based on an oral saga and the typical bookprose saga based to some extent on oral tradition but the work of an individual author.”²¹¹ Two examples of Book-Prose scholars leaning towards Free-Prose theories can be found in the work of Sigurður Nordal and Finnur Jónsson.²¹² Firstly, Sigurður Nordal’s conclusions that *Hrafnkels saga* is fictional because it is not historically accurate, while still holding *Egils saga Skalla-Grímssonar* to contain much traditional material. Secondly, Finnur Jónsson acknowledges that *Njáls saga*’s traditional material had been redacted much later in the saga material’s life, although he does not argue for the existence of an oral saga. This is to be expected since almost all the Book-Prose supporters recognised the existence of an oral tradition, but, as Else

²⁰⁹ Bibire, “On Reading the Icelandic Sagas,” p. 11.

²¹⁰ Heusler, *Die Anfänge der isländischen Saga*, p. 442; Mundal, “Bookprose/Freeprose Theory,” p. 52.

²¹¹ Mundal, “Bookprose/Freeprose Theory,” p. 52.

²¹² These examples are given by Bibire in Bibire, “On Reading the Icelandic Sagas” p. 11.

Mundal points out, a Book-Prose scholar could never really hold a Free-Prose view of a saga origin, “since the bookprose theory denied the possibility of an oral saga.”²¹³

The two key differences to these approaches is their differing conceptions of the connection “between realism and reality,”²¹⁴ and of the sources for the extant (written) saga.²¹⁵ According to Book-Prose theory, the sagas have a literary style in the sense of a written development, and their main sources are written ones in conjunction with oral prose and poetic traditions; in opposition, the Free-prose theorist held that saga style had developed at the oral stage, and that an oral saga was the main source for a Free-prose saga, although the saga writer (Book-prosaists preferred “author”), was free to use written sources and the oral prose and poetic traditions as secondary sources.²¹⁶

Although the Free-Prose/Book-Prose debate has calmed as such, its themes are still under discussion and continue to underpin scholarship on the development of particular genres, as will be seen below in Part Three on the development of the *fornaldarsaga* genre in particular. The most recent sizable work on the *fornaldarsögur* by Torfi H Tulinius seeks to build upon and transcend the issues surrounding Free Prose and Book Prose by emphasising what he terms the “Socio-historical considerations” as another key factor in the question of *fornaldarsaga* origins. Book-Prose and Free Prose scholars looked to the past for the origins of their material; Torfi however maintains that we must look to the Icelandic culture of the 13th century, contemporary to when the literature was composed (or at least written down), to seek explanations for its origins.²¹⁷

²¹³ Mundal, “Bookprose/Freeprose Theory,” p. 52.

²¹⁴ Bibire, “On Reading the Icelandic Sagas” p. 11.

²¹⁵ Mundal, “Bookprose/Freeprose Theory,” p. 52. That this is still a live issue in modern scholarship is documented by Preben Meulengracht Sørensen in “Historical Reality and Literary Form,” *Viking Revaluations: Viking Society Centenary Symposium*, ed. Anthony Faulkes and Richard Perkins (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1993) pp. 172-181, where he also gives an overview of the matters discussed here.

²¹⁶ Mundal, “Bookprose/Freeprose Theory,” p. 53.

²¹⁷ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 44-45.

Torfi looks to the motivations behind the birth of saga literature in connection with social relationships in medieval Iceland, and sees the development in connection with three phenomena in the culture:

1. a strong oral tradition going back to Pre-Christian times, and one in which the learned were very interested;
2. an intensive engagement with the learned European culture promoted by the Church;
3. the use of literature to the social classes in power at the time.²¹⁸

The use of the literature to the uppermost social classes was that it demonstrated their venerable lineages, justified their possession, tenancy and control of lands, as well as their right to judge, and thirdly a wish to emulate wider European aristocratic culture.²¹⁹ Literature was one means by which the upper classes distinguished themselves in the medieval period.²²⁰ The combination of all these factors in medieval Iceland proved powerful, and, Torfi argues, make up the historical framework in which both Snorri's *Gylfaginning* and the earliest written *fornaldarsögur* appeared.

²¹⁸ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 45.

²¹⁹ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 45.

²²⁰ Cf. Jón Viðar Sigurðsson, "Historical Writing and the Political Situation in Iceland 1100-1400," *Negotiating Pasts in the Nordic Countries: Interdisciplinary Studies in History and Memory*, ed. Anne Eriksen and Jón Viðar Sigurðsson (Lund: Nordic Academic Press, 2009) pp. 59-78.

Old Norse-Icelandic Prosimetrum

There are two types of prosimetrum in Old Norse divided on the basis of whether verse or prose is more dominant. Prosimetrum in which prose is prevelant is most common in the so-called “prose genres” of saga literature. The other type of prosimetrum might more properly be termed versiprose, and here verse is prevelant in the prose-verse complex. The versiprose is most common in the *Poetic Edda* poems, but some heavily versified sections of sagas, for example *Hervararkviða* in *Hervarar saga* might be termed versiprose.

The prose-verse mixed form in Old Norse Icelandic texts preserves much of our extant skaldic and eddic poetry from the early medieval period. This mixed literary form was apparently long established before being committed to writing in Old Norse,²²¹ and is termed *prosimetrum* after its service in describing a similarly mixed classical form, most notably menippean satire²²² and Boethius’s *Consolatio Philosophiae*. It is a medieval term with its earliest recorded use in Hugh of Bologna’s *Rationes dictandi*, c. 1119, a treatise on the art of composition.²²³ Hugh defines ‘prosimetrum’ as a branch of metrical, measured composition, and thus for him it is

²²¹ Russell Poole, *Viking Poems on War and Peace: A Study in Skaldic Narrative*, Toronto Medieval Texts and Translations 8 (Toronto: U of Toronto P, 1991) 23; Hans Kuhn, “Heldensaga vor und außerhalb der Dichtung,” *Edda, Skalden, Saga: Festschrift zum 70. Geburtstag von Felix Genzmer*, ed. Hermann Schneider (Heidelberg: Carl Winter Universitätsverlag, 1952) pp. 262-278, at p. 276-7; Heather O’Donoghue, *Skaldic Verse and the Poetics of Saga Narrative* (Oxford: Oxford UP, 2005) 2.

²²² See Rory McTurk, “*Snorra Edda* as Menippean Satire,” *Myths, Legends and Heroes: Essays on Old Norse and Old English Literature in Honour of John McKinnell*, ed. Daniel Anlezark (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2011) pp. 109-130. McTurk suggests *Snorra Edda* should be read as an example of the genre. Franz Rolf Schröder has also suggested that *Lokasenna* may be a menippean satire and goes as far as to suggest that Classical form may have reached Scandinavia (“Das Symposium der Lokasenna,” *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 67 (1952): 1-29). In Classical literature and scholarship, the term *menippean satire* is often best approached through genre and content; see Gareth Schmeling, “The Satyricon: Forms in Search of a Genre” *Classical Bulletin* 47 (1971): 49-52. Note that Old Norse studies uses the term *prosimetrum* somewhat more loosely than in Classical Studies to describe any prose text in which verse occurs. See F. Anne Payne, *Chaucer and Menippean Satire* (Madison: The University of Wisconsin Press, 1981) pp. 1-11 for a summary of the scholarship and the salient features of the menippean satire.

²²³ *Rationes dictandi* II: Duo quidem dictaminum genera nouimus, unum uidelicet prosaicum, alterum quod uocatur metricum. Metricum uero a Greco metron trahitur, quod latine mensura dicitur. inde metricum id est mensuratum dictamen Latina lingua exprimitur. Hoc autem repperitur tripliciter: aut cum pedum mensura, et carmen uocum consonantia, et tunc riddimus appellatur; seu utroque mixtum, quod quidem prosimetrum compositione dicitur, ut sequential declarant exempla. est enim carmen: *bella per Emathios*. riddimus solus ut hic: *hostis Herodes impie*, et cetera, et est cantui satis congruous, quia utrobique repperitur octogonus. ceterum prosimetrum possumus dicere, quando pars uersificae pars uero profertur prosaice, ut exempla declarant: *Ugo, patris matrisque loco quem habui semper, quicquid habet quecumque ualet dat mihi libenter*. Set de his alias. nunc ad prosaicum reuertamur. Ed. Ludwig Rockinger, *Briefsteller und Formelbücher des 11.-14. Jahrhunderts* (München: Scientia Verlag Aalen, 1969) 47-94, at 54-55.

the poetic aspect that defines the nature of the form.²²⁴ Although the term is also recorded known in mid-seventeenth century Britain in a dictionary of hard words to denote texts “consisting partly of prose, partly of meeter or verse,”²²⁵ it was not adopted into modern scholarship until the 1920s to denote the mixed style.²²⁶

Ultimately, the prosimetric form could be an ancient form of narrative with Indo-European roots.²²⁷ Nevertheless, in a Norse context, as such, the term ‘prosimetrum’ does not indicate exactly what one might expect to find in terms of narrative content, and its generic applications are rather diverse.

Although prosimetra are extant in a number of Old Norse-Icelandic written genres, the oral prehistory of Norse-Icelandic prosimetrum is speculative. The oldest preserved prosimetra are runic, but they are too short to bear solid witness to oral

²²⁴ For other medieval examples, including Hugo Bononiensis, see Eduard Norden, *Die Antike Kunstprose*, vol. 2 (Darmstadt: Wissenschaft Buchgesellschaft, 1958) 756-757.

²²⁵ Thomas Blount (1618-1679) in his *Glossographia: or A dictionary, interpreting all such hard vvords, whether Hebrew, Greek, Latin, Italian, Spanish, French, Teutonick, Belgick, British or Saxon; as are now used in our refined English tongue*, 1659. Microfilm copy from British Library, reel position: Thomas / 199 : E. 1573 [1].

²²⁶ According to Dagmar Bartoňková, O. Immisch began to use the term ‘prosimetrum’ in 1921. See Bartoňková, “Prosimetrum, the Mixed Style, in Ancient Literature,” *Eirene* 14 (1976): 65-92, at 65.

²²⁷ See O’Donoghe, *Skaldic Verse*, p. 1; M. L. West, *Indo-European Poetry and Myth* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007) pp. 61-62, see in particular p. 67 fn. 97 for further references; Maurice Winternitz, *A History of Indian Literature*, vol. 1 (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1981) 2. It should be noted that while perhaps present at the proto-Indo-European stage of development, the prosimetric form is not exclusively Indo-European, and its ancient use was widespread. One clear example is the quotation of songs in the Old Testament, a prosimetric form analysed in Terry Giles and William J. Doan, *Twice Used Songs: Performance Criticism of the Songs of Ancient Israel* (Peasbody, MA: Hendrickson, 2009). The prosimetric form in the Ancient Near East is discussed in *Verse in Ancient Near Eastern Prose*, ed. Johannes C. de Moor & Wilfred G. E. Watson, *Alter Orient und Altes Testament* 42 (Kevelaer: Verlag Butzon & Bercker; Neukirchen-Vluyn: Neukirchener Verlag, 1993). For discussion of the boundaries between prose and verse in Old English, see Thomas A. Bredehoft, “The Boundaries Between Verse and Prose in Old English Literature,” *Old English Literature in its Manuscript Context*, ed. Joyce Tally Lionarons, *Medieval European Studies* 5 (Morgantown: West Virginia University Press, 2004) pp. 139-172. Further examples of prosimetra from around the world can be found *Prosimetrum: Cross-Cultural Perspectives on Narrative in Prose and Verse*, ed. Joseph Harris & Karl Reichl (Cambridge: Brewer, 1997).

narrative prosimetric traditions.²²⁸ Most metrical runic inscriptions are in eddic metre, with only a few skaldic inscriptions extant.²²⁹

In terms of narrative prosimetrum, the conjectures are thus:

- Verse survives that once had lost oral prose attached to it.
- Oral verse must have been explained in normal language, and this prose is described as 'lost' because it was fluid and changing.
- The extant prose with the verse is thus (probably) not the same as that which accompanied the verse in the oral period.
- The presence of prose in extant Norse prosimetra could be an indicator that prose was present in the oral period.²³⁰

As also noted by Joseph Harris, these speculations are despite some occurrences of prosimetra in the related medieval vernacular literatures of England, Germany and Scandinavia that likely predate Old Norse-Icelandic examples.²³¹ As for the extant Norse-Icelandic prosimetra, eddic forms can be observed in legal texts, and in the collection called the Poetic Edda (the *Codex Regius* manuscript GKS 2365 4to), with several kindred poems appearing in a limited number of other manuscripts. The Icelandic grammatical and poetic literature is prosimetric, the prominent example being Snorri Sturluson's *Edda*, which contains numerous examples of both types of

²²⁸ A full discussion of runic prosimetra is beyond the scope of this project. For several examples and commentary, see further Patrick Larson, "Runes," *A Companion to Old Norse-Icelandic Literature*, ed. Rory McTurk, Blackwell Companions to Literature 31 (Malden, MA: Blackwell, 2007) pp. 403-426. See also Michael Schulte, "Early Runic 'metrical' inscriptions - How metrical are they?" *Versatility in Versification: Multidisciplinary Approaches to Metrics*, ed. Tonya Kim Dewey & Frog, Berkeley Insights in Linguistics and Semiotics 74 (New York: Peter Lang, 2009) 3-22; Terje Spurkland, *Norwegian Runes and Runic Inscriptions*, trans. Betsy van der Hoek (Woodbridge: Boydell, 2005) 120-121 (*fornyrdislæg*), 182 (Latin verse) 183 and 194 (*dróttkvætt*).

²²⁹ Most notably the Karlevi stone on Öland, Sweden (Öl 1; DR 411). See Larson, "Runes," p. 404.

²³⁰ Cf. Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 131, cf. 133.

²³¹ He notes prosimetra are found in these languages in charms, runic inscriptions, in the Anglo-Saxon Chronicle and in the composition of Anglo-Saxon manuscripts. C. E. Wright in *The Cultivation of Saga in Anglo-Saxon England* (Edinburgh: Oliver and Boyd, 1939) suggests analogous saga telling in Anglo-Saxon England. Nicolas Jacobs in "Celtic Saga and the Contexts of Old English Elegiac Poetry," *Études celtiques* 26 (1989): 95-142 at p. 111 ff. argues that the balance of probabilities is in favour of Old English having had a prosimetric saga in oral performance. See also Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 131, and fn. 2, same page. For a discussion of the prosimetrum of the Anglo-Saxon Chronicle see Thomas A. Bredehoft, *Textual Histories: Readings in the Anglo-Saxon Chronicle* (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2001) 72-118; for the composition of prosimetra in Anglo-Saxon manuscripts see Thomas A. Bredehoft, "The Boundaries Between Verse and Prose in Old English Literature."

poetry in verses that function as quotations, as well as longer sections of skaldic and eddic poems.²³² The first section, *Gylfaginning*, is predominantly eddic, whilst subsequent sections preserve examples of the skaldic form in what was conceived of as a handbook for skalds.²³³ As for the saga genre, the *konungasögur*, *Íslendingasögur*,²³⁴ *fornaldarsögur* and *Sturlunga saga*²³⁵ (contemporary sagas of Icelandic history from the 12th and 13th centuries), consistently contain verse. The *fornaldarsögur* containing both prose and verse belong to this prosimetric strand in Old Norse literature.²³⁶

The *biskupasögur* [‘sagas of bishops’] are on the whole not heavily prosimetric, most having no verse at all in their prose narratives.²³⁷ One version of *Jóns saga Helga* (the older redaction) has a stanza in what is probably an independent story (the younger version has no verse). The stanza is a speech stanza introduced with “þá kvað hann vísu,” and the performance context of the stanza is not particularly strong.²³⁸ *Hungrvaka* has two occurrences of verse, one in Latin,²³⁹ *Páls saga* has four,²⁴⁰ and *Kristni saga* has eleven stanzas. The 14th century version of the saga of Bishop Guðmundr Arason by Arngrímur Brandsson has 116 stanzas, many of which are excerpts from longer poems.²⁴¹

²³² Cf. Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 136.

²³³ Although skalds typically composed verse in the skaldic metres, sometimes they used eddic metres for skaldic subject matter; in these cases they counted the syllables more strictly. See above for the problems faced in dividing the eddic from the skaldic form.

²³⁴ See Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” pp. 148-55.

²³⁵ See Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” pp. 141-145; Quinn, “The Use of Eddic Poetry in Contemporary Sagas.”

²³⁶ Since the present thesis is concerned chiefly with the prosimetrum of the *fornaldarsögur*, the remarks on the prosimetrum of the other saga subgenres are intended for orientation only.

²³⁷ Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” pp. 135, fn. 16, 136.

²³⁸ *Jóns saga helga (eldri gerð)*, *Byskupa sögur*, ed. Guðni Jónsson, vol. 2 (n.p.: Íslendingasagnaútgáfan, 1953) pp. 1-74, at pp. 11-12.

²³⁹ *Hungrvaka*, *Byskupa sögur*, ed. Guðni Jónsson, vol. 1 (n.p.: Íslendingasagnaútgáfan, 1953) pp. 1-31, at pp. 19, 26.

²⁴⁰ *Páls saga*, *Byskupa sögur*, ed. Guðni Jónsson, vol. 1 (n.p.: Íslendingasagnaútgáfan, 1953) pp. 251-283, at pp. 269, 281-282.

²⁴¹ See *Saga Guðmundar Arasonar, Hólabiskups, eptir Arngrím Ábóta*, *Biskupa sögur*, vol. 2 (Kaupmannahöfn: Íslenska bókmentafélag, 1878) pp. 1-220.

The verses in the *riddarasögur*, or lack thereof, will be covered in part three on the *fornaldarsögur*. Both types of Old Norse poetry, eddic and skaldic, are found in prosimetra of various genres: typically, the prose in *Íslendingasögur* and *konungasögur* is mixed with skaldic poetry, whereas eddic poetry is found in prosaic *fornaldarsögur* narratives.²⁴²

The Role of Verse in the Sagas

The role of verse in a prosimetrum can be approached in two ways, firstly by examining the contexts in which verse appears in terms of what affect the author hopes the verse to achieve,²⁴³ and secondly by determining the functional role of the stanza in its prose (whether it is an evidence stanza or an occasional/dialogue stanza). The context of the appearance of each stanza must be examined by reference to the individual saga in which it appears, and this is what I do in Part Three for the individual *fornaldarsögur*. Nevertheless, some general observations will be considered here in brief before moving on to a discussion of the role of verse in prosimetra.

The role of verse in achieving a certain affect is well-documented; Davíð Erlingsson's expression of the various uses of prose and verse is typical: "The straightforward, objective prose is obviously well suited to advancing the action but dialogue, direct speech, often in verse, was the main vehicle for finer characterisations and psychological interpretation."²⁴⁴ Here the verse is thought to be able to achieve affects that were impossible in saga prose. Lars Lönnroth too posits verse to play an enhancing role in the saga prose: the saga writers "pushed the separation between factual narration and dramatic exhortation a step further by letting the saga prose take

²⁴² The majority, although not all, of the texts in these genres are prosimetric. See below for a list of prosimetric *fornaldarsögur*.

²⁴³ See, for example, Arthur Hruby, *Wann sprechen die Personen der isländischen Saga eine Strophe? Eine Studie zur Technik der Saga* (Wien, 1932).

²⁴⁴ Davíð Erlingsson, "Prose and Verse in Icelandic Legendary Fiction," p. 383.

care of the former while reserving poetry for the latter.”²⁴⁵ Related to this are Vésteinn Ólason question as to why saga authors (of the *Íslendingasögur*, but this is also relevant to the *fornaldarsögur*) include verses when they rarely move the narrative forward and indeed sometimes retard it. The four reasons he gives are: 1) the verses were an important part of the oral tradition that the saga author drew upon and worked in, and it was therefore obvious to him to include the stanzas, 2) due to the influence of older sagas, especially *konungasögur*, in which stanzas function in an authenticating manner, 3) the author used verse to express emotion for the character, since this is unnatural in the saga prose-style, especially when regarding the characters’ “inner-life,” 4) they are used as a retardation device in the narrative, allowing the narrative to become dense before something significant happens.²⁴⁶ Half the reason therefore for including verse, in Vésteinn’s view, is for their artistic affect that could not be conveyed in prose.

The functional role of verse in sagas can be more readily abstracted, and has been the topic of a number of papers in which the role of verse in saga prose has been analysed and classified. Here I discuss those papers which have proved most illuminating for me in the study of eddic verse in the *fornaldarsögur*.²⁴⁷

²⁴⁵ Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue,” p. 83; see also “*Hjálmar’s Death Song* and the Delivery of Eddic Poetry,” p. 198.

²⁴⁶ Vésteinn Ólason, p. 124-125. On the role of stanzas as a retardation device see also Hallvard Magerøy, who argues that suspense is only one of many factors to be considered in a narrative using retardation devices, “Skaldestrofer som retardasjonmiddel i Islendingesogene,” *Sjöttíu Ritgerðir: Helgaðar Jakobi Benediktssyni 20. júlí 1977*, ed. Einar G. Pétursson and Jónas Kristjánsson, vol. 2, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar á Íslandi Rit 12 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1977) pp. 586-599.

²⁴⁷ Note that most work done in this vein relates to skaldic rather than eddic prosimetra, although much of this is still useful. In addition to those essays commented on in detail here, the following bibliography has been important in formulating my thoughts: S. Beyschlag, “Möglichkeiten mündlicher Überlieferung in der Königssaga,” *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 68 (1953): 109-139, in which he argues for the concept of *Begleitprosa*, which has most recently been argued against by Shami Ghosh, *Kings’ Sagas and Norwegian History: Problems and Perspectives*, The Northern World 54 (Leiden: Brill, 2011) p. 71 ff.; Alois Wolf, “Zur Rolle der Vísur in der altnordischen Prosa,” *Festschrift Leonhard C. Franz zum 70. Geburtstag*, ed. Osmund Menghin and Hermann M. Ölberg, Innsbrucker Beiträge zur Kulturwissenschaft 11 (Innsbruck: Sprachwissenschaftliche Institut der Leopold-Franzens Universität, 1965) pp. 459-484; Dietrich Hofmann, “Vers und Prosa in der mündlich gepflegten mittelalterlichen Erzählkunst der germanischen Länder,” *Frühmittelalterliche Studien* 5 (1971): 135-175; “Die mündliche Sagaerzählkunst aus pragmatischer Sicht,” *skandinavistik* 12 (1982): 12-21; “Sagaprosa als Partner von Skaldenstrophen,” *Mediaeval Scandinavia* 11 (1978-79): 68-81; Klaus von See, “Skaldenstrophe und Sagaprosa: Ein Beitrag zum Problem der mündlichen Überlieferung in der altnordischen Literatur,” *Medieval Scandinavia* 10 (1977): 58-82 (who builds on Wolf); “Mündliche Prosa und Skaldendichtung. Mit einum Exkurs über Skaldensagas und Trobadorbographien,” *Mediaeval Scandinavia* 11 (1978-1979): 82-91; Guðrún Ingólfsdóttir, “Un hlutverk vísna í Íslendinga sögum,” *Skáldskaparmál*

While it was Sigurður Nordal who in 1920 introduced the concept of the two functional roles of verse into modern Norse literary studies,²⁴⁸ it was Bjarni Einarsson's article "On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature" that was to prove the most influential,²⁴⁹ and all the most important comments since his article appeared build on his conclusions. A notable exception is Alois Wolf's article from 1965,²⁵⁰ which appeared in between Sigurður Nordal and Bjarni Einarsson's pieces. Part of the point of Einarsson's article is to exonerate saga writers who allow discrepancies in their prosimetra between the prose and verse to stand, but in doing so also provides a survey of the role of verse in various saga subgenres. His arguments will be reviewed in brief here and I will discuss how Diana Whaley and Bjarne Fidjestøl expand on his conclusions.²⁵¹

Bjarni identifies two main roles of verse in saga prose (and it is the prose that indicates how a stanza should be taken): the first role is as evidence, and the second is the verse is part of the story.²⁵² Evidence stanzas are introduced with formulae such as "svá segir X," "þess getr X," and "sem X segir," where X is the name of a skald. If such

1 (1990): 226-240; the collection of articles *Skaldsagas: Text, Vocation, and Desire in the Icelandic Sagas of Poets*, ed. Russell Poole, *Ergänzungsbande zum Reallexikon der Germanischen Altertumskunde* 27 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2001).

²⁴⁸ *Egils saga Skalla-Grimssonar*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, Íslenzk fornrit 2 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenzka fornritafélag) p. lxxv; Sigurður Nordal, *Snorri Sturluson* (Copenhagen: n. p., 1920) 169.

²⁴⁹ Bjarni Einarsson, "On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature," *Mediaeval Scandinavia* 7 (1974): 118-125.

²⁵⁰ Wolf, "Zur Rolle der Vísur in der Altnordischen Prosa."

²⁵¹ See also Joseph Harris, who, in his overview article on Norse prosimetrum, refines Bjarni Einarsson's role division of evidence and "art and entertainment" and instead locates the use of verse at two poles: one evidential and one dramatic. Verse used in an evidence capacity "is part of the 'telling'" of the narrative, its authority coming from a poet who is not the narrator of the saga. Dramatic verse is part of the 'showing' of the saga, and the verses come from the mouths of characters in the saga, (p. 142) and Harris argues this is a superior description of the role of verse in comparison to Bjarni's because "dramatic verse can supply 'art and entertainment' and at the same time lend some kind of support or create an atmosphere" (p. 157). Harris recognises the subtleties in saga narration by acknowledging that these values sometimes blend: "In practice, however, dramatic verses may have evidential value, and verses that are not strictly dramatic may contribute to a sense of interactive density in the scene" (Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 142). Cf. Frog, "Speech-Acts in Skaldic Verse."

²⁵² The same distinctions have been labelled differently by other scholars. For example, Diana Whaley terms them 'authenticating stanzas' and 'situational stanzas' and she notes that they have also been described as 'substantiating' and 'non-substantiating' stanzas and alternatively 'reports' and 'speech-acts,' see Diana Whaley, "Skalds and Situational Verses in Heimskringla," p. 252.

stanzas are omitted, the story is not damaged, but the artistic enjoyment of the narrative is damaged.²⁵³ Stanzas that are part of the story are typically introduced with “þá kvað X,” or “þá kvað X vísu,” and are often “a rhymed reply to a question.”²⁵⁴ As for the saga subgenres, Bjarni adduces that the *konungasögur* employ mainly evidence stanzas,²⁵⁵ but that the *Íslendingasögur* employ stanzas mainly for entertainment and rarely for evidence or confirmation.²⁵⁶ In the *fornaldarsögur*, however, Bjarni concludes that the occurrence of verse for the purpose of providing evidence, introduced with the formula “sem hér segir” or similar, is much more common than in the *Íslendingasögur*:

The reason is obviously that some of these sagas were written on the basis of older poems about heroes of the past. But some of these quotations may of course be wholly fictitious. There are also dialogues in verse in some of them and many cases of versified replies and statements which were either written by the saga-authors themselves or made by the story-teller if it was originally an oral saga.²⁵⁷

Here Bjarni has blended discussion of the function of verse (evidence) with the context in which verses are found (all of which in his examples of dialogue or versified replies would be stanzas that are part of the story) and with speculation on their origin. Ideally, these three aspects should be considered separately (function, context and origin of the stanzas) since, for example, the origin of a stanza need not impact upon its function in a prosimeton, although their permutations must be also be included together in a rounded discussion of the generation of meaning in prosimetra. According to Bjarni, the *fornaldarsögur* thus occupy a middle ground in between the role of verse as found in the *konungasögur* and the role of verse as found in the *Íslendingasögur*, which between them display “a marked qualitative difference” in the

²⁵³ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature,” p. 118.

²⁵⁴ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature,” p. 118.

²⁵⁵ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature,” pp. 119, 224.

²⁵⁶ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature,” pp. 122, 124. Several have objected to an overly strong association of only the stanzas as part of the story being linked with art and entertainment, and suggest that the aesthetic affects of evidence stanzas ought to be kept more firmly in mind. See e.g. Whaley, “Skalds and Situational Verses in Heimskringla,” p. 254. Cf. also Wolf, who comments that both the source value and the entertainment factor of the stanzas must be considered, “Zur Rolle der Visur,” p. 461.

²⁵⁷ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature,” p. 124.

manner in which they employ verse,²⁵⁸ and thus a mixture of stanzas as evidence (which can be quoted as sources) and as part of the story can be expected in the legendary sagas.²⁵⁹

Diana Whaley in her 1993 article “Skalds and Situational Verses in *Heimskringla*” builds on Bjarni Einarsson’s analysis, and uses his division of the role of stanzas into evidence stanzas and those that are part of the story as the starting point of her own discussion, but elaborates on their topic and their context in the saga before turning her attention to a more sophisticated method of classifying those stanzas that Bjarni describes as “part of the story.”

Whaley attributes to the evidence verses “a primarily authenticating function” and states that in skaldic prosimetra such as those that make up *Heimskringla* the evidence verses “are typically cited at a pause in the prose narrative in order to validate, and perhaps elaborate on, what goes before – more often than not an account of a battle.”²⁶⁰ Whaley also emphasises the source-quality of the authenticating stanzas: their content “often duplicates that of the prose,” and their removal, although the narrative would not collapse without them, “would be diminished in authority and aesthetically poorer.” The evidence verses therefore can be seen as not simply providing the means by which to validate the narrative, but also many times provide the actual source for the prose and also contribute an important part of the narrative’s artfulness. Whaley also elaborates on the role of stanzas that Bjarni Einarsson terms “part of the story.” Whaley points out that the speakers of such verses are protagonists within the story, and belong “to the same time and place as the events described there.” The composition of the stanzas is impromptu in such circumstances, and the

²⁵⁸ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature,” p. 124.

²⁵⁹ Hubert Seelow uses Bjarni’s classifications in his paper on the role of verse in the *fornaldarsögur*, in which he reviews Bjarni’s article and the percentage of evidence and story verses in several *fornaldarsögur*. He notes the existence of hybrid strophes that function both as evidence and speech stanzas (p. 9), and argues that strophes classed by Bjarni as part of the story stanzas are used in a greater variety of functions than evidence stanzas (p. 16). He also surveys a limited number of prosimetric *fornaldarsögur* to discuss the role of verse in their prose narratives. “Zur Rolle der Strophen in den Fornaldarsögur,” *Fourth International Saga Conference, München, July 30th - August 4th, 1979* (München: [n.p.], 1979) papers paginated individually.

²⁶⁰ Whaley, “Skalds and Situational Verses in *Heimskringla*,” p. 251.

content of the stanzas may well affect events: “Thus they potentially form the kernel of an episode, and their removal would damage the plot structure.”²⁶¹

Whaley moves beyond an analysis of the role of verses in saga prose to an analysis of how the verse affects the narrative world and in what manner it does so. This is an important contribution by Whaley to the study of the manner in which situational verses affect their use of being part of the story, although it is outside the scope of this thesis. It can be summarised by saying that Whaley undertakes the sophisticated categorisation of situational verses using a typology adapted from John R. Searle’s “A Classification of Illocutionary Acts”²⁶² and applies his typology to skaldic poetry, particularly that found in *Heimskringla*.²⁶³ It should be noted that this classification system differs from those discussed before because Whaley’s assignation of stanzas to various types relies on the content of the stanza rather than its role in the prose, and thus it will not be used in the present discussion of the role of verse in prosimetra.

Building on Whaley’s analysis of the differences between evidence verses and verse used as part of the story in prosimetra, we can see that both evidence/authenticating stanzas and those that are part of the story in fact both have the potential to be “the kernel of an episode,” as Whaley puts it, the difference being that the first type (evidence stanzas) are accompanied by supplementary prose that comes before them, whereas this is not needed for the latter type (story stanzas). We can also see from this observation that neither type of verse need necessarily be older than the prose context in which it is found: both types of verse could easily be composed for their respective functions in prosimetra, to add an authenticating feature to the narrative or to become part of the story. Likewise, depending on the prose context, the same stanza could potentially be used as either an authenticating verse or

²⁶¹ Whaley, “Skalds and Situational Verses in Heimskringla,” p. 251.

²⁶² John R. Searle, “A Classification of Illocutionary Acts,” *Language and Society* 5 (1976): 1-23.

²⁶³ See Whaley, “Skalds and Situational Verses in Heimskringla,” p. 256 ff.

as part of the story, since it is the prose context of a verse that determines its role rather than the content of the verse per se – nevertheless, some stanzas may lend themselves more readily to one role or the other. From this, we could also note that it might not be a surprise to encounter stanzas that are in between functions, for example stanzas used as part of the story that also play a quasi-authenticating role in the narrative. In the context of the *fornaldarsögur*, this can be seen when characters report back on what has happened earlier in the plot.

Bjarne Fidjestøl's article "Skaldic Stanzas in Saga-Prose: Observations on the Relationship Between Prose and Verse in Snorri's *Heimskringla*" is found in the same volume as Whaley's useful article discussed above, and his article also builds on Bjarni Einarsson's discussion. Fidjestøl terms the manner in which the verse is used in the prose as 'the mode of presentation.'²⁶⁴ Fidjestøl goes in a slightly different direction from Bjarni Einarsson (whose divisions he does use)²⁶⁵ by emphasising the importance of the temporality of the context in which the verse and prose are used in combination. He employs a threefold division: 1) sections in which temporality is absent (for example in descriptions or introductions), 2) the narrative, which is "conditional on the passage of time" and 3) reports or scenes in the narrative, records "of events in which the time taken in the telling is far shorter than the time actually taken by the events related." Speech is usually included in these reports or scenes, and in these the past and the present is merged. In such a context, skaldic poetry is usually quoted.²⁶⁶ This discussion of temporality is a useful one, and in addition I take from Fidjestøl's article his emphasis on determining how well integrated the stanza is into the narrative of the saga prose, particularly for the stanzas that are part of the story.

²⁶⁴ Bjarne Fidjestøl, "Skaldic Stanzas in Saga-Prose," p. 261.

²⁶⁵ I do not find the manner in which Fidjestøl attempts to build upon Bjarni Einarsson's twofold division particularly helpful. He terms the evidence/authenticating role of verse as 'report' and the role in which the stanza contributes to the story as the presentation of a 'scene' or a 'staged episode.' He also differentiates between sources and dialogue. The taxonomy he build is not helpful in clarifying the role of stanzas in prosimetrum up to this point due to a confusing use of the word 'scene' and an overly complex and overlapping construction of types of uses of verse.

²⁶⁶ Fidjestøl, "Skaldic Stanzas in Saga-Prose," p. 261.

He also makes the point that “for the study of the relationship between prose and verse it is however of more significance that the essential content of the stanza is not reduplicated in the prose.”²⁶⁷

In summary, typically, there are thought to be two roles played by verse in Old Norse prose: evidence-based quotations or verses in a situational role.²⁶⁸ Bjarni Einarsson, however, has a slightly different classification, preferring to divide verses into one group of evidence based stanzas and a second group of story stanzas, those that are considered part of the story, and this classification has proved popular.²⁶⁹ This implies two different opinions on whether the verses carry the narrative, because although evidence stanzas can be skipped without damaging the content, if one skips story stanzas the understanding of the context as a whole is damaged, largely because story stanzas are usually a rhymed reply to a question.²⁷⁰ The latter type of prosimetric verse has also been termed ‘ornamental,’ but, as Heather O’Donoghue has pointed out, the narrative function of situational or non-narrative carrying non-corroborative verse exceeds that of merely ornamental.²⁷¹

In the *konungasögur*, stanzas are chiefly quoted as evidence, but in the *Íslendingasögur* this is rarely the case, where they function mainly as entertainment. Similarly, in the contemporary sagas, stanzas are chiefly quoted for entertainment (80% of the time), rather than evidence (20% of the time).²⁷² Bjarni Einarsson emphasises that in the *fornaldarsögur*, verse is used as evidence far more commonly than in *Íslendingasögur*,²⁷³ whereas Karsten Friis-Jensen emphasises that the

²⁶⁷ Fidjestøl, “Skaldic Stanzas in Saga-Prose,” p. 264.

²⁶⁸ O’Donoghue, *Skaldic Verse and the Poetics of Saga Narrative*; Carl Phelpstead, “‘With Chunks of Poetry in Between’: *The Lord of the Rings* and Saga Poetics,” *Tolkien Studies* 5 (2008): 23-28, at 25, 35 n. 12.

²⁶⁹ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the rôle of verse in saga-literature,” p. 118.

²⁷⁰ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the rôle of verse in saga-literature,” p. 118, 122.

²⁷¹ O’Donoghue, *Skaldic Verse and the Poetics of Saga Narrative*, pp. 5-6.

²⁷² Bjarni Einarsson, “On the rôle of verse in saga-literature,” pp. 118-119, 121.

²⁷³ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the rôle of verse in saga-literature,” p. 124.

prosimetric form is displayed in the abundance of versified dialogue in the *fornaldarsögur*.²⁷⁴ Either way, such verses in the *fornaldarsögur* may, of course, be wholly fictitious (invented by the saga author), or made up by the story-teller if it originally were an oral saga.²⁷⁵ Certainly evidence based quotations of verse make up a clear category if one needs to define the obvious roles of the verse in their prose contexts; the idea that some verses are story verses and thus carry narrative is an important one, although they are not in the majority in the *fornaldarsögur*; the last useful category however - dialogue verses - are common in *fornaldarsögur*.

²⁷⁴ Friis-Jensen, *Saxo Grammaticus as Latin Poet*, p. 46. Nevertheless, “the structural description of Ingimundr’s *Orms saga* suggests that a recurrent formal arrangement in which longer poems cluster at the end of a saga may be very old.” He gives the examples of *Egils saga Skalla-Grímssonar*, *Qrvar-Odds saga*, and *Hákonar saga góða* in *Heimkringla* (Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 135, and 135 fn. 14). He is anticipated by Friis-Jensen and Peter G. Foote, “Sagnaskemtan: Reykjahólar 1119,” *Saga-Book of the Viking Society* 14 (1955-56): 226-39.

²⁷⁵ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the rôle of verse in saga-literature,” p. 124.

The Prose of the *Poetic Edda*

The *Poetic Edda* and several of the full poems in the “eddic appendix” are versiprose, that is, they largely consist of verse with a small amount of prose interspersed at points between the stanzas. This is contrast to the format we find in most of the *fornaldarsögur*, which are prosimetric, and contain more prose than verse. Certain sections of several *fornaldarsögur* could be described as versiprose, for example *Hervararkviða* in *Hervarar saga*, which contains small amounts of prose narrative inbetween the stanzas, as could other blocks of verse that contain small connecting phrases inbetween the stanzas, usually of the type “and yet he said.”

What follows is an investigation into the prose of the *Poetic Edda* and several of the associated poems. Note that *Grottasöngur* is treated separately, in part two of the thesis as an appendix to the analysis of *Gylfaginning*. This is to keep the comments on sections of *Snorra Edda* together. The following explores whether it is conceivable that the prose found in the *Poetic Edda* and with the associated poems can have come from oral tradition (in one form or another), and what prose must have been added as a result of the transition of the poems into written forms. Neither of these possibilities is privileged, and I explore equally the workings of the prose that must have come from a written context and prose in positions and in content that may represent oral prose traditions. In order to make it completely clear in which manuscripts and in what order the poems appear, I will head this discussion with a presentation of the manuscripts of the *Poetic Edda* and the associated poems.

The Origins of the Prose of the *Poetic Edda*

The two manuscripts of the *Poetic Edda*, R and A, are thought to go back to a common original, designated *R.²⁷⁶ Since some of the prose pieces in the Codex Regius manuscript are also found its sister manuscript, AM 748 4to (which is not a copy of the Codex Regius), the prose pieces cannot originate in the Codex Regius.

²⁷⁶ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Heusler, p. 18.

Robert Kellogg calls the figure responsible for adding these prose pieces to the poems “the Compiler.” Heusler points out that such a compilation is unlikely to be the work of one man, and has rather developed over time,²⁷⁷ but nevertheless I accept the Compiler as a convenient shorthand term for this longer process of compilation. According to Kellogg, the Compiler is not identical with the scribe of the manuscript, but “a more abstract, anterior figure,” and nor does Kellogg identify the Compiler with the author of the poems.²⁷⁸ Kellogg thus envisages a process whereby an ‘author’ has created the poems (presumably orally), they have been compiled in a written form into an antecedent collection to the several we now have by the Compiler, who has added prose pieces, and this collection has been copied several times by scribes to account for the two copies extant. The two extant *Poetic Edda* manuscripts retain the voice of the Compiler, as both “guiding organizer” and “speaker.”²⁷⁹ Although this is one way of explaining the appearance of the prose passages, I disagree that the prose pieces are necessarily additions to pieces that were always purely in verse. It is possible that the explanatory prose context was present and necessary in the oral prehistory of the poems, and came into a written form at the same time of the poem. It is worth remembering that in all of the contexts in which eddic poetry is now preserved (*Gylfaginning*, the *fornaldarsögur*), it is preserved along with prose, and this may have also been the case in the oral period.

One indication perhaps of whether the poems were once purely verse compositions without prose is to analyse whether the prose is necessary in comparison to what is told in the verse. In any case, it is necessary to distinguish between the prose that conceivably could have been necessary or at least present in the oral period, and the prose which obviously owes its existence to the preservation of the poems in written form; one type of prose found in the *Poetic Edda* that must belong to this is the prose speaker markings, which would seem unnecessary for a

²⁷⁷ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Heusler, p. 30.

²⁷⁸ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 92.

²⁷⁹ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 91.

performance of the poems in a purely oral environment, and likewise when plays are performed from scripts today the character markings for dialogue are not spoken as part of the play when it is performed.

The prose is narrated in two voices. One is same voice as the verse, since the narrator moves back and forth from the prose to the verse without comment; Kellogg identifies this voice with one adopted by the Compiler, who “moves the narrative back and forth from his prose to the poetry that he has presumably inherited from oral tradition.”²⁸⁰ In Kellogg’s view, the prose is part of the written, literate aspect of the Poetic Edda, while the poetry equals the oral part. Kellogg identifies a second voice adopted by the compiler as that of the 13th century scholar, who has critical distance from the material, one that is able to refer to the poems as poems and provide what I describe below as “descriptive titles” for the poems, as well as being able to comment on the poems from an ideological remove and to recognise a discontinuity of time between the tradition and his own time, for example by referring to an event as having happened in ancient times or being recorded in *fornfræði* [‘ancient literature’], in *The Death of Sinfjötli*.²⁸¹ Likewise, in the prose passage described by Kellogg as “a note” between *Reginismál* and *Fáfnismál* he moves even more rhetorically back from the text when he explains a custom from “heathen times,” and in doing so makes the distance between then and now very clear for his audience/reader.²⁸²

Kellogg conceives of the prose pieces in the *Poetic Edda* as “summaries of background information” provided by the Compiler “for the short eddic poems,”²⁸³ and the head notes to the poems are there to “assist in telling the story clearly.”²⁸⁴ Torfi H. Tulinius suggests the initial role of the prose was to put the verse in context

²⁸⁰ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 92.

²⁸¹ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 92, 93.

²⁸² Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 93.

²⁸³ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 91.

²⁸⁴ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” p. 92.

by providing the story, such as in *Lokasenna*, but that the role of the prose gradually became diversified. In *Reginismál* and *Fáfnismál*, for example, the prose advances the plot while the stanzas carry the dialogue. The prose in *Grímnismál*, meanwhile, not only puts the poem in context but adds additional information not found in the verses.²⁸⁵

Although it has been suggested that in the oral period too, the prosimetric saga-like form was a context in which eddic poetry existed,²⁸⁶ it is impossible to know, however, to what extent these *Begleitprosa* [‘prose accompaniments’]²⁸⁷ supplemented the verses in the oral period, if at all. Harris notes that “once explanatory prose had entered the manuscript tradition, it would have been copied and adapted, and could even have been subject to influence from written sagas or Latin sources,”²⁸⁸ and to this it might be worth adding that oral tradition may also still have had a part to play, even when the prose accompaniments were written down, providing differing contexts and new influences that became part of the manuscript tradition. Similarly, John Lindow links the prose that likely accompanied eddic and skaldic verse in oral tradition with the explanations that Snorri gives of the stanzas he quotes, as if Snorri knew prose explanations of mythological and heroic allusions, he likely made use of them in his *Edda*, although Lindow points out that this cannot be proved, and that Snorri must have in any case faced some instances of unclear material which he attempts to homogenise and elucidate.²⁸⁹

²⁸⁵ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 58.

²⁸⁶ See e.g. Cecil Wood, “A Skaldic Note.” *Neophilologus* 44 (1960): 338-343; Lars Lönnroth, “Hjálmar’s Death-Song and the Delivery of Eddic Poetry,” *The Academy of Odin: Selected Papers on Old Norse Literature*, The Viking Collection 19 (Odense: University Press of Southern Denmark: 2011) pp. 191-218 [Originally published: *Speculum* 46 (1971): 1-20]; “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga.” Cf. Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 133.

²⁸⁷ I use Beyschlag’s term in an extended sense, and not just in a skaldic context. Beyschlag, “Möglichkeiten mündlicher Überlieferung in der Königssaga.”

²⁸⁸ Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 133.

²⁸⁹ Lindow, “Myth and Mythography,” p. 36.

The Manuscripts of the *Poetic Edda*

There are two manuscripts of the *Poetic Edda*: the Codex Regius manuscript and a fragmentary manuscript, A. The Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda* is a small quarto, the pages 19cm tall and 13cm in width.²⁹⁰ There are 90 written pages in total, on six gatherings (the first 5 have 8 leaves, the last has 5), written by one scribe throughout, and although the manuscript is complete at the beginning and the end, after the fourth gathering there is a lacuna,²⁹¹ which was present before Bishop Brynjólf acquired the manuscript between 1639-1643.²⁹² The manuscript is from around 1270.²⁹³

GkS 2365 4to contains c.29 poems as separated in the editions, although Heusler counts around 40 poetic units (some fragmentary and not counting what he considers interpolations).²⁹⁴ Of the 3037 lines of texts of the manuscript, Heusler counts 370 as prose (not including the titles), this is around 12%, and they are distributed unequally throughout the manuscript.²⁹⁵ The Codex Regius manuscript shows evidence of a deliberate organisational scheme; the first half of the codex holds mythological poems, while the second half holds the heroic poetry.

The fragmentary manuscript of the *Poetic Edda* from 1300-1325, AM 748 I a 4to,²⁹⁶ is an extremely important manuscript because it is the only source of variants for some

²⁹⁰ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edd*, intro. Andreas Heusler, p. 15. Where I reference a general edition of the *Poetic Edda*, I use Bugge. GkS 2365 4to is available in facsimile in *Codex Regius of the Elder Edd*, intro. Andreas Heusler.

²⁹¹ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edd*, intro. Andreas Heusler, p. 15.

²⁹² *Codex Regius of the Elder Edd*, intro. Andreas Heusler, pp. 7-8.

²⁹³ *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda: AM 748 I and II 4:O*, intro. Elias Wessén, *Corpus codicum Islandicorum Medii Aevi* 17 (Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1945) 16.

²⁹⁴ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edd*, intro. Andreas Heusler, p. 18.

²⁹⁵ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edd*, intro. Andreas Heusler, p. 19.

²⁹⁶ This manuscript exists in two facsimile editions. The first from 1896 is edited by Finnur Jónsson: *Håndskriftet Nr. 748, 4to, bl. 1-6, i den Arna-magnæanske samling (Brudstykke af den ældre Edda) i fototypisk og diplomatisk gengivelse*, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur (København: Møllers, 1896), and this edition also includes a diplomatic transcription. The younger facsimile is *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda. AM 748 I and II 4:O*, intro. Elias Wessén, *Corpus codicum Islandicorum Medii Aevi* 17 (Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1945).

of the poems found in GkS 2365 4to, the Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda*, to which A can be considered a sister, and is the only record of the poem *Baldrs draumar*. When the manuscript came into Arni Magnússon's possession it was bound into one book with AM 748 I b 4to and AM 748 II 4to, although as I and II clearly had nothing to do with each, they quickly were separated.²⁹⁷ The manuscript is dated 1300-1325,²⁹⁸ making it contemporary with the Codex Regius manuscript of *Snorra Edda* and about a generation younger than the Codex Regius of the *Poetic Edda*.²⁹⁹ Although somewhat riddled with gaps – it is not possible to say how extensive the manuscript one was – it contains the complete texts of the following eddic poems: *Baldrs draumar*, *Grímnismál* (prose and poetry) and *Hymiskviða*. In addition, it contains portions of *Skírnismál* (prose and poetry, equivalent upto stanza 27), *Vafþrúðnismál* (from the equivalent of s. 20:2 onwards) and *Hárbarðsljóð* (from the equivalent of s. 19:7 onwards). It also contains the beginning of the heading prose of *Völundarkviða* (equivalent to ll. 1-5).

AM 748 I a 4to has extant extant leaves, but originally consisted of one gathering of seven leaves, one now lost after leaf 2; how large the manuscript once was is not known.³⁰⁰ There are obviously several lacuna in this manuscript: the first text, *Hárbarðsljóð*, starts in the middle; the end of *Skírnismál* and the beginning of *Vafþrúðnismál* are absent and the beginning of the prose of *Völundarkviða* is present but finishes off abruptly: presumably at least this poem once followed. The order of the poems is not the same as the much lauded order of the poems in the R manuscript nor can a deliberate order of poems in A be readily discerned; the only real similarity is that *Vafþrúðnismál* and *Grímnismál* come together in both manuscripts, and Wessén also notes that “a first division of the lays into mythological and heroical was also

²⁹⁷ *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda*, intro, Elias Wessén, p. 12.

²⁹⁸ Thus is the manuscript dated by *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda*, intro, Elias Wessén, p. 14; K. Kälund dated the manuscript to c. 1300 in *KAH*, vol. 1, p. 174; Heusler commits himself to “the early fourteenth century,” *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro, Andreas Heusler, p. 23.

²⁹⁹ *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda*, intro, Elias Wessén, p. 16.

³⁰⁰ *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda*, intro, Elias Wessén, pp. 12, 16.

found in this manuscript,” since A ends with the beginning of the prose of *Völundarkviða*, which he considers to be the first heroic poem of manuscript R.³⁰¹

There are numerous paper manuscripts of the *Poetic Edda*, but only one has any independent value as regards the textual criticism of the text; this is a paper manuscript that contains the last nine stanzas of *Sigdrífumál*, that were copied from the Codex Regius manuscript shortly before 1643 and before the lacuna developed.³⁰²

³⁰¹ *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda*, intro, Elias Wessén, pp. 17-18.

³⁰² *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Andreas Heusler, pp. 13, 15.

The Use of Prose in the Poetic Edda

The first, mythological section of the *Poetic Edda* uses prose to mark the names of the speakers, as a narrative introduction and conclusion to the stanzas, as narrative in between the stanzas, and to provide descriptive titles of the action. To say that they ‘frame’ the poem is not quite accurate, because both the prose and verse relations of the events seem to be accorded equal value when the narrative is viewed as whole.³⁰³

The mythological poems of the *Poetic Edda* use prose rather more independently of each other than the heroic poems of the same collection. In the heroic section, prose is used to unify the poems that we separate into a series, as well as having the same uses as those we find in the mythological section.

Prose occurs in the *Poetic Edda* in the following roles:

1. To mark the name of the speaker of the stanza. (*Vafþrúðnismál*, *För Skírnis*, *Hárbarðsljóð*, *Lokasenna*, *Þrymskviða*, *Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar*, *Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Reginismál*, *Fáfnismál*, *Helreið Brynhildar*, *Atlamál*)
2. To mark the stanza is dialogue, but the speaker is unnamed (*Grímnismál*, *Hárbarðsljóð*, *Sigrdrífumál*)
3. As a narrative introduction to the stanzas. (*Grímnismál*, *För Skírnis*, *Hárbarðsljóð*, *Lokasenna*, *Völundarkviða*, *Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar*, *Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Grípisspá*, *Reginismál*, *Sigrdrífumál*, *Guðrúnarkviða in fyrsta*, *Helreið Brynhildar*, *Guðrúnarkviða in forna*, *Guðrúnarkviða in þriðja*, *Oddrúnargrátr*, *Atlakviða*, *Guðrúnarhvöt*)
4. As a narrative conclusion to the stanzas. (*Grímnismál*, *Lokasenna*, *Þrymskviða*, *Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Reginismál*, *Fáfnismál*, *Guðrúnarkviða in fyrsta*)
5. As prose narrative in between the stanzas (*För Skírnis*, *Lokasenna*, *Völundarkviða*, *Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar*, *Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Reginismál*, *Fáfnismál*, *Sigrdrífumál*)

³⁰³ Cf. *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Andreas Heusler, p. 19; Lee M. Hollander, “For Whom Were the Eddic Poems Composed?,” *Journal of English and Germanic Philology* (1963): 136-142; Heinz Klingenberg, “Types of Eddic Mythological Poetry,” *Edda: A Collection of Essays*, ed. Robert J. Glendinning and Haraldur Bessason (Winnipeg: University of Manitoba Press, 1983) pp. 134-164.

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6. To provide a “title” descriptive of the action (*Hýmiskviða, Lokasenna x 2, Völundarkviða x 2, Helgi Hundingsbana in fyrri, Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar, Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur, Fáfnismál, Helreið Brynhildar, Oddrúnargrátr, Atlamál, Atlakviða, Guðrúnarhvöt*)
 7. As prose only/to link two poems. (*Frá dauða Sinfjötla, prose before Fáfnismál, prose linking to Sigrdrífumál, Frá dauða Sigurðar, prose before Guðrúnarkviða in fyrsta, Sigurðarkviða in skamma, Helreið Brynhildar, Dráp Niflunga, prose before Guðrúnarkviða in forna, Guðrúnarkviða in thriðja, prose before Atlamál, Guðrúnarhvöt*)
 8. To name the poem at the end. (*Hamðismál*).

The prose of the Poetic Edda works in fundamentally different ways in the mythological and heroic sections of the *Poetic Edda*. This division between the mythological and heroic sections has long been cited as a division not only recognised by the manuscript compiler but one that it based on the content of the poems. I would like to revise this concept slightly, and argue that, while the mythological poems use prose as a relatively simply framing device, the much heavier and diverse use of prose in the section recording the heroic poems reflects a different material and situational dimension of the heroic as compared to the mythological eddic genre. To begin with, I will discuss the mythological eddic poems and their simple use of prose, before I return to the more complex matter of the heroic poems. I look here at the division between narrative matters in the prose and dialogue or dramatic material as encouraged by Lönnroth in “The Old Norse Analogue.”

The following analysis of the prose of the mythological and heroic poems concentrates on what function the prose has in relation to the poem and whether it was possible for the poem (and its wider context in the tradition) to be understood without the prose.

The Prose of the Mythological Poems

The mythological eddic poems have the following uses of prose:

1. To mark the name of the speaker of the stanza. (*Vafþrúðnismál, Skírnismál, Hárbarðsljóð, Lokasenna, Þrymskviða*)
2. To mark the stanza is dialogue, but the speaker is unnamed (*Grímnismál, Hárbarðsljóð*)

3. As a narrative introduction to the stanzas. (*Grímnismál*, *Skírnismál*, *Hárbarðsljóð*, *Lokasenna*, *Völundarkviða*)
4. As a narrative conclusion to the stanzas. (*Grímnismál*, *Lokasenna*, *Þrymskviða*)
5. As prose narrative in between the stanzas (*Skírnismál*, *Lokasenna*, *Völundarkviða*)
6. To provide a “title” descriptive of the action (*Hýmiskviða*, *Lokasenna x 2*, *Völundarkviða x 2*)

The mythological poems do not ever use prose to link two poems or to name the poem at its end. These functions of prose are only seen in connection with the heroic poems. It is clear from the above list that the principle uses of prose in the mythological poems is as a speaker marking, to introduce and conclude the story told by the stanzas, to provide prose narrative connections between the stanzas, and to provide a title descriptive of the action (not connected with the titles of the poems as we know them). The following will consider these functions of the prose in comparison with similar information to be found in the stanzas themselves, and to see whether the prose inserts are really necessary. It treats the poems in the order that they are found in the R manuscript of the *Poetic Edda*, with reference to A as possible.

Vafþrúðnismál

Vafþrúðnismál is fully extant in R and partially preserved in A (from Bugge 20.2 æði dvgir).³⁰⁴ The poem has a title written in red ink: “vaþrúðnif mal”.³⁰⁵ *Vafþrúðnismál* does not have extensive prose inserts in amongst the stanzas, rather it has prose speaker markings. The following is an attempt to deduce whether these speaker markings are in fact necessary when the stanzas are considered on their own, and whether the fifth stanza, which is the poem’s lone narrative stanza, serves a crucial role in the poem.

³⁰⁴ Stanza numbers and citations from Bugge, pp. 65-74.

³⁰⁵ *Håndskriftet Nr. 2365 4to gl. kgl. Samling på det store kgl. bibliotek i København (Codex Regius af den ældre Edda) i fototypisk og diplomatisk gengivelse*, ed. Ludv[ig] F. A. Wimmer and Finnur Jónsson, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur (Copenhagen: S. L. Møllers Bogtrykkeri, 1891) 14.9.

The stanza speaker markings are lacking for the first 17 or so stanzas in R. Bugge records that there are speaker markings in the margin of R from stanza 21 inclusive, and notes that of the formula “o q” (Óðinn qvaþ) or “v q” (Vafþrúðnismál qvaþ) either one or both of the letters is missing, having been cut away with the binding of the manuscript.³⁰⁶ We can infer a similar fate for the markings that likely accompanied the stanzas at the opening of the poem. Wimmer and Finnur Jónsson note marginal markings for stanzas earlier than Bugge, determining that stanzas 18-20 also have marginal markings.³⁰⁷ A contains marginal speaker markings for the part of the poem that it contains and these are better preserved, both characters of the abbreviation being present apart from those marking stanzas 42 and 43 where just “q” is extant.³⁰⁸ A does not have a marking for the final stanza spoken by Vafþrúðnir when he realises that he is doomed (Bugge st. 55),³⁰⁹ possibly because the scribe wanted a smooth transition into the prose heading of *Grímnismál*, which occurs directly underneath on the same page. This smooth transition is not realised in R, where there is a “v q” next to the large initial “H” that begins the prose at the head of *Grímnismál*. Here the scribe has chosen to mark the final stanza of the poem in two places, at the head of the stanza and at the beginning of the final long line (Bugge st. 55.7-9), “Nv ec við Óðin deildac / mina orþspeci, / þv ert ę visastr vera.” It seems the scribe here is treating the third long line (the neighbouring stanzas have only two long lines) like a final conclusion to the poem similar to the manner in which prose lines are found for example in *Þrymskviða*: “Sva com Opins sonr endr at hamri” (Bugge p. 128). Bertha Philpotts suggests that here the prose annotator ought to have added a prose conclusion similar to that found at the end of *Grímnismál*,³¹⁰ but this is unnecessary: the stanzas themselves have indicated what will happen should

³⁰⁶ Bugge pp. 67-68.

³⁰⁷ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 15, ll. 4-8.

³⁰⁸ *Håndskriftet Nr. 748, 4to, bl. 1-6, i den Arna-magnæanske samling (Brudstykke af den ældre Edda) i fototypisk og diplomatisk gengivelse*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur (Copenhagen: S. L. Møllers Bogtrykkeri, 1896) p. 6, ll. 1-2.

³⁰⁹ Bugge st. 55; Nr. 748, 4to, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 6, ll. 19-22.

³¹⁰ Bertha S. Philpotts, *The Elder Edda and Ancient Scandinavian Drama* (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1920) p. 105.

Vafþrúðnir loose his wager, and the audience can imagine this will be carried out. The extra speaker marking for stanza 55 in R thus acknowledges that the stanza is expanded and suggests the function of the extra line, which echoes the prose finales of other eddic poems.

Vafþrúðnismál is a dialogue poem with four speakers (three characters and a narrator). The first four stanzas are an exchange between Óðinn and Frigg. The characters are initially identified by being named in the stanzas. Stanza one names two characters (although not its speaker) in addition to their qualities:

‘Ráð þú mér nú, Frigg, allz mic fara tíðir
at vitia Vafþrúðnis;
forvitni micla qveð ec mér á fornom stöfom
við þann inn alsvinna iqtun.’ (Bugge, p. 65, st. 1)

This stanza indicates the identities of the other speakers we can expect to encounter, and that Frigg will speak stanza two, as well as indicating to the audience the motivation behind a trip to see *Vafþrúðnir* and the likely content of the poem, a contest in ancient lore. We also learn that Frigg is a source of (presumably good) advice and that *Vafþrúðnir* is a giant and is “all-wise.” Stanza two, that stanza one tells us is spoken by Frigg, names the speaker of stanza one as *Heriaföðr* (Óðinn) in reply to him and tells of their location, *i gorrðum goða* [‘in the courts of the gods’].

The third stanza, the reply to Frigg that must be spoken by “Host-father” begins with three lines that foreshadow the questioning in a wisdom contest:

‘Fiöld ec fór, fiöld ec freistaða,
fiöld ec reynda regin’ (Bugge, p. 65, st. 3, ll.1-3)

Indeed, this later used as a refrain in the contest (stt. 46, 48, 50, 52, 54). The use of the refrain in stanza three serves to identify Óðinn as the speaker of these later stanzas. The speaker of stanza three gives his second motivation for the journey that Frigg implies will happen in the second stanza, *‘hitt vile ec vita, / hvé Vafþrúðnis / salakynni sé* [‘one thing I’d know: what company is kept with *Vafþrúðnir*’s court’ (Orchard)], and also indicates where the contest of ancient lore will take place (in *Vafþrúðnir*’s court), which also juxtaposes the court of the gods (where, Frigg implies, Óðinn is safe) with the danger of *Vafþrúðnir*’s court (since she says no giant can match *Vafþrúðnir*’s

might). Stanza four begins with a charm-like instruction: “Heill þú farir,/ heill þú aþtr komir, heill þú á sinnom sér!” and concludes by affirming the identity of the first speaker by addressing him directly as *Aldafǫðr* (Óðinn), and he will indeed “bandy words with that giant.” The first four stanzas have thus given the audience a lot of information about what will happen in the poem: the speakers, the initial and subsequent locations, where the second speaker will be going, and what is going to happen next. The fifth stanza is narrative:

Fór þá Óðinn, at freista orðspeki
þess ins alsvinna iǫtuns;
at hǫllo hann kom, oc átti Íms faðir;
inn gecc Yggr þegar.

This stanza does not tell us anything that the other dialogue stanzas do not other than explicitly naming Óðinn as the figure who must have spoken the first and third stanzas by naming him in the first line as the actor connected with the narrated action in the third and fourth lines (a cognomen of Óðinn is also used to being line four). Stanza six begins with “Heill þú nú, Vafþrúðnir! / nú em ec í hǫll kominn, / á þic síalfan síá,” indicating Óðinn’s location has now changed and that he is inside Vafþrúðnir’s hall in the giant’s presence, something confirmed by Vafþrúðnir enquiring who he is in stanza six. In stanza six, Óðinn also announces he will test the giant’s wisdom and so repeats what is narrated in stanza five. The third and fourth lines of stanza five are descriptive of his movements, and replace stage directions, but these are unnecessary since the dialogue stanzas also make it clear what motion has happened.

Stanza five is one that could easily be rendered in prose, and there are no other narrative stanzas in the poem. After five stanzas (stt. 6-10) to set up the wisdom contest, it begins in a typical question and answer format. Óðinn names himself Gagnráðr in stanza eight (thereby disguising his real identity from the giant), and Vafþrúðnir first asks him questions in an exchange lasting eight stanzas, and addresses Gagnráðr by name at the head of each question. Stanza nineteen, which we can tell is spoken by Vafþrúðnir since he addresses the *gestr* and identifies himself as a giant, marks a reverse in who asks and answers the questions. Óðinn’s last answer above in

stanza eighteen is the first stanza to receive a prose marker of who speaks the stanza: *Óðinn qvað* ['Óðinn said']. The transitional nineteenth stanza is marked as *Vafþrúðnir qvað* ['Vafþrúðnir said'], even though, as demonstrated above, it is clear who the speaker of the stanza is. Each stanza is then alternately marked with Odin and Vafþrúðnir as speakers.

As Vafþrúðnir addressed Gagnráðr as the one who would answer his questions, so Óðinn in his much longer question sequence addresses Vafþrúðnir with the refrain in the third line *oc þú, Vafþrúðnir, vitir*, again making it obvious who will be answering his questions. In *Vafþrúðnismál*, both the narrative stanza by the narrator and the prose markers of speakers are unnecessary. Only stanza nineteen gives directional information of movement that is not indicated by other stanzas. The questions asked by Vafþrúðnir begin with the refrain "Segðu þat. Gagnráðr, / allz þú á gólfi vill / þíns um freista frama," making it obvious that Óðinn is to be imagined as standing on the hall floor addressing the giant rather than as seated. In the nineteenth stanza, the giant invites Óðinn: "far þú á becc iqtuns, / oc mælomc í sessi saman!" This is a reiteration of an invitation to Óðinn to take a seat in stanza 9, when he (judging by the refrain to Vafþrúðnir's questions) evidently did not.³¹¹ There is no objection by Óðinn to seating himself and no further comment by Vafþrúðnir that Gagnráðr is standing, so we should understand this stanza as indicating that Óðinn moves to sit down.

Indeed, the last two stanzas of the poem are given added force if the two disputants are thought of as sitting next to each other. In the penultimate stanza (54), Óðinn asks Vafþrúðnir: "hvat mælti Óðinn, / áðr á bál stigi, / siálfr í eyra syni?". This reflects the dramatic situation of the speakers, speaking into each others ears together on the seat. As Óðinn asks what he said into the ear of a dead man, their situation too is connected with death, and Óðinn is once more speaking into the ear of a dead man, since they have wagered their heads (st. 19). This question makes Vafþrúðnir realise to whom he has been talking (ll. 1-2 and 5-6 of the stanza), and the fact that he is now

³¹¹ Stanza 10, spoken by Óðinn may be a declination of the first invitation to seat himself, but he does not say no explicitly, only making a gnomic statement about poor people not talking to much when visiting the rich.

doomed, since Óðinn's final question is one he cannot answer (ll. 1-2). The end of the poem implies that Vafþrúðnir will now be killed, although this is not shown directly.

The speaker markers in *Vafþrúðnismál* are unnecessary. At no point would a listener to the poem be unaware of who is talking. The speakers in the poem also reiterate whom they are addressing to make it completely clear. The fifth, narrative stanza could also be done without and one would still be able to deduce what was happening from the other dialogue stanzas. It could be noted though that the narrative stanza is the only one that directly names Óðinn (the others, and the end of stanza five, use cognomens) and that gives genealogical information about Vafþrúðnir, identifying him as the father of Ímr. Since the prose speaker markers play no narrative or identifying function for a listener, they are most likely present for the convenience of a reader in this poem, since they are marginal – for example if the manuscript of the poem were to be used as a play script. Written speaker indications may have helped a reader locate which characters spoke which stanzas quickly.

Grímnismál

This poem is preserved whole both in the Codex Regius (GKS 2365 4to) and in AM 748 I 4to.³¹² *Grímnismál* is titled twice in the manuscript, once at the head of the prose “introduction,” and once at the verse. The poem is preceded by an introductory prose section.³¹³ The title above the prose is almost unreadable in R and Bugge and the edition by Wimmer and Finnur Jónsson hit upon two different readings. Bugge's expanded title reads “Synir Hrauvd̄vngs konungs” (p. 75), the unexpanded version he has recorded as “ss. hraudv̄gs k's” (p. 75) written in red ink. Wimmer and Finnur Jónsson read this as “*ǫra sonom. hrad̄vngf konvngf.*”³¹⁴ Both Bugge and Wimmer-

³¹² Stanza numbers and citations from Bugge, pp. 75-89.

³¹³ This introductory prose has been described by Jeffrey A. Mazo as “a short prose narrative that is younger than the poem, but represents a reliable tradition.” He does not clarify whether he considers the narrative as part of the oral life of the poem (which he indicates exists by mentioning “oral performances” of *Grímnismál*). See Jeffrey A. Mazo, “Grímnismál,” *Medieval Scandinavia: An Encyclopedia*, ed. Phillip Pulsiano, Garland Encyclopedias of the Middle Ages 1, Garland Reference Library of the Humanities 934 (New York: Garland Publishing, 1993) p. 243.

³¹⁴ *Nr. 2365 4^{to}*, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 16, ll. 31.

Finnur Jónsson agree on “fra hraðvngi konvngi” in A, also written in red ink (Bugge, p. 75).³¹⁵ In A, the title emphasises King Hrauðungr, although he is a very peripheral character; it is his sons (Geirrøðr and Agnar), the focus of the title in R, who are the main human characters in the story told by the prose.³¹⁶ The first verse, that is introduced by *Hann qvaþ* in the prose, has in RA the title “grimnis mal” written by it, in black ink (Bugge, p. 75), indicating that the speaker of the following will be Grímnir, who has been introduced in the prose (there are no marginal speaker markings for this poem in either R or A), and the “H” at the beginning of the first stanza in both manuscripts is a large initial.

Some of the information towards the end of the introductory prose connects with what is told in the stanzas at the beginning of the poem. In the second half of the first stanza we hear that Grímnir’s cloak is singeing (Bugge, p. 76), a detail also captured in the prose. The first five lines of the second stanza give the information that Agnar, son of Geirrøðr, is the only one to have offered Grímnir food for the eight nights that he has been sat between the fires. In stanza three, however, it refers to the one draught that Agnarr has given to him (line 4). Both these instances conflict with the prose, which mentions only that Agnarr had given him drink and that it was a full horn.

Also perhaps referring to the story related in the introductory prose are stanzas 51 and the first half of 52. These are likely connected with Óðinn and Geirrøðr’s past

³¹⁵ Nr. 748, 4to, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 6, ll. 22-23.

³¹⁶ The story in the prose of both R and A can be summarised thus: Agnarr (age 10) and Geirrøðr (age 8) are the sons of King Hrauðungr. They go fishing, are shipwrecked and adopted by cottagers for the winter; the woman adopts Agnarr and the man Geirrøðr. In the spring, they return to their home in a boat. Before they leave the cottagers, the old man has a private word with Geirrøðr, and when they land at their home, he is at the fore of the ship, jumps out and shoves the boat out with Agnarr in it, and says “Go now, where the *smyl* [‘evil ones’] can have you!” Geirrøðr becomes king (their father has died), and becomes mighty. Looking over their scene are Óðinn and Frigg, from Hliðskjálf. Óðinn asks Frigg whether she can Agnarr, her protégé, raising children with a *gygr* [‘hag’] in a cave, while his fosterson, Geirrøðr, is a mighty king. Frigg slanders Geirrøðr, saying he is mean with food and abuses guests if he deems them too numerous. Óðinn says this is a lie, and they place a wager on it. Frigg sends her maiden, Fulla, to Geirrøðr to warn him of a wizard who had arrived in his land, lest he be bewitched by him, and that he could be recognized by the sign that no dog would jump up at him. Such a man is seized. Clad in a blue cloak, he names himself Grímnir, although says nothing else about himself. King Geirrøðr has him tortured to make him speak, and sits him between two fires for eight nights. Geirrøðr’s ten year old son, named Agnarr after his brother, gives Grímnir a full horn to drink, and says his father does wrong to have an innocent man tortured. Grímnir drinks from it, and the fire has come so close that the cloak has burnt off him. See Bugge, pp. 75-76.

relationship in general, in which Óðinn has assisted and defended Geirrøðr. Stanza 51 line 4 however refers to the *gengi* [‘aid’ or ‘support’] that Óðinn has given Geirrøðr, which may refer to the assistance he received as a child from Óðinn disguised as a cottager, and lines 1-3 of stanza 52 continues by saying Geirrøðr has not remembered much of what he (Óðinn) has said and that friends are proving deceitful, also probably referring back to their previous relationship. From these points, it seems possible that the prose found at the head of *Grímnismál* should be thought of as separate to the poem, i.e. not dependant on it for its content. This is also indicated in the manuscript by two sets of headings. The prose presents an expansion of the traditions found in the poem, and could have been transmitted in oral tradition either as a story told separately from the stanzas or as an accompaniment to provide the background story for the story in the stanzas. That this prose has been adapted to its current context in the manuscript is shown by the fact that the end of the prose has been more carefully linked with the content of the stanzas directly following than the rest of the prose has been connected to what happens in the poem, and it seems that stanzas 51 and 52 allude to this background story.

There is a small amount of prose narrative that concludes the poem in both RA.³¹⁷ This ending prose also relates to both the beginning and the end of the poem. In stanza 2, Óðinn tells that Agnarr, as he knows he will kill Geirrøðr for his poor hospitality, will rule alone, and then addresses Agnarr directly in the third stanza that he will have luck, since he, Veratýr [‘Man-god,’ ie. Óðinn] has bidden it, and that this is his reward for the single draught he received from him, and in the prose, it is duly stated that “Agnarr var þar konvngur lengi síðan” (Bugge, p. 88). Andy Orchard notes that Angarr, son of Geirrøðr, is said to be ten years old in the introductory prose, the same age that Geirrøðr’s brother Agnarr was when Geirrøðr cast him out to sea in a boat.³¹⁸ The two Agnarr’s are thus balanced, one with good luck to balance the other’s

³¹⁷ This can be summarised as: King Geirrøðr is sitting with a half-drawn sword on his lap, but when he realises that it is Óðinn who is sitting between the fires, he wants to get him away from them. He stands up, and sword slips from his hand, turns hilt-down and goes through and kills Geirrøðr as he stumbles. Óðinn then disappears, and Agnarr becomes king there for a long time afterwards.

³¹⁸ *The Eldar Edda: A Book of Viking Lore*, trans. Andy Orchard, Penguin Classics (London: Penguin, 2011) 282.

poor luck, and both of these were destined by Óðinn, who has changed his allegiance from Geirrøðr to Agnarr the second (see line 3 of stanza 52: *of þic vela vínir*). In relation to the prose, this is because of Geirrøðr's poor behaviour towards guests.

At the end of the poem, Grímnir makes it quite clear that Geirrøðr is doomed. As stanza 51 and the first half of stanza 52 relate to the background provided by the introductory prose, so the second half of stanza 52 and stanza 53 relate to the concluding prose. In the second half of 52, Óðinn says “męki liggia / ec se mins vinar / allan i dreyra drifinn” [‘I see my friend’s sword lying showered with blood’], captured in the prose as Geirrøðr’s own sword going through him, although the image of his sword lying covered in his own blood is not given directly in the prose. Stanza 53 expresses Óðinn’s desire for a corpse killed by a sword (*Eggmoþan val / nu mun Yggr hafa*), and since he is addressing Geirrøðr, it is clear it is he who will be killed, and Óðinn taunts in the stanza *þitt veit ec líf vm líþit* (line 3). In stanza 53, Óðinn mentions himself by name directly, revealing who is (previously he has used a long list of cognomens to refer to himself, and st. 49.1 reveals he has called himself Grímnir at Geirrøðr’s), and challenges Geirrøðr to come closer to him if he can. This is portrayed in the prose not as a taunt to Geirrøðr to come nearer, but rather as Geirrøðr wanting to get him away from the flames, although both of these actions lead to Geirrøðr being killed being killed by his own sword, implied by the poetry and stated directly in the prose.

The prose of *Grímnismál* in both RA seems an expansion of some details found in the stanzas, coupled with more background information to introduce the characters and provide the background for Óðinn’s arrival at Geirrøðr’s hall and his change of allegiance from Geirrøðr to his son, Agnarr. This is particularly marked because Geirrøðr’s son has the same name as his brother whom he got rid off in the introductory prose, although this is never explained in the stanzas. A speaker marking is given at the end of the introductory prose in RA, “hann qvaþ,” and although it does not mention his name, it is directly after the prose that says Grímnir is being burnt by fire. It is clear that the poem is a monologue because it has a number of references in

the first person, and no further speaker markings are needed since this is a monologue.

Although some extra details are added by the prose, as noted above, they are mainly peripheral and set the poem in a grander frame, for example Óðinn and Frigg looking down over the world. The essential part of the prose narrative is indicated in the stanzas: Grímnir has been between fires for eight nights and his cloak is burning, it is Agnarr who will prosper in life as a reward, he is Geirrøðr's son, Geirrøðr is doomed because he has given Grímnir neither food nor drink, Geirrøðr will be killed by a sword, and the sword will be his own, the speaker Grímnir is Óðinn, and he causes Geirrøðr to come closer to him. In part the prose is placed as an elaboration on the verses, and the beginning and ending stanzas that relate to the prose as analysed above are an adequate frame to Grímnir's outpouring of wisdom in the poem in itself. In addition, the introductory prose in particular records an expansion of the tradition that in the manuscripts may be used as background for the stanzas but which, particularly in combination with the concluding prose, tell the story in its own right.

Skírnismál

Skírnismál has a small section of introductory prose, prose speaker markings and two prose narrative inserts in amongst the stanzas.³¹⁹ *Skírnismál* is preserved complete in R and is partially in A (see source section). Both RA title the poem; R has *for scirnis* and A has *skirnis mal*, both in red ink above the prose introduction. In R, this is at the end of the last line of *Grímnismál* (11r8). In R, the prose of *Skírnismál* begins on l. 9, with the *F* of Freyr as a large green initial five lines high. The initial of each stanza is pen-flourished. The initial *S* of *Scirrir* at the beginning of the first prose insert (on Bugge, p. 92) is also pen-flourished at 11r30, and the *Þ* at the beginning of the second at 12r24 is a capital (on Bugge, p. 96). The prose speaker markings are within the text of the poem and are not marginal to begin with, thus we find *Þa męlti Scaði* and the first *Scirrir qvað* in the text on 11r, but after this, from the *Scirrir qvað* above stanza

³¹⁹ Stanza numbers and citations from Bugge, pp. 90-96.

three, the speaker markings are marginal (except the introduction of st. 10, see below), although the abbreviation *q* for *quað* has usually been cut away on the recto pages leaving on the speakers' initials. On the verso, the speakers' initials have been cut away, usually leaving only the *q*; sometimes, neither remain (for example on 12r there do not appear to be any, although we can probably assume they once were there).³²⁰

As for the content of the introductory prose of *Skírnismál*, it is the prose that tells us that Skaði speaks stanza one. Previous scholars have commented on this poem's prose passages that the head note "assists in the telling the story clearly" and that the prose passages found amongst the stanzas hold the stanzas "together in a comprehensible narrative."³²¹ Kellogg notes that if the prose pieces were not there, we would be able to get the gist of the story from *Snorra Edda*, since the story is told in *Gylfaginning* 37.³²² The speaker of stanza one addresses Skírnir (l. 1), making it clear it is Skírnir who will be speaking the second stanza. In the third stanza, we can assume the speaker is the same, and he addresses Freyr directly in the first line. Since Skírnir was instructed in stanza 1.1 *ristv*, we can also assume the location has changed by the time he is addressing "ocarn...mavg" (st. 1.3). The manner in which the content of stanzas four to nine alternates makes it obvious whether it is Skírnir or Freyr speaking. The speaker marking of stanza ten is rather more unusual: *Scírnir mælti við hestinn*. Unless this was present, we would have little idea that the one addressed in stanza 10 was a horse. Since Skírnir talks of *ocr*, and has just been talking to Freyr, we would assume that he is addressing Freyr, although in stanza nine just before, Freyr does promise Skírnir a horse. Later in the poem, however, when Skírnir is talking to the giant's daughter about Freyr, he does so in such a way to make it clear that Freyr cannot be present, and stanza fifteen, spoken by a maid, says that *maþr er her vti / stigin af mars baci, / ió letr til iardar taca*, making it clear that Skírnir arrived on horseback, and that his travelling companion addressed in stanza ten must have in fact

³²⁰ R lacks *Gq* on stanzas 17, 20, 24, 37 and 39. It is not clear why Gerðr should be neglected in this way, unless the speaker marking has been cut off. A has the *Gq* speaker marking for st. 17, 20 and 24.

³²¹ Kellogg, "Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda," p. 92.

³²² Kellogg, "Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda," p. 92.

been the horse. It is thus deducible to whom Skírnir is talking in stanza ten, but only later in the poem.

The introductory prose rationalises how Freyr in stanza six was able to see in to *jötunheimar* and see the beautiful giant girl; he has, according to the prose, been sitting in *Hliðscialf*, the gods' vantage point over all the worlds. That Freyr is love sick is related by the stanzas (e.g. stt.1-2) as well as the prose, as is the identity of girl as Gýmir's daughter. The prose also informs us that Skírnir is Freyr's *scósveinn*; this we would not know exactly, although Skírnir reassures Freyr in the stanzas by reminding him that *vngir saman / varoom I árdaga, / vel meðtim tvær trýasc* (st. 5.3-6). Thus only *Hliðscialf* is mentioned by the prose and is not something we could necessarily identify in the stanzas.

The second prose insert is a narrative piece that identifies a change of scene has occurred in the poem. Again, this is nothing that could not be inferred from the stanzas, and what sounds like specific detail in the prose could likely have been lifted straight from the stanzas. The prose begins by saying that Skírnir arrives in *jötunheimar* to Gýmir's courts. That he is about to journey to a giant is made clear in stanza ten in the last line directly before the prose, and that the object of Freyr's affection is in Gýmir's *garðr* is stated by Freyr in stanza six. The prose then says there are ferocious dogs guarding Gerðr's hall (the giantess whom Freyr is in love with), and that Skírnir rides up to a herdsman sitting on a burial mound and greets him. The ferocious dogs we hear of at the end of the eleventh stanza, and at the beginning of the same stanza, Skírnir identifies directly to whom he is talking: *Segðv þat, hirþir! / er þv a hagi sitr*. The information in the prose is thus unnecessary, and that Skírnir has ridden there is also obvious by the fact that in stanza nine Freyr has promised Skírnir a horse to get him there. The name of the girl Freyr has fallen in love with is revealed in the prose as Gerðr. We have not been told this before, only that she is Gýmir's daughter, but it is said in the poem a little further along, in stanza nineteen, when Skírnir addresses her directly.

In conclusion, we find nothing in the prose that an attentive audience could not have worked out from the poem itself, although the prose does give us information that helps us make immediate identifications that otherwise we might not make until later (for example, the horse). It is unclear, however, why a writer might think these identifications necessary, unless perhaps the poem was not well known to his audience. It is possible that the prose is derived from the poem, rather than representing extra information.

Hábarðsljóð

*Hábarðsljóð*³²³ has the following prose features: to mark the name of the speaker of the stanza; to mark the stanza as dialogue, but the speaker is unnamed, as a narrative introduction to the stanzas, and as one line statements, a mixture recently described as “combining rather choppy bits of interpolated prose (in the poem itself) and verse of an uneven metre.”³²⁴ A mixture of eddic metres is uncommon in neither the poems of the *Poetic Edda* nor in the *fornaldarsögur*; this probably reflects the circumstances of the verses’ preservation. In the oral prehistory of the material that now makes up the poems, it is possible that various versions of the poems in different (eddic) metres circulated and these versions have coalesced to form the extant version; otherwise, it could have been the case that mixed metres was of no concern to the audience during the oral life of the eddic poems and was a normal mode. It is also not clear here what is meant by the prose as an interpolation, and whether Orchard considers the prose to be an interruption added at the written stage (perhaps during transmission) to a poem that was free of such prose in the oral stage, or whether he surmises that the prose was interpolated when the poem was preserved orally. One aspect of the poem that is unusual are the prose replies from a puzzled Þórr, outwitted by his opponent.³²⁵

³²³ Stanza numbers and citations from Bugge, pp. 97-104.

³²⁴ *The Elder Edda*, trans. Orchard, p. 287.

³²⁵ See Carol J. Clover, “*Hábarðsljóð* as Generic Farce,” *Scandinavian Studies* 51 (1979): 124-145, and in reply, Marcel Bax and Tineke Padmos, “Two Types of Verbal Dueling in Old Icelandic: The Interactional Structure of the *senna* and the *mannjafnaðr* in *Hábarðsljóð*,” *Scandinavian Studies* 55 (1983): 149-174.

The written version of the poem is extant in full in R and is partially preserved in A, from st. 19.7. In R, there is a title in red ink, “harbarz lioð,” followed by the prose introduction:

Þorr for or aþstrvegi oc kom at svndi çino; aþrom megom svndzins var feriokarlinn með scipit.

That Þórr has been performing deeds in the east is mentioned in several of the stanzas (stt. 23 and 29), although it is by no means evident that this quarrel with Hárbarðr happens on the return leg of one of these particular excursions; it might be intimated that Þórr has been away for a long time however, by some of the put downs Hárbarðr hurls at him: that his mother is dead (st. 3); he is of ragged appearance (st. 6); that his wife has taken a lover (st. 48); all these suggest Þórr’s prolonged absence, and given the mentions of the east in the poem, it is an obvious candidate for Þórr’s previous whereabouts. That a ferryman stands on the other side of the strait to Þórr with a boat is evident in many of the stanzas of the poem (for example stt. 1, 3, 7). If the prose is original to the oral stage of the poem, then the audience may have known from which trip Þórr is returning and thus the prose would have functioned to situate the exchange more firmly in mythic chronology. If the prose was added during the writing down of the poem or its transmission, then the writer of the prose achieved nothing else than to set the scene at the beginning of the poem and provide a likely context for Þórr arriving at a river bank on his way home.

The poem has speaker markings in which the speakers are both named and unnamed. The first continues on from the introductory prose, and directly names Þórr, “Þórr call,” which Bugge expands to “callaþi,” but which, as he notes, could also be expanded to “callar.” After two lines of verse, R has “hann svaraþi” to introduce st. 3. Bugge replaces “hann” with “Feriokarlinn” to make it obvious who is speaking, but this emendation seems unnecessary since the one that Þórr addresses must have a boat when Þórr demands in st. 3.1 to be taken over the sound (“ Ferþv mic vm svndit!”); Þórr explicitly mentions a ferryboat in st. 7 and in st. 52.3, the ferryman refers to himself as a “fehirði” in R and as a “fæ hirði” in A, and it seems that Bugge’s interpretation of both of these as “farhirði,” nominative “farhirðir” meaning “ferryman” (p. 103), must be correct. The Þórr speaker marking is more necessary,

since otherwise we could guess that one of the speakers was a ferryman without knowing who was addressing him, since Þórr only makes his identity clear in st. 9. This type of speaker marking is more interesting than the marginal speaker initials because it is conceivable that this type of speaker indication could be directly linked with or be a part of the prose that is at the head of the poem. The heading prose should be seen as a separate phenomenon to the speaker markings, which are likely born out of performance concerns.³²⁶ The heading prose could indeed have been introduced as the poems entered their codified stage, but it is equally possible the heading prose (in some incarnation) functioned to provide context in the oral period as an introduction to the poem that likely had some flexibility.

Speaker markings for the speech stanzas are missing in R for stanzas 3-18, with the exception of st. 11, where “þ. q.” (“Þórr qvaþ”) is written in the margin; it seems likely that the other stanzas had speaker markers that were trimmed off in the binding of the manuscript. Indeed, this is Bugge’s conclusion regarding the remainder of the speaker markers for the rest of the stanzas in the manuscripts, where speaker markings are found but are partially disrupted by the trimming of the pages (p. 99). In R from 19 onwards the speaker initials are given with either þ. q. or h. q. appearing marginally. Those connected with stt. 23, 36, 37, 40, 47 and 57 have suffered from the binding process (Bugge p. 99). For stt. 57, 58, 59, only q remains in the margin, and H. q. is written in the line rather than in the margin for st. 32. In A, the situation is similar, although here all of the speaker markings h. q. or þ. q. stand in the line rather than in the margin, and on two occasions a fuller version of the name is given than the initial: st. 20 has “hárbarðr q.” and st. 37 has “þórr q.” Two speaker initials appear in the margin when the “q” for “qvaþ” appears in the line, for stanza 51 and stanza 55.³²⁷ On the whole the speaker markings even where they are extant in the manuscripts are superfluous as the speakers name their opponents in a formulaic, challenging way, either “Hvat vantv þa meþan, Hárbarðr?” (st. 15.7, see also stt. 19, 23, 29, 39) or “Hvaþ

³²⁶ Gunnell, *The Origins of Drama in Scandinavia*.

³²⁷ Nr. 748, 4to, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 2, ll. 8, 11.

vanntv þa meðan, Þorr?” (st. 18.13, see also stt. 22, 28, 36; st. 36 contains only this question).

Hýmiskviða

Hýmiskviða is extant in both manuscripts of the *Poetic Edda*, and a prose descriptive title is found only in R: “þorð dro miðgarz oðm” [‘Þórr drew up the Miðgarð serpent’].³²⁸ The poem receives its name only in AM 748 4to, in which it is titled “hýmif kviða” in red ink.³²⁹ To a modern reader both titles are somewhat problematic: titling the poem “Hýmiskviða” [‘The Song of Hýmir’] is odd because Hýmir speaks relatively little in the poem – there is not much direct speech at all to be found – and the poem centres on the exploits of Þórr; Hýmir is rather secondary. As for the descriptive prose title found in R about Þórr drawing up the world serpent, it seems that in both of the two versions of the poem we have preserved, there is a gap that begins in stanza 19. Whilst the other exploits of Þórr do not appear in *Snorra Edda*, Þórr fishing up the world serpent does appear, and we can surmise the content of the missing text from this: Þórr uses the ox’s head as fishing bait, Hýmir expresses caution about going into the deeper waters where the world serpent is known to live, but Þórr is unworried.³³⁰ This descriptive prose title in R is the only prose element found in *Hýmiskviða*.³³¹

Lokasenna

Lokasenna has many of the uses of prose common to the mythological poems of the Poetic Edda as a whole.³³² In addition to prose used to mark the speaker of the stanza, it also has narrative introducing and concluding the stanzas, twice has titles descriptive of the action and has prose narrative in between the stanzas on five occasions. It is

³²⁸ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 26, l. 26. Stanza numbers from Bugge, pp. 105-112.

³²⁹ Nr. 748, 4to, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 10, l. 25.

³³⁰ Snorri Sturluson, *Edda: Prologue and Gylfaginning*, ed. Anthony Faulkes (Oxford: Clarendon Press) pp. 43-45.

³³¹ Note that Bugge adds some speaker markings; these are in neither of the manuscripts.

³³² Citations and stanza number from Bugge, pp. 113-123.

only preserved in R, and is titled in that manuscript “loka fena” split across two lines.³³³

The prose speaker markings are similar to those found in the mythological poems discussed above. The first speaker statement is included with the introductory prose: “Loci *qvaddi hann*” (p. 114, l. 10). From the poem itself, the reader or listener would not know that this was Loki until stanza 6.3 (when he refers to himself as Loptr, a byname) were it not for this marking. The first line of st. 1, “Segðv þat, Eldir!,” makes the speaker of the reply in the second stanza obvious, and this exchange continues for the first five stanzas. As Bugge notes (p. 114), both stanzas (stt. 2 and 4) spoken by Eldir were once marked with “e. q.” in the margin, although the q. of this marking next to stanza 2 has been cut away. All stanzas in the poem spoken by Loki were likewise probably all marked l. q., and these markings remain for stanzas 3, 5 and 6. Only l. remains for stanzas 32, 36, 38, 40 and 42, and only the q. remains for stanzas 13, 15, 17, 20, 22 and 24; for the remaining verses no marginal speaker markings survive for those stanzas that seem to be spoken by Loki (in the absence of markings). As for the stanzas spoken by other characters, stanza 8, which is Bugge’s edition (p. 115) is marked with “Bragi qvaþ,” R has “bra” in the margin, with the probable q cut away. Bugge supposes (p. 115) that although they are now cut away, the initial of the speaker’s name always stood in the margin followed by q.; these speaker initials for stanzas 9-31 inclusive are all cut away, although most have q remaining. For stanzas 32, 33, 35-42 inclusive, the opposite is true, with the initial of the speaker in the margin and the q cut away (Bugge p. 118). For stanza 43, the name “Byggvir” stands in the line. The remaining stanzas in the poem lack the speaker’s initial. (Bugge p. 118).

The majority of these speaker markings are superfluous. Once we know the antagonist is Loki, he almost always names in the stanza itself those he addresses or replies to. Possible exceptions are stanza 42, in which Freyr is not named by Loki but

³³³ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 29, ll. 16-17. See A. G. van Hamel, “The Prose-Frame of Lokasenna,” *Neophilologus* 14 (1929): 204–214.

the story in *Skírnismál* involving Freyr is alluded to, and stanza 54 in which the goddess Sif is not named but referred to in connection with Hlórriði (Þórr).

The prose internal to the poem should be seen as separate to that at the beginning and end of the stanzas. The introductory and concluding prose frames contains stories, whereas the five pieces of prose internal to the poem contribute to the narration of the action as it is happening in verse. The first of these describes something not explicitly said in the stanzas:

*Síþan gecc Loci inn i hallina. Enn er þeir sa, er fyr varo, hverr inn var kominn, þagnobo þeir allir.*³³⁴

This prose piece comes between stanzas 5 and 6. That Loki will enter Ægir's hall is fairly clear from the preceding stanzas, in which he asks Eldir what is happening “*her inni*” (p. 114, st.1.4), and in stanza 6 after the prose Loki announces he has arrived to the halls. His question at the beginning of stanza 7.1-2, “*Hvi þegit er sva, / þrvngin goð!*” [“Why so silent, uptight gods?”] is clearly reflected in the prose description of the gods falling silent when they see he has entered the hall; the function of the prose thus seems to be to reinforce the change of location from the outside questioning of Eldir to the location inside after the first five stanzas of the poem.

The second prose piece likewise occurs five stanzas after the first prose passage. Rather than indicate a change of location, it indicates an action that Víðarr performs:

*Þa stoð Viðarr vp oc skenciti Loca; enn aþr hann drycci, qvaddi hann asona*³³⁵

The point of the prose seems to be to highlight not that Víðarr stood up (afterall, he is ordered to by Óðinn in st. 10.1), but rather that he serves Loki a drink, which seems the hospitable thing to do (Loki complains he has arrived thirsty in st. 6), and also seems to be necessary for Loki's toast in stanza 11. The prose statement that “*qvaddi*

³³⁴ Bugge, p. 114. [“Afterwards Loki went in into the hall. But when they saw, who was before them, who had come in, they all fell silent.”]

³³⁵ Bugge, p. 115

hann asona” (p. 115) is perfectly obvious from the address to the gods and goddesses directly afterwards at the beginning of stanza 11.

The third prose fragment also concerns Loki being given a drink (this time specifically of mead as requested in stanza 6):

Þa gecc Sif fram oc byrladi Loca i hrimcaldi miþ oc męlti:
Heill ver þv nv, Loci!
oc tac viþ hrimcalci
fvllom forns miaðar! (p. 121, st. 53.1-3)

The name “Sif” in the prose passage is an editorial emendation; in R the name is lacking. Sif, identified in st. 54 as the wife of Hlórriði, tries to reverse Loki’s tactics of the prose between stanzas 10 and 11, when Loki is given a drink and greets the Æsir; here Sif gives him a drink and hails him, although he does not spare her slander. The fourth prose piece, “*Hann toc viþ horni oc dracc af*” (p. 121), also mirrors the previous situation when Víðarr gives Loki a drink, except then he spoke then drank, and st. 54 drinks then speaks. The fourth and fifth prose pieces thus seem to be describing the actions of the characters, since the cold mead offered to Loki and the direct speech of Sif can be gathered from stanza 53.

Whether or not the two introductory prose pieces as extant in R ought to be considered separate pieces to the poem *Lokasenna*, akin to the prose piece *Frá dauða Sinfjötla* in the Heroic poems, is an open question. That this perhaps ought to be so is indicated in the manuscript by the separate heading of the introductory prose, “*Fra Egi oc godom*” (p. 113) with red ink, followed by the prose, then the title “*loka senna*” in red ink followed by the stanzas (p. 113).³³⁶ On the other hand, it is a possibility that the prose introduction and conclusion could be considered a type of *Begleitprosa* and thus be intimately connected with the transmission of *Lokasenna* as it appears in R. *Lokasenna* has clear echoes of other eddic poems and alludes to many myths; whether this is a result of oral or written intertextuality is hard to say. Furthermore, the quotation of *Lokasenna* in *Gylfaginning* (examined further below) might indicate that

³³⁶ In paper manuscripts, *Ægisdrekkja* and *Lokaglepsa* can be found in place of *Lokasenna* (Bugge p. 113).

Snorri knew a somewhat different version of the poem, since one stanza he cites is a conflation of stt. 4-6 as they appear in R, and this is uncharacteristic of Snorri's method of quotation in the text (see below).

The content of “*Fra Egi oc godom*” appears to be a combination of elements that are clearly part of the written tradition of the manuscript and derived from the poem, and elements that might indicate the story of *Lokasenna* was an oral tradition and that the text is a reflex of accompanying prose. As for the written elements, the phrase “*sem nv er sagt*” (p. 113) is a conscious link between the Compiler of the manuscript and what has been placed before; it refers to the statement: “Egir, er aðro nafni het Gýmir, hann hafði hvít asom al, þa er hann hafði fengit ketil inn micla” (p. 113). The poem before is *Hýmiskviða*, and this statement in the prose seems to refer specifically to the final stanza of *Hýmiskviða* rather than to the narrative as whole:

Þrottaflvgr kom
 a þing goda
 oc hafði hver,
 þannz Hymir atti;
 enn veur hverian
 vel scolo drecca
 alþr at Egis
 eitt harmeitiþ (p. 112, st. 39)

As such, the insertion of this sentence into the prose to make a link to what has gone before is not very far reaching, since the inserter of the sentence, assuming he had the Codex Regius or a very similar codex in arrangement copied up to that point in front of him, could in fact have made the link by reading only a line or two up. The identification of Ægir with the giant Gymir is somewhat questionable, and in this context would imply that Ægir is the Gymir referred to in *Skírnismál*, in which Gymir is the father of Gerðr, giving the prose further reach back into the manuscript.

The list of gods and a summary for some of them of their key myths need not necessarily be derived directly from the poem. Were this to be the case, the prose should be a more direct summary of the characters and action. As it is, the gods and goddesses are listed in a different order to that in which they appear in the poem. In the prose, we find them listed first Ægir, then Óðinn, Frigg, Þórr, Sif, Bragi, Iðunn, Týr, Njörðr, Skaði, Freyr, Freyja, Víðarr, Loki, Byggvir, and Beyla. Then Ægir's two

servents, Fimafengr and Eldir. Three of these listed in the prose do not speak in the poem: Ægir and Víðarr, both though are clearly present, Ægir as the brewer/host, and Víðarr as the one who serves Loki his first drink, and Fimafengr, who is dead at the point where the poem begins. In the poem, the speakers are presented in the following order: Loki, Eldir, Bragi, Óðinn, Iðunn, Gefjon, Frigg, Freyja, Njörðr, Týr, Freyr, Byggvir, Heimdallr, Skaði, Sif, Beyla, then Þórr. Amongst the speakers we find Gefjon and Heimdallr who are not mentioned in the prose. The list of gods and associates present at the feast could thus have been made from memory, and has not been written by referring to the poem in its written form. The final sentence of the main list of gods in the prose, “*Mart var þar asa oc alfa*” (p. 113) is likely a direct reflection stanza 2, line 4 where Eldir mentions the gods and elves at the feat, the “*mart*” in place to emphasise the list aspect of the prose.

The second part of the prose provides the explanation of why Loki should be outside when the rest of the gods are at a feast, and a comparison of its contents shows that it is very unlikely to have been derived from the poem. As such, it must either present the traditional context of the poem that was told in prose, or it was added by the Compiler as an attempt to rationalise Loki’s malice for going in and upsetting the feasting. The servant Fimafengr, who is killed in the prose by Loki, is not mentioned in the poem, and nor is the prose claim that Loki was at the feast, was thrown out and having turned back rejoins the party. Stanza six implies rather the opposite, that he has come “*vm langan veg*” (l. 3) and in stanza seven he demands a drink or to be told to leave – according to the prose, this has already happened. The bright gold in place of firelight and the ale that serves itself seems to have been taken from Romance traditions and strikes a fairytale rather than mythological note, but does add the air of sanctuary of the place expressed in the prose “*þar var gríþastadr micill*” (p. 114) something that Óðinn also seems conscious of in stanza 10, “*siþr oss Loci / qveþi lastastafom / Eðgis hállo í*” (ll.4-6).

The concluding prose is titled “*ǫra loca*.”³³⁷ The details in the concluding prose to the stanzas relate to the stanzas: it tells of Loki’s transformation to a salmon to hide in a waterfall to evade capture from the Æsir, then tells how they caught him and tied him up with the guts of his son, and how his other son turned into a wolf. Skaði then takes a snake and ties it so that venom drips onto Loki’s face; his wife holds a bowl to catch the venom, but when she leaves to empty the bowl, the venom falling on Loki’s face causes him to fit so violently it causes earthquakes. The details in the stanzas that relate to this are spoken by Skaði:

Scaði qvaþ:
 Leṭt er þer, Loci!
 mvnattv lengi sva
 leica laðsom hala;
 þviat þic a hiorvi scolo
 ins hrimcalda magar
 gornom binda goð.»

Loci qvaþ:
 «Veiztv, ef mic a hiorvi scolo
 ens hrimcalda magar
 gornom binda goð:
 fyrstr oc qfstr
 var ec at fiorlagi,
 þars ver a Þiaza þrifom.»

Scaði qvaþ:
 «Veiztv, ef fyrstr oc qfstr
 vartv at fiorlagi,
 þa er ér a Þiaza þrifvð:
 fra minom veom
 oc vangom scolo
 þer ę kald ráþ coma. Bugge pp. 120-121, stt. 49-51.

In the stanzas, Skaði predicts what Loki’s punishment will be, or the gods have already decided that this is how they plan to incapacitate him. Her threat he will be bound “a hiorvi scolo” (st. 49.4) is not realised in the prose, else being bound with guts of his son is mentioned in both. The binding of Loki is also threatened earlier in the poem by Freyr, when in st. 41 he threatens Loki with being tied up at a river-mouth next to another bound wolf (presumably the Fenrisúlfr). That Loki is tied up in at a river-mouth in the prose can be inferred by the fact he is caught in the shape of a salmon; otherwise in the prose he is hiding “i Fráangrs forsi” (p. 122). Skaði’s action in

³³⁷ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 33, ll. 5

the prose of torturing Loki with snake-venom is not explicitly suggested in the stanzas, other than perhaps in stanza 51 when she informs Loki that when it comes to him, “kauld ráþ coma” (l. 6). The stanzas are suggestive of the details, whereas the prose is expansive.

*Þrymskviða*³³⁸

Only found in R where it is titled “þrymf qvída,”³³⁹ *Þrymskviða* lacks any substantial prose narration at its beginning, and this is well explained by the fact that the stanzas themselves contain a substantial narrative element. Stanzas are often mixed narration and speech. Þórr’s speech at the beginning of the poem often introduced with the formulaic “Oc hann þat orða / allz fyrst vm qvaþ” (stt. 2.1-2; 3.3-4; 9.9-10; 12.3-4), other similar, formulaic speech introductions also occur, although none consistently through the poem: “Þa qvaþ þat Loci, / Lárfeyiar sonr” (stt. 18.1-2; 20.1-2); “Þa qvaþ þat Þrymr, / þvrsa drottinn” (stt. 22.1-2; 25.1-2; 30.1-2); “Þa qvaþ þat Heimdallr, / hvitastr ása” (15.1-2); “Þa qvaþ þat Þórr, / þrvðugr ass” (st. 17.1-2). These formulaic, metric introductions of speech render the type of marginal speaker annotations found in the other poems superfluous, and only two instances are found in R of prose speaker markings written over the line: “Freyia qvaþ” above stanza 4, and “Þrymr qvaþ” above stanza 7. Half way through stanza 7, the speaker changes to Loki, although “Loci qvaþ” is not found in the manuscript. Indeed it is not needed; Loki’s speech is clearly a reply to Þrymr’s question, and stanza 8 is clearly a reply to Loki’s question at the end of stanza 7.

The only other prose to be found in the poem is at the end, where it is stated “Sva com Oþins sonr endr at hamri” (p. 128) in conclusion to the action of the stanzas, a conclusion that was likely added to balance the narrative begun in stanza one of Þórr losing his hammer.

³³⁸ Citations and stanza numbers from Bugge, pp. 124-128.

³³⁹ *Nr. 2365 4^{to}*, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 33, ll. 12-13.

Vǫlundarkviða

The poem was once evidently preserved in both manuscripts of the *Poetic Edda*, but now it is only fully extant in R; A contains the beginning of the prose (the first 7 lines in Bugge's edition p. 163),³⁴⁰ which is made up of a descriptive prose heading and three lines of text in the manuscript.³⁴¹ The poem now commonly referred to as *Vǫlundarkviða* is named thus in neither R nor A and instead prose headings are found in both manuscripts. R has “*ǫra volvndi*”³⁴² and A “*ǫra niðaði konvngi*”;³⁴³ both headings are written in red ink. R also has an additional title after the prose, heading the stanzas: “*ǫra volvndi. oc niðaði.*”³⁴⁴ Their difference suggests that the headings were added by the scribe of each manuscript rather than being transmitted as a traditional descriptive title with the material each accompanies. Although such titles are thus fluid, the fact that they and others like them are scattered throughout particularly R suggests that the practice itself of describing a section of either prose or poetry is a traditional act possibly carried into the written record through its oral use.³⁴⁵ Most of the pieces headed by descriptive prose titles belong to broader narratives, and the prose pieces under such titles frequently make these connections clear at the same time as they expand the story. Such a device to simultaneously link and tell stories should be viewed in the light of Carol Clover's imminent saga theory, only these descriptive titles are employed to show which bit of the saga the prose or poetry elaborates on. In a manuscript context, this should be seen in conjunction with the titles' role as a form of rubric, in which it is also a device to help readers find their place in the manuscript more easily, since they are visually highlighted by being written in red ink.

³⁴⁰ Stanza numbers and citations from Bugge, pp. 163-170.

³⁴¹ *Nr. 748, 4to*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 12, ll. 26-28.

³⁴² *Nr. 2365 4^{to}*, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 35, l. 4.

³⁴³ *Nr. 748, 4to*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 12, l. 26.

³⁴⁴ Note the “ð” in “*volvndi*” is part of an expansion. *Nr. 2365 4^{to}*, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 35, l. 18.

³⁴⁵ A modern analogue can be found in the titling of each episode of the US sitcom *Friends*: each episode title begins with “The one where...” or “The one with...”

The fact the stanzas have a different title to the prose suggests that perhaps the stanzas ought to be read separately to the prose that is above them. The prose indeed tells a different part of the *Völund* story, material previous to the story-time in the stanzas. After concluding the prose with “Niðvǫr konungr let hann hǫndom taca” (p. 163), at the end of the prose a sentence is added to provide continuity in the manuscript as a whole “sva sem her er vm qveþit” (p. 163). The whole poem thus expands on the short sentence “Niðvǫr konungr let hann hǫndom taca” (p. 163) and, the poem, given its introduction in the prose “sva sem her er vm qveþit”, could be read a corroborating device for what was told in the prose. The content of the poem detailing *Völundr*’s life after his wife had left retells the story of the arrival of the maidens, their taking of husbands and departure and a detailed description of *Völundr*’s capture. His life post-capture is not detailed by the first section of prose.

The first section of prose in *Völundarkviða* seems extracted from the poem itself, with only a couple of expansion to the material that the prose writer has interpreted from the poem itself. Overwhelmingly, the information that the first section of prose contains only information in the poem that comes before the second section of prose located between stanzas 16 and 17. Differences between the prose and poem can be one of phrasing; in the prose the *Níðuðr* is the king “i Sviðioð” (p. 163), in the poem in stanza 13.2 he is “Niara drottinn.” The prose writer adds that *Níðuðr*’s daughter is called *Bödvilðr*, something that the audience does not find out until much later in the poem: she is mentioned explicitly as his daughter only in stanza 36, although her status as *Níðuðr*’s daughter is reaffirmed by the prose piece between stanzas 16 and 17 earlier on. The prose writer also takes the opportunity to clarify the relationship of *Slagfiðr*, *Egill* and *Völundr*: he adds that they are brothers and the sons of the king of the Finns. That they “scriþo” [‘slide on snow-shoes’] in the prose is not mentioned in the poetry and was likely added to emphasise their status as Finns, although that they “veiddo dýr” is reflected in stanza 9, when *Völundr* roasts a she-bear that he has caught. The settlement of *Úlfdalr* by the brothers is not mentioned in the prose, and is an extrapolation of the information in stanza 5, where *Völundr* is sat alone in the location. The lake, called in the prose “*Úlfsjár*,” exists in the poem in

stanza one, but is not named. The name is again an extrapolation from the name of the valley as Úlfdalr. The spinning of the maidens on the lakeshore in the prose is also in stanza one, but the addition that “þar váro hia þeim alptarhamir þeirra; þat váro valkyrior” is only in the prose and is an interpretation made from the fact that they fly (stanza one), and that they fulfil fate (stanzas one and three), and second sister, Hlaðguðr, wears swan feathers (st. 2). Their lineage in the prose is found in stanza 15, spoken it seems by Níðuðr’s queen. That in the prose the men take the maidens “til scala” is evident in the poem from stanza 4 when the men arrive back from hunting to find their halls empty. The pairing of which maiden with which man described in the prose is found in stanzas two and four. In stanza two Hlaðguðr/Svanhvít taking a husband is missing, and it seems clear that something has dropped out here. That the maidens stay for seven years is found in stanza three, although in the poetry their feelings are more complex and they only actually depart after nine years. The prose explanation that they go “at vitia viga” is not suggested by the stanzas, where it simply says that they “orlog drygia” in stanza one and three. The prose statement that they never return is borne out by them never returning in the poetry, at least. Two of the brothers striking out to look for their wives is described in stanza four, and in stanza five and in the prose we find that Vǫlundr alone remained behind. His attribution, that “hann var hagrastr maþr sva at men viti i fornóm sǫgom,” seems an addition to explain why King Níðuðr was so keen to capture him. The prose writer simply extracts the information from the poetry and puts the elements in chronological order, with a saga-style introduction of the protagonists and their basic genealogical facts and where they are from.

The first piece of prose between the stanzas 16 and 17 (p. 166) interrupts the speech of a female, either Níðuðr’s queen or his daughter Bǫdvíldr. The prose between the stanzas assumes that they take place at different times, 16 at Vǫlundr’s capture, and 17 later on after Vǫlundr’s sword and ring have been given to the king and to Bǫdvíldr. The prose insert explains that King Níðuðr does this himself in order to provide context for the comment in stanza 17 that Vǫlundr looks distinctly annoyed when he sees other people with his possessions, and orders him to him to be hamstrung; the prose attributes this to the queen; from the stanzas it could also be

Bǫðvildr. The second prose piece between the stanzas come directly after, between stanzas 17 and 18. The prose seems to have been taken from the poetry: it reports that the order in stanza 17 to have Vǫlundr hamstrung was carried out, and the prose identifies “Sęvarstaþr” as a “holmr” (p. 167), the fact it is an island is not mentioned in st. 20 when the place is named, and then the prose describes Vǫlundr making the king all kinds of treasures, related to st.20.1-4. The prose assertion that “Engi *maþr* þorþi at fara til hans nema konungr einn” (p. 167) seems directly contradicted by the stanzas, since after that both of Níðuðr’s sons (stt. 20-23) come twice to see Vǫlundr and his daughter Bǫðvildr (stt. 26-29). His encounter with Níðuðr meanwhile, (stt. 30-37) happens in Níðuðr’s halls after Vǫlundr has flown there, since Vǫlundr directs Níðuðr to his smithy in order to find the evidence for what he is saying (st. 34). On this point the prose and the poetry thus do not support each other.

There are no marginal speaker markings in this poem. Those that occur do so either at the end of the prose sections, or in one instances in the midst of the manuscript line (before st. 27), where it says: “Vǫlvndr q.”³⁴⁶ As mentioned above, the end of the introductory prose introduces the stanzas as corroboration (“fem her er ým qveþit”),³⁴⁷ while the first piece of the prose between the stanzas ends “en ðrotning qvaþ.”³⁴⁸ to introduce one stanza, while the second piece of prose ends: “Vǫlvndr q.”³⁴⁹ Appending a speaker marking to prose is a practical way of ensuring that everyone is immediately clear who is speaking when the flow of the stanzas have been interrupted, and the “Vǫlvndr q.” before stanza 27 seems somewhat unnecessary since it seems obvious that in stanza 27 it would be Vǫlundr speaking as the character with the famed ability for handiwork.

³⁴⁶ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 37, l. 8.

³⁴⁷ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 35, l. 18.

³⁴⁸ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 36, l. 18.

³⁴⁹ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 36, l. 24.

The prose associated with *Vǫlundarkviða* is drawn from the same tradition as the poem or more likely from the poem itself. The narrative frame it provides is unnecessary to the audience's comprehension of the stanzas and does not add any substantial information, the fragments it does add (such as identifying the flying maidens as Valkyries) seems to be an interpretation of the poem rather than an additional tradition. It seems unlikely that the prose piece would have been transmitted independently from the stanzas. The addition of the prose may have been inspired by the relatively frequent narrative stanzas (or partially narrative stanzas) in the poem. The first eleven stanzas are all narrative stanzas, for example, and form the basis for the most of the material in the prose introduction.

The Heroic Poems

The heroic section of the *Poetic Edda* is prosimetric: it contains poems with prose in varying degrees framing the narratives, between stanzas and providing descriptions of the contents of the poems:

The second part of the Codex Regius begins the accounts of traditional heroes with a poem that stands without accompanying prose, but as it continues we find ourselves in mixed forms in which much of the narrative is in prose. Most scholars believe that the Sigurd poems, which follow next after saga-like material about the hero Helgi, were once part of a lost prosimetric *Sigurðar saga* of mixed origins, and in any case the extant manuscript proceeds step by step with prose narratives and transitions.³⁵⁰

This prose and verse mixed form has led scholars such as Vésteinn Ólason (most recently), to describe this section of the *Poetic Edda* in terms of the *fornaldarsaga* subgenre:

The middle section of *Codex Regius*, from the second poem of Part II to the lacuna, is characterized by a mixture of poetry and prose, a prosimetrum, consisting of direct speech in verse linked with prose passages that are necessary for the coherence of the plot and its understanding. The main parts have frequently been referred to as '*fornaldarsögur*' (i.e. 'legendary or heroic mythical sagas'), the 'saga' of the two Helgis and the 'saga' of Sigurðr. Since Helgi Hundingsbani and Sigurðr Fáfnisbani are presented as (half)brothers in the prose passage linking the poems about them, one can indeed talk about one 'saga'. As regards narrative method, the '*fornaldarsaga*' proper begins with HHjv and is then followed by HH II.³⁵¹

³⁵⁰ Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 133; Andreas Heusler, "Altnordische Dichtung und Prose von Jung Sigurd," *Kleine Schriften*, vol. 1 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1943) pp. 26-64 [Originally published: *Sitzungsberichte der Preussischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, phil.-hist. Klasse*. Berlin, 1919. Pp. 162-195]; Theodore M. Andersson, *The Legend of Brynhild*, *Islandica* 43 (Ithaca, NY: Cornell UP, 1980).

³⁵¹ Vésteinn Ólason, "The Poetic Edda: Literature or Folklore?," pp. 237-238. See also the pages following.

The term *fornaldarsaga* is applied to this section of the *Poetic Edda* precisely because we find heroic, eddic poetry with a prose framework, but caution should be taken about applying the saga subgenre label to this particular section of prose and poetry. Prosimetry it certainly is, perhaps we could even use the term ‘versiprose,’ which makes clear that in this section of the *Poetic Edda* poetry is the dominant form, and prose the secondary form, even allowing for the slightly more substantial prose pieces such as *Dauði Sinfjötla*. Saga is a prose genre, and the prose here is not chief. It should also be noted that the function of the prose in the *Poetic Edda* is to explain the verse, and, as I will demonstrate in Part Three, this is not the function of the prose in the *fornaldarsögur*, in which we find a more sophisticated and varied narrative use of verse in action. One might also ask what using the label ‘fornaldarsaga’ assumes: that the *Poetic Edda* versiprose section is close to an oral *fornaldarsaga* in which verse might be presumed primary, or whether it is being aligned with the written examples of the subgenre that are extant? Do we assume that the verse-prose mix in the *Poetic Edda* prompted the prosimetric form of the *fornaldarsaga*, or that it reflects it? In other words, did the prosimetric *fornaldarsaga* cause the versiprose section of the *Poetic Edda*, or is this versiprose section a prototype of the more mature prosimetric *fornaldarsögur*?

Prose occurs in the heroic section of the *Poetic Edda* in the following roles:

1. To mark the name of the speaker of the stanza. (*Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar*, *Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Reginismál*, *Fáfnismál*, *Helreið Brynhildar*, *Atlamál*)
2. To mark the stanza is dialogue, but the speaker is unnamed (*Sigrdrífumál*)
3. As a narrative introduction to the stanzas. (*Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar*, *Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Gripisspá*, *Reginismál*, *Sigrdrífumál*, *Guðrúnarkviða in fyrsta*, *Helreið Brynhildar*, *Guðrúnarkviða in forna*, *Guðrúnarkviða in þriðja*, *Oddrúnargrátr*, *Atlakviða*, *Guðrúnarhvöt*)
4. As a narrative conclusion to the stanzas. (*Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Reginismál*, *Fáfnismál*, *Guðrúnarkviða in fyrsta*)
5. As prose narrative in between the stanzas (*Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar*, *Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur*, *Reginismál*, *Fáfnismál*, *Sigrdrífumál*)

6. To provide a “title” descriptive of the action (*Helgi Hundingsbana in fyrri, Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar, Helgakviða Hundingsbana in önnur, Fáfnismál, Helreið Brynhildar, Oddrúnargrátr, Atlakviða, Guðrúnarhvöt*)
7. As prose only/to link two poems. (*Frá dauða Sinfjötla, prose before Fáfnismál, prose linking to Sigdrífumál, Frá dauða Sigurðar, prose before Guðrúnarkviða in fyrsta, Sigurðarkviða in skamma, Helreið Brynhildar, Dráp Niflunga, prose before Guðrúnarkviða in forna, Guðrúnarkviða in þriðja, prose before Atlamál, Guðrúnarhvöt*)
8. To name the poem at the end. (*Atlamál (before), Hamðismál*).

Heusler suggests that *Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar* and *Helga kviða Hundingsbana II* make up a section of their own in the Codex Regius; the two poems are connected by the statements that Helgi and Svava in the first poem are reborn in the second.³⁵²

Heusler does not have much praise for the writer of the prose in this section, giving the following characteristics: “1) The patching together of complete and fragmentary lays, and probably *lausavísur* as well, held together by prose passages of unusual length and frequency..., causing the literary genre of certain verse passages to remain uncertain. 2) In both halves the story proceeds without classifying headings and without parallel texts. 3) Another common trait is the helpless incapacity of the writer of the prose passages, which is unparalleled in any other part of the Regius. Stanzas also appear out of their right place, in *Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar* 34. 35 and *Helgakviða Hundingsbana II*.39.”³⁵³

Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar

The title *Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar* is not found in the Codex Regius manuscript, which has a descriptive title “*frá hiozvarþi. oc figrlin.*”³⁵⁴ The introductory prose is lengthy and names several characters who do not appear elsewhere in the poem: two of Hjörðvarðr’s wives and their sons, Særiðr and Humlungr and Sinrióð and Hymlingr have no role to play in the poem. The story presented at the beginning of the poem

³⁵² Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 26.

³⁵³ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 27.

³⁵⁴ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, ll. 4-5.

presents the plot out of order. The prose begins by summarising the whole of Atli's mission to Sigrlinn and her father Sváfñir, and Atli's unsuccessful mission ends with "oc þóz iarlinn. heim."³⁵⁵ Note that in the prose it is said to be Atli's father Iðmundr who is the jarl, and since the poem goes on to make it clear that it is Atli who went on the mission, "jarlinn" is often emended to "Atli" for clarity.³⁵⁶

After Atli heading home, the prose continues. Firstly, Atli's identity as the "iarlf f."³⁵⁷ is reconfirmed from above. This is unnecessary because in the second stanza Atli himself speaks his identity as Iðmundr's son.³⁵⁸ His location "viþ lvnð nocco2n"³⁵⁹ given in the prose so that he is placed. This is not given in the poetry, but is a location that makes sense. Curiously, the next thing to occur in the prose is the narrator telling the audience the thoughts of a bird sat in the branches above Atli's head: it "haþði heyrtr tıl at hanf .menn kalloþo venftar kónoz þer er hıozvarþr konvnr. attı."³⁶⁰ The prose then goes on to say that the bird twittered and Atli paid attention to what it said, the first stanza then being introduced with "hann qvab."³⁶¹ The stanza repeats what the bird was told as having heard in the prose, but adds the question whether its unidentified conversation partner has seen Sigrlinn and implies she is more beautiful than Hjörvarðr's wives.³⁶² Atli's short response of four lines is introduced with "a. q" as marginal speaker notations, and the bird's four line response is marked with "f. q." Such marginal indicators are also extant as speaker initials for the first, fourth and five stanzas of the poem. The exchange of six stanzas continues.

³⁵⁵ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 12.

³⁵⁶ "Helgakviða Hjörðzsonar," *Edda: Die Lieder des Codex Regius nebst verwandten Denkmälern*, ed. G. Neckel, 3rd ed., rev. H. Kuhn, Vol. 1, Text, Germanische Bibliothek 4 (Heidelberg: Carl Winter, 1962) p. 140, l. 11; Bugge, "Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar," p. 171, l. 19.

³⁵⁷ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 13.

³⁵⁸ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 18.

³⁵⁹ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 13.

³⁶⁰ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, 14-15.

³⁶¹ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 16.

³⁶² Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, ll. 16-18.

The second piece of prose, which comes after the five stanzas, complicates the time of the story: “Þetta var áþr atli fúðr;”³⁶³ this episode must then be inserted into the story told in the introductory prose, and thus the beginning of the stanzas are analeptic. The continuation of the prose then clearly joins with a point in the introductory prose, since there it says that Atli went home; the second piece of prose says: “en er hann com heim,”³⁶⁴ and the sixth stanza is introduced as a reply to the king’s request for news. It is introduced with “hann q,”³⁶⁵ which is not marginal but in the body of the poem itself. The stanza Atli speaks is unremarkable in content but does mention two landscape features that are mentioned in the third piece of prose.

The third piece of prose is a lengthy inserted piece and is notable for its description of the landscape through which the party travel.³⁶⁶ The tone of the piece, relating journey, an encounter with a supernatural creature, description of action and the identification and location of a king are all topics common to the *fornaldarsaga* genre, but this piece is extremely compressed. The information does not come from the stanzas. The following four stanzas after the prose insert are speech stanzas spoken by a Valkyrie. The stanzas sound prophetic in tone, but they are not reacted to after them, and the scene of the poem moves on.

The fourth prose insert tells the provenance of the Valkyrie mentioned in the third prose insert. The fourth prose piece thus harks back to earlier information, and it seems odd that this information is split up. The beginning of the 8th stanza, “Hvat letr þv fylgia helga nafni,”³⁶⁷ cross references with the fourth piece of prose, in which it says the Valkyrie gave Helgi his name. The prose suddenly switches at the end of the fourth prose to introduce speech by Helgi, addressed to Hjörvarðr. Neither the

³⁶³ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 24.

³⁶⁴ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, ll. 24-25.

³⁶⁵ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 25.

³⁶⁶ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 43, l. 28 – p. 44, l. 7.

³⁶⁷ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 44, ll. 9-10.

poem nor the prose here controlled the switch in topic. The Valkyrie information in the fourth piece thus proves to be ending that miniature scene in the poem, and the next is not sketched out in the prose except from the introduction of Helgi's utterance. The two stanzas that Helgi speaks addressed to his father are replied to, but in the fifth prose section.

The fifth prose section is notable in that it begins with reported speech.³⁶⁸ Then, the prose informs the reader that Helgi goes to hunt for the sword to which he had been directed in the stanzas before the fourth prose insert. The prose does not describe what happens on this trip, and we are left to assume it was successful. The poem thus do not take the opportunity to expand the narrative details of an event that in a saga would merit an episode of its own. The thirteenth stanza is a demand for their indentification by Hríngerðr, who it is revealed in the stanzas that follow is a giantess. She speaks only one stanza, then the dialogue switches to Atli and he trades insults with the giantess for 18 stanzas.³⁶⁹ There are no prose speaker markings nor any other kind of inset prose in this section, which is similar to episodes found in several *fornaldarsögur* although the example of this exchange is unusually long. The prose framework that ends it moves on, and provides no closure to the poem.

The sixth prose episode, that follows the long exchange between Atli and the troll woman, returns to the tale of Helgi and his betrothed, the Valkyrie Sváva. As well as narrating the cursing of Heðinn, Helgi's brother, by a troll woman, with the result that he swears to marry Sváva, the prose also reports direct speech and indirect speech. The following four stanzas firstly repeat the information given in the prose, at Heðinn recounts what has happened to Helgi. After this, Helgi and Heiðinn speak one stanza each; the speaker is not marked, but they address each other by name.³⁷⁰ The seventh prose piece relates directly back to the previous one, connecting the prose

³⁶⁸ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 44, ll. 21-26.

³⁶⁹ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 44, ll. 31-33 – p. 46, l. 2.

³⁷⁰ Nr. 2365 4^{to}, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 46, ll. 3-21.

surrounding the poem with insights about the troll woman riding the wolf who cursed Heðinn. The continuation of the prose narrates the circumstances of the battle Helgi will engage in and be killed. The prose ends by introducing an utterance by Helgi.³⁷¹

The stanza that Helgi speaks is introduced as an extemporised speech stanza in the style of a skaldic evidence stanza.³⁷² The verse is not addressed to anybody, and is separated from the narrative thirty-seventh stanza by a prose line informing the reader that Helgi has received a death-wound.³⁷³ The following seven speech stanzas are spoken by Sigar, Sváva, and Heðinn variously, although the speakers are not marked.³⁷⁴ The poem ends with a short prose line that reports the belief that Helgi and Sváva were born again.³⁷⁵

Helgakviða Hundingsbana 9nnur

Helgakviða Hundingsbana 9nnur is titled in the Codex Regius “*ǫra vaulfvngom*”³⁷⁶ and the saga opens with prose piece that tells of the son of Vǫlsung and his enemy. The prose introduces speech from Helgi, grandson of Vǫlsung, and his stanza mentions a character called Hamall who has otherwise not been identified.³⁷⁷ This is left to the second piece of prose, which is followed by an exchange of three speech stanzas, followed by more narrative prose and another nine stanza dialogue.

The prosimetric structure changes slightly when the fourth piece of prose in the poetry describes a scene and then introduces evidence stanzas: “*ǫva fem fegir ivolfvnga qviþo. ini ǫozno.*”³⁷⁸ Five evidence stanzas then follow until more prose

³⁷¹ Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 46, ll. 21-26.

³⁷² Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 46, ll. 26-28.

³⁷³ Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 46, 28-29.

³⁷⁴ Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 46, ll. 29-33 – p. 47, ll. 1-12.

³⁷⁵ Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 47, l. 12.

³⁷⁶ Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 47, l. 13.

³⁷⁷ Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 47, ll. 23-24.

³⁷⁸ Nr. 2365 4⁰, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 48, l. 32.

breaks in to continue with a description of the narrative being told in the poem. The end of the prose section reports speech and also declares that it is a quotation from a poem written earlier: “*Sva fem þyr er ritað. i helga qviþo.*”³⁷⁹ The rest of the narrative of the poem is made up of dialogue stanzas interspersed with prose. Characters speaking the dialogues often speak more than two stanzas each, rather than the exchange being tightly structured. The prose ending looks to the future of the characters in order to conclude the poem.

The questions I posed above about the connections of heroic poems to the *fornaldarsögur* are not easy to answer, but the stylistic dissimilarities between the heroic poetry and the sagas in the way that the prose in particular is used means that one should not assume that the eddic poetry is responsible for the generation of the prosimetric saga genre, and thus it should not be described in terms that suggest it ought to be. Given that the prosimetric *fornaldarsaga* seems to be known to have existed in the oral period, it might be more likely that the prose-verse mix found in the heroic part of *Poetic Edda* was prompted by the oral *fornaldarsaga*, rather than the reverse. Perhaps the most profitable way to restrain our judgement of the prose of the heroic poems of the *Poetic Edda* is as metatextual commentary of the verse through the prose frame, rather than considering the prose a structuring device of a versiprose proto-*fornaldarsaga*.

³⁷⁹ Nr. 2365 4^o, ed. Wimmer & Finnur Jónsson, p. 49, ll. 14-15.

Early Nordic Prosimetra (Pre-*Edda*)

My intention in this section is provide an overview and analysis of the prosimetric style of several of the oldest Old Norse works that likely informed the manner and style in which Snorri constructed not only the works in *Heimskringla* but also the prosimetra of his *Edda*, as well as subsequent saga writers. I do not claim that Snorri or the authors of the *fornaldarsögur* (written or oral) necessarily knew these works, only that they reflect the tradition in which they were grounded. The works I will use to explicate the prosimetric profile of early prosimetra are two learned texts, *Íslendingabók*, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, and two *konungasögur*, *Sverris saga* and *Fagrskinna*. In the next section, I will investigate the prosimetric structure of *Gylfaginning*.

These rather early written examples of prosimetric historical texts are likely responsible for prompting the setting down in writing of the prosimetric sagas and *Gylfaginning*. Both the *Edda* and many saga narratives were formed using earlier poetic verses on the same subject matter.³⁸⁰ Prosimetra were a part of the Old Norse oral tradition, and although exactly how they may have sounded (whether, for example, the narratives were predominantly verse and were accompanied by a good deal of fluid prose) is in the main unrecoverable, we do have written prosimetra surviving. If the difference between these speculative oral prosimetra and the written prosimetra is indeed due to a development in the prosimetric form (i.e. the written prosimetric sagas are different to the oral in construction), then it is important to bear in mind that what we have evidence of in the saga narratives is the *result* of a process in which the prosimetra developed, rather than the process itself preserved.

The *konungasögur* are amongst the oldest of the prose genres; only some religious prose, such as the genre of translated hagiographical material, is older. It would be strange that the *konungasögur* are written predominantly by Icelanders about

³⁸⁰ Cf. Clunies Ross, "Snorri's *Edda* as Narrative," p. 17.

the Norwegian kings were it not clear that the genesis of the *konungasögur* lies in the belief that Iceland's own history was rooted in that of the kings; Heather O'Donoghue uses the example that Ari's *Íslendingabók* dates the settlement of Iceland in relation to Norwegian history and also mentions *konunga ævi*.³⁸¹ This interest in Norway combined with other prominent narrative skills present in early medieval Iceland: "factual scholarship" – a love of list making (e.g. genealogies and annals), oral storytelling skills, (oral) skaldic poetry, the 12th-century Latin chronicles written in Norway in a continental style, and the strong European clerical tradition of producing hagiography (the prime candidates for which were canonized royals).³⁸² The coming together of these interests and narrative abilities formed both the prompt and the basis for lengthy and historically rich sagas about the Norwegian kings. These sagas are also strikingly prosimetric.

The eddic stanzas quoted in *Gylfaginning*, corroborative or evidence stanzas used to confirm the veracity of what has been said in the prose, are used rather differently to the stanzas in the *Íslendingasögur*, in which skaldic stanzas usually come out of the mouths of characters as part of the story; Snorri's use of evidence stanzas in *Gylfaginning* thus finds its most likely origin in the *konungasögur*, where stanzas are routinely quoted as evidence verses, although these are usually skaldic and not eddic. It seems that the *Edda* is the first of Snorri's work, and thus comes before his *Heimskringla*,³⁸³ although it is not inconceivable that Snorri was working on *Heimskringla* at the same time as he was working on his *Edda* in 1220-1225, although he is thought to have finished *Heimskringla* by 1236.³⁸⁴ Snorri was well versed in the *konungasögur* and wrote a later collection of kings sagas himself, those that make up *Heimskringla*, and for these, he used a number of earlier kings sagas and skaldic stanzas as sources.

³⁸¹ Heather O'Donoghue, *Old Norse-Icelandic Literature: A Short Introduction*, Blackwell Introductions to Literature 6 (Malden, MA: Blackwell, 2004) 94-95.

³⁸² O'Donoghue, *Old Norse-Icelandic Literature*, p. 95.

³⁸³ I will not engage with questions of Snorri's supposed authorship of various works, including *Egils saga*.

³⁸⁴ Wanner, *Snorri Sturluson and the Edda*, p. 28.

Which of the *konungasögur* did Snorri know and may have affected his prosimetric style? For this, one can consider the sources of *Heimskringla*, the identification of which has been a central concern in the scholarship.³⁸⁵ In terms of written sources, *Óláfs saga Tryggvasonar*, for example, has a lot of material supplied from *Ágrip*, Oddr Snorrason's saga of Óláfr Tryggvason, *Jómsvíkinga saga*, and *Fagrskinna*, and *Morkinskinna* is an important source for the later sagas in the collection.³⁸⁶ Ári Þorgilsson, author of *Íslendingabók*, is admired in the Prologue to *Heimskringla*,³⁸⁷ but his text is short and he cites only one *kviðlingr* and Snorri does not really utilise Ári's "restrained, scholarly approach."³⁸⁸ *Sverris saga*, one of the oldest lives of kings,³⁸⁹ seems to be mentioned by Snorri: "svá hefir Sverir konungr rita látit"³⁹⁰ [thus King Sverrir had [the saga] written']. *Sverris saga* was partially written at the dictation of King Sverrir himself, and is plentiful in details, and this style, along with its "literary speeches," is thought to have influenced Snorri.³⁹¹ Oral sources must have also been very important to Snorri.

For my treatment of the early Nordic prosimetrum, I have not attempted a full intertextual reading, as would be possible with many of the stanzas in the *konungasögur*, since they are borrowed in and out of various prose contexts. Rather, I have concentrated on the role of the verses in the individual narratives as they stand (or at least as they stand in the editions), to gauge what the predecessors were to

³⁸⁵ I do not attempt to give an exhaustive list of every text Snorri may have known or may have known versions of. For a survey of *Heimskringla* sources that considers many types of sources, including oral tradition, see chapter four, "Sources and Influences" of Diana Whaley, *Heimskringla: An Introduction*, Text Series 8 (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1991).

³⁸⁶ Whaley, *Heimskringla*, p. 64.

³⁸⁷ *Prologus*, *Heimskringla*, ed. Bjarni Aðalbjarnarson, vol. 1, Íslenzk fornrit 26 (Reykjavík: Hið Íslenska fornritafélag, 1941) pp. 3-7, at p. 7.

³⁸⁸ Whaley, *Heimskringla*, 65. Cf. Sverrir Tómason, *Formálar íslenskra sagnaritara á miðöldum: Rannsókn bókmennatæfðar*, Rit 33 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1988) 213-214.

³⁸⁹ *Fagrskinna A Catalogue of the Kings of Norway: A Translation with Introduction and Notes*, trans. Alison Finlay, *The Northern World* 7 (Leiden: Brill, 2004) p. 1.

³⁹⁰ *Haraldssona saga*, *Heimskringla*, ed. Bjarni Aðalbjarnarson, vol. 3, Íslenzk fornrit 28 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska fornritafélag, 1951) pp. 303-346, at p. 346.

³⁹¹ Whaley 68-69.

Gylfaginning and prosimetric *fornaldarsaga* literature in terms of their prosimetric profiles.

Íslendingabók

There is only one stanza quoted in *Íslendingabók*, a stanza in *runhent* spoken by Hjalti Skeggjason in chapter seven. The stanza is quoted in order to explain why Hjalti had been subjected to lesser outlawry, and is presumably quoted in full to demonstrate its offensive content:

Vil ek eigi goð geyja;
grey þykki mér Freyja.³⁹²

It is introduced thus: *En þat vas til þess haft, at hann kvað at logbergi kviðling þenna* [‘and the reason for this was that he recited this ditty at the Law-Rock’]. It is notable that this *kviðlingr* is included given the lack of acknowledgement of any other poetic source in the work. Its role in the prose is rather idiosyncratic; on the one hand, it is a type of evidence stanza, since Hjalti was outlawed because he was offensive, and the quotation is the proof that he was, on the other hand, evidence stanzas usually repeat what is in the prose, but this stanza does not directly summarise any event that happened in the prose, and so in its status as evidence of a speech act and not an event, it is unusual for the genre of history writing.³⁹³

The First Grammatical Treatise³⁹⁴

The only extant copy of anonymous First Grammatical Treatise (FGT, or *Fyrsta málfræðiritgerðin*) is preserved in the Codex Wormianus with three other texts on grammatical matters, after the *W* version of *Snorra Edda*. The codex is from around

³⁹² *Íslendingabók, Íslendingabók. Landnámabók*, ed. Jakob Benediktsson, Íslensk Fornrit 1 (Reykjavík: Híð Íslenska fornritafélag, 1968) 3-28, at 15.

³⁹³ Similar ditties, some connected to Hjalti, are found elsewhere. For further on this, see *Íslendingabók* 15, fn. 7; *Íslendingabók, Kristni Saga. The Book of the Icelanders, The Story of the Conversion*, trans. Siân Grønlie Text, Series 18 (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 2006) 24-25, fn. 69.

³⁹⁴ All textual references are to *The First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, University of Iceland Publications in Linguistics 1 (Reykjavík: Institute of Nordic Linguistics, 1972). The page number is given, then folio and line number, following the conventions used in the edited text.

the mid-14th century, but it seems that this version of the FGT is a copy rather than an original, and furthermore, must be at least the second remove from the original, which is thought to have been written between 1125 and 1175.³⁹⁵ There are three quotations of verse in the treatise.³⁹⁶

The first verse quotation in the FGT is an unattributed first quarter of a stanza found complete in *Haralds saga Sigurðarsonar* and in *Hákonar saga Ívarssonar*.³⁹⁷ The stanza is by Þjóðólfr Arnórsson, who lived in the mid-11th century. It is quoted in a section concerning the distinction between long and short vowels, where the grammarian says he will mark the long with a stroke.³⁹⁸ He then goes on to give minimal pairs to illustrate this, and then an illustrative narrative containing these words:

Vel likvðv *goprørpe góþ rórpe*. Þat erv goðar árar sem skalld qvað[.]
 Rætt kann ræði slita
 ræsis herr or verri.³⁹⁹

Well did *Godred (Goprørpe)* like *góþ rórpe*, that is *good oars*, as the scald said:
 The chief's men can pull
 straight *oars (rórpe)* out of the sea.⁴⁰⁰

The skaldic stanza complements both the subject matter and the word choice of the prose above. The word *ræði* is defined in the prose with the more usual *ár*. The introductory phrase, *sem scald qvað*, shows that this quotation is used for evidence.

The second and third quotations are linked, and the section is worth quoting at length:

³⁹⁵ *First Grammatical Treatise: The Earliest Germanic Phonology*, ed. Einar Haugen, *The Classics of Linguistics*, 2nd ed. (London: Longman, 1972) 7-8; *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, pp. 22-23, 31. The dating of the original of the First Grammatical Treatise is rather a vexed question; for an overview of opinions and bibliography, see *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Haugen, p. 78, esp. note 1.

³⁹⁶ The Third and Fourth grammatical treatises contain many stanzas to illustrate their points, but they are dated too late for this survey.

³⁹⁷ *Haralds saga Sigurðarsonar*, ed. Bjarni Aðalbjarnarson, pp. 142-143, st. 122 and the note on st. 122.

³⁹⁸ *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, p. 218, fol. 86.3.

³⁹⁹ *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, p. 222, fol. 86.13-15.

⁴⁰⁰ *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, p. 223, fol. 86.

Skalld erv hofvndar allar rynní ęða mááls greinar sem smiđir [smiđar] ęða lođmenn laga. En þessa lund kvađ æinn þeira ęða þessv likt.

Hofđv hart of krafđir
hilldr ox við þat skilldir
gang en gamler sprvngv
gvnn þings earn hringar.

Nv þo að kveđandinn skldi hann til at slita æina sam stöfv i svndr ok gíora tvær vr. til þess at kveđandi halldiz i hætti þa rak hann þo æingi navđr til þess at skipta stöfvnm ok hafa *e*. fyrir *i* ef helldr ætti *i* at vera en *e* þo at mer litiz æigi at því. Enn ef nokkvR verđr sva æin mááll ęða hia máll at hann mæler a mot sva morgvm monnmv skynsmvm sem bæði letvz sialfir kveđa þetta orđ aðr ek ritađa þat ok sva hæyra aðra Menn kveđa sem nv er ritađ ok þv lætr *i* skvlv kveđa enn æigi *e* þo at þat orđ se i rvær samstöfv deillt. þa vil ek hafa áastráđ katonis þat er hann ređ syni sínum i versvm.

Contra verbos os noli contendere verbis.

Serrmo datvr cunctis animi sapientia pavcis.

þat er sva að skilia. hirđ æigi þv að þræta við maalrofs menn[.] Malróf er gefit mōrgum em spekin fam.⁴⁰¹

The scalds are authorities in all (matters touching the art of) writing or the distinctions (made in) discourse, just as craftsmen (are) [in their craft] or lawyers in the law. One of them made a verse somewhat as follows:

The shield, strongly urged
to conflict, made headway;
battle's fury mounted,
but the old *iron (earn)* swords burst.

Now, even though the (metrical) rhythm forced him to split one syllable and make two out of (it), in order for the rhythm of the meter to be preserved, still no necessity compelled him to change the letters and use *e* instead of *i*, if *i* should (in fact) be (used) rather than *e* in spite of my belief to the contrary. But if anyone becomes so insistent or obstinate as to contradict so many sensible men, who have said, (even) before I wrote this word, that they themselves pronounce it as I have now written (it), and also that they have heard others pronounce it so – and (if) you (still) say that *i* should be pronounced and not *e*, even though this word is divided into two syllables – then I shall apply Cato's affectionate advice, which he gave his son in verse:

Contra verbosos noli contendere verbis;
sermo datur cunctis, animi sapientia pavcis.

That is to say: Do not quarrel with loquacious people; loquacity is given to many, but wisdom to few.⁴⁰²

The first quotation is cited both to demonstrate the authority of the skalds in matters concerning language, but also to be illustrative of and evidence of his point regarding whether one should use *e* or *i*.⁴⁰³ The beginning of the introduction to the passage states the authority of the skalds, and the introductory sentence to the stanza gives a somewhat vague introduction to the stanza, which is unattributed (it is the second half a strophe that is preserved in Óláfs saga helga in *Heimskringla* complete.⁴⁰⁴ Although

⁴⁰¹ *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, pp. 224, 226, 228, fol. 87.4-15.

⁴⁰² *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, pp. 225, 227, 229, fol. 87.

⁴⁰³ For an explanation of the issue behind the word *earn* see *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, 156-158.

⁴⁰⁴ *Ólaf's saga helga*, ed. Bjarni Ađalbjarnarson, p. 16.

the prose after the passage is talking about *earn* in the stanza, this is not indicated explicitly; the manuscript has *éärn*, but, as Hreinn Benediktsson points out, the accent and diaeresis are almost certainly a later addition.⁴⁰⁵ The skaldic stanza quoted is by the early 11th century skald Óttarr svarti, and by saying that nothing was forcing the skald to use *e* rather than *i*, and certainly not the grammarian himself (who was much later; the irony in this passage is also noted by Hreinn Benediktsson).⁴⁰⁶ The grammarian is thus highlighting the role of the stanza as evidence independent of his own arguments.⁴⁰⁷

Should his reader not be swayed by his presentation, the grammarian also includes a quotation to dissuade them from presenting their objections too voraciously. The quotation from Latin is attributed (correctly) to Cato, giving advice to his son. Framing the quotation in these terms puts the grammarian in the paternal, and thus more powerful role here, and the content of the quotation, not to engage with those who are garrulous, since they are numerous and the wise are few, further points out the grammarian's lack of inclination to argue about what he has written, and that he, as one of the few, is wise. The two quotations that frame this section thus both affirm the astuteness and authority of the grammarian, as well as displaying his learning in both vernacular and Latin poetics (by quoting skaldic and Latin verse), and, by pointing to the skalds as vernacular authorities whilst at the same time quoting Cato, he may also be implying that vernacular poetics have the same worth as those in the Classical languages.

Sverris saga

Although they are not mentioned as sources in the well-known prologue to the saga, there are eighteen instances of poetic quotation in manuscript AM 327 4to of *Sverris saga*, which is the manuscript version discussed here in this prosimetric analysis of the

⁴⁰⁵ *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, p. 226, note to fol. 87.7.

⁴⁰⁶ *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, p. 227, note to fol. 87.9-10.

⁴⁰⁷ Cf. *First Grammatical Treatise*, ed. Hreinn Benediktsson, p. 227, note to fol. 87.9-10.

saga. The saga has four principle manuscripts, AM 327 4to, AM 47 fol.,⁴⁰⁸ GKS 1005 fol. (Flateyjarbók),⁴⁰⁹ and AM 81a fol.⁴¹⁰ AM 327 4to, Den Arnamagnæanske Samling, Copenhagen, is usually taken by editors to be the principal manuscript, and the references here are to its edition by Gustav Indrebø.⁴¹¹ *Sverris saga* is the only text in the manuscript of 92 sides and the manuscript is from c. 1300. according to Kålund,⁴¹² although the saga itself is thought to have been completed before 1210.

Sverris saga is a biographical rather than synoptic kings' saga. The author of *Sverris saga* takes time at the beginning to introduce his theme, King Sverrir, and his sources, which in the prologue he proclaims to be both written and oral:

Her hefr upp oc segir fra þeim tíðindum er nu hava verit um rið oc i þeira Manna minnum er fyrir þeffi bok hava fagt. En þat er at segia fra Sverri konungi fysi Sigurþar konungs Harallz-sonar oc er þat uphaf bocarinar er ritat er eptir þeiri bok er fyrft ritaði Karl aboti Ion-son. en yfir fat sialfr Sverrir konungr. oc reð fyrir hvat rita skyldi er fu fra-fogn eigi langt fram komin. þar er fagt fra nockorum hanf orroftum. Oc fua fem a liðr bokina vex hanf styrkr. oc segir fa hinn sami styrkr fyrir hina meiri luti. kailloðu þeir þan lut bocar fyrir þui Grylu hinn siðari lutr bocar er ritaðr eptir þeira manna fra-fogn er minni hofðu til fva at þeir sialfir hofðu fet oc heyrtr þeffi tíðinde oc þeir men sumir hofðu verit i orostom með Sverri konungi. Sum þeffi tíðinde varo sva i minne feft at men ritaðo þegar eptir er ny-orðin varo. oc hava þau ecki breyz siðan.⁴¹³

The author (or perhaps the narrator) of the prologue seems to equate fixity of the stories with their being written down not long after the events happen, and he is concerned on several occasions with the veracity of his narrative:

...er fu fra-fogn eigi langt fram komin.⁴¹⁴
Sum þeffi tíðinde varo sva i minne feft at men ritaðo þegar eptir er ny-orðin varo. oc hava þau ecki breyz siðan.⁴¹⁵

⁴⁰⁸ Also known as "Erspenill," the manuscript is dated by Kålund to the first part of the 1400s (KAH, vol. 1, p. 33). *Sverris saga* is found on 1v-194.

⁴⁰⁹ Written in the period 1387-1394. *Sverris saga* in on 145r-164r.

⁴¹⁰ Also known as "Skálholtsbók yngsta." *Sverris saga* is, with *Hákonar saga Sverrissonar* and a fragment of *Guttorms ok Inga*, on 1-64r. The manuscript is from the 15th century, according to KAH, vol. 1, p. 60.

⁴¹¹ *Sverris saga etter Cod. AM 327 4º*, ed. Gustav Indrebø (Kristiania: Den Norske Historiske Kildeskriptommission, 1920). Page and line numbers are given.

⁴¹² KAH, vol. 1, p. 570. Handrit.is gives 1290-1310. Detailed information about the manuscript is given in *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø pp. v-xii; about its orthography pp. xv-xxxi; about the differences between this and other manuscripts of the saga and their relationship to each other pp. xxxi-li.

⁴¹³ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 1, ll. 2-16.

⁴¹⁴ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 1, ll. 7-8.

Oc þickir os at licara at þær fagnir mune vera við fannýndum er a bokum ero fagðar fra agætifmonnum þeim er verit hava i fornæskió.⁴¹⁶

And, in the style of Ari, the author invites his audience to alter the text should they know better:

En vera kan þat ef þeir mēn fia þesa bok er allkunnt er um. at þeim þicki skyndiliga yfir farit i morgum stoðom oc mart þat eptir ligia er frafagnar mynde vert þickia. oc mego þeir þat ænn væl lata r[ita ef] þeir vilia.⁴¹⁷

The author of *Sverris saga* is concerned to reassure his readers that his history writing is well-researched and to maintain the very bookish character of his sources, even those which he admits spring from oral history are linked quickly to the stability of the written record. The author of *Sverris saga* seems eager to centre the origin of his narrative to close proximity with the authenticating figure of the king:

...oc er þat uphaf bocarinar er ritat er eptir þeiri bok er fyrft ritaði Karl aboti Ion-son. en yfir fat fialfr Sverrir konungr. oc reð fyrir hvat rita skyllði er fu fra-fogn eigi langt fram komin.⁴¹⁸

Hinn siðari lutr bocar er ritaðr eptir[ir] þeira manna fra-fogn er minni hofðu t[i]l fva at þeir fialfir hofðu fet oc heyrð þessi tíðinde oc þeir mēn fumir hofðu verit i orostom með Sverri konungi.⁴¹⁹

The author does not mention any poetry as the source of his narrative. As the *konungasögur* develop, at least chronologically, as a genre, more and more stanzas are added to the prose, reflecting an increasing taste for the prosimetric and probably paving the way for the writing down of the *Íslendingasögur* and the *fornaldarsögur*. The other early written prose genre, the translated hagiographical material, is not prosimetric.

The first stanza in *Sverris Saga* is an evidence stanza and begins “Fylgðu ræfi Rygir oc Horðar.”⁴²⁰ The authenticating role is a normal one for a stanza in the *konungasögur*

⁴¹⁵ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 1, ll. 14-16.

⁴¹⁶ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 1, ll. 22-24.

⁴¹⁷ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 1, ll. 16-19.

⁴¹⁸ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 1, ll. 5-8.

⁴¹⁹ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 1, ll. 11-14.

⁴²⁰ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 47, ll. 15-18. Note that I will give the first line of stanzas for orientation purposes when I do not cite the whole stanza. These are for identification and will not be translated.

and the verse is introduced with the unremarkable “*fem her fegir*” [‘as it says here’].⁴²¹ However, this first stanza of the saga is unusual because it is eddic (in *fornyrðislag*), whereas the *konungasögur* commonly employ stanzas in skaldic metre. As an anonymous *lausavísa*, it simply names the parts of Norway that the levy of King Magnús came from, and in doing so is comparable to other eddic stanzas that preserve lists of place names, for example in *Ketil saga hængs* when the hag Forað reels off the places she has visited – this stanza is perhaps part of or at least referencing this tradition.⁴²² The prose directly before the stanza lists the places that the *lið* are from, making reference, it seems, directly to the contents of the stanza, since the places are listed in the same order. Directly before the stanza the prose also states prominent individuals who accompanied the king. The prose directly after the stanza continues with the relation of the episode without commenting on the stanza, as is standard.

The second stanza of *Sverris saga*, an anonymous couplet, is presented as an adage that has come to pass:

Er þat fcamlaft at þigia oc sva at veita ftor hag. fem fcalldit qvað.
 Era fem kol-við cliufi
 Carll fa er veqr at iarle.⁴²³

Who “fcalldit” [‘the poet’] is is not known, and although it could, in a different context, be an extemporised saying, here it sounds proverbial, and this is likely since it is in the context of a farmer giving advice to his son as he goes to war.⁴²⁴

⁴²¹ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 47, l. 14.

⁴²² “Gang hóf ek upp í Angri. / Eigraðak þá til Steigar. / Skálm glamrandi skrapti. / Skarmtak þá til Karmtar. / Elda munk á Jaðri / ok at Útsteini blása. / Þá munk austr við Elfi, áðr dagr á mik skíni, / ok með brúðkonum beigla ok brátt gefin jarli.” [‘I went to a feast up in Angri, / Then I walked heavily to Steigar. / The short sword, jingling, clattered. / Then I pressed on to Karmtar. / I will take fire to Jaðri / and at Útsteinn blow. / Then I will go east with the Elfi / before day shines on me, / and quarrelled with the bridesmaids / and soon got the earl.’] *Ketils saga hængs, Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, eds. Guðni Jónsson and Bjarni Vilhjálmsson, vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Bókauþgáfan forni, 1943) 245-266, at ch. 5, p. 260. This stanza in *Ketils saga hængs* preserves the sailing route down the coast of Norway; see Helen F. Leslie, “The Matter of Hrafnista,” *Quaestio Insularis* 11 (2010): 169-208, at 199-200.

⁴²³ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 50, ll. 9-12.

⁴²⁴ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 50, ll. 13-15.

Just one *helmingr* of a skaldic stanza, stanza three of *Sverris saga* is an anonymous *lausavísa* attributed to an unknown poet, as in the style of stanza two, above.

Veit ec þat oc fannlega um alla Þrændi at þeim er sva gefit. fem fcalldit qvað.
 Etlá ec mer hina mæro
 munfagra Jnguni
 hvegi er fundr með frægium
 fer Magnufi oc Sveri.⁴²⁵

The third stanza seems to be one that sprang to the author’s mind and that seemed to exemplify the situation well rather than being presented as adage that has come to pass. Theodoricus also uses many of his verse quotations in the same way, as stanzas that typify the situation he is describing in his prose. The *Sverris saga* stanza is part of a speech by King Sverrir and the stanza is used to exemplify the thoughts of the *Þrændir* [‘people from Trondheim’] whose thoughts are presented to be ostensibly more on women than the battle – and thus they mean to stay unwounded (i.e. not to fight hard).⁴²⁶ The quotation of the stanza is thus a quotation within a quotation, since it is part of the saga narrative quoting the king.

The fourth occurrence of verse is made up of two stanzas that begin “Glym-vollu riftr gulli” and “Ber fyrir Holm þar er hari” respectively, introduced as the quotation of stanzas composed by the skald Hallr Snorrason: “þa var með Magnusi konungi. Hallr Snora-son fcalld. Hann orti þa vifur þesar” [‘Then Hallr Snorrason was with King Magnús. Then he composed these stanzas’].⁴²⁷ After the stanza, the prose continues with the narration of the episode undisturbed.

The sixth stanza in the saga, which begins “Fant fe ec hvern a hesti,” is attributed in the narrative to the skald Bjarni Kalfsson and introduced with “hann qvað visu” [‘he said a stanza’].⁴²⁸ The composition of the *runhent* stanza is incidental to

⁴²⁵ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 51, ll. 1-6.

⁴²⁶ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 50, l. 37 – p. 51, l. 1.

⁴²⁷ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 72, ll. 2-3.

⁴²⁸ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 75, l. 3.

the action, and is related at the end of the episode, perhaps as a record of what the skald said about the situation. The exact context he says it in is not recorded. The tenth stanza in the saga by the skald Nefari, which begins “*Tynum Birkibeinum*,”⁴²⁹ and the eleventh and twelfth stanzas by the skald Blakkr, that begin “*Reifum ve firir vifa*” and “*Aulld man helldr at hœll duz*” respectively, are introduced similarly. The stanza by Nefari is introduced “*þa qvað Nefari þesa visu*,”⁴³⁰ and both of Blakkr’s stanzas are introduced with “*þa qvað Blacer (þesa, stanza ten) visu*” [‘then Blakkr said (this) stanza’].⁴³¹ All three come amidst uninteresting descriptions of the movement of people or armies and do not have a performance context given for them; they are simply quotations of the occasional stanzas composed about that particular event. After Nefari’s stanza and Blakkr’s first stanza, the narration continues unperturbed, and after the second of Blakkr’s stanza, the saga switches subject rather than recording any response to the composition of the stanzas.

The seventh stanza, which begins “*Byr gefðu bratt hin arui*,” is introduced as an occasional stanza by the skald Máni with the phrase he “*kvað visu*,”⁴³² but this stanza is unusual because the king comments on it in the prose following the stanza: “*Vel er kvepit Tungli*” [‘well composed, Tungli’].⁴³³ Unlike stanza six, this stanza is thus set in some kind of performance context – the king was clearly listening, and rewards the skald with a kirtle for his efforts.⁴³⁴ The favour Máni finds continues with the seventh stanzas continues with the recitation of the the eighth and ninth stanzas, beginning “*Slægr fer gar með ggiu*” and “*Gigian fyngr þar er ganga*” respectively, come together and are also by him. These stanzas have a clear performance context in the saga, and are truly occasional stanzas by Máni about the jugglers in the court, since

⁴²⁹ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 112, l. 1.

⁴³⁰ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 111, ll. 37-38.

⁴³¹ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 113, ll. 4-11, 30-37.

⁴³² *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 90, l. 27.

⁴³³ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 90, l. 36.

⁴³⁴ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 90, ll. 36-38.

the king encourages him to compose about them, “*yrœðu um þa vifu*” [‘compose a stanza about them’].⁴³⁵ The uproarious appreciation of the audience to the stanzas and the jugglers subsequent discomfort demonstrates the social leverage skaldic poetry could have; as the king says to Máni, it “*ma vera at þer verþi helldr gagn at*” [‘maybe that it will be of use to you’].⁴³⁶ The stanzas are separated by the phrase “*Oc en qvað hann*” [‘and yet he said’],⁴³⁷ and it is not clear as to whether the stanzas were said back to back or at different points in time.

The 13th and 14th stanzas, which begin “*Biort kveða brenna kerti*” and “*Hafði her meðan lifði*” respectively, occur together and form a short chapter all of their own in the manuscript, with minimum prose accompanying them. Although there is no rubric/chapter heading, as normally found in AM 327 4to at the beginning of a new episode, there is an initial E in red ink to begin the section, and a line separates this short section containing the two stanzas from the previous capital.⁴³⁸ The stanzas, recited by Blakkr, are about Breiðskeggr and are uncomplimentary. The point of the short chapter is to emphasise Breiðskeggr’s lack of merit as a person after his death. The chapter does not quote Blakkr’s first stanza as a demonstration of this, but cites the stanza in order to illustrate what Blakkr said when he spoke against the rumour that Breiðskeggr might be saint-like.⁴³⁹ After the first stanza comes an explanation that Blakkr had also composed an *erfidrápa* about Breiðskeggr, *Breiðskeggsdrápa*, and the second stanza cited is said to be the *stef* of the poem.⁴⁴⁰ After the second stanza, the saga switches subject completely and a new chapter begins, without any further comment on the subject of the verse.

⁴³⁵ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 91, l. 12.

⁴³⁶ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 91, l. 13.

⁴³⁷ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 91, l. 22.

⁴³⁸ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 122, l. 10; see also note 2, same page.

⁴³⁹ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 122, ll. 10-17.

⁴⁴⁰ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 122, ll. 18-22.

The 15th and 16th stanzas, beginning “Mana-dag kvaddi milldingr fina” and “Mana-dag kvaddi niðingr fina” respectively, are unusual in that they are cited as being composed by two peoples, the Baglar and the Birkibeinar, and so are presented as collectively authored: “þa ortu Baglar visu þesa” [‘then the Baglar composed this vísa’] and “En Birkibeinar kvaðu þesa visu” [‘But the Birkibeinar recited this vísa’].⁴⁴¹ The second stanza closely mirrors the first; both are in *hrynhent*, several lines are repeated exactly (ll. 1, 5, 6), others are changed minimally to reflect badly on their opponents. This exchange of insults is followed by a different episode starting.

The 17th stanza, the first line of which “Vlikr ertu ydrum nudíum,” is an anonymous stanza in *fornyrðislag* quoted in the midst of King Sverrir speaking to Sigurðr Sverrisson lávarðr. It is introduced with “ok er sva fem qvedit er,”⁴⁴² giving a verse version of what Sverrir has just said in a quasi-authenticating manner. The narrative continues directly after the verse with “ok enn mælti hann,”⁴⁴³ and this introduction of the second part of the speech in prose mildly acknowledges the interruption of the stanza but does not otherwise comment on it. The final stanza of the saga, beginning “fær er huatr,” is found in the continuation of Sverrir’s speech and is a quotation of half of the 18th stanza of the poem *Fáfnismál*, and is used by Sverrir as a saying: “enn þat er fatt er mælt er. at...”⁴⁴⁴ and his speech continues after this piece of verse in a natural manner.

In summary, the stanzas play the following roles in *Sverris saga*: as evidence, as adages or sayings, as examples, and as occasional verse. Stanzas one and seventeen are evidence stanzas: their contents corroborate and reinforce what is said in prose. Stanzas two and eighteen have a proverbial air to them; likely they were well-known to the saga’s original audience or readership and imbue their speakers with a humanity

⁴⁴¹ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 159, ll. 4-5 and l. 14.

⁴⁴² *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 178, ll. 3-4.

⁴⁴³ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 178, l. 7.

⁴⁴⁴ *Sverris saga*, ed. Indrebø p. 178, l. 11.

the audience can relate to – particularly important in the sympathetic presentation of King Sverrir. Only one exemplifying stanza, stanza three, is found in the saga: here the stanza quoted seems to simply be an apt stanza that was inserted into the narrative, possibly for aesthetic interest. This range of uses may have been deployed in order to engage the interest of the audience.

The occasional stanzas, of which there are twelve (stanzas four to sixteen), are in the majority in the saga. These are stanzas uttered by a named skald about the situation in hand in the prose. Stanzas four to six and ten to twelve are straightforward. Their inclusion does not overly trouble the narrative and they add nothing dramatic to the action. Stanzas seven to nine, however, by the poet Máni, have a strong performance context and their recitation and reception are commented upon in the prose. These stanzas are essential in moving the plot forward as well as being records of a poet's speech on a subject. We also find occasional stanzas cited from a longer poem (stanzas thirteen and fourteen), and perhaps it was assumed that the audience were capable of fully appreciating this intertextual reference (e.g. they knew the *drápa* already). Stanzas fifteen and sixteen remain. These too are occasional stanzas and would be straightforward were they not said to be collectively authored by a people, a feature usually (silently) attributed to eddic verse. They present a very interesting example of the suppression of individual authorship in the skaldic context. Overall, *Sverris saga*, considering it has relatively few stanzas in comparison to other *konungasögur*, has an interesting and varied use of stanzas that no doubt aided in places the construction of the saga prose, particularly, for example, in the case of Máni's stanzas and their detailed, motivated recitation in the prose, and in the section included on the basis of *Breiðskeggsdrápa*. The anecdotal seems a particular concern in *Sverris saga*, and this is reflected in the use of verse in the saga prose.

Fagrskinna

Fagrskinna, which seems to have been called *Nóregs konunga tal* in the Middle Ages, in its oldest version originates in the 13th century (the B redaction; the A redaction is from the first half of the 14th century), and is thought to be a few years older than

Heimskringla, since it appears Snorri knew the work. Both original manuscripts of the two redactions are lost, although in the case of B one leaf survives in Oslo (NRA 51). Textual editions are thus based on copies. The text draws heavily on earlier written sources, although the manner in which they are arranged I suggest may nevertheless be derived from oral skaldic prosimetra, in which *Begleitprosa* accompanies the stanzas, as argued in the conclusion to my discussion of *Fagrskinna*. This may be particularly evident in the sections in which more than one verse is cited (which are numerous).⁴⁴⁵ Of particular interest to eddic prosimetra is the manner in which the narrative of *Fagrskinna* displays accretive quotation, in which stanzas are quoted consecutively or with only a small amount of prose inbetween in order to build up a unit of verses. This is common in both *Gylfaginning* and the *fornaldarsögur*, and a kings' saga such as *Fagrskinna* could be looked to as a model for the written construction of prosimetric narratives, since the written *konungasögur* predate the writing down of the *Edda* or the *fornaldarsögur*.

This section attempts to give an overview of the style and narrative use of the verse in the prose of *Fagrskinna* and to demonstrate the various methods with which narrative prose can incorporate stanzas. *Fagrskinna* has been chosen because it is rather long and has many stanzas, and thus has the potential to display a wide range of narrative uses of verses; its author was clearly very interested in skaldic verse and the uses to which it could be put. The prosimetrum of *Fagrskinna* is analysed from the perspective of how the stanzas are introduced. There is only one set of stanzas in *Fagrskinna* that does not have an introduction. At the end of chapter 74, three stanzas appear that simply run on from the prose.⁴⁴⁶ This is highly unusual in the saga; all other stanzas are provided with a context of some kind.

⁴⁴⁵ For a detailed introduction to the text and the manuscript, see the introductions of *Fagrskinna – Nóregs konunga tal, Ágrip af Nóregskonunga sögum. Fagrskinna – Nóregs konunga tal*, ed. Bjarni Einarsson, Íslenzk fornrit 29 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenzka fornritafélag, 1984) and *Fagrskinna*, trans. Finlay. Citations and translations are also taken from these two editions. Finlay's excellent translation follows the Íslenzk fornrit edition and Finlay numbers her stanzas accordingly. Translations will only be given of material appearing in the body of the text. Quotations from *Fagrskinna* that appear in the footnotes will not be translated – refer to Finlay's translation.

⁴⁴⁶ *Fagrskinna*, pp. 291-293 stt. 245-247.

The most frequent stanzas to occur in the saga are evidence stanzas. The simplest introductory phrase to occur in *Fagrskinna* is a simple evidence stanza quoted without the name of the poet: these stanzas are introduced with “sem hér segir”⁴⁴⁷ or “svá sem hér segir.”⁴⁴⁸ These are introductions of evidence stanzas that are nevertheless anonymous. Similar are simple evidence stanzas with the name of the poet, the introductory formulae “sem segir/sagði NAME”⁴⁴⁹ and “svá sagði/segir NAME”⁴⁵⁰ are both popular for one or more stanzas. A number of related formulations also occur: “sem NAME sagði/segir”⁴⁵¹ and “svá sem segir NAME”⁴⁵² occur a handful of times, whereas “svá kvað NAME”⁴⁵³ and “svá sem NAME segir”⁴⁵⁴ occur just once each. The formulas can be used either in a blunt manner, where they and their stanzas are simply stated without any concern for narrative flow, or blended neatly into the prose, as in chapter 27 before stanza 127: “Níundu orrostu átti hann við Nýjarmóðu, ok segir Sighvatr, at hann barðisk þá enn við Dani” [‘The ninth battle he fought by Nýjamóða, and Sighvatr says that he was fighting against the Danes again then’].⁴⁵⁵ More strangely inserted is stanza 108. It is introduced with the phrase “Þetta orð váttaði Hallfrøðr á þá lund” [‘These words Hallfrøðr attested in this way’]⁴⁵⁶ in the

⁴⁴⁷ Such stanzas occur at p. 88 stt. 43-45; p. 120 st. 84; p. 239 st. 195; p. 305 st. 256; p. 308 st. 258.

⁴⁴⁸ Such stanzas occur at p. 109 st. 69; p. 115, st. 79 (also explains the content of the verse on p. 116 “Svá mikit var manfall, at hér segir, at jarlinn gengi at manna höfðum af þessum fundi”); p. 116 st. 80; p. 118 st. 81; p. 119 stt. 82-83.

⁴⁴⁹ Such stanzas occur at pp. 91-92 stt. 48-51; p. 94 stt. 52-54; p. 101 stt. 64-65; p. 139 stt. 96-98; pp. 141-144 stt. 99-104; p. 148 st. 105; p. 152 st. 152⁴⁴⁹ (an uncertain categorisation); pp. 155-156 stt. 110-112; p. 164 st. 122; pp. 167-168 st. 124; p. 168 st. 125; p. 169 st. 126; p. 173 st. 128; p. 180 st. 136; p. 194 st. 54; p. 201 st. 161; p. 207-8 st. 164; pp. 222-223 st. 175; p. 225 st. 179; pp. 227-228 st. 183; pp. 240-241 stt. 196-198; p. 253 st. 207.

⁴⁵⁰ Such stanzas occur at p. 163 st. 121, p. 166 st. 123⁴⁵⁰; p. 181, st. 137; p. 198 st. 158; p. 199 st. 159; p. 208 st. 165; p. 216 st. 172; p. 219 st. 173; p. 222 st. 174; p. 223 st. 176; p. 224 stt. 177-178; p. 225 st. 181; p. 238, st. 194; p. 256 st. 213; p. 258 st. 216; pp. 260-261 st. 218; pp. 265-266 st. 224; p. 267 st. 226; p. 267 st. 227; p. 268 st. 228; p. 268 st. 229; p. 303 st. 254; p. 317 st. 261; p. 319 st. 262; p. 325 st. 263; p. 325 st. 264; pp. 326-327 st. 265; p. 330 st. 268.

⁴⁵¹ Such stanzas occur at p. 111 st. 70; p. 113 st. 74; p. 113 stt. 75-76; p. 231 st. 186; p. 234 st. 188; p. 264 st. 221.

⁴⁵² Such stanzas occur at p. 108 stt. 67-68; p. 114 stt. 77-78 (introduced with “Svá er sagt, at sjau tignir men fylgðu hönun, svá sem segir Einarr”); p. 266 st. 225.

⁴⁵³ Occurs at p. 157 s. 113.

⁴⁵⁴ Occurs at p. 158 st. 114.

⁴⁵⁵ *Fagrskinna*, p. 169 st. 127. Trans. Finlay, p. 135. See also *Fagrskinna* p. 180 st. 136.

⁴⁵⁶ *Fagrskinna*, p. 152 st. 108. Trans. Finlay, p. 122.

middle of a passage reporting the king's speeches. These stanzas are not reacted to in the prose,⁴⁵⁷ and while they may be of more than one stanza, do not have connecting prose between them.⁴⁵⁸

Another relatively straightforward type of introduction gives more information about, for example, the name of the poem or who it was composed about. We find simple evidence stanzas (occurring individually or in groups) with the name of the poet and who he composed the poem about in the prose⁴⁵⁹ and simple evidence stanzas with the name of the poet and the poem.⁴⁶⁰ These stanzas, or groups of stanzas, do not have any prose between multiple stanzas that are quoted, although extra information may be provided in the accompanying prose, for example by providing the name of the son of the poet.

I term 'complex evidence stanzas' those stanzas that clearly work in an evidentiary role in the narrative but are not as simple in prosimetric construction as straightforward quotations. Such complex quotations typically have prose inbetween the stanzas. An introduction can name only one poet. We find the formula "svá sem segir NAME" on pp. 59-63, where we have the pattern: [prose] stt. 1-6 [prose] stt. 7-11 [prose]. There is also extra information given about the poet: "gamall vinr konunga, er jafnan hafði í hirðum verit frá barnæsku" ['an old friend of kings who had been in courts constantly since his childhood']⁴⁶¹ in the first piece of prose, as well as the

⁴⁵⁷ Although note p. 99 stt. 61-62: this verse has consequences: "Hér fyrir gaf Haraldr konungr Eyvindi banasök" – and he must buy his head a second time with a verse p. 100 st. 63 – so it is clear that this verse is also used as reported speech, even though it is introduced as an evidence stanza.

⁴⁵⁸ The remaining stanzas in this selection are p. 238, st. 193 "þat segir Stúfr enn blindi"; p. 245, st. 201 "Þetta sannar Þolverkr, bróðir Þjóðólfs skálds"; p. 306 st. 257 "svá segir skáldit"; p. 341 st. 272 "svá sem vátar Einarr Skúlason" (cf. st. 269).

⁴⁵⁹ Such stanzas occur at: p. 129-130 stt. 87-89 "Þetta segir Þórðr Kolbeinssonr í kvæði, er hann orti um Eirík jarl"; p. 138 st. 95 "svá sem segir í kvæði því, er orti Eyjúlfr dáðaskáld um Eirík" (immediately after p. 139: "Þetta er tallit et fyrsta fra<ma>verk Eiríks í hans sögu"); p. 191-193 stt. 150-153 "Í frá þessi ferð Knúts konungs segir Þórarinn loftunga í kvæði því, er hann orti um Knút konung"; p. 195 st. 155 "Svá segir í kvæði því, er orti Bjarni gullbráskáld um Kálf Árnason"; p. 227 st. 182 "sem segir Valgarðr á Velli, er orti um Harald"; p. 279 st 237 "svá segir Steinn" st. 237 "Þetta orti hann um Ólaf...."

⁴⁶⁰ Such stanzas occur at: pp. 65-66, stt. 16-17: "Svá segir Eyvindr skáldaspillir, faðir Háreks í Þjóttu, í kvæði því er kallat er Háleygjatal" (gives extra information about poet – his son's name); p. 102 st. 66 "Synir Eiríks drápu ok Tryggva Ólafsson ok marga aðra konunga ok jarla ok aðra ríkismenn, sem Glúmr Geirasonr segir í Gráfeldardrápu, er hann orti um Harald konung" (gives extra info about the poem – who he composed it about).

⁴⁶¹ *Fagrskinna*, p. 59. Trans. Finlay p. 43.

introductory phrase. It also comments after the stanzas on what they show: “Hér þat sýnt í þessi frásögu, hvern siðr var Haralds konungs þá hríð, er hann ruddi ríki fyrir sér” [‘It is shown in this narrative what the custom of King Haraldr was at the time when he was conquering the kingdom’].⁴⁶² Although it does not name the poem, in the prose after the 6 stanzas it does acknowledge that the following group of stanzas are from the same poem “Þetta er enn kveðit í sama kvæði ok spurt á þessa lund eptir mildin hans” [‘The same poem goes on to ask in this fashion about his generosity’].⁴⁶³ Again after the second block of stanzas, stt.7-11, it is explained what is proved by these stanzas: “Þetta ber vitni mildi konungs” [‘This bears witness to the king’s generosity’].⁴⁶⁴ In addition to authenticating the narrative, this occurrence of prosimetrum demonstrates how self-conscious the use of verse can be by the saga author, and the statement of what the verse is evidence of shows how seriously these authenticating statements were taken in terms of the validation of narrative construction.⁴⁶⁵

Occuring on nine occasions in *Fagrskinna* are units of complex evidence stanzas with multiple stanzas cited. A number of these units of stanzas with prose inbetween have the same poet cited as the author of all of the stanzas. An extreme example of this is in chapter 57, pp. 271-273 stt. 230-234: “sem segir Þjóðólfr ” st. 230 “...svá segir Þjóðólfr ” st. 231 “...Frá því segir enn Þjóðólfr... ” st. 232 “...svá segir Þjóðólfr ” st. 233 “...sem segir Þjóðólfr ” st. 234.⁴⁶⁶ A typical example of complex evidence stanzas citing

⁴⁶² Trans. Finlay p. 44.

⁴⁶³ *Fagrskinna*, p. 61. Trans. Finlay p. 44.

⁴⁶⁴ *Fagrskinna*, p. 63. Trans. Finlay p. 45.

⁴⁶⁵ Other instances of complex evidence stanzas with one poet occur at: p. 95, st. 55 “Áðr en Hákon felli, hǫfðu synir Haralds ens hárfagra átta orðit vǫpndauðir sem Eyvindr segir skáldaspillir ok kvað sem konungrinn kœmi til Valhallar, fyrir því at sá var átrúnaðr heiðinna manna, at allir þeir er af sárum ǫnduðusk skyldu fara til Valhallar” The stanza that follows, according to footnote 55 on p. 95, is lacking in the B redaction; and since this is a case of corresponding intertextuality in the same text (as evidence stanzas by nature repeat something that has gone before), it seems reasonable that it could be excluded without harming the narrative understanding; pp. 241-242 stt. 199-200 comments after the stanzas on what the poem talks about: “sem Valgerðr segir ” stt. 199-200 “Hér segir, hversu Haraldr kom til Nóregs, frá því er hann fór ór landi út til Miklagarðs...”; p. 249 st. 202 comments after the stanzas on what the poem talks about “Þat segja allir menn á eina lund, at engi konungr hafi verit jafnvinsæll í Nóregi sem Magnús enn góði.”

⁴⁶⁶ Such stanzas also occur at: pp. 111-112 “svá sem segir Einarr” st. 71 “Þá var fríðr góðr með árinu, sem enn segir Einarr ” st. 72 “Í annarri drápu segir Einarr á þessa lund”; pp. 160-162 stt. 116-120 “Þetta vitni bar Hallfrøðr” stt. 116-117 “Ok enn kvað hann þetta” st. 118 “Ok enn kvað hann” st. 119 “Ok enn sagði hann st. 120”; p. 225 st. 180 (the run of stt. 179 to 181 is

multiple poets can be found on pp. 67-70, where it reads “svá sem segir NAME” stt. 18-22 “Hér minnsk NAME þessi orrostu” stt. 23-25. The corroborative function of the evidence stanzas is here strengthened by quoting two named poets.⁴⁶⁷ The title of the poem can also be stated within the unit of complex evidence stanzas. In chapter 29, the prosimetric section cites a number of stanzas and explains what the poem is talking about a number of times. In addition, the stanzas also more or less act as an explicit source for the prose.⁴⁶⁸ Likewise, there is one instance of an evidence stanza with the same poet and an anonymous poem cited multiple times in chapter 32, stt. 138-143: “...sem segir Sighvatr skáld í erfidrápu þeiri, er hann orti um Knútr gamla” [‘as the skald Sighvatr says in the memorial *drápa* that he composed for Knútr gamli (the Old)’]⁴⁶⁹ stt. 138-139 “Í þessi sǫmu drápu sagði Sighvatr frá norðanferð Óláfs konungs” [In this same *drápa* Sighvatr told of King Óláfr’s journey from the north’]⁴⁷⁰ stt. 140-143.⁴⁷¹ Here the existence of a long poem is acknowledged, which the prose may or may not cite all of (it does not commit either way).⁴⁷² Complex evidence stanzas also

accretative with the skald named each time and a separate introductory formula, each stanza is quite separate though); pp. 297-298 stt. 249-251 “sem segir Steinn” st. 249 “Þess minnsk ok Steinn...” st. 250 “Ok enn þetta” st. 251; p. 329 stt. 266-267 “Einarr Skúlasonar getr þess ok...” st. 266 “Enn segir Einarr svá” st. 267; pp. 337-338 stt. 269-271 “...svá sem vátta Einarr Skúlasonar” st. 269 “...Einar kvað þá vísu” st. 270 “Enn kvað Einarr aðra vísu.”

⁴⁶⁷ Such stanzas also occur at: pp. 120-121 “sem segir Einarr skálaglamm” st. 85 “Ok svá segir skáldaspillir” st. 86; pp. 186-187 stt. 144-146 “Svá segir Sighvatr” st. 144 “Þessar orrostu minntisk ok Óttarr, er hann orti um Knút” st. 145 „Þórðr Sjárekssonr orti erfidrápu um Ólaf konung ok gat enn þessar orrostu”; p. 230 stt. 184-185 “Svá sagði Þjóðólfr” st. 184 “Svá sagði Illugi Bryndælaskáld” st. 185 “Hér segir þat...” (afterwards it explains what the stanza is about); pp. 235-236 stt. 189-191 “Svá segir Þórainn í drápu sinni” st. 189 “Svá segir ok Þjóðólfr” (st. 190) “Valgarðr segir frá drápi varðmanna”; pp. 250-252 stt. 203-206 “Þá orti hann [Haraldr] vísu þessa ok Þjóðólfr” st. 250 “Þessar farar getr ok Þólverkr” st. 251 “Þá brenndi Haraldr konungr bœ Þorkels geysu, ok váru þá dætr hans leiddar bundnar til skipa. Þá var þetta ort” st. 205 (the prose after which there is an evidence stanza introduced with “svá sagði Grani skáld”) st. 206. On p. 253 the prose reacts to the last line of the st. 206, which “Svá hét dóttir Þorkels geysu” before moving on; p. 257 stt. 214-215 (with a group composed stanza) “Þá ortu menn hans þetta” st. 214 “Þessa minnsk ok Þorleikr fagri, þá er hann spurði, at Sveinn konungr var eigi kominn til móts við Harald konung ok eigi tekizk bardaginn við Elfina” st. 215; pp. 286-287 stt. 241-242 “svá segir Stúfr skald” st. 241 “En þetta kvað Arnórr jarlaskáld”; pp. 287-288 stt. 243-244 “Svá segir Arnórr” st. 243 “Í þessi dvöl, áðr en fylkingar gengi saman, orti Þjóðólfr vísu þessa”.

⁴⁶⁸ Pp. 174-177 stt. 129-135 “Sighvatr segir gǫrst frá þessum bardaga í Nesjavísium” st. 129 “...Sighvatr hefr svá Nesjavísur” st. 130 “Hér get þess, at þá váru þessi tíðendi ný orðin, er kvæðit var ort, ok sá orti sjálf, er í var bardaganum, ok í sama kvæði segir hann enn svá” st. 131 “Ok enn kvað hann þetta” st. 132 „Hér vísar til þess, er fyrr var sagt, ok enn kvað hann þetta” st. 133 “Ok enn kvað hann þetta” st. 134 „Þetta vísar til, at Þroendir höfðu svarit hǫnum eiða ok heldu eigi, því at þeir þorðusk í mót hǫnum með Sveini jarli, ok enn kvað hann þetta” st. 135.

⁴⁶⁹ Trans. Finlay p. 147.

⁴⁷⁰ Trans. Finlay p. 147.

⁴⁷¹ *Fagrskinna*, pp. 183-185.

⁴⁷² The reconstruction of poems from quotations such as these is an interesting topic, but outside the scope of the thesis.

need not have a name of poem nor even of poet, as the example in chapter two shows. The unit is introduced usually enough with “svá sem hér segir” in the prosimetric structure [prose] stt. 12-13 [prose] stt. 14-15 [prose].⁴⁷³ The second set of verses are more explicitly used a source rather than corroboration: stt. 14-15 (p. 64) are preceded by “Hér er ok sagt, at Haraldr konungr hafði leikara í hirð sinni” [‘Here it is also said that King Haraldr had a jester in his retinue’],⁴⁷⁴ and are followed by “Með þessu öllu verður hann ágætr ok haldsmar á sinni fõðurleifð” [‘In all these ways he became outstanding and secure in his patrimony’].⁴⁷⁵ In this manner, the unit switches from evidence verses to source verses at the end.

On several occasions the narrative does indicate explicitly that the verse is a source for the prose: in chapter 12, the prose is told “eptir því sem Eyvindr segir”⁴⁷⁶ [‘according to what Eyvindr says’].⁴⁷⁷ Elsewhere, the stanza is used as a source to contradict the fact the narrator (and thus saga author) has heard nothing else about the event: “ok er Sigvalda lítt við orrostuna getit, en þó segir Skúli Þorsteinssonar í sínum flokki, at Sigvaldi var þar”⁴⁷⁸ [‘and little is said of Sigvaldi in connection with the battle, and yet Skúli Þorsteinsson says in his *flokkr* that Sigvaldi was there’].⁴⁷⁹ This is probably also indicative that oral tradition played an important role in furnishing content for the narrative, both for prose and poetry.

The last type of evidence stanza used in a prosimetrum to mention is the evidence stanza that states its own authority. There are two of these in *Fagrskinna*. The first example is found in chapter 51 before stanzas 187, the prose insists on the

⁴⁷³ *Fagrskinna*, pp. 63-64.

⁴⁷⁴ Trans. Finlay p. 46.

⁴⁷⁵ Trans. Finlay p. 47.

⁴⁷⁶ *Fagrskinna*, p. 88 st. 42.

⁴⁷⁷ Trans. Finlay p. 67.

⁴⁷⁸ *Fagrskinna*, p. 154 st. 109

⁴⁷⁹ Trans. Finlay p. 123.

veracity of the source: “Svá segir Stúfr, er heyrt hafði Harald frá þessum tíðendum segja”⁴⁸⁰ [“So says Stúfr, who had heard Harald tell of these events”].⁴⁸¹ After the stanza, the prose goes on to explain what the verse tells us: “Hér segir frá því, at...” [“This verse tells us how that...”].⁴⁸² Stanzas in which extra veracity can be claimed, due to, for example, an eye-witness account, seem to have extra status in the narrative.

Another prosimetric context in which verse appears in *Fagrskinna* is that in which the origin of the poem is explained; either the event is given that the verse is explicitly said to commemorate, or the person who prompted the poem to be composed is mentioned. A typical example of the first kind is “Um þat orti Vígfúss Víga-Glúmsson” [‘About that Vígfúss Víga-Glúmsson composed’].⁴⁸³ This kind of introduction is relatively simple and differs from the regular introduction of evidence stanza because it does not explicitly identify the stanza as evidence, rather as the result of something the prose also reports.⁴⁸⁴ The other type of prosimetric circumstance in which the origin of the poem is explained concerns those poems that were specifically commissioned. For example, in chapter eight we find the pattern: [prose] stt. 27-34 [prose],⁴⁸⁵ where the first piece of prose is “Eptir fall Eíríks lét Gunnhildr yrkja kvæði um hann, svá sem Óðinn fagnaði honum í Valhöll, ok hefr svá” [‘After Eiríkr’s death Gunnhildr had a poem composed about him, as if Óðinn was greeting him in Valhöll, and it begins like this’].⁴⁸⁶ After the poem is quoted, it explains what the poems tells, and acknowledges its status as a source: “Hér segir þat, at fimm konungar fellu með

⁴⁸⁰ *Fagrskinna* p. 233 st. 187.

⁴⁸¹ Trans. Finlay p. 187.

⁴⁸² Trans. Finlay p. 188. For the other example of this kind of stanza, see pp. 264-265 stt. 222-223 “Svá segir Steinn Herdísarsonr, er þá var þar á skipi Úlfs” st. 222 “Steinn segir ok, hversu mikit lið hvárir höfðu” st. 223.

⁴⁸³ *Fagrskinna* p. 134 st. 92. Trans. Finlay p. 106.

⁴⁸⁴ Other such stanzas occur at: pp. 90-91 [prose] st. 46 [prose] st. 47 where the events are given then it is explained it gave rise to two stanzas, p. 90 “Um þetta orti síðan Eyvindr skáldaspillir” and then p. 90 “Aðra vísu orti hann um fall Eyvindar skreyju”; p. 151 st. 106 “Fyrir þessa sök kvað Stefnir þetta um Sigvalda”; p. 210 st. 166 “Um þetta orti Arnórr jarlaskáld”; p. 260 st. 217 “Um þetta orti Þorleikr”; p. 300 st. 253 “Til þess at eigi sé þetta lygi þá segir Arnórr jarlaskáld, hversu hann sat með Þorfinni jarli.”

⁴⁸⁵ *Fagrskinna*, pp. 77-79.

⁴⁸⁶ Trans. Alison Finlay p. 58.

hónum ok svá hvat mikill hermaðr hann hafði verit.” [‘Here it says that five kings fell with him, and also what a great warrior he was’].⁴⁸⁷ These quoted stanzas and their following prose analysis are also back up by another prose statement, where they are corroborated by another named poet, even those his verse is not quoted: “Svá segir ok Glúmr Geirasonr í sínu kvæði...” [‘Glúmr Geirason also says in his poem’].⁴⁸⁸ Although not very common in *Fagrskinna*, this prose introduction acknowledges the existence of deliberately composed poems that, although presumably memorized, would initially have been transmitted orally.⁴⁸⁹

The remaining stanzas in *Fagrskinna* are those that are speech stanzas rather than evidence stanzas. In the first type, the performance context of the stanza is also reported explicitly. A typical example is “Þá kvað hann þetta ok gekk fyrir konung” [‘Then he spoke this, going before the king’].⁴⁹⁰ Other extemporised speech stanzas function as part of a dialogue in the narrative; “Þá svaraði Eyvindr” is a typical example.⁴⁹¹ The short introductory tag can also give more information, such as that the speaker laughed while speaking. In this prosimetric context, the speech’s status as

⁴⁸⁷ *Fagrskinna* p. 79, trans. Alison Finlay p. 59.

⁴⁸⁸ *Fagrskinna* p. 79, trans. Alison Finlay p. 59.

⁴⁸⁹ Similar stanzas occur at: pp. 86-87 [prose] stt. 37-39 “sem Eyvindr segir í kvæði því, er hann orti eptir fall Hákonar, ok setti hann þat eptir því sem Gunnhildr hafði látit yrkja um Eirík sem Óðinn byði hónum heim til Valhallar, ok segir hann marga atburði í kvæðinu frá orrostunni, ok hefr svá:” (This is directly followed by the exchange between Eyvindr and king Hákon in the battle, pp. 87 stt. 40-41); p. 97 st. 58 “Þá váru þeir hræddir um Eyvindr vinir hans ok ætluðu, at konungurinn myndi láta drepa hann. Ganga til beggja vinir ok biðja konung fríðar ok segja, at Eyvindr má bæta á þá leið, sem brótit var ok biðja hann yrkja aðra vísu ok kaupa sér svá vináttu konungs.” This stanza does not have any other introductory phrase. (This is followed slightly later by a second attempt at reconciliation, see p. 98 st. 59.); p. 237 st. 192 “Í þessum ferðum orti Haraldr gamanvísur ok eru sextán ok eitt niðrlag at öllum. Þessi er ein”; pp. 213 stt. 167-171 “Þá orti Sighvatr flokk um Magnús konung, ok er þetta þar í” st. 167 “Þetta er ok þar í” st. 168 “Ok enn þetta” st. 169-171 (Then the prose is focused on the source value of this poem as advice to the king, on p. 215); pp. 253-255 stt. 208-211 “Þetta sumar kom útan af Íslandi Þorleikr fagri ok tók at yrkja um Svein konung flokk ok spurði, er hann kom til Nóregs, at Haraldr konungur var farinn suðr til Elfar í móti Sveini konungur. Þá orti hann þetta”; pp. 295-296 st. 248 “Hann var hirðmaðr Valbjófs jarls, ok orti hann kvæði eptir fall jarlsins, ok er þetta þar í.”

⁴⁹⁰ *Fagrskinna* p. 98 st. 59, trans. Alison Finlay p. 75. Similar stanzas occur at: pp. 95-96 stt. 56-57 “Þat lýsisk í orðaskipti þessa tveggja skálda. Glúmr Geirasonr kvað þetta” st. 56 “Þá er Eyvindr skáldaspillir heyrði þessa vísu, kvað hann í móti aðra” st. 57 (this is perhaps the only example in the text of a conversation in verse. Note that this has consequences, because he angers the king and must buy his life with a verse. See pp. 97-98, stt. 58-59); p. 277 st. 235 “Sá maðr kvað vísu þessa fyrir konunginum”; p. 277 st. 236 “ok kvað þetta” (this is said by a woman who appears in a dream); p. 299 st. 252 “Þar vikur Steinn svá málinu í sinni drápu”; p. 310 st. 259 (group composed) “kvaðu þeir þetta”; p. 313 st. 260 “En er liðit flýði frá Magnúsi konungi, kvað hann vísu þessa.”

⁴⁹¹ *Fagrskinna* p. 85, st. 36.

verse is not explicitly acknowledged.⁴⁹² The prose introducing other extemporised stanzas, however, acknowledges explicitly that the speaker is speaking in verse, for example “Þá orti Skúmr vísu.”⁴⁹³ Extemporised stanzas not introduced as verse or particularly said to be in verse.⁴⁹⁴

The last prosimetric context to be identified is one in which a verse is attributed to a character without the attribution being certain: “Þessi vísa er kennd Óláfi konungi” [“This verse is attributed to King Óláfr”].⁴⁹⁵ This stanza demonstrates the possibility that some skaldic stanzas are anonymous because they have lost the connection with their skald, rather than necessarily claiming anonymity for verse in skaldic form, as discussed above in the section on eddic and skaldic poetry.

As stated before, the building up of narrative units by citing multiple verses seems to be particularly important. Often this is done by citing multiple evidence stanzas. This accretive corroboration can be achieved by three methods:

- 1) by quoting more than one stanza in a block of stanzas
- 2) by quoting more than stanza interrupted by prose lines

⁴⁹² Such stanzas occur also at: “Hón svaraði á þessa lund” p. 75, st. 26; “Eyvindr segir” p. 84, st. 35; p. 87 “Í þessum þys kvað Eyvindr skáldaspillir einn gamankviðling til Hákonar konungs...” st. 40 “Þá svaraði konungr” st. 41 Then it acknowledges the source value of this exchange: “Á þvílíku má sjá, hversu óhræddr konungr var...” (p. 88)

“Þá kvað Eyvindr þetta” p. 100 st. 63 (when Hákon tell him to give him the Moldi); pp. 131-132 stt. 90-91: “Hann svaraði á þessa lund” st. 90 “Þá kvað hann ok þetta” st. 91; p. 135 st. 93 “Sá mælti þetta ok hló at” cf. p. 205 stt. 162-163 “Á þessa lund hefir sagt Sighvatr skáld”; pp. 255-256 st. 212 “Þá mælti Haraldr konungr til Þjóðólfs” (one line of stanza) “Þá svaraði Þjóðólfr” (rest of stanza); pp. 262-263 stt. 219-220 (performance context; also contains an attributed stanza) “Þá mælti konungrinn þetta, svá at margir heyrðu” st. 291 “Þat segja menn, at Haraldr kvæði ok þetta...” st. 220; p. 304 st. 255 “Þá mælti Þórir ok glotti við.”

⁴⁹³ *Fagrskinna* p. 137 st. 94.

⁴⁹⁴ Other stanzas acknowledging that a verse is extemporised are found at: p. 188 st. 147 “Hann orti vísu þessa”;

p. 189 st. 148 “...orti hann vísu”; p. 190 st. 149 “ok þá er hann spurði ætlan Knúts konungs ok Hákonar, orti hann þetta”; p. 197 st. 157 “Sá maðr hlaut at stýra Skeggjanum, er Jökull hét, ok hann orti vísu þessa”; p. 200 st. 160 “Haraldr svaraði ok kvað vísu”; pp. 284-285 stt. 239-240 (two poets) “...ok kvað þá þetta” and then “Þá orti Þjóðólfr þessa vísu.”

⁴⁹⁵ *Fagrskinna* p. 196 st. 156; trans. Alison Finlay p. 157. See also p. 284 st. 238 “Þat segja menn, at Haraldr konungr kvæði vísu þessa.”

- 3) by quoting another poem to corroborate the prose and what was said in the first place in verse

Additional information can also be added to these contexts. It is notable that this technique is much less common with speech stanzas. Verses approaching dialogue are found in one instance where characters share the speaking of a stanza: stanza 212 is shared “Þá mælti Haraldr konungr til Þjóðólfs” (one line of stanza) “Þá svaraði Þjóðólfr” (rest of stanza).⁴⁹⁶ In a second example, the second stanza quoted is said to be a direct reaction to the first: “Þá er Eyvindr skáldaspillir heyrði þessa vísu, kvað hann í móti aðra” [‘When Eyvindr skáldaspillir heard this verse, he spoke another in return’].⁴⁹⁷ Conversation in *Fagrskinna* takes place in prose, and the composition and expression of and in verse can be a self-conscious process. This might indicate that in the oral tradition(s) upon which *Fagrskinna* drew, dialogue in verse did not feature. Rather prose contexts for individual or connected stanzas were preserved; it could be that in those examples termed “complex evidence stanzas,” the prose between the stanzas is an oral connecting medium to build up units around which a prose written saga was then constructed. Although the prose inserts between verses may be oral in origin, this does not mean that the exact wording need be drawn directly from oral tradition, just the general idea. This type of construction avoids lengthy dialogues in skaldic verse whilst employing multiple stanzas in the favoured role as evidence verse.

⁴⁹⁶ *Fagrskinna* pp. 255-256.

⁴⁹⁷ *Fagrskinna* p. 96 st. 57.

Part Two: The Prosimetric Structure of *Gylfaginning*

From what can be judged from the work he left behind, Snorri Sturluson had intimate knowledge of both the oral and written traditions in medieval Iceland. The second part of the thesis presents a study of the prosimetrum of *Gylfaginning*, the first main part of *Snorra Edda*. The section identifies the roles that the eddic stanzas play in *Gylfaginning*. I have included *Gylfaginning* as an important comparative text to the *fornaldarsögur* because while it seems likely that many of the written prosimetric *fornaldarsögur* have an oral background, *Gylfaginning* must be thought of as an eddic prosimetrum belonging to the world of the written. Nevertheless, Snorri must have been fully versed in the Icelandic oral traditions of the 13th century, and much of what he put into *Gylfaginning* must have been drawn from oral tradition. Thus the written text of *Gylfaginning*, seemingly constructed on models including both vernacular wisdom contests and Latin-influenced school texts, employed this oral material to construct a text that must be viewed as belonging to written genre of the *Ars poetica*. I look at how the stanzas are introduced in *Gylfaginning* and whether the poem they are from is named (since most of them are quotations from poems extant in the *Poetic Edda*), and argue that, especially in relation to *Grimnismál*, that whether or not Snorri names a poem in the prose is quite deliberate. This suggests a writer who had his reader firmly in mind when constructing his text.

The majority of the eddic poems *Gylfaginning* draws upon are also found in a collection referred to as the *Poetic Edda*, in two manuscripts, as discussed above. The standard role of an eddic stanza in *Gylfaginning* is one that is quoted as evidence for something stated in the prose. These eddic stanzas are used as evidence stanzas in a similar way to the style found in the *konungasögur* as evidence verses, and yet, due to their metre and content, one should think they might be more aligned in nature and use with the *fornaldarsögur*.⁴⁹⁸ Deviations from this basic pattern are usually interesting and differ slightly from manuscript to manuscript, particularly in

⁴⁹⁸ See Bjarni Einarsson, "On the rôle of verse in saga-literature," esp. p. 124.

manuscript U which is abbreviated in comparison to manuscripts RTW (see below). This chapter covers the introduction of stanzas into the narrative of *Gylfaginning* and focuses on an analysis of whether excerpted poems are named in *Gylfaginning* and the patterns that arise from this, and the blocks that the verses form and how they guide the overall structure of the prose narrative.

Four manuscripts of *Snorra Edda* are held to have independent textual value (as far as *Gylfaginning* is concerned):

- R Codex Regius (*Snorra Edda*), GkS 2367 4to, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, Reykjavík, c.1325⁴⁹⁹
- T Codex Trajectinus, University Library Utrecht MS No. 1374, c. 1600⁵⁰⁰
- W Codex Wormianus, AM 242 fol. Det Arnamagnæanske Institut, Copenhagen, 1350⁵⁰¹

⁴⁹⁹ The manuscript R has 55 leaves, but lacks its first leaf and thus also the beginning of the prologue, to p. 5, l. 13 of Snorri Sturluson, *Edda: Prologue and Gylfaginning*. See also *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda: Ms. no 2367 in the old Royal collection in the Royal library of Copenhagen*, intro. Elias Wessén, Corpus codicum Islandicorum medii aevi 14 (Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1940) 5. After *Háttatal* are the poems *Jómsvíkingadrápa* and *Málsháttakvæði*, which are not considered part of *Snorra Edda* and are were perhaps copied there simply to use the space remaining the manuscript (*Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, ed. Wessén, p. 7). The manuscript was written around 1325 (*Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, ed. Wessén, p. 6). Although thought to be younger than the U manuscript of the *Edda*, it is nevertheless thought to be copied from an older exemplar, “which at any rate comes fairly near to the time of the original” and is considered by Wessén to come nearest to Snorri’s text (*Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, ed. Wessén, p. 6). The closest thing to a standard edition of this manuscript remains Finnur Jónsson’s edition, *Edda Snorra Sturlusonar* (København: Gyldendal, 1931), which uniquely preserves the spelling of the manuscript whilst offering a full treatment of textual variants in other manuscripts in distinct contrast to the normalising tendencies of previous and subsequent editions. (See Jørgen Rischel, “The Contribution of Scandinavian Neogrammarians,” *The Nordic Languages: An International Handbook of the History of the North Germanic Languages*, ed. Oskar Bandle, vol. 1, Handbücher zur Sprach- und Kommunikationswissenschaft 22.1 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2002)133-148, in particular 142.) However, as far as the 1931 edition goes, in cases where W, T or U have majority readings these are used in the main text and the R reading given as a variant, for example “eða” p. 17, l. 21 is in W and T, and R “ok” is provided as a variant in the apparatus. Faulkes also comments that the edition “has many inaccuracies and inconsistencies and is difficult to use” (*Edda: Prologue and Gylfaginning* xxxiii). Therefore for an exact reading of R, reference must be made to the 1940 facsimile edition of R *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, ed. Wessén.

⁵⁰⁰ T is thought to be a copy of a medieval manuscript that no longer survives (Faulkes, *Edda: Prologue and Gylfaginning* xxix). It too lacks the beginning of the prologue, to p. 3, l. 33 of Snorri Sturluson, *Edda: Prologue and Gylfaginning*, and also the end of *Háttatal*. The standard edition of T is W. van Eeden’s diplomatic edition *De Codex Trajectinus van de Snorra Edda* (Leiden: Eduard Ijdo, 1913). The manuscript is available in facsimile edited by Anthony Faulkes, *Codex Trajectinus: the Utrecht Manuscript of the Prose Edda*, Early Icelandic Manuscripts in Facsimile 15 (Copenhagen: 1985).

⁵⁰¹ The interpolations, abbreviations and adaptations found in the Codex Wormianus (Ormsbók) means that is generally held to be of secondary importance to the Codex Regius manuscript, which seems to have the “best” manuscript of *Snorra Edda*. However, these differences in the use of *Snorra Edda* in W compared to manuscripts R, T and U simply highlight the thoughtful engagement with the intellectual life of the mid fourteenth century that the collection of texts in W testifies to. Sigurður Nordal in his introduction to the facsimile dates the manuscript to 1360, see Sigurður Nordal, introduction, *Codex Wormianus : Ms. no.242 fol. in the Arnarnagæan collection in the University library of Copenhagen*, Corpus codicum

U Codex Upsaliensis, University Library Uppsala DG 11 8vo, early fourteenth century⁵⁰²

Earlier work on the history of the manuscripts⁵⁰³ has prioritised establishing the significance of each manuscript in relation to the others in conjunction with assessing *Snorra Edda*'s textual history.⁵⁰⁴ In this discussion the U version naturally plays an important role, since it is so different to the other redactions, and conclusions tend to be either centred around the idea that either U is a condensed version of the Codex Regius *Edda*, or that the Codex Regius *Edda* is an expansion of U. This is held to be of importance because whichever is the earlier work is the one closest to Snorri's original text.

One school of thought has held U to be closer to Snorri's original, a view that finds its roots in the work of Karl Müllenhoff,⁵⁰⁵ and followed by Eugen Mogk⁵⁰⁶ and

Islandicorum medii aevi 2 (Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1931) 16; most others generally date it to 1350. There are two codicological layers to this manuscript: the medieval pages from c.1350 and paper leaves inserted in the 17th century in order to complete the text. The standard edition of W is *Edda Snorra Sturlusonar: Codex Wormianus, AM 242, Fol.*, ed. Finnur Jónsson (København: Gyldendal, 1924). Neither the diplomatic edition nor the facsimile include all the material or pages that are present in AM 242 fol.

⁵⁰² U is a vellum manuscript housed in the University Library Carolina Rediviva in Uppsala. It was written in the first quarter of the 14th century as dated by its handwriting (Gothic), orthography and word forms. The manuscript itself is discussed most recently in Snorri Sturluson, *The Uppsala Edda: DG 11 4to*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, trans. Anthony Faulkes (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 2012) pp. xxx-xxxii, and see xxxiv-xli for a discussion of the paper copies of U. U lacks the *þulur* present in R and T at the end of *Skáldskaparmál* and its version of *Gylfaginning* lacks the first paragraph and the end of the last paragraph as found in the RTW, but it also has a quite different text overall from RTW. The material is briefer, sometimes concise to the point of being almost nonsensical, rearranged in order or simply lacking. *Háttatal* is incomplete. Additional material included in the material extraneous to the *Edda* includes a version of *Skáldatal*, a genealogy of the Sturlung family, a list of Icelandic lawspeakers and a version of the second *Grammatical Treatise*. It is notable that this material has strong connections to Snorri himself: a version of *Skáldatal* also appears in *Heimskringla*, which Snorri is also thought to have composed, Snorri belonged to the Sturlung family and the list of lawspeakers ends with his name. Although it is impossible to say whether these come from Snorri's papers, as Faulkes has pointed out, they certainly reflect his interests. (*Edda: Prologue and Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, xxx.)

⁵⁰³ For an overview of the scholarship covering the relationships of the manuscripts, see Lindow, "Myth and Mythography," p. 35.

⁵⁰⁴ Cf. Lindow, "Myth and Mythography," p. 35. See also Thomas Krömmelbein, "Creative Compilers: Observations on the Manuscript Tradition of Snorri's *Edda*," *Snorrastefna 25.-27. júlí 1990*, ed. Úlfar Bragason, Rit Stofnunar Sigurðar Nordals 1 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Sigurðar Nordals, 1992) pp. 113-129.

⁵⁰⁵ Karl Müllenhoff, "UUára und uara," *Zeitschrift für deutsches Altertum und deutsche Literatur* 16 (1873): 148-156, at p. 152.

⁵⁰⁶ Eugen Mogk, "Untersuchungen über die Gylfaginning, 1-2," *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache und Literatur* 6: 477-537; 7:203-318 (1879-80); "Zur Bewertung des Cod. Upsaliensis der Snorra-Edda," *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache und Literatur* 49 (1924-1925): 402-415.

Friedrich Wilhelm Müller.⁵⁰⁷ Opposing this view are those of Finnur Jónsson⁵⁰⁸ and R. C. Boer,⁵⁰⁹ who argue that the manuscripts preserving the longer version of the text, in particular R, have the version of the text closest to Snorri's original. Rasmus Kristian Rask suggests that the Uppsala Edda is an epitome of the other versions (note he did not know the Utrecht version), and thus was the latest of the complete versions of the *Edda*.⁵¹⁰ Delmar Olof Zetterholm argues for a middle way,⁵¹¹ and suggests that Snorri's own text could have been between the shorter and longer versions, and furthermore that Snorri may himself have prompted the two redactions. Baetke, on the other hand, concludes that the differences between the Codex Regius version(s) and U are a result of two different redactions, but that the differences in the Codex Regius version were the result of a later redactor.⁵¹² Most recently, Heimir Pálsson states the scholarly consensus (with which he agrees) to be "DG 11 4to is not the original, not even a copy of the original."⁵¹³ Heimir Pálsson has argued that for a third possibility, that is that Snorri made two original versions, one of which is reflected in the Codex Regius group, the other in U.⁵¹⁴

⁵⁰⁷ Friedrich Wilhelm Müller, *Untersuchungen zur Uppsala Edda* (Dresden: M. Dittert, 1941).

⁵⁰⁸ Finnur Jónsson, "Edda Snorra Sturlusonar: Dens opprindelige form og sammensætning," *Aarbøger for nordisk oldkyndighed og historie* (1898): 283-357; "Indledning," *Edda Snorra Sturlusonar*, ed. Finnur Jónsson (Copenhagen: Gyldendal, 1931).

⁵⁰⁹ R. C. Boer, "Studier over Snorra Edda," *Aarbøger for nordisk oldkyndighed og historie* (1924): 145-272; "Studien über die Snorra Edda: Die Geschichte der Tradition bis auf den Archetypus," *Acta Philologica Scandinavica* 1 (1926-1927): 54-150.

⁵¹⁰ *Snorra-Edda ásamt Skáldu og þarmeð fylgjandi ritgjörðum*, ed. Rasmus Kristian Rask (Stockholm, 1818) pp. 8-9.

⁵¹¹ Delmar Olof Zetterholm, *Studier i en Snorre-text: Tors färd till Utgård i Codices Upsaliensis DG 11 4^o*, Nordiska texter och undersökningar 17 (Stockholm: Geber; Copenhagen: Munksgaard: 1949).

⁵¹² Walter Baetke, *Die Götterlehre der Snorra-Edda*, Berichte über die Verhandlungen der sächsischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Leipzig, phil.-hist. Kl., 97.3 (Berlin: Akademie Verlag, 1950) p. 234.

⁵¹³ *The Uppsala Edda*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, p. xxxiii.

⁵¹⁴ *The Uppsala Edda*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, p. xliiii; Heimir Pálsson, "Tertium vero datur: A study of the text of DG 11 4to," (2010) <<http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:uu:diva-126249>>

The Order the *Edda* Was Written In

Stephen Tranter summarises his article “Das Háttatal von Snorri Sturluson, mündlich trotz Schriftlichkeit?” by saying that “Snorri felt obliged to follow patterns set by the written Latin tradition wherever possible, but that he was prevented from doing so throughout the tract by the strength of the pre-existing oral skaldic tradition.”⁵¹⁵

Whilst this may be true for most of the *Edda* in its skaldic sections, in the eddic part of the *Edda*, *Gylfaginning*, it is useful to consider whether we might be able to observe influence from the eddic oral tradition, as far as it can be judged, seeing as the section is built from eddic stanzas, and indeed, this does seem to be the case. As Tranter argues, the influence from the written Latin tradition is strong, likely from the dialogue form of Latin textbooks, but that the eddic situation of a wisdom contest, known from *Vaffrúðnismál* and *Grímnismál* in particular, also noticeably contribute to the structure of the section and inform its prosimetrum.

Here, I attempt to discern my approach to *Gylfaginning* as a mythological text as a whole, and its relationship to both the rest of the *Edda* and to eddic poetry. Guðrún Nordal has made the clear statement that “The different components of the *Edda* are generically different,”⁵¹⁶ and here I suggest how these different sections fit together and how the process of the composition of the *Edda* perhaps occurred. I point to a few elements that might suggest that *Gylfaginning* as a part of the *Edda* could have been written first rather than last, as has been generally accepted since Wessén’s article in the 1940s,⁵¹⁷ and contend that skaldic poetry as a subject of the text was a secondary thought or development. Although skaldic poetry is certainly not of secondary importance to the *Edda* as it now stands, it is possible that the initial idea behind what became the *Edda* was to present quotations of eddic poetry in a narrative form in a

⁵¹⁵ “Das Háttatal von Snorri Sturluson, mündlich trotz Schriftlichkeit?” *Snorri Sturluson: Kolloquium anlässlich der 750. Wiederkehr seines Todestages*. Ed. Alois Wolf. ScriptOralia 51. Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag, 1993. Pp. 179-192.

⁵¹⁶ Guðrún Nordal, *Tools of Literary*, p. 43.

⁵¹⁷ The view has made its way into general handbooks, e.g. “edda,” *The Penguin Dictionary of Literary Terms and Literary Theory*, J. A. Cuddon, rev. C. E. Preston, 4th ed. (London: Penguin, 1998) 249.

manner inspired by Latin grammatical literature, *konungasögur* and the prose associated with eddic poetry (in either its written or oral form).

Snorra Edda is understood in scholarly literature as the product of an antiquarian aspiration to conserve the art of skaldic poetry and to record the mythological beliefs held in pagan times in a coherent fashion in order to provide context for the kennings and myths told in relation to the skaldic verse.⁵¹⁸ This belief stems from Snorri's following statement in *Skáldskaparmál*:

En þetta er nú at segja ungum skáldum þeim er girnask at nema mál skáldskapar ok heyja sér orðfjöldá með fornum heitum eða girnask þeir at kunna skilja þat er hulit er kveðit: þá skili hann þessa ból til fróðleiks ok skemtunar. En ekki er at gleyma eða ósanna svá þessar sögur at taka ór skáldskapinum for[nar ke]nningar þær er höfuðskáld hafa sér líka látit.⁵¹⁹

But these things now have to be told to young poets who desire to learn the language of poetry and to furnish themselves with a wide vocabulary using traditional terms, or else they desire to understand what is expressed obscurely. Then let such a one take this book as scholarly enquiry and entertainment. But these stories are not to be consigned to oblivion or demonstrated to be false, so as to deprive poetry of ancient kennings which major poets have been happy to use.⁵²⁰

From this perspective, the purpose of including the mythological material in the *Edda* is somewhat secondary to the main point of preserving the skaldic tradition, as Kevin J. Wanner's comment exemplifies: "It does seem clear that his [Snorri's] chief wish was to promote the continued production and appreciation of skaldic verse, and that the mythological material...was included mainly to provide needed background for the comprehension and crafting of this poetry,"⁵²¹ since, as E O G Turville Petre writes, "Scaldic poetry was dependent upon the Eddaic. No one could understand the scaldic kennings unless he knew the myths and legends to which scalds alluded. These myths and legends lived in their most coherent form in the Eddaic lays."⁵²² As the quotation

⁵¹⁸ Another less common approach has been that of the *Edda* in relation to cultural capital. Kevin J. Wanner argues, somewhat differently, that "Snorri was not invested in skaldic verse on antiquarian grounds, but rather he strove through the creation of a novel literary product to preserve the capacity of this ancient art form to function as a marker of social prestige and tool of political power in the present." See Wanner, *Snorri Sturluson and the Edda*, p. 8.

⁵¹⁹ Snorri Sturluson, *Háttatal*, ed. Faulkes, p. 5.

⁵²⁰ *Snorri Sturluson: Edda*, trans. Anthony Faulkes, Everyman (London: J. M. Dent, 1987) 64.

⁵²¹ Wanner, *Snorri Sturluson and the Edda*, p. 6.

⁵²² Turville-Petre, *Origins of Icelandic Literature*, p. 38; Lindow, "Myth and Mythography," p. 28. Cf. Kuhn, "Heldensaga vor und außerhalb der Dichtung."

from Wanner demonstrates, the association of the *Edda* most strongly with skaldic poetry, even though that it could not be understood except by reference to the eddic tradition, has led to the importance of eddic poetry in the composition of the *Edda* to be given a back seat.

It is this assumption of the secondary nature of *Gylfaginning* for the point of Snorri's *Edda* that leads Elias Wessén to ask in 1940: "Why does Snorri's poetics embody precisely the works that it actually does? How is it that he begins with a mythology, and passes on to stylistics and metrics? Can Snorri be imagined to have had this plan before him already from the beginning?"⁵²³ In other words, when the main focus of *Snorra Edda* is on "stylistics and metrics" of skaldic poetry, why does the work begin with *Gylfaginning*? Wessén's response to this has become the standard view: he concludes that Snorri wrote the *Edda* in the reverse order in which the parts are found today, that is *Háttatal*, *Skáldskaparmál*, *Gylfaginning*, and then *Fórmáli*. It is worth citing Wessén's summary of his theory at length:

For in Norway the [skaldic] art had died out, but in the court circles in which Snorri moved there was doubtless a great interest in this old kind of poetry that still survived in Iceland – just as there was also a lively interest in the contemporary romantic and legendary European literature. It made Snorri desirous of surpassing all earlier skalds in a panegyric which was to give examples of all known metres.

While writing the commentary on *Háttatal* it became clear to him that there was much more that a skald should know. He then conceived the idea of writing *Skáldskaparmál*, and later *Gylfaginning*. Indeed it seems improbable that he should have proceeded in any other order during the composition. That he should have begun by writing a mythology when it was his intention to write a manual for skalds would be quite incomprehensible. On the other hand, it is only natural that later on, when the work was completed, the most entertaining part, *Gylfaginning*, should be placed at the beginning.

The compilation of the large collection of 'kennings' and 'heiti' with examples from the poetry, which occur in *Skáldskaparmál*, must have taken a very long time. It was during this protracted work with the skaldic language that Snorri became more and more absorbed in the mythology and felt the need of a coherent exposition. *Gylfaginning* was likely the result of one continuous effort, whereas *Skáldskaparmál* was revised and enlarged on several occasions. A ground-work for the exposition of the skaldic language has come into existence just after the *Háttatal* commentary, but in its present form *Skáldskaparmál* is later than *Gylfaginning*.

It is evident that in the course of the work Snorri's interest underwent a considerable change, perhaps more than he himself was conscious of. He began as a theorist, analysing metres and arranging his collections of 'kennings' and 'heiti'. But as the work progressed, he became more and more of a story-teller. He began as a scholar, but he finished as an artist.⁵²⁴

⁵²³ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 14.

⁵²⁴ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 32.

Wessén's vision of the process of composition is thus: that while *Háttatal* was being written, Snorri got the idea for *Skáldskaparmál*. While putting together *Skáldskaparmál*, Snorri got the idea for *Gylfaginning*, but, at some point, *Skáldskaparmál* was revised and edited to its present version after *Gylfaginning* was complete. Wessén's sequence, following Heimir Pálsson, can be summarised in order as: *Háttatal* > Commentary > *Skáldskaparmál*, first version > *Gylfaginning* > Prologue > *Skáldskaparmál*, second version. Heimir too finds this sequence unlikely.⁵²⁵

Wessén begins his discussion (not quoted above) by pointing out that the *Prologue* is an introduction only to *Gylfaginning*, and does not mention the *Edda*'s perceived purpose as a handbook for skalds, but, "it is, however, evident that the Prologue has been written last." He continues, "But it would then seem rather improbable that *Gylfaginning* should have been the first part of the *Edda* to be written."⁵²⁶ Given that the *Prologue* does not mention the *Edda*'s status as a handbook for poets, Wessén's suggestion that it was written last ought perhaps to be reconsidered. If were written last and written deliberately in order to front the text of the parts of *Edda* as it stands, its content would have probably reflected this. From this perspective, it seems more likely the *Prologue* was written first, with the content of only *Gylfaginning* in mind.⁵²⁷ It follows that *Gylfaginning* would have been written second, with a magnificent frame-story that comes to a natural end with the end of the story in *Gylfaginning*. Following this trajectory, it would have been at this point that *Skáldskaparmál* was added to the work, the frame story in it suggested by *Gylfaginning* as a logical way to proceed. Note too that that passage claiming that *Skáldskaparmál* is

⁵²⁵ *The Uppsala Edda*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, p. xxiv.

⁵²⁶ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 14.

⁵²⁷ Margret Clunies Ross points out that the Prologue is also relevant to *Skáldskaparmál* and *Háttatal* and that "its referential value for *Skáldskaparmál* and *Háttatal* as expositions of the language of the old religion should not be ignored." *Skáldskaparmál: Snorri Sturluson's ars poetica and Medieval Theories of Language*, The Viking Collection 4 (Odense: Odense University Press, 1987) 16. It could be noted that Snorri's authorship of the Prologue has been disputed: against Snorri's authorship see Andreas Heusler, "Die gelehrte Urgeschichte im altisländischen Schriftum" *Kleine Schriften*, ed. Stefan Sonderegger, vol. 2 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1940) pp. 80-161 at pp. 88, 99-108; Klaus von See, "Zum Prolog der Snorra Edda," *Skandinavistik* 20 (1990) 111-126. Margaret Clunies Ross, amongst others, has challenged von See in "Mikill Skynsemi er at Rifja Vandliga þat Upp: A Response to Klaus von See" *Saga-Book* 23 (1990): 73-79.

advice to younger poets refers back to the “beginning of the book,” which refers to the Prologue, for how Christians must not believe in heathen gods and how the stories ought to be understood.⁵²⁸ In the frame story found in *Skáldskaparmál*, Ægir and Bragi meet each other at a feast in Ásgarður, the content of which, as Wessén notes, was likely to have been suggested to Snorri by the frameworks of *Lokasenna* and *Hymiskviða*.⁵²⁹ Wessén must thus take the prose story of these poems to have been available in the oral tradition, since he earlier concludes that only *Völuspá*, *Vafþrúðnismál*, *Grímnismál* and perhaps *Hávamál* were available to Snorri in written form.⁵³⁰ However, the point of the section after *Gylfaginning* is to be, as Snorri more or less states and Wessén notes, an explication of skaldic, poetical usage, and “several myths which had not found room in the *Gylfaginning* are also included here,”⁵³¹ a statement in which Wessén implies that *Gylfaginning* must have come prior to *Skáldskaparmál* in Snorri’s thought sequence, and it would seem logically so. Otherwise, these myths that Wessén refers to (he does not identify them directly), might have entered *Skáldskaparmál* during one of Wessén’s proposed revisions of the section, but this does not seem to be the simplest solution.

It seems possible that *Gylfaginning* comes prior to *Skáldskaparmál* in the order of composition. *Skáldskaparmál* is likely to have been composed second, after *Gylfaginning*, its subject itself suggested by the eddic material found in *Gylfaginning*, the stories of which are necessary to understand skaldic kennings. This, and perhaps a desire to balance *Gylfaginning* with skaldic material, perhaps led to *Skáldskaparmál* being added to the *Prologue* and to *Gylfaginning* as a semi-fluid compilation, as the existence of other redactions of *Skáldskaparmál* that are preserved outside the *Edda* as whole demonstrate.⁵³² However, to build a comprehensive handbook of skaldic poetry

⁵²⁸ Cf. Clunies Ross, *Skáldskaparmál*, p. 16.

⁵²⁹ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 20.

⁵³⁰ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 9.

⁵³¹ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 11.

⁵³² Guðrún Nordal, *Tools of Literacy*, pp. 44-45.

was not the point of the *Edda* collection when it was begun, as the *Prologue*, whether it was written first or last, shows. The decision to switch from eddic to skaldic poetry and launch into a text intended for quasi-pedagogical purposes (entertainment and didacticism) likely led to the statement about the point of *Skáldskaparmál* being added and the composition of *Skáldskaparmál* in a frame story begun to ease the transition between eddic myth and skaldic peculiarities in the version of *Skáldskaparmál* transmitted in the context of the *Edda* as extant. However, the frame story is not so necessary to the point of the *Skáldskaparmál* as in *Gylfaginning*, and it peters out in *Skáldskaparmál* in favour of concentrating on the explication of kennings. Once again, Wessén contradicts his own argument that *Gylfaginning* was written after *Skáldskaparmál*: “The tale is obviously modelled on *Gylfaginning*. Like Gylfi Ægir is *fiðlkunnigr*. He set out for Asgard, but the Æsir saw his intention before he arrived and received him well, ‘and yet much was done by delusions’. Here these delusions are quite irrelevant for an invited guest. They are only remembrances from *Gylfaginning* and give evidence of the framework of *Skáldskaparmál* being indisputably a duplicate of that of *Gylfaginning*.”⁵³³ Margaret Clunies Ross also argues against a casual employment of the frame story in *Skáldskaparmál*, and points out that the dialogue between Ægir and Bragi helps “to advance Snorri’s main argument,” and are centrally relevant “and lead into Snorri’s presentation of the kenning system.”⁵³⁴ Wessén argues that the frame story of *Skáldskaparmál* was added to a revised version of the text,⁵³⁵ and must thus envisage this happening after *Gylfaginning* was complete. Since these inbetween revisionary periods of *Skáldskaparmál* cannot be known, it seems simplest to conclude that indeed the frame story of *Skáldskaparmál* was borrowed from

⁵³³ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 20.

⁵³⁴ Clunies Ross, *Skáldskaparmál*, p. 18.

⁵³⁵ Konráð Gíslason, “De ældste Runeindskrifters sproglige Stilling,” *Aarbøger for nordisk Oldkyndighed og Historie* (1869): 35-148.p. 21.

Gylfaginning, but that it was done so when the idea for the section of *Skáldskaparmál* arose and it had begun to be written.⁵³⁶

In Wessén's schema, *Háttatal*, a panegyric to King Hákon Hákonsson and Skuli Jarl with commentary on the metres employed, was written first. It has been argued by Konráð Gíslason that it was written in the winter of 1222-1223,⁵³⁷ upon Snorri's return from a trip to Norway during which he became friends with Skuli and admitted to the king's retinue. This indeed seems a logical motivation for such a praise-poem. However, the thorough exposition of metre in the poem as it stands makes it an obvious successor to *Skáldskaparmál*. Wessén points out that the 100th stanza is particularly proud of the skills *Háttatal* imparts:

Gløggva grein
hefi ek gert til bragar,
svá er tíróett hundrað talit;
hróðrs ørv<er>ðr
skala maðr heitinn vera
ef sá fær alla háttu ort.⁵³⁸

Close account have I given of poetic form so that ten tens are told. A man must not be called unworthy of renown if he is able to compose in all verse forms.⁵³⁹

This example of *ljóðaháttir* seems to reflect the statement in *Skáldskaparmál* about young skalds who wish to teach themselves the language of skaldic poetry: it could not be employed without equal ability in the skaldic metrical system. If the subject of *Háttatal* as a praise poem really was suggested by Snorri's trip to Norway in 1218-1220, then it is possible that *Gylfaginning* and *Skáldskaparmál* were written either before or directly after this trip, and perhaps when *Háttatal* was composed it was done so with a double aim in mind: a metrical exposition and a praise poem. It could be noted that the *Prologue* does not mention anything relevant to *Háttatal* either, in

⁵³⁶ This is not at odds with the fact that *Skáldskaparmál* is itself a compilation. As Guðrún Nordal says, "its rendering in the manuscripts shows that it originated, and continued to be perceived, as a *compilation* within the framework of *Snorra Edda*," *Tools of Literacy*, p. 43.

⁵³⁷ Konráð Gíslason, "De ældste Runeindskrifters sproglige Stilling," *Aarbøger for nordisk Oldkyndighed og Historie* (1869): 35-148. See also Wanner, *Snorri Sturluson and the Edda*, p. 28.

⁵³⁸ Snorri Sturluson, *Háttatal*, ed. Faulkes, p. 39.

⁵³⁹ *Snorri Sturluson: Edda*, trans. Faulkes, p. 220.

addition to ignoring *Skáldskaparmál*, as Wessén notes, and this is likely because when the *Prologue* was written, the idea for the two latter sections had not yet been conceived. Indeed it makes sense that *Háttatal* was written in 1222-1223, giving Snorri perhaps ample time to work on *Gylfaginning* and then *Skáldskaparmál* in the interim period between getting back from Norway and the point at which his political mission of subjecting Iceland to the Norwegian king had obviously failed in 1222-1223, and *Háttatal* could be, as Wessén suggests, “an unparalleled poetical achievement to make amends for his failure in this political mission.”⁵⁴⁰ However, another developmentary path is also possible.

The content of *Háttatal* as a praise poem is separable from the commentary, and could have been composed separately and added to the end of *Skáldskaparmál* when it became obvious that an account of skaldic metre was needed.⁵⁴¹ At this point, commentary could have been added to the already largely formed praise poem, and stanzas such as the 100th, quoted above, added at that point to underline the achievement of the poet in composing in so many forms, and pointing out to young skalds the honour they stood to gain should they master the art. That *Skáldskaparmál* and *Háttatal* as they stand are intended for pedagogical purposes is obvious, and the editing that *Skáldskaparmál* has undergone to form its various redactions indicates that this is likely to have taken place in an educational setting.⁵⁴² This section of the *Edda* had a life of its own outside the work as a whole, although the *Edda* seems to have been the original context for the piece.

Distinguishing between the genesis of the pieces and the genesis of the *Edda* as a collection is probably necessary. It seems that the *Prologue* and *Gylfaginning* were conceived of without the thought of making the work into an *ars poetica*, as they make no reference to such an aim. For this reason it is reasonable to suggest that they were

⁵⁴⁰ *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén, p. 15.

⁵⁴¹ Although see Faulkes in Snorri Sturluson, *Prologue and Gylfaginning*, p. xix.

⁵⁴² Guðrún Nordal, *Tools of Literacy*, p. 43.

written first, because if they were written with the intention to frame the mythological stories present in *Skáldskaparmál* and *Háttatal* as pedagogical works, they would be likely express this. *Skáldskaparmál* and *Háttatal* are explicitly pedagogical extensions of *Gylfaginning*, and could have possibly originated separately (especially *Háttatal*), but were nevertheless reformulated at an early stage to become parts two and three in *Snorra Edda*. As such, initially there was no “idea” behind the *Edda* as whole. Rather, *Edda* developed into an *ars poetica* rather than being designed as one.

It is eddic rather than skaldic poetry that could have possibly triggered the creation, or putting together, of the text that became the *Edda*. *Gylfaginning* was not thought of at first as an *ars poetica* as such, and likely began as an amusing tale, an attempt to write a *konungasaga*-style story that related history (from this perspective the *frá sagnir* episodes in *Gylfaginning* should be read as analogous to the *þættir* in the kings sagas), using eddic poetry since this conveyed the myths of the Æsir, and drawing the inspiration to cite these poems in a sustained prose narrative from the prose surrounding the eddic poems and from the *fornaldarsögur*. That Snorri chose the textbook dialogic style that is employed throughout the piece to begin with in *Gylfaginning* is likely because he wanted to demonstrate the lasting value and importance of the myths in Icelandic cultural heritage, and sought to formalise their expression in a format that carried authority and credibility. The several different versions of the *Edda* show that its construction and unity were not canonically fixed. Nevertheless, while I have outlined here some elements that might point towards *Gylfaginning* being composed first of all the *Edda* parts, ultimately it is an open question.

Vernacular and Latin Models for *Gylfaginning*

Here I would like to suggest that influence from learned texts that Snorri was exposed to orally or in written form is can be seen in the way that prosimetrum is used in *Gylfaginning*, as the narrative negotiates between two types of question and answer format: the native format found in the wisdom poems and the question and answer format of the educational texts of the time. The stimulus for the dialogue structure of *Gylfaginning* was from Latin pedagogical texts in which there was a dialogue between a student and a master. Guðrún Nordal summarises the situation particularly clearly:

Snorri Sturluson's narration in *Gylfaginning* is structured after the well-known model of didactical treatises in the Middle Ages, where the dialogue between a pupil and the master is used to explicate and present the matter at hand. In *Gylfaginning* the dialogue is carried out between the Swedish king Gylfi, disguised as an old man called Gangleri, and the three representatives of Óðinn: Hárr ('High'), Jafnhárr ('Just-as-High'), and Þriði ('Third').⁵⁴³

The intellectual or learned or Latinate background to *Snorra Edda* that sets the work against a background of Christian learning has long been explicated by scholars.⁵⁴⁴

Snorri's work comes out of the tradition of 12th century humanism,⁵⁴⁵ taught in

⁵⁴³ Guðrún Nordal, *Tools of Literacy*, p. 277. Margaret Clunies Ross has also drawn attention to the place of the Latin genre the *exemplum* in forming the fictions of the Edda; see "Snorri's Edda as Narrative," *Snorri Sturluson: Beiträge zu Werk und Rezeption*, ed. Hans Fix, *Ergänzungsbände zum Reallexikon der Germanischen Altertumskunde* 18 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1998) pp. 9-21, at p. 15.

⁵⁴⁴ For example, Heusler "die gelehrte Urgeschichte" (1908). See also Bætke, *Die Götterlehre der Snorra-Edda*; Ursula and Peter Dronke, "The Prologue of the Prose Edda: Explorations of a Latin Background," *Sjötiú ritgerðir helgaðar Jakobi Benediktssyni 20. júlí 1977*, ed. Einar G. Pétursson and Jónas Kristjánsson, vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1977) pp. 153-76; Ursula Dronke, "Classical Influences on Early Norse Literature" *Classical Influences on European Culture, AD 500-1500: Proceedings of an International Conference held at King's College, Cambridge*, ed. R. R. Bolgar (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1971) pp. 143-149; Anthony Faulkes, "Pagan Sympathy: Attitudes to Heathendom in the Prologue to *Snorra Edda*," <<http://www.vsnrweb-publications.org.uk/Pagan-sympathy.pdf>> [Originally published in *Edda: A Collection of Essays*, ed. Robert J. Glendinning and Haraldur Bessason, The University of Manitoba Icelandic Studies 4 (Winnipeg: University of Manitoba Press, 1983) pp. 283-314]; "The Sources of *Skáldskaparmál*: Snorri's Intellectual Background," <<http://www.vsnrweb-publications.org.uk/Sources-of-Skaldskaparmal.pdf>> [Originally published in *Snorri Sturluson: Kolloquium anlässlich der 750. Wiederkehr seines Todestages*, ed. Alois Wolf, *ScriptOralia* 51 (Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag, 1993) pp. 59-76]; Anne Holtsmark, *Studier i Snorres mytologi*, *Skrifter utgitt av det norske videnskabsakademi i Oslo*, 2. hist.-filos. kl., ny serie, nr. 4 (Oslo: Universitetsforlaget, 1964). Clunies Ross's book length study of *Skáldskaparmál* in 1987 demonstrates that Snorri's intellectual approach to his material was creative and yet to a large extent the "intellectual premises" (p. 174) from which he approached vernacular material were firmly based in medieval Latin traditions and particularly in 12th century humanism (p. 20).

⁵⁴⁵ See Vivian Law, *Grammar and Grammarians in the Early Middle Ages* (London: Longman, 1997); Martin J Ryan, "Latin Learning and Christian Art," *A Companion to the Early Middle Ages: Britain and Ireland c. 500-1100*, ed. Pauline Stafford, *Blackwell Companions to British History* (Malden, MA: Blackwell, 2009) pp. 177-192. That Icelandic writers could attain a firm grounding in the medieval grammatical tradition is evidenced by the existence of the First Grammatical Treatise, part of Europe's Twelfth-Century Renaissance, written by the unknown first grammarian who was well-versed in the learning of his time (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 73; Hreinn Benediktsson, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 33). Unusually, although the grammarian's "framework of technical terminology" is rooted in this European tradition of scholarship, his work dispenses with defining basic concepts, using traditional definitions or with quoting Latin

Iceland in the schools⁵⁴⁶ established by educated men who had often studied abroad,⁵⁴⁷ although the basic grammatical texts of Snorri's time were from late antiquity.⁵⁴⁸

It is not possible to identify with certainty individual works that may have influenced the *Edda*, since many of the ideas were commonplace in theological and educational texts,⁵⁴⁹ nor is it possible to claim that Snorri was even able to read Latin.⁵⁵⁰ The

grammarians as we might expect with comparison to other medieval grammatical works (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 5-6; Hreinn Benediktsson, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 41). Because of this, scholars have not agreed whom this textbook is aimed at. Anne Holtsmark suggests that the grammarian wrote the work to be used in his own school for those beginning clerical training, "det er en lærebok" (*En islandsk scholasticus fra det 12. Århundre*, Det Norske Videnskaps-Akademi i Oslo II. Hist.-Filos. Klasse 3 (Oslo: Jacob Dybwad, 1936) 89), but Haugen argues that the noted difference between this work and those by, for example, Donatus, Remigius, Ælfric (Ælfric wrote a grammar in the year 1000. It is a Latin grammar with interlinear Old English to aid neophyte priests (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 72)) and compilations like the *Auraicept* (The *Auraicept* is a large compendium of Latin grammarians and appears to be the first study of a Western European vernacular. It dates from the 7th century) makes this unlikely, since the writing is pitched rather at the level of speaking to a colleague than a pupil (*The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 5). Indeed, the usual medieval textbook format of expounding a subject by having a conversation between a master and a pupil (for example, in *The King's Mirror*), is not found in the FGT (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 5). Haugen gives the example of the Third Grammatical Treatise, written c. 1245 by Ólafr Þórðarson, to illustrate the difference: Ólafr ran a school at Stafaholt, and he starts with the basics in his treatise. He explains his terms and states his concepts. The first grammarian argues for his rules, the third grammarian simply states them, as is more suitable in a textbook aimed at the elementary learner. (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 5). Haugen concludes that the FGT was written by a scholar for other scholars, and was not an elementary textbook but was rather written to improve an already learned style (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 6).

⁵⁴⁶ Although relatively many learned Icelandic men travelled abroad for their education, in the early 12th century there were not a few opportunities to acquire a decent Latin/grammatical education in Iceland (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 76). The episcopal seats at Skálholt and Hólar and the monasteries at Þykkvibær, Þverá and Þingeyrar and the chieftain's farms at Oddi and Haukadal all had established schools (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 76). See also Björn M. Ólsen, *Den tredje og fjerde grammatisk afhandling i Snorres Edda*, Islands Grammatisk Litteratur i Middelalderen III-IV (Copenhagen: 1884) p. xx. See also Hermann Pálsson, *Oral Tradition and Saga Writing*, Studia Medievalia Septentrionalia 3 (Fassbaender: Wien, 1999) 22.

⁵⁴⁷ See Hermann Pálsson, *Oral Tradition and Saga Writing*, pp. 22, 27-29; Björn M. Ólsen, *Den tredje og fjerde grammatisk afhandling*, p. xviii; Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 72.

⁵⁴⁸ The European medieval grammatical tradition in which Iceland partook grew out of a tradition of grammatical studies dating back to antiquity. Donatus and Priscian became the two Latin grammarians whose works achieved widespread dissemination in medieval Europe and became the standard grammatical texts; see Hreinn Benediktsson, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, pp. 34-35, 54). Knowledge of the works of Donatus and Priscian, supplemented by for example the work of Remigius of Auxerre from the 10th century, would account for all the grammatical doctrine found in the FGT (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 73), and Clunies Ross concludes that Donatus was likely "the foundation of medieval Icelanders' knowledge of Latin stylistics" since there is no evidence of other classical rhetorical works (Cicero and Quintilian) but ample evidence that Donatus was known (*Skáldskaparmál* p. 24). Holtsmark has found echoes in the FGT of the teachings of Petrus Helie in Paris in c. mid 12th century, especially with regard to the harmonisation of the attributes (*En islandsk scholasticus*, p. 42). Other examples of Latin learning noted by Haugen include the Latin abbreviation for *et*, the use of *x*, *y*, and *z*, the terms *capitulum* and *vers* and the Latin quotation of Cato in a text written in the vernacular (Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 73). Although the first grammarian's learning is solid, it is not exceptional, and reflects what we could expect of a learned man of the mid-12th century. It has also been suggested that the first grammarian may have known other languages: Greek, Hebrew, Gaelic, English and French. Apart from English, these seem unlikely; see Haugen, *The First Grammatical Treatise*, p. 74-76 for an overview of this.

⁵⁴⁹ Clunies Ross, *Skáldskaparmál*, p. 13. Whether there were models for Snorri to follow is also doubtful, his seems to be a unique achievement in vernacular poetics. There seems to be no doubt however that *Háttalykill* demonstrates that there was an interest in the systemisation of vernacular poetics as early as c. 1140, and is as such a predecessor to *Háttatal* (see *Codex of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén p. 30; Guðrún Nordal, *Tools of Literacy*, pp. 32-35)

interplay between Latin and native learning found in Snorri's works is best summarised as a practice in which "communal ways of thought confined to oral expression were being invaded by impersonal literary methods which dictated new forms and at the same time fossilised older practices."⁵⁵¹ All the sections of the *Edda* show a fusion of Latin and native concepts in various ways,⁵⁵² and below I focus only the use of poetry in *Gylfaginning* to analyse Snorri's working method in that section.

The contours of Snorri's life have been traced many times,⁵⁵³ and here I will restrict myself to the briefest comments. Although from a powerful family himself, the context of Snorri Sturluson's learning is most probably his fosterage by Jón Loptsson, another powerful chieftain and a grandson of Sæmundr Sigfússon inn fróði. Snorri was brought up and educated at Oddi, Jón's family seat, "a literary and cultural centre" where presumably Snorri could have held conversations with learned men⁵⁵⁴ and would have had access to a sufficiently stocked library.⁵⁵⁵ Snorri seems to have begun his literary career a few years after returning to Icelandic from Norway and Västergötland in Sweden during 1218-1220, in which time he visited Hákon

⁵⁵⁰ Vésteinn Ólason in "Snorri Sturluson – tiden, mannen og verket," *Høvdingen: Om Snorre Sturlasons liv og virke*, ed. John Ole Askedal and Klaus Johan Myrvoll (Oslo: Vidarforlaget, 2008) pp. 21-40 argues that Snorri doubtless learnt some Latin, but Anthony Faulkes in "The Sources of Skáldskaparmál" does not think that Snorri necessarily knew Latin. Heimir Pálsson says "Snorri had only a limited amount of Latin," in *The Uppsala Edda*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, p. xxviii, see also xiv-xv.

⁵⁵¹ G. T. Shepherd, "The Emancipation of Story in the Twelfth Century," *Medieval Narrative: A Symposium* (Odense: Odense University Press, 1979) pp. 44-57, at 51.

⁵⁵² There are however certain differences between the narrative situation in each part. Where Wessén and I differ on this point is that he is more likely to assign the influence of school-books to only *Háttatal* and *Skáldskaparmál*, and he attributes the theme of *Gylfaginning* as having been borrowed from poems such as *Vafþrúðnismál* (see *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, ed. Wessén p. 22). Wessén notes that, regarding the question-and-answer situation in *Háttatal*, there "is not as in *Gylfaginning* a particular person who asks and who answers, nor is there any concrete situation which gives rise to the colloquy, it is merely a stylistic form of exposition. It recalls the Latin textbooks of the Middle Ages, in which the pupil puts the question and the teacher replies. And doubtless it had such a learned model," and he states that the exposition of *Skáldskaparmál* accords with *Háttatal* (see *Codex Regius of the Younger Edda*, intro. Wessén pp. 16, 87). See also Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 137.

⁵⁵³ Most recently in Snorri Sturluson, *The Uppsala Edda: DG 11 4to*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, trans. Faulkes, pp. xi-xii, xviii-xxiv; Wanner, *Snorri Sturluson and the Edda*, pp. 16-73, esp. 18-25, and references there.

⁵⁵⁴ For Oddi and learned traditions in Jón's family, see *The Uppsala Edda*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, pp. xii-xiii; Halldór Hermannsson, *Sæmund Sigfússon and the Oddaverjar*, *Islandica* 22 (Ithaca: Cornell UP, 1932); Helgi Þorláksson, "Snorri Sturluson og Oddaverjar," *Snorri: Átta alda minning* (Reykjavík: Sögufélag, 1979) pp. 53-88.

⁵⁵⁵ Lindow, "Myth and Mythography," p. 34.

Hákonarsson (king of Norway) and Hákon's uncle Jarl Skúli.⁵⁵⁶ The only statements to declare Snorri as author of the *Edda* are two rubrics in U:

Bók þessi heitir Edda. Hana hefir saman setta Snorri Sturluson eptir þeim hætti sem hér er skipat. Er fyrst frá ásum ok Ymi, þar næst skáldskapar mál ok heiti margra hluta. Síðast Háttatal er Snorri hefir ort um Hákon konung ok Skúla hertuga.⁵⁵⁷

Háttatal, er Snorri Sturluson orti um Hákon konung ok Skúla hertuga.⁵⁵⁸

I agree with Margaret Clunies Ross when she writes: “most of us who write about *Snorra Edda* probably use the name “Snorri Sturluson” as a kind of shorthand to refer to a shaping unity of purpose that we detect in the works attributed to man so named;”⁵⁵⁹ she also refers to ‘Snorri Sturluson’ as a shorthand for the “narrating voice” of the *Edda*.⁵⁶⁰

⁵⁵⁶ “Myth and Mythography,” p.34.

⁵⁵⁷ Snorri Sturluson, *The Uppsala Edda: DG 11 4to*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, trans. Faulkes, p. 6.

⁵⁵⁸ Snorri Sturluson, *The Uppsala Edda: DG 11 4to*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, trans. Faulkes, p. 262.

⁵⁵⁹ Clunies Ross, “‘Mikill Skynsemi er at Rifja Vandliga þat Upp’,” p. 75; Úlfar Bragason, “Snorri the Author,” *Snorri Sturluson and the Roots of Nordic Literature: Papers of the International Conference Held at “St. Kliment Ohridski,” University of Sofia (October 14-16, 2002) Dedicated to the 10th Anniversary of the Founding of the Scandinavian Studies in Bulgaria*, ed. Vassil Giuzelev et al. (Sofia: “St. Kliment Ohridski,” University of Sofia, 2004) pp. 35-41.

⁵⁶⁰ Margaret Clunies Ross, “Snorri’s *Edda* as Narrative,” p. 10.

Were Snorri's Eddic Sources Oral or Written?

Snorri's immense learning has in part come from books, and this is particularly true of the *konungasaga* material, and likely true for a few of the eddic and skaldic poems used by Snorri.⁵⁶¹ Vésteinn Ólason comments that Snorri's "comprehension of the material handed down by tradition and his immense knowledge must have deep roots,"⁵⁶² and it is likely that Snorri absorbed much of his learning from the community as whole. Nevertheless, Guðrún Nordal has demonstrated convincingly in her book *The Tools of Literacy* that the skaldic tradition was firmly linked to the education system in Snorri's time,⁵⁶³ but it is not clear that the eddic tradition was 'taught' in the same manner as Guðrún has argued the skaldic tradition to have been. Indeed, one can use the existence of the final form of *Snorra Edda* as evidence of this, and Heimir Pálsson suggests that the compilation of *Skáldskaparmál* may even have been part of Snorri's own studying of the tradition.⁵⁶⁴

Both eddic and skaldic verse and prose stories came down to Snorri through oral tradition, although it seems likely that he had written versions of some of the poems.⁵⁶⁵ Gustaf Lindblad suggests that Snorri used a pamphlet of two poems, *Vafþrúðnismál* and *Grímnismál* when writing his *Edda*,⁵⁶⁶ and thus that these poems used by Snorri had been put into writing before Snorri's time. As discussed above, this had earlier been suggested by Karl Müllenhoff, who believed the entire Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda* was the result of a combination of pamphlets containing poetry, a suggestion also put forward by Wessén;⁵⁶⁷ Heusler cautions against such a

⁵⁶¹ Lasse Mårtensson and Heimir Pálsson, "Anmärkningsvärda suspensioner i DG 11 4to (Codex Upsaliensis av Snorra Edda) – spåren av en skriven förlaga," *Scripta Islandica* 59 (2008): 135-155.

⁵⁶² Vésteinn Ólason, "Snorri Sturluson: tiden, mannen og verket," p. 26

⁵⁶³ *Tools of Literacy*.

⁵⁶⁴ *The Uppsala Edda*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, pp. xvii-xviii.

⁵⁶⁵ Sigurður Nordal, *Snorri Sturluson*; Gustaf Lindblad, "Poetiska eddans förhistoria och skrivskicket i Codex Regius," *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 95 (1980): 142-167.

⁵⁶⁶ Gustaf Lindblad, "Snorre Sturlasson och eddadiktningen." *Saga och sed* (1978): 17-34.

⁵⁶⁷ *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda*, intro. Elias Wessén, p. 21.

belief “in broadsheets with single poems” since written eddic collections were for antiquarian interests rather than for entertainment.⁵⁶⁸ In Lindblad and Müllenhof’s view, the *Snorra Edda* was thus not a prerequisite for the existence of the *Poetic Edda* collections, contrary to the views of other scholars, who hold that *Snorra Edda* in some way prompted the collection of the eddic poems,⁵⁶⁹ the major originators of this view being Heusler⁵⁷⁰ and Wessén.⁵⁷¹ Wessén, following Heusler contends that Snorri had *Völuspá*, *Vafþrúðnismál* and *Grimnismál* written down in order to aid him in writing *Gylfaginning*; these were thus the first eddic poems committed to writing. Following this, either Snorri himself, or educated men inspired by him, wrote down eddic poems on loose leafs, in no particular order, and those assembled in no particular order were the ancestor of manuscript A; further down the line, these were rearranged to form the Codex Regius manuscript.⁵⁷² Lindblad objects to Wessén’s prehistory of the Codex Regius because, as stated, he believes there were eddic poems written prior to Snorri; secondly, Lindblad’s investigations suggest that traces of older collections can be found in the Codex Regius, and thirdly because *Snorra Edda* and the *Poetic Edda* are independent interpretations and, in some cases recordings (as in the case of *Völuspá*), of the same material.⁵⁷³ Lindblad does however suggest *Snorra Edda* provided the impetus for making the larger mythic collection of poems between 1225-1240 (perhaps 1250), an unordered collection reflected in manuscript A. Following this, the mythic booklet was put with an heroic one and the mythological poems ordered at this point – the Codex Regius manuscript may be this manuscript or a later copy of it.⁵⁷⁴

⁵⁶⁸ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Andreas Heusler, p. 31.

⁵⁶⁹ Harris, “Eddic Poetry,” p. 75.

⁵⁷⁰ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Heusler.

⁵⁷¹ Elias Wessén, “Den isländske eddadikningen: Dess uppteckning och redigering,” *Saga och sed* (1947): 1-31.

⁵⁷² *Fragments of the Elder and the Younger Edda*, intro. Elias Wessén, pp. 20-21. For an overview of this, see Harris, “Eddic Poetry,” pp. 68-156, at 76.

⁵⁷³ Harris, “Eddic Poetry,” p. 76; Mundal, “Oral or Scribal Variation.”

⁵⁷⁴ Harris, “Eddic Poetry,” p. 76.

The Sources and Quotation of Eddic Stanzas in Gylfaginning

There have been several hypotheses regarding the sources of the prose explanations found in *Gylfaginning*, although it seems most likely that the prose of the *Edda* is a result of what Snorri knew from oral tradition and the deductions and links he made from and between his poetic sources when such cohesive factors were lacking in the tradition he was familiar with; in other words, it is a mixture of tradition and Snorri's aptitude in presenting and clarifying myth.⁵⁷⁵ Eugen Mogk's hypothesis was that Snorri invented any material in *Snorra Edda* not found in a poetic source.⁵⁷⁶ John Lindow links the prose that likely accompanied eddic and skaldic verse in oral tradition (*Begleitprosa*) with the explanations that Snorri gives of the stanzas he quotes, as if Snorri knew prose explanations of mythological and heroic allusions, he likely made use of them in his *Edda*, although Lindow points out that this cannot be proved, and that Snorri must have in any case faced some instances of unclear material which he attempts to homogenise and elucidate.⁵⁷⁷

Quotations of eddic poetry is used in an evidence based role in *Gylfaginning*, which "projects an oral world, and authority rests with the poetic discourse of supernatural figures which is represented as authorising the prose of the narrative text."⁵⁷⁸ Direct allusion or quotation of the type found in *Gylfaginning* is a particularly interesting form of intertextuality because it destroys the illusion of reality in the text and the suspension of disbelief:

This is a particularly self-conscious form of intertextuality: it credits its audience with the necessary experience to make sense of such allusions and offers them the pleasure of recognition. By alluding to other texts... this practice reminds us that we are in a mediated reality, so it can also be seen as an alienatory mode which runs

⁵⁷⁵ Cf. Frog, "Snorri *qua* Fulcrum: Perspectives on the Cultural Activity of Myth, Mythological Poetry and Narrative in Medieval Iceland," *Mirator* 12 (2011): 1-28 <<http://www.glossa.fi/mirator/pdf/i-2011/Snorriquafulcrum.pdf>>.

⁵⁷⁶ Eugen Mogk, *Novellistische Darstellung mythologischer Stoffe Snorris und seiner Schule*, Folklore Fellows Communications 51 (Helsinki: Suomalainen Tiedekatemia, 1923); *Zur Bewertung der Snorra-Edda als religionsgeschichtliche*.

⁵⁷⁷ Lindow, "Myth and Mythography," p. 36.

⁵⁷⁸ Clunies Ross, "Snorri's *Edda* as Narrative," p. 15.

counter to the dominant realist tradition which focuses on persuading the audience to believe in the ongoing reality of the narrative. It appeals to the pleasures of critical detachment rather than of emotional involvement.⁵⁷⁹

In the dichotomy of prose and verse in the work, the prose is signifier and the verse the signified. In *Gylfaginning*, this emotional peaking and troughing of the narrative is counteracted somewhat by occasional inserts of versified dialogue, throwing the receiver into a story-world reminiscent of a *fornaldarsaga*. This is probably not accidental: eddic verse as the words of gods is fitting enough, and the dialogue provides a welcome break in the narrative from the positive verse as quoted as evidence to the prose tales.

Manuscripts RTW have 71 verses embedded into their prose, two of which are skaldic⁵⁸⁰ and sixty nine in eddic metres. Manuscript U has substantially fewer, with 61 verses present. Of the ten verses in RTW that do not appear in U, one is skaldic (a stanza from *Ragnarsdrápa*, the first verse that RTW quote) but the rest eddic: two non-consecutive verses of *Vafþrúðnismál* (stanzas 30 and 18), *Skírnismál* stanza 42, and six stanzas of *Völuspá* that are quoted in *Gylfaginning* in RTW are not present in U. U does not have any additional stanzas to those also appearing in RTW, but there are variations, usually minor, between the verses as they appear in the four manuscripts.

Eight eddic poems that are known from other sources apart from *Snorra Edda* are quoted in *Gylfaginning*. These are *Hávamál* (1 stanza in RTWU), *Völuspá* (28 stanzas in RTW, 22 in U), *Völuspá hinn skamma* (so called in *Snorra Edda*, where there is one stanza in RTWU, although known by the title *Hyndluljóð* elsewhere), *Vafþrúðnismál* (nine stanzas in RTW and 7 in U), *Grímnismál* (20 stanzas in RTWU), *Fáfnismál* (1 stanza in RTWU), *Lokasenna* (1 stanza in RTWU), and *Skírnismál* (one stanza in RTW, not present in U). One stanza of *Heimdallargaldr*, an eddic poetry named thus in *Snorra Edda*, is not known from elsewhere, and there are five verses

⁵⁷⁹ Daniel Chandler, *Semiotics: The Basics*, 2nd ed. (London: Routledge, 2007) 202.

⁵⁸⁰ I will not be considering the first two skaldic-type stanzas here; see John Lindow, "The Two Skaldic Stanzas in *Gylfaginning*: Notes on Sources and Text History," *Arkiv för Nordisk Filologi* 92 (1977): 106-124.

present in all four manuscripts that are not from otherwise identifiable poems and that are not named.

The Prosimetric Outline of *Gylfaginning*

What I hope to establish is the prosimetric structure of *Gylfaginning* and the way in which this “Latin” model is employed in *Gylfaginning*, and to elaborate on how vernacular and Latin models interact in the work and how this is reflected in the use of prose and verse in the text. I will be asking the following questions of the text:

- How are the stanzas used in the construction of the narrative?
- Do the stanzas inspire the question?
- How important is *Völuspá* to the actual structure of the piece?
- Where in the answers do the stanzas come? (cf. to the *konungasögur*)
- Are the stanzas related to the answer?
- What is the function of the quotation of units of stanzas?
- Is the prosimetric structure of U as a whole substantially different to RTW?

It is possible to find a tension in *Gylfaginning* between a dialogue structure supposedly familiar from Latinate school books, and a dialogue and prosimetric structure that could come directly from traditional, vernacular sources. This in part removes from the Old Norse verses a claim to complete structural authority in this text, and one wonders, in terms of compositional strategy of the piece, what was foremost in Snorri’s mind as he set about constructing the work that we have extant in the two versions (RTW and U).

Gylfaginning is constructed as a dialogue within a frame of Gylfi visiting the euhemerised Æsir. The dialogue is constructed as a series of questions and answers, with Gylfi (who calls himself *Gangleri* in the Æsir’s company), posing the questions, and characters called *Hár* [‘High’], *Jafnhár* [‘Equally High’], and *Þriði* [‘Third’], answering them. Their answers form the contexts for the majority of the verses in *Gylfaginning*; *Gangleri* speaks only one, the first eddic stanza quoted from *Hávamál* (as discussed above). The vernacular wisdom contest, for example in *Vafþrúðnismál*, provides one model for the structure of the text, but *Gylfaginning*’s prose form and the content of the verse being only sometimes tangentially related, displays the tension between the vernacular model and the model of the dialogic Latin schoolbook, in

which questions and answers were posed in verse. Snorri has used this prose model, adapting it to 13th century Icelandic literary culture by including eddic verse as an authenticating device in a manner similar to that found in the use of skaldic stanzas in the *konungasögur*. Simultaneously, the use of eddic stanzas links the extant texts of *Gylfaginning* with those in the dialogic, eddic wisdom exchange tradition.

*Gangleri's Introduction and Arrival*⁵⁸¹

The first eddic stanza quoted in *Gylfaginning*, *Hávamál* st. 1, is not uttered in response to a question by Gangleri; indeed, it is spoken by Gangleri to himself, as a kind of internal warning.⁵⁸² Nevertheless, the stanza is surrounded by questions in indirect speech, and these are constructive comparisons to the questions posed in direct speech by Gangleri, to which the eddic quotations form part of the answers. In the first part of the reception at the hall, it is reported by the narrator that Gylfi is asked his name, to which he replies it is Gangleri, and is then said to ask in response who owns the hall to which he has arrived. This provokes an answer in mixed reported and direct speech from the anonymous one who receives him (“Hann svarar at þat var konungr þeira. ‘En fylgja má ek þér at sjá hann. Skaltu þá sjálfr spyrja hann nafns”),⁵⁸³ and is told in direct speech in RTW “Skaltu þá sjálfr spyrja hann nafns” (R); U does not have this sentence, although Gangleri asks the name of the chief in this manuscript all the same, as in the others. The reported questions and answers continue, with Hár asking Gangleri why he has come, to which he replies that first he will ask if there is any wise man in the hall, thus setting up a wisdom contest scenario akin to that found in *Vafþrúðnismál*. This provokes another answer in mixed reported and direct speech, although on this occasion, the direct speech is metrical, in *fornyrðislag*. It is not clear whether this is a quotation from an unknown poem; it could be intended to anticipate

⁵⁸¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, pp. 7-8.

⁵⁸² This comparative study of the four versions of *Gylfaginning* was facilitated by a comparative online edition of the text: “Snorra-Edda: Formáli & Gylfaginning, Textar fjögurra meginhandrita,” *Jörmungrund*. <<https://notendur.hi.is/~eybjorn/gg/index.html>>. However, references and stanza numbers in the present work refer to *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes. His text is based on R, and the textual notes for the other versions of the manuscript are on pp. 73-76.

⁵⁸³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 8, ll. 2-4.

the great deal of verse that Hár, Jafnhár and Þriði will be speaking in the rest of the text. Certainly the lines imply that the spacial arrangement of the characters during the exchange will be similar to that in *Vafþrúðnismál*. As shown in Part One in the analysis of the prose of the *Poetic Edda*, Óðinn moves around the hall, standing on the floor to ask his questions, despite Vafþrúðnir's invitation to take a seat. The situation in *Gylfaginning* is identical in terms of the arrangement of the characters, but Snorri has reversed the scene from *Vafþrúðnismál*: here the owner of the hall insists that Gangleri shall stand on the floor to ask, while those who own the hall shall sit to answer.

Gangleri Begins His Questioning

Once so instructed by Hár, the text reports that “Gangleri hóf svá mál sitt” (RTWU),⁵⁸⁴ thus marking off the beginning of the section in which Gangleri formally questions the wisdom of the Æsir from the frame of the Prologue and then his arrival to their hall, which can be considered a secondary frame to the wisdom exchange. This is indicated most strongly in U, whose rubric to the section begun states “Frá spurningu Ganglera,” which is reminiscent of the end section of the first set of rubrics “frá spurning Gylva.”⁵⁸⁵ This denotes that the two sets of questions that Gangleri is involved in are thought to be distinctly separate in U: first come the questions concerning his arrival and reception in the hall, in which he is Gylvi/Gangleri, and then come the questions from Gangleri in his speech. Gangleri's arrival and reception at the hall in which he questions the disguised Æsir as to their chief and wisdom and so on, is thus marked as the introduction to a wisdom exchange. The use of the word *mál* to introduce the questions that Gangleri asks in prose and which are answered with a mixture of prose and verse is also likely ironic: in the texts that contain *mál* as part of their title (for example *Hávamál*, *Vafþrúðnismál*, *Grímnismál*), the title person of the poem (Hávi, Vafþrúðnir and Grímnir) are the ones who display

⁵⁸⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 8, l. 26.

⁵⁸⁵ *Uppsala Edda*, ed. Heimir Pálsson, p. 2.

knowledge; here *mál* is linked with Gangleri, but he is the one who is asking and who is receiving the knowledge.

*The First Three Questions*⁵⁸⁶

The first three questions in the sequence do not have stanzas as part of their replies. Question one, “Hverr er æztr eða elztr allra goða?”, is not introduced as such, it just begins Gangleri’s *mál*; the second question (“Hvar er sá guð, eða hvat má hann, eða hvat hefir hann unnit framaverka?”) is introduced as a question in RTW (“þá spyr Gangleri”), but is shown to be provoked by the answer to the first question in U, since it is introduced with “þá svarar Gangleri.” The third question in RTWU is shown to be part of an ongoing discourse, introduced with *mælti/mællir* (RTW) and *segir* (U), and this is typical of Gangleri’s questions in the rest of the text; along with his comments and asides at the nature of the information given to him, his questions are often presented in the narrative as coming organically from the section before.

*Völuspá 3; Hyndluljóð 33; Vafþrúðnismál 30-31*⁵⁸⁷

The fourth question provokes two stanzas in the speech used to reply to it. The first stanza (*Völuspá 3*) is unusually placed, because although it is an evidence stanza it is used as a direct answer to Gangleri’s question: “Gangleri mælti: Hvat var upphaf eða hversu hófsk, eða hvat var áðr? Hár svarar: Svá sem segir í Völuspá...”⁵⁸⁸ The stanza of *Völuspá* that follows is directly and thematically related to the initial question, although the prose following the stanza relates that Muspell was the first world, guarded by Surtr, and then his activities at the end of the world. The second stanza follows this, about the end of the world. A question about the beginning of the world is thus finally answered with a quotation about the end times. This is recognised in U by the insertion of a rubric above the Þriðji’s description of Muspell and Surtr. Nevertheless, the end of the section is rather more usual in structure, with the

⁵⁸⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, pp. 8-9.

⁵⁸⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, pp. 9-10.

⁵⁸⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 9, ll. 8-11.

evidence verse from *Völuspá* at the end of a prose answer and coming directly before the next question, with nothing inbetween.

The fifth question has two and a half stanzas as part of its answer:

Hversu skipaðisk áðr en ættirnar eða aukaðisk mannfólkit?⁵⁸⁹

First, it is related in prose how ice created from the Élivágar, how its fills Ginnungagap, and then how some of it melts from sparks from Muspell, and then the prose tells of the creation of Ymir. Then, a stanza from *Hyndluljóð* (33) (called *Völuspá inn skamma* in *Gylfaginning* RTW) relates the ultimate ancestor of all *völur*, wizards, *seiðberendr*, and the *jötnar* (*völur*, *vættir* and *jötnar* in U), while the beginning of a quotation from stt. 30-31 of *Vafþrúðnismál* is used as part of the narrator's frame to introduce, *Gylfaginning* states, words from the giant Vafþrúðnir himself. In U, the quotation from *Vafþrúðnismál* is used somewhat differently. The three lines from st. 30 that function as part of the narration in RTW are not cited in U, and the introduction by mentioning Vafþrúðnir (*En hér segir svá Vafþrúðnir jötnunn*) is instead in U *Ok enn segir svá at*. This relates the quotation from the (unnamed) *Vafþrúðnismál* to the unnamed quotation from *Hyndluljóð*, and implies that they are part of the same composition. In U, the content of the second stanza is juxtaposed directly with the end of the second verse where the mention of Ymir connects the giants who came out the poison drops in the *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza directly with Ymir rather inserting extra narration about the giant Auregelmir as in RTW, which the prose in all the manuscripts interprets as another name for Ymir. The stanzas here are related to the question ("Hversu skipaðisk áðr en ættirnar eða aukaðisk mannfólkit?") in that they tell about the ancestors that existed other and previous to humans, while the prose begins to answer the question only with an explanation of the environmental conditions before humans came to be, and how these caused the creation of the giant Ymir. It is possible in this instance that knowledge of the stanzas prompted the question of Gangleri's to be created, the prose between the question and the answer

⁵⁸⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 9, l. 39-40.

providing an expansion of the information in stanza 31 of *Vafþrúðnismál*. The quotation from *Hyndluljóð* is a straight forward evidence stanza, the only part of which that it relevant to the section is “allir jötnar frá Ymi komnir.” The backstory to this statement is evidenced by the second quotation from *Vafþrúðnismál*, and thus the stanzas evidence the prose in reverse, the conclusion first and the explanation following.

*Questions Six to Eight*⁵⁹⁰

The sixth question, “Hvernig óxu ættir þaðan eða skapaðisk svá at fleri menn urðu? Eða trúir þú þann guð er nú sagðir þú frá?,” is not answered with a verse and follows directly on in content from the prose and verse answer to the fifth question, as the question enquires how other men came out after the development of Ymir is described previously. The sixth question is actually made up out of two questions; the second question demonstrates that Gangleri is more knowledgeable than he might seem to the other characters, or at least that he might have ideas of religion creationism of his own, since the second question, enquiring whether Ymir is a god, implies that Gangleri might presume gods and men, described in *Vafþrúðismál* 30-31 quoted in answer to the question before as a *jötunn* (RWT, just in st. 31 in U), to be created differently from each other.

The seventh question, “Hvar bygði Ymir, eða við hvat lifði hann?,” is preceded by a rubric in U, “Frá því er sköpuð var kýrin Auðumla,” is not answered by a verse, but a description of the coming into being of the cow Auðhumla (R, Auðumbla TW, Auðumla U), whose milk sustains Ymir. That the question about what Ymir lives on will be answered by this is indicated by the rubric in U. Hár answers the question in TU, but in RW, no speaker is given for the answer, which is rather unusual. The eighth question, “Við hvat fœddisk kýrin?” is not answered by verse, and no speaker indication for the answer is given in T (it is Hár for the other manuscripts). The question is not present in U, in which the answer to question seven continues into the

⁵⁹⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, pp. 10-11.

information given to question eight in the other manuscripts, in a somewhat more concise form. Up to this point in the narrative, the answers have been limited to a large extent by what has been asked by Gangleri. In the answer to question eight (seven in U), the answer goes forwards beyond the question, and after saying that the cow feeds by licking rime-stones, and telling what emerged from the rime-stones, goes on to a statement of religion belief:

Ok þat er mín trúa at sá Óðinn ok hans bræðr munu vera stýrandi himins ok jarðar. Þat ætlum vér at hann muni svá heita, svá heitir sá maðr er vér vitum mestan ok ágæztan, ok vel megu þeir hann láta svá heita.

The statement is interesting because it begins in RTW by stating only what Hár believes as opposed to their collective beliefs, which he moves on to. In U, the description of what they believe is introduced with “ok þat ætlum vér” and is thus always portrayed as collective belief. The statement in RTW appears to end with the advice that he ought to conform to their beliefs (“vel megu þér láta hann svá heitir” TW) although R says “megu þeir,” and the plural, if intentional, might be a rare address intended for the audience.

*Vafprúðnismál 35*⁵⁹¹

The ninth question, “Hvat varð þá um þeira sætt, eða hvárir váru ríkari?,” is followed by a prose answer and an anonymous authenticating stanza, which is *Vafprúðnismál* stanza 35. In U, the answer follows a rubric, “Frá því er synir Burs drápu Ymi.” The question itself is not asked nor a speaker of the prose given. This means the prose and verse that follows the question in RTW directly follows the rubric in U. The question enquires which group, either the frost giants or the gods, were strongest. The verse is introduced at the end of the prose answer with “svá sem hér segir” in RTW, but in U, the stanza is integrated into the prose a little differently. In U, the verse at the end of the answer to question nine is not an authenticating stanza but spoken aloud by the unidentified answerer of the question. In RTW, the prose does not answer the question directly, leaving the reader to infer that the gods are stronger from the fact

⁵⁹¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 11.

that they kill the giant Ymir and drowned the other frost giants with his blood. The giant spared this fate, Bergelmir, saves himself by taking to a vessel (which could be an ark), and this section of the prose seems to be taken from the verse used as evidence as the end of the prose. The stanza has very little to do with the question. Bergelmir is not directly involved in the conflict between Ymir and Borr's sons (who include Óðinn) and the stanza makes no reference to the struggle between the groups:

Ørófi vetra
 áðr væri jörð sköpuð
 þá var Bergelmir borinn.
 Þat ek fyrst of man
 er sá hinn fróði jötunn
 á var lúðr of lagðir.

The stanza rather emphasises the ancient age of Bergelmir, who it seems was created before the speaker can remember. The first even the speaker remembers is Bergelmir being laid on a *lúðr*, which is translated by Faulkes as “box” in this instance.⁵⁹² Tim William Machan suggests that it should be interpreted as “cradle,”⁵⁹³ and thus the box is one Bergelmir was laid in as an infant; this is sensible when the stanza is focused on beginning times: in this case, the first thing that the speaker remembers is Bergelmir being laid in his crib as a newborn. Alternatively, it has been suggested that Bergelmir is rather at the opposite end of his life cycle and is laid down dead on a bier.⁵⁹⁴ I agree with Machan when he says that “either ‘cradle’ or ‘bier’ is thematically acceptable, though one might argue that in answer to a question about an earlier memory, recollection of a beginning, suggested by a birth, is more thematically and stylistically appropriate.”⁵⁹⁵ The question that Óðinn asks Vafþrúðnir in stanza 34 that prompts

⁵⁹² *Edda*, trans. Faulkes, p. 11.

⁵⁹³ *Vafþrúðnismál*, ed. Tim William Machan, 2nd ed., Durham Medieval and Renaissance Texts 1 (Durham: Centre for Medieval and Renaissance Studies, Durham University, 2008) 131.

⁵⁹⁴ Hallfrid Christiansen in “Det norrøne ord lúðr,” *Maal og Minne* (1952): 101-6 argues, on the basis of the poem's context in *Vafþrúðnismál*, that the giant Vafþrúðnir must be younger than Bergelmir and thus remember his death, not birth. Similarly, Holtsmark in “Det norrøne ord lúðr,” *Maal og Minne* (1946): 49-65 interprets the word in this context as “bier.” For an overview of the suggestions about the word *lúðr* in *Vafþrúðnismál*, see *Vafþrúðnismál*, ed. Machan pp. 89-90.

⁵⁹⁵ *Vafþrúðnismál*, ed. Machan p. 90.

stanza 35 in the eddic poem is “hvat þú first mant eða fremst um veitzst,”⁵⁹⁶ to which stanza 35 is clearly a more apt reply that it is to the question in *Gylfaginning*.

If the stanza is understood in relation to its context in *Vafþrúðnismál*, its inclusion in this section makes little sense, but as interpreted by the prose, it helps to answer the first question as to how the groups got on together. In the prose, it seems that the *lúðr* that Bergelmir is on is interpreted as an ark, saving Bergelmir and his family from the flood that wipes out the rest of the frost-giants. If we are not to accuse Snorri of accidentally misinterpreting this stanza, we can conclude that he understands it as using it as fit for his purposes rather than assigning to it the meaning we can logically deduce from the context we have it preserved in in *Vafþrúðnismál*. Although it seems reasonable to conclude that Snorri knew *Vafþrúðnismál* as a dialogic wisdom poetry, there is no reason to assume that he knew exactly the same stanzas or the same stanzas in the same order, so it could be that the context in which he knew this stanza could have made it more suitable for interpreting the *lúðr* as an ark. If this is the case, it could be case that the stanza has inspired the question. Otherwise, read in the context of *Vafþrúðnismál*, the choice of this stanza is an uneasy one.

Völuspá 5⁵⁹⁷

The tenth question, “Hvat höfuðusk þá at Bors synir, ef þú trúir at þeir sé guð,”⁵⁹⁸ is followed by a lengthy prose reply, spoken by Hár, Jafnhár and Þriði (in RTW, it is only spoken by Hár in U), supported by one authenticating verse in all of the manuscripts, *Völuspá* stanza 5 (the poem is named in RTW; unnamed in U). In R, the question is framed as a reply by Gangleri to what he has just heard (“Þá svarar Gangleri”) but in the other manuscripts he is presented as simply saying his question. The stanza is related to the question insofar as it is about the beginning of the world, but it also jars with what is related in the narrative: the answer the question details the

⁵⁹⁶ *Vafþrúðnismál*, ed. Machan p. 65, st. 34, l. 3.

⁵⁹⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, pp. 11-12.

⁵⁹⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 11, ll. 33-34.

stages the gods undertook to build the world, but the stanza at the end of this details what the world was like before they had done this. The introduction to the stanza fails to take this into consideration: “Svá er sagt í fornum vísindum at þaðan af váru dægr greind ok áratál, svá sem segir í Völuspá,”⁵⁹⁹ forcing the author to add a sentence after the stanza, which is obviously about the times before this was able to happen (“Svá var áðr en þetta væri of jörð”) ⁶⁰⁰ in a weak attempt to bring cohesiveness to the quotation of the stanza in the prose. The stanza is unusual because it has this sentence after it in order to align it with the prose that goes before it.

Grímnismál 40-41

After this, Gangleri comments on their answer⁶⁰¹ and asks the eleventh question “Hvernig var jörðin háttuð?” in RTW. In U, there is only the comment “Mikil merki eru þetta ok mikil smíð” and no question, and so Hár’s response (“Hár svarar”) is in reponse only to the comment. Hár is also said to answer the comment and question in RW; in T, it says simply “þá segir Hár.” The prose answer is rather short but it is supported by two anonymous authenticating stanzas (*Grímnismál* stt. 40-41). Interestingly, only the content of the second verse is reflected in the prose. The first stanza, beginning “Ór Ymis holdi var jörð of sköpuð,”⁶⁰² which details that the earth was created from Ymir’s flesh, sea from his blood, trees from his hair, and the sky from his skull, is not presented at all in the prose with this question. The content of the second stanza is, however, used to lead into this stanza in the prose, and because it also has to do with what parts of the natural world were made from Ymir, the omission of the information in *Grímnismál* stanza 40 does not sound unnatural. The contents of the first stanza can be found further back in the prose in the answer to the

⁵⁹⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 12, ll. 11-12.

⁶⁰⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 12, l. 19.

⁶⁰¹ The comments that both Gangleri, Hár, Jafnhár and Þriði make as they exchange question and answers is an interesting part of the narrative in its own right. These short comments reveal the characters’ attitude to what is happening and also provide interest and relief for the audience from the information that is presented in otherwise a rather dense manner. They will not be analysed further here.

⁶⁰² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 12, ll. 28-29.

tenth question, in the reply about how Borr's son made the world, and this seems a more appropriate place for the stanza to have been cited. The stanzas did not prompt the asking of question eleven, after which they are cited, but likely were in mind when question ten was formed. Otherwise, in the context it is now found in *Gylfaginning*, stanza 40 actually supplies information to the narrative rather than authenticating it.

Questions 12-14

Directly after *Grímnismál* stanzas 40-41 comes, in RTW, a comment on the information by Gangleri and the twelfth question: “hvaðan kómu menninir þeir er heim byggja?”⁶⁰³ In U, the comment and question are missing and a rubric is found instead: “Burs synir sköpuðu Ask ok Emlu.” U also lacks the speaker marking, “Þá svarar Hár” (RW) or “Þá segir Hár” (T) found in the other manuscripts, going straight from the rubric into the discussion. What follows is a rather long prose piece answering the question, with no verses cited. The actual question is answered only very briefly and then the answer moves on to a description of the founding of Troy, then Ásaþórr, and the ancestry and duty of Nótt [‘Night’] and her son, Dagr [‘Day’]. In U, the information ending with Ásaþórr and the telling about Nótt and Dagr is separated with a rubric: “Frá Nóra jötni ok Nótt, dóttur hans.” This leads directly onto the thirteenth question, which is missing in U (although what is the answer in RTW is present): “Hversu stýrir hann gang solar ok tungls?”⁶⁰⁴ The answer also does not contain verse; most noteworthy about this section is that the explanation to the question prompts Gangleri to give a comment that is not followed with a question, and that Hár replies in a matter-of-fact manner. Gangleri's comment is a rhetorical one; it seems he knows why the sun moves so fast. The fourteenth question is prompted by and follows directly on from this, “Hverr er sá er henna gerir þann ómaka?”⁶⁰⁵ It is answered in a very brief and direct way; the information is all relevant and comes from *Grímnismál* stanza 39, although no verse is cited here. In U, the

⁶⁰³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 13, l. 3.

⁶⁰⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 13, l. 34.

⁶⁰⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 14, l. 13.

situation is rather different. Gangleri's comment is present, but Hár's reply is formulated in just one sentence: "Nær gengr sá er hana leiðir." After this, the fourteenth question is lacking but the answer given, very concisely.

Völuspá 40-41

In all the manuscripts, the answer prompts the following question, "Hver er ætt úlfana?,"⁶⁰⁶ the fifteenth in RTW. The fifteenth question about the origins of the wolves chasing the sun has two stanzas as part of its reply in all the manuscripts. The prose answer in U is abbreviated in comparison to the others, and while the poem is named in the other manuscripts, it is not in U. The stanzas end the section and the narrative immediately moves on, so the stanzas are used in a very standard way. The stanzas quoted are *Völuspá* stanzas 40-41. The content of the prose and the content of the stanzas are very similar and both the prose and the stanzas answer the question directly. The prose has several extra pieces of information not found in the stanzas: that "í þeim skógi byggja þær tröllkonur er Járnvíðjur heita."⁶⁰⁷ In addition, "in aldna" in stanza thirteen is described as "Gýgr ein" in the prose. These women are not mentioned in the stanzas, in which only to a singular female is referred to in stanza 13.

In U, there are important differences to the prose and stanzas found in this section in comparison to RTW. In U, the prose is much shorter. The information about the woodland called "Járnvíður" and its trollish female inhabitants the "Járnvíður" are condensed into one thought. The mother of the giants and wolves is a "gýgr" in RTW but a "gamla tröllkona" in U, and in U, the idea in RTW that all wolves come from the woodland is not present. U is more definite than RTW that Mánagarmr comes from the woodland; in U the introductory phrase in RTW "ok svá er sagt" is absent. In U, the detail in RTW about the winds that "eru þá ókyrrir ok gnýja heðan ok handan" is also missing. In the stanzas, the most significant differences are in stanza 13. In U we find "in arma" rather than "in aldna," and "tungls tregari"

⁶⁰⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 15, l. 18.

⁶⁰⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 14, ll. 20-21.

rather than “tungls tjúgari.” These differences in the stanza do not seem to account for the differences found in the prose. They do however give a different idea of the mother of the giants and trolls.

Question 16

The sixteenth question by Gangleri, “Hver er leið til himins af jörðu?,”⁶⁰⁸ is not answered with a stanza but instead contains an unusual and interesting reply. Firstly, it is said that as Hár answers he “hló við,” and his answer is preceded by a comment (“eigi er nú fróðliga spurt”) and a rhetorical question of his own (“Er þér eigi sagt þat at guðin gerðu brú til himis af jörðu, ok heitir Bifröst?”).⁶⁰⁹ Hár’s reply to Gangleri answers Gangleri’s question directly and also looks forward to the end of the world when the rainbow, functioning as a bridge, will break. This prompts a comment rather than a question from Gangleri that the bridge cannot be have been made in good faith by the gods, if it will break so easily, and Hár’s response is to defend the gods by saying nothing will be safe when Muspell’s sons advance. This section is notable for its personification of Muspell, which earlier in *Gylfaginning* is a region. The sons of Muspell should probably be taken to be the giants. In U it should be noted that this section is headed with a rubric, “Hár segir frá Bifröst,” and this time Gangleri’s question is indeed included. U is more specific about the questioning than RTW: in U we find “þá spyr Gangleri” whereas RTW have *mælti* or *mælir*. Otherwise there are not notable differences in this section between RTW and U.

Völuspá 9, 10-13, 15-16

The seventeenth question has stanzas quoted to authenticate the response, although the stanzas are not directly related to the question. The question is “Hvat hafðisk Alföðr þá at er gørr var Ásgarðr?” and followed by a fairly lengthy prose answer.⁶¹⁰ There are six stanzas quoted at the end of the answer in a prose-verse complex, the

⁶⁰⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 15, l. 4.

⁶⁰⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 15, ll. 5-6.

⁶¹⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 15.

verse is all from *Völuspá*. Stanzas 9, 10.5-8, 11-13, 15, and 16.1-4 are present, with stanza 10.1-4 and stanza 14 of the poem paraphrased in the surrounding prose. This section thus shows that stanzas nine to sixteen as a unit was known to Snorri. It is noticeable that in this section U is fairly close to RTW in structure; the prose is around the same length and all the same stanzas are quoted. The first stanza is introduced as a quotation from a named poem: “Svá segir í *Völuspá*,” and this is true of all the manuscripts. The prose answer begins by answering the question directly. The inclusion of the information about the dwarves at this point was perhaps prompted by the content of the first stanza quoted, stanza nine of *Völuspá*:

Þá gengu regin ǫll
 á rǫkstóla
 ginnheilug goð,
 ok of þat gættusk
 at skyldi dverga
 drótt of skepja
 ór brimi blóðgu
 ok ór Bláins leggjum.
 Þar mannlíkum
 mǫrg of gerðusk,
 dvergar í jörðu,
 sem Durinn sagði.⁶¹¹

Here it clearly states that the gods go to their judgement seats and deliberate, and this is reflected in the prose. From this point onwards, however, the intentions in the prose and in the verse seem disparate. In the prose, the gods discuss the dwarves from the perspective that they have already been created. They talk of “hvaðan dvergar hǫfðu kviknat í moldunni,”⁶¹² how the dwarves had taken shape in the flesh of Ymir and then how, by the decision of the gods, “urðu þeir vitandi mannvits.”⁶¹³ All these things are in the past. In the stanza however, it is not clear that these things have already happened when the gods take their seats. It seems that they discuss the imminent creation of the dwarves. Durinn is invoked in both the prose and the verse: in the prose he is the second dwarf to be created, but in the stanza he is referenced as

⁶¹¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 15, ll. 39-40 – p. 16, ll. 1-10.

⁶¹² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 15, l. 33.

⁶¹³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 15, l. 36.

the source of the story of the creation of the dwarves, “sem Durinn sagði,” or the source of knowledge of how to create the dwarves themselves. The authenticating stanza is thus used to show the same information existed in dwarf-form, but the story is woven into the plot of the prose in quite a different manner to that in which it exists in the stanza.

Inbetween the first and the second stanza in this section is a sentence linking the creation of the dwarves with lists of their names. This sentence is slightly different in R, TW and U. In RTW, the sentence serves to explain that it is a “hon” who lists the names of the dwarves. This seems to be a direct reference back to the poem *Völuspá* that these stanzas are quoted from, and provides evidence that in this text the reader is expected to know and appreciate the original context of the stanzas. In U however, it is Durinn who tells the gods their names, “ok segir þeim nöfn þeira,” linking the following stanzas with the first and its statement that Durinn is the source of knowledge for the creation of the dwarves (“sem þeim Durinn kendi”). In U then, the first and second and third stanzas are much more intergrated into the main prose answer to the question than in RTW, since the focus is on Durinn telling the gods, presumably as they sit in their judgement seats.

After the third stanza (the second and third list dwarf names), the prose that links the stanzas shifts tone into a narratorial voice that is simply introducing lists: “En þessir eru ok dvergar ok búa í steinum, en inir fyrri í moldu,” and in RTW “En þessir kómu frá Svarinshaugi til Aurvanga á Jöruvöllu, ok eru komnir þaðan Lofarr. Þessi eru nöfn þeirra.” In U however, again the second sentence is made to reference back to the overall answer to the question, and does so by prefacing an introduction similar to that in RTW with “Hár segir.”

Völuspá 28; Grímnismál 29

In the eighteenth question, “hvar er höfuðstaðrinn eða helgistaðrinn goðanna?,”⁶¹⁴ U once again has a specific question word, “spyr,” while RTW have “mælti”/“mælir.”

⁶¹⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 17

All four manuscripts have a very short answer that is directly to the point and which is not supported by any stanzas.

The nineteenth question is an invitation by Gangleri to elaborate upon that short answer, “Hvat er at segja frá þeim stað?,” and in the answer we find two stanzas, one from *Völuspá* (st. 28.7-14) and one from *Grímnismál* (st. 29). The first stanza is not about Yggdrasil, the main place of the gods, as such, but about Mímir’s well, which is located under a root of the tree. The stanza is introduced with the name of the poem it comes from in all four manuscripts, and the final line of the stanza, “vituð þér enn eða hvat?,” is an intriguing remainder from the context the stanza has in *Völuspá*. In addition to the line discussed above in which RTW seem make direct reference to the seeress, here we find another indication that the audience is expected to bring their knowledge of the eddic poems quoted in *Gylfaginning* to bear when reading the text. It would have been easy for the compiler of *Gylfaginning* to omit this line. It was possibly included ironically and could be a reference by Jafnhár (who is speaking this section) to the questioning of Gangleri, especially since Gangleri is an Odinnic figure and is it Óðinn who is doing the questioning in *Völuspá*, as the first line of the quoted stanza makes clear as the speaker (the seeress/Jafnhár) addresses Óðinn directly (“Allt veit ek Óðinn”). After this stanza, the prose answer continues (which is unusual, since stanzas usually come at the end of replies), and at the end of the section that details how the gods reach their meeting place, quotes a stanza (*Grímnismál* 29) that lists the rivers that Þórr must wade on his journey. The stanza is not introduced as a quotation and so the poem is not named. Rather, the stanza is introduced as a list: “En Þórr gengr til dóms sins ok veðr ár þær er svá heita.” The two stanzas are thus not entirely relevant to the question that Gangleri posed about what was there to tell about the holy place of the gods. At the end of the second stanza, the section ends and another question is asked.

Fáfnismál 13

The next question by Gangleri (question twenty) demonstrates that the characters Hár, Jafnhár and Þriði should be thought to speak the stanzas as part of their answers. The verses are not simply narratorial interruptions of the dialogue. Gangleri’s

question is “Brenn eldr yfir Bifrøst?,”⁶¹⁵ a question clearly designed to be prompted by two lines in the stanza at the end of the previous section: “þvíat Ásbrú / brenn öll loga.”⁶¹⁶ The inclusion of this connection aids the compiler or author of *Gylfaginning* in introducing coherency to the narrative where possible and also helps to imbue an air of authentic dialogue to the exchange presented. Nevertheless, the stanza cited as the end of the prose answer spoken by Hár (*Fáfnismál* st. 13) is one of the most outstanding examples of the stanza cited having nothing to do with the question posed. The question is whether fire burns over Bifrøst, but the stanza is about the parentage of the norns. In its introduction however the stanza is unremarkable, it is introduced as an anonymous quotation with “svá sem hér segir,” and a new question is asked straight after the stanza.

Gangleri’s Comment

Gangleri next speaks a comment rather than a question, and this too, like question twenty, is thematically related to the end of the question before. The stanza ending question twenty about the norns is reflected in the question “Ef nornir ráða ørlögum manna, þá skipta þær geysi ójafnt, er sumir hafa got líf ok ríkulegt, en sumir hafa lítit lén eða lof, sumir langt líf, sumir skamt.”⁶¹⁷ This is similar in its criticism of mythological figures to his previous comment that Bifrøst can not have been built in good faith if it will be destroyed by Muspell’s sons marching over it. Like that comment, it prompts a defensive reply by Hár (no verse), of two types of norns, good and evil. Hár thus takes the side of the mythological creatures.

Grímnismál 35, 34, Völuspá 19

Gangleri’s next question (number twenty-one) reveals that the intervening questions between this one and the one about the gods’ holy place being Yggdrasil were in fact a digression, since he brings the subject back to Yggdrasil: “Hvat er fleira at segja

⁶¹⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 18, l. 7.

⁶¹⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 18, ll. 4-5.

⁶¹⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 18, ll. 23-25.

stórmerkja frá askinum?”⁶¹⁸ This question is preceded in U by a rubric, “Frá Aski Yggdrasils.” This diversion back to the tree is done with a knowing question by Gangleri, and as a result reads as an authorial realisation that more ought or must be said about Yggdrasil and as a result of Gangleri already knowing the answer to the questions he poses; this is reinforced by Hár’s comment at the top of his answer: “Mart er þar af at segja.”⁶¹⁹

The answer to the question is lengthy and includes three stanzas (*Grímnismál* 35, 34 and *Völuspá* 19). Since the question is extremely general, the whole reply, since it is all about Yggdrasil in some way, is relevant. Only the prose holds the information about eagle on top of the ash and the hawk Veðrfölnir, Ratatoskr, and the names of the stags that eat the foliage of the tree. The first stanza quoted, *Grímnismál* stanza 35, is introduced an anonymous stanza, “svá segir hér.”⁶²⁰ Not mentioned in the prose is that the ash experiences the movements and nibblings of the animals as privations (lines 1-3 of the stanza),⁶²¹ but the hart biting the tree (here one seems to represent many) and Níðhöggr gnawing from below are in the both the stanza and the prose.

This stanza is linked to the next with “svá er sagt” in RT, “svá er enn sagt” in W and “ok enn segir hér svá” in U; the manuscripts thus link *Grímnismál* 34 with *Grímnismál* 35 subtly differently. In RT the link might emphasise the similarity of the content as well as its continuation, the following stanza naming the snakes that plague the tree (these snakes are mentioned but not named in the prose). In W, the link emphasises that there is more to say on the matter, and U points this directly, presenting the exact place (“hér”) that more information is recorded. This followed by another piece of prose, introduced with “enn er þat sagt,” that mirrors the link between the stanzas and eliminates the need for what would be a repetitive question

⁶¹⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 18, ll. 28-29.

⁶¹⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 18, l. 30.

⁶²⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 18, ll. 36-37.

⁶²¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 18, ll. 38-40.

from Gangleri. The prose appears to be an attempt to rationalise the content of the third stanza about the white mud that Yggdrasil is drenched in, assigning it to the norns' act of preservation in the prose so that the tree does not rot, because the water in "Urðar brunni" (in the stanza) is so holy that it turns all it touches white (in the prose). Unusually there is prose following the stanza that represents the end of the section, rather than finishing with the stanza. The prose comments on dew "er í dali falla"⁶²² in the stanza, and adds in comment about the birds in the well being the ancestors of the modern swan, in a topic not commented on in the stanza.

Völuspá 23

From the Yggdrasil and the well, Gangleri moves on to ask about other important places, "hvat er þar fleira höfuðstaða en at Urðar brunni?,"⁶²³ (question twenty-two) an echo of a question he has already asked and a rather poorly concealed attempt by the author to move on to a new topic. In U, this follows the rubric "Hér segir frá Álf[heimum]." The answer is supported by one verse, related to the part of the prose that describes the various halls of the gods. Since the question is so general, the stanza is broadly related. The emphasis in the prose answer about Gimlé, the subject of the verse, is that it will stand for all-time, and in the stanza, which is *Völuspá* stanza 23, this is expressed as men "of aldrdaga / ynðis njóta."⁶²⁴ This longevity is in contrast to the concern in previous passages about Bifröst being destroyed at the end of the world, and the theme is reflected in Gangleri's next question: "Hvat gætir þess staðar þá er Surtalogi brennir himin ok jörð?,"⁶²⁵ which links back to Gangleri's concern with the sons of Muspell destroying Bifröst. Hár's reply to the question is non-committal, "svá er sagt at..."⁶²⁶ and there is no verse given to back up what he says.

⁶²² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 19, l. 25.

⁶²³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 19, ll. 32-33.

⁶²⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 20, ll. 17-18.

⁶²⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 20, ll. 19-20.

⁶²⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 20, l. 21.

Vafþrúðnismál 37

The following question (number twenty-four), is a curious comment that enquires about a natural feature, the wind, that Gangleri is already aware of, rather than asking after mythological information as such:

Hvaðan kemr vindr? Hann er sterkr svá at hann hrœrir stór höf ok hann æsir eld en svá sterkr sem hann er þá má eigi sjá hann. Því er hann undarliga skapaðr.⁶²⁷

The reply from Hár is in RTW introduced with “Þat kann ek vel segja þér,”⁶²⁸ and is a short and direct answer, undoubtedly facilitated by the existence of a stanza directly on this topic, *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza 37, and Hár’s answer comes directly from this stanza. The author seems to have had this stanza in mind when he formulated Gangleri’s question, and we can assume Gangleri must have known the answer, and that the naïve comment after his actual question is an attempt to disguise this. The short section is concluded with the stanza.

Question 25

The next question, twenty-five, is not in U. The section is simply omitted. In RTW, Gangleri’s question “Hví skilr svá mikit at sumar skal vera heitt en vetr kald?”⁶²⁹ provokes a lengthier comment from Hár than those that have appeared previously in the text: “Eigi mundi svá fróðr maðr spyrja, þvíat þetta vitu allir at segja, en ef þú ert einn orðinn svá fáviss at eigi hefir þetta heyrtr, þá vil ek þó þat vel virða at heldr spyrir þú eitt sinn ófróðliga en þú gangir lengir duliðr þess er skylt er at vita.”⁶³⁰ This self-reflexive comment is perhaps related to two matters. The first is the text book model for the narrative, designed to educate young scholars, in which the basic structure is a tightly configured question and answer sequence. The second is the episode at the beginning of *Gylfaginning* where Gylfi/Gangleri enquires as to whether there are any

⁶²⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 20, ll. 26-28.

⁶²⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 20, l. 29.

⁶²⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 21, ll. 1-2.

⁶³⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 21, ll. 3-6.

wise men in the building, Hár replying that he would fare badly unless he turned out to be the wiser. This stems from the model of the wisdom contest that the narrative also employs. Hár's earlier threat is here tempered with a wish to impart information. There is no stanza employed in this section, but nevertheless the two models upon which the narrative is formed are clearly seen at this point.

Lokasenna 29, 21

U is back in tandem with the other three manuscripts at the beginning of the twenty-sixth question, which in U follows the rubric "Hér segir frá nöfnum Óðins ok ríki." The question is "Hverir eru Æsir þeir er mönnum er skylt at trúa á?"⁶³¹ The pattern in the prose answer of all three respondents answering one after the other, Hár, Jafnhár and Þriði, seems a logical manner to answer the questions put forth by Gangleri, seeing as there are three of them. It is tempting to speculate that this may have been the original intention for the format of the answers in *Gylfaginning*, one that is now lost or that was never fully realised. The stanzas quoted towards the end of the answer are directly relevant to what was asked but can not be said to have inspired the question. The first stanza is part of the answer telling about Óðinn, and is quoted in connection with explaining who Óðinn's wife is and her capabilities. Most notably the stanza is introduced in such a way as to acknowledge its status as both quotation and dialogue: "...ok veit hon ørlög manna þótt hon segi eigi spár, svá sem hér er sagt at Óðinn mælir sjálfr við þann Ás er Loki heitir."⁶³² The stanza that follows is unusual because, unlike the other stanzas which are more or less direct quotations of (usually) whole stanzas that are extant, the stanza here is an amalgamation of stanzas 29.1, 4-6 and 21.1-2 of *Lokasenna* in the Codex Regius manuscript. The beginning of the stanza, "Ærr ertu Loki / ok ørviti, / hví ne legskapu, Loki?,"⁶³³ Is irrelevant to the point of the answer, that is to tell of Frigg's abilities, but is likely included because the introduction of the stanza as dialogue as well as evidence adds an extra layer of

⁶³¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 21, ll. 11-12.

⁶³² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 21, ll. 18-20.

⁶³³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 21, ll. 21-23.

authentication to the narrative. The prose continues after the stanza with alternative names for Óðinn, culminating in a list stanza that Óðinn is, again, said to have spoken, this time when he arrived in the past at Geirrøðr's hall. The Óðinnic nature of all the characters is highlighted by the inclusion of the names Hár, Jafnhár, Þriði and Gangleri, and also of the name Grímnir, when *Grímnismál* as a named poem is quoted in an authenticating role in the narrative. The comment this prompts from Gangleri is that one would have to be very learned to be able to explain all these names, and Hár's subsequent agreement supports the irony of the piece, since this is exactly what they are doing, and exactly what the narrative *Gylfaginning* is for; as Hár says, “muntu eigi mega fróðr maðr heita ef þú skalt eigi kunna segja frá þeim stórtíðindum.”⁶³⁴ Here the text reflects both on the characters within and its external readers, who are simultaneously learning the mythological information. The deflection by Hár of the mythological reasons behind Óðinn's names by instead saying that different languages have adapted his name as necessary is done so on the same premise as the famously euhemeristic Prologue to the *Edda*.

Grímnismál 12, Skaði's stanza, Grímnismál 11, 14

Gangleri's next question (twenty-eight) refocuses the narrative on the dialogic exchange of information rather than a reflection on its value. The question is related to those before it: “Hver eru nöfn annarra ásanna? Eða hvat hafask þeir at? Eða hvat hafa þeir gert til frama?”⁶³⁵ The presentation of three questions invites the relation of a wide range of material about the gods, and is an authorial device for presenting information together that might not be directly related. The stanza cited in the answer is unusual because it comes half way through the prose answer. It is about Þórr's hall Bilskirnir and is the second of the gods' dwelling places to warrant memorialising and quoting through verse (the first was Gimlé). The stanza is introduced with “svá segir í Grímnismálum”⁶³⁶ in all the manuscripts, although its status as a verse that was

⁶³⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 22, ll. 25-27.

⁶³⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 22, ll. 28-29.

⁶³⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 22, l. 34.

spoken in its original context is clear from the stanza in which someone speaks of themselves in the first person. Although the question opens up the possibility to engage with a lot of material in this section, in fact only Þórr is talked about, and Gangleri is forced to prompt for more information: “Spyrja vil ek tíðinda af fleiri Ásunum”⁶³⁷ (in U, Gangleri asks rather specifically about more of Óðinn’s sons).

The subsequent reply by Hár is a complex of prose and verse. The beginning of the reply, “Annarr son Óðins er Baldr,” is particularly fitting for the comment as expressed in U, opening the answer in a list fashion about Óðinn’s sons. The first part of the answer about the identities of the Æsir is about the god Baldr. Similarly to the previous section about Þórr, the stanza authenticating the biography of Baldr is about his hall. The stanza is a quotation from *Grímnismál* stanza 12:

Breiðablik heita
þar er Baldr hefir
sér of gerva sali,
í því landi
er ek liggja veit
fæsta feiknstafi.⁶³⁸

The “fæsta feiknstafi” is expressed in the prose as “óhreint” and it is debatable about whether this implies the same thing. The stanza is introduced with “svá sem hér segir” and is anonymous. The answer continues in a list fashion with the third god, Njörðr, although this time he is not a son of Óðinn. The stanzas quoted in this section are speech stanzas from Njörðr and Skaði, each explaining why they hate living where their spouse would like to live. The stanzas are of unknown provenance although are clearly much older than *Gylfaginning*, since Saxo recognisably quotes them in Latin translation. The first stanza, spoken by Njörðr, is introduced with “þá kvað hann þetta,”⁶³⁹ introducing the stanza as dialogue and as part of the story. The second stanza, Skaði’s stanza, is introduced with “þá kvað Skaði þetta,”⁶⁴⁰ to set up a short

⁶³⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 23, l. 13.

⁶³⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 23, ll. 22-27.

⁶³⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 24, l. 2.

⁶⁴⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 24, l. 9.

dialogue reminiscent of the lengthier examples found in the *foraldarsögur*. The third stanza in the section is from *Grimnismál*, stanza 11, and authenticates the end of the story about Skaði:

Þrymheimr heitir
er Þjazi bjó,
sá hinn ámatki jötunn,
en nú Skaði byggvir,
skír brúðr guða,
fornar toptir fǫður.⁶⁴¹

Like the episodes about Þórr and Baldr above, this stanza also identifies the hall in which Skaði dwells after her father. The stanza is introduced with “svá er sagt,” and so here the narrative reverts to using authenticating stanzas in the story of Skaði and Njǫrðr rather than remaining in dialogue mode. This continues with the similarly authenticating stanza introduced with “svá er sagt”⁶⁴² when the story relates what happens to Njǫrðr and his subsequent children:

Fólkvangr heitir,
en þar Freyja ræðr
sessa kostum í sal.
Hálfan val
hon kýss á hverjan dag,
en hálfan Óðinn á.⁶⁴³

This is the fourth stanza about the name of the hall or residence in which a deity dwells, and the naming of halls can thus be seen to be an important theme in this section of *Gylfaginning*, and the emphasis on naming could perhaps be contrasted to the anonymous hall into which Gylfi/Gangleri enters at the beginning of the text. Although before the stanza it states that “hon [Freyja] á þann bæ á himni er Fólkvangar heita,”⁶⁴⁴ in the prose after the stanza it is said that actually, her hall is called Sessrúmnir, and is “mikill og fagr.”⁶⁴⁵ This separates two aspects of Freyja into

⁶⁴¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 24, ll. 19-24.

⁶⁴² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 24, l. 18.

⁶⁴³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 24, ll. 32-37.

⁶⁴⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 24, ll. 29-30.

⁶⁴⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 24, l. 1.

two separate spaces: on the one hand, as the important mythological information relayed in the stanza makes clear, she is a receiver of half the slain, but on the other hand, she is a goddess of love, and her second hall is a different space in which this role is played.

Grímnismál 13, Heimdallrgaldr

Gangleri's subsequent comment again emphasises the power of knowledge,⁶⁴⁶ and is ended with his next question, the thirtieth, enquiring if there are yet more gods.⁶⁴⁷ In U, this is preceded with a rubric: "Hversu biðja skal ásinn, ok frá Braga ok Heimdall." The prose that follows relates Týr and Bragi and his wife Iðunn, the story of which provokes a comment from Gangleri and a reply by Hár in which he laughs as he is speaking.⁶⁴⁸ Such inclusions give a realistic air to the dialogue. The catalogue of gods continues with Heimdallr, and at the end of the information about him comes yet another stanza about the hall of the gods from *Grímnismál* stanza 13, which seems to serve primarily to identify the hall and the fun the gods have in it, although it also identifies one of Heimdallr's role as the "valda véum,"⁶⁴⁹ the ruler of the holy places. This stanza is an authenticating stanza introduced with "hér er svá sagt" (R), "svá segir hér" (T), "þat er sagt" (W) or "svá segir" (U) and is thus anonymous. Immediately following this stanza comes another quotation, from an otherwise unknown poem named in the narrative as *Heimdallrgaldr*, in which the speech of Heimdallr is explicitly presented as being extra authenticating: "ok enn segir hann sjálfr í Heimdargaldri"⁶⁵⁰ (this stanza concerns his rather mysterious parentage). The narrative, unprompted by further questions or comments, turns back to listing gods with brief information, and Høðr, Viðarr, Áli and Ullr are covered until the narrative reaches Forseti, and the quotation of the next stanza. Like the first stanza connected

⁶⁴⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 25, ll. 6-8.

⁶⁴⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 25, ll. 8-9.

⁶⁴⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 25, l. 29.

⁶⁴⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 26, ll. 2-7.

⁶⁵⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 25, l. 8.

to Heimdallr, the stanza about Forseti relates the name of his hall and his mythological role and is introduced with “svá segir hér” as an authenticating stanza.⁶⁵¹ After this there is a long prose piece about the god Loki, introduced in U straight after the stanza with “Hér segi frá æ[si L]oka,” and no stanzas are cited as part of this short story, although in U it is broken up with an additional rubric, “Frá Fenrisúlfi ok ásum.” Gangleri contributes to its relation only with a comment and question that prompts Hár to relate the second part of the narrative about the fettering of the wolf that Loki sires, and his comment and question is prompted by Hár by Hár’s own reflective comments on the situation,⁶⁵² with a second question and comment from Gangleri oddly placed right towards the end of the lengthy narrative about it being terrible that Loki begot the monster and asking why the gods simply did not kill it.⁶⁵³ Hár’s short reply is followed by a completely unrelated question by Gangleri, and with that the inset story of Loki and the wolf ends and the dialogue between Gangleri and the respondents resumes.

Grímnismál 36

Gangleri’s thirty-second question, “hverjar eru Ásynjurnar?,”⁶⁵⁴ opens the way for a list structure to the narrative similar to that encountered when the male gods are discussed, and the goddesses are listed by Hár in a numbered fashion. Verse occurs in the relation of the fourteenth goddess, Gná. Here, similar to the episode in which Njǫrðr and Skaði speak, there are two stanzas (provenance unknown) that document a conversation Gná is meant to have had with an unnamed person, the first introduced with “þá mælti enn,”⁶⁵⁵ asking what it is flying through the sky, and her response, introduced with “hon svarar,” explaining she is not flying but travelling through the air on a horse (both the stanza and the prose name the horse as Hólfvarfnir). In the

⁶⁵¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 26, l. 27.

⁶⁵² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 28, ll. 7-15.

⁶⁵³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 29, ll. 11-13.

⁶⁵⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 29, l. 17.

⁶⁵⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 30, l. 10.

same section relating the female goddesses, a stanza list stanza is quoted that ends with “þær bera einherjum ǫl.”⁶⁵⁶ The contents of this stanza, from *Grímnismál* (stanza 36), are interpreted in the prose as references to valkyries.⁶⁵⁷ The stanza is introduced with “svá eru þær nefndar í Grímnismálum”⁶⁵⁸ and thus clearly introduces the stanza as both a quotation and a list of names, with the mythological role of those named as the last line in the stanza. Such a structure of object/person plus mythological role was observed several times above when stanzas are quoted in *Gylfaginning* about the gods and their halls. The section on the goddesses is concluded with a short piece of prose detailing a couple more female figures counted amongst the goddesses.

Skírnismál 42

After the section about the goddesses comes a division that is silent in RTW but marked with a rubric in U: “Freyr fekk Gerðr.” The inset tale is that told in the poem *Skírnismál*. The tale is much abbreviated in U, but the extended version in RTW contains a quotation of *Skírnismál* stanza 42 and a comment by Gangleri on what he has just heard (this comment is also absent in U). The quotation from *Skírnismál* is introduced as dialogue (“En er Skírnir sagði Frey sitt eyrindi þá kvað hann þetta”).⁶⁵⁹ The stanza is clearly quoted from the past and may on this occasion have been selected for quotation for its romantic qualities, quite different to the other stanzas included in the text, which are more factual. Directly after the stanza, Hár sums up the ultimate outcome of the story (which explains why Freyr is unarmed and killed Beli with an antler), and Gangleri’s comment that the loss of the sword was not wise prompts Hár to comment that it will be worse at the end of the world, which reveals the true mythological reason for revealing that Freyr is unarmed; in this discussion, Rangnarǫk is presented as in the future. These comments are absent in U.

⁶⁵⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 30, l. 33.

⁶⁵⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 30, l. 34.

⁶⁵⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 30, l. 24.

⁶⁵⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 31, l. 26.

Grímnismál 18, 19

From here, the subject changes. In U, this is marked by a rubric: “Frá vist ok drykk með ásum.” In RTW, a comment by Gangleri brings the subject back around to those who have fallen in battle and go to Óðinn in Valhöll, and ends his comment with the question “Hvat hefir hann at fá þeim at vistum? Ek hugða at þar skyldi vera allmikit fjölmenni.”⁶⁶⁰ In U the question is phrased quite differently. The introductory comment is left out, and instead the question reads “Hvat hefir Óðinn at fá svá mǫrgu fólki sem þar er, ef allir vǫpndauðir men koma til hans?” and the prose answer in U is also slightly briefer than in RTW. At the end of the prose answer in all the manuscripts however, the stanza cited (stanza 18 of *Grímnismál*) is directly relevant to the question. The prose introduction to the stanza emphasises the status of the stanza as a particularly esoteric piece of information:

En þessi spurning er nú spyr þú þykki mér líkara at fáir muni svá vísir vera at hér kunni satt af at segja. Andhrímnir heitir steikarinn en Eldhrímnir ketillinn. Svá er hér sagt:

Andhrímnir lætr í Eldhrímn
 Sæhrímnir soðinn,
 fleska bazt.
 En þat fáir vitu
 við hvat einherjar alask.⁶⁶¹

The knowledge that the voice in the stanza claims is transferred to those who quote the stanza, and serves to emphasise the perceived wisdom of the speakers, and by extension, the author of the work.

The stanza about the feeding of the einherjar closes that section and Gangleri moves on with the logical next question: “Hvart hefir Óðinn þat sama borðhald sem einherjar?”⁶⁶² The short prose reply to the question is fashioned directly from a stanza that is quoted as an authenticating stanza at the end of the answer from *Grímnismál* stanza 19, the only extra information the prose supplies is that Geri and Freki are wolves. Mention of these two wolves that Óðinn feeds provokes the mention of two

⁶⁶⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 32, ll. 5-6.

⁶⁶¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 32, ll. 15-20.

⁶⁶² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 32, ll. 21-22.

other animals that Óðinn keeps: the ravens Huginn and Muninn. The stanza is introduced with “svá sem hér segir”⁶⁶³ although in the stanza it is clear that it is a stanza spoken by a character at some point, since it contains the first person pronoun. In *Gylfaginning*, we thus find a variety of ways of dealing with stanzas that were obviously once spoken in a different context in the first person. One method is to ignore it and treat the stanza as a pure authenticating stanza anyway, which is what this section does. Another method is to incorporate the stanza as dialogue, using the first person to bring immediacy and interest to the story. Another method is to combine the two, using the stanza in a quasi-authenticating manner whilst making it clear it is spoken by another character at another time and is an acknowledged quotation.

Grímnismál 23

The following sections of *Gylfaginning* are especially conscious of the question and answer format and retain it strictly, and there are also a number of comments by both Gangleri and Hár amongst them. The first question follows logically from the question about the food the einherjar receive, and Gangleri would now like to know what they receive to drink; Hár’s comment that “undarliga spyrðu nú”⁶⁶⁴ points out that this is indeed a strange question to Hár, perhaps since the answer should be obvious as he already mentioned in the narrative the wine that Óðinn drinks. Hár himself makes a comment that allows him to continue with a story about what the slain warriors drink: “Annat kann ek þér þaðan segja”⁶⁶⁵ and Gangleri’s comment that the tree that feeds the mead-producing goat that Hár mentions must be very good allows Hár to continue with information not related to the question, where he produces a list of the rivers that flow from the horns of the stag that stands on Valhöll and feeds from the same tree as the goat. Here it seems that the information given is related by association to the information given in the direct answer to the question.

⁶⁶³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 32, l. 36.

⁶⁶⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 33, l. 6.

⁶⁶⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 33, l. 11.

In the section that follows, the characters themselves comment on the process itself of creating and answering questions. Gangleri comments that Valhøll must be incredibly large,⁶⁶⁶ and Hár's reply is revealing:

Þá svarar Hár: 'Hví spyr þú eigi þess, hversu margar dyrr eru á Valhøll eða hversu stórar? Ef þú heyrir þat sagt þá muntu segja at hit er undarligt ef eigi má ganga út ok inn hverr er vill. En þat er með sonnu at segja at eigi er þrøngra at skipa hana en ganga í hana. Hér máttu heyra í Grímnismálum.'⁶⁶⁷

In previous similar sections, such a comment by Gangleri has been sufficient to elicit an answer or information from Hár. Here, Hár formulates a question to feed to Gangleri, and thus one that he obviously knows the answer to. Here the format moves away from a wisdom contest, seeing as the competitive aspect is here removed. Hár suggests the question because he anticipates Gangleri will find the answer amazing, but rather than rephrase the information he would authenticate with a stanza, Hár simply cites a stanza as the answer, which is named in the narrative as coming from *Grímnismál* (stanza 23). Hár specifically indicates that the stanza is the source of the answer, "hér máttu heyra í Grímnismálum." Here the stanza is between an authenticating and dialogue stanza: it is clearly spoken at the answer to the question but also acknowledged as a quotation. This is the situation in RTW. In U, the section is structured differently. The comment by Gangleri that provokes Hár answer cited above is abbreviated in U, and is sufficient to provoke an answer from Hár (the stanza) without the prose cited above. The stanza is simply introduced as "þá segir Hár" and the self-conscious comments by Hár are absent. The poem the stanza comes from is not named in U, and the stanza is quoted as dialogue, making it a rather unusual section in the text of U.

Vafþrúðnismál 41

The following section is also carefully constructed using verse. The section begins with a comment by Gangleri leading to a question: "eða hvat er skemtun einherjanna

⁶⁶⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 33, ll. 26-28.

⁶⁶⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 33, ll. 29-33.

þá er þeir drekka eigi?”⁶⁶⁸ The answer is structured typically at first: a short prose answer (which is very short in U) leading to an authenticating verse (*Vafþrúðnismál* 41) introduced with “svá sem hér segir.”⁶⁶⁹ Hár however continues with “En satt er þat er þú sagðir: mikill er Óðinn fyrir sér,”⁶⁷⁰ making an explicit reference to something else said in the narrative and acknowledging the validity of the knowledgable statements that Gangleri makes. Hár is also here very conscious of the evidence that he can use to authenticate his statements: “Mörg dæmi finnask til þess. Svá er hér sagt í orðum sjálfra Ásanna”⁶⁷¹ and here presents the words of the Æsir themselves as a particularly strong form of evidence. It is possible therefore that the reader is also meant to understand previous quotations in which characters (usually gods) speak in the first person as a particularly valid form of evidence for the narrative. This form of authentication in *Gylfaginning* is likely related to the use of evidence verses in the *konungasögur*, in which a verse is related as spoken by a skald, sometimes in the first person, rather than including impersonal stanzas purely for the sake of their content.

Völuspá 25-26

The section following is linked to what has come before by mention of the horse Sleipnir in the stanza. In RTW, this prompts the following: “Þá mælti Gangleri: ‘Hverr á þann hest Sleipni? Eða hvat er frá honum at segja?’”⁶⁷² In U, a shorter question about the horse follows a rubric: “Frá því er er Loki gat Sleipni við Svaðilfœra. Gangleri segir: ‘Hvaðan kom hestrinn Sleipnir?’” This is an invitation for all kinds of material pertinent to Sleipnir to be brought forth in the narrative in both manuscripts, but it is the beginning of Hár’s answer in RTW that makes it clear that Hár is about to begin a lengthy tale: “Hár segir: ‘Eigi kanntu deili á Sleipni ok eigi veiztu atburði af

⁶⁶⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 34, l. 3.

⁶⁶⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 34, l. 7.

⁶⁷⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 34, l. 14.

⁶⁷¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 34, ll. 14-15.

⁶⁷² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 34, ll. 25-26.

hverju hann kom! – en þat mun þér þykkja frásagnarvert.”⁶⁷³ This is not present in U and the answer is also somewhat more abbreviated in that manuscript than in RTW. The answer is the tale of the giant builder, and the immediate context of the citation of two stanzas (25 and 26, although in W only the second half of 26 is present) from *Völuspá* towards the end of the tale in fact provide the direct answer to the question: “En Loki hafði þá ferð haft til Svaðilfœra at nokkvoru síðar bar hann fyl. Þat var grátt ok hafði átta fœtr, ok er sá hestr beztr með goðum ok mǫnnum. Svá segir í Völuspa.” The content of the stanzas however have nothing to do with the conception and birth of Sleipnir, but rather the overall story leading up to the creation of the horse – they do not actually mention the horse itself though, nor hint in that direction. The stanzas thus do not answer the question directly at all, leaving that to a small section of the prose before them, as quoted, and function rather as background to the story behind the answer given in the prose.

An Anonymous Stanza

Gangleri does not pause to comment on the lengthy tale Hár has told, and rather moves the narrative on to subject that was touched upon much further back in the narrative: “Þá mælir Gangleri: ‘Hvat er at segja frá Skíðblaðni er hann er beztr skipa? Hvárt er ekki skip jafngott sem hann er eða jafnmikit?’⁶⁷⁴ (In U, this is “Hvat er sagt frá Skíðblaðni, er hann bezt skipa?” The question was probably inserted here to form a pair of questions concerning “the best of” various items (horses and ships). There is no verse present to authenticate the answer that Hár gives, and in RTW a complex of comments ensue reflecting the model of the wisdom dialogue that the text draws upon. Gangleri asks a question that he then judges the respondents as having difficulty answering:

Þá mælir Gangleri: ...Hvárt hefir Þórr hvergi svá farit at hann hafi hitt fyrir sér svá ríkt eða ramt at honum ofrefli í verit fyrir afls sakar eða fjölkyngi?

Þá mælir Hár: ‘Fár maðr vættir mik at frá því kunni segja, en mart hefir honum harðfœrt þótt. En þótt svá hafi verit at nokkvorr hlutr hafi svá verit ramr eða sterkr at Þórr hafi eigi sigr fengit á unnit, þá er

⁶⁷³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 34, ll. 27-28.

⁶⁷⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 36, ll. 12-14.

eigi skylt at segja frá, fyrir því at mǫrg dæmi eru til þess, ok því eru allir skyldir at trúa, at Þórr er mátkastr.’
Þá mælir Gangleri: ‘Svá lízk mér sem þess hlutar mun ek yðr spurt hafa er engi er til fœrr at segja.’⁶⁷⁵

This clearly refers back to the model of the wisdom contest, for example in *Vafþrúðnismál* where the consequences seem more serious; here, Gangleri does not assume a particularly threatening tone. After this, however, the respondents defend themselves and Þriði tells a long tale of Þórr’s trip to Útgarðaloki. It is noticeable that it is Þriði rather than Hár that assumes the narration here, since it has been primarily Hár who has done the talking in *Gylfaginning* up to this point. In U, the role of Þriði is explicitly pointed out in a rubric: “Hér þegir Þriði.” In U, Þriði does not speak; he is not introduced to tell the tale and, after another rubric “Hér hefr sögu Þórs ok Útgarðaloka,” Hár tells the story instead. This is a rather inexplicable narrative difference between RTW and U, although one suggestion might be that the title was added to U by someone who was familiar with the longer RTW version, and found the difference in speakers remarkable. The story in U is abbreviated in comparison with RTW, and no stanzas are quoted in the inset tale. The reflective comments in the narrative by the characters also differ between RTW and U. In U, the comment “Nú ætla ek engan kunna þér sannara at segja frá þessi ferð Þórs”⁶⁷⁶ in RTW is absent, and the ensuing comment and question (“Eða hvárt hefir Þórr ekki þessa hefnt?”)⁶⁷⁷ by Gangleri in RTW replaced in U with a rubric “Hér segir frá því er Þórr fór at draga Miðgarðsorminn,” and in U, Hár’s comment that the story is widely known even amongst those who are not scholars is not present.⁶⁷⁸ Similarly, when the narrative moves on to the story of slaying of Baldr, the question in RTW (“Hafa nokkvor meiri tíðindi orðit með Ásunum? Allmikit þrekvirki vann Þórr í þessi ferð”)⁶⁷⁹ is replaced by a rubric and comment in U to introduce the new theme: “Frá lífláti Baldrs ok fór

⁶⁷⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 36, ll. 23-33.

⁶⁷⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 43, ll. 37-38.

⁶⁷⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 44, ll. 1-2.

⁶⁷⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 44, ll. 3-4.

⁶⁷⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 45, ll. 14-15.

Hermóðs til Heljar. Þá mælti Gangleri: ‘Mikit afrek var þetta.’” Although there is no question here, Hár’s reply is introduced with “Hár svaraði.”

The one stanza included in the inset tale recounting the death of Baldr is a speech stanza of unknown provenance:

Þeir biðja hana gráta Baldr ór Helju. Hon segir:
 ‘Þökk mun gráta
 þurru tárur Baldrs bálfarar.
 Kyks né dauðs
 nautka ek karls sonar:
 haldi Hel því er hefir.’
 En þess geta menn at þar hafi verit Loki Laufeyjason er flest hefir illt gert með Ásum.⁶⁸⁰

After this stanza in RTW comes a comment and question in RTW enquiring whether Loki received punishment for ensuring Loki could not be retrieved from Hel, but in U, there is no divide (no question or rubric) between this stanza and the next section. After the long tale of Loki’s imprisonment, Gangleri’s next question is prompted by the mention of Ragnarøkkr in the prose: “þá mælti Gangleri: ‘Hver tíðindi eru at segja frá um ragnarøkkr? Þess hefi ek eigi fyrr heyrt gefit.’”⁶⁸¹ This is a disingenuous comment by Gangleri, since the resonvents have mentioned Ragnarøkkr to him twice before.⁶⁸² So in RTW, although in T, there is a rubric, “UM RAGNARØKKR.” In U, the rubric and question is formulated somewhat differently: “Frá Fimbulvetri og ragnar[ø]kkrum. ‘Hvat segir þú frá Fimbulvetri?’ segir Gangleri.” In all four of the manuscript there is an authenticated verse cited, *Völuspá* stanza 45. In RTW, the poem is named, “svá segir í *Völuspá*,”⁶⁸³ but after a short, and somewhat different answer in comparison to RTW, in U the poem is not named. In RTW, the Fimbulvetr is introduced in the answer and then described, whereas the text in U simply tells about the winter. The stanza quoted does not tell

⁶⁸⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 48, ll. 2-11.

⁶⁸¹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 49, ll. 18-19.

⁶⁸² *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 25, l. 26; p. 29, l. 10.

⁶⁸³ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 49, l. 26.

about the extreme winter weather as emphasised in the prose, but rather focuses on the discord in society that will take place, until finally “veröld steypisk.”

Völuspá 46, 48, 50-53, 55-57, Vafþrúðnismál 18, Völuspá 38-39

As the narrative of *Gylfaginning* draws towards the end of the world, more stanzas from *Völuspá* are cited. In RTW, a long unit of stanzas is cited to authenticate the narrative, with the poem named in RTW and anonymous in U. The stanzas relate to the whole story of the end of the world, rather than simply their immediate introductory context. There are initially nine stanzas cited, stanzas 46, 48, 50-53, 55-57 of *Völuspá*. In U, we find stanzas 46, some lines of 48, and 57. In RTW, after the final verse, we find “hér segir enn svá” and then *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza 18 appears. The long unit of stanzas may have been chosen in order to reinforce the sense of narrative flow when relating the dramatic events leading to the demise of the gods, and the *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza tagged on at the end reads very much like an afterthought, seeing as it authenticates only a small detail in the prose narrative, the size of the field Vígríðr, unless the immense size of the battlefield was held to be of particular importance to the author or reader.

The prosimetric structure of the episode is typical, and after the *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza (absent in U), the narrative moves directly on with a question from Gangleri (in all four manuscripts). It is notable that in U, part of Gangleri’s question in RTW, “...hafið þér áðr sagt at hvern maðr skal lifa í nokkvorum heimi um allar aldir?”⁶⁸⁴ seems to appear as part of Hár’s answer: “Hvern skal þá búa í nökkurum heimi.” In RTW, Hár does not speak here and the narrative voice goes straight to Þriði (this happens after the statement by Hár in U). The end of the section is authenticated in all manuscripts with the citation of stanzas 38 and four lines of 39 of *Völuspá*. All the manuscripts have this as an anonymous quotation that authenticates what is told in the prose. However, after the end of the quotation from stanza 39 comes “En í Hvergelmi

⁶⁸⁴ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 53, ll. 6-7.

er verst,”⁶⁸⁵ followed by the last two lines from *Völuspá* stanza 39. This is not told in the prose and here the narrative uses the two lines from *Völuspá* as story-stanzas to impart information. A comparison can be made between this occurrence and the first quotation from *Vafþrúðnismál*, in which the words of Vafþrúðnir in the poem are used to introduce the part of the poem used as a quotation. These two examples display several of the unusual ways in which *Gylfaginning* uses verse. This section also marks a return to the dialogue structure of *Gylfaginning* seen in the earlier parts of the text before the inset stories in the middle of the text introduce a section light on quotations of poetry.

Vafþrúðnismál 51, 45, 47

This brings us to the final section of *Gylfaginning* before the dialogue structure dissolves back into the frame story. Three stanzas from *Vafþrúðnismál* are given. The section begins with Gangleri’s last question: “Þá mælti Gangleri: ‘Hvárt lifa nokkvor goðin þá? Eða er þá nokkvor jörð eða himinn?’”⁶⁸⁶ The three stanzas cited relate directly to this question. All are included in one prose answer as authenticating stanzas. The first stanza, *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza 51, mentions that Víðarr, Váli, Móði and Magni will reappear after Surtr has quietened. In the prose this authenticates, there is also the detail that Baldr and Höðr will join them from Hel, and “Setjask þá allir samt ok talask við ok minnask á rúnar sínar ok rœða of tíðindi þau er fyrrum höfðu verit, of Miðgarðsorm ok um Fenrisúlfr.”⁶⁸⁷ The second and third stanzas combine with the first to situate the dialogue a pre-Ragnarøk world, whilst placing the reader of *Gylfaginning* in a post-Ragnarøk world. In the second stanza (*Vafþrúðnismál* 45), also an authenticating stanza, it is told how mankind will grow from Líf and Leifþrasir after Ragnarøk, and stanza three (also authenticating) tells that there will be a sun in the sky after Ragnarøk because the daughter (unnamed) of the first sun destroyed during Ragnarøk (Álfröðul) survives. This scheme supports the euhemiristic

⁶⁸⁵ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 53, l. 29.

⁶⁸⁶ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 53, ll. 32-33.

⁶⁸⁷ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 53, l. 39 – p. 54, ll. 1-2.

concerns of the text: there is no need to worry about whether those reading it could believe in the Norse gods because they are dead: mankind, according to stanza two, comes from Líf and Leifþrasir only after this has happened. The reader too now has access to their mysteries when they have read *Gylfaginning*, explained in the narrative by the spreading of the story from Gangleri himself: “Ok eptir honum sagði hverr maðr qðrum þessar sǫgur.”⁶⁸⁸

The final speech of Hár before the glamour created by the Æsir crumbles relates the limit of his knowledge:

En nú ef þú kant lengra fram at spyrja þá veit ek eigi hvaðan þér kemr þat, fyrir því at øngan mann heyrða ek lengra segja fram aldarfarit. Ok njóttu nú sem þú namt.⁶⁸⁹

Hár’s comment simultaneously acknowledges Gangleri’s precocious ability to question his respondents about the whole of mythological time and also acknowledges he has reached the limit of his knowledge. His answer also stresses the sources of his, Jafnhár, and Þriði’s learning – what others have related – and his final comment echoes the formulation at the end of *Hávamál* in which the human listener is told to use the knowledge he has gained wisely.

⁶⁸⁸ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 54, l. 35.

⁶⁸⁹ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes p. 54, ll. 28-30.

The Quotation of Eddic Poems in *Gylfaginning*

Methods of Quotation in *Gylfaginning*

Naming the poems in the prose

The majority of verses introduced into the prose have some kind of introductory phrase, and sometimes this includes the name of the poem. This is interesting for several reasons: firstly it indicates that the compiler of the manuscript had a relationship with the poem that saw it as some kind of self-contained entity with an name, and secondly, the introduction of the name into the prose indicates that presumably the compiler intended or assumed that the name of the poem was meant to mean something to whoever was reading or hearing the narrative. It could be pointed out here that a lack of a name does not necessarily imply the reverse of this or that the poem did not have a name. The name of the poem, when present, is given in the introductory phrase itself, but not all stanzas quoted have such an introductory phrase because a number of blocks of stanzas are also included when verses run consecutively without prose inserts. One very noticeable feature about the way the poems are named is that it is inconsistent: because a stanza is named as coming from a particular poem in one instance, does not mean that a stanza coming from the same poem in the *Poetic Edda* is notified as doing so in the prose.

Quoting Blocks of Poetry

In the case of the poem *Grímnismál* above, whether the verses form blocks or the proximity of the quoted verses from one poem to each other can have an effect on whether the poem is named or not. The introduction of a number of blocks of verses into the *Gylfaginning* narrative allows a direct comparison of the order of verses to that found in the *Poetic Edda* and also to assess the role that blocks play in building the *Gylfaginning* narrative. A 'block' of verse is defined as several stanzas from the same poem (either identified as such by the *Gylfaginning* prose narrative through introductory phrases or as identified in the *Poetic Edda*), quoted consecutively in *Gylfaginning* and not substantially split by prose (more than one line, for example).

There are nine blocks of eddic verse in *Gylfaginning*, five from *Völuspá*, three from *Grímnismál* and one from *Vafþrúðnismál* in RTW that does not form a block in U. This first block of verse from *Vafþrúðnismál* consists of two stanzas in RTW, *Poetic Edda* stanzas 30 and 31 (RTW 8a and 8b) and one stanza in U (U 7, which is *Poetic Edda* stanza 31). In RTW this block is unusual because the first stanza is used to continue the prose narrative and introduce the second stanza, as the first summarises what the second stanza says:

En hér segir svá Vafþrúðnir jötunn
 hvaðan Aurgelmir kom
 með jötna sonum
 fyrst, inn fróði jötunn:

“Þá er ór Élivágum
 stukku eitrdropar
 ok óx unz ór varð jötunn,
 þau eru órar ættir
 komnar allar saman;
 því er þat æ allt til atalt.”⁶⁹⁰

The second stanza thus functions as a standard evidence verse, the first providing its context. In U, the *Vafþrúðnismál* quotation is more standard; the introductory first stanza is not present and the second is simply introduced with “Ok enn segir svá at” in recognition that the information given by this stanza is supplementary to the directly preceding one from *Völuspá inn skamma*.

The Quotation of *Völuspá*

Stanzas that we identify as coming from *Völuspá* are introduced into the narrative of *Gylfaginning* twelve times, but the poem is only named as *Völuspá* on ten occasions. In U, *Völuspá* is also introduced twelve times but named on only six occasions. There are also substantially fewer stanzas of *Völuspá* in U, although those that are absent in comparison to RTW are not introductory stanzas but rather form part of a block in the other manuscripts. As such, the ‘authorising’ stanzas in the manuscript U remain.

⁶⁹⁰ *Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes, p. 10.

It is difficult to pinpoint a clear motivation for not naming *Völuspá*: on the one hand, not naming the poem as many times could indicate that the compiler expected his audience to be able to identify the poem easily and so they did not need it reiterating which poems he was drawing on, or, on the other hand, perhaps naming the poem as such meant nothing to them. *Völuspá hinn skamma* is introduced once in RTW and named as such, but although it is present in U no name for the poem is given. As mentioned, the poem that this stanza appears in elsewhere is called something different, but in view of the fact that named poems are sometimes not labelled, not much importance should be attached to the fact that U does not name the stanza as having come from a particular poem.

There are five blocks of verse quoted from *Völuspá* in RTWU, two of which are straight forward units of verses used as evidence quotations.⁶⁹¹ Of the three remaining blocks of verse, one quite long unit of six stanzas (RTW 15-20, U 14-19, *Poetic Edda* stanzas 9-12 and then parts of 15, 13 and 16) is unusual in that although the verses are clearly grouped together and can be seen to have one overall introductory phrase “Svá segir í *Völuspá*” (RTWU), there are three secondary introductory phrases throughout the block signposting the content of the verses, which are all names of dwarves. The first of these secondary introductions is the most interesting, since it directly refers to the prophetess who is the speaker of *Völuspá*: “Ok þessi segir hon nöfn þeira dverganna” (R) or “ok þessi segir hon nöfn þeira” (TWU), and thus making it perfectly clear that what follows is also from *Völuspá*. The second sentence to interrupt the verses also refers back to the first: “En þessir eru ok dvergar ok buá í steinum, en inir fyrri í moldu.” The third, slightly longer, sentence is more descriptive about how the particular dwarves mentioned fit into wider genealogies, but is straightforward in actually introducing the list of names: “þessi eru nöfn þeira” (RTW) “en þessi eru nöfn þeira” (U). The three secondary introductions thus serve to link all the verses together and make sure the dwarf names are listed and taken

⁶⁹¹ These are the blocks from *Völuspá Poetic Edda* stanzas 40 and 41, RTW 13 and 14 and U 12 and 13, and *Poetic Edda* (Codex Regius) stanzas 25 and 26, RTW 52 and 53 and U 50 and 51.

together and in a context that the narrator wishes to stress (that they all come from the poem *Völuspá* and whether the dwarves live above or below ground).

The fourth block of stanzas from *Völuspá* are a block of nine stanzas in RTW and a block of three in U (RTW 56-64, U 54-56, *Poetic Edda* stanzas 46, 48, 50-3, 55-57 in RTW, just 46, 48 and 57 in U). This is one of the longest omissions of eddic stanzas in U, and the following verse of *Vafþrúðnismál* in RTW (65, *Poetic Edda* stanza 18) is also absent in U. The abbreviation of U here in comparison to RTW still manages to capture most of the important information about the end of the world, the topic of this section, and simply cuts down on the evidence verses. The last block of verses from *Völuspá* is made up of two stanzas consecutive in the *Poetic Edda* (38 and 39, RTW 66-67, U 57-58) and function as straightforward evidence stanzas as can be seen by their introduction “svá sem hér segir” (RTW, ÷ svá U). In U however, a prose narratorial comment is inserted half way through the second stanza: “Í Hvergelmi er verst” (U58), which directs the location of the action of the verses away from Náströnd and thus provides extra information to that found in the prose before the main block.

The blocks of *Völuspá* are of great importance to *Gylfaginning*, and the sheer volume of verses excerpted from the poem in its narrative means that in many ways the poem functions as the backbone of this first part of *Snorra Edda* (although the narrators would have the audience read it the other way round, that the verses simply provide evidence for what they claim rather than actually provide the information upon which they have built their stories). This is certainly the case for RTW, but in U fewer *Völuspá* verses are quoted and the lengthy block of *Völuspá* at the end of *Gylfaginning* much shortened. A substantial number of verses in *Gylfaginning* also come from *Grímnismál*, and the distribution of these is more even over RTWU, although in U again the verses are used for dialogue more frequently than in RTW. In U, more control of the narrative is handed to *Vafþrúðnismál*, and the verses taken from this poem have a greater tendency to be used to add information to the narrative rather than be introduced as simple evidence verses. By using verses more frequently to add information or dialogue, U retains the slightly more conversational flavour of

the dialogue poems (*Völuspá*, *Vafþrúðnismál* and *Grímnismál*) around which the narrative winds; in comparison, the RTW narratives are slightly more stilted as they simply excerpt the majority of stanzas to function as some kind of authority or evidence for what is said in the prose, despite their narrators being in conversations of their own in the context in which the stories are told and verses quoted.⁶⁹²

The Quotation of *Vafþrúðnismál*

Vafþrúðnismál too, as well as *Völuspá* and *Grímnismál*, is drawn upon for a number of stanzas in *Gylfaginning*, but is used slightly differently since it is never explicitly named and in manuscript U, on four out of the seven occasions when it is brought into the narrative it lacks an introductory phrase. In RTW stanzas from the poem are introduced eight times, in U 7, but it is named in neither; instead, in RTW *Vafþrúðnir* is introduced as the speaker in a short block of two stanzas. The first stanza of the block, *Vafþrúðnismál* 30 of the *Poetic Edda*, is instead introduced by naming *Vafþrúðnir* as the speaker of a verse drawn from elsewhere and the stanza itself is used as a continuation of the prose narrative to introduce the second stanza; in U, the second stanza is simply introduced as a standard, unnamed stanza acting as evidence for the prose. The two non-consecutive stanzas of *Vafþrúðnismál*, *Poetic Edda* stanzas 37 and 41 (RTW 28m U 27 and RTW 50, U 48), also function as standard, unnamed evidence verses in all the manuscripts.

Concerning quotations of *Vafþrúðnismál*, introductory phrases in U tend to be absent. *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza 35 (RTW 9, U 8), it is not named and in RTW functions as a standard stanza providing evidence; in U, there is no introductory formula, which makes the *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza (*Poetic Edda* stanza 35) function as speech in the

⁶⁹² For Snorri's use of *Völuspá*, see also Else Mundal, "Snorri og *Völuspá*," *Snorrastefna 25.-27. júlí 1990*, ed. Úlfar Bragason, Rit Stofnunar Sigurðar Nordals 1 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Sigurðar Nordals, 1992) pp. 180-192; Dora Macek, "Some notes on Snorri's Interpretation of the *Völuspá*," *Sagnabeimur: Studies in Honour of Hermann Pálsson on his 80th birthday, 26th May 2001*, ed. Ásdís Egilsdóttir and Rudolf Simek, *Studia mediaevalia Septentrionalia* 6 (Wien: Fassbaender, 2001) pp. 149-157; Stefanie Würth, "The Role of *Völuspá* in the Perception of Ragnarök in Old Norse-Icelandic Literature," *Old Norse Myths, Literature and Society*, Viking Collection 14 (Odense: University Press of Southern Denmark, 2003) pp. 217-33, at 221-224, for the differences in the portrayal of Ragnarök in *Völuspá* and *Snorra Edda*.

narrative, the 'ek' of the poem simply being transferred to the speaker of the prose in the *Gylfaginning*. This lack of attribution in U to a poem is not consistent with the previous use of *Vafþrúðnismál* in manuscript U as previously the stanza was used to provide evidence. *Poetic Edda* stanza *Vafþrúðnismál* 18 (RTW 65) is actually absent from U, in an abbreviation of the poetic elements of the section consistent with omission of several *Völuspá* stanzas. There are three instances of the introductory phrase accompanying a stanza of *Vafþrúðnismál* being absent from U towards the end of *Gylfaginning*. The stanzas do not form a block, are separated by prose (also much abbreviated in U) and are not consecutive stanzas from the *Poetic Edda*, although they are quite close (*Poetic Edda* stanzas 51, 45, and 47). Unlike *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza 35 (RTW 9, U 8), these three stanzas are also not dialogue stanzas, but rather serve to continue the narrative. The preference of U for using *Vafþrúðnismál* as true prosimetrum in which the poetry adds to the narrative rather than simply providing dialogue or exemplifying stanzas is unusual for the use of eddic poetry in *Gylfaginning*, and adds a rhythmical pace to the end of the *Gylfaginning* narrative describing the rebirth of the world, particularly given that in U the prose pieces between the verses are short. After the final verse in U, the final piece of prose before the *Gylfaginning* epilogue (the end part of the frame of the story), is also absent, meaning that *Vafþrúðnismál* stanza 47 (RTW 70, U 61) is the end of *Gylfaginning* proper. As indicated above, *Vafþrúðnismál* is never explicitly named in *Gylfaginning*. In RTW the fact that *Vafþrúðnir* is named as a speaker could be felt to be enough to make it obvious from which context the quotations are drawn on that occasion, but subsequent verses have no such pointers. A parallel could perhaps be found in the verse quoted from *Lokasenna* (RTW 29, U 28, conflation of *Poetic Edda* stanzas 29:1, 4-6, 21: 1-2): "svá sem hér er sagt at Óðinn mælti sjálfr við þann ás er Loki heitir." Here, even as Óðinn is credited as the original speaker of the stanza, Loki is named, possibly to help the audience identify more quickly from which poem the stanza is drawn.

The Quotation of *Grímnismál*⁶⁹³

Although *Völuspá* is named a comparatively high number of times in RTW, *Grímnismál* is also drawn upon for many of the stanzas that are used to provide evidence in *Gylfaginning*, but the poem is rarely named. In RTW stanzas from the poem are introduced sixteen times but the poem is only named three times; in U the usage is almost the same, with it being introduced fifteen times and only named twice. An additional usage of a *Grímnismál* stanza in U is that it is embedded in the prose without the use of an introductory phrase, and as such simply runs on from the prose as part of the narrative sequence rather than acting in the capacity of a stanza to provide evidence. Again, it is difficult to say what this implies for the audience's anticipated knowledge of *Grímnismál* as a poem in its own right. Perhaps certain stanzas were less popular than others and thus less readily identified. The stanzas that are named (*Poetic Edda* stanzas 24, 36 and 23) are from different parts of the poem and there seems no reason why these stanzas should be any less or well known than those which are not named. It could also be noted that the named *Grímnismál* stanzas are fairly spread out through the prose, and this could be one explanatory factor for their being named: the other *Grímnismál* stanzas either tend to form blocks or, when single stanzas are quoted, still run on from each other sequentially. For example, although *Grímnismál* stanzas 18, 19 and 20 are not quoted as a block, they do follow on from each other with prose in between but are not named. The stanza quoted after stanza 20 is *Grímnismál* 23 which is named, and perhaps it is the close proximity of stanzas that would help the audience identify a poem. When the narrative stream is broken, by jumping from 20 to 23, an aid is given by providing the poem's name. The same could be said of the context of *Grímnismál* 24, which is a lone stanza after a block of *Grímnismál* stanzas 46, 47 and a conflation of 48, 49, 50 and 54, and is named. Close by are *Grímnismál* stanzas 12, 11, 14, 13 and 15; although they do not form a block they are more or less consecutive with prose in between (in fact two otherwise unknown

⁶⁹³ Note that the material in this section has also appeared as Helen F. Leslie, "Prose Contexts of Eddic Poetry: *Snorra Edda* and the *foraldarsögur*," *The 15th International Saga Conference: Sagas and the Use of the Past. 5th-11th August 2012, Aarhus University. Preprints of Abstracts*, ed. A. Mathias Valentin Nordvig and Lisbeth H. Torfing et al. (Aarhus: Department of Aesthetics and Communication, Department of Culture and Society, Faculty of Arts, 2012) pp. 39-43.

stanzas used as dialogue separate stanza 12 from 11, 14 and 13, and the *Heimdallargaldr* likewise is in between 13 and 15). After two more dialogue stanzas, *Grímnismál* 36 is then named. This stanza is likewise out on a limb, coming from a completely different part of the *Poetic Edda* poem than its neighbours *Grímnismál* 18, 19 and 20 from which it is separated by a stanza of *Skírnismál*. This consistent pattern of when a stanza of *Grímnismál* is named indicates that sections of a poem, typically three stanzas consecutively even if they have prose in between, is enough to make the poem from which they come recognisable, and it is only single stanzas that maybe unexpected – that come from a very different part of the poem – that need signposting. This also seems to indicate that the verses of *Grímnismál* formed some kind of fixed sequence that was not too far away from the order of verses found in the *Poetic Edda Grímnismál*. This suggests that the poem was at a remove from the stage of oral transmission in which stanza order could vary,⁶⁹⁴ as is usually thought to be the reason behind the variation in stanza order between the Hauksbók and *Poetic Edda* versions of *Völuspá*.⁶⁹⁵

The first *Grímnismál* block is of two uninterrupted stanzas, *Poetic Edda* stanzas 40 and 41 (RTW 11 and 12, U 10 and 11) that both function as standard evidence stanzas in the narrative. The second *Grímnismál* block is also of two stanzas but separated by a short line of prose: “Svá er sagt” (RT); “Svá er enn sagt” (W), “Ok enn segir hér svá” (U). This introductory phrase for the second stanza is perhaps rendered necessary by that fact that *Grímnismál Poetic Edda* stanzas 34 and 35 are quoted in *Gylfaginning* in reversed order. The stanzas of *Grímnismál* are virtually identical to the *Poetic Edda* order in blocks and even when separated by narrative prose, as discussed above, they generally run in the same order as in the *Poetic Edda*. The second prose introductory phrase in *Gylfaginning* thus simply serves as a recognition that the stanzas are quoted

⁶⁹⁴ Lindblad in "Poetiska eddans forhistoria och skrivskicket i Codex Regius" has suggested that Snorri had access to written versions of eddic poems, in which case *Snorra Edda* was not the first stage in the transition of Norse mythological material between orality and the written record.

⁶⁹⁵ See for example the articles by Judy Quinn, 'Editing the Edda: the case of *Völuspá*', *Scripta Islandica* 51 (2001), 69-92 and *Völuspá* and the Composition of Eddic Verse', in *Atti del 12° congresso internazionale di studi sull'alto medioevo. Poetry in the Scandinavian Middle Ages*, ed. Teresa Pàroli (Spoleto: Centro italiano di studi sull'alto medioevo, 1990), pp. 303-20.

‘out of order’ and that stanza 34, although placed after stanza 35, adds additional information.

The third *Grímnismál* block consists of three stanzas, *Poetic Edda* stanzas 46 and 47 and a third containing parts of stanzas 48, 49, 50 and 54 (RTW 30-32, U 29-31). In RTW the block is used in an unusual way: it is clearly introduced as quotation coming from elsewhere but is not used as an evidence stanza: “ok enn hefir hann nefnzk á fleiri vega þó er hann var kominn til Geirrøðar konungs.” The quoted stanzas that follow almost function as dialogue as Óðinn speaks in the first person. Similar use of the first person in a quoted poem can also be observed in the one stanza quoted from the otherwise unknown *Heimdallargaldr*, introduced with variations on “ok enn segir hann sjálfr i Heimdallargaldri” (W). From the point of view of maintaining good control over the narratorial delivery of the story, it is understandable that more first person verse is not included, since it introduces yet another narrator in the already complex scenario of narration in *Gylfaginning* that is avoided when standard evidence verses do not mention an additional speaker. In U, however, these *Gylfaginning* stanzas are clearly quotations, as “segir hann svá” is added after “Geirrøðar konungs”. This is in contrast to how U usually differs to the other manuscripts in terms of introductory contexts, since in the other cases U omits an introductory phrase altogether, leaving open the possibility of the quoted verses instead functioning as dialogue rather than as evidence stanzas (see *Vafþrúðnismál Poetic Edda* stanza 35, RTW 9, U 8; *Grímnismál Poetic Edda* stanza 15, RTW 41 U 40; *Vafþrúðnismál Poetic Edda* stanzas 51, 45 and 47, RTW 68, 69, 70, U 59, 60, 61). The one quoted stanza from *Lokasenna* too (RTW 29, U 28, conflation of *Poetic Edda* stanzas 29:1, 4-6, 21: 1-2), is positioned in RTW as a quotation verse by “hér” in the introductory phrase “svá sem hér er sagt at Óðinn mælti sjálfr við þann ás er Loki heitir.” However, this obviously borders on dialogue even as it reports direct speech in a quotation context common to the rest of *Gylfaginning*. In U however, the “hér” is omitted and thus the strong sign that this is quotation. This allows the verse to function freely as a dialogue stanza.

The Quotation of the Remainder

Hávamál, *Völuspá inn skamma* and *Heimdallargaldr* are each introduced once into *Gylfaginning*. *Hávamál* is the first eddic stanza in the text and is not named. In *Gylfaginning*, this stanza is said after entry into an unfamiliar hall, and Gangleri expresses caution at his situation. Gangleri speaks this stanza to himself, and it is the only verse the character utters during the text. It is spoken as he looks around himself, and as it is in the midst of dialogue in both indirect and direct speech (*oratio mixta*),⁶⁹⁶ the use of verse here helps to imply a sense of wonder as Gangleri takes in all the astonishing things he sees. *Heimdallargaldr* is named in RTWU (RTW 40, U39) and as it is not preserved anywhere else other than this one occurrence of this stanza, it is interesting for us to know that this named poem once existed at all, presumably in a longer form. *Völuspá inn skamma* is named in RTW (RTW 7) but not in U (U6) and it seems that its title in RTW seeks to associate it somehow with the verses quoted from the poem referred to as *Völuspá*, although the content of the stanza has more in common with those stanzas quoted from *Grímnismál* that refer to the giant Ymir. *Völuspá inn skamma* however does exist elsewhere, although not in the *Poetic Edda*: it is referred to as the poem *Hyndluljóð* in *Flateyjarbók* (from which stanza 33 is quoted here).

⁶⁹⁶ An oral narrative feature also conspicuous in some *Íslendingasögur*, see Þórir Óskarsson, “Rhetoric and Style,” *A Companion to Old Norse-Icelandic Literature and Culture*, ed. Rory McTurk, Blackwell Companions to Literature and Culture 31 (Oxford: Blackwell, 2007) 354-371, at 366.

Conclusions

All of the manuscripts of *Gylfaginning* under consideration have two structural principles for relaying mythological information: on the one hand the question and answer format and, on the other the, verses that are quoted. In using the dialogue form to present his material, Snorri was following the standard practice of learned treatise in the Middle Ages written in Latin and simultaneously the native tradition of wisdom poems. It seems highly unlikely that these traditional poems were influenced in their structure by learned Latin treatise. As there seems to have been an ancient Scandinavian tradition of composing poems of mythological instruction as dialogues or dramatic monologues, and as the vernacular material like the poems from which Snorri draws his poetic quotations have this question and answer format, there is no need to assume from the outset that this form in *Gylfaginning* was prompted by influence from Latin learning. The dialogue form in *Gylfaginning* is used effectively and with a sense of fun in a manner fairly close to that found in the dialogue poems it draws from. One important difference is that the verses in the vernacular poems and sagas directly answer the questions that are asked in the poems. In *Gylfaginning*, the verses in most cases do not answer the questions whose answers they purport to authorise, for example the question, “does fire burn over bifrost?”, has included in the reply the verse beginning, “Of very diverse parentage I think the norms are,” and goes on to give the origin of the Old Norse norms. Most verses are at least tangentially related to the answers in the dialogue, but my crucial problem is that the verses do not inspire the questions they answer. If, as frequently assumed, the verses enjoy precedence in the structure of the text, why are they not more intimately related to the questions and answer format?

Gylfaginning is a text that has been very carefully put together and this makes this haphazard-seeming pairing of answer verses and questions more problematic: “he was a scholar assembling his sources, trying to make sense of them, reconcile conflicts among them, and reformulate them in a way meaningful to him and his presumably

learned medieval audience.”⁶⁹⁷ The stanzas are introduced into the narrative with great care and the poems they are cited from are often named, for example. Usually in *Gylfaginning*, the answers are structured so that the prose comes first, with an authenticating verse at the end. As a dominant feature of *Gylfaginning*, it is frequently commented upon that the verses form the backbone of *Gylfaginning*, providing it with chronology, coherence and content. All of these attributes are debatable when you read the stanzas carefully in their places in the question and answer format as a second structural component of the text.

The dramatic situation of the text is a familiar one in many respects from the wisdom poem, Latin educational works and Old Norse translation of didactic or pedagogical texts (such as the *Elucidarius*). One man is set up to ask questions, called Gangleri, faced by three respondents, Hár, Jafnhár and Þriði, who seem to be of royal status. About half the answers these royal respondents give contain no verse in fact, although sometimes the prose is obviously based on a stanza that we know from the *Poetic Edda*.⁶⁹⁸

The verses in *Gylfaginning* are for the most part excerpted from other poems, and the intertextual dimension and the richness these stanzas quoted bring to *Gylfaginning* is very important. Broadly speaking the narrative follows the chronology of *Völuspá* as it charts the beginning and the end of the world, although this is achieved simply by quoting many of verses rather than by the explicit design of the dialogue structure. From this perspective it cannot be said that the verses in *Gylfaginning* are the backbone of the narrative, and thus mould the definitive structure for the text, because there are many sections to which the verses make no contribution. For example there are many sections of the text that include no verses, and there are longer tales put like short stories into the narrative that contain no verses, for example the tale of Þórr’s adventures, which must also be taken into

⁶⁹⁷ Lindow, “Myth and Mythography,” p. 42.

⁶⁹⁸ Where Snorri’s prose is obviously based on verse is noted by Snorri Sturluson, *Edda: Prologue and Gylfaginning*, ed. Faulkes in the notes to the edition.

consideration on account of their length. In a number of places in *Gylfaginning*, Gangleri comments on what he has just been told, and Hár, Jafnhár and Þriði comments on Gangleri's questions. These short comments reveal the characters' attitude to what is happening and also provide interest and relief for the audience from the information that is presented in otherwise a rather dense manner. The inclusion of these comments, especially in Gangleri's speech, is more common in RTW than in U. Additionally, they become more common as *Gylfaginning* progresses; as this happens, the questions become sparser and the prose answers become longer.

The text is pulled between conforming to the question and answer dialogue style and between the style used in the kings' sagas of incorporating verses as evidence. If this conflict were fully resolved, the narrative would align more to the idea of prosimetric coherence found in the sagas, where the verse and the prose context complement each other; were this principle followed in *Gylfaginning*, the verses would be related to the questions they follow. The tight dialogue structure found in vernacular sources such as sagas and eddic dialogues appears to be dispensed with. I suggest that if the dialogue structure on a narrative level were 100% rooted in the vernacular style, the questions, answers and the verses would be bound to answer each other more firmly. Rather, it seems here that the dialogue structure in combination with the verses is held to the mythological material with a somewhat slippery grasp. Certainly the dialogue structure contributes to the entertainment and performative aspect but in terms of content its structure is dubious and changing. The verses though are mindfully inserted and carefully plotted, but unfortunately sometimes leave their questions unanswered, or at least unauthorised.

To summarise, I have suggested that *Gylfaginning* on the surface has a structure that can be seen as having its origin and model in traditional Old Norse literature; that is, mythological poems in dialogue or dramatic monologue and sagas, which happily combine prose and verse. However, *Gylfaginning* fails where such vernacular texts succeed in relating answers directly to questions. This is a very important format in Old Norse texts. It is my contention then, that as an educated scholar, Snorri was

trying too hard in trying to make his poetic manual like the dialogue school books he would have been exposed to. These are the most likely models. This came at the expense of maintaining clarity of argumentation in the Question and Answer scheme of citing verses as authentication, which seems to be firmly rooted in vernacular tradition otherwise, as scene in *Fagrskinna*. The deployment of standard vernacular structures in the fictional and mythological material of *Gylfaginning* is surprisingly fragile.

Part Three: The *Fornaldarsögur* with Verse

The third section of my thesis outlines the nature of prosimetrum in the *fornaldarsögur*. I begin by briefly considering definitions of the genre and the extent of corpus, and the *fornaldarsögur* in oral and literate times. I go on to discuss issues pertaining to the development of the genre. I then move on to an analysis of each *fornaldarsaga* containing verse. I finish by collecting together my findings about the role of stanzas in the *fornaldarsögur*. The *fornaldarsögur* without prose will be touched upon only briefly, since my interest here is those *fornaldarsögur* with verse.

The stanzas in the *fornaldarsögur* can be approached from two perspectives: firstly as an aspect of the sagas' development, and secondly from the point of view of the role of the verses in the sagas as we have them preserved now. But, this approach only seems viable for some of the *fornaldarsögur* since they are not all prosimetric. Before the sagas are treated individually, it is necessary to establish definitions for the genre of the *fornaldarsögur*, which sagas constitute the corpus, what categories the sagas are normally split into and whether the prosimetric structure of the sagas can be linked to this, i.e. whether there are familial affiliations in the groups of *fornaldarsögur*. After that, I will discuss the prosimetric construction of each individual saga, and summarise my conclusions on what this can tell us about prosimetra and the subgenre.

Since the same verse form occurs in the *Poetic Edda*, *Gylfaginning*, and the *fornaldarsögur* it is tempting to look for a connection between them. Prior studies have noted the likelihood that the eddic poetry in the *Poetic Edda*, the eddic poetry in the *fornaldarsögur* and the eddic quotations in *Gylfaginning* are linked. Often, this is expressed as a developmental relationship, for example Torfi H. Tulinius states: "The legendary sagas arise out of a narrative tradition that is older than they are and is to some extent common to all the Scandinavian peoples, namely the heroic poems of the Elder Edda."⁶⁹⁹ Otherwise, stylistic similarities have been highlighted in the method of

⁶⁹⁹ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 19.

presentation, Lars Lönnroth commenting that “several Eddic lays are also presented within the framework of a *fornaldarsaga*,”⁷⁰⁰ a statement that also indicates a possible genetic relationship. I suggest that although these contexts of eddic poetry may be related in content, it is rather more difficult to posit an absolute connection in prosimetric form and subsequently, their development from one to another.

⁷⁰⁰ Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue,” p. 75.

The *Fornaldarsögur* in Oral and Written Tradition

From the heroic content of the *fornaldarsögur* it seems likely that the material upon which the sagas are based was transmitted in oral tradition,⁷⁰¹ although whether or not these oral traditions were prosimetric is another question. Related to this is the question of whether such oral traditions were in a complex saga form similar to the extant written prosimetric sagas, or were what we might consider to be simpler oral narratives. It is these issues that this section seeks to address.

The nature of the relationship between the *fornaldarsögur* and their heroic content that has likely come from oral tradition is not one based the transmission of historical fact. The legendary sagas are clearly related to other sagas set in the far past, such as *Ynglinga saga* and *Skjöldunga saga*, but these sagas are not *fornaldarsögur* as such because they seem to have been viewed by contemporary Icelanders as historical, and thus to be classed with the *konungasögur* written in the late 12th and early 13th centuries. The material in the *fornaldarsögur* was regarded as fictional, and this is why, suggests Jónas Kristjánsson, heroic material was able to survive for five to seven centuries before it took the form we find written down in the extant *fornaldarsögur*, because the oral tradition behind the sagas was not one that was regarded as true. As those that told and recorded the sagas realised they were dealing with material that was, at least in comparison to the *konungasögur*, fantasy, they were able to shape their material without the concern of adhering to a ‘true’ story.⁷⁰²

The beginnings of the written history of the *fornaldarsögur* can be characterised by saying that, in general, they are older oral stories written down late or are stories that rework older material, and for these reasons the genre’s actual age is rather difficult to pin down. From manuscript evidence, it seems that the *fornaldarsögur*

⁷⁰¹ See Peter Buchholz, “Fornaldarsaga und mündliches Erzählen zur Wikingerzeit,” *Les Vikings et leur civilisation: Problèmes actuels*, ed. Régis Boyer, Bibliothèque arctique et antarctique 5 (The Hague: Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales) pp. 133-178; *Vorzeitkund: Mündliches Erzählen und Überliefern im mittelalterlichen Skandinavien nach dem Zeugnis von Fornaldarsaga und eddischer Dichtung*, Skandinavistische Studien 13 (Neumünster: Karl Wachholtz Verlag, 1980).

⁷⁰² *Eddas and Sagas: Iceland’s Medieval Literature*, trans. Peter Foote (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska bókmenntafélag, 1988) p. 342.

could date no further back than the late 12th century,⁷⁰³ but it is very likely that the sagas circulated in some form in oral tradition well before then and that verses were central to these oral texts (I will come back to this).⁷⁰⁴ As for the earliest extant manuscripts, one leaf is extant, known as AM 567 4to, XIV, from c. 1300, that is a fragment of *Hrólfs saga Gautrekssonar*. The oldest manuscript of *Qrvar-Odds saga*, Sth. 7, 4to, is from 1325-50. Finnur Jónsson concludes neither of these manuscripts to be an original.⁷⁰⁵ The first written *fornaldarsögur* are thought to have appeared “at the end of the Literary Golden Age in Iceland in the late 13th century;”⁷⁰⁶ indeed, in his monograph on the *fornaldarsögur*, Torfi H. Tulinius chooses to focus on nine *fornaldarsögur* that he dates to the 13th century because he is interested in the beginnings of the genre,⁷⁰⁷ and he considers these nine sagas to be “the linchpin sagas of the genre; they exemplify the form it took until at least the final decades of the thirteenth century. In the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries, the genre continues to exist, and the majority of the legendary sagas date from these centuries.”⁷⁰⁸ Their popularity is then generally thought to have increased in the 14th century, when many are thought to have been committed to parchment first.⁷⁰⁹ The manuscript *Hauksbók*,

⁷⁰³ Cf. Peter Hallberg, who states “Fornaldarsögur existed in oral tradition as early as the twelfth century; but it is thought that they were not written down before the thirteenth century, especially during the latter decades.” *The Icelandic Saga*, trans. Paul Schach (Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1962) 46. Jón Helgason places the beginning of the genre in the 13th century in “Norges og Islands Digtning,” *Litteraturhistorie: Norge og Island*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, Nordisk kultur 8B (Stockholm: Bonnier, 1953) pp. 3-179, at p. 84. Sigurður Nordal dates the written attestation of the *fornaldarsögur* to around the mid 13th century in “Sagalitteraturen,” *Litteraturhistorie: Norge og Island*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, Nordisk kultur 8B (Stockholm: Bonnier, 1953) pp. 180-273, at p. 228. Peter Buchholz traces the individual elements that come together to demonstrate that the *fornaldarsögur* are the product of an oral milieu in *Vorzeitkund*.

⁷⁰⁴ Hermann Pálsson, for instances, comments “there are good reasons to assume that in the pre-literary period tales were being told about heroes from the legendary past,” and lists Icelandic heroes mentioned in *Háttalykill in forni* and additional Norwegian heroes as evidence, most of which are found in the *fornaldarsögur*. Hermann Pálsson, *Oral Tradition and Saga Writing*, pp. 88, and fn. 64, same page. See also Sigurður Nordal, “Sagalitteraturen,” p. 228 and Jón Viðar Sigurðsson, “Historical Writing,” p. 69.

⁷⁰⁵ Finnur Jónsson, *Den oldnorske og oldislandske Litteraturs Historie*, vol. 2, 2nd ed. (Copenhagen, 1923) p. 787.

⁷⁰⁶ Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland: Historical and Literary Contacts, A Survey of Research*, *Studia Islandica* 46 (Reykjavík: Bókautgáfa Menningarsjóðs, 1988) 48.

⁷⁰⁷ Torfi H. Tulinius, *Matter of the North* 19. Sigurður Nordal meanwhile establishes *Völsunga saga*, *Hervarar saga*, *Hrólfs saga kraka*, *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, *Gautreks saga*, *Friðþjófs saga*, *Qrvar-Odds saga* and *Hálfs saga* as the sagas with a firm basis in older poetry, in “Sagalitteraturen,” p. 230.

⁷⁰⁸ Torfi H. Tulinius, *Matter of the North* 20. See also Jón Helgason, “Norges og Islands Digtning,” p. 85.

dated by Stefán Karlsson to the first decade of the 14th century,⁷¹⁰ contains a version of *Hervarar saga* and the *Þáttr af Ragnarssonum*. It is true, however, that most of the *fornaldarsögur*, or most versions of them, are preserved predominantly in manuscripts that date from the 15th century onwards.

Several statements by classical authors indicate that a genre that was similar to the *fornaldarsögur* existed in the oral traditions of the Germanic tribes.⁷¹¹ Evidence for this is found in the works of Tacitus, Jordanes and Priscus. The earliest reference is in the *Germania (De Origine et situ Germanorum)* of Tacitus from around c. 100 A.D:

Celebrant carminibus antiquis, quod unum apud illas memoriae et annalium genus est, Tuistonem deum terra editum et filium mannum originem gentis conditoresque. Manno tris filium adsignant, e quorum nominibus proximi Oceano Ingaevones, medii Herminones, ceteri Istaevones vocentur. quidam, ut in licentia vetustatis, pluris deo ortos plurisque gentis appellationes, marsos Gambrivios Suebos Vandilios adfirmant, eaque vera et antiqua nomina.⁷¹²

In their ancient songs, their only form of recorded history, the Germans celebrate the earth-born god, Tuisto. They assign to him a son, Mannus, the author of their race, and to Mannus three sons, their founders, after whom the people nearest Ocean are named Ingaevones, those of the centre Herminones, the remainder Istaevones. The remote past invites guesswork, and so some authorities record more sons of the god and more national names, such as Marsi, Gambrivii, Suebi and Vandilici; and the names are indeed genuine and ancient.⁷¹³

Tacitus establishes the apparent antiquity of the traditions that the Germans⁷¹⁴ record in their songs and genealogies, and his point that their oral songs are “their only form of recorded history” is an implied comparison to his own work, which as a written

⁷⁰⁹ Finnur Jónsson, *Den oldnorske og oldislandske Litteraturs Historie*, p. 787 is in favour of an earlier date, but says they could have easily enough been written down in the 14th century; Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*, p. 48;; Einar Ólafur Sveinsson, “Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda,” *Kulturhistoriskt Lexikon för nordisk Medeltid* 4 (Malmö, 1959) col. 499-507.

⁷¹⁰ Stefán Karlsson, “Aldur Hauksbókar,” *Fróðskaparrit* 13 (1964): 114-21.

⁷¹¹ Anne Holtmark has made the most notable comments on this in “Heroic Poetry and Legendary Sagas,” pp. 9-10, but see as far back as Sven Lagerbring and Johan Adolf Stechau, *Dissertatio gradualis de fide historica monumentorum Islandicorum* (London: 1763) p. 24 ff., in which the classical authors commenting on ancient Germanic song as also repeatedly mentioned. See also Gade, “On the Recitation of Old Norse Skaldic Poetry,” p. 129 ff.

⁷¹² Cornelius Tacitus, *Germania, Cornelii Taciti Opera Minora*, ed. Henry Furneaux (Oxford: Clarendon: 1899) [no page numbers] ch. 2, ll. 3-10.

⁷¹³ *Germania, Tacitus on Britain and Germany*, trans. H. Mattingly, Penguin Classics (West Drayton: Penguin, 1948) pp. 101-140, at p. 102, ch. 2.

⁷¹⁴ The designation ‘Germans’ is used loosely here to denote various Germanic tribes that Tacitus considers together as ‘Teutonics.’

text is thus granted more authority. He notes apparent discrepancies in the contents of the songs, giving examples of different descendants of gods and variations of tribal names, but his conclusion “that the names are indeed genuine and ancient,” even though they are guesses by the Germans in his judgment, not only gives narrative credence to the Germans’ oral tradition and the history he might glean from them, but in positioning himself as the one able to judge this, reinforces his own superior authority as an historian whose work is based in the written rather than the oral. Nevertheless, this is an interesting portrait of early vernacular heroic and genealogical material preserved orally. Tacitus also gives other applications of song by the Germans. He observes:

Fuisse apud eos et Herculem memorant, primumque omnium virorum fortium ituri in proelia canut. sunt illis haec quoque carmina, quorum relatu, quem barditum vocant, accendunt animos futuraeque pugnae fortunam ipso cantu augrantur; terrent enim trepidantve, prout sonuit acies, nec tam vocis ille quam virtutis concentus videtur. adfectatur praecipue asperitas soni et fractum murmur, obiectus ad os scutis, quo plenior et gravior vox re percussu intumescat.⁷¹⁵

Hercules, among others, is said to have visited them, and they chant his praises before those of other heroes on their way into battle. They also have a different kind of chant. Its recital – *barritus*, to use their own name – serves to kindle their courage and helps them by its sound to forecast the issue of the coming battle. They inspire or feel terror according to which army roars the louder, and they regard the competition as one of valour rather than voice. What they aim at most is a harsh tone and hoarse murmur, and so they put their shields before their mouths, in order to make the voice swell fuller and deeper as it echoes back.⁷¹⁶

In this quotation, Tacitus notes two further types of song or chant: one in which they honour the god Hercules and another that the Germans use to try and frighten enemies. The first type of chant here assumes both religious and martial functions, since the Germans not only praise Hercules but presumably, since it is chanted on their way into battle, hope that he will aid their victory or protect them. The second kind of chant has a martial role and an almost prophetic value, since it is used to try and determine which side will win a battle. The method the warriors employ to amplify their voices is recorded by Tacitus as an ethnographical oddity, but the fact that the method has a title, *barritus*, accords it seriousness. These three uses of song amongst the Germanic tribes discussed by Tacitus are comparable with the 5th

⁷¹⁵ Tacitus, *Germania* ed. Furneaux, ch. 3, ll. 17-25.

⁷¹⁶ *Germania*, trans. Mattingly, pp. 102-103, ch. 3.

century work of Priscus, who also notes the content and performance context of vernacular song.

A fragment of Priscus of Panium's *History of Byzantium*, a 5th century Greek work, records his visit to the court of Attila the Hun, his contemporary, and the entertainment he witnesses there:

When evening fell torches were lit, and two barbarians coming forward in front of Attila sang songs they had composed, celebrating his victories and deeds of valour in war. And of the guests, as they looked at the singers, some were pleased with the verses, others reminded of wars were excited in their souls, while yet others, whose bodies were feeble with age and their spirits compelled to rest, shed tears.⁷¹⁷

Sadly Priscus did not record any of the verses! Nevertheless, the report is valuable since it tells us that vernacular songs about the achievements of the ruler of the Huns were sung in the 5th century as praise-poems to Attila, focusing on his martial achievements. The performance context is also clearly provided in the account (entertainment at court) and the favourable audience reaction is highlighted. In common with Tacitus, the songs are martially rousing, and they seek to honour a particular person. They also have the latter trait in common with a 6th century reference from the historian Jordanes, who notes in his description of a search for a dead king during a battle:

cumque diutius exploratum, ut viris fortibus mos est, inter densissima cadaver repperissent, cantibus honoratum inimicis spectantibus abstulerunt.⁷¹⁸

When, after a long search, they found him where the dead lay thickest, as happens with brave men, they honored him with songs and bore him away in the sight of the enemy.⁷¹⁹

There is no indication in any of these classical sources of the structure of the songs, whether they were in verse or had accompanying prose, but they likely furnish

⁷¹⁷ For Priscus fragment 8 (which contains the court scene) in the original Greek, see *Fragmenta Historicorum Græcorum*, ed. Charles Müller, vol. 4 (Paris: Didot, 1873) fragment 8 is pp. 77-95, and the episode with the singers praising Attila is found on p. 92. The translation can be found in J. B. Bury, *A History of the Later Roman Empire from Arcadius to Irene (395 A.D. to 800 A.D.)*, vol. 1 (London: Macmillan, 1889) 222.

⁷¹⁸ Jordanes, *Getica, Romana et Getica*, ed. Theodor Mommsen, *Monumenta Germaniae Historica, auctores antiquissimi* 5.1 (Berolini: Apud Weidmannos, 1882) pp. 53-138, at pp. 112-113, ch. 41.

⁷¹⁹ Jordanes, *History of the Goths, Readings in Medieval History*, ed. Patrick Geary, 4th ed. (New York, Ontario: University of Toronto Press, 2010) pp. 78-110, at p. 97.

evidence that heroic *fornaldarsögur*-type material (and similarly found in the eddic lays) was in oral circulation from the first century onwards.

Evidence also exists to demonstrate that material more recognisably *fornaldarsaga*-like (for example, in form) circulated before the sagas were written down. The first to mention is a runic inscription that indicates that tales related to the *fornaldarsögur* were told orally: “Hér lágu þeir men er kómu af / Risalandi með hlöðnu skipi af gulli, / ok þat er í þessum steini” (normalised inscription) [‘Here lay the men who came from Giantland with a ship loaded with gold, and that is inside this stone’].⁷²⁰ This inscription is found inscribed in rock on Hennøy in Nordfjord (Sogn og Fjordane). The inscription is thought to be from the 13th century. Jónas Kristjánsson suggests an early date around 1200,⁷²¹ although McKinnell and Simek suggest that it could even be post 13th century, a late medieval date being suggested by regular spelling, a **p** rune and a double **ll**.⁷²² Journeys to and from Giantland are distinctly *fornaldarsaga*-like, and Rísaland is mentioned in *Qrvar-Odds saga* in the younger and longer version,⁷²³ represented, for example, by manuscript AM 343 a 4to, a 15th century manuscript,⁷²⁴ demonstrating that story material in sagas from the later period could very well contain material drawn from oral tradition.

The wedding-feast that took place at Reykjahólar in 1119 as told about in *Porgils saga ok Hafliða*, part of *Sturlunga saga*,⁷²⁵ is highly suggestive that *fornaldarsaga*-like material was told in a prosimetric structure early in the 12th century.⁷²⁶ The saga

⁷²⁰ Normalised inscription and translation cited from John McKinnell & Rudolf Simek with Klaus Düwel, *Runes, Magic and Religion: A Sourcebook*, *Studia Mediaevalia Septentrionalia* 10 (Wien: Fassbaender, 2004) p. 130, inscription P4.

⁷²¹ Jónas Kristjánsson, *Eddas and Sagas*, p. 343.

⁷²² McKinnell & Simek, *Runes, Magic and Religion* p. 131.

⁷²³ *Qrvar-Odds saga*, ed. R. C. Boer (Leiden: Brill, 1888) pp. 121, 130.

⁷²⁴ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 578.

⁷²⁵ *Porgils saga Hafliða*, *Sturlunga saga*, ed. Jón Jóhannesson et al., vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Sturlunguútgáfan, 1946) pp. 12-50, see 23ff., especially p. 27.

⁷²⁶ If the source is reliable. Ursula Brown reasons that *Porgils saga ok Hafliða* is from the fourth decade of the thirteenth century; see Ursula Brown, ed., *Porgils saga ok Hafliða*, Oxford English Monographs (London: Oxford University Press, 1952) xxix. It has been questioned whether a saga composed so longer after the event is valid evidence for the claims made

author tells that a saga was delivered and “margar vísur með” [‘many stanzas accompanying it’] as part of a descriptive title that could be compared to those found particularly in the Heroic section of the *Poetic Edda*: “Hrólfr af Skálmarnesi sagði sögu frá Hrǫ[n]g[vi]ði ok frá Óláfi liðmannakonungi ok haugbroti Þráins berserks ok Hrómundi Gripssyni” [‘Hrólfr of Skálmarness told a saga about Hrǫngviða and about Óláfr King’s-Retainer and the mound breaking of the berserk Þráinn and Hrómundr Gripsson’].⁷²⁷ The material said to be told appears in extant Icelandic versions and seems to be from a lost version of *Hrómundar saga Gripssonar*.⁷²⁸ The saga as it survives now is from the 17th century, not prosimetric and based on *rímur* (extant and called *Griplur*), so clearly the 12th century version was somewhat different in structure but likely very similar in content, since *Griplur* is thought to follow the lost saga rather closely.⁷²⁹ In the same account, it also says that “Ingimundr prestr sagði sögu Orms Barreyjarskálds ok vísur margar ok flokk góðan við enda sögunnar, er Ingimundr hafði ortan” [‘Ingimundr the priest told the story of Ormr Barreyjarskáld and many verses and a good *flokkur* [‘poem’] at the end of the saga, which Ingimundr had composed’].⁷³⁰ Bibire argues that it should not be taken as given that the more fantastic *fornaldarsögur* are later, and takes as his example the Saga of Hrómundr Gripsson. Bibire reasons that the only reason that the existing saga of Hrómundr Gripsson is not identified with that saga mentioned in the wedding description is because it is ‘fantastic,’ and thus could not have been in circulation as early as 1119. He supports this point by reminding us that Saxo seems to have had access to fantastic

about the saga. Sigurður Nordal notes that it is uncertain how soon the episode was written down, and that this certainly would impact on the value of the episode. Nevertheless, he also comments that the event may have been considered newsworthy and duly recorded. In “Sagalitteraturen,” p. 229. See Peter Foote, “Sagnaskemtan: Reykjahólar 1119,” *Saga-Book of the Viking Society* 14 (1955-56): 226-39; Judith Jesch, “Hrómundr Gripsson Revisited,” *skandinavistik* 14 (1984): 89-105; Ursula Brown, “The Saga of Hromund Gripsson and Þorgilssaga,” *Saga-Book* 13 (1947-1948): 51-77; Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 64.

⁷²⁷ *Þorgils saga ok Hafliða*, ed. Brown, ch. 10, p. 18.1-5. Although Bibire has argued that it could in fact be the same version of the saga as extant; I discuss this below. See Bibire, “On Reading the Icelandic Sagas,” p. 7.

⁷²⁸ *Þorgils saga ok Hafliða*, ed. Brown, ch. 10, p. 18.2-3 and p. 75.

⁷²⁹ Einar Ólafur Sveinsson, “Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda.”

⁷³⁰ *Þorgils saga ok Hafliða*, ed. Ursula Brown, Oxford English Monographs (London: Oxford University Press, 1952) ch. 10, p. 18.7-9.

fornaldarsögur material in c. 1200, which is likely before many of the *Íslendingasögur* were written.⁷³¹ Hrólfr's material may have been *fornaldarsaga*-like, but it has been suggested that Ingimundr's saga may have been an ancestor of the poets' sagas, and may have occupied a middle ground between the *fornaldarsögur* and sagas of poets in the oral period.⁷³²

If we can take as true these intimations that prosimetric sagas existed in oral times, then the prosimetric form is much older than the extant saga writing, and the mixed style of prose and verse could well go as far back as we are able to conceive of the performative tradition of storytelling including verse.⁷³³ At the very least, the author of *Porgils saga* must have had some reason to think that prosimetric sagas were recited orally in his own time, if not earlier.⁷³⁴ The wedding scene at Reykjahólar is also of interest for the point of telling these sagas, which is *skemmtun* ['entertainment']:⁷³⁵ "En þessarri sögu var skemt Sverri konungi, ok kallaði hann slíkar lygisögur skemtiligastar."⁷³⁶ The king (or the saga writer) describes the sagas discussed above as *lygisögur* ['lying sagas'], although the term does not seem to be used

⁷³¹ Paul Bibire, "On Reading the Icelandic Sagas," p. 7. See also Friis-Jensen, "Saxo Grammaticus og fornaldarsagaerne," *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighed. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Agneta Ney, Ármann Jakobsson and Annette Lassen (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 67-77.

⁷³² Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 135.

⁷³³ Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 135; Else Mundal, "Den norrøne episke tradisjonen," *Hellas og Norge. Kontakt, komparasjon, Kontrast. En artikkelsamling*, ed. Øivind Andersen & Tomas Hägg (Bergen: Klassisk institutt, Universitetet i Bergen, 1990) pp. 65-80; Carol Clover, "The Long Prose Form," *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 101 (1986): 10-39; Hofman, "Vers und Prosa in der mündlich gepflegten mittelalterlichen Erzählkunst der germanischen Länder."

⁷³⁴ Jónas Kristjánsson, *Eddas and Sagas* p. 343.

⁷³⁵ See the analysis by Paul Bibire, "On Reading the Icelandic Sagas," pp. 6-7 and especially 8 on this point.

⁷³⁶ *Porgils saga ok Haflíða*, ed. Brown, ch. 10, p. 18.4-5.

pejoratively.⁷³⁷ From this passage, scholarship has lifted the genre-term, although not entirely appropriately.⁷³⁸

Another possible reference to an oral *fornaldarsaga* appears in the *Skarðsárþók* version of *Landnáma*, which mentions that a story about King Vatnarr and his two sons, Sniallr and Hialldr, is told,⁷³⁹ and Finnur Jónsson has suggested this saga may have been told before 1100.⁷⁴⁰ A saga of King Vatnarr is not extant, but Vatnarr and his sons Snjallr and Hjallr appear briefly in *Hálfs saga hálfrekka*, where their burial mounds (“Uattnars haugi” and “bræðra haugi”⁷⁴¹) are mentioned.

In addition to the scene from *Þorgils saga ok Haflíða* discussed above, the inclusion of *fornaldarsaga* type material in Saxo Grammaticus’s *Gesta Danorum* from around 1200 shows that such material was in oral tradition across Scandinavia.⁷⁴² Saxo was a cleric writing his chronicle at the end of the 12th and the beginning of the 13th centuries. His Scandinavian sources were oral and included some prosimetra, and Saxo attempts to transform the vernacular verse to Latin verse; I discussed the clear instances of this above in Part One. Karsten Friis-Jensen argues that Saxo’s

⁷³⁷ As Bibire notes, in *Jómsvíkinga þáttur*, which contains the other attested use of the term, the ‘false reports’ (apparently the best translation of *lygisaga* in this context), is certainly negative. Paul Bibire, “On Reading the Icelandic Sagas: Approaches to Old Icelandic Texts,” *West Over Sea: Studies in Scandinavian Sea-Bourne Expansion and Settlement Before 1300. A Festschrift in Honour of Dr Barbara E. Crawford*, ed. Beverley Ballin Smith, Simon Taylor & Gareth Williams., *The Northern World* 31 (Leiden: Brill, 2007) pp. 3-18, at 6.

⁷³⁸ See Paul Bibire, “On Reading the Icelandic Sagas: Approaches to Old Icelandic Texts,” *West Over Sea: Studies in Scandinavian Sea-Bourne Expansion and Settlement Before 1300. A Festschrift in Honour of Dr Barbara E. Crawford*, ed. Beverley Ballin Smith, Simon Taylor & Gareth Williams., *The Northern World* 31 (Leiden: Brill, 2007) pp. 3-18, at 6, esp. fn. 5. Bibire orients his discussion of *lygisögur* towards analysing truth-value in the sagas (see pp. 6-14); that is not the present concern, but see further Foote, “Sagnaskemtan: Reykjahólar 1119,” and Ralph O’Connor, “History or Fiction? Truth-Claims and Defensive Narrators in Icelandic-Romance Sagas,” *Mediaeval Scandinavia* 15 (2005): 101-69.

⁷³⁹ *Skarðsárþók*, ed. Jakob Benediktsson (Viðauki, 1958) 191-192.

⁷⁴⁰ Finnur Jónsson, *Den oldnorske og oldislandske Litteraturs Historie*, p. 785.

⁷⁴¹ *Hálfs saga ok Hálfrekka*, ed. Hubert Seelow, *Stofnun Árna Magnússonar á Íslandi, Rit 20* (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1981) p. 171, ll. 34-35.

⁷⁴² Bjarni Guðnason, “The Icelandic Sources of Saxo Grammaticus,” *Saxo Grammaticus. A Medieval Author Between Norse and Latin Culture*, ed. Karsten Friis-Jensen (Copenhagen, Museum Tusulanum Press, 1981) pp. 79-93.

prosimetrum is influenced by both his Latin and vernacular models and sources,⁷⁴³ much as I have argued for a similar influence on Snorri's *Gylfaginning*, above.

The final depiction of an oral *fornaldarsaga* to be found in *Norna-Gests þáttr*. In this *þáttr*, an Odinnic figure akin to a wandering performer performs saga and eddic verse before the king and his men. The verses he cites are quotations from eddic poems that are extant (this is discussed further in my analysis of *Norna-Gests þáttr* below), posited to be genuine in the narrative not from the weight of tradition but because the performer, in his great age, was an eye-witness to the heroic figures actually speaking the verse. Harris suggests that the performance situation of the material recalls that of skaldic verse,⁷⁴⁴ but the material performed, with its saga-like prose and eddic quotations, is distinctly like a prosimetric *fornaldarsaga*, and Lars Lönnroth has argued that the prosimetrum itself originated out of an oral performance akin to that found in *Norna-Gests þáttr*, and that the main character of the *þáttr* is “a legendary oral performer.”⁷⁴⁵ The performance situation in *Norna-Gests þáttr* is thus suggestive that, at least to the mind of the *þáttr* writer, such performance was plausible. The eddic and *fornaldarsaga* material being performed in a court context also suggests that, even if skaldic verse were the most prestigious poetic form, eddic verse and prosimetra were appropriate forms of court entertainment. The frame of the story too is a traditional, mythic one, rather than historical,⁷⁴⁶ planting the depiction of an oral *fornaldarsaga* into a *fornaldarsaga* itself, perhaps an ironic allusion and reinforcement of the type of performance the *þáttr* depicts and is.

The earliest reference to a written *fornaldarsaga* could potentially be from 1263, when Sturla Þórðarson entertains the crew of a ship belonging to Magnús lagabætir with *Huldar saga*,⁷⁴⁷ which is not extant (and was perhaps never written down), but

⁷⁴³ Friis-Jensen, *Saxo Grammaticus as Latin Poet*.

⁷⁴⁴ Harris & Reichl, “Performance and Performers,” p. 156.

⁷⁴⁵ Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue,” pp. 77-79.

⁷⁴⁶ Harris & Reichl, “Performance and Performers,” p. 156.

⁷⁴⁷ *Sturlu þáttr, Sturlunga saga*, ed. Jón Jóhannesson et al., vol. 2 (Reykjavík: Sturlunguútgáfan, 1946) pp. 227-236, at 232-33.

seems to have been of the *fornaldarsaga*-type.⁷⁴⁸ After this, the queen invites Sturla to see her, “ok hafa með sér tröllkonusöguna” [‘and to have with him the story about the troll’],⁷⁴⁹ which likely shows that the author of the *þáttr* thought the saga to be written down. Gottskálk Jensson argues that, in the narrative, the saga is not thought to have been invented by Sturla, only that his telling of it was particularly good.⁷⁵⁰

The impetus to commit pen to paper and record the *fornaldarsögur* seems to have come from the translation into Old Norse of French romances (the translated *riddarasögur*). This translation programme took place in the Norwegian court of King Hákon Hákonarson (1217-1263) in an apparent effort to cultivate the court and to use narrative to legitimate the state,⁷⁵¹ and began with *Tristrams saga ok Ísöndar*,⁷⁵² and it seems probable that it caused stories of the romance type to be acceptable as written literature in a society in which secular, written vernacular texts had previously been only of the realistic type (*Íslendingasögur* and *konungasögur*) and indigenous sagas of the romance type (*fornaldarsögur*) had circulated only orally.⁷⁵³ The ascendancy of the *riddarasögur*, Sigurður Nordal suggests, increased the taste for more polished and put-together romance tales, prompting the finished and detailed written development of the *fornaldarsögur* instead of the more “primitive og kortfattede sagnmeddelelser, som man kan forudsætte i den ældre tid” [‘primitive and concise oral narratives which one can presume for the older time’].⁷⁵⁴ Sigurður thus partly assigns the complexity of the

⁷⁴⁸ Jónas Kristjánsson, *Eddas and Sagas*, pp. 344-345.

⁷⁴⁹ *Sturlu þáttr*, ed. Jón Jóhannesson et al., p. 233.

⁷⁵⁰ Gottskálk Jensson, “Were the Earliest *fornaldarsögur* Written in Latin?,” *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighed, Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Agneta Ney, Ármann Jakobsson, and Annette Lassen (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) 79-91, at 85. The queen may have misunderstood; see *Sturlunga saga*, ed. Jón Jóhannesson et al., vol. 2 (Reykjavík: Sturlunguútgáfan, 1946) 310, note 2.5. Cf. Hermann Pálsson, *Sagnaskemmtun Íslendinga* (Reykjavík: Mál og Menning, 1962) 168-169.

⁷⁵¹ Cf. Jón Viðar Sigurðsson, “Historical Writing and the Political Situation,” p. 71.

⁷⁵² See Paul Schach, “Some Observations on *Tristrams saga*,” *Saga-Book 15* (1957-61): 102-129; “Some Observations on the Influence of *Tristrams saga ok Ísöndar* on Old Icelandic Literature,” *Old Norse Literature and Mythology: A Symposium*, ed. Edgar C. Polomé (Austin: University of Texas, 1969) pp. 81-129.

⁷⁵³ Sigurður Nordal “Sagalitteraturen” p. 229; Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland* 48-49. Hákon Hákonarson, who imported these Romances, also valued skaldic verse, see Wanner, *Snorri Sturluson and the Edda*, 80-87.

⁷⁵⁴ Sigurður Nordal, “Sagalitteraturen” p. 229.

fornaldarsögur as a written genre, or at least the taste for them, to influence from the translated literature in the first instance.⁷⁵⁵ Nevertheless, it should be emphasised that this is posited as the background only for the recording of the *fornaldarsögur* as ‘written literature,’ since much of the material in the *fornaldarsögur*, and likely their basic prosimetric form too, is of oral provenance.

Haraldur Bessason, however, ascribes the writing down of the *fornaldarsögur* to the increasingly acceptability of the *Íslendingasögur* as quasi-historical narratives in the 12th and 13th centuries. He links the writing down of the *fornaldarsögur* with a rise in how prestigious the narrative was in comparison to the status of the genre in the oral period, in which, he argues, it was not a prestigious form at all, but also cites the ascension of the *Íslendingasögur* in the 12th and 13th centuries as acceptable semi-historical works as a factor that made the idea of a written *fornaldarsaga* appropriate. Furthermore, he argues that this lack of prestige is the cause of the anonymity of legendary and semi-legendary poetry and prose. Likewise, he attributes the recording of the *Poetic Edda* and *Snorra Edda* before the *fornaldarsögur* to the former texts being linked to the world of learning and literature and thus having more prestige – this meant they were written down first.⁷⁵⁶

Jón Viðar Sigurðsson attributes the writing down of the *fornaldarsögur* to the political changes that took place in Iceland in the second half of the 13th century and in the 14th century.⁷⁵⁷ He argues that the Icelandic aristocracy used the written

⁷⁵⁵ Gerd Wolfgang Weber attributes the attitude of the *fornaldarsögur* to hagiography as well as romances: “Hagiography lent some legitimation and aura to the supernatural and imaginative in the foreign romances and in *fornaldarsögur* such as *Qrvar-Odds saga* or *Yngvars saga víðfjrla*. The influence of the hagiographic sagas – which belong to the oldest forms of literature in the North – together with that of the romances, enhanced the exemplary nature of conduct and ethics in the autochthonous *fornaldarsögur*, which, for example, voice the stereotyped precept that the hero should fight evil Vikings (robbers and waylayers), but never farmers and merchants.” Gerd Wolfgang Weber, “The Decadence of Feudal Myth – Towards a Theory of *riddarasaga* and romance,” pp. 423-424.

⁷⁵⁶ Haraldur Bessason, “Mythological Overlays,” *Sjöttú Ritgerðir: Helgaðar Jakobi Benediktssyni 20. júlí 1977*, ed. Einar G. Pétursson and Jónas Kristjánsson, vol. 1, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar á Íslandi Rit 12 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1977) pp. 273-292, at. 274.

⁷⁵⁷ See also Haraldur Bessason, “Mythological Overlays,” p. 290, where he argues that the collapse of the Old Icelandic Commonwealth and the ensuing political turmoil provided a strong incentive for saga writers. On the one hand, he presents the *fornaldarsögur* and the other heroic poems and literature as individualising conflicts, whereas the *Íslendingasögur* focus on “the ethical dilemmas of individuals,” the sagas of the Icelanders ascent due to a decrease in political stability.

fornaldarsögur “to create a common past for the Nordic countries” in order to negotiate with the new political situation in Iceland and in Scandinavia. This was largely achieved in the sagas by Icelanders using the *fornaldarsögur* to trace their familial lines back to kings and heroes in the *fornaldarsögur* and in doing so link themselves to Scandinavian kings and nobles. The sagas were thus written down to legitimise them as a history of the Icelanders and emphasise the noble background of the Icelanders.⁷⁵⁸

Lars Lönnroth, on the other hand, classes the writing of the *fornaldarsögur*, Iceland’s loss of independence and the translation of French Romance together as factors that could possibly explain the major change in Iceland’s literary history in the 13th century, that is, a decline in oral tradition and the increase in manuscripts. He goes on to reject these as an explanation and instead attributes the rise in manuscripts in the 13th century to a change in *sagnaskemtan* in the 13th century, when stories began to be read aloud from manuscripts and because of this the oral storytelling craft declined, although he lists the *fornaldarsaga* as a genre in which the oral tradition lingered.⁷⁵⁹ Nevertheless, in the light of more recent research showing the oral and written tradition as symbiotic entities rather than mutually exclusive, Lönnroth’s conclusion now reads as slightly extreme.

One important question is whether a long prose (prosimetric) form could exist orally.⁷⁶⁰ Verse has long been thought to be the primary medium for material transmitted orally, and prose thus linked to literacy.⁷⁶¹ Jan de Vries finds it unlikely that a prose form could have been primary to a poetic one on the grounds that in Indo-European traditions poetry precedes prose.⁷⁶² However, Hans Kuhn in 1952 made the

⁷⁵⁸ Jón Viðar Sigurðsson, “Historical Writing and the Political Situation in Iceland 1100-1400,” p. 70 ff.

⁷⁵⁹ Lars Lönnroth, *Njáls saga: A Critical Introduction* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1976) 211-212.

⁷⁶⁰ Cf. Dietrich Hofmann, “Die mündliche Vorstufe der altnordischen Prosaerzählkunst,” *Annales Universitatis Saraviensis* 10 (1961): 163-178.

⁷⁶¹ Cf. Carol Clover, “The Long Prose Form.” *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 101 (1986): 10-39, at 11-12.

⁷⁶² de Vries, *Heroic Song and Heroic Legend*, p. 92.

important argument that the eddic lays, for example, presume the hearer's familiarity with the legends that they reference, and not vice versa, and that the legends cannot have come about on the basis of the extant poems, thus arguing for a loose prose narrative as preceding the eddic poems.⁷⁶³ Edward R. Haymes took Kuhn's argument to its logical conclusion: "this made the songs of the eddic type a derivative rather than primary art form."⁷⁶⁴ Davíð Erlingsson too in his analysis of prose and verse in medieval Icelandic storytelling, argues for the secondary nature of poetry, and that a poem "is probably always a creation secondary to prose reports which, however, might not have yet reached a fixed form,"⁷⁶⁵ and Lars Lönnroth also suggests that "it is more natural to assume that the dramatic form developed out of narrative, rather than the other way around."⁷⁶⁶ Although it seems prose traditions must have existed at an oral stage, likely the idea of "prose" must be qualified, as something more fluid than modern notions of prose, and likely rhythmical, repetitive and perhaps even formulaic.⁷⁶⁷

Vésteinn Ólason discounts the possibility of there having existed oral sagas similar in length to the extant sagas, and argues that the written form of the saga is not representative of the oral form of a traditional narrative:

There is no evidence for the existence of fixed oral sagas of a length and complexity comparable to most of the written sagas. It seems likely that the tradition was fluid, with an oral "saga" composed in the course of narration by a story-teller or saga-man who would articulate traditional elements in traditional ways, with due attention paid to the nature of the occasion and the audience. The form established for the written saga is a literary phenomenon derived from narrative forms known to the Icelanders from other genres and profoundly affected by the fundamental nature of written communication, in which there are no immediate ties between story-teller and audience.⁷⁶⁸

⁷⁶³ Kuhn, "Heldensage vor und außerhalb der Dichtung," pp. 262-278.

⁷⁶⁴ Edward R. Haymes, "Oral Poetry and the Germanic *Heldenlied*," *The Rice University Studies* 62. no. 2 (1976): 47-54, at p. 48. <<http://hdl.handle.net/1911/63223>.>

⁷⁶⁵ Davíð Erlingsson, "Prose and Verse in Icelandic Legendary Fiction," p. 372.

⁷⁶⁶ Lönnroth, Lars. "The Old Norse Analogue," p. 79; cf. Andreas Heusler, "Der Dialog in der altgermanischen erzählenden Dichtung," *Kleine Schriften*, ed. Stefan Sonderegger (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1969) pp. 611-689.

⁷⁶⁷ Clover, "The Long Prose Form," pp. 18-19.

⁷⁶⁸ Vésteinn Ólason, *Dialogues with the Viking Age: Narration and Representation in the Sagas of the Icelanders*, trans. Andrew Wawn (Reykjavik: Heimskringla, 1998) pp. 19-20.

Carol Clover too suggests that the Icelandic sagas do not display typical ‘oral’ features because they never existed as a long form, although she also notes that the many more of the *fornaldarsögur* in comparison to the other saga subgenres fall within her upper limit for performance integrity – works that could be naturally performed from beginning to end by a performer in one sitting.⁷⁶⁹ Additionally, she puts forward the argument for an “immanent saga”: “Briefly stated, it is that a whole saga existed at the preliterate stage not as a performed but as an immanent or potential entity, a collectively envisaged ‘whole’ to which performed parts of *þattir* of various sizes and shapes were understood to belong, no matter what the sequence or the frequency of their presentation.”⁷⁷⁰ The ramifications of Clover’s suggestion is that we should not be thinking about how an oral saga would have been structured, but more like what elements might be available to make up many different structures. A narrative would be created as the performer saw fit at the time of performance, using these building blocks drawn from the immanent tradition.

Theodore M. Andersson reformulates Clover’s arguments and takes them to their logical conclusions in view of the fact that her theory does not explain why the sagas display such a developed narrative form when they appear in writing if no long prose form existed in oral tradition as a prototype.⁷⁷¹ He argues that the immanent saga was not only theoretically possible, it was also practiced in the oral culture.⁷⁷² The telling of such long prose forms (or prosimetric forms) in the preliterate period was a precondition for the narrative and formal style that appeared with the written saga.

Because of this idea of smaller, *þattir* type pieces of differing lengths and styles coming together to form a narrative in oral tradition, in my analysis of the written *fornaldarsaga* I will treat the stanzas as they appear to be grouped in each saga, and

⁷⁶⁹ Clover, “The Long Prose Form,” p. 28.

⁷⁷⁰ Clover, “The Long Prose Form,” p. 34.

⁷⁷¹ Theodore M. Andersson, “The Long Prose Form in Medieval Iceland,” *Journal of English and Germanic Philology* 101 (2002): 380-411, at 387.

⁷⁷² Andersson, “The Long Prose Form in Medieval Iceland,” pp. 405, 411.

thus will extract what I will term 'episodes' from the sagas to explore in terms of prosimetric structure. How the episodes portray the stanzas as having being performed, or in what circumstances, I will term 'performance context.' Not all stanzas have a performance context, or at best, a weak one. Nonetheless, the portrayal of how a stanza comes to be spoken and reacted to in saga narrative when it does happen must reflect on how the medieval author of the narrative understood the performance of the stanza, and these depictions of prosimetric recitals are interesting. It seems like that chunks of verse aided the development of an oral saga sequence.

The Development of the *Fornaldarsögur*

The development of the *fornaldarsögur* is almost always discussed in relation to their prosimetric form in the scholarship. While the *fornaldarsögur* are preserved in 13th and 14th century manuscripts, it has been argued that some sagas, such as *Völsunga saga*, are very old and based on a core of ancient poetry,⁷⁷³ and are thus based on much older oral traditions⁷⁷⁴ affiliated with those mentioned above upon which the extant eddic poetry drew. Lars Lönnroth argues that the prosimetrum that appears in writing the 13th century must have been in oral tradition before their time because a similar division between prose and poetry appears in Saxo's tales from the 12th century.⁷⁷⁵ This implies that extant prosimetric *fornaldarsögur* judged as younger on the basis of their manuscript tradition (for example *Hrólfs saga kráka*, manuscripts of which are from the 17th century), include verse in imitation of these older sagas. This need not be the case, since they may be drawing upon an older oral tradition that is only just coming to be written down or using the material found in stanzas to structure the outline of a saga, the story filled out with creative material extrapolated from the stanzas (for example as in *Ásmundar saga kappabana*, as discussed below).

Several accounts indicate that prosimetra was probably part of the context of eddic poetry in the oral period.⁷⁷⁶ Lönnroth argues that "several Eddic lays are...presented within the framework of a *fornaldarsaga*," and that "the prose of the *fornaldarsaga* and the poetry of the Eddic lays were meant to supplement each other in 13th century texts."⁷⁷⁷ The story of Norna-Gestr from the 14th century tells of an entertainer whose entertainment material seems akin to the *fornaldarsögur*, in both

⁷⁷³ Heusler, "Die Anfänge der isländischen Saga," pp. 440-441; Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 145

⁷⁷⁴ Buchholtz, *Vorzeitkunde*; Jürg Glauser, *Isländische Märchensagas: Studien zur Prosaliteratur im spätmittelalterlichem Island*, Beiträge zur nordischen Philologie 12 (Basel: Helbing & Lichtenhan, 1983); Lönnroth, "The Old Norse Analogue," p. 74.

⁷⁷⁵ Lönnroth, "The Old Norse Analogue," p. 75.

⁷⁷⁶ Cf. the discussion in Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," pp. 133-135.

⁷⁷⁷ Lönnroth, "The Old Norse Analogue," p. 75.

prose and prosimetrum, and who cites eddic verses also known from the *Poetic Edda* collections. Harris suggests that “in the figure of the entertainer the author of the piece is probably reflecting life and tradition,” even though the narrative situation is fictional.⁷⁷⁸ Texts that seem to belong to the *fornaldarsögur* genre are orally performed at a wedding in Reykjahólar in 1119 amongst other entertainment,⁷⁷⁹ suggesting not only a likely performance context but also that the *fornaldarsögur* or *fornaldarsaga*-like material in a prosimetrical structure existed earlier than their first attested written form in Saxo Grammaticus later in the 12th century.⁷⁸⁰

Paul Bibire cautions against the evolutionary view of the *fornaldarsögur*, in which the legendary sagas are the degenerate followers and poor cousins of the great 13th century *Íslendingasögur*, which had themselves developed from the *konungasögur* in the late 12th century onwards. Sigurður Nordal, for example, presents an evolutionary model of the development of saga writing as an ascendant and descendant process, as Whaley puts it, “from dry scholarship to wild fantasy.”⁷⁸¹ This view is reverberates throughout later scholarship, for example: “The earliest preserved *sögur* tell of the kings of Norway, and were written for them, while those on Icelandic bishops were strongly influenced by translated legends of saints and apostles. And the Sagas of the Icelanders, which were written after the types just mentioned, seem to have given way in turn to a fashion for Mythic-Heroic and Courtly Sagas, entertainingly legendary and romantic genres of foreign origin and escapist purpose.”⁷⁸² The *konungasögur* are on the ascendant path, the *Íslendingasögur* stand resplendent at the saga genres peak,

⁷⁷⁸ Concurring with view are Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 134; Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue,” pp. 76, 77-79; Davíð Erlingsson, “Prose and Verse in Icelandic Legendary Fiction,” p. 380. See further Joseph Harris & Thomas D. Hill, “Gestr’s “Prime Sign”: Source and Signification in *Norna-Gests þátr*.” *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 104 (1989): 103-122.

⁷⁷⁹ Hermann Pálsson argues that the stories told by Hrólfr and Ingimundr were actually written down and read out. He suggests that they stories are mentioned at the wedding because their beings written down and read out was the novelty-factor that prompted them to be mentioned in the saga in the first place, in *Oral Tradition and Saga Writing*, p. 78.

⁷⁸⁰ Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 134.

⁷⁸¹ Diana Whaley, “The Kings’ Sagas,” *Viking Revaluations: Viking Society Centenary Symposium*, ed. Anthony Faulkes and Richard Perkins (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1993) pp. 43-64, at 48.

⁷⁸² John Tucker, “Introduction: Sagas of Icelanders,” *Sagas of the Icelanders: A Book of Essays*, ed. John Tucker (New York: Garland, 1989) pp. 1-26, at pp. 3-4.

while the *fornaldarsögur* have slid dramatically downwards in artistic and literary merit.⁷⁸³ Bibire argues that it should not be taken as given that the more fantastic *fornaldarsögur* are later, and takes as his example the Saga of Hrómundr Gripsson, discussed above. Bibire reasons that the only reason that the existing saga of Hrómundr Gripsson is not identified with that saga mentioned in the wedding description is because it is ‘fantastic,’ and thus could not have been in circulation as early as 1119. He supports this point by reminding us that Saxo seems to have had access to fantastic *fornaldarsögur* material in c. 1200, which is likely before many of the *Íslendingasögur* were written.⁷⁸⁴

The origins of the *fornaldarsögur* genre are lost despite the hints that may be listed as to the oral *fornaldarsaga*’s existence and form, and the subgenre’s written form has likely had a myriad of influences that cannot be seen clearly individually. Nevertheless, this lack of potential to ever gain absolute clarity on the beginnings of the genre has not prohibited scholars from making educated guesses based on historical and literary probability and evidence from the subgenres in its written form. The following is an overview of the discussion about the development of the genre from oral times.

It seems probable that the specifically Icelandic contribution to the development of the legendary sagas was to give the material its form. The *fornaldarsögur* in their early oral stages were built upon or around stories about legendary heroes from distant times past in Scandinavia,⁷⁸⁵ and as time went on were likely influenced by many motifs and story elements from other genres and places; the material (the content) of the *fornaldarsögur* cannot thus be said to be specifically

⁷⁸³ Sigurður Nordal, *Snorri Sturluson*, pp. 128-30; “Sagalitteraturen,” p. 251.

⁷⁸⁴ Paul Bibire, “On Reading the Icelandic Sagas,” p. 7.

⁷⁸⁵ As Aðalheiður Guðmundsdóttir has put it, the Icelanders “used the ancient source of legends as a base for a literary novelty that later became known as *fornaldarsögur norðurlanda*” and that the base material was “a well that Nordic people also drew from for other genres” in Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” *Viking and Medieval Studies* 2 (2007): 275-296, at 288. Harris posits that it is the Heroic group of *fornaldarsögur* that preserve the older eddic and narrative material and whose origin must be from the Migration Age; see “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 145.

Icelandic – the crucial impact of the Icelandic handling of the material was to shape it into a recognisable narrative form:

...a clear distinction has to be made between the provenance of saga-elements and story-motifs, and the saga-form om [*sic*] which Saxo based his work. It may be assumed that the Icelandic contribution consisted especially in the organization of heterogeneous and fragmentary story-material into a greater unity, fashioning sagas in conformity with a system.⁷⁸⁶

This recognises that material can be shared with other national literatures (e.g. Danish in the work of Saxo) but that the form and style of the saga are a distinctly Icelandic phenomenon. Whilst this view would seem to prevail, there is a hypothesis about the origins of the *fornaldarsögur* that involves the contact of Iceland with the Gaelic (Scottish and Irish) people.⁷⁸⁷ This contact gave rise to what are called the “Viking-Sagas,” a saga subgenre that is thought to have stemmed from Vikings in the West having contact with the Gaelic population, and this saga subgenre then spreading to Scandinavia and Iceland in the 11th century (although Gísli Sigurðsson points out that such a strong influence at such an early date is unlikely).⁷⁸⁸ The idea that the resultant “Viking-Sagas” take firm root in Iceland thus posits an important role for the both the contact and the sagas themselves in Norse literary history.⁷⁸⁹

⁷⁸⁶ Bjarni Guðnason, “The Icelandic Sources of Saxo Grammaticus,” p. 84.

⁷⁸⁷ This has been summarised by Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland* pp. 50-51. See also Peter Robinson, “Vikings and Celts,” *Introductory Essays on Egils saga and Njáls saga*, ed. John Hines and Desmond Slay (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1992) pp. 125-139. Both authors provide extensive bibliography.

⁷⁸⁸ Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*, p. 50.

⁷⁸⁹ See Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*, p. 50; Axel Olrik, *Nordisches Geistesleben in heidnischer und frühchristlicher Zeit*, Germanische Bibliothek series 5, Altertumskunde 1 (Heidelberg: Carl Winter, 1908) pp. 124-42 <<http://archive.org/stream/nordischesgeist00olriooog#page/n6/mode/2up>> [a translation of the Danish *Nordisk Aandsiv i Vikingstid og tidlig Middelalder*, 1907]; Alexander Bugge, “Havelok and Olaf Tryggvason,” *Saga-Book* 6 (1910) 257-95; “Irsk paavirkning paa den islandske saga,” *Til Gerhard Gran 9. December 1916 fra Venner og Elever* (Kristiania: Aschehoug, 1916) pp. 17-31 <http://urn.nb.no/URN:NBN:no-nb_digibok_2006102700027>. It is rejected by Andreas Heusler, *Die Anfänge der isländischen Saga*, at p. 391 ff., and by Finnur Jónsson, *Den oldnorske og oldislandske Litteraturs Historie*, p. 785. See also de Vries, *Heroic Song and Heroic Legend*, pp. 72-98; Hermann Pálsson, *Keltar á Íslandi* (Reykjavík: Háskólaútgáfan, 1997); Helgi Guðmundsson, *Um hafinnan: Vestrænir men og íslensk menning á miðöldum* (Reykjavík: Háskólaútgáfan, 1997); Bo Almqvist, „Gaelic/Norse folklore contacts: Some Reflections on their scope and character,” *Irland und Europa im früheren Mittelalter / Ireland and Europe in the early Middle Ages*, ed. Próinséas Ní Chatháin and Michael Richter (Stuttgart: Klett-Cotta): pp. 139-72; Diego Poli, “Scandinavians and Celts in the North Sea Area,” *Sagnaþing: helgæð Jónasi Kristjánssyni sjötugum 10. apríl 1994*, vol. 2 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska bókmenntafélag, 1994) pp. 665-668; Nicolas Jacobs, “Celtic Saga and the Contexts of Old English Elegiac Poetry,” *Études celtiques* 26 (1989): 95-142 (see also pp. 115-116, fn. 78 for additional references).

The Irish hypothesis was rejected by Andreas Heusler in 1913.⁷⁹⁰ Gísli counters the arguments Heusler brought against the hypothesis. Firstly, Heusler objects that the sagas found their written form not in the Western colonies or in Scandinavia, but in Iceland; to this, Gísli points out that Gaelic influence could well have occurred in Iceland during the settlement period, as the Irish were exported to Iceland as slaves, and would have told stories to entertain themselves.⁷⁹¹ Heusler's second objection is that no Irish saga is extant in Iceland;⁷⁹² Gísli contends that the Irish slave stories about their Gaelic ancestors would have held no attraction for a Norwegian or proto-Icelander; rather they would have encouraged the slaves to tell stories about Scandinavian heroes, and this would explain why Gaelic heroes are not found in old Nordic literature.⁷⁹³ How Gaelic slaves would have known exciting stories about Scandinavian heroes, Gísli does not say. Heusler's third argument against the "Viking-Sagas" hypothesis is that in Icelandic literary history *Íslendingasögur* and *konungasögur* are thought to have preceded to *fornaldarsögur*. Gísli objects that the *fornaldarsögur* are likely to be oldest subgenre in Icelandic saga literature, only one that developed early but was written late;⁷⁹⁴ and given the evidence for oral *fornaldarsögur* discussed above, this seems correct. Although it is unlikely to ever be accepted as a major theory to account for the development of the *fornaldarsögur*, the other suggestions of Irish influence on aspects of the *fornaldarsögur* narrative deduced by Gísli and others⁷⁹⁵

⁷⁹⁰ Heusler, *Die Anfänge der isländischen Saga*, p. 391. Heusler also provides a review of the earlier literature.

⁷⁹¹ Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*, pp. 30-33, 50.

⁷⁹² Heusler, *Die Anfänge der isländischen Saga*, pp. 391, 398-99. Heusler's arguments have been summarised by Andersson, *The Problem of Icelandic Saga Origins*, pp. 56-61.

⁷⁹³ Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*, p. 34.

⁷⁹⁴ Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*, pp. 50-51.

⁷⁹⁵ For an overview and further reading see Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*. See also in particular Einar Ól. Sveinsson, "Celtic Elements in Icelandic Tradition," *Béaloideas* 25 (1957): 3-24; Nora K. Chadwick, "Literary Tradition in the Old Norse and Celtic World," *Saga-Book* 14 (1953-55): 164-99; Jan de Vries, "Keltisch-Germanische Beziehungen im Gebiete der Heldensage," *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache und Literatur* 75 (1953): 229-247; Jan de Vries, *Kelten und Germanen*, Bibliotheca Germanica 9 (Bern: Francke, 1960); C. W. von Sydow, "Tors färd till Utgard," *Danske Studier* (1910): 65-105, 145-82. Joseph Harris has surveys tale types and the reflex of Celtic elements in *The Story of Rognvald and Raud* in *Flateyjarbók*, concluding that in order to better understand how the international tale types are used in *þattir*, more work needs to be done on adaptation as an artform in the Icelandic context; see "Folktale and Thattr: The Case of Rognvald and Raud," *Folklore and Medieval Studies*, ed. Carl Lindahl and Erika Brady, *Folklore Forum* 13.2-3 (1980): 158-198.

makes it seem likely that the Irish narrative material had some impact on vernacular Icelandic narrative traditions, even if they were not the stimulus.

One intriguing question in cross-cultural contacts such as that suggested above for Iceland and Ireland is in what language did communication take place between the Nordic and Gaelic population? Gísli Sigurðsson points out that although the Norse were integrated into Irish society by the start of the 11th century, the Old Norse language remained current until 13th century,⁷⁹⁶ while Michael Chesnutt has suggested that the *lingua Latina* must have been the *lingua franca*⁷⁹⁷ and thus have been the language in which any literary activity was carried to Iceland. Whilst he does not espouse the view that the *fornaldarsögur* are the product of “Viking-sagas” carried from Iceland, Gottskálk Jensson has recently suggested that Latin and a ‘Latin education’ involving grammatical training may be more directly responsible for the development of the *fornaldarsaga* subgenre than previously thought.⁷⁹⁸

In summarising the development of the *fornaldarsögur*, Gottskálk Jensson comments thus:

The composition of prosimetric as well as prose histories in the Middle Ages, even in the vernaculars, was surely the outgrowth of Latin learning and letters. Saxo shows only too well how the genre of *fornaldarsaga* is a learned, medieval, and Latin form, notwithstanding its other source in vernacular poetry – and its general vernacularization in later centuries.⁷⁹⁹

Gottskálk’s comment runs counter to received ideas about the development of the genre. Firstly, the prosimetric form is usually seen as indigenous, rather than as a form borrowed from the outside, although as I have argued above in connection with *Gylfaginning*, Latin literary customs will have undoubtedly produced tensions when they met with vernacular forms. Secondly, Saxo is usually assumed to have developed

⁷⁹⁶ Alexander Bugge, “Nordisk Sprog og Nordisk Nationalitet i Irland,” *Aarbøger for Nordisk Oldkyndighed og Historie* 15 (1900) 279-332, at 306-25 <<http://archive.org/stream/1900a01aarbger00norduoft#page/n285/mode/2up>>; Gísli Sigurðsson, *Gaelic Influence in Iceland*, p. 19.

⁷⁹⁷ Michael Chestnutt, “An Unsolved Problem in Old Norse-Icelandic Literary History,” *Mediaeval Scandinavia* 1 (1968): 122-137, at 126.

⁷⁹⁸ Gottskálk Jensson, “Were the Earliest *fornaldarsögur* Written in Latin?”

⁷⁹⁹ Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 290.

his *Gesta Danorum* from Old Norse material, some definitely in verse and other of it likely in prosimetric form, from Icelanders, rather than his authorial production being a shaping factor in Medieval Icelandic literary history.

Gottskálk's suggestion of the Latin origins of the *fornaldarsögur* is based on what the oldest chronicle and historiographical sources have to say about prose and prosimetrum in the *fornaldarsaga*-style. He reads Saxo's *Gesta Danorum*, imbued with *fornaldarsaga* content as it is, as a "ground breaking literary precedent,"⁸⁰⁰ and emphasises the Latin hypotext of Oddr Snorrason's *Yngvars saga víðförla*.⁸⁰¹ He concludes that Icelanders began to write *fornaldarsögur* in Old Norse following the example of these two Latin authors, "and that these learned Latin origins were a necessary precondition for this class of literature in the vernacular to arise."⁸⁰² This rather extreme hypothesis fails to take into consideration the likelihood of lengthy oral transmission of the genre, and the author does not defend his suggestion against the possibility that the *fornaldarsögur* developed from Heroic lays,⁸⁰³ instead describing written prose and prosimetry as "highly developed, late and literary form[s]."⁸⁰⁴ Although the parallels between Saxo and the *fornaldarsögur* must be acknowledged, it seems overhasty to assume that Saxo must be the source of the prosimetric style rather than a recipient of an already formed oral tradition. Overall, the focus of Gottskálk's argument seems too much on "literary erudition,"⁸⁰⁵ without the benefit of much nuance from the prospect of oral tradition, for the hypothesis of a Latin background for the *fornaldarsögur* to be very convincing at present.

⁸⁰⁰ Gottskálk Jensson, "Were the Earliest *fornaldarsögur* Written in Latin?," p. 82.

⁸⁰¹ Gottskálk Jensson, "Were the Earliest *fornaldarsögur* Written in Latin?," pp. 82-84.

⁸⁰² Gottskálk Jensson, "Were the Earliest *fornaldarsögur* Written in Latin?," p. 90. He expresses similar views in a more condensed manner in Judy Quinn et al., "Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*," pp. 280-282.

⁸⁰³ Anne Holtsmark, "Heroic Poetry and Legendary Sagas,"; Karsten Friis-Jensen, "Saxo Grammaticus og *fornaldarsagaerne*," *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighed. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Agneta Ney, Ármann Jakobsson and Annette Lassen (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 68-77.

⁸⁰⁴ Gottskálk Jensson, "Were the Earliest *fornaldarsögur* Written in Latin?," p. 81, fn. 3.

⁸⁰⁵ Gottskálk Jensson, "Were the Earliest *fornaldarsögur* Written in Latin?," pp. 79-91, at 81.

Margaret Clunies Ross accepts the background of classical and Latin literatures for vernacular Icelandic material as obvious, but rather than argue for direct inspiration from these foreign models, instead posits that sagas are an original development, although the saga literature naturally contains influences and borrowings.⁸⁰⁶ The distinction of the various types of saga, if it is accepted the development of the various types began at the same time, was an evolution that was “gradual and variable” and that revolved around cores of different types of poetry from which prosimetra developed, the *fornaldarsögur* developing around eddic poetry. *Völsunga saga* and *Hervarar saga* are given by Clunies Ross as obvious examples of this.⁸⁰⁷ The simultaneous development of the saga subgenres in different directions whilst remaining connected somehow at the base level is an important one in the light of the light of the sagas’ dependence on the prosimetric form in many cases, since this form is the route many indigenous saga subgenres took whilst developing around different types of poetry in different ways. Clunies Ross concludes that as literature, the prosimetric form “took off” as the primary form, and that the absence of stanzas in some sagas represents a moving away “from its traditional poetic base” since the genre was “labile.”⁸⁰⁸

It has been argued by scholars such as Lars Lönnroth and Davíð Erlingsson that the prose saga in the literate Icelandic tradition fulfilled the function formerly played by epic heroic verse in the pre-literary tradition. This development entailed a decrease in the narrative elements of the eddic poems and an increase in dialogue (the dramatic element).⁸⁰⁹ As a result of the two, narrative and drama, splitting, in the case of those

⁸⁰⁶ Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 278.

⁸⁰⁷ Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 277. It could be noted here that while both of these sagas develop around poetry that for the most part was pre-existent, from the evidence of the extant written sagas it seems that they did so in rather different ways. *Völsunga saga* cites individual quotations of ‘Poetic Edda’ type eddic poetry and clearly developed from an amalgamation of heroic poems, many of which can be found in the Codex Regius manuscript of *Poetic Edda*. *Hervarar saga* however seems to have developed around four lengthy poems that were included whole at the beginning and end of the saga. The prose is designed to bridge the gaps between them, rather than lifting its content from the poetry, as is the case in *Völsunga saga*.

⁸⁰⁸ Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 277.

⁸⁰⁹ Cf. Werner Ludwig, *Untersuchungen über den Entwicklungsgang und die Funktion des Dialogs in der isländischen Saga*, Rheinische Beiträge und Hilfsbücher zur germanischen Philologie und Volkskunde 23 (Halle (Saale): Max Niemeyer Verlag,

poems that are accompanied by prose, we see a development towards saga. This, according to Lönnroth and Ellingson, would explain why only particularly dramatic speeches can be thought to occur in verse in the sagas.⁸¹⁰

The most widely accepted theory of the development of the *fornaldarsögur* is that by Anne Holtsmark in 1965, who argues that the current prosimetric form of the *fornaldarsögur* developed from verses set in a framework of prose in the oral period. She suggests that the prose passages likely first accompanied verses in *fornaldarsaga*-like oral material for explanatory reasons and provided context, something she argues is directly the same as the purpose of the prose passages that appear around many of the poems in the collection of eddic poetry found in manuscript GkS 2635 4to, the Codex Regius of the Elder Edda. The basic principle was to narrate the action in prose to have the dialogue in verse, and it was the enlargement of these verses in the *fornaldarsaga* material that eventually formed the prosimetric *fornaldarsaga* as we have it today.⁸¹¹ A similar process is envisaged by Lars Lönnroth, who conceives of the verses of a *fornaldarsaga* as the “nucleus” around which the saga would be built up.⁸¹²

With regards to the oral *fornaldarsaga*-like material told wedding feast at Reykjahólar in 1119 discussed above, Ursula Brown describes the saga of Hrómundr Gripsson’s likely format as resembling “in form the Helgi lays of the *Edda*: i.e. it consisted of verses set in a simple narrative framework of prose,”⁸¹³ and Mitchell has suggested that this is likely to have been the origin for many of the *fornaldarsögur*: traditional poetic material transformed into prose sagas. This argument that would

1934) esp. pp. 7-9; Andreas Heusler, “Der Dialog in der altgermanischen erzählenden Dichtung,” *Kleine Schriften*, ed. Stefan Sonderegger, vol. 2, Kleinere Schriften zur Literatur- und Geistesgeschichte (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1969) pp. 611-689.

⁸¹⁰ Davíð Erlingsson, “Prose and Verse in Icelandic Legendary Fiction,” pp. 375, 379, 382; Lönnroth, “The Old Norse Analogue: Eddic Poetry and Fornaldarsaga,” pp. 78-79, 83-84; *Hjálmar’s Death Song and the Delivery of Eddic Poetry*, p. 196; Robert Kellogg too argues that the eddic poems and the *fornaldarsögur* are a result of the breakup of epic, Robert Kellogg, “The Prehistory of Eddic Poetry,” pp. 195ff.

⁸¹¹ Holtsmark, “Heroic Poetry and Legendary Sagas,” p. 15.

⁸¹² Lars Lönnroth, “The Double Scene of Arrow-Odd’s Drinking Contest” *Medieval Narrative. A Symposium*, ed. Hans Bekker-Nielsen, Andreas Haarder, Preben Meulengracht Sørensen & Peter Foote (Odense: Odense University Press, 1979) pp. 94-119, at 105.

⁸¹³ *Borgils saga ok Haflíða*, ed. Brown, p. 75.

also explain the genre's distinct preference for eddic rather than skaldic poetry.⁸¹⁴

Karsten Friis-Jensen summarises this evolutionary model:

jeg...tror på den evolutionsmodel, der hævder at den heroiske fornaldarsaga er en videreudvikling af den heroiske edda-digtning. Det bedste eksempel på denne udvikling er naturligvis *Völsunga saga*, der efter al sandsynlighed har en digtologi med nær forbindelse til Codex Regius af den ældre Edda som forlag. Den anden gruppe af fornaldarsagaer, vikingesagaerne, har muligvis undergået en tilsvarende udvikling, som Ursula Dronke påpegede i et af sine allerførste videnskabelige arbejder.... Denne generelle udviklingsmodel fra poesi til prosa, med mulighed for prosimetrisk mellemstadier, er en af flere mulige grundmodeller inden for mange slags litteraturer, ikke kun den nordiske.⁸¹⁵

The view that the *fornaldarsögur* as we have them now developed from eddic poetry with prose, such as *Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar* and *Helgakviða Hundingsbana önnur*, is held by several other scholars. Joseph Harris, for example, believes “there is a generic and probably a development continuum from the prosimetrum of some eddic poetry to that of the *fornaldarsögur*,”⁸¹⁶ and Torfi H. Tulinius also accepts Holtmark's evolutionary view of the *fornaldarsögur* developing from the prose passages of Eddic lays in the *Poetic Edda*. He locates the reason for this development from versiprose into prosimetric saga in the tandem developments in the poetic and historical traditions (which also influenced each other), for the ideological reasons of increasing the prestige and power of families and individuals through their genealogical connections.⁸¹⁷

Such a development of the prosimetric form in the *fornaldarsögur* from nuclei of previous poetry has also been placed as a part of the Indo-European tradition of mixed prose and verse forms.⁸¹⁸ Heather O'Donoghue has the following to say:

The use of verse in early Irish prose narrative is remarkably similar to Old Norse-Icelandic tradition, and the mixed form in Irish used to be regarded as a survival of ‘a partial or arrested form of a literary evolution which as run its full course in Indian literature’. Prosimetrum in Icelandic literature might

⁸¹⁴ Mitchell, *Heroic Sagas and Ballads*, pp. 67, 72.

⁸¹⁵ Karsten Friis-Jensen, “Saxo Grammaticus og fornaldarsagaerne,” *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighed. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Agneta Ney, Ármann Jakobsson and Annette Lassen (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 68-77, at p. 70. See also *Saxo Grammaticus as Latin Poet*, pp. 39-52 for an extended survey.

⁸¹⁶ Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 145. See also Andersson, “‘Helgakviða Hjörvarðssonar’ and European Bridal-Quest Narrative,” *Journal of English and Germanic Philology* 84 (1985): 51-75, at p. 52.

⁸¹⁷ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, pp. 55-63.

⁸¹⁸ West, *Indo-European Poetry and Myth*, p. pp. 61-62, see in particular p. 67 fn. 97 for further references.

then be understood as the result either of a similarly 'arrested development', or even of direct influence from the neighbouring Celtic tradition.⁸¹⁹

Both the Celtic and Icelandic cultures used the same form of long prose narratives peppered with poetry, a narrative method not common elsewhere in Europe at the time,⁸²⁰ although whether or not this shared form between the Irish and the Icelandic material is coincidental is impossible to say.⁸²¹ Nevertheless, the similar form found in Irish literature has been seen by Myles Dillon, its best known advocate, as having undergone the same developmental path as surmised for Sanskrit literature, in which "the narrative element [in ancient ballads] developed into epic and the dialogue element in drama."⁸²² Indeed, the developmental path suggested for the Indian material is almost identical to the development proposed independently for the Norse material by Holtsmark. Dillon draws upon the writings of Ernst Windisch and Hermann Oldenberg for the comparison of Irish to Indian material.⁸²³ Windisch's theory (and Oldenberg's after him) explains the nature of the dialogic Akhyana hymns (also known as the Samvada hymns) in the *Rigveda*, and suggests that although technically in verse, these hymns were actually in a mixed prose and verse form because in performance a reciter would add prose that explained both the context and content of the verse. Eventually, the unfixed prose was lost, but then later reciters improvised "the prose narrative to link the verses and give them a proper context for the benefit of his audience,"⁸²⁴ which was fixed in tradition and is found in the

⁸¹⁹ O' Donoghue, *Skaldic Verse* p. 1. In the quotation given she cites Proinsas Mac Cana, "Notes on the Combination of Prose and Verse in Early Irish Narrative," *Early Irish Literature – Media and Communication. Mundlichkeit und Schriftlichkeit in der frühen irischen Literatur*, ed. Stephen N. Tranter and Hildegard L. C. Tristram, ScriptOralia 10 (Tübingen, 1989) pp. 125-147, at p. 125.

⁸²⁰ Prosimetrum can also be found in medieval Latin writings, see Friss-Jensen, *Saxo Grammaticus as Latin Poet*, pp. 29-38; Peter Dronke, *Verse with Prose From Petronius to Dante: The Art and Scope of the Mixed Form* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard UP, 1994.)

⁸²¹ Peter Robinson, "Vikings and Celts," *Introductory Essays on Egils saga and Njáls saga*, ed. John Hines and Desmond Slay (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1992) pp. 125-139, at 125. See also Joseph Falaky Nagy, "Orality in Medieval Irish Narrative: An Overview," *Oral Tradition* 1.2 (1986): 272-301, at 281.

⁸²² M. L. Varapande, *History of Indian Theatre*, vol. 1 (New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 1987) 21.

⁸²³ Myles Dillon, *The Archaism of Irish Tradition*, Proceedings of the British Academy (London: 1947).

⁸²⁴ Varapande, *History of Indian Theatre*, p. 21.

brāhamas.⁸²⁵ According to Dillon, the prosimetric form in Indian literature demonstrated that this development never completed in Irish literature,⁸²⁶ and the similarly, the Norse prosimetra could be viewed as having stopped at a similar stage or have adopted this form from Celtic influence.⁸²⁷ This trajectory can be neither proven nor disproven.⁸²⁸

The final theory of the development of the *fornaldarsögur* that has been put forward by scholars is that the saga subgenre developed out of the *konungasögur*, and Ursula Dronke describes them as “a late, subsidiary development of the historical sagas.”⁸²⁹ Einar Ól. Sveinsson characterises the written sagas as initially a branch of the *konungasögur*, but one that quickly became independent.⁸³⁰ As such, it could be expected that the early written *fornaldarsögur* might display prosimetrum typical of a *konungasaga*, such as use of evidence verse and a relatively low number of speech stanzas. This theory is not necessarily easy to reconcile with the idea put forward by Lönnroth that the *fornaldarsögur* came about as a result of narrative and drama splitting, with the dialogue function being taken over by verse.⁸³¹

⁸²⁵ Ernst Winisch, *Geschichte der Sanskrit-Philologie und Indischen Altertumskunde* (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1992) esp. 404 ff. [1917, 1920, 1921]; Hermann Oldenberg, “Das altindische Ākhyāna, mit besonderer Rücksicht auf das Suparṇākhyāna,” *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft* 37 (1883): 54-86; Hermann Oldenberg, “Ākhyāna-Hymnen im R̥gveda,” *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft* 39 (1885): 52-90. Indu Shekhar summarises the argument and gives opposing views to the theory in *Sanskrit Drama: Its Origin and Decline* (Leiden: Brill, 1960) 4-5. See also Lawrence McCrea, “Ancient Narratives of South Asia,” *The Encyclopedia of the Novel*, ed. Peter Melville Logan, vol. 1 (Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2011) pp. 28-35.

⁸²⁶ Myles Dillon, *The Archaism of Irish Tradition*, p. 10. See Proinsias Mac Cana, “Notes on the Combination of Prose and Verse in Early Irish Narrative,” *Early Irish Literature – Media and Communication. Mundlichkeit und Schriftlichkeit in der frühen irischen Literatur*, ed. Stephen N. Tranter and Hildegard L. C. Tristram, *Script Oralia* 10 (Tübingen, 1989) pp. 125-147 for a more recent summary and reflection on Dillon’s arguments.

⁸²⁷ O’ Donoghue, *Skaldic Verse*, p. 1.

⁸²⁸ Cf. the conclusions of Mac Cana, “Notes on the Combination of Prose and Verse,” pp. 145-146.

⁸²⁹ Ursula Brown, “The Saga of Hromund Gripsson and Þorgilssaga,” *Saga-Book* 13 (1947-1948): 51-77, at p. 56.

⁸³⁰ Einar Ól. Sveinsson, “Fornaldarsögur,” *Kulturhistorisk Leksikon for Nordisk Middelalder* IV (1959): cols. 500-508, at col. 501.

⁸³¹ See also *Danakonunga sögur*, ed. Bjarni Guðnason, *Íslensk fornrit* 35 (Reykjavík: Hið íslenska fornritafélag, 1982) p. lxx; Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 61.

Should we conceive of the oral material as a “saga”? Brown conceives of the oral predecessor to written the *fornaldarsaga* as an “oral saga,” whereas both Mitchell and Torfi Tulinius consider the oral, old sources to be something other, and from it “a new literary form has gradually diverged.”⁸³² Whether or not we refer to the oral material in terms of a “saga” or not, it remains true that what we have in written form is the result of a process of development, if indeed the *fornaldarsögur* really did develop out of poetry, and not the process itself. The need to separate the development of the sagas at their oral and written stages is strongly put forward by Aðalheiður Guðmundsdóttir,⁸³³ whilst at the same time recognising that the *fornaldarsögur* in their written form drew upon “ancient and ongoing oral traditions.”⁸³⁴

⁸³² Torfi H. Tulinius, *Matter of the North*, p. 20.

⁸³³ Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” pp. 287-289.

⁸³⁴ Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” pp. 289.

Deciding whether the prose or verse is earlier in saga

Deciding whether the prose or verse of a particular saga is older a difficult task, but as, Einar Ólafur Sveinsson says, “vera má, að nokkrar vísur í fornaldarsögum séu ortar með penna í hendi.”⁸³⁵ One obvious method is to search for discrepancies between the prose and the verse, but as Bjarni Einarsson argues, there can be many reasons why a saga author may choose to include discrepancies between the prose and verse, and one cannot automatically assign primacy to the stanzas.⁸³⁶ For the sagas judged as older, it is usually assumed that the stanzas were primary and the existing prose is later. This is because of the sagas’ heroic content. When we suspect that a scene has been built up around existing verses, we do not know whether the verses are the only basis the author is using.⁸³⁷ In many cases where the *fornaldarsögur* cite verse, it is impossible to be certain whether the prose or the verse is older, i.e. whether the written saga prose is composed around pre-existing stanzas, or whether the stanzas were composed specifically for that narrative.

The poetry in the *fornaldarsögur* is often portrayed to be spoken by a legendary figure from the distant past, and eddic poetry is affiliated in nature with ancient times. In purporting to be spoken by legendary figures, the poetry is claiming to be ancient, and although we cannot be certain of the actual age of most eddic poetry, it seems some of poems are indeed old.⁸³⁸ *Hljóðskviða* (known in English as *The Battle of the Goths and the Huns*) from *Hervarar saga* (Heusler & Ranisch 1903: 1-12), *The Death Song of Hildibrandr* from *Ásmundar saga kappabana* (Heusler & Ranisch 1903: 53-54), and *Vikarsbálkar* from *Gautreks saga* (Heusler & Ransich 1903: 38-43) are thought to be amongst the oldest Old Norse poetry.⁸³⁹ Other narratives that seem to contain old

⁸³⁵ Einar Ólafur Sveinsson, *Íslenzkar bókmenntir í fornöld* (n.p.: Almenna bókafélagið, 1962) p. 195.

⁸³⁶ Bjarni Einarsson, “On the Rôle of Verse in Saga-Literature,” *Mediaeval Scandinavia* 7 (1974): 118-125.

⁸³⁷ Joseph Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” *Prosimetrum: Crosscultural Perspectives on Narrative in Prose and Verse*, ed. Joseph Harris & Karl Reichl (Cambridge: D. S. Brewer, 1997) pp. 131-163, at 141.

⁸³⁸ Margaret Clunies Ross, *A History of Old Norse Poetry and Poetics* (Cambridge: Brewer, 2005) 11.

⁸³⁹ Clunies Ross, *A History of Old Norse Poetry and Poetics* (Cambridge: Brewer, 2005) 11.

verse are *Vǫlsunga saga* and *Norna-Gests þáttr*,⁸⁴⁰ which contain eddic stanzas known from elsewhere and that must predate their saga context. External evidence indicates that *Hrólfs saga kraka* must also contain old material. The saga is preserved only in 17th century paper manuscripts and contains twelve instances of verse, but Saxo's inclusion of the *Bjarkamál* (see above) in a section to do with the Hrólfr kraki story material strongly suggests that in the 12th century a vernacular and prosimetric **Hrólfs saga* was in circulation, at least in Denmark.⁸⁴¹ Otherwise, it is difficult to tell whether poetry in the *fornaldarsögur* is older than the prose that contains it, or if it is the same age.

⁸⁴⁰ Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 146.

⁸⁴¹ Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 146.

Genre and Corpus

The purpose of this section is to examine the notion of the *fornaldarsaga* genre, particularly as it pertains to the inclusion of verses in the sagas.⁸⁴² The typology of genres that modern scholarship uses to discuss Old Norse literature is on the whole not a medieval one, especially where the *fornaldarsögur* are concerned;⁸⁴³ as discussed below, the life of the corpus and the title of the subgenre began in the 19th century with the publication of a collection of sagas assembled on the basis that they are set in pre-Christian Scandinavia before the settlement of Iceland. Whilst most terms for the types of sagas employed by modern critics to study the sagas are not found in medieval times (with the notable exception of *riddarasögur* in the field of romance sagas), something that Margaret Clunies Ross comments “may be taken to reflect the fact that fully agreed criteria based on sets of conventions representing the shared literary expectations of both writers and audiences did not exist during the formative period of the *fornaldarsaga* and other saga kinds,”⁸⁴⁴ certain codicological decisions in medieval manuscripts seem to indicate that while Icelandic medieval scribes did not have an articulated genre system, certain types of sagas were thought to go together in books. The most convincing evidence of this is found in the great *konungasögur* and *Íslendingasögur* collections, for example *Fagrskinna* (*konungasögur*) and *Möðruvallabók* (*Íslendingasögur*), and the contents of *Möðruvallabók* have to some degree shaped the boundaries of the genre of the sagas of the Icelanders.⁸⁴⁵ There are several examples among the earlier Romance codices that could be described as ‘romance anthologies,’ such as the manuscripts AM 343 a 4to and AM 471 4to, two related vellum manuscripts from the 15th century. AM 343 a 4to groups *fornaldarsögur* and

⁸⁴² For a debate on many of the issues touched upon here, see Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 275-296.

⁸⁴³ For this reason, Clunies Ross chooses to use two different spellings of the saga genre suffix, spelling terms that cannot be found in medieval sources in modern Icelandic (*-sögur*) and terms that are attested in medieval Icelandic in classical (13th century) Icelandic (*-sögur*). I have used *-sögur* throughout. See Clunies Ross, *The Cambridge Introduction to The Old Norse-Icelandic Saga*, Cambridge Introductions to Literature (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010) xi-xii.

⁸⁴⁴ Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 276-277.

⁸⁴⁵ *Möðruvallabók* is AM 132 fol., written between 1330 and 1370, and is the first extant codex to contain only *Íslendingasögur*. See Clunies Ross, *The Cambridge Introduction*, p. 144.

riddarasögur together, while AM 471 4to groups *Íslendingasögur* together with those *fornaldarsögur* that have been described as leaning towards that subgenre (see below), and one popular *riddarasaga*. AM 343 a 4to has the following contents, in manuscript order:

1. *Þorsteins þáttr bæjarmagns* (1r-5v);
2. *Samsons saga fagra* (5v-14r);
3. *Egils saga einhenda og Ásmundar berserkjabana* (14r-21v);
4. *Flóres saga konungs og sona hans* (21v-30v);
5. *Vilhjálmss saga sjóðs* (30v-48v);
6. *Yngvars saga víðfjrla* (48v-54r);
7. *Ketils saga hængs* (54r-57v);
8. *Gríms saga loðinkinna* (57v-59v);
9. *Qrvar-Odds saga* (59v-81v);
10. *Áns saga bogsveigis* (81v-87r);
11. *Sálus saga ok Nikanórs* (87r-98v);
12. *Hálfðanar saga Eysteinsonar* (99r-103v);
13. *Bósa saga* (2 fragments: the first on 103v, the second on 104);
14. *Vilmundar saga víðutan* (105r-108r);
15. *Perus saga meistara* (108r-110r).

Of the fifteen sagas, nine are *fornaldarsögur* and six are *riddarasögur*. AM 471 4to preserves the following sagas:

1. *Þórðar saga hreðu* (1r-21v);
2. *Króka-Refs saga* (21v-36r);
3. *Kjalnesinga saga* (36r-49r);
4. *Ketils saga hængs* (49r-56v);
5. *Gríms saga loðinkinna* (57r-60v);
6. *Qrvar-Odds saga* (61r-96v);
7. *Viktors saga ok Blávus* (96v-108v).

These are three *Íslendingasögur* (which lean towards the Romance sagas), three *fornaldarsögur* and one *riddarasaga*. Although typologies are not explicit in such codices, they are suggested. There is, then, no medieval description of the

fornaldarsögur genre beyond what we can glean from certain codicological decisions made by medieval compilers.

Modern classification of the *fornaldarsögur* is descriptive. ‘*Fornaldarsaga Norðurlanda*’ is not a medieval term but rather was coined by the Dane Carl Christian Rafn (1795-1864), who first collected together thirty-two similar sagas from manuscripts and published them under that title in his three volume edition of 1829-1830 in Copenhagen.⁸⁴⁶ ‘*Norð(u)rlanda*’ [‘of the Northern/Nordic lands’] is sometimes appended as a clarifying element to *fornaldarsögur*, since all these tales are set in ancient Scandinavia (as opposed to Iceland, the scene of much other medieval Icelandic literature).⁸⁴⁷ Rafn’s rationale was in selecting the sagas was those “er orðit hafa hér á Norðrlöndum, áðr enn Island byggðist á 9dn öld” [‘which are set here in the Nordic countries before Iceland was settled in the ninth century’].⁸⁴⁸ To all intents and purposes these criteria remain unchanged and the subgenre label *fornaldarsaga* has stuck: “time has proved it an apt term.”⁸⁴⁹ The sagas and *þættir* [‘short tales,’ sg. *þáttr*] making up the *fornaldarsögur* corpus are those then that take place in Scandinavia before the settlement of Iceland (and thus before, as Torfi H. Tulinius notes, the unification of Norway by Haraldr hárfagri), and so what separates the *fornaldarsögur* from “other sagas is their chronological and geographical setting.”⁸⁵⁰

⁸⁴⁶ This is counting what Rafn titles *Frá Fornjóti ok hans ættmönnum* as two texts, since it is made up of *Hversu Noregr byggðist* and *Fundinn Noregr*. See *Fornaldar Sögur Norðurlanda, eptir gömlum handritum*, ed. C. C. Rafn, 3 vols. (Copenhagen: n. p., 1829-30).

⁸⁴⁷ Cf. Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 19.

⁸⁴⁸ *Fornaldar Sögur Norðurlanda, eptir gömlum handritum*, ed. C. C. Rafn, vol. 1 (Copenhagen: n. p., 1829) v.

⁸⁴⁹ Torfi H. Tulinius, “Sagas of Icelandic Prehistory (*fornaldarsögur*),” *A Companion to Old Norse-Icelandic Literature and Culture*, ed. Rory McTurk, Blackwell Companions to Literature and Culture 31 (Malden, MA: Blackwell, 2007) pp. 447-461, at p. 447. Similarly, Ármann Jakobsson comments that the term *fornaldarsaga* “has now become integrated into our way of thinking about sagas” in Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 282, and in the same collective article at p. 279, Torfi defends the term on the basis that “a minimal definition of the *fornaldarsögur* as genre is actually quite good: ‘*Fornaldarsögur* are the sagas that C. C. Rafn published under this blanket title.’”

⁸⁵⁰ Torfi H. Tulinius, “Sagas of Icelandic Prehistory (*fornaldarsögur*),” p. 447.

The *fornaldarsögur* corpus according to Rafn is made up of the following sagas, which I here divide into prose-only sagas and those containing verse:⁸⁵¹

Prose-only sagas:

1. *Af Upplendinga konungum;*
2. *Egils saga einhenda ok Ásmundar berserkjabana*
3. *Eiríks saga víðförla*
4. *Fundinn Noregr*
5. *Göngu-Hrólfs saga*
6. *Hálfðanar saga Brönufóstra*
7. *Hálfðanar saga Eysteinnsonar*
8. *Högna saga Hálfðanarsonar*⁸⁵²
9. *Hrólfs saga Gautrekssonar*
10. *Hrómundar saga Gripssonar*
11. *Hversu Noregr byggðist*
12. *Illuga saga Gríðarfóstra*
13. *Sögubrot af nokkrum fornkonungum í Dana ok Svíaveldi*
14. *Sörla saga sterka*
15. *Þorsteins saga Víkingssonar*

Fornaldarsögur with verse:

1. *Áns saga bogsveigis*
2. *Ásmundar saga kappabana*
3. *Bósa saga ok Herraudís*
4. *Friðþjófs saga frækna*
5. *Gautreks saga ok Gjafa-Refs*
6. *Gríms saga loðinkinna*
7. *Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka*

⁸⁵¹ *Fornaldar Sögur Norðrlanda*, ed. Rafn.

⁸⁵² Also known as *Héðins saga ok Högna* or *Sörla þátr.*

8. *Heiðreks saga konungs ok Hervarar*⁸⁵³
9. *Hjálmþe(r)s saga ok Qlvis*
10. *Hrólf's saga kraka*
11. *Ketils saga hængs*
12. *Norna-Gests þáttir*
13. *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*
14. *Ragnarssona þáttir*⁸⁵⁴
15. *Sturlaugs saga starfsama*
16. *Sqrla þáttir*
17. *Vqlsunga saga*
18. *Qrvar-Odds saga*

Guðni Jónsson and Bjarni Vilhjálmsson extended the corpus in their edition, adding *Yngvars saga víðförla*, *Þorsteins þáttir bæjarmagns*, *Göngu-Hrólf's saga*, and *Helga þáttir Þórissonar*.⁸⁵⁵ The last two contain verse.

Hermann Pálsson takes exception to a selection policy such as Rafn's when he writes "Where else in the world of literary studies do we find the nationality of the protagonist serving as the sole factor for determining the category to which a story belongs?"⁸⁵⁶ since the *Íslendingasögur* ['Sagas of the Icelanders'] and *Íslendingaþættir* ['Short Stories of the Icelanders'] are also chosen on similar grounds, admittance to the corpus demanding that the protagonist be an Icelander.⁸⁵⁷ Other attempts distinguish the *fornaldarsögur* from other saga genres are more descriptive in nature, and often include observations that they have "traditional heroes, eddic-style poetry, wide-

⁸⁵³ Also known as *Hervarar saga*.

⁸⁵⁴ Also known as *Þáttir af Ragnarssonum*.

⁸⁵⁵ The numbers in brackets after the title of the saga is the number of stanzas that the saga contains, according to the three volume collection edited by Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsson, *Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, 3 vols. (Reykjavík: Bókaútgáfan Forni, 1943-1944). Cf. my discussion of the selection of the corpus below.

⁸⁵⁶ Hermann Pálsson, "Towards a Definition of *Fornaldarsögur*," *Fourth International Saga Conference* (München: Institut für Nordische Philologie der Universität München, 1979) p. 5 (papers paginated individually).

⁸⁵⁷ As Diana Whaley notes, the *konungasögur* are a slightly different case, not least because although the Kings' sagas are written by Icelanders, they are mostly about Norwegian monarchs. In opposition to Hermann Pálsson, Whaley sees the major defining criteria of sagas, especially *fornaldarsögur* and *samtíðarsögur*, as their narrative distance from the time of the events related. She points out that the *konungasögur* cover all time periods, from the legendary past to the recent periods. Diana Whaley, "The Kings' Sagas," p. 45.

ranging geography, and occasional trips to the Otherworld,”⁸⁵⁸ or, as Lars Lönnroth comments, describe the sagas as “fictional,” “fantastic,” and “stories told for pure entertainment,” in order to juxtapose them with the realism of the *Íslendingasögur*.⁸⁵⁹ The latter statements are particularly unhelpful in this regard, since they deal not so much with the text itself, but rather to the reaction of the audience to the text.⁸⁶⁰

Others have called for a complete reassessment of the overall genre system in Old Norse literature, largely as a result of the problems caused texts which fit into more than one type of saga subgenre; these are perhaps usefully thought of as ‘hybrid’ texts in the sense that they straddle generic boundaries.⁸⁶¹ Hermann Pálsson argues that genre categories ought to accommodate each individual saga in only one type, and that “the criteria used for classificatory purposes should be chosen on scientific principles and rigorously applied”;⁸⁶² Matthew Driscoll on the other hand supports the hybridity of both the genre designations and the sagas themselves: “Not all the sagas normally classed as *fornaldarsögur* will exhibit all these features, and some of the features will also be found in sagas normally regarded as being of other types. This is, after all, the nature of all such generic distinctions, which does not...render them any less useful.”⁸⁶³ Marianne Kalinke suggests approaching the medieval Icelandic literary material as examples of “different narrative types” in order to go beyond the setting of

⁸⁵⁸ Mitchell, *Heroic Sagas and Ballads*, p. 13.

⁸⁵⁹ Lars Lönnroth, “The Concept of Genre in Saga Literature,” *Scandinavian Studies* 47 (1975): 419-426, at 419-420.

⁸⁶⁰ Paul Bibire, “From Riddarasaga to Lygisaga: The Norse Response to Romance,” *Les sagas de chevaliers (Riddarasögur)*, ed. Régis Boyer, *Civilisations* 10 (Toulon: Juillet, 1982) pp. 55-74, at 55.

⁸⁶¹ See also Elizabeth Ashman Rowe, “Generic Hybrids: Norwegian ‘Family’ Sagas and Icelandic ‘Mythic-Heroic’ Sagas,” *Scandinavian Studies* (1993) 65:539-554.

⁸⁶² Hermann Pálsson, “Towards a Definition of *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 5. Note that other scholars such as Rudolf Keyser had noted that, despite their efforts to classify the sagas, it is impossible to draw a sharp line between them. Keyser for example divides the saga genre into mythical-heroic sagas, romantic sagas, and historical sagas in *Nordmændenes Videnskabelighed* p. 344, and into poetic/fictitious sagas (including the mythic and romantic sagas) and historical sagas (including histories, in which he counts the *Íslendingasögur*, and biographies) in *Religion of the Northmen*, trans. Barclay Pennock (New York: Norton, 1854) p. 60.

⁸⁶³ Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 294.

Nordic *forn öld* and to “take into account such other indicators of genre as form, style, structure, context, nature of the protagonists and their quests, and function.”⁸⁶⁴

A useful starting point in a discussion of genre and corpus context for the *fornaldarsögur* is Stephen A. Mitchell’s definition, which he calculates to include distinguishing characteristics of the *fornaldarsögur* but not those aspects that they share with other saga subgenres:

fornaldarsögur: Old Icelandic prose narratives based on traditional heroic themes, whose numerous fabulous episodes and motifs create an atmosphere of unreality.⁸⁶⁵

Some years later, Mitchell proposed another way to define the *fornaldarsögur*:

if, for example, our main interest were simply to show as efficiently as possible how the *fornaldarsögur* can be distinguished from other varieties of saga writing, we could content ourselves by saying they are the sagas that contain eddic-style poetry.⁸⁶⁶

The second definition is of particular interest. As far as the first definition offered by Mitchell, whilst the supernatural is certainly central to the *fornaldarsögur*, this is not a definite criterion to divide the sagas from other subgenres; as I have argued elsewhere “their narrative worlds are rooted in our reality” and they blend “the gritty realism of the *Íslendingasögur* ... smoothly with fantastic occurrences, supernatural beings and a multitude of Other Worlds.”⁸⁶⁷ I also doubt that being based on “traditional heroic themes” is a suitable characteristic to be included in a definition without qualifiers; as Matthew Driscoll notes, only some of the *fornaldarsögur* have a basis in the older heroic tradition (such as *Völsunga saga* and *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*), and have been accorded merit on that basis. Others, such as *Egils saga einhenda ok Ásmundar berserkjabana* and *Bósa saga ok Herrauðs*, are clearly not related to an old heroic

⁸⁶⁴ Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” pp. 275-276.

⁸⁶⁵ Mitchell, *Heroic Sagas and Ballads*, p. 27.

⁸⁶⁶ Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 287.

⁸⁶⁷ Helen F. Leslie, “Border Crossings: Landscape and the Other World in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” *Scripta Islandica* 60 (2009): 119-135.

tradition in origin or theme, rather being closer to the romance tradition, and their literary qualities have been derided.⁸⁶⁸ Most problematic is that these narratives are not wholly prose: like other saga genres described as prosaic, they are in fact prosimetric, that is, they contain a good deal of verse interspersed in the prose.⁸⁶⁹ More specifically, whereas the *Íslendingasögur* ['sagas of Icelanders'] and *konungasögur* ['sagas of kings'] contain large amounts of skaldic verse, the *fornaldarsögur* contain mainly eddic verse, suggesting an immediate connection in their development with the eddic tradition,⁸⁷⁰ as I have discussed. From this perspective, it seems that Mitchell's second suggestion of the *fornaldarsögur* being those sagas that contain eddic-style poetry warrants closer investigation.

Divisions of the *Fornaldarsögur* Subgenre

Although both the genre definition of the *fornaldarsögur* and the corpus have been problematized, Rafn's selection of sagas, made on the basis of the saga being set in the Nordic lands before the settlement of Iceland, established a corpus that, in practical terms, remains largely unchanged today.⁸⁷¹ The normal genre grouping has been challenged on the grounds that the sagas fulfill the criteria of being set in ancient Scandinavia before the settlement of Iceland are in fact rather dissimilar to each other,⁸⁷² although this has not prevented several studies that analyse the *fornaldarsögur* as though they were a cohesive group in terms of content.⁸⁷³ The problem of unlike

⁸⁶⁸ Matthew James Driscoll, "A New Edition of the *Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*. Some Basic Questions," *On Editing Old Scandinavian Texts: Problems and Perspectives*, ed. Fulvio Ferrari and Massimiliano Bampi (Trento: Università degli studi di Trento, Dipartimento di studi letterari, linguistici e filologici, 2009) pp. 71-84, at 72.

⁸⁶⁹ For an overview of Old Norse prosimetric tendencies, see Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives."

⁸⁷⁰ Torfi H. Tulinius, "Sagas of Icelandic Prehistory (*fornaldarsögur*)," p. 448.

⁸⁷¹ Although the additions made by Guðni Jónsson are by and large accepted; see above and cf. Driscoll 2009: 73-74.

⁸⁷² Torfi H. Tulinius, "Sagas of Icelandic Prehistory (*fornaldarsögur*)," p. 448.

⁸⁷³ For example, Righter-Gould's study of the structure of *fornaldarsögur* in "The *Fornaldar Sögur Norðurlanda*: A Structural Analysis," *Scandinavian Studies* 52.4 (1980): 423-441 and Hallberg's treatment of the *fornaldarsögur* as a corpus in "Some Aspects of the *Fornaldarsögur* as a Corpus," *Arkiv for nordisk fiologi* 97 (1982): 1-35. Righter-Gould's conclusions have been deemed "unconvincing and unacceptable" by Marianne Kalinke since her findings are equally applicable to the *riddarasögur*, although from the point of view of genre development, this makes Righter-Gould's results even more interesting; see Marianne E. Kalinke, "Riddarasögur, Fornaldarsögur and the Problem of Genre," *Les sagas de chevaliers (Riddarasögur)*, ed. Régis Boyer, *Civilisations* 10 (Toulon: Juillet, 1982) pp. 77-87, at p. 81.

forms (i.e. prosimetric or non-prosimetric) has not occupied scholarly discussion. I propose this as an area of interest since the prosimetric form of many of the *fornaldarsögur* thought to be older is taken to be an indicator of how the genre may have developed. The focus has rather been on grouping the *fornaldarsögur* into categories that reflect their thematic content, although, as I will demonstrate, this often coincides with whether or not a particular group of sagas is prosimetric.

Scholars have attempted to compensate for the subgenre's lack of internal cohesiveness by dividing the corpus into subcategories, the most enduringly popular being Helga Reuschel's 1933 division of the corpus into *Heldensagas* ['Heroic sagas'], *Wikingersagas* ['Viking sagas'], and *Abenteuersagas* ['Adventure sagas'],⁸⁷⁴ subdivisions that became entrenched by Kurt Schier's adoption of them in his handbook of 1970. Below are the subdivisions of *fornaldarsögur* following Schier.⁸⁷⁵

The letters in parentheses after the saga name indicate which other subdivisions the saga leans towards: H = *Heldensaga*/Heroic saga; W = *Wikingersaga*/Viking saga; A = *Abenteuersaga*/Adventure saga.⁸⁷⁶ A superscript 'P' after the saga title indicates the saga is prosimetric.

Heldensaga/Heroic sagas:

- *Völsunga saga*^P
- *Norna-Gests þáttur*^P
- *Hervarar saga*^P (W)
- *Hrólfs saga kraka*^P
- *Sögubrot af nokkrum fornkonungum* (H)
- *Ásmundar saga kappabana*^P (W)

⁸⁷⁴ Helga Reuschel, *Untersuchungen über Stoff und Stil der Fornaldarsaga*, Bausteine zur Volkskunde und Religionswissenschaft 7 (Bühl-Baden: Konkordia, 1933).

⁸⁷⁵ Kurt Schier, *Sagalitteratur* (Stuttgart: Metzler, 1970) 86-91.

⁸⁷⁶ Note that I have excluded here *Þiðreks saga af Bern* and *Hemings Þáttur Áslákssonar*, since although Schier includes them at the periphery of his discussion of the *fornaldarsögur* subgenre, he does not place them in the subdivisions he borrows from Reuschel. Both sagas are related to the *fornaldarsögur* but are not *fornaldarsögur* themselves. *Ynglinga saga* occupies a similar position on the border of the subgenre.

Wikingersaga /Viking sagas:

- *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*^P (H, A)
- *Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka*^P (H, A)
- *Qrvar-Odds saga*^P
- *Ketils saga hængs*^P (A)
- *Gríms saga loðinkinna*^P (A)
- *Áns saga bogsveigis*^P (A)
- *Friðþjófs saga frækna*^P
- *Hrómundar saga Gripssonar*

Abenteuersaga /Adventure sagas:

- *Sorla þáttur*^P (H)
- *Gautreks saga*^P (W, H)
- *Hrólfs saga Gautrekssonar*
- *Bósa saga*^P
- *Göngu-Hrólfs saga*^P
- *Egils saga einhenda ok Ásmundar berserkjabana*
- *Hjálmþérs saga ok Ölvis*^P
- *Hálfðanar saga Eysteinsonar*
- *Hálfðanar saga Brönufóstra*
- *Sturlaugs saga starfsama*
- *Illuga saga Gríðarfóstra*
- *Þorsteins saga Víkingssonar*

Reuschel and Schier attempt to introduce a certain flexibility into their typology by indicating other subcategories of which the sagas display characteristics. The above list shows that all of the Heroic sagas are prosimetric (*Sögubrot* is an exception, but the fragmentary text only leans towards this category). Likewise, the Viking sagas are predominantly prosimetric, the exception being *Hrómundar saga Gripssonar*, which can be explained by the fact that this saga is based on long, later (most are post-medieval) metrical narratives (*rímur*), as mentioned. However, in a previous,

unrecoverable form, the saga (or a similar saga) did once contain lots of stanzas, as the account of the wedding at Reykjahólar discussed above tells us. The Adventure sagas are predominantly prose. *Sqrla þátr* and *Gautreks saga* both lean towards the other categories in content, and confirmation of this can be seen by their prosimetric form. *Bósa saga*, marked as prosimetric, contains only one sequence of stanzas, a metric charm (more of a curse), known as *Buslubæn* [‘Busla’s Prayer’], which is followed by a runic inscription in certain of its manuscripts,⁸⁷⁷ and nor is *Göngu-Hrólfs saga* heavily prosimetric, containing only three stanzas. Of Reuschel’s and Schier’s sagas classed only as adventures sagas, only *Hjálmþes saga ok Ölvis* is heavily prosimetric, containing forty six stanzas, but this saga is rather late, found in 17th to 19th century manuscripts. It is dated earlier on the basis of *Hjálmþérsrímur*, a 15th century analogue, but the development of the saga itself and its form is obscure.⁸⁷⁸

Hermann Pálsson makes the alternative suggestion that the *fornaldarsögur* be divided into two subgroups: ‘hero legends’ and ‘adventure tales’ (he also considers ‘Viking romances’ to be a possible label rather than ‘adventure tales’).⁸⁷⁹ Torfi H. Tulinius interprets Hermann Pálsson’s division to be between the earlier and later *fornaldarsögur*, the earlier being the heroic sagas and the later the adventure sagas.⁸⁸⁰ The latter category, the adventure tales, would presumably be a blending of the Viking sagas and Adventure sagas as delineated by Reuschler and Schier; this does not alleviate the problem of unlike forms, since the prosimetric *fornaldarsögur* in the Adventure group are simply lumped together with the prosimetric Viking sagas, along

⁸⁷⁷ See Claiborne W. Thompson, “The Runes in *Bósa saga ok Herraúðs*,” *Scandinavian Studies* 50 (1978): 50-56.

⁸⁷⁸ Ralph O’Connor, “‘Stepmother sagas.’ An Irish Analogue for *Hjálmþés saga ok Ölvés*,” *Scandinavian Studies* 72 (2000): 1-48, at 1-2.

⁸⁷⁹ Hermann Pálsson, “Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda,” *Dictionary of the Middle Ages*, ed. Joseph L. Strayer, vol. 6 (New York: Scribner, 1985) pp. 137-143, at p. 138. See also for example Hermann Pálsson’s publication with Paul Edwards of *Seven Viking Romances* (Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1985) which contains English translations of *Örvar-Odds saga*, *Gautreks saga*, *Hálfðanar saga Eysteinsonar*, *Bósa saga ok Herraúðs*, *Egils saga einhenda ok Ásmundar berserkjabana*, *Þorsteins þátr Þejarmagns*, and *Helga þátr Þórissonar*. All these sagas fall into Hermann Pálsson’s group of Adventure stories (or Viking Romance). Elizabeth Ashman Rowe provides an interesting table denoting what separates Heroic Legends and Adventure Tales in Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 285, but does not consider the prosimetric aspect of the division.

⁸⁸⁰ Torfi H. Tulinius, *Matter of the North*, p. 20.

with the non prosimetric texts of each group. From the perspective of whether verse is included, this simplification of saga groups is not an improvement.

Reuschel and Hermann Pálsson both create their sub-groups on the basis of important aspects of the material and content of the *fornaldarsögur*: they come out of heroic legends and traditions, stories of Viking travellers, myth and folktales, and influences from continental romance traditions.⁸⁸¹ Heroic sagas/hero legends and adventure stories are set at two extremes of content, with Viking tales in between. Certainly the *fornaldarsögur* are in many ways a hybrid genre in terms of their use of material, and from this perspective Lars Lönnroth counters these attempts to introduce divisions into the corpus by suggesting we perhaps ought “uppfatta alla fornaldarsagor som blandade eller hybridartade texter med store eller mindre inslag av Edda-myt, hjältesaga, folksaga och riddarroman” [‘perceive all *fornaldarsögur* as mixed or hybrid-like texts with larger or smaller elements of Edda-myth, heroic saga, folktale and tales of chivalry’].⁸⁸² Along the same line of thought, a more nuanced categorisation in terms of content is to be found in the work of Elizabeth Ashman Rowe, whose classification acknowledges the hybridity of the *fornaldarsögur* by dividing the legendary sagas into genealogies and regnal lists, Germanic heroic legends and Scandinavian mythology, Kings’ sagas, family sagas and romances:⁸⁸³

Genealogies and Regnal Lists:

- *Sögubrot af fornkonungum*
- *Fundinn Noregr*
- *Hversu Noregr byggðist*

⁸⁸¹ Torfi H. Tulinius, “Sagas of Icelandic Prehistory (*fornaldarsögur*),” pp. 448-449.

⁸⁸² Lars Lönnroth, “Fornaldarsagans genremässiga metamorfoser: mellan Edda-myt och riddarroman,” *Fornaldarsagornas struktur och ideologi. Handlingar från ett symposium i Uppsala 31.8-2.9 2001*, ed. Ármann Jakobsson, Annette Lassen & Agnete Ney (Uppsala: Uppsala Universitet, 2003) pp. 37-45, at p. 44.

⁸⁸³ Elizabeth Ashman Rowe, *Fabula i þeim bestu sögum. Studies in the Genre of the Medieval Icelandic Mytho-Heroic Saga* (Ann Arbor, MI: University Microfilms, 1990) 26.

- *Af Upplendinga konungum*

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- *Völsunga saga*^P
- *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*^P
- *Þáttr af Ragnars sonum*^P
- *Hervarar saga*^P
- *Hrólfs saga kraka*^P
- *Ásmundar saga kappabana*^P

Kings' sagas:

- *Þorsteins þáttr bæjarmagns*
- *Helga þáttr Þórissonar*^P
- *Norna-Gests þáttr*^P
- *Tóka þáttr Tókasonar*
- *Sqrla þáttr*^P

Family sagas:

- *Ketils saga hængs*^P
- *Gríms saga loðinkinna*^P
- *Áns saga bogsveigis*^P
- *Qrvar-Odds saga*^P

Romances:

- *Qrvar-Odds saga*^P
- *Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka*^P
- *Hrómundar saga Gripssonar*
- *Hálfðanar saga Brönufóstra*
- *Sqrla saga sterka*
- *Sturlaug's saga starfsama*^P
- *Göngu-Hrólfs saga*^P
- *Þorsteins saga Víkingssonar*
- *Hálfðanar saga Eysteinsonar*

-
- *Gautreks saga*^P
 - *Hrólfs saga Gautrekssonar*
 - *Hjálmþés saga ok Ölvis*^P
 - *Egils saga ok Ásmundar*
 - *Bósa saga ok Herrauðs*^P

This division serves to illustrate the other genres towards which the *fornaldarsögur* variously lean. There is also a clear pattern in terms of the prosimetric form. This is not to say that Rowe's classification is without problems; certainly some sagas could fit into more than one category (and indeed *Orvar-Odds saga* is listed twice), nor does she consider all the sagas usually held to be in the corpus, but overall this seems a useful scheme with which to consider the role of the verse in the *fornaldarsögur*. This is not to say that I expect sagas in Rowe's groups to have the same prosimetric profile; even the briefest glance at, for example, the Family Saga group will reveal the sagas are rather different in their use of verse. Nevertheless, the groupings can be said to exhibit elements of ethnic grouping (Ben-Amos): the sagas in the Family group are most often found together in manuscripts, for example; *Ragnars saga* is, in its main manuscript, a continuation of *Völsunga saga*.⁸⁸⁴

⁸⁸⁴ Klaus von See has argued that the two works were originally one, see "Die kulturideologische Stellung der Völsunga saga ok Ragnars saga," *Europa und der Norden im Mittelalter* (Heidelberg: Winter, 1999) pp. 397-412 [Originally published in *Studien zum Altgermanischen: Festschrift für Heinrich Beck*, ed. H. Uecker (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1994) pp. 584-600], although Carolyne Larrington highlights their divergent natures in "Völsunga saga, Ragnars saga and Romance in Old Norse: Revisiting Relationships," *The Legendary Sagas: Origin and Development*, ed. Annette Lassen, Agneta Ney and Ármann Jakobsson (Reykjavík: University of Iceland Press, 2012) pp. 251-269.

The Fornaldarsögur Containing Verse: A Prosimetric Analysis

Here I present an analysis of the prosimetrum of each saga. For the sagas with more verses, I have outlined the character of the prosimetrum of the saga, discussed its manuscript preservation and redaction history, and then carried out an analysis on the basis of these redactions. For those sagas or *þættir* with few verses, I have outlined the manuscript preservation of the saga and then discussed the prosimetric qualities of the stanza(s). Note that while it would have been preferable to check manuscripts of the *fornaldarsögur*, due to the large number of sagas covered, my comments here are limited to editions and the information contained therein.

The first line of stanzas is offered by way of orientation; since they do not pertain to my argument I have not translated them. I have otherwise translated quotations when it makes my point clearer. Where an accurate, modern translation exists I have used it and a reference will be found in an accompanying footnote; stanzas and prose with no citation for the translation I have translated myself.

I offer a fairly detailed reading of each saga, sometimes stanza by stanza, because this is necessary in order to gauge the different roles of the verse in the sagas, to determine the prosimetric structure of episodes in the sagas, to determine the performance context of each stanzas, and to discuss how the construction of the saga as a whole is influenced or determined by the prosimetra that occur within it. I discuss each saga episode by episode, and then at the end of the presentation of prosimetric scenes, I draw together conclusions about the role of verse in each saga and what it might be able to tell us about Old Norse prosimetra, and whether the prosimetra discussed are purely literary or whether they might have roots in the oral period.

Germanic Heroic Legends and Scandinavian Mythology

Völsunga saga

Völsunga saga is preserved in the same vellum manuscript as *Ragnars saga*, NKS 1824 b 4to, from c. 1400 (see above), as well as in several paper copies.⁸⁸⁵ The saga is quoted from this manuscript via the edition by Karen Grimstad, and the references give the page number in this edition and the folio number of the manuscript.⁸⁸⁶ Despite the manuscript dating from 1400, scholarly consensus dates the saga from 1260-1270, after the Codex Regius of the *Poetic Edda* is thought to have been written.⁸⁸⁷ A somewhat different version, not influenced by *Piðreks saga af Bern*, may have existed several decades previously to this;⁸⁸⁸ in any case, *Völsunga saga* is likely one of the oldest of the *fornaldarsögur*.⁸⁸⁹

There has been much scholarly interest in the relationship between *Völsunga saga* and the heroic poetry preserved in the *Poetic Edda*, because the saga is based on these heroic poems and includes quotations of four of them (and several from unknown poems). The saga paraphrases or quotes in total fifteen of the eddic poems from the *Poetic Edda* as we know them in the Codex Regius,⁸⁹⁰ and though the two texts are

⁸⁸⁵ Overviews of the manuscript tradition of *Völsunga saga* can be found in Torfi H. Tulinius, *Matter of the North*, p. 26; *Völsunga saga ok Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Magnus Olsen, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur 36 (København: S. L. Møllers, 1906-1908) pp. i-cii; *Völsunga saga, The Saga of the Volsungs*, ed. R. G. Finch, Icelandic Texts (London: Nelson, 1965) p. xxxviii.

⁸⁸⁶ *Völsunga saga. The Saga of the Volsungs. The Icelandic Text According to MS Nks 1824 b, 4^o*, ed. and trans. Karen Grimstad, Bibliotheca Germanica Series Nova 3 (Saarbrücken: AQ-Verlag, 2000).

⁸⁸⁷ See Kellogg, "Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda," 96; Torfi H. Tulinius, *Matter of the North* 26; Stefanie Würth, "The Rhetoric of *Völsunga saga*," *Fornaldarsagornas Struktur och Ideologi. Handlingar från ett symposium i Uppsala 31.8-2.9. 2001*, ed. Ármann Jakobsson, Annette Lassen & Agneta Ney, Nordiska texter och undersökningar 28 (Uppsala: Uppsala Universitet, 2003) pp. 101-111, at p. 101. Finch gives a wider date of between c. 1200 and c. 1270 in *Völsunga saga* p. xxxviii.

⁸⁸⁸ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Finch, p. xxxvi; Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 26. For *Piðreks saga* as a prose source for *Völsunga saga*, see Per Wieselgren, *Quellenstudien zur Völsungasaga, Acta et Commentationes Universitatis Tartuensis B 34* (Tartu: [n.p.], 1935) 139-143.

⁸⁸⁹ Würth, "The Rhetoric of *Völsunga saga*" p. 101.

⁸⁹⁰ A list of the correspondences can be found in Finch, *Völsunga saga* pp. 85-89, and are detailed at length in Wieselgren, *Quellenstudien zur Völsungasaga*.

close, neither the Codex Regius nor *Völsunga saga* in NKS 1824 b 4to are copied from one another; the ultimate relationship between the two texts thus remains unknowable.⁸⁹¹ Certainly though, the compiler of *Völsunga saga* had the use of a manuscript similar (but not identical with) the Codex Regius manuscript, and transformed the heroic poems to do with Sigurðr Fáfnisbani and the Niflung clan into prose, clarifying and explaining as he did so.⁸⁹² Stefanie Würth has gone so far to argue that the saga “paraphrase[s] in the nature of a hermeneutic act... characteristic of medieval *ars grammaticae* (a commentary and interpretation of the pre-text)” (her italics),⁸⁹³ and a comparison might be made of this process with that which took place in the construction of *Gylfaginning*, as I argue above.

The Codex Regius presently has a lacuna in the heroic poems, by Heusler’s reckoning of around 550 manuscript lines or 2200 half-verses if the section contained no prose (as unlikely as that might be);⁸⁹⁴ presumably the exemplar of the *Poetic Edda* that the compiler of *Völsunga saga* used did not, for the saga tells of events that the lost poems are thought to deal with.⁸⁹⁵ The saga is thus the only available witness as to what material might once have been in the lacuna of the Codex Regius of the *Poetic Edda*.⁸⁹⁶ Although, as Finch has shown, the compiler of the saga has been quite

⁸⁹¹ Kellogg, “Literacy and Orality in the Poetic Edda,” 96.

⁸⁹² This process has been studied by R. G. Finch, “The Treatment of Poetic Sources by the Compiler of *Völsunga saga*,” *Saga-Book* 16 (1965): 315-353 and in “*Atlakviða*, *Atlamál* and *Völsunga Saga*: A Study in Combination and Integration,” *Speculum Norroenvm: Norse Studies in Memory of Gabriel Turville-Petre*, ed. Ursula Dronke et al. (Odense: Odense University Press, 1981) pp. 123-138. The literary aspects of the saga have been studied by Manuel Aguirre, who demonstrates what narrative techniques are at play in the saga in “Narrative Composition in *The Saga of the Volsungs*,” *Saga-Book* 26 (2002): 5-37. Agneta Ney situates *Völsunga saga* in the “europeiska riddarkultren” in “Genus och ideology i *Völsunga saga*,” *Fornaldarsagornas Struktur och Ideologi. Handlingar från ett symposium i Uppsala 31.8-2.9. 2001*, ed. Ármann Jakobsson, Annette Lassen & Agneta Ney, *Nordiska texter och undersökningar* 28 (Uppsala: Uppsala Universitetet, 2003) pp. 113-122.

⁸⁹³ Würth, “The Rhetoric of *Völsunga saga*.” This quotation is on p. 103.

⁸⁹⁴ *Codex Regius of the Elder Edda*, intro. Heusler, p. 21.

⁸⁹⁵ In addition, Finch in *Völsunga saga* p. xxxviii fn. 2 states that the fact that the saga in stanza 11 gives in full *Sigrdrífumál* stanza 8, which is defective in the Codex Regius, and that it gives prose supplements to the also defective *Fáfnismál* stanza 3 and 18 are additional factors that mean the Codex Regius manuscript cannot have been the direct source of the *Völsunga saga* compiler.

⁸⁹⁶ For more on this see Per Wieselgren, “Völsungasaga und Liederlücke,” *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 50 (1934): 70-89; Andreas Heusler, “Die Lieder in die Lücke im Codex Regius der Edda,” *Kleine Schiften*, ed. Stefan Sonderegger, vol. 2 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1969) pp. 223-291; Theodore M. Andersson, “The Lay in the Lacuna of *Codex Regius*,” *Speculum Norroenvm: Norse Studies in Memory of Gabriel Turville-Petre*, ed. Ursula Dronke et al. (Odense: Odense University Press, 1981) pp. 6-26;

faithful to his sources and tried to reconcile them where they conflict,⁸⁹⁷ in comparison to the eddic poems he has given Óðinn a greater role in the fate of the Vǫlsung clan, something which Torfi H. Tulinius has argued “indicates that the author/compiler was bent on giving his own interpretation of the poetic tradition.”⁸⁹⁸

Vǫlsunga saga is both a written and an oral saga, more clearly than most of its genre-mates. In its written form, Stephanie Würth comments that:

Vǫlsunga saga's debt to oral tradition has been identified in the narrative and structural characteristics which it shares with other *fornaldarsögur* for example, [sic] the chronological course of its narrative, which is given in relatively short episodes, the typed-based characterisation of the protagonists in contrast with genuinely delineated characters, the formulaic repetition of themes and narrative patterns, and the importance attributed to the number three.⁸⁹⁹

To this list of oral features she also adds paratactic syntax.⁹⁰⁰ It is clearly a written saga in the sense that it is based on what appear to be written sources, but the material it contains was in all likelihood transmitted orally and is from pre-literary times. This is shown by related material in South and West Germanic tradition in the *Nibelungenlied*, *Beowulf*, *Widsith* and *Waldere* in which the Sigurðr legend is found manifested rather differently than in the Nordic tradition of which *Vǫlsunga saga* is a part.⁹⁰¹ For this reason, the saga itself, in a form different to exactly what is extant but based on the same material, likely comes from oral tradition and experienced an unknowable number of “different forms and medial manifestations,” as Würth puts it,⁹⁰² before reaching its present, written form.

Finch, “*Atlakviða, Atlamál and Vǫlsunga Saga*”; Per Wieselgren, *Quellenstudien zur Vǫlsungasaga, Acta et Commentationes Universitatis Tartuensis B 34* (Tartu: [n.p.], 1935) esp. 239-352.

⁸⁹⁷ Finch, “The Treatment of Poetic Sources.”

⁸⁹⁸ Torfi H. Tulinius, *Matter of the North*, p. 27. Finch suggests that we perhaps ought to consider the person behind the saga an author rather than compiler; “The Treatment of Poetic Sources,” 353.

⁸⁹⁹ Würth, “The Rhetoric of *Vǫlsunga saga*,” p. 101.

⁹⁰⁰ Würth, “The Rhetoric of *Vǫlsunga saga*,” p. 109.

⁹⁰¹ Würth, “The Rhetoric of *Vǫlsunga saga*” p. 101. For a long list of the analogues of the saga, see *Vǫlsunga saga*, ed. Finch pp. ix-xiii.

⁹⁰² Würth, “The Rhetoric of *Vǫlsunga saga*” p. 101.

Here discussion is limited to the analysis of those stanzas that are actually found quoted in verse form in the extant narrative of the saga; prose episodes based on poetry but which do not cite stanzas are beyond the limits of this thesis.⁹⁰³ The stanzas of *Völsunga saga* appear in ten episodes:

1. Sigmundr and Sinfjotli cut a rock with a sword, st. 1.
2. Loki takes Andvari's gold, stt. 2-3.
3. Sigurðr and his men encounter Fjǫlnir, st. 5.
4. Brynhildr teaches Sigurðr rune-lore, stt. 6-21.
5. Sigurðr rides through Brynhildr's wall of fire, stt. 22-23.
6. Brynhildr and Guðrún discuss Sigurðr and Gunnarr, st. 24.
7. Brynhildr sends Sigurður away, st. 25.
8. Gunnarr and Hogni make a magic brew for Guttormr, st. 26.
9. Guðrún is visited by Grimhildr and her brothers, stt. 27-29.
10. Sorli and Hamðir kill their brother Erpr, st. 30.

Of the thirty stanzas quoted in the saga, twenty-four are quotations from four known poems preserved in the heroic section of the Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda*. The six stanzas that are not drawn from these extant poems are likely of mixed provenance, either from heroic poems lost due to the gap in the Codex Regius, or from other lost sagas or poems. The origins that scholars have postulated for these six stanzas have been clearly tabulated in the sixth volume of the *Kommentar zu den Liedern Edda* and will not be dealt with here, although their prosimetric aspects in the narrative will be.⁹⁰⁴ The quotations from extant poems are as follows:

Episode two: *Reginsmál*, stt. 1-2, 6.

Episode three: *Reginsmál*, st. 18.

⁹⁰³ For a discussion of how the compiler of the saga has turned the material he found in the heroic eddic poems into prose, see Finch "The Treatment of Poetic Sources" and *Völsunga saga* p. ix.

⁹⁰⁴ *Kommentar zu den Liedern der Edda*, ed. Klaus von See et al., vol. 6 *Heldenlieder* (Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2009) 944-945.

Episode four: *Sigrdrífumál*, stt. 5-6, 10, 12, 7-9, 11, 13, 15-21.

Episode nine: *Guðrúnarkviða II*, stt. 19 (second half), 22-23.

Episode ten: *Hamðismál*, st. 28.

The stanzas in the saga are a combination of lone stanzas and units of verses. Only episodes two, four, five and nine contain more than one stanza: two and nine each contain three stanzas, five contains two stanzas, while episode four, in which Brynhildr teaches Sigurðr rune-lore, amounts to sixteen stanzas. While, as other scholars have shown, the saga is certainly built upon the heroic poems, it is not built around the citation of poetry as such, in the same way that *Hervarar saga* or *Hálfs saga* could be said to be, even if much of the prose material is clearly drawn from extant heroic poems. Instead, the citations are mainly used as authenticating verses, Brynhildr's speech about rune-lore being a notable exception, where the stanzas are quoted as part of the story. The authenticating stanzas are used with mixed success in the saga, their insertion often clumsy and interrupting instead of buttressing the narrative.

Episode one: Sigmundr and Sinfjötli cut a rock with a sword, st. 1. This stanza is an authenticating stanza and is not known from the *Poetic Edda*. It authenticates a scene where Sigmundr and his son Sinfjötli escape from a mound in which they have been imprisoned to die, the men separated by a great stone slab. Signý, Sigmundr's sister and, incestuously, Sinfjötli's mother, secretly throws a sword into the mound with Sigmundr's sword stuck into it, with which they are able to escape. The prose states that “*nv fkytr sinfjotli bloð refflinvm fyrir ofan hellvna ok dægð faft. sverit bitr hellvna. sigmundr tekr nv blodzefilinn ok ristu nv i milli sin helluna. ok letta eigi fyr enn lokit er at rista sem kuedit er*”⁹⁰⁵ [‘Now Sinfjotli thrust the sword's point up over the rock and pulled hard. The sword bit into the slab. Sigmund grasped the point and they sawed the rock between them, as is told’].⁹⁰⁶ The verse is fairly similar, the *hella* [‘tablet

⁹⁰⁵ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad pp. 100, 102, 10r-10v.

⁹⁰⁶ *The Saga of the Volsungs: The Norse Epic of Sigurd the Dragon Slayer*, trans. Jesse L. Byock, Penguin Classics (London: Penguin, 1999) p. 46.

of stone'] requiring the strength of Sigmundur and Sinfjötli to cut it with a sword, although the stanza says nothing about it being Sigmundur's sword or about how the sword came to be in the mound.⁹⁰⁷ The stanza does not interrupt the narrative flow, and the introductory formula, "sem kuedit er" ['as is told'] acknowledges the poetic telling of the event as primary to the prose narrative, and that what is meant can be found in the poem that follows.⁹⁰⁸

Episode two: Loki takes Andvari's gold, stt. 2-4. The second section contains three stanzas, two as a unit and the third separately. All three are found in *Reginismál*, as stanzas 1-2 and stanza 6. All are introduced as spoken by Loki, although the third stanza in the saga (the second stanza of the episode) is spoken by Andvari; a prose introductory phrase is not given because the first line, "Annðvare ek heite,"⁹⁰⁹ makes it obvious who is speaking, although as demonstrated above, this does not always negate the use of prose speaker markings in the *Poetic Edda*. The two prose introductions of the stanzas in the saga place all the stanzas as dialogue – as part of the story. The first two stanzas of the episode clearly refer to their context in *Reginismál*. In *Völsunga saga*, the story and stanza is told as part of a recounting of the episode by Reginn as he is telling Sigurðr what has happened to his family. This narration is marked by a proliferation of past tense forms and the third person. At the end of the story in the saga, it is presented as an explanation of the origin of the name "otturf giolld"⁹¹⁰ as name for gold; although the episode is obviously taken from the prose of *Reginismál*, the explanation of the name for gold is not. In the first stanza of the episode, in which Loki demands gold from Andvari in order to spare his head, echoes the third, in which Loki comments that the price the Æsir have paid in compensation for Otr, and which has saved his own head, was a high one. These are the first and sixth stanzas of *Reginismál* (as the poem is now extant), and were likely selected for quotation on this

⁹⁰⁷ The stanza can be found out *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 102, 10v.

⁹⁰⁸ See *kveða, Glossary to the Poetic Edda: Based on Hans Kubn's Kurzes Wörterbuch*, ed. Beatrice La Farge and John Tucker, *Skandinavistische Arbeiten* 15 (Heidelberg: Winter, 1992) 149-150, p. 150.

⁹⁰⁹ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 128, 18v.

⁹¹⁰ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 128, 19r.

basis, the repetition of the demand for head ransom in two contexts is aesthetically pleasing, since two quotations bring unity to this section of the text and also moves the story along, since they are dialogue stanzas that are part of the story. This is reinforced by Andvari's description of the Norns' curse in the second half of the second stanza in the episode, and Loki's pronouncement of doom in the third; the saga narrative progresses from ancient times to the more recent past in including these two stanzas. The second stanza in the episode spoken by Andvari is a naming stanza identifying his father and giving a brief summary of his situation,⁹¹¹ although his identity has been more or less indicated in the prose by describing Loki as going "til andvara fozlf"⁹¹² [to Andvari's falls] (although this itself is taken from the prose of the eddic poem). The third stanza in the episode is stanza six of the eddic poem. The phrase "kvað Loki" ("q. l." in the manuscript) in the eddic poem is taken out of the stanza and inserted into the prose of the saga to provide the introduction of the verse in a prose narrative context. This means that the saga author can more easily use the stanza as a dialogue stanza, rather than as an authenticating stanza. The curse pronounced by Loki in the stanza is in the saga shown by how the remainder of Reginn's story plays out, and in both the saga and eddic poem Fáfnir kills Hreiðmarr and Sigurðr kills Fáfnir at Reginn's behest. The stanzas of this section are introduced as part of the story, the first unit introduced with "þa m(ęlir) loki"⁹¹³ and the second stanza of the episode introduced with "þa kvað loki,"⁹¹⁴ so in this case stanzas that are known to be quotations are used as dialogue stanzas rather than as authenticating stanzas.

Episode three: Sigurðr and his men encounter Fjölfnir, st. 5. This stanza is extant in *Reginismál* as stanza 18. In this third episode containing a stanza, Sigurðr and his men encounter a man on the shore when sailing in a storm. Improbably, the man is

⁹¹¹ In the stanza, Andvari's father is given as "oþinn" which Magnus Olsen takes as a mistake for Oinn, the name of Andvari's father in *Reginismál*. *Völsunga saga ok Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 35.

⁹¹² *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 126, 18v).

⁹¹³ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 126, 18v.

⁹¹⁴ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 128, 18v.

able to shout to the ship and ask who is in command. The stanza the stranger speaks serves to identify himself. In the stanza's context in *Reginsmál*, the situation is similar but the stanza is a reply to a versified question as to his identity and is not the first stanza that the man speaks. The wisdom that the man dispenses in *Reginsmál* is not mentioned in the saga. The stanza makes it clear that the man is standing on a cliff as he shouts to the ship, and helps to build up a mental picture of the scene for the reader/audience. The names he gives are clearly Óðinnic names, and his apparent ability to cause the storm to subside and his subsequent disappearance confirm this. His demand to go with the sailors in the final line of the stanza lends him an air of authority, even as he acknowledges Sigurðr as without equal in the prose.⁹¹⁵ Hnikarr's claim to have been a victorious warrior in the first half of his stanza foreshadows the war-havoc Sigurðr and his men cause directly after the stanza in the prose of the saga.

Episode four: Brynhildr teaches Sigurðr rune-lore, stt. 6-21. Brynhildr's lengthy recounting of rune-lore is, in the saga, a response to Sigurðr's asking her "kenn off rað til ftoza lvtá,"⁹¹⁶ and this is introduced as direct speech: "brynhilldr fyllde eitt ker ok fērde sigurðe ok mełti"⁹¹⁷ ['Brynhild filled a goblet, gave it Sigurd, and spoke'].⁹¹⁸ The sixteen stanzas are also found in *Sigrdrífumál*, stanzas 5-6, 10, 12, 7-9, 11, 13, 15-21, in which Brynhildr goes by an alternate name, Sigrdrífa. All the stanzas in this part of the saga are found in the poem, but they are in a somewhat different order:

⁹¹⁵ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 134, 20r.

⁹¹⁶ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 146, 24v.

⁹¹⁷ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 148, 24v.

⁹¹⁸ *The Saga of the Volsungs*, trans. Byock, p. 67.

<i>Völsunga saga</i> stanza number	<i>Sigrdrífumál</i> stanza number
6	5
7	6
8	10
9	12
10	7
11	8
12	9
13	11
14	13
15	15
16	16
17	17
18	18
19	19
20	20
21	21

The difference in order is most pronounced towards the beginning of the unit of saga stanzas, and there is no difference towards the end of the quotation. The end of the poem *Sigrdrífumál* is not quoted, where Sigdrífa gives her enumerated advice, even

though this seems to be most directly what Sigurðr has asked for in the saga prose. Instead, she shares her knowledge of runes and the content of many of her advice stanzas are given instead in prose.⁹¹⁹ Stanza 14 in *Sigrdrífumál* is notably absent in the saga when the stanzas surrounding it are quoted. This is because in the eddic poem, stanzas 15 and onwards are spoken by Mímir, and Sigrdrífa is quoting his words. In the saga, all the stanzas are attributed to Brynhildr and stanza 14 omitted because in it Sigrdrífa introduces Mímir. In the saga we thus have a case of a (silent) quotation within a quotation. The use of the stanzas spoken by Mímir in the poem attribute the wisdom to even further back in ancient times than the heroic age in which the narrative is set. This creates a triple layer of narrative: the saga layer, the *Sigrdrífumál* layer and the wisdom from Mímir that *Sigrdrífumál* itself quotes. The wisdom Brynhildr offers in the saga is blended into the beer she offers to Sigurðr in the first stanza of her lengthy outpouring. At the end of the saga stanzas she addresses Sigurðr directly, and invites him to engage in talking with her. The last stanza is spoken by Sigurðr in reply to her confirms his love for her (and you could say thereby directly contravening the advice she has just given to him). In the poem, the speaker attribution to Sigurðr (“sigurdr sv(arar)”) ⁹²⁰ is lacking (in Bugge’s edition it is an editorial addition taken from the saga), so the saga author at this point has endeavoured to make it clear who is speaking when it might not otherwise be obvious.

After the last stanza and a subtitle, the saga continues with “Sigurðr mełłti”⁹²¹ and he asks for more advice; this is a somewhat clumsy continuation since Sigurðr was already speaking and did not need to be introduced again. Nevertheless, the direct progression of the scene after the stanzas is confirmation of the stanzas’ role as dialogue rather than authenticating verses (even though they are quotations), since after authenticating verses the sagas usually continue with different episode. As Würth also points out, after Brynhildr’s stanzas, the narrative also shifts from a

⁹¹⁹ See *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad pp. 152-154.

⁹²⁰ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 152, 25v.

⁹²¹ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 152, 25v.

mythical past into the human world, and this episode, coming about half way through the saga, marks the transition from the first part of the saga, which takes place in a undefined past and place, to the second half, which, Würth concludes, gives the impression of taking place at a point in time closer to that of the narration.⁹²²

Episode five: Sigurðr rides through Brynhildr's wall of fire, stt. 22-23. The two stanzas quoted in the episode where Sigurðr, having exchanged appearances with Gunnarr, rides through Brynhildr's wall of fire are not found in any other extant poem or saga. They are used in the saga as authenticating verses and as such repeat what has just been told in the prose. They are quoted as a block and are introduced with "sva er kveðit."⁹²³ The first stanza emphasises the intensity of the fire (also mentioned in the prose), and the second half of the same stanza relates that no warrior had before wanted to spur his horse on through the flames (also mentioned in the prose) – this is presumably disallowing Gunnarr's attempt on his own horse and then on Grani, attempts that are not mentioned in the stanza. The second stanza emphasises Sigurðr's status as the bravest warrior. That the flames died down after Grani's initial leap through them is also recorded in the prose and verse. The raiment that Reginn had owned now in the stanza being worn by Sigurðr is not mentioned explicitly in the prose, only the sword Gramr that Reginn forged for Sigurðr and Sigurðr's golden spurs are mentioned in the prose, the presence of the sword being expected and the presence of the spurs inferred from the fact that the second stanza begins with Grani needing a little bit of encouragement from Sigurðr before he leaps through the flames.

Episode six: Brynhildr and Guðrún discuss Sigurðr and Gunnarr, st.24. The stanza in the episode in which Brynhildr and Guðrún bicker about their husbands is a side comment by the narrator in a scene full of prose dialogue and as such jars the flow of the section. It is not known in the *Poetic Edda*. This is if the stanza is taken as a quotation by the narrator for authenticating purposes and not as a stanza spoken by

⁹²² Würth, "The Rhetoric of *Völsunga saga*" p. 106.

⁹²³ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 172, 31v.

Brynhildr, which is also possible. It is introduced by “*sua sem kvedit er.*”⁹²⁴ The clumsy insertion of the stanza is further shown by the continuation in prose with “*Guðrun sv(arar)*”⁹²⁵ rather than the usual continuation after an authenticating stanza with description by the narrator and/or a switch in the action. Here, the stanza interrupts Brynhildr and Guðrún’s conversation. The stanza could be read as spoken in the saga by Brynhildr, especially since in it Brynhildr (who would be quoting herself) addresses Guðrún directly, referring to her brother. That Brynhildr actually speaks the stanza is also implied by the fact that Guðrún’s reply in prose responds directly to Brynhildr’s accusation in the stanza: in the second half of the stanza, Brynhildr says that Guðrún’s brother (Gunnarr) was not brave enough to ride through the the flames to her hall, and in her answer directly after this, Guðrún counters that Grani would not go through the flames ridden by Gunnarr, directly answering Brynhildr’s speech in verse rather than her prose speech before the stanza; in fact, the prose conversation makes little sense if the content of the stanza is not taken into consideration. It seems to be this direct address in the stanza that has caused the saga author problems in including it in the prose. The direct speech and address to Guðrún in the stanza also emphasises the saga’s status as a retelling of a story already told in verse, especially since dialogue is implied in the quoted verse itself. The prose around the stanza thus sounds artificial. The way this stanza is included in the saga can be said to directly counter Bjarni Einarsson’s claim that authenticating verses are not important for story purposes and can be skipped by the reader without harm. On balance, it seems that the narrative construction including this stanza is not done very skilfully, since its enclosure in the prose is awkward.

Episode seven: Brynhildr sends Sigurðr away, st. 25. The 25th stanza in the saga is not known from the *Poetic Edda*. As the stanza in sixth episode, this stanza has a role that is in-between that of a story-stanza and an authenticating stanza, although

⁹²⁴ Völsunga saga, ed. Grimstad p. 178, 33v.

⁹²⁵ Völsunga saga, ed. Grimstad p. 178, 33v.

it is introduced as a quotation from a named poem: “*sva segir i sigurþar qviðv.*”⁹²⁶ This because directly before the stanza, Sigurðr is said to go away (from Brynhildr), and directly after the stanza he enters the hall where Gunnarr is waiting. The stanza placement relates Sigurðr’s emotions *between* these events: he is left in grief as he travels. That his mail-coat shattered is recorded in both poetry and prose. In the prose, this occurs as he offers to leave Guðrún for Brynhildr. The stanza in non-committal about when the mail-coat shatters, it only seems linked to Sigurðr’s luck having departed him. The stanza is not a quotation from an extant eddic poem and is presented as being spoken by the narrator of the saga.

Episode eight: Gunnarr and Högni make a brew for Guttormr, st. 26. The stanza in episode eight is introduced as a stanza by anonymous skald, although the verse is eddic: “*sem íkallðit kvad.*”⁹²⁷ This stanza is used as a classic authenticating stanza and directly repeats what is in the prose – although the stanza adds that they added beer to the brew they gave to Guttormr. The prose continuation after the stanza is a little clumsy, and again the prose author has trouble continuing the scene after the interruption of the verse. The prose after the stanza begins “ok margha lute aða i tyfrum”⁹²⁸ [‘and many other kinds of witchcraft’],⁹²⁹ not making any allowance for the interruption of the verse. The stanza is not from an extant poem.

Episode nine: Guðrún is visited by her brothers and her mother Grimhildr, stt. 27-29. The three stanzas of this section are extant in *Guðrúnarkviða II*. Stanza 27 of the saga is equivalent to the last part of the 19th stanza of the extant eddic poem, and stanzas 28 and 29 of the saga equate to stanzas 22 and 23 of the poem. The first stanza of the episode is separated from the rest by a block of prose, then the second and third stanzas are quoted as a unit. The tones of the two separate quotative blocks are also

⁹²⁶ Völsunga saga, ed. Grimstad p. 188, 36v.

⁹²⁷ Völsunga saga, ed. Grimstad p. 192, 37v.

⁹²⁸ Völsunga saga, ed. Grimstad p. 192, 37v.

⁹²⁹ *The Saga of the Volsungs*, trans. Byock, p. 90.

different: the first is simply descriptive of warriors, while the second and third stanzas are sinister, describing magic and runes. The first stanza is introduced as an authenticating stanza “*sem kveðit er*”⁹³⁰ and both the prose and the stanza describe the warlike appearance of the men travelling. A notable difference between the poem and the saga at this point is that in the poem Grimhildr brings Guðrún the evil brew described in the second and third stanzas, but in the saga it is Gunnarr.⁹³¹ The saga prose gives the ingredients of the potion as a mixture of “*iarðar magne ok fe ok dzeira fonar hennar*”⁹³² [‘the strength of the earth and the sea and the blood of her son’],⁹³³ whereas the stanzas are more specific as to its contents and they do not specify that the entrails the potion contains are those of Guðrún’s son. The effect of the potion in the stanza is that her grief was soothed (“*sakar deyfðe*”) but in the prose it rather says that she “*munde síþan einghar sakar*” – she could not remember the wrongs against her, although in the quotation it does not specifically say that she forgets these things. In the second stanza in the episode, a personal voice comes through the quotation: “*raða ek ne mattak*”⁹³⁴ as Guðrún’s voice comes through as she recalls the encounter with her family in the poem. The prose does not comment on Guðrún’s inability to understand the runes carved into the horn she is given, only that she was forced to drink what the horn contained. Despite this jarring between the quotation and the third person prose narration for the second stanza, after the third stanza the saga continues in a normal manner since the third stanza is in the 3rd person.

Episode ten: Sqrli and Hamðir kill Erpr, st. 30. The 30th and final stanza in *Völsunga saga* is an authenticating stanza introduced with “*fem kveðit er.*”⁹³⁵ Although in the third person plural, the saga prose does not intrude on the authenticating nature

⁹³⁰ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 200, 40v.

⁹³¹ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 202, 40v.

⁹³² *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 202, 40v.

⁹³³ *The Saga of the Volsungs*, trans. Byock, p. 94.

⁹³⁴ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 202, 41r.

⁹³⁵ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 234, 49v.

of the stanza, since the prose continues after the stanza by making reference to the general act they have committed in killing Erpr and commenting on its implications,⁹³⁶ rather than continuing with narration. There are no clashes between the content of the quotation and that of the saga prose. The verse is extant elsewhere as the first half of stanza 28 of *Hamðismál*. In the saga it is Hamðir that utters the prose based on the stanza, but in the eddic poems it could well be Sörli who speaks the stanza – although this detail does not matter much to the prosimetrum of the scene overall. The brothers do not speak again in the saga.

Völsunga saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

As Judy Quinn observes, the stanzas found in *Völsunga saga* do not exactly commemorate the most essential points of the saga.⁹³⁷ No doubt the quotations of verse work alongside, rather than outshine, the notable conversion of verse to prose for most the crucial points as observed in the saga by Finch,⁹³⁸ and the detailed use of dialogue, studied by Quinn.⁹³⁹ At the end of her study subtitled “Verse quotation and dialogue in *Völsunga saga*,” in which she focuses more on dialogue than verse quotation, Quinn concludes that the verse quotations in the saga “focus on the efficacy of speech,” and in doing so, work together with “detailed reporting of dialogue” in order to articulate “the saga-narrator’s interest in individual motivation and reaction to each turn in the saga of dynastic misfortune.”⁹⁴⁰ She summarises that the authenticating stanzas in the saga work by reiteration, particularly of the names of the characters, and that they serve to emphasize heroic prowess. The remaining, lengthier quotations, she notes,

⁹³⁶ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad p. 234, 50v.

⁹³⁷ Judy Quinn, “Trust in Words: Verse Quotation and Dialogue in *Völsunga saga*,” *Fornaldarsagornas Struktur och Ideologi. Handlingar från ett symposium i Uppsala 31.8-2.9. 2001*, ed. Ármann Jakobsson, Annette Lassen & Agneta Ney, Nordiska texter och undersökningar 28 (Uppsala: Uppsala Universitet, 2003) pp. 89-100, at p. 90.

⁹³⁸ Finch, “The Treatment of Poetic Sources.”

⁹³⁹ For a study of dialogue in *Völsunga saga*, see Fredrik J. Heinemann, “Saga Dialogue and Brynhildr’s Mousetrap,” *alvissmál* 8 (1998): 51-66, in which Heinemann makes a convincing argument that parts of the dialogue do not have any grand literary leanings and “very little psychological function” (p. 65), rather some dialogue is purely present for narrative convenience – for getting certain narrative facts out there.

⁹⁴⁰ Judy Quinn, “Trust in Words” p. 100.

focus on “mind-altering brews” and “spoken-pacts.”⁹⁴¹ Stephanie Würth lists paratactic syntax, the sagas chronological narrative and its relatively short episodes as some indicators of the saga’s debt to oral tradition. However, this can only be true of the way that the saga is presented and structured, since as discussed in the introduction to the saga, much of the verse content seems to have been drawn from a manuscript akin to the *Codex Regius* of the *Poetic Edda*. It is then worth considering what aspects of the saga’s prosimetric structure and narrative construction might also reflect the saga’s oral background.

An important point to bear in mind when considering that some aspects of *Völsunga saga*’s prosimetrum is that as one of the oldest written *fornaldarsögur*, there may have not been many models in the oral tradition for sagas built on stanzas when *Völsunga saga* was written. This is probably reflected by its sometimes awkward use of stanzas, which in the main are quotations extant from other eddic poems. Note that this contradicts Anne Holtsmark’s arguments that the *fornaldarsögur* are similar in developmental origin to the versiprose heroic poems; one would assume that if *Völsunga saga* came out of this tradition, which presumably by the time the saga was written down would have been established in the oral and written tradition of the eddic poems already, the occasional evident jarring at the points in the prose at which the verse occurs would have been avoided.

The fact that the saga uses a lot of evidence verses in its prosimetrum may also point to its age and influence from the type of oral (and later written) traditions that produced the prosimetric *konungasögur*, which are typically replete with skaldic evidence verses. Both the lack of a model of a written *fornaldarsaga* built on stanzas and influence from the *konungasögur* may account for the uncomfortable quotation of some stanzas that play both a quasi-speech and quasi-evidence role; in this manner, the prosimetric construction may have become trapped between the apparently oral

⁹⁴¹ Judy Quinn, “Trust in Words” pp. 90-91.

habit of the *fornaldarsögur* of having dialogue/speech in verse, and the evidence role of stanzas common to *konungasögur*; this tension in *Völsunga saga* is not resolved well.

The use of evidence verses indicates that the saga author considered the stanzas to be primary to his prose narrative; this can be seen, for example, in the quotation of stanza 1, which is introduced with “sem kveðit er.” In addition, as mentioned, parts of the prose seem to be based on extant stanzas. Nevertheless, it is quite possible that the explanatory framework of quoting selected verses from all those that the performer knew, and using *Begleitprosa* to form an engaging narrative may have followed the *Völsunga saga* material from oral into written tradition. Evidence for this in the narrative may be visible in the scene where Sigurðr asks Brynhildr for rune-lore: she speaks a lot of stanzas, but the most relevant part that answers Sigurðr’s question is converted from verse into prose by the saga author, as if to construct a prose narrative for what would otherwise be a long scene almost entirely in speech stanzas, which was perhaps not felt fitting for a written saga (although we can gather from the evidence afforded by *Norna-Gests þáttr* that this was more likely acceptable in an oral setting).

It is a marked difference to the *konungasögur* that *Völsunga saga* has lengthy speech stanzas (they exist in *Fagrskinna* but they are neither abundant nor lengthy units) in its prosimetrum. The appearance of eddic verse in written form is apparently without substantial parallels in the skaldic prosimetric tradition, and this could suggest that this is eddic feature has its roots in oral tradition. We can also see how stanza 4 is adjusted by the prose author in order to account for the transference of the stanza from a poetic into a prosimetric saga context. Additionally, the transference of “kvað Loki” into the prose and the subsequent avoidance of inserting an evidence stanza also demonstrates a step away from the predominantly evidence-based verse quotation in *konungasögur*.

One notable use of verse in *Völsunga saga* is its use in identifying the characters. These are spoken by Andvari for example, and by Fjölfnir in stanza 5. This prominent use of verse in *Völsunga saga* can be found in other *fornaldarsögur*, as will be discussed.

The episode in which Sigurðr asks Brynhildr for advice is notable for its length, as Würth notes, saga episodes in the legendary sagas are usually shorter, likely as a reflection of an oral past in which narratives moved from one scene to another. The extension of the narrative in the section is done with dialogue stanzas rather than authenticating stanzas. Although as seen in *Fagrskinna*, complex authenticating stanzas can extend a scene, they are relatively uncommon, and after the skaldic stanza, the scene shifts. Employing the eddic stanzas as speech and using them to lengthen the scene even when they occur as monologues rather than dialogues seems particular to the eddic tradition. In a saga context, this kind of inset lengthy quotation seems to have come about as a means by which to balance the oral eddic saga tradition for monologue (for example, death songs, discussed below) with the demands of a written narrative and its potential for lengthier scenes. That this may have been somewhat unnatural to the saga author is perhaps indicated in the insertion of an extraneous “Sigurðr męlti” when the character was already speaking.⁹⁴²

The sixth prosimetric episode of the saga in which stanza 14 is cited demonstrates perhaps the lack of a model for a *fornaldarsaga* built around stanzas. The scene is heavy in dialogue which is given in prose, similar to the method used in *Fagrskinna*. The stanza’s impediment of the flow of the section may reflect the fact that the author felt compelled to include a stanza by the weight of tradition; the fact that it could be read as either an authenticating verse or a speech stanza (and that st. 25 is similarly uncertain in status) may demonstrate momentary uncertainty in the construction of a written *fornaldarsaga* scene. This suspicion of slight uncertainty when dealing with conventions found in either eddic or skaldic prose might also lie behind the introduction of an otherwise unknown eddic stanza with the phrase “sem skallðit kvað^ð”⁹⁴³ – a rare occurrence of an eddic stanza being introduced as a skaldic example.

⁹⁴² *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad, p. 152, 25v.

⁹⁴³ *Völsunga saga*, ed. Grimstad, p. 192, 37v.

Given that there was no prior oral model of a *fornaldarsaga* built around quotation stanzas, it seems reasonable to ask why *Völsunga saga* was then constructed in such a way. It should be pointed out here that *Völsunga saga* in this respect is rather different from the other legendary sagas, which include either *lausavísur*, dialogues or lengthier eddic poems, but do not seem to use quotations from extant poems so explicitly, nor on the whole have they obviously converted verse into prose for their narrative. As argued above, I do not think the structure of *Völsunga saga* as a prose narrative built around quotations came from the heroic eddic poems, but there is a possibility that the oral *fornaldarsaga* subgenre and the heroic versiprose genre existed side by side, and that the heroic poetry with prose frames and prose insertions between some of the stanzas suggested the format of *Völsunga saga*, which was then otherwise built in the style of a *fornaldarsaga*. It seems most logical, given the obvious developmental gaps we face in trying to trace the transformation of the heroic poetry to prose sagas, to maintain the heroic poetry and the *fornaldarsaga* subgenre were separate, both in the pre-literary and written tradition, but that they could influence each other. Neither *Völsunga saga* nor the other legendary sagas can be said with certainty to be directly related to prosimetric heroic poetry.

Ragnars saga loðbrókar

Ragnars saga loðbrókar exists in two redactions, Y and X, although X is fragmentary.⁹⁴⁴ The Y version is found in Ny kgl. saml. 1824 b 4to from around 1400 (from which all other manuscripts seem to derive),⁹⁴⁵ and the X version in AM 147 4to (this part of the manuscript is 15th century).⁹⁴⁶ It also seems likely that in the 14th century Haukr Erlendsson had access to a third version of the saga, which he used in his *Þáttr af Ragnarssonum* (see below).⁹⁴⁷ Consensus as to when the saga was written seems to have rested at the second half of the 13th century, or possibly later, for the Y version,⁹⁴⁸ and the X version is thought to date from c. 1250.⁹⁴⁹ Since the X version is fragmentary and rather difficult to reconstruct, the analysis here follows the Y version as edited by Magnus Olsen.⁹⁵⁰

Many of the stanzas in *Ragnars saga* are in irregular skaldic metre, all but the last three, which are in *fornyrðislag*, but this saga is undisputably a *fornaldarsaga* since it is so concerned with an ancient hero. Ragnarr and his family may be portrayed as having spoken in skaldic instead of eddic metre to confer upon them extra dignity,

⁹⁴⁴ For overviews of the manuscript transmission of *Ragnars saga*, see *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, pp. ii-x; Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North* 24-25.

⁹⁴⁵ See *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, pp. ii, lxiii; Rory McTurk, "The Relationship of *Ragnars saga loðbrókar* to *Þiðreks saga af Bern*," *Sjötiú ritgerðir helgaðar Jakobi Benediktssyni 20. júlí 1977*, ed. Einar G. Pétursson & Jónas Kristjánsson, vol. 2, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar á Íslandi, rit 12 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1977) pp. 568-585, at p. 568 and n. 3, same page; McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, pp. 53, 55; Elizabeth Ashman Rowe, "Ragnars saga loðbrókar, Ragnarssona þáttr, and the Political World of Haukr Erlendsson," *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighed. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Agneta Ney, Ármann Jakobsson and Annette Lassen (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 347-360.

⁹⁴⁶ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 432. Olsen dates it to the second half of the 15th century in *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. lxxxiii-iv and note 1.

⁹⁴⁷ On this see Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 24; Bjarni Guðnason, "Gerðir og ritpróun Ragnars sögu loðbrókar," *Einarsbók: Afmæliskeðja til Einars Ól. Sveinssonar, 12. desember 1969* (Reykjavík: n.p., 1969) pp. 28-37; Rory McTurk, "The Earliest Extant Icelandic Manifestations of *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*," *Gripa* 1 (1975): 43-75, at pp. 43-64; McTurk, "The Relationship of *Ragnars saga loðbrókar* to *Þiðreks saga af Bern*."

⁹⁴⁸ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, 24; McTurk, "The Relationship of *Ragnars saga loðbrókar* to *Þiðreks saga af Bern*," p. 583; McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, p. 55.

⁹⁴⁹ See McTurk, "The Relationship of *Ragnars saga loðbrókar* to *Þiðreks saga af Bern*," p. 583 and n. 128; *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, p. 54.

⁹⁵⁰ McTurk provides a summary of the content of X, especially which verses seem to have been included, in *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, pp. 54-55, although the extant text is almost illegible. What can be read is edited in *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, pp. 176-194, and see also pp. lxxxiii-xcv.

since Ragnarr is such a mighty (historical) hero of old. It seems clear that *Ragnars saga* is part of a complex that remembers a historical Ragnarr, a Viking who harried around Europe in the mid 9th century, and who as a consequence was remembered by English and French writers into the 12th and 13th centuries.⁹⁵¹ Although the stories around Ragnarr were initially oral, in Scandinavia it seems that such stories had been committed to writing by the 12th century:⁹⁵² other texts that relate the story of Ragnarr include *Krákumál* (a 12th century Icelandic poem),⁹⁵³ the 9th book of Saxo's late 12th century *Gesta Danorum*,⁹⁵⁴ *Skjöldunga saga* (likely also late 12th century but today found only in a 17th century Latin version),⁹⁵⁵ and the *Þáttr af Ragnarsonum* (see below).⁹⁵⁶ There are forty stanzas in *Ragnars saga* and they appear more or less evenly throughout the saga, although nine stanzas appear rather close together at the end of the saga.⁹⁵⁷

The first stanza, beginning “Hętt hefi ek leyfdv life,”⁹⁵⁸ is spoken by Ragnarr after he has killed an *ormr* that has wrapped itself around the bower of a princess. The occasional stanza is firmly put in its performance context. It is introduced with “hann nemr stadar ok kvad visu þetta,” [‘he stopped and said this verse’]⁹⁵⁹ and afterwards it

⁹⁵¹ Rory McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar and its Major Scandinavian Analogues*, Medium Ævum Monographs, New Series 15 (Oxford: The Society for the Study of Mediaeval Languages and Literature, 1991) 1-6; Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 24-25.

⁹⁵² Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 25.

⁹⁵³ A monologue in a variant of *dróttkvætt*, *Krákumál* follows the Y version of *Ragnars saga* in its manuscript, but ends halfway through st. 22 (of 29 preserved elsewhere), and also lacks st. 16. In the X version, it forms part of the narrative, rather than being appended to it. See McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, pp. 53, 54, 125-33.

⁹⁵⁴ See McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, pp. 53-54.

⁹⁵⁵ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 25.

⁹⁵⁶ See McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar* for a full investigation of all of the Nordic analogues of the story.

⁹⁵⁷ I have relied on the edition and his reconstruction of the stanzas in *Ragnars saga loðbrókar, Volsunga saga ok Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Magnus Olsen, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur 36 (København: S. L. Møller, 1906-1908) pp. 111-175, and the stanzas are edited separately on pp. 195-222.

⁹⁵⁸ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 119, ll. 1-8.

⁹⁵⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 118, ll. 30-31.

is said that he “mælti ecki fleira við hana” [‘didn’t speak more with her’].⁹⁶⁰ The stanza is thus of extra importance because it is the only thing Ragnarr says at the present time. In particular, the stanza makes the princess think: “Nu er hun hefir þessa visu heyrda, skilde hun, hvat hann sagde til um sitt ærendi, ok sva hve gamall hann var. Ok nu hyggr hun at fyrir ser, hveir hann munde vera...” [‘When she had heard this verse, she understood what he said about his errand, and thus how old he was. And now she guesses who he might be...’].⁹⁶¹ The function of Ragnarr’s speech is thus uncovered by the prose as a way to convey information, although not a straight-forward one, and thus the prosimetrum as a device that can lead to the discovery of the speakers’s identity. Because of this, the stanza plays an important part in the unfolding of the scene.

The second stanza, beginning “Þori ek eigi þod briota,”⁹⁶² is in *fornyrðislag* and is spoken by Kráka to Ragnarr, as an answer to a question: “Ok nu kallar Ragnarr a hana ok spyrr, hver hun veri, eða hvern hun villde finna. Hun svarar ok kvad visu” [‘And now Ragnarr calls to her and asks who she might be, or who she wanted to find. She answers and says a verse’].⁹⁶³ In the stanza, however, she does not identify herself explicitly but does address Ragnarr by name. The stanza does not provoke a reply as such, but rather an action (he sends men to accompany her to his ship). Her eventual company proves so delightful to Ragnarr that, in the third stanza beginning “Svrvmdi vist ef veri,”⁹⁶⁴ Ragnarr hopes the lovely lady will “join hands with him,” but in the second half of the third stanza, which Kráka speaks (beginning “vamlausa skaltu vise”),⁹⁶⁵ she declines and wishes to leave. The stanza is introduced unremarkably as a speech stanza by “Hann kvad visu”⁹⁶⁶ (the marking for Kráka speaking the second half

⁹⁶⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 119, ll. 9-10.

⁹⁶¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 119, ll. 11-14.

⁹⁶² *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 125, ll. 11-18.

⁹⁶³ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 125, ll. 8-10.

⁹⁶⁴ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 126, ll. 1-4. It is a half stanza.

⁹⁶⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 126, ll. 6-9.

of the stanza is lacking), and Ragnarr replies to Kráka in indirect speech in the saga (“nu segir hann, at...”),⁹⁶⁷ but the sharing of the stanza by the two speakers gives a sense of intimacy between the characters.

In the same scene, there are further stanzas when Ragnarr attempts to give Kráka a tunic that Þóra (Ragnarr’s wife) had owned. The fourth stanza of the saga is introduced with “þa bydr Ragnar Kracu a þa lund” [‘then Ragnarr asked Kráka in this manner’],⁹⁶⁸ and Ragnarr speaks a versified question to Kráka, beginning “Villtu þenna þiggia,”⁹⁶⁹ if she will have the silver embroidered tunic, and Kráka rejects the offer in the fifth stanza, starting with “Þori ek eigi þann þiggia,”⁹⁷⁰ and finishing her answer with a prose line: “Ok vil ek vist eigi taka vid serknum” [‘and I will certainly not take the tunic’].⁹⁷¹ The stanzas enliven the scene, Ragnarr describes a beautiful object and Kráka’s stanza defiantly rejects it, outlining the darker items she is known to wear. The stanzas complement and balance each other, Ragnarr’s echoing the information in the prose and Kráka’s giving more information about herself to Ragnarr and the reader.

The context of the sixth stanza is Ragnarr and Kráka’s wedding night, when a prophetic stanza is spoken by the bride. The stanza is in reply to a question in reported speech the prose by Ragnarr, how long they must wait after the marriage before its consummation.⁹⁷² The stanza begins with “Þriar nætr skulum þessar,”⁹⁷³ detailing they must wait three nights or the son that they will conceive will have no

⁹⁶⁶ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 125, l. 30.

⁹⁶⁷ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 126, l. 10.

⁹⁶⁸ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 126, ll. 18-19.

⁹⁶⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 126, ll. 20-25 – p. 127, ll. 1-2.

⁹⁷⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 127, ll. 4-11.

⁹⁷¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 127, l. 12.

⁹⁷² *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 128, ll. 29-30.

⁹⁷³ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 129, ll. 1-8.

bones. Directly after the stanza comes a comment in prose from the narrator: “Ok þo hun kvæddi þetta, gaf Ragnar at því enngan gaum ok bra æ sitt rad.”⁹⁷⁴ The fact that she has recited this in verse, emphasised by the use of the verb “kvæddi” in the prose, and that Ragnar ignored it – with the implication that he did so foolishly, means that the stanza is given extra weight in the narrative, both because of its prophetic content and because of the fact this was delivered in a stanza.

The seventh stanza moves away from the interactions of Ragnar and Kráka and is spoken by Björn Ragnarsson, in the midst of a battle. The stanza, beginning “Vpp rvndv ver opi,”⁹⁷⁵ has an historical tone, recording what has happened and where in battle in the style of a stanza in a *konungasaga*. The performance context is not very concrete in the prose, the stanza simply being recited “Ok er þeir hverfa apr til borgarinnar” [‘when they turned back to the city’]⁹⁷⁶ and the contents are not commented on after the stanza. Instead there is a continuation in the prose of “Ok er þeir koma afr i borgina” [‘and when they come back into the city’],⁹⁷⁷ and this repetition makes the placement of the stanza in the prose sound clumsy. Nevertheless, the contents of the historical-sounding stanza are rather dynamic, the third line reading “satt mvn ek til þess segia” [‘the truth I will say about this’], emphasising the accuracy of the information in the stanza, which also includes two placenames. The stanza is not very typical for the action of a *fornaldarsaga*, since stanzas with a similar tone tend to be part of longer retrospective poems. Nevertheless, the fact that these retrospective stanzas do exist elsewhere means that the stanza does not sound wholly out of place.

The eighth stanza, further on in the saga after the birth of Ragnar’s son, is a naming stanza, although it is unlike those frequently found in *fornaldarsögur* in which a person

⁹⁷⁴ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 129, ll. 9-10.

⁹⁷⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 132, ll. 7-15.

⁹⁷⁶ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 132, ll. 6-7.

⁹⁷⁷ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 132, l. 16.

names himself in order to identify himself. Here, Ragnarr gives the baby a name, and the stanza begins “*Sigurdr mvn sueinn of heitinn*” [‘the boy will be called Sigurðr’].⁹⁷⁸ In the stanza Ragnarr predicts great things for his son (he will be foremost of Óðinn’s line, for example), and makes the comment that the child has “*ormr i avga*” [‘a serpent in his eye’], which becomes Sigurðr’s nickname and proves his mother’s parentage as the daughter of Sigurðr Fáfnisbani and Brynhildr Buðladóttir. The next two stanzas function in the narrative as Ragnarr’s acceptance of his wife’s noble origins and comment on the traits that bely the son and mother’s kin; stanza nine, beginning “*Brynhíldar leizt baraugtunn*,”⁹⁷⁹ confirms the relationship to Brynhildr, and stanza ten, beginning “*Sea er enngi sveni. nema sigurde einum*,”⁹⁸⁰ the relationship to Sigurðr Fáfnisbani. These two stanzas are introduced with “*ok nu kvad hann visu*” and “*ok enn kvad hann*,”⁹⁸¹ typical introductory and linking structures. Nevertheless, the reaction recorded by the narrator to the stanza, “*Ok nu kemr upp þett Aslaugar, sva at þat veit hverr madr, at hun er dottir Sigurdar Fafnnisbana ok Brynhíldar Budladottur*” [‘And now comes up the lineage of Áslaug, so that each man knew that she was the daughter of Sigurðr Fáfnisbáni and Brynhildr Buðladóttir’],⁹⁸² means that these stanzas were publically received and highlights the role of stanzas in transmitting information in the narrative world of the saga.

The next four stanzas are spoken by Eiríkr Ragnarsson, after he and his brother Agnarr were harrying in the kingdom of King Eysteinn and Agnarr is killed and Eiríkr captured and offered peace by King Eysteinn. The first stanza, stanza eleven beginning “*Vil ek eigi bod fyrir brodur*,”⁹⁸³ is introduced with “*Eirekr segir ok kvad visu*” [‘Eiríkr speaks and says a verse’], rejects the offer of peace and is a dialogue

⁹⁷⁸ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 125, ll. 1-8.

⁹⁷⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 136, ll. 14-21.

⁹⁸⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 136, ll. 23-26 – p. 137, ll. 1-4.

⁹⁸¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 136, l. 13 & l. 22.

⁹⁸² *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 137, ll. 7-9.

⁹⁸³ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 139, ll. 10-17.

stanza rather than a historical-sounding stanza in which he proclaims he will die rather than accept peace and Eysteinn's daughter. The tone continues for the next two stanzas, in which Eiríkr declares how he wishes to die (stanzas twelve, beginning "Mvnað eins *konungs* efni"⁹⁸⁴ and thirteen, beginning "bera skuloð ord it ęfra"). The thirteenth stanza is the most interesting, because in it, Eiríkr acknowledges the informative and commemorative properties of verse:

bera skuloð ord it ęfra
 nv ero orrir firar lagþir.
 at mer hafi mina.
 mic aslaugv bauga.
 þa man mest af mode.
 er mic spyria dauðan.
 min stiop modir sinum.
 mogum þavgul segia.⁹⁸⁵

By requesting them to convey his last words to Áslaug, he is referring to the next and fourteenth stanza in the saga, beginning "Hlackar hrafn of hofdi,"⁹⁸⁶ that he speaks as he is dying atop spears with ravens overhead. This shows that occasional stanzas could be planned as well as spontaneous compositions, and that their speakers were aware of their future impact. His final words are duly recited to Áslaug later in the saga: "Ok nv kvad hann þa visu, er Eirekr hafde kvedit, er hann sendi henne hringin. Nu sea þeir, at hun felldi tar..." ["and now he says that verse, which Eiríkr had composed, when he sent her the ring. Now they saw, that she shed a tear..."].⁹⁸⁷ The saga author seems here to be acutely aware of the memorial and historical function of verse, and likewise this is demonstrated by the fifteenth and sixteenth stanzas. That stanzas can be used to ask questions is demonstrated in the *fornaldarsögur* largely by the existence of stanzas that request the identity of another. In the fifteenth stanza (beginning "Hvat sege þer or yþru")⁹⁸⁸ however, the informational capacity of verse is highlighted

⁹⁸⁴ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 139, ll. 27-28 – p. 140, ll. 1-6.

⁹⁸⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 140, ll. 11-18.

⁹⁸⁶ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 140, ll. 21-28.

⁹⁸⁷ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 142, ll. 3-5.

⁹⁸⁸ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 141, ll. 15-22.

by Áslaug using a stanza to ask for news and conveying what she has already heard so that she can be updated. The sixteenth stanza, beginning “Þer segiv ver þina,”⁹⁸⁹ is a situational verse that addresses the recipient (“kona,” in the second line) and identifies the men talked about in the stanza (“sonum þorv,” in the fourth line), and otherwise conveys news to Áslaug about what has happened. The stanzas retells something that the audience-reader already knows has happened, but this dramatic irony helps to reinforce the story and leave the reader free to focus on the reactions of Áslaug to the news and the consequences.

The saga also comments on the tone of the stanzas that are spoken. The seventeenth verse, beginning “kaga letu mic minir,”⁹⁹⁰ records Áslaug’s reaction when she is given the news of the death of her son Rognvaldr, and in the prose is the comment “Enn ecki fær henna þat mikils ok kvad...”⁹⁹¹ The awareness in *Ragnars saga* about the impact of verses is extended to the characters. In the eighteenth stanza, beginning “Ei mvndi ydar,”⁹⁹² Áslaug, as part of her urging her reluctant sons to avenge her dead stepsons, says she had rather they had lived and her sons, who are refusing to avenge their halfbrothers, had died; her son Ívarr then comments: “Eigi er vist, segir Ivar, ‘hvert þat stodar nackvat, þottu kvedir aþra visu at annari’” [“it is not certain,” Ívarr says, “whether that helps anything, even if you speak one verse after another”].⁹⁹³ Characters in the saga are thus displayed as listening to, reacting to and being attuned to the social significance of characters speaking stanzas.

The episode of Áslaug urging her sons to revenge their halfbrothers continues with conscious references to the power of poetry to convince; initially, Áslaug is offended because “þotti henna þeir eigi mikils meta sin ord” [‘it seemed to her that

⁹⁸⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 141, ll. 24-29 – p. 142, ll. 1-2.

⁹⁹⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 142, ll. 22-29.

⁹⁹¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 142, ll. 21-22.

⁹⁹² *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 143, ll. 15-22.

⁹⁹³ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 143, ll. 23-24.

they did not attach much value to her words’];⁹⁹⁴ on this occasion, her fondness for speaking in verse, as noted by Ívarr, has been ineffective in manipulating others to do her will. Her son, Sigurðr ormr í auga, reveals his thoughts on the matter in stanza nineteen, beginning “Þat skal þrigia natta,”⁹⁹⁵ recording Sigurðr ormr í auga in the stanza as the instigator of his judgments, his thoughtful, poetic response to her goading causes his brothers to reconsider their refusal to take vengeance: “Ok er hann hafde þessa visu kvedit, skipazt nockut hugr þeirra brædra” [‘and when he had said this verse, the brothers somewhat changed their minds’].⁹⁹⁶ The saga thus once more demonstrates the transformative power of the skaldic stanza as a communicative medium, as thus prompts each of the other brothers, Björn járnsíða, Hvítserkr hvati and Ívarr beinlauss,⁹⁹⁷ to say a stanza in turn. Ívarr recognises that he must speak a stanza in response to those spoken by his brothers: “Ok nu tok Ivar til orða ok segir, at þa var þar komit, er hann munde nockurn lut i eiga, ok nu kvad hann visu” [‘And now Ívarr began to speak and says, that it had come to the point when he must have some part in it, and now he said a stanza’].⁹⁹⁸ These are situational stanzas, and they are carefully used by the prose author to demonstrate not only the value of poetry as an artform, but also its memorial and social role, its ability to record and persuade and to question.

The next episode to contain verse in the saga is a section in which Randalín (the name that Áslaug, previously Kráka, has taken), tries to persuade Ragnarr to take smaller and more ships to England. The first two stanzas contain Ragnarr’s defence of his plans, the twenty-third in the saga, beginning “Spari mangi raufrinar,”⁹⁹⁹ defends his

⁹⁹⁴ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 144, l. 12.

⁹⁹⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 144, ll. 17-24.

⁹⁹⁶ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 144, ll. 25-26.

⁹⁹⁷ These are stanzas twenty, twenty-one and twenty-two, beginning “dvga mvn hvgr ok hiata,” “hyggium at hinn” and “hafit ofr hvga ęrin” in *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 145 ll. 3-10; p. 145, ll. 12-20; p. 145, ll. 26-27 – p. 146, ll. 1-6.

⁹⁹⁸ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 145, ll. 23-25.

⁹⁹⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 155, ll. 10-17.

honour, while the twenty-fourth, beginning “*hvat er þat bax or bavgum*”¹⁰⁰⁰ connects more immediately with its prose context. He seems forced to comment because “*Nu er fiolrętt um hans fyrirętlan*” [‘now there is much talk about his plans’]¹⁰⁰¹ and his stanza is introduced with “*ok enn kvad hann visu*” [‘and he said yet another stanza’].¹⁰⁰² This is an interesting choice of introduction, one used normally when stanzas are quoted very close together or indeed separated only by this phrase. In this instance, however, Ragnarr has done a lot since uttering the stanza before this one: he has had his ships readied, his army gathered, and the ships loaded. Using this introduction gives an air of immediacy and hustle and bustle to the narration, implying that Ragnarr’s actions were performed very quickly; it might also suggest that stanzas twenty-three and twenty-four were felt to go together in content and style (their tone is similar) and because of this strong pairing they were introduced as being said very close together in time. The final stanza in the episode is about a protective shirt Randalín gives to Ragnarr; it is introduced as a situational stanza with “*Enn hun kvad visu*” [‘again she spoke a verse’],¹⁰⁰³ and while the “*enn*” could signal that her discourse (previously in prose) is continuing, it might also refer to Randalín’s/Áslaug’s/Kráka’s partiality for speaking in verse at emotionally high moments in the saga (such as when urging her sons to avenge their half-brothers). In this episode we thus see stanzas carefully employed for narrative effect.

The next two stanzas occur in the episode when Ragnarr is killed, and they are linked closely by their imagery and wording to the prose that surrounds them. Here a pair of stanzas occur, separated only by “*ok enn kvad hann*”¹⁰⁰⁴ rather than the lengthier prose and similar phrase used in the episode above. In the first half of the twenty-sixth

¹⁰⁰⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 155, ll. 21-26 – p. 156, ll. 1-2.

¹⁰⁰¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 155, ll. 19-20.

¹⁰⁰² *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 155, l. 20.

¹⁰⁰³ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 156, l. 10.

¹⁰⁰⁴ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 158, l. 18.

stanza, which begins “Orrostur hefi ek attar,”¹⁰⁰⁵ Ragnarr boasts of his past glory, but quickly switches to his current demise:

eigi hvggda mik ormar.
at allðr lagi mi nv.
þat verdr miok maugv sinne.
er minnz varit sialfan.¹⁰⁰⁶

The snakes fastened onto him refer to the snake-pit, into which he has been thrown in the prose, “heingu ormar ollum meginna a honum” [‘snakes hung on him from all sides’].¹⁰⁰⁷ The last two lines of the stanza speak of his surprise that he, of all people, ended up dying in this way. The second stanza of Ragnarr’s death scene, beginning “Gnyðia munðc grisir,”¹⁰⁰⁸ is echoed in the prose above it. In the prose, Ragnarr says “Gyndia mundu nu grisir, ef þeir visse, hvat enn gamle þyldi,”¹⁰⁰⁹ which is related to “Gynðia munðv grisir. / ef galltar hag visse.”¹⁰¹⁰ This death scene is related to his sons later in the saga, in another case of dramatic irony:

Ok nu er þessi saugu var þar komit, er hann hafði þetta mellt: ‘gnydia mundu grisir,’ þóckar Biornn hondum sinum a spiotskaptinu, ok sva hafði hann tekit fast, at handastadinn sa æ eptir.¹⁰¹¹

In the saga, the phrase about the pigs squealing about the treatment of the boar is held to have special importance. It is memorable and relates to a key moment in the narrative (the death of Ragnarr), as well as being part of the complex of Ragnarr’s death song (the two stanzas he says). Ragnarr’s final speech in stanza twenty-nine is to announce his injuries and his impending death, as is usual in death songs. The two stanzas use structures and motifs typical of comparable death songs in the

¹⁰⁰⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 158, ll. 19-26.

¹⁰⁰⁶ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 158, ll. 23-26.

¹⁰⁰⁷ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 155, ll. 13-14.

¹⁰⁰⁸ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 159, ll. 1-8.

¹⁰⁰⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 158, ll. 15-16.

¹⁰¹⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 159, ll. 1-2.

¹⁰¹¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 161, ll. 21-25.

fornaldarsögur, but at the same time they are integrated into the saga prose, because they are both foreshadowed and repeated in the narrative.

The next two stanzas in the saga, spoken by Björn, have a curious performance context: “Þat er ein morginn, at Biornn iarnnsida vaknar ok kvad visu” [‘One morning, Björn járnsíða woke up and said a verse’]. The prose context of the two stanzas he says is that he and his brothers had been harrying the Southern Kingdom, but the inhabitants heard they were coming and fled, leaving the brothers barely able to provide food for their troops.¹⁰¹² In the first stanza that Björn says upon waking, which begins “her flygr hverian morginn,”¹⁰¹³ he talks of a raven that would die of hunger in the area they are in, which is taken in the prose as an indirect description of the situation he and his men find themselves in. The second half of the stanza says rather the raven should go “svdr vm sanða” [‘south over the sands’] to where there have been many deaths, turning the stanza into a boast. The second stanza (the twenty-ninth in the saga, beginning “Þat var fyrst er forvm”)¹⁰¹⁴ is a more historical stanza in tone, recording their deeds in “romi velli” (Rómaveldi), a line about the eagle shrieking over the fallen slain offering a contrast to the hungry raven in the previous stanza. There is no comment after the second stanza to round off the performance context of the stanza, and instead the saga simply moves on.

The next episode in the saga that contains verse is about the death of Hvítserkr: “ok er Randalin spyrr þetta, þa kvad hun vísu” [‘and when Randalín hears this, then she said a verse’].¹⁰¹⁵ Randalín actually speaks two stanzas, the thirtieth and thirty-first stanzas in the saga,¹⁰¹⁶ separated by the phrase “ok enn kvad hun” [‘and yet she said’],¹⁰¹⁷ a

¹⁰¹² *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, pp. 159-161.

¹⁰¹³ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 160, ll. 9-16.

¹⁰¹⁴ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 160, ll. 18-25.

¹⁰¹⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 168, ll. 20-21.

¹⁰¹⁶ The first beginning “Sonr beið einn sa ek atta,” *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 168, ll. 22-29, and the second “hofdum let of hrvndít,” *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 169, ll. 2-9.

¹⁰¹⁷ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 169, l. 1.

standard dividing phrase for stanzas quoted otherwise consecutively. In the prose, Hvítserkr chooses that his death should be on a bonfire made out of mans' heads and this is what his mother reports in the stanzas she speaks, and that he died valiantly. Both of his mother's stanzas are historical or commemorative in tone, and thus do not sit well in the prose as immediate comments on what she has supposedly just heard. Additionally, the two stanzas are rather similar in content and tell of the same event. Here it seems clear that the older stanzas recording the event as thought to be spoken by Hvítserkr's mother (note that his name and their relationship is recorded in the first stanza), and that these have been used in the saga as appropriate stanzas in the narrative context, but they have not been used well.

The final episode containing stanzas in *Ragnars saga* is a *mannjafnaðr*, "a formal comparison of male accomplishment,"¹⁰¹⁸ in a rather curious context. We hear in the saga after the death of Ragnarr's sons, the troops who accompanied them dispersed and travelled far and wide,¹⁰¹⁹ and

Peir voru II men, er foru vida um laund at leita, ef þeir fynde nauckurn haufdingia þann, er þeim þetti ser eigi svivirdingh i at þiona, ok foru þeir eigi badir saman.¹⁰²⁰

They were two men who travelled widely across the land to discover if they could find a chief who it did not seem disgraceful for them to serve, and they did not travel both together.

The scene changes to a great feast to mark the death of a king in a far off land, and two enormous strangers arrive, separately, sit down to drink and the first to arrive challenges the second: "Sa er fyre kom, bad, at þeir skyllde eigha gaman saman: 'ok mun ek fyre.' Hann stakk vid honum hende ok kvad visu" ["The one who arrived first asked that they should have a game together, "and I will go first." He shoved the other one with his hand and said a verse"].¹⁰²¹ The first stanza, beginning "Segh þv fra

¹⁰¹⁸ Jonathan Grove, "The Place of Greenland in Medieval Icelandic Saga Narrative," *Journal of the North Atlantic* 2 (2009): 30-51, at p. 36. < <http://www.bioone.org/doi/full/10.3721/037.002.s206>>

¹⁰¹⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 170, ll. 1-4.

¹⁰²⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 170, ll. 4-8.

¹⁰²¹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 171, ll. 21-23.

þegnaskaupum þinum,”¹⁰²² is the thirty-second in the saga, and issues a formal challenge to the opponent: “Segh þv fra þegnaskaupum þinum. / þig radumzt ek spyrrja” [“Tell about your honour, explain to us, I ask you”].¹⁰²³ Then follows a question about his achievements and the stanza concludes with an insult:

hvar sattu hrafn a hrislu
hrolla dreyra fvllan.
optar þattv at audrum.
j aunðvegi fvndinn.
enn þv dreyrvg hrę dręgir.
j dal fyrir valfugla.

Where did you see the raven on a branch
shuddering, full of blood.
More often than otherwise you accepted hospitality
and were found in the highseat
than procuring bleeding carrion
for birds of war in the dale!

It should be noted that these insults are levelled even though the two men taking part do not know each other. The beginning insults and challenges therefore have an initiatory purpose in the performance rather than being an actual personal attack (this contrasts, for example, to *Lokasenna*, in which Loki levels personal attacks at the assembled gods and goddesses). Indeed, this is the function accorded to the stanza by the saga prose: “Nu þickir þeim, er utar sat, til leitad vid sig i sliku tilkvędi ok kvad visu i moti” [“Now it seemed to the one, who sat further out, that he was challenged by such an address in verse, and he spoke a verse in reply”].¹⁰²⁴ The retaliating stanza the second arrival speaks is similarly neutral in its personal attack, but the third stanza is a boast by the first arrival of his exploits, the details countered by the second arrival in the fourth stanza. By this point it seems clear that the men know each other. This is confirmed in the fifth stanza:

Samira ockr at avlldrum
of onduęhe þręta.
hvar ockar hefir vnnit

¹⁰²² *Ragnars saga lođbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 171, ll. 24-31.

¹⁰²³ *Ragnars saga lođbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 171, ll. 24-25.

¹⁰²⁴ *Ragnars saga lođbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 172, ll. 1-2.

hvaðarr frammar odrum.¹⁰²⁵

This suggests that the willingness to undertake such a match and the ability to undertake it as well as the content of the stanzas exchanged are qualities that define a warrior, since here they lead to recognition. The sixth stanza, stanza thirty-seven beginning “Fylgdvm birne badir,”¹⁰²⁶ is an acknowledgement by the second man to arrive that they were indeed warriors together with Björn and Ragnarr, and the stanza ends with the invitation “sittu innar meir granni.”¹⁰²⁷ In the prose context, the second man to arrival was placed further in (in a more honoured position on the benches) than the first to arrive. The stanza sequence thus serves to acknowledge that the men are equals and comrades: “Ennda kenduz þeir þa vid of sidir ok voru þar siþan at veizlu.”¹⁰²⁸ This is rather than to establish a hierarchy as usual in *mannjafnaðr* (for example, the drinking contest in *Qrvar-Odds saga*).

The final episode containing stanzas also ends the saga. The three stanzas are spoken by a treeman, who stands, mighty, on the shore.¹⁰²⁹ The prose context surrounding the stanzas is irrelevant to the saga of Ragnarr and his sons; rather these stanzas have been included because the second stanza, stanza thirty-nine of the saga, mentions the sons of Ragnarr. The first stanza, beginning “þat var fyrir launghv,”¹⁰³⁰ is likely to have been borrowed from *Hálfs saga*.¹⁰³¹ The speaker in the stanza is not specific about who he is or what he rules, and thus the stanza can be used successfully in *Ragnars saga*.

¹⁰²⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 173, ll. 6-9.

¹⁰²⁶ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 173, ll. 15-22.

¹⁰²⁷ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 173, l. 22.

¹⁰²⁸ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 173, ll. 23-24.

¹⁰²⁹ The second and third stanzas of the treeman episode have been analysed at some length by McTurk in *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, pp. 17-39, in which their connection to fertility rituals are examined.

¹⁰³⁰ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 174, ll. 10-17.

¹⁰³¹ McTurk concludes that the stanza is likely to have been added to NKS 1824 b by the scribe of the manuscript (probably rather than the redactor of the Y version, as such, although this redactor may have known the stanza from a source other than *Hálfs saga*), *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, p. 18

The second stanza, beginning “ok þvi settv,”¹⁰³² begins with a line that makes it obvious that it comes after another stanza (although what this originally may have been is impossible to know).¹⁰³³ The second stanza links the stanza sequence more firmly to the prose context. In the prose, the men who find the treeman wonder “hverr blotad mundi hafa þetta et mikla god” [‘who might have sacrificed to this great god’].¹⁰³⁴ In the prose, this is in fact what the treeman responds to with his stanzas, introduced with “Ok þa kvedr tremadrinn” [‘and then the treeman says’]¹⁰³⁵ directly after the men voice their question. In the stanza, the treeman says: “þa var ek blotin / til bana monnum” [‘then I was sacrificed to for the deaths of men’].¹⁰³⁶ Stanza two also locates the treeman “i sams eyiv,”¹⁰³⁷ which is also in the prose above these stanzas. The detail from the third stanza that the treeman is covered in moss is also in the prose.¹⁰³⁸ The final sentence of the stanza, “Ok þetta þotti monnum undarligt, ok saughdu sidan fra audrum monnum” [‘and this seemed wonderful to the men, and afterwards they spoke of it to other men’],¹⁰³⁹ rationalises how these stanzas and the story about the treeman was transmitted after the episode took place.

Ragnars saga loðbrókar and Prosimetrum

In *Ragnars saga*, many of the stanzas are given a strong performance context: that is, in the prose surrounding the stanza, the verse can be seen to have an impact on the narrative, or characters or the narrator in the saga react to what the verse has said. This

¹⁰³² *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 174, ll. 17-25.

¹⁰³³ Perhaps the knowledge of Hávamál st. 49 prompted stanzas two and three spoken by the treeman to be linked to the first (also preserved in *Hálfs saga*). See McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, p. 29

¹⁰³⁴ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 174, ll. 8-9.

¹⁰³⁵ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 174, l. 9.

¹⁰³⁶ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 174, ll. 22-23.

¹⁰³⁷ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 174, l. 24.

¹⁰³⁸ For the significance of the treeman being covered in moss (as opposed to naked), see McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, pp. 29-30, in which he interprets the treeman’s lament in the third stanza as evidence that a ritual in which such treemen were decked with clothes has died out.

¹⁰³⁹ *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, ed. Olsen, p. 175, ll. 9-10.

is to be expected more with speech stanzas rather than evidence stanzas (although technically narrators could react to these, too). It is hard to say whether strong performance context in a prosimetric structure is likely to be an innovation when the legendary saga was committed to writing or whether it has roots in the oral tradition. The notion of *Begleitprosa* as explanatory prose following an oral stanza might to some degree suggest an interest in oral times for a narrative performance context, but even so, the burden of conveying performance characteristics in a narrative may have fallen largely on the performer himself. Nevertheless, we must not discount the possibility that a certain amount of setting the scene as well as something approaching dramatic tellings may have happened orally. The need for setting the scene is perhaps more obvious in a narrative with a narrator who speaks from a written page rather than one who is voiced through a performer with the possibility for movement, tone and gesture. Either could conceivably have used prose to capture or convey the reaction to a stanza, such as in the context of the first stanza of *Ragnars saga*. Not only is the description given of him speaking the stanza before and after it, the prose also records the princess's internal reaction to the stanza. This reaction in the prose can also be found in the skaldic prosimetra of *Fagrskinna*, and may be used to give the episode an anecdotal air in the hope that by bringing the episode to life in this way it will seem more authentic.

The third stanza of *Ragnars saga* is remarkable because it is spread across two speakers: we have also seen an example in *Fagrskinna* where one character speaks the first line of a verse and another character finishes the stanza. It is difficult to decide either way for certain whether this might be a product of the oral or written tradition behind the sagas. In an oral context, if one character were able to respond with a complementary half stanza to another character's speech, no doubt this would have been considered very skilled and witty. In application, this kind of 'sentence finishing' is easier to achieve in a written text.

Certainly extra emphasis is given to what is said in verse in *Ragnars saga*. Kráka's defiance about not accepting a tunic in the fifth stanza is highlighted in verse, and she concludes it with a prose line. This emphasis could come from an oral

prosimetric context, in which important dialogue was spoken in verse with an explanatory prose line added, clarifying the meaning of the stanza to listeners. In stanza six, Kráka speaks a prophecy in verse and the extra weight it seems to carry comes both from its verse form and its content.

The prosimetric structure is used to ask questions in the narrative of legendary sagas, and this dialogue structure is likely from the oral period. The stanzas that contain questions usually request that a person indentifies themselves, and often this descends into threats (for example in *Ketils saga hængs*). However, Áslaug uses a stanza to ask for news. In using a verse in this way instead of using prose, Áslaug may be asserting her social superiority and this may also be a connotation of verse requests for identification in the other legendary sagas, since versifying was a valuable social skill.

The episode in which Áslaug urges her sons to avenge their dead halfbrothers displays a prosimetric construction that the characters themselves deem to have come out of an oral context: Ívarr comments “Eigi er vist...hvart þat stodar nackvat, þottu kvedir aðra visu at annari” [‘it is not certain...whether that helps anything, even if you speak one verse after another’]. This tells us about the prosimetric form that it could be used in extemporaneous, communicative contexts to persuade as well as to question and inform. It seems that Áslaug thought her words might carry extra weight were she to speak in verse, but her son prosaically informs her that he and his brothers will not be so easily persuaded. It seems that here the prosimetric form is noticed when it is used in speech contexts by the characters, again highlighting the important social and oral role of poetic speech with prose reply.

It is usual for stanzas cited immediately after one another in both the *konungasögur*, the *fornaldarsögur*, and the heroic eddic poetry to have a joining prose statement. Typically it is similar to the one found introducing the twenty-fourth stanza of *Ragnars saga*: “ok enn kvað hann visu.” The phrase itself does not indicate at what point in time the stanza is spoken, only that it is relative to the verse before it comes after. Ordinarily one might assume in the prosimetra that the second stanza came directly after the first. However, the episode in *Ragnars saga* suggests otherwise,

since it becomes clear that inbetween the stanzas being spoken, Ragnarr has had his ships prepared and loaded, and an army gathered. This indicates that accretive stanzas can be used in speech contexts as well as in the evidence role discussed in *Fagrskinna*. Having prose between the stanzas is ubiquitous in all the prosimetric saga subgenres and likely has its roots in oral tradition in a declamatory context. The accretive method of constructing a prosimetrum is traditional and as *Ragnars saga* shows, can help substantially in moving the plot along.

Stanzas 28-29 are two stanzas of Ragnarr's death song, a well known oral genre from both Old Norse and other Germanic traditions. The stanzas integration into the prose is achieved by foreshadowing and repetition of the content of the verse in the prose, and role of the verse is as speech stanzas. It is quite unusual to have the content of speech stanzas repeated in the prose and this perhaps tells us that it was considered a special type of prosimetra at the point of death of the hero, and the structure thus served to emphasize the special status of the dying character. The saga also contains another traditional, oral prosimetric form: the *mannjafnaðr*, from stanza 32 onwards. The structure as employed in *Ragnars saga* demonstrates that the form can be used for positive purposes as well as name calling, since it is by the *mannjafnaðr* that the men who are taking part recognise each other as former comrades.

From the final prosimetric episode in the saga concerning the treeman, we can conclude that verses play a role as speech stanzas in saga narrative even though they were clearly never composed for that role. A verse can be drawn in because it is somehow considered relevant, even if only tangentially. This is perhaps a hangover from the oral period when demands on narrative coherency may have been less strict; employing a stanza from elsewhere may have even been done for comic effect.

The most important conclusion to be drawn from an analysis of the prosimetric structure of *Ragnars saga* does not concern the compilation of the saga itself like *Völsunga saga* but rather the construction of individual episodes: a well-integrated performance context for the stanzas has probably been a key concern in both the oral and written periods, as authors, performers and narrators in both periods captured the

characters' imagined responses to the stanzas cited in the verse. In this manner, prosimetrum was probably viewed as a dynamic and engaging method of building up a scene in a saga, and one in which the mental aspects of the characters could also be explored as they reacted in the narrative to the verse they heard. Such prosimetric scenes have formed the building blocks of this saga.

Þáttr af Ragnarssonum

This short *þáttr* is found in the Hauksbók manuscript AM 544 4to at 105r21-107v, written in Haukr's own hand. The manuscript is dated 1306-1308, although the *þáttr* itself was likely composed in the late 13th or early 14th centuries.¹⁰⁴⁰ This *þáttr* may represent an earlier stage of the traditions surrounding Ragnarr than those captured in his saga; various sources are pulled together in the text to emphasise the genealogical aspect, perhaps because both Haukr Erlendsson (who commissioned and partly wrote the Hauksbók manuscript) and his wife said themselves to be part of the Skjöldung clan. As well as having the lost *Skjöldunga saga* as a source, the *þáttr* seems also to be based on a lost version of *Ragnars saga*, from which the X and Y versions (although the Y version less directly) both descended.¹⁰⁴¹

The *þáttr* contains nine stanzas, seven of which also occur in *Ragnars saga*. The first prosimetric episode in the *þáttr* contains all seven of these stanzas from *Ragnars saga*. The first stanza of the saga begins “Uil ek eigi boð fyri broðvr,”¹⁰⁴² is introduced as a normal dialogue stanza and are Eiríkr's words as he dies aloft on spears. The prose line that links his next stanza informs the reader of a sight Eiríkr had seen before he was put up on the spears, and so thus is a brief moment of flashback. The second stanza, beginning “Þav berið orð eð efra,”¹⁰⁴³ is again spoken by Eiríkr and introduced with “þa q(vað) hann,”¹⁰⁴⁴ the introductory formula indicating that this stanza is further on in time than the first.

The tightly structured episode continues with the news of his death reaching his step-mother and half-brothers, whose exchange lasts for five stanzas. Two of those are

¹⁰⁴⁰ McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, p. 56.

¹⁰⁴¹ Rory McTurk, “The Earliest Extant Icelandic Manifestations of *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*,” pp. 43-64; McTurk, *Studies in Ragnars saga loðbrókar*, p. 56.

¹⁰⁴² *Ragnars sona þáttr*, *Hauksbók*, ed. Finnur Jónsson (København: Thieles, 1892-96) pp. 458-467, at p. 460, ll. 4-9.

¹⁰⁴³ *Ragnars sona þáttr*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 460, ll. 11-13.

¹⁰⁴⁴ *Ragnars sona þáttr*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 460, ll. 10-11.

introduced with “svaraði” which intensifies the depiction of verbal interaction between the characters.¹⁰⁴⁵ After the exchange is finished, the saga moves on.

The eight stanza is a half strophe in *tøglag*, which is a quotation from Sigvatr Þórðarson’s *Knútsdrápa*: “Sva segir Sigvatr skalld i Knutz drapv.”¹⁰⁴⁶ The quotation is introduced as an evidence stanza from a named poet and poem in the style found in *konungasögur*. This quotation is not in *Ragnars saga*. The final stanza in the *þáttr* is a speech verse spoken by Áslaug, which begins “Sitia veiði vitiar.”¹⁰⁴⁷ There is no reaction to the stanza in the prose.

Þáttr af Ragnarssonum and Prosimetrum

Ragnars saga and the *þáttr* contain mainly eddic verse. Nevertheless, they are *fornaldarsögur*. It is thus interesting that the one of final stanzas in the *þáttr*, neither of which are not in the saga, is very much in the style of how skaldic poetry is used in the *konungasögur*. The skaldic quotation from a named skald and named skaldic poem is unique in the *fornaldarsaga* genre. This is in contrast to the way that the dialogue between Áslaug and her stepsons is set up, which is fast, tightly structured and lasts for five stanzas, and in prosimetric structure has many parallels in other *fornaldarsögur*. Skaldic dialogue in *Fagrskinna*, for example, is much shorter; five of the skaldic verses that the *þáttr* shares with the saga are then used in a manner typical of eddic dialogues in the *fornaldarsögur*.

¹⁰⁴⁵ *Ragnars sona þáttr*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 461, ll. 1, 8.

¹⁰⁴⁶ *Ragnars sona þáttr*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 464, ll. 7-8.

¹⁰⁴⁷ *Ragnars sona þáttr*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, p. 466, ll. 13-16.

*Hervarar saga ok Heiðriks*¹⁰⁴⁸

Hervarar saga, dated to the 13th century,¹⁰⁴⁹ is thought to contain some of the oldest Norse poetry, most famously the poem towards the end of the saga known as *Hlǫðskviða* [‘Hlǫðr’s Poem’] (usually *The Battle of the Goths and the Huns* in English), which Tolkien suggests acquired its present form in Viking-Age Norway even though elements of it could stem from even more “remote antiquity;” L. M. Hollander identifies these ancient elements as “Gothic traditions” that “must be very old,” and also seems to consider the poem reliable.¹⁰⁵⁰ The great age of the poem also seems to be confirmed by its metre, a West Germanic alliterative metre common to that found in *Hamðismál*, in which the syllabic length of lines show a lot of variation, in contrast with the stricter metre of most Eddic poems.¹⁰⁵¹ A riddle collection in the saga, *Heiðreks gátur*, also seems to be very old.¹⁰⁵² To these poems can be added *Hervararkviða*, in which Hervǫr wakes her dead father Angantýr from the grave to recover the sword Tyrfingr, and a version of Hjálmar’s death song (which is also found in *Qrvar-Odds saga*).¹⁰⁵³

It seems that these poems and riddles form the core(s) of the saga, and the prose has been composed around them.¹⁰⁵⁴ If the saga “gives the impression of having been pulled together from sundry sources which have been unified with varying

¹⁰⁴⁸ Note that *Hervarar saga* is known by several names. The full title of the saga in modern editions is normally given as *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks konungs*, shortened either to *Heiðreks saga* or *Hervarar saga*; I opt for the latter. Jón Helgason, the editor of the current standard edition of 1924, used *Heiðreks saga* as the shortened title for his edition, so references to his edition will use this form of the shortened title.

¹⁰⁴⁹ L. M. Hollander, “The Battle on the Vin-Heath and the Battle of the Huns,” *The Journal of English and Germanic Philology* 32 (1933): 33-43, at 38.

¹⁰⁵⁰ Hollander, “The Battle on the Vin-Heath and the Battle of the Huns,” pp. 38, 41.

¹⁰⁵¹ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Christopher Tolkien & ed. G. Turville-Petre, Text Series 2 (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1956) xi-xii.

¹⁰⁵² Cf. Torfi H. Tulinius 2002:22-23; Brynjulf Alver, “Norrøne gåter frå mellomalderen,” *Syn og segn* 60 (1954): 29-36; Brynjulf Alver and Anne Holtsmark, “Gátur,” *Kulturbistorisk Leksikon for nordisk middelalder* 5 (1960), 648-653; Anne Holtsmark, “Den uløselige gåten,” *Maal og mine* 1964: 101-105.

¹⁰⁵³ See Christopher Tolkien, “The Battle of the Goths and Huns,” *Saga-Book* 14 (1953-7): 141-163; Jón Jóhannesson, “Bjorn at Haugi,” trans. G. Turville-Petre, *Saga-Book* 17 (1966-9): 293-301.

¹⁰⁵⁴ Cf. Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 23.

degrees of success,” as Torfi H. Tulinius has observed,¹⁰⁵⁵ then the question of the development and the age of the prose is open: if the saga did develop from poetic cores, and these versi-prose cores were then pulled together to form a long saga, was extra prose slotted in to fill in the narrative gaps? Several scholars have posited that narrative continuity is given by the sword Tyrfingr,¹⁰⁵⁶ and I wonder whether this narrative continuity was demanded by the medieval compiler, wishing to put together myriad poetic sources into a convincing narrative saga, or whether the search for narrative continuity is a demand of the modern reader, who strains to see how the poetic sources have been combined when there may in fact be no strict underlying conscious plan, but rather a gradual bringing together of various poetic elements at different times in the tradition. The poetic sources, if we accept that each group of stanzas I refer to above as “poems” moved together as units, may have come together gradually, forming their current constellation because of their shared interest in the lines of certain characters or because that was simply the direction in which the story ended up extending, and certain poems (or themes, like the sword Tyrfingr) seemed to fit.

There are three redactions of *Hervarar saga*, referred to by the sigla R, H and U,¹⁰⁵⁷ preserved in six manuscripts of independent value. These redactions are thought to descend from a common lost archetype, although they have significant differences between them in terms of events and characters.¹⁰⁵⁸ The oldest of these redactions is H, preserved in *Hauksbók*, AM 544 4to at 72v9-76v, which dates to the very beginning of the 14th century.¹⁰⁵⁹ The saga is written in Haukr’s own hand.¹⁰⁶⁰ The H version of

¹⁰⁵⁵ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 23.

¹⁰⁵⁶ Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 148; *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Christopher Tolkien & ed. G. Turville-Petre, p. xi; Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 23.

¹⁰⁵⁷ For convenient overviews of the manuscript traditions of *Hervarar saga*, see Torfi H. Tulinius (2002: 21-22); *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Christopher Tolkien & ed. G. Turville-Petre, pp. xvii-xix.

¹⁰⁵⁸ Cf. *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Christopher Tolkien & ed. G. Turville-Petre, pp. xviii-xix; Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, pp. 22.

¹⁰⁵⁹ Stefán Karlsson. “Aldur Hauksbókar.” *Fróðskaparrit* 13 (1964): 114-21. Note that the manuscript is today broken up into three parts: AM 371 4to, AM 544 4to, and AM 675 4to. Kâlund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 683.

the saga as a whole seems to have been shortened, although there is a mythological prologue to the H version not present in the others, and which Torfi H. Tulinius concludes “does not seem to have been present in the earlier version of the saga.”¹⁰⁶¹

The version in this manuscript ends at the beginning of *Heiðreks gátur*, from the answer to the second riddle (Turville-Petre’s edition 38/17), since there is a lacuna between folia 76 and 77, and the manuscript picks up again in *Fóstbræðra saga*.¹⁰⁶² Two 17th century paper manuscripts, AM 281 4to (h1) on 98v-101r,¹⁰⁶³ and AM 597 b 4to on 49r-51v (h2),¹⁰⁶⁴ are indirect copies of Hauksbók and contain the riddle episode until the end, and thus we have the H version until the end of the riddles.¹⁰⁶⁵

The redaction known as R is found in GKS 2845 4to, the main vellum of *Hálfs saga Hálfsrekka* (see above) at 61v-73v, the last saga of the manuscript, although the saga is fragmentary in this manuscript and has a lacuna where one leaf has been lost (Turville-Petre’s edition pp.21/19-24/11) and is missing the end (Turville-Petre’s edition from 56/22).¹⁰⁶⁶ The manuscript dates from, the 15th century, possibly around 1400.¹⁰⁶⁷ This is thought to be a “fuller version of the saga, though some of the variants in H seem to be more correct.”¹⁰⁶⁸ The maligned third redaction, known as U, is to be found in Uppsala University Library, manuscript R:715. It dates from the mid-17th

¹⁰⁶⁰ *Heiðreks Saga: Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks Konungs*, ed. Jón Helgason, Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur 48 (Copenhagen: J. Jørgensen, 1924) xvii.

¹⁰⁶¹ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 21.

¹⁰⁶² *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. xviii.

¹⁰⁶³ From the end of the 17th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 533.

¹⁰⁶⁴ From the second half of the 17th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 764.

¹⁰⁶⁵ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Christopher Tolkien & ed. G. Turville-Petre, pp. xvii.

¹⁰⁶⁶ Several scholars have made full descriptions of the manuscript. See the following: *Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka*, ed. Hubert Seelow, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar á Íslandi Rit 20 (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1981) pp. 83-106; *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, pp. i-ix. For the paper manuscripts descended from R, see *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, pp. ix-xvii.

¹⁰⁶⁷ See *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. i. Kálund in *KAH*, vol. 1, p. 49, dates the manuscript to the 15th century. Hubert Seelow dates the manuscript to around 1450 in *Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka*, ed. Seelow, pp. 105-106.

¹⁰⁶⁸ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 22.

century.¹⁰⁶⁹ Thought to be very corrupt, it is used to fill the lacuna in the R version from the fragmentary GKS 2845 4to. HU are thought by Jón Helgason to derive from *u*, and that H is a condensed redaction of *u*.

A fourth manuscript, the 17th century AM 203 fol. in Den Arnamagnæanske Samling, Copenhagen, is also of importance in the manuscript tradition of *Hervarar saga*, which is found on 88r-114v.¹⁰⁷⁰ The scribe of AM 203 fol., Síra Jón Erlendsson, is thought to have had access to be a better copy of *u* than that available to the scribe of U. He also had access to the H version (possibly Hauksbók itself) and a version of the R-type; he copied that but used *u* at the beginning of the saga (to 2/ 13 of G. Turville-Petre's edition),¹⁰⁷¹ and then to fill in the missing conclusion (55/20 to the end of G. Turville-Petre's edition),¹⁰⁷² and in these places, AM 203 fol. has independent value.¹⁰⁷³

In terms of the differences between the three redactions, HU are closer to each other than R is to either of them, to the point where Tolkien has commented “that it would be truer to speak of two major redactions ... than of three.”¹⁰⁷⁴ Tolkien has claimed that R stands nearer to the original written *Hervarar saga*, while U is a completely reworked version of the saga; H and U have a common original, although H or its exemplar was combining two versions (the second is close to the R type) that were sometimes contradictory;¹⁰⁷⁵ however, it seems an obvious suggestion that the differences between the versions may in fact be due to them being different recordings from oral tradition, especially in the case of U as compared to R and it being “entirely

¹⁰⁶⁹ *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. xx. For a full description of the manuscript see pp. xx-xxv.

¹⁰⁷⁰ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 167.

¹⁰⁷¹ The variants of AM 203 fol. are given against U at this part of the saga in Jón Helgason's edition of in *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, pp. 89-94.

¹⁰⁷² The variants of AM 203 fol. are given against U at this part of the saga in Jón Helgason's edition *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, pp. 143-161. See also *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, pp. xxix-xxxiii.

¹⁰⁷³ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xviii.

¹⁰⁷⁴ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xviii.

¹⁰⁷⁵ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xviii.

reworked” (Tolkien’s emphasis),¹⁰⁷⁶ these entirely different versions sounds like a good candidate for a different oral version. Likewise, the following description, typical of those of H, also suggests that H may have been another version from oral tradition: the version “cuts down the stories in a negligent way, as if the scribe were in haste.”¹⁰⁷⁷ The concise version of the story could perhaps be a half-remembered version, or simply a different, less full version than R, rather than a story copied badly in written transmission.

It is very noticeable in *Hervarar saga* that the only verse included in the saga is in the four poems discussed at the beginning; we find no other *lausavísur* in the middle section of the saga, since the four poems are bunched up at either end, Hjálmar’s Death Song and *Hervararkviða* towards the beginning of the poem, and *Heiðreks gátur* and *Hlǫðskviða* towards the end.¹⁰⁷⁸ This use of poetry in a *fornaldarsaga* – as the inclusion of whole poems very much at either end of the saga – is rather unusual.

The following comments are based on Jón Helgason’s edition of 1924. R and H are printed R above U on pp. 1-88. He prints the H edition from *Hauksbók* as far as it goes, and then pp. 58.23-83.26 are used to provide the end of the saga, taken from AM 597 b 4to, with full variants given from AM 281 4to. The edition of H is a normalised edition. U is printed after, pp. 89-161.

Hjálmar’s Death Song

Hjálmar’s death song is in R and U but is not present in H, where the action is summarised very briefly in prose: “Hjálmar drap Angantý ok dó þar sjálfr síðan af sárum” [‘Hjálmar killed Angantýr and died there himself afterwards of wounds’].¹⁰⁷⁹

¹⁰⁷⁶ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xviii.

¹⁰⁷⁷ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xix.

¹⁰⁷⁸ The prose story as a whole has been divided into seven sections by Alaric Hall, four of which contain verse. See Alaric Hall, “Changing Style and Changing Meaning: Icelandic Historiography and the Medieval Redactions of *Heiðreks saga*,” *Scandinavian Studies* 77 (2005): 1-30, at 2-3.

¹⁰⁷⁹ *Heiðreks Saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 12, ll. 28-29.

The episode is also present in *Qrvar-Odds saga*. I will compare the version in *Qrvar-Odds saga* with the version in *Hervarar saga* in my discussion of *Qrvar-Odds saga*.

Hjálmar's death song is a prosimetric episode containing 12 stanzas in R and 13 in U. In R, the first stanza is spoken by Oddr as berserkers approach him and Hjálmar. The stanza, beginning "þa uar mer otti,"¹⁰⁸⁰ is introduced with "Þa quad Oddr" (U "Oddur quad")¹⁰⁸¹ and describes, in the past tense, Oddr's momentary fear as he saw their attackers disembark. In R, Hjálmar replies, "þa mællti Hialmar til Odds,"¹⁰⁸² in prose to Oddr's verse, meaning there is no poetic dialogue set up here. The function of the verse seems only to be to express Oddr's fear. The ensuing conversation between the characters is reported in prose, with the narrator pausing to offer two authenticating verses: "þetta uídr mæli þeira sanna þessar uisur, er Híalmar quad" ['their words are proved true by these verses, when Hjálmar says'], and then a verse by Hjálmar, beginning "Fara halir hraistir,"¹⁰⁸³ is quoted, followed by "Oddr segir," and then a verse by Oddr, the third stanza of the saga beginning with "Þui mun ordi / ansuar ueíta." ['That speech will be replied to with'],¹⁰⁸⁴ making it clear that this stanza is a response to another. Although used as evidence by the narrator, the stanzas are actually speech stanzas which blend into reported quotations: 'when Hjálmar said this..., Oddr says this....' From there, the saga in R switches back to prose, and describes how Hjálmar begins to fight with the Angantýr.

In U, the prosimetric construction of the scene is rather different. Hjálmar replies to the first stanza spoken by Oddr in verse: the second stanza (beginning

¹⁰⁸⁰ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 9, ll. 22-25 – p. 10, ll. 1-2.

¹⁰⁸¹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 97, ll. 18-19.

¹⁰⁸² *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 10, l. 3.

¹⁰⁸³ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 10, ll. 17-24.

¹⁰⁸⁴ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 10, ll. 25-26.

“Ganga halir hraustir”¹⁰⁸⁵ comes immediately in reply, introduced with “Hialmar quad.” The third stanza, beginning “Þui mun eg ordi,”¹⁰⁸⁶ is introduced “Þetta eitt mælti Hialmar ædruord, suo men viti. Oddr quad þa” [‘This was the only time Hjálmar spoke words of fear, so men know. Oddr then spoke’],¹⁰⁸⁷ and these speeches replaces the authenticating function of the stanzas in the R, where Hjálmar’s fear is not commented upon. Up to this point, the stanzas in R and U have been in the same order. After the third stanza shared between the redactions, however, U has an extra stanza. This fourth stanza is spoken by Hjálmar and begins “Flyum [vier] fyrir,”¹⁰⁸⁸ and is a regular speech stanza by Hjálmar that is not reacted to in the text.

The fourth stanza in R and U (where it is the fifth) is a speech stanza introduced with “Oddr kallar á berserki ok quad” [‘Oddr called to the berserks and said’] and in it Oddr challenges the berserks to single combat; the following prose describes how Oddr kills them individually. In R, the narrator comes back in with a comment to bring the focus back to Hjálmar with “EN fra leik þeira Hialmars er þat at segía...” [‘And about the fight between Hjálmar and his opponent is there this to tell...’],¹⁰⁸⁹ and with this short piece of prose, Hjálmar’s death is clearly approaching, as Oddr speaks a stanza (the fifth of the saga, beginning “Huat er þier, Híalmir?”)¹⁰⁹⁰ that informs the reader that Hjálmar looks like he is dying. With this, Hjálmar’s death song proper begins. U simply begins after the description of Oddr’s fights with Oddr’s stanza, which in U is the sixth, and then Hjálmar’s death song begins.

¹⁰⁸⁵ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 97, ll. 27-34.

¹⁰⁸⁶ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 98, ll. 3-8.

¹⁰⁸⁷ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 98, l. 1.

¹⁰⁸⁸ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 98, ll. 11-14.

¹⁰⁸⁹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 11, l. 31 – p. 12, l. 1.

¹⁰⁹⁰ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 12, ll. 4-11.

In R, Hjálmar's speech of seven stanzas is introduced with "*Híalmar quad*"¹⁰⁹¹ and the second stanza is reintroduced with "*Ok en quad hann*,"¹⁰⁹² after which the remainder of the stanzas follow in a monologue. In U, the speech is also seven stanzas long, and the first stanza is also introduced with "*H(ialmar) quad*,"¹⁰⁹³ and the second stanza is also reintroduced with "*Enn kuad hann*,"¹⁰⁹⁴ after which the rest of the stanzas follow. The stanzas are not reacted to immediately in the prose, which follows the verse up by simply reporting that Hjálmar dies; however, in R, Oddr "*segir þessi tíðindí heim i Suiþíod*" ['tells this news at home in Sweden'], and it is not clear whether he is reporting only the general events or reporting the contents of the death song in addition. After the death song has ended, there is a medium length prose description of the birth and early years of Hervor, after which *Hervararkviða* begins.

Hervararkviða

Hervararkviða (usually known in English as 'The Waking of Angantýr') forms part of the Sámsey episode of the saga,¹⁰⁹⁵ of which Hjálmar's Death Song can also be considered a part. As for the origins of *Hervararkviða*, many scholars have supposed it born of a connection between an adaptation of some parts of *Hlǫðskviða* and the Sámsey episode, and thus to have united into one figure two originally distinct Angantýrs, one cognate with the Incgenþeow of *Widsith* and the one killed on Sámsey, and Tolkien has suggested that this combination of the two men into one was "a primary point of fusion in the growth of the *Hervarar saga*."¹⁰⁹⁶

¹⁰⁹¹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 12, l. 12. The stanzas are p. 12, ll. 13-27 – p. 14, ll. 1-14.

¹⁰⁹² *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 12, l. 21.

¹⁰⁹³ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 99, l. 25.

¹⁰⁹⁴ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 100, l. 3.

¹⁰⁹⁵ This episode appears in other sagas and genres, for example in *Qrvar-Odds saga* and in two versions in Saxo; further see Stephen A. Mitchell, "The fornaldarsögur and Nordic Balladry: The Sámsey Episode across Genres," *Fornaldarsagornas struktur och ideologi*, ed. Ármann Jakobsson, Annette Lassen & Agneta Ney (Uppsala: Uppsala Universitet, 2003) pp. 245-56.

¹⁰⁹⁶ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xvi.

In R, *Hervararkviða* begins at stanza 13, and the first stanza is spoken by Hervör before she moves into the supernatural realms of her father Angantýr’s barrow. It is a speech stanza, and its performance context is given in detail in the prose: “*Hervor uard uid þessi ord æfar reid ok gengr þegar firi iall ok quad*” [‘Hervör became enraged with these words and immediately went before the jarl and said’].¹⁰⁹⁷ The jarl responds immediately with a stanza (beginning “*Logít er mart at þer*”).¹⁰⁹⁸ That Hervör’s address to the jarl is in verse is likely meant to highlight her extreme emotion at that moment, and the jarl’s speech is in verse to match the intensity of the moment in the narrative, and also to confer upon the same dignity as her in engaging in a dialogue conversation. Hervör replies to the jarl in two stanzas introduced with “*Hon quad*”¹⁰⁹⁹ (stanzas 15 and 16 of R), but the third stanza in the unit of three stanzas that make up her reply in total is addressed to her mother, introduced with “*Síþan mallti Heruor uid modr sina ok quad*” [‘Afterwards Hervör spoke to her mother and said’].¹¹⁰⁰ It is not clear whether we are to imagine Hervör’s mother as present with the jarl and the stanza thus being spoken at the same time, or whether there is a gap of time implied by the introduction to the third stanza.

In U, the same stanzas appear, although they are numbered differently due to their being an extra stanza in U in *Hjálmar’s* death song. In U, the first stanza Hervör speaks in her rage is introduced as a speech stanza as in R, except the introductory tag is “*ok kuad uisu þessa*” [‘and said this verse’],¹¹⁰¹ and the prose thus explicitly acknowledges that she speaks in verse. The jarl too replies in verse (st. 15 in U, beginning “*Logid er margt ad þier*”)¹¹⁰² and Hervör replies with a unit of three

¹⁰⁹⁷ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 15, ll. 15-16.

¹⁰⁹⁸ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 15, ll. 26-27 – p. 16, ll. 1-6.

¹⁰⁹⁹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 16, l. 7.

¹¹⁰⁰ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 16, l. 24.

¹¹⁰¹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 102, ll. 22-23.

¹¹⁰² *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 103, ll. 6-13.

stanzas as in R. However, in U, the prose inbetween the stanzas that indicates the verse is spoken to her mother is not included and the stanza is thus addressed to the jarl as part of her address to him.

The poetry continues when Hervor reaches the island on which her father is buried. In R, Hervor, now called Herverðr, reaches the island and meets a shepherd. He begins the dialogue, stanza 18 (a half stanza) introduced with “*Hann quad*,”¹¹⁰³ and the second stanza (st. 19 of the saga, beginning “*Munka ek ganga*”)¹¹⁰⁴ is clearly spoken by Herverðr, although it is not introduced as such (there is no prose insertion naming the speaker). The third stanza of the episode is spoken by the shepherd again, introduced with “*Hann quad*”¹¹⁰⁵ and her reply in stanza 21 and his final verse in stanza 22 are both marked by the prose. There are five stanzas in total.

In H, the prosimetric construction is somewhat different. The seven stanzas present are presented as one long dialogue with no prose insertions to mark who is speaking. They are introduced with “*Þetta er kveðit eptir viðræðu þeira*” [“This is composed after their conversation”].¹¹⁰⁶ It is not clear that this is meant to introduce the stanzas as evidence stanzas, although this does seem to be part of their function in H. Rather, it seems the verses are introduced as a poem that was made to memorialise their conversation. There are two stanzas more than in R, which in U are the fourth and seventh stanzas. In U, the opening the of poem contains a narrative framework of four lines that is absent in R (the second half of stanza 1, and stanzas 2-6 in U are dialogue) and stanza 7 closes the narrative framework; this narrative role is undertaken by the prose in R.

The U redaction presents a prosimetric construction that is between R and H in style. It has the same stanzas as H and in the same order. The narrative elements of

¹¹⁰³ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 18, l. 2; the stanza is ll. 3-6.

¹¹⁰⁴ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 19, ll. 1-8.

¹¹⁰⁵ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 19, l. 9; stanza ll. 10-17.

¹¹⁰⁶ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 18, l. 24.

the verse in H is in U transformed in speech, which means the stanzas are slightly altered, but, in the style of R, prose insertions are provided labelling who is speaking. The seventh stanza in the episode (stanza 25 of U, which equates to stanza 7 of H), is introduced with several lines of prose, to compensate for what is a narrative description of the stanza in H being used as a speech stanza in U. In the prose, the narrator describes what the shepherd does (flee to the forest), whereas in the stanza, the shepherd himself gives this information. With this, the story moves on to Hervor's trip to the mounds in which the berserks are buried.

In R, her call to rouse Angantýr from his grave is introduced with “þa *quad* hon,” and similarly in H and U.¹¹⁰⁷ Four stanzas of speech follow, to which Angantýr replies, introduced in R with “Þa *quad* Angantyr”¹¹⁰⁸ and in H as “Þá svarar Angantýr.”¹¹⁰⁹ In R he speaks two stanzas before Hervor is introduced again with “Hon *quad*,”¹¹¹⁰ but in H, she is not reintroduced, meaning that the reader must realise by the content of the verse (H stanza 14, which equates to R stanza 29) that the speaker of the stanza is Hervor and not Angantýr. In both redactions there then appears a small amount of prose to describe how the mound stood open ablaze. Their conversation then continues, the speaker being introduced in prose each time they switch. In R, this conversation is stanzas 30-40, and in H stanzas 15-30. The three last stanzas are lacking in R, since it is missing a page. In H, the prose continues by simply describing what Hervor did next, rather than commenting on the verses.

In U, after Hervor's initial call to her father, rather than Angantýr speaking directly straight away, verses simply are shown to emanate from Angantýr's barrow: “þa var þetta kvedid i haugi Anganntyrs” [‘then was this recited in Angantýr's barrow’].¹¹¹¹ From here however, Hervor and Angantýr's verse conversation continues

¹¹⁰⁷ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 21, ll. 17, 31; p. 107, l. 15.

¹¹⁰⁸ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 24, l. 5.

¹¹⁰⁹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 24, l. 20.

¹¹¹⁰ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 25, l. 5.

¹¹¹¹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 108, l. 24.

normally, with each speaker introduced in prose, for 18 stanzas until the poem concludes. There is a small amount of extra prose before stanza 41 in U, which describes very briefly how Hervor now has the sword, but otherwise there is no additional information and the saga moves on after the stanzas in the same manner as the RH redactions.

Heiðreks Gátur

A complete analysis of the differences between the riddles in each version of the saga is outside the scope of this thesis; Jón Helgason has outlined in the past the differences between the order of the riddles,¹¹¹² and neither this nor their content will be commented upon here. Rather I will seek to characterise the prosimetric structure of this section.

From a prosimetric perspective, the riddle sequence of *Hervarar saga* known as *Heiðreks Gátur* is particularly interesting, since the riddles are metrical (in a mixture of *fornyrðislag* and *ljóðaháttur*), but the answers to the riddle are in prose, and, according to Tolkien, there is no evidence that they were ever in verse.¹¹¹³ The consensus is that the riddles are anterior to the prose, and that the composer of the prose scene of the contest between Heiðrekr and Gestumblindi had collected riddles that were circulating individually.¹¹¹⁴ The content of the riddles is drawn from the natural world, and due to this and the lack of any indication of martial imagery, Finnur Jónsson dated the riddles to the middle of the 11th century to the end of the 12th century, which was a period of peace and of great scholarly and learned activity in Iceland. Although Tolkien may have a point when he says that there is no need to connect the riddles to the learned activities of the 12th century,¹¹¹⁵ nevertheless, the riddles in *Hervarar saga* hold a special place in Old Norse and indeed in medieval vernacular literature, since

¹¹¹² *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. lxxxi.

¹¹¹³ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xiv.

¹¹¹⁴ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xiv.

¹¹¹⁵ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xv.

they have almost no parallels in content and no other information whatsoever is recorded about any riddle traditions.¹¹¹⁶ The question with which the riddle sequence ends is the same as that which Óðinn asks Vafþrúðnir at the end of *Vafþrúðnismál*, about what Óðinn said in the ear of the dead Baldr, which is unanswerable. In the absence of any further evidence whatsoever of an Old Norse riddle tradition, it is to the wisdom contest poems and prose *mannjafnaðr* that we ought to look for comparanda in terms of their narrative construction.

The construction of the presentation of a riddle is such that Gestumblindi (or Gestur in U), is introduced as speaking, and immediately speaks a stanza that contains a riddle. After this, the king replies in prose, usually prefacing his comments with a statement that the riddle was a good one, and then the king gives the answer to the riddle.

In RH, it is immediately noticeable that during the contest, Gestumblindi is always labelled as a speaker, but his opponent almost never is. This is despite the fact that Gestumblindi almost always speaks in verse and the opponent in prose, so after the initial set up of the scene, it would not be difficult to understand who was speaking. Looking at this another way, we might conclude that Gestumblindi is labelled precisely because he speaks in verse and is speaking the important part of the exchange: the riddle itself, which is in verse but in stanzas of unequal length. Often the response to the riddle is a prose passage of six or so lines; however, these are several responses that are much shorter and simply give the answer to the riddle.¹¹¹⁷ In U, however, the king is usually introduced as making a reply when the prose begins after the stanza, and his comments after the riddle are on the whole shorter than in RH.

¹¹¹⁶ Those riddles that are similar in the modern Icelandic riddle tradition should be considered as borrowings from *Heiðreks gáttur*, and the only riddle that does come up elsewhere is the Cow-Riddle (on Turville-Petre's edition p. 49/13-20) that appears all over Europe (*Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xiv).

¹¹¹⁷ E.g. *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 79, ll. 10-11, 26-27; p. 81, ll. 10-11, 26-27; p. 82, l. 9.

Gestumblindi picks riddles as a way in which to redeem himself in order to avoid being judged by the king's wisemen.¹¹¹⁸ At the end of the section, it becomes clear that the mysterious figure putting forth the riddles is Óðinn, and the king is eventually killed. This is in accordance with other Óðinnic wisdom contests, for example *Grímnismál*.

Hlōðskviða

As explained above, *Hlōðskviða* is considered to be one of the oldest Old Norse poems extant on the basis of its content, metre and from the sense of certain words; all suggest an pre-Norse origin for the poem.¹¹¹⁹ The poem was likely already a prosimetrum by the time it was incorporated into *Hervarar saga*, and indeed may have always been prosimetric.¹¹²⁰

Names in the poem seem to point to an Southern-Eastern European area of origin for the poem: *Danþarstaðir* found in the poem seems to be the same as the form *Danaþer* used by the Gothic Jordanes of the river Dnieper in the 6th century, and the word *Harvaða-fjöll* used of the Carpathians seems to have developed from the Germanic **Xarfap-* as a result of the Germanic consonant-shift.¹¹²¹

The assumption that an historical battle underlies the poem is one repeated often enough to have become a consensus. A number of suggestions have been put forward as to the identity of the actual historical event underlying the poem, and, though now dismissed, the assumed event was for a long time identified with the mighty battle of 451 that took place between the Huns (ruled by Attila) and his subjected peoples, and the Western Empire with Visigothic allies.¹¹²² Other theories

¹¹¹⁸ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 56, ll. 5. ff and 18 ff.; p. 130, l. 11 ff.

¹¹¹⁹ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xii; Hollander, "The Battle on the Vin-Heath and the Battle of the Huns," p. 36.

¹¹²⁰ Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 148.

¹¹²¹ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre, p. xii.

¹¹²² *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre xii.

proposed since situate the battle in Europe post the defeat of Attila, in battles recorded by the 4th century Roman historians, and in battles in which either the Huns or Goths were absent, or both.¹¹²³ Tolkien deems the suggestion that the oldest material in the poem goes back to the late 4th and early 5th centuries and the wars of the Goths north of the Black Sea, soon after the Huns had appeared the most likely; in support of the idea, the South Eastern names discussed above point at least to the region.¹¹²⁴ It seems safest to conclude that whether or not the poem is based upon an actual battle is unrecoverable, and that lack of positive identification makes it seem likely that it perhaps was not, although there may be some traces left in the poem of the regional identity of its some of its names.

Another important point in the prehistory of the poem is its connection to the Old English poem *Widsith* 116ff. The Anglo-Saxon poem mentions the characters Heoporic (cf. *Heiðrekr*), Sifeca (cf. *Sifka*), Hliþe (cf. *Hlöðr*), Incgenþeow (cf. *Angantýr*), and Wyrnhere (cf. *Ormarr*), and this is important with regard to the debate as to whether the conflict between the brothers *Hlöðr* and *Angantýr* is an original part of the poem, since Henrik Schück in *Studier i Hervararsagen* argued that Saxo had access to two poems about the Battle of the Huns, one about the huge battle, and one about the conflict between *Hlöðr* and *Angantýr*, which did not include the battle. In Schück's view, the two separate motifs have been combined in *Hervarar saga*.¹¹²⁵ Hollander, on the other hand, finds it more likely that Saxo heard an earlier version of *Hervarar saga* than the one extant, and in book 5 of the *Gesta Danorum* we find a vague recollection of the story told to him by Icelandic or Norwegian authorities.¹¹²⁶ It seems reasonable to assume that the Old English and Old Norse characters share a common origin, especially considering that the Old English poem

¹¹²³ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre xii.

¹¹²⁴ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre xiii.

¹¹²⁵ Henrik Schück, *Studier i Hervararsagen*, *Uppsala universitets årsskrift* (1918) p. 23 ff.; cf. *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre p. xiii.

¹¹²⁶ Hollander, "The Battle on the Vin-Heath and the Battle of the Huns," pp. 39-40.

also mentions *Ætlan leode* (the Huns), and *Hrædas* (the Goths, Norse *Reiðgotar*, and earlier *Hreiðgotar*), and that the poems tell of the same events.¹¹²⁷

The prose that leads up to *Hlǫðskviða* proper begins by describing the death of King Heiðrekr at the hands of slaves, as Óðinn predicted (or cursed) at the end of *Heiðreks Gátur*, and the theft of his sword Tyrfingr. His son, Angantýr, travels to avenge his father and hears a man on a fishing trip speak a verse, the content of which alerts him to the fact that the sword the fisherman have in Tyrfingr. The stanza the man speaks is a regular speech stanza (beginning “þess gallt hon gedda”),¹¹²⁸ and has a close performance context, because it is addressed to other men and overheard by Angantýr, to whom it conveys information. This resolution of the theft of the sword connects the riddle section to *Hlǫðskviða* in the saga by providing a situation in which Angantýr can gather nobles for his father’s funeral feast.

The funeral feast is the context in which the first stanza of *Hlǫðskviða* appears, stanza 72 in R beginning “Ar quopu Humla.”¹¹²⁹ It is introduced in the style of an evidence stanza with “sem her segir,” but upon closer inspection, it does not provide evidence for what is said in the prose. Rather the prose uses the stanza to provide information that it does not repeat: “Þa redu þessir konungar landum, sem her segir” [‘These kings ruled over the lands then, as it says here’].¹¹³⁰ The narrative then speeds up, the slow scene of Angantýr’s retrieval of his father’s sword replaced by a faster-paced prosimetrum. This stanza is not in U.

¹¹²⁷ *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre p. xiii. Tolkien also comments that if we are prepared to accept the common origin of the poems on these bases, we should count the mention in *Widsith* of “Vistula Wood” as a “distortion of the legend” in *Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks*, intro. Tolkien & ed. Turville-Petre p. xiv. I do not agree: *Widsith* in this particular probably simply preserves a different version of the tale rather than something that ought to be classified as an error. For further on this, see Hollander, “The Battle on the Vin-Heath and the Battle of the Huns,” pp. 33-43, esp. 38-40. For further connections between *Widsith* and the North Germanic tribes, see William Witherle Lawrence, “Structure and Interpretation of ‘Widsith,’” *Modern Philology* 4 (1906): 329-374. See also Kemp Malone, “Widsith and the Hervararsaga,” *Publications of the Modern Language Association* 40 (1925): 769-813.

¹¹²⁸ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 84, ll. 28-31; p. 141, ll. 8-11.

¹¹²⁹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 85, ll. 12-19.

¹¹³⁰ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 85, ll. 10-11.

The second to fourth stanzas in R of the episode (numbers 73-75), are evidence stanzas in the narrative and have prose inbetween them that the stanzas corroborate. In stanza 75 in particular however, it can be seen that the stanza is also contributing to the story. Stanza 74 gives more details about what the prose introduction to it says, because the dialogue in stanza 75, in which Hloðr tells a man to go to Angantýr and tell him to speak with him, is necessary for the prose following the stanza to make sense: “Sa geck inn firi konungs bord...” [“So the man went in before the king’s table...”].¹¹³¹ The action in the prose following the stanza is a direct result of the demand in the stanza. In this way, evidence stanzas can also be used to add to the narrative. The following stanza (number 76, beginning “Her er Hlaidr komin”)¹¹³² is a speech stanza introduced with “ok mælti siþan,” and as such follows on from the previous stanza in giving information to the story. Here in the prosimetrum, a speech stanza included in a scene is reported both under the umbrella of the evidence stanza before it.

In R, this alternation between evidence stanza and speech stanza continues: stanza 77, beginning “Rymr uar i ranni,”¹¹³³ is an evidence stanza introduced with “sem her segir,” and the following two stanzas are speech stanzas issuing Hloðr’s demands to his brother Angantýr.¹¹³⁴ The reply by Angantýr is initially in prose, however, when his sentence is finished, the narrator adds “þa quad Agantyr,” and he continues speaking in verse. This is a marked shift between prose and poetry. Angantýr continues in R in prose with an offer, but then R breaks off.

In U, the whole prosimetric episode is preserved.¹¹³⁵ The major difference is the lack of alternation between the speech and evidence stanzas. Instead, the majority

¹¹³¹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 86, l. 29.

¹¹³² *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 97, ll. 1-8.

¹¹³³ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 87, ll. 14-19.

¹¹³⁴ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 87, ll. 26-33; p. 88, ll. 1-10.

¹¹³⁵ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, pp. 142-155.

of the stanzas presented in the prose are straightforward dialogue/speech stanzas, which are labelled by the prose as to who is speaking them. Notable features are that a four stanza long speech by Angantýr has its second stanza introduced with “Og enn quad A(nganntyr),”¹¹³⁶ further suggesting, in comparison to other *fornaldarsögur*, that this is an important feature of giving many consecutive stanza of eddic verse.¹¹³⁷

Stanza 93 of U is not given as verse by all editors, although it is in Jón Helgason’s edition: “Obrodurlega varstu leikinn / hin agiæta systir” [‘Unbrotherly you have been treated, noble sister’].¹¹³⁸ The couplet is introduced in such a manner as to convey Angantýr’s deliberation over his words: he “varð seint til orða og mællti þetta vmm sidar” [‘he was slow to speak and at last said this’].¹¹³⁹ The prose following the couplet also reflects that Angantýr is thinking deeply, and we might be more inclined to accept the lines as verse in a moment of high emotional intensity. Likewise, two lines marked as verse by Jón Helgason are spoken by King Humli “Eigi skulum / arum spilla” [‘we must not harm heralds’], which is followed in prose by “þeim er fara einir samann” [‘those who travel alone’].¹¹⁴⁰ This, and the following stanza are,¹¹⁴¹ according to Christopher Tolkien, the confused remnants of verses,¹¹⁴² and both sets of lines are unusual in that they are directly either begun or ended with prose that finishes the thought.

Given the structure of Hloðskviða just described, it seems that it is a strong contender for traditional *Begleitprosa*, particularly since in the configuration in which the stanzas are usually used as evidence stanzas and the configuration in which they

¹¹³⁶ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 144, l. 16.

¹¹³⁷ The same happens at *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 149, l. 22; p. 152, l. 17; p. 155, l. 19.

¹¹³⁸ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 150, ll. 16-17.

¹¹³⁹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 150, ll. 14-15.

¹¹⁴⁰ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 153, l. 11.

¹¹⁴¹ *Heiðreks saga*, ed. Jón Helgason, p. 153, ll. 21-24 – p. 154, ll. 1-4.

¹¹⁴² *Saga Heiðreks konungs: The Saga of King Heiðrek the Wise*, ed. Christopher Tolkien, Icelandic Texts (London: Nelson, 1960) 56.

are used as speech stanzas needs the verses to add information to the prose narrative. Nevertheless, any prose that moved with the stanzas is likely to have been fluid, whether the stanzas were used as evidence or speech stanzas.

Hervarar saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

The opening prosimetric section of Hjalmar's death song is shown by the variations between redactions to be flexible as to whether stanzas are used as speech or as evidence stanzas. This flexibility in the use of verse in both of these roles is an important point, and it might be that in the eddic tradition, verses switched roles more readily than in the skaldic traditions, since eddic verse is used more frequently for speech stanzas. This readiness to employ a verse in either role also supports my identification of stanzas throughout various *fornaldarsögur* as quasi-authenticating and quasi-speech stanzas – that is, they could play both roles simultaneously. This serves to bring an engaging voice to the narrative, whilst at the same time underlining its credibility, such as the stanzas spoken by Starkaðr in *Gautreks saga*. The willingness to tease verses into both evidence and speech roles could perhaps have arisen from an oral eddic tradition in which this flexibility was felt to be perfectly acceptable. It is noticeable that no instances of this were found in the many stanzas of *Fagrskinna*, suggesting that this feature may be unique to eddic prose contexts.

In *Hervararkviða*, it seems likely that the verses serve to underline that emotions are running high, as well as providing the medium in which this episode has likely always been transmitted. Although part of the Samséy episode with Hjalmar's death song, the tones of the two pieces are not similar and different origins seem likely. Again, at the point at which Hervor is encountering her dead father, one redaction (H) shows a preference for giving the stanzas as evidence stanzas rather than as dialogue. This underlines what I argued above about the flexibility of eddic verse in prosimetric construction – it was probably up to the saga author or performer to concoct whichever permutation suited his particular mode of telling. The use of evidence stanzas rather than speech stanzas might indicate the author sought to introduce extra

credibility into his narrative in the manner observed in the *konungasögur*, and may also reflect the desire of an author/performer to display a variety of uses of verse in his narrative for the sake of interest.

Similar impulses may be detected in the difference between the H and U redactions in using narrative verse: in H, the verse has narrative properties; in U these are transferred into speech. This might also highlight the perceived distinction of using prose for narrative and verse for dialogue in the saga prose.

From the riddle exchange in *Hervararsaga* we might conclude an important role for prosimetrum in the transmission of such word games. As noted, the riddle is always in verse but the answer is always in prose: this lends a lot of flexibility to the creation of a prose answer. This is likely a hangover from an oral tradition in which there was a genuine performance situation involving the transmission of riddles where they were recited in verse for ease of memorisation, and the answers suggested in prose by the audience. The neat delineation of one riddle after another in the saga is a feature we can also observe in *mannjafnaðr* and in *Gylfaginning*, where the taking in turns of insults or questions and answers is orderly. This is presumably a written convention, since oral displays of riddle-prowess would likely have been rowdier as people shouted suggestions for the solution.

In *Hlǫðskviða*, several examples can be found of evidence verses actually supplying information to the narrative. This might suggest that the evidence stanza was partially seen as a convention that had to be included in order to formulate a credible narrative, likely under the influence of the *konungasögur*, but one that was flexible enough in a prose context of eddic verse to be exploited for narrative purposes at the same time. The opening of *Hlǫðskviða* in R also demonstrates the ability of prosimetrum to make the narrative suddenly much livelier and engaging than previously, as the pace picks up. In the written tradition then, the placement of prosimetra in long saga texts may have been carefully considered for the benefit of reader engagement (I assume here, perhaps wrongly, that the prose sections of oral sagas would have been shorter, albeit still present). The placement of two poetic

sections at either end of *Hervarar saga* may thus be an attempt to provide a strong opening and ending for the saga, with copious prose in the middle.

Hrólfs saga kraka ok kappá hans

Although the saga is usually dated to the 14th century,¹¹⁴³ the earliest surviving manuscript of *Hrólfs saga kraka* is from the 17th century. The manuscripts that are extant are all thought to go back to one common original.¹¹⁴⁴ Despite the late date of the extant saga, the materials contained in the saga are thought to be ancient and go back to oral times; this is particularly true with relation to the material found in the saga that is thought to be related to the *Bjarkamál*.¹¹⁴⁵

There are eleven stanzas in the saga in seven episodes:

1. Signý recognises her brothers (stanza 1)
2. Heiðr prophecies to King Fróði (stanza 2-5)
3. Reginn warns King Fróði (stanza 6)
4. Elk-Fróði greets his brother (stanzas 7-8)
5. King Aðil describes Svipdagr (stanza 9)
6. A couplet is said (stanza 10)
7. A proverb is said (stanza 11)

Episode one: Signý recognises her brothers (stanza 1)

The first stanza is a story-stanza that is crucial to the scene. Signý recognises her disguised brothers (called Hróarr and Helgi, with the assumed names Hrani and Hamr respectively), and begins to cry; the stanza is a response to her husband asking her why she is crying. The stanza, which begins “Qll er orðin / ætt Skjöldunga,”¹¹⁴⁶ is

¹¹⁴³ *The Saga of King Hrolf Kraki*, trans. Jesse Byock (London: Penguin, 1998) vii.

¹¹⁴⁴ The manuscripts have been extensively studied by Desmond Slay: see *The Manuscripts of Hrólfs saga kraka*, *Bibliotheca Arnarnagæana XXIV* (1960); “Hitherto Unused Manuscripts of Hrólfs saga kraka,” *Opuscula IV* (1970): 260-268; “More manuscripts of Hrólfs saga kraka” *Speculum Norroenvm. Norse Studies in Memory of Gabriel Turville-Petre*, ed. Ursula Dronke et al. (Odense, 1981) pp. 432-439; “Perhaps the last Hrólfs saga kraka manuscript,” *Strengleikar slegnir Robert Cook 25. nóvember 1994*, ed. Margrét Eggertsdóttir et al. (Reykjavík, 1994) pp. 59-61. For a summary of the major manuscripts, see *Hrólfs saga kraka og Bjarkarímur*, ed. Finnur Jónsson, *Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur 32* (København: S. L. Møller, 1904) pp. i-v.

¹¹⁴⁵ *The Saga of King Hrolf Kraka*, trans. Byock pp. xiii-xiv.

¹¹⁴⁶ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 10, ll. 11-12.

used in the prose by Signý to tell her husband Jarl Sævill that the two boys on bare-backed horses are her brothers (“bræðr sák mina / á berum sitja”);¹¹⁴⁷ this detail is not in the prose, which states rather that the horse Helgi rides is “ótamit” [‘untamed’] and that his brother Hrani’s (Hróarr’s) horse was similar.¹¹⁴⁸ The brothers are contrasted in the stanza to Sævill’s men who ride “á sǫðluðum” [‘with saddles’].¹¹⁴⁹ In the prose the stanza is addressed to Sævill, but the stanza itself talks of him in the third person (“en Sævils rekka”).¹¹⁵⁰ This could suggest an origin for the stanza outside this conversation; it could be spoken as part of an interior monologue by Signý as she watches the scene unfold.

Episode two: Heiðr prophecies to King Fróði (stanza 2-5)

The *vǫlva* Heiðr speaks four stanzas spoken to King Fróði when he is attempting to use her powers to divine what she can about the location of the boys Helgi and Hróarr, who, unbeknownst to him, are in the same hall. The first stanza is introduced as a prophecy stanza: “Seiðkonan slær þá í sundr kjǫptunum ok geispar mjök, ok varð henni þá ljóð á munni.”¹¹⁵¹ The gasping *vǫlva* and the phrase “varð henni þá ljóð á munni” are typical of such scenes. The stanza describes the situation as she sees it:

Tveir ro inni,
trúik hvárigum,
þeirs við elda
ítrir sitja.¹¹⁵²

Two are inside, I trust neither, they the excellent ones who sit by the fire.

¹¹⁴⁷ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 10, ll. 15-16.

¹¹⁴⁸ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 10, ll. 1-4.

¹¹⁴⁹ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 10, l. 18.

¹¹⁵⁰ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 10, l. 17. Note “Sævils” is the manuscript reading; Finnur Jónsson amends this to “Sevils.”

¹¹⁵¹ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 11, ll. 17-19.

¹¹⁵² *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 11, ll. 20-23.

The stanza does not make it clear who the “two” are she refers to, and the king asks her who they are, which prompts her to continue. The second stanza in the episode is thus introduced with “hún svarar”¹¹⁵³ as a direct reply to the question in the prose. The stanza, which begins “Þeir í Vífilsey / váru lengi”¹¹⁵⁴ is in the past tense, and reveals the names the boys went under on Vífilsey, Hoppur and Hó, “hunda nofnum.”¹¹⁵⁵ It is noticeable that in the three final stanzas of the episodes all the cognomens of the boys who are hunted are revealed. These stanzas can thus be said to preserve the outline of this section of the story, and the second stanza makes it clear that when they have the names Hoppur and Hó, they must answer to dogs’ names and be on the island of Vífilsey, as happened earlier in the saga. According to the prose description of Signý trying to bribe Heiðr to stop and the vǫlva’s efforts to abort the *seiðr* session, the third stanza is introduced thus: “hún gapir mjök ok verðr erfiðr seiðrinn ok nú kvað hún vísu.”¹¹⁵⁶ This stanza brings the action into the present tense of the saga:

Sék hvar sitja
synir Hálfðanar,
Hróarr ok Helgi,
heilir báðir;
þeir munu Fróða
fjörvi ræna,¹¹⁵⁷

The boys’ real names are cited in this stanza, along with the prophecy that they will kill Fróði (which does happen). The fact that she is able to see them brings dramatic force to the saga scene, and at the end of the stanza she breaks off into prose: “nema þeim sé fljótt fyrirfarit, en þat mun eigi verða.”¹¹⁵⁸ The spell evidently broken, “stiklar hún ofan af seiðhjallinum”¹¹⁵⁹ and recites the final stanza (beginning “Ötul eru augu”),¹¹⁶⁰

¹¹⁵³ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 12, l. 2.

¹¹⁵⁴ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 12, ll. 3-4.

¹¹⁵⁵ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 12, ll. 5-7.

¹¹⁵⁶ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 12, ll. 24-26.

¹¹⁵⁷ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 12, ll. 27-28 – p. 13, ll. 1-4.

¹¹⁵⁸ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 13, l. 5.

¹¹⁵⁹ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 13, ll. 6-7.

¹¹⁶⁰ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 13, l. 8.

revealing the last set of cognomens, Hamr and Hrani, that the boys have lived under. The stanzas that thus, again, crucial to the scene, even though they are staged as prophecies they give information on the dramatic unfolding of the episode and corroborate things that have happened previously in the saga prose as well as predicting what will happen in the future. The final stanza is not part of the prophecy but an observation on the “*oðlingar*” [‘princes’],¹¹⁶¹ acknowledging their noble character and also, in the plot, buying time for the boys to realise she is warning them – all three of them then escape.

It is difficult to assess whether the stanzas are possibly primary to the prose here; at least they are certainly integral. The recitation of the stanzas in this section is thus crucial not only for aesthetic interest (for example, a *seiðr* session), but also for reasons of corroboration with what happened earlier (the second stanza corroborates what happened when the boys stayed with Vífill) and for the dramatic timing of the scene, in which the time it takes to speak a stanza is vital – this is rather unusual in the *fornaldarsögur* and is here used with great effect, since it highlights the alarm the boys feel when their identities are uncovered.

Episode three: Reginn warns King Fróði (stanza 6)

The sixth stanza in the saga is spoken by Reginn to King Fróði as a warning, even though Reginn is party to the actions that will lead to Fróði’s death, he must issue a warning about what is happening in order to fulfill his oaths to him: “ok í þessu heyra þeir utar til hallardyra, at Reginn kvað vísu.”¹¹⁶² The stanza is thus introduced as an occasional/speech stanza. It is full of double meanings. The first half of the stanza introduces the situation and the second half is the warning. The first line “Reginn er úti”¹¹⁶³ could mean either the man Reginn is speaking (thus recording the speaker of

¹¹⁶¹ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 13, l. 10.

¹¹⁶² *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 15, ll. 17-18.

¹¹⁶³ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 15, l. 19.

the stanza) or that it is raining outside, and, since ‘reginn’ is the plural of ‘god,’ also indicates the gods may be involved.¹¹⁶⁴ The second to fourth lines, “ok rekkr Hálfðanar, / snæfir andskotar, / segið þat Fróða,” record who the stanza is addressing (Fróði) and who he is about to face. The second half plays on the smiths’ names Varr, ‘varr’ meaning ‘cautious,’ a warning to be careful veiled in a message about smiths making nails.¹¹⁶⁵ The king’s men understand it the stanza in the more innocent manner, but the king is able to interpret that Reginn is giving a warning;¹¹⁶⁶ even though this is the case, the stanza is not particularly important to the action and the short episode serves only to preserve Reginn’s good character and also probably to give the reader an opportunity to delight in the double meanings of the stanza.

Episode four: Elg-Fróði greets his brother Þórir hundsfótr (stanzas 7-8)

The two stanzas that occur in the episode in which Elg-Fróði encounters and threatens his brother Þórir hundsfótr without recognising him are curious, threatening short strophes. In each stanza a brother states what type of weapon he has and that he will use it:

Litlu síðarr kemr Fróði heim ok lítr ekki hýrliga til hins komna manns, bregðr nú skálminni ok mælti:
 Grenjar skálm,
 gengr ór slíðrum,
 minniz hønd
 hildar verka,
 ok keyrir niðr a stokkinn hjá sér ok geriz mjök ólmr ok illiligr. Þórir kvað þá:
 En ek læt víðs
 á vegi oðrum
 øxi mína
 jafnt hljóð bera.
 Ok þá duldiz Þórir ekki lengr, ok kendi þá Fróði broður sinn...¹¹⁶⁷

¹¹⁶⁴ *The Saga of King Hrolf Kraka*, trans. Byock p. 9.

¹¹⁶⁵ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 15, ll. 23-26.

¹¹⁶⁶ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 16, ll. 1-8.

¹¹⁶⁷ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 56, ll. 12-26.

Fróði is aggressive to his brother in his stanza because he does not recognise him, but his brother is also aggressive back, even though he knows who Fróði is and that he is concealing his identity from him. The aggressive action of Fróði drawing his short sword in the prose align with the first stanza, and although in prose the stanza is said after the sword is drawn, the content of the stanza suggests it may have been supposed that sword was drawn and the stanza spoken simultaneously. The stanzas are not crucial for telling the story of the episode, but rather function to highlight the aggression of the characters and also serve as a dialogue greeting, however unfriendly, between the two men. The contents of the stanzas are simple promises of violence. It should be noted that it in the prose it is not the recitation of the stanza that causes Fróði to recognise his brother Þórir, nor does the content of the stanzas indicate this is one of their intended functions.

Episode five: King Aðil describes Svipdagr (stanza 9)

The ninth stanza is spoken in a tight performance context in which it is obviously said loudly in a public setting. The content is designed to embarrass Svipdagr:

Þá tók Aðils konungr til orða: ‘ok þú ert nú kominn hér Svipdagr félagi, eða hvert mun erindit kappans?, eða mun ekki vera sem mér sýniz,
dalr er í hnakka,
auga er ór hofði,
orr er i enni,
hogg eru á hendi tvau,
ok svá er Beigaðr bróðir hans allr knýttr.’¹¹⁶⁸

It seems that the king’s reference to Svipdagr as the ‘champion’ (“hvert mun erindit kappans?”)¹¹⁶⁹ is an ironic one, since the verse sounds like it describes a warrior who has been beaten rather than taken victory. Although part of an apparent attempt at public humiliation, the stanza aligns Svipdagr with Óðinn. The stanza is not personalised in content to Svipdagr (it does not mention his name), nor does the

¹¹⁶⁸ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 80, ll. 3-10.

¹¹⁶⁹ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 80, ll. 4-5.

stanza suggest internally who the speaker might be. The verse is part of direct speech and has a very particular performance context in the prose; this is emphasised by most of the description being in verse and then the king switching to prose to finish his comments on Svipdagr and Beigaðr. The reaction of Svipdagr, that he spoke “svá hátt, at allir máttu heyra,”¹¹⁷⁰ confirms that this exchange of which the stanza is part is loaded with social significance, and serves in the narrative to heighten the tension in the scene, as Svipdagr and his companions are about to be attacked. The detailed description of Svipdagr’s appearance helps the reader/audience to imagine the scene, and this continues after the stanza with a detailed inscription of the interior of a hall.

Episodes six and seven: A couplet and proverb are said (stanzas 10-11)

The last two verse elements of *Hrólfs saga* are of dubious standing in terms of whether they should be considered as part of the saga’s prosimetric structure. In the first instance, a couplet occurs: “Aukum nú eldana / at Aðils borg” [‘Let us now increase the fires at Aðils stronghold’].¹¹⁷¹ Although metrical enough to be considered *fornyrðislag*, the introduction of the stanza indicates it might have been considered alliterative prose by the saga writer: “Þá mæltu þeir Bøðvarr ok Svipdagr.”¹¹⁷² It is difficult to see how an occasional stanza could be conceived of as being spoken simultaneously by two men. Considering the couplet as something said at the same time by close acquaintances seems to make more sense. As for the second instance, we find: “Eigi flýr sá eldinn, / sem yfir hleypr” [‘that one flees no fire, [he] who jumps over it’].¹¹⁷³ Prosaic proverbial material is the most likely candidate, although this proverb too is metrical enough to be verse (it is in *fornyrðislag*), even if only two lines long. It is introduced by “Eptir þetta unnit teka Hrólfr konungr til orða” [‘after this

¹¹⁷⁰ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 80, l. 11.

¹¹⁷¹ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 83, ll. 13-14.

¹¹⁷² *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 83, l. 12.

¹¹⁷³ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 84, ll. 1-2.

occurred, King Hrólfr began to speak’].¹¹⁷⁴ The introduction does not indicate one way or another whether the lines that followed could be verse. The content of the first couplet about Aðil’s stronghold seems integrated enough with the surrounding saga that it was probably written for the purpose, but the second sounds to be of common proverbial (oral) origin. Such alliterative, short statements could be taken as prose – there is nothing in the prose surrounding them that indicates they are verse – but they are usually considered verse.

Hrólfs saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

The stanzas in *Hrólfs saga* seem to be concerned with the theme of identity: recognising, concealing and revealing it. Nevertheless, the saga has a rather unique prosimetric profile in the corpus of legendary sagas. Rather than building the narrative from versified dialogue, monologues or otherwise long sections of stanzas (e.g. the evidence stanzas of *Hlǫðskviða*), the saga instead has very few stanzas that are found scattered throughout it. They appear singularly on the whole. The only two units emerge from the analysis are the second episode in which Heiðr prophecies to King Fróði (stanzas 2-5) and the fourth, in which Elk-Fróði greets his father (stanzas 7-8). The contents of both of these units occur elsewhere, for example the prophesying in verse at the beginning of *Qrvar-Odds saga*, and eddic dialogue in which demand for identification is made and the name and origin of the opponent versified;¹¹⁷⁵ often such situations descend into threats, which is reflected in the Elk-Fróði episode in *Hrólfs saga*. The saga then is not built as a traditional *fornaldarsaga* but nevertheless can be said to employ verses in its episodes that contain traditional and old content.

¹¹⁷⁴ *Hrólfs saga kraka*, ed. Finnur Jónsson p. 83, ll. 24-25.

¹¹⁷⁵ Cf. Harris, “Eddic Poetry as Oral Poetry: The Evidence of Parallel Passages in the Helgi Poems for Questions of Composition and Performance,” pp. 203-204.

Ásmundar saga kappabana

The saga survives in two later medieval manuscripts: one is Perg. 4to nr 7 in the kungliga biblioteket in Stockholm, and the other is AM 586 4to. The full saga is preserved only in Stockholm Perg. 4to nr 7 from the first half of the 14th century,¹¹⁷⁶ since the saga in AM 586 4to is only a fragment, occupying 33r-33v. This manuscript is dated to the 15th century,¹¹⁷⁷ but the style of the fragment is rather different to that of the saga preserved in the Stockholm manuscript, and has been described by E. F. Halvorsen as being “verbose.”¹¹⁷⁸ The saga is dated by E. F. Halvorsen to around end of the 13th century.¹¹⁷⁹

Previous criticism of the saga has been largely concerned with the origins of the saga in connection with the *Hildebrandslied*¹¹⁸⁰ and with the similar material told by Saxo,¹¹⁸¹ but, as Halvorsen rightly points out, “it is of the greatest importance to distinguish between the written saga, which can hardly be older than the end of the 13th century, and the Hildebrand legend, which was known to Saxo Grammaticus a

¹¹⁷⁶ E. F. Halvorsen, “On the Sources of the Ásmundarsaga Kappabana,” *Studia Norvegica* 5 (1951): 1-57, at 4.

¹¹⁷⁷ Handrit.is dates the manuscript between 1450 and 1499, while Halvorsen dates the manuscript as from about 1400 in “On the Sources” 4. Kålund commits only to the 15th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 747.

¹¹⁷⁸ Halvorsen, “On the Sources” 4.

¹¹⁷⁹ Alison Finlay concurs with the late 13th century, “The Saga of Ásmundr, Killer of Champions,” trans. Alison Finlay, *Making History: Essays on the Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Martin Arnold and Alison Finlay (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 2010) pp. 119-139, at 119.

¹¹⁸⁰ A literary reading of the dynamic and verbal exchanges between Hildebrand and Hadubrand in the German poem is provided by Albrecht Classen, “Why Do Their Words Fail? Communicative Strategies in the “Hildebrandslied,”” *Modern Philology* 93 (1995): 1-22.

¹¹⁸¹ See Siegfried Gutenbrunner, *Von Hildebrand und Hadubrand: Lied- Sage-Mythos*, Germanische Bibliothek 3 (Heidelberg: C. Winter, 1976) pp. 132-138 and pp. 187-192, which provide a graphical reconstruction of the literary history of this tale. Older scholarship on the connection of the saga with the German poem is neatly summarised by Halvorsen, “On the Sources” 4-5. The stanzas in the saga have been compared with the material found in Saxo many times. See for example: *Zwei Fornaldarsögur (Hrólfs saga Gautrekssonar und Ásmundar kappabana) nach Cod. Holm. 7 4to*, ed. Ferdinand Dettler (Halle: Max Niemeyer, 1891) 101-103; Alison Finlay, “The Saga of Ásmundr” 120-122; the comparison has been made in most detail by Halvorsen, “On the Sources” 8-22.

century earlier,¹¹⁸² and the present discussion will focus on the saga as an Old Norse prosimetrum.¹¹⁸³

The saga contains nine stanzas split into two poems, only found in the Stockholm manuscript and all of which are part of recounting the death of Hildibrandr in elagic eddic verse. The first five stanzas are spoken by Hildibrandr after he is badly wounded (“en hann var þá sárr mörgum sárum” ‘and he was then wounded with many wounds’)¹¹⁸⁴ and are introduced by the words “Síðan kvað hann vísur þessar” [‘Afterwards he spoke these verses’].¹¹⁸⁵ This kind of prose introductory statement is ambiguous as to whether it is introducing direct speech or a quotation that is meant to have the ring of the traditional to it. The second poem is four stanzas long and is spoken by Ásmundr as he enters a hall door, when he recounts his heroic fighting. The stanzas are introduced with “Ásmundr kvað, er hann kom í hallardyrrnar” [‘Ásmundr said, when he came to the hall’s doorway’],¹¹⁸⁶ and the stanzas are thus used as direct speech.

It has been concluded that for the most part the content of prose material of the saga originated from the stanzas.¹¹⁸⁷ Evidence of this may be seen in the way that the saga author makes some unlikely sounding expansions of the allusive lines he finds in the verse; Alison Finlay has noted this in the case of the prose sentence in which

¹¹⁸² Halvorsen, “On the Sources” 5. Otto L Jiriczek however concludes that the saga and the *Hildebrandslied* tell the same tale, in *Deutsche heldensagen* (Strassburg: Trübner, 1898) pp. 283-87. Hermann Schneider holds the Hildebrandr’s Death Song to be influenced by the Hildebrandslied in *Germanische Heldensage*, vol. 1, Grundriss der germanischen Philologie 10.1 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1928) pp. 320-321. Jan de Vries holds the Norse verses to have come from a Rhenish source in *Altnordische Literaturgeschichte*, vol. 2, Grundriss der germanischen Philologie 16 (Berlin: de Gruyter, 1967) pp. 481-483, and B. Symons considers the saga stanzaz to be derived directly from a German source in “Heldensage,” *Grundriss der germanischen Philologie*, ed. Hermann Paul, vol. 3 (Strassburg: Trübner, 1900) pp. 606-734, at p. 630.

¹¹⁸³ Fr. Kauffmann argues that is necessary to distinguish between the prose of the saga and the stanzas, and that “Was die prosa der isländischen saga bringt, ist völlig wertlos,” in “Das Hildebrandslied,” *Philologische Studien: Festgabe für Eduard Sievers zum 1. Oktober 1896* (Halle a. s., 1896) pp. 124-178, at p. 166 (see also p. 165, where he states the stanzas are certainly older than the prose).

¹¹⁸⁴ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 98.28-29.

¹¹⁸⁵ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 98.29.

¹¹⁸⁶ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 99.21.

¹¹⁸⁷ “The Saga of Ásmundr,” trans. Finlay 119. Halvorsen summarises previous scholarship on this matter, see pp. 4-6.

Hildibrandr suddenly kills his own son after going into a berserk rage, since the son had never before been mentioned in the prose.¹¹⁸⁸ The killing takes place directly before Hildibrandr himself is killed;¹¹⁸⁹ the prose author seems not to have known what to do with the reference in the third stanza¹¹⁹⁰ to Hildibrandr's dead son (who, it is clear, Hildibrandr killed himself), and the statement was perhaps inserted simply to have the killing take place at some point. This supports Halvorsen's argument that the author's knowledge of the Hildibrandr material comes solely from the verses as given in the saga,¹¹⁹¹ although there are clearly echoes throughout of other *fornaldarsögur*. Halvorsen suggests that the verses may have originated in a collection not dissimilar to the *Poetic Edda*, and that the stanzas may have been accompanied by some kind of *Begleitprosa*.¹¹⁹² In this case, the prose saga represents an expansion of written stanzas and possibly written prose. The suggestion of accompanying prose is impossible to prove, but it does seem that the author having drawn these stanzas from a written context is more likely than their being known to the saga author from oral tradition, since in that case it might be expected that the author would know a more fluent, if more fluid, story to go with the stanzas. This does not seem to be the case in the saga as extant, given the saga's apparent stretching of material only found in the stanzas. The following explores how the author has built his saga from the stanzas.

Stanza one resolves the dramatic irony in the saga, as it is clearly announced that Hildibrandr and Ásmundr are brothers without either of them having previously acknowledged it, although the audience has all the details of how this has happened. It

¹¹⁸⁸ "The Saga of Ásmundr," trans. Finlay 120.

¹¹⁸⁹ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 98.19-20.

¹¹⁹⁰ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 99.8-10.

¹¹⁹¹ "The Icelander who originally wrote down these stanzas naturally knew the tale of which they formed a part, and this oral saga was probably the ultimate source of Saxo's version. Then, many years later, the author of our Asms. found them, and tried to make a coherent saga out of the hints in the *vísur*." Halvorsen p. 52.

¹¹⁹² "One cannot quite exclude the possibility that the original collector wrote a short introduction and some lines to connect the two poems." This original collector, Halvorsen reckons, would have got the poem from oral tradition. Halvorsen p. 52 and see also p. 10. The concept of *Begleitprosa* has been an important one in the discussion of Norse prosimetra, to describe prose that accompanies a verse, see S. Beyschlag, "Möglichkeiten mündlicher überlieferung in der Königssaga," *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 68 (1953): 109-139, esp. p. 113.

is stated that “Ásmundr vissi eigi frændsemi milli þeirra Hildibrandz, þvíat móðir hans sagði honum ecki frá,”¹¹⁹³ something prompted by the fact that the first stanza explains how they are brothers and where each was born. It would hardly make sense for Hildibrandr to announce this if Ásmundr knew it. The prose constructs the scenario that Hildibrandr is elder and born in Sweden (ch. 2), and Ásmundr born later in Denmark (ch. 3) to reflect the second half of the verse: “þik Drótt of bar af Danmörku, / en mik sjálfan á Svíþjóðu.”¹¹⁹⁴ Although the prose hints that Hildibrandr might guess their relationship when their swords are revealed as very similar,¹¹⁹⁵ this is not entirely clear from the poem. Hildibrandr in stanza one seems unaware Ásmundr was set to kill him while in the second stanza he recognises the common origin of their weapons.

The second stanza has prompted the story of the dwarves forging swords for King Buðli and one sword being cursed. That Buðli left two incomparable swords forged by dwarves is expanded into the section on the cursing of one sword, its deposit in the sea, Ásmundr retrieving it and Vöggr’s comment on how alike the swords are. No mention is made of a curse in the poem, nor was that one sword buried at sea, as is told in the prose.

The third stanza, a description of Hildibrandr’s tally-marked shield, is simply translated into one sentence in the prose: “Þann skjöld hafði hann, er á vóru markaðir menn svá margir, sem hann hafði drepit,”¹¹⁹⁶ although the prose author does use this public death tally as a device with which to inflame Ásmundr’s resolve to fight Hildibrandr. As already discussed, the author likely faced a problem with stanza four when he did not know anything about Hildibrandr’s dead son, and he is forced to have

¹¹⁹³ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 85.26-28.

¹¹⁹⁴ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 98.32-33.

¹¹⁹⁵ “Vöggr segir: hans yfirbragð er með því, at hann er látaðr vel ok allíkr yðr í augum ok sýndiz mér líkligr til, at vera muni ofrhugi, ok þat sverð hefir hann, er ek sá ecki jafnlíkt því, sem þú hefir, ok þat hygg ek, at or einum afli sé borit. Hildibrandr mælti: mikit finnz þér um þenna mann; ætlar þú eigi, at mitt sverð muni vera jafnt hans sverði eða hann muni mínnt eða hann muni mínnt jafningi?” *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter p.94.32-33.

¹¹⁹⁶ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 98.21-22.

Hildibrandr suddenly kill him in order to fulfil in prose the information in the stanza, and as a result this part of the prose is not very smooth.

Stanza five did not provide the author with any content material to use earlier in the saga, since it is Hildibrandr's instruction for his funeral. Hildibrandr's repetition that Ásmundr is his brother connects this stanza with previous ones, as they both emphasise family connections. Reminding Ásmundr of their relationship also makes it seem more likely that Ásmundr will heed Hildibrandr's plea for an honourable funeral. Ásmundr does not acknowledge Hildibrandr as his brother in either the prose or stanzas, even once it has been revealed to him, a curious decision by the saga author since the bulk of the saga up to the death song is replete comments on the likeness between them: Ásmundr never comments on their truth, and it only says in the prose that Ásmundr "hugði þá illa sínu verki" after he has killed Ásmundr.¹¹⁹⁷ After the death of Hildibrandr, the saga author may be trying to establish Ásmundr as a champion in his own right, and thus his brotherhood with Hildibrandr is somewhat irrelevant. That Ásmundr killed his own brother is not expanded on except in concluding Ásmundr's battle prowess in stanza nine, where Hildibrandr's name but not his relation to Ásmundr is given. The concern to build up Ásmundr as a hero is the reason why their kinship is not acknowledged on Ásmundr's side.

There are several features in these five stanzas that may be observed in death songs in the *fornaldarsögur*. Hildibrandr's last words before he dies, reported in stanza five, are such an utterance typical of the death song: "Nú verð ek liggja lífs andvana, / marki undaðr, þannz magna sár."¹¹⁹⁸ This affirmation from the hero that he is fatally wounded and about to die is also in Hjálmar's death song and in Ragnarr's death song, for example. The funeral directions in stanza four are also usual; as is the comment in stanza three about an heir (both Hildibrandr and Hjálmar lament their lack of heir). These shared motifs clearly show the poem's alignment with the

¹¹⁹⁷ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 99.18.

¹¹⁹⁸ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 99.15-16.

traditional death song genre, which is likely to have existed also in oral times, but do on occasion cause the prose author some problems when he tries to convert them into a likely sounding story scenario.

The second poem is narrated by Ásmundr, and provides the material for the prose author to construct Ásmundr's battle scenes against increasing numbers of warriors. His first stanza, the sixth of the saga, is an introduction to his fights:

Litt varði mik laga þeirra
at mik mannz einskis ófyrir kvæði,
þá er mik til kappu kuru Húnmegir
atta sinnum fyrir jöfurs ríki.¹¹⁹⁹

This explained in the prose by a duke, when Ásmundr hears he is to face eleven men, offering that the dukes will accompany him to fight and thus implying that he will not win if he attempts the deed alone. The hesitation that Ásmundr admits to in stanza eight is woven in here as “er Ásmundr spyrr þetta, þá þagnaði hann,” so the duke in fact rather accurately reads his mood. Stanza seven enumerates that Ásmundr fought one, two, five, four, six, seven and then eight men, and the prose author logically straightens out the order (four men are fought before five). That the prose author follows these numbers exactly rather than inserting Ásmundr fighting against three men is taken by Alison Finlay as another sign of the prose author's reliance on the verses for his material.¹²⁰⁰ The eighth stanza, beginning “Þá hvarflaði hugr í brjósti,” is expanded in prose in chapter seven, the “dísir” who appear to Ásmundr in his sleep in the stanza are the “spádísir” in the prose, and the report of what they spoke in the stanza (“...sogðu dísir, / at ek hjörleik þann heyja skyldak”)¹²⁰¹ is expanded into a report of their actual words in the saga prose: “hvat veit óttabragð þitt? þú ert ætlaðr, at vera forgangsmáðr annarra, en þú óttaz ellifu menn; vér erum spádísir þínar ok skulum vér vörn veita þér móti mönnum, er atberjaz við hertugana, en þá er þú hefir at

¹¹⁹⁹ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 99.22-25.

¹²⁰⁰ “The Saga of Ásmundr,” trans. Finlay 134 fn. 4.

¹²⁰¹ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 99.32-33.

reyna við þik.”¹²⁰² Although the manuscript is difficult to read at this point, Detter’s educated guess at the Old Norse prose likely indicates that in the prose the *dísir* do not so much tell him to fight as merely tell Ásmundr that they are there to protect him. This is enough to spur him on.

The ninth and final stanza in the saga, beginning “Þá kom inn hári Hildibrandr,”¹²⁰³ describes Ásmundr’s meeting with Hildibrandr in the first person and the wound that Ásmundr uses to beat Hildibrandr. The description of the infliction of the wound that kills Hildibrandr in the stanza, “ek markaða meðan á hónum, / herkumbl harðlig fyrir hjálm neðan” is not reported in the prose, which in fact does not portray Ásmundr giving Hildibrandr his death-wound in such a manner, only that “en hann var þá sárr mörgum sárum.”¹²⁰⁴ Rather, in the prose Hildibrandr attempts to wound Ásmundr in a rather similar manner: “þá neytti Hildibrandr afls ok hjó til Ásmundar af öllu afli tveim höndum, ok í því er sverðit kom í hjálminn, þá brast þat sundr undir hjáltinu ok för brandrinn grenjandi niðr í ána.”¹²⁰⁵ It could be the prose writer has mixed, deliberately or otherwise, the blow described in the ninth stanza, attributing it to Hildibrandr in the prose and Ásmundr in the stanza. In the verse, no mention is made of Hildibrandr’s sword failing and that being the cause for his death, Ásmundr simply kills him.

The performance context of Ásmundr’s poem is such that the poem is necessary to determine reception his will receive: “Eptir þat fögnuðu men hónum vel”¹²⁰⁶ and indicates that as he stood in the hall door reciting his poem, as the prose before the poem indicates,¹²⁰⁷ his audience paid attention to him. The poem also earns

¹²⁰² *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 97.31-35. Note that Detter had difficulty with the manuscript being blurred and indistinct with the reading of “vér vörn” to “við þik.”

¹²⁰³ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 100.1-4.

¹²⁰⁴ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 98.28-29.

¹²⁰⁵ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 98.25-28.

¹²⁰⁶ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 100.5.

¹²⁰⁷ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 99.21.

Ásmundr a nickname in the prose, “kappabani.”¹²⁰⁸ The second poem spoken by Ásmundr is thus more securely placed in a dramatic context than the first. Hildibrandr’s death song is presumably overheard only by Ásmundr, who must be assumed in the saga to be responsible for reporting it afterwards, whereas for his own poem recounting his deeds, the prose allots him an audience.

Ásmundar saga kappabana is based on a traditional poem which, given the similarity of the material it contains to that found in Saxo, likely was once in oral tradition in some form. However, the stanzas and any traditions surrounding them were not in the oral milieu of the saga author, who must have encountered them in a written form and formed a saga out them, perhaps using, for example, the death song of Hjálmar and Qrvar-Oddr as inspiration; it is worth noting that Oddr’s death song, as Hildibrandr’s, is also at the end of the saga.

Ásmundar saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

Given the unusual origin of the saga as argued for above (the imaginative expansion of a few stanzas), it is doubtful how much the saga as a whole can tell us about the nature of eddic prosimetrum, although it certainly demonstrates that saga authors were free to elaborate on their eddic stanzas in prose as they saw fit, a feature we also find in *Gylfaginning*. It also shows us that information captured and transmitted in stanzas can be stretched to provide a large amount of prose material, although admittedly *Ásmundar saga* is an extreme case. It is notable that the stanzas are integrated in the saga as stanzas at the point of death and as retrospective stanzas, both well-testified uses of eddic verse in legendary sagas.

¹²⁰⁸ *Zwei Fornaldarsögur*, ed. Detter 100.6.

Kings' Sagas

Helga þátr Þórissonar

There is a single stanza in *Helga þátr Þórissonar*,¹²⁰⁹ preserved in *Flateyjarbók* GKS 1005 fol., Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum, from 1397-1394. It is a situational stanza spoken by Óláfr Tryggvason. It is characteristic of stanzas that function as dialogue in the *fornaldarsögur* to be rhymed replies to a question, but not so here: the king's stanza is very much a comment on the narrative happenings:

Konungr lætr fylla hornin Gríma af góðum drykk ok lætr byskup blessa ok lét færa þeim Grímunum, at þeir drykki fyrst af. Þá kvað konungr vísu þessa:

Gestir skulu hornum
í gegn taka,
meðan hvílast látum þenna
þegn Guðmundar,
ok af samnafna
sínnum drekki;
svá skal Grímunum
gott öl gefast.

Þá taka Grímar við hornunum ok þykkjast nú vita, hvat byskup hefir yfir lesit drykkinum. Þeir segja þá: "Eigi ferr nú fjarri því, sem Guðmundr, konungr várr, gat til. Er þessi konungr prettóttur ok kann illa gott at launa, því at konungr várr gerði til hans sæmiliga. Stöndum nú upp allir ok verðum í brottu heðan."¹²¹⁰

The king has the horns Grímr and Grímr filled with good drink, and has the bishop bless them and had them brought to the men Grímr and Grímr, so that they could drink first. Then the king said this verse: "Guests shall take the horns while they get to rest, Guðmundr's thanes, and drink from their namesakes, so shall the Grímrs be given good beer." Then the Grímrs took the horns and now it occurred to them what the bishop has read over the drinks. Then they say: "now it's not far from what Guðmundr, our king, supposed. This king is deceitful, and can reward good with evil when our king deserves his honourable treatment. Everyone stand up now and get away from here!"

The metre of the stanza is (eddic) *fornyrðislag*, as is normal in *fornaldarsögur*, although the *konungasögur*, where this stanza is preserved, usually contain skaldic verse. The stanza here reiterates the names of the characters in the *þátr*, making it clear that both the two guests and the two horns are each called Grímr, and reaffirming the

¹²⁰⁹ Quoted here from *Helga þátr Þórissonar, Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsson, vol. 3 (Reykjavík: Bókaútgáfan Forni, 1944) pp. 421-426.

¹²¹⁰ *Helga þátr Þórissonar*, ed. Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsson ch. 2, p. 424.

relationships between the characters.¹²¹¹ The eddic stanza is an occasional verse, and focuses purely on the characters and their beer drinking. The wider details of the immediate story – their anger at the blessing of the ale by the bishop, for example – are not found in the verse.

¹²¹¹ This episode is also mentioned in *Norna-Gests þáttr*, although no verse is cited: “Á því ári kómu ok til hans [Ólafr konungr] þeir men, er Grímar hétu ok váru sendir af Guðmundi af Glasisvöllum. Þeir færðu konungi horn tvau, er Guðmundr gaf honum. Þau kölluðu þeir ok Gríma. Þeir höfðu ok fleiri erendi til konungs, sem síðar mun sagt verða.” [‘In that year came also to him [king Ólafr], those men who were [both] called Grímr, and were sent by Guðmundr of Glasisvellir. They brought to the king two horns, which Guðmundr gave to him. They called [each of] them Grímr as well. They had also more business with the king, as will be said later.’] *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurðr Nordal, p. 385, chapter 282. The reference to the further dealings of the two Grímrs with the king is to the events in *Helga þáttr Þórissonar*, which comes directly after *Norna-Gests þáttr* in *Flateyjarbók*.

Sǫrla þáttr

Sǫrla þáttr is part of *Ólafs saga Tryggvasonar hin mesta* in *Flateyjarbók*, GKS 1005 fol., Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum, from 1397-1394. The *þáttr* is found on 36va-37va. The *þáttr* contains only one stanza, on 36vb42.

In *Sǫrla þáttr*, the role of the single *haðarlag*¹²¹² stanza is evidence based:

En Sörli lifði þeirra skemr ok fell í Austrvegi fyri víkingum, sem segir í Sörla stikka ok hér segir:

Fell enn forsnjalli
fyst inn víglysti
ýgr í Aurtrvegi
allr á helpalla;
dauðr um dalreyðar
dádögunnr miskunnar,
beit at brandmóti
brynstíngur víkingum.¹²¹³

But Sörli lived the shorter of them, and was killed out east by Vikings, as it says in *Sǫrlastikka* and says here: “The foresighted one fell, the one foremost in desire for battle, fierce in the east dead on the dais of Hel, the brave one dead during the summer, a sword bit at the battle against Vikings.”

A *stikka* is a type of short, measured poem,¹²¹⁴ but *Sǫrlastikka* does not survive otherwise, and it is not clear from its context in the *þáttr* whether this verse is indeed from *Sǫrlastikka*, as has been assumed, since its introductory formula is a little unusual: “sem segir í Sörlastikka ok hér segir” [‘as it says in *Sörlastikka* and says here’]. If the stanza were presented as a straightforward quotation from *Sǫrlastikka*, one might expect an introductory formula similar to this example from *Vǫlsunga saga*: “Sigurðr geck i brott. Sva segir í Sigurþarqvidu” [‘Sigurðr went away. Thus it says in *Sigurðarkviða*’],¹²¹⁵ and a quotation duly follows from *Sigurðarkviða*, a stanza from an otherwise unknown poem about Sigurðr. As it is, the introductory stanza in *Sǫrla þáttr* suggests that the *Sǫrlastikka* might be a different poem to the one quoted in the *þáttr*. The stanza quoted in *Sǫrla þáttr* thus may not be from *Sǫrlastikka*, but simply

¹²¹² *Haðarlag* is a simple metre somewhat in between eddic and skaldic measures; it has been described as *málháttur* with *dróttkvætt* rhymes (see Turville-Petre, *Scaldic Poetry* pp. xxxiv-xxxv). It is most well-known for its use in *Hrafnsmál*.

¹²¹³ *Sörla þáttr*, *Fornaldar sögur norðurlanda eptir gömlum handritum*, ed. C. C. Rafn, vol. 1 (Copenhagen, 1829) pp. 389-407, at 397.

¹²¹⁴ See “stikka,” *An Icelandic-English Dictionary* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1874) p. 592.

¹²¹⁵ *Vǫlsunga saga*, ed. Olsen, p. 77.

refer to similar material. The *Sörla þáttr* stanza could be from another unknown poem, or be contemporaneous with the saga prose.

Sörlastikka is mentioned elsewhere in the prose: “Síðan börðust þeir, sem segir í Sörla stikka.”¹²¹⁶ There follows a list of men killed and by whom in prose. This suggests that perhaps the *stikka* may have contained a catalogue-type stanza naming the men, and this is what is referred to in *Flateyjarbók*. The fact that the stanza is not given although the poem is named indicates again that the actual stanzas of the poem may not have been known to the author of the *þáttr*, even if he knew the story behind it.

¹²¹⁶ *Sörla þáttr*, ed. C. C. Rafn p. 397.

Norna-Gests þátr

All twenty-seven stanzas of *Norna-Gests þátr* are quotations from the two heroic eddic poems *Reginismál* and *Helreið Brynhildar*. Unlike *Gylfaginning* and *Völsunga saga*, *Norna-Gests þátr* never acknowledges that stanzas that are used as quotations from elsewhere, but simply integrates the stanzas as dialogue. Lars Lönnroth has argued that the verse functions to convey the characters' high emotions in contrast to the objectivity of the prose.¹²¹⁷ It seems that the prosimetrum as constructed in *Norna-Gests þátr* is a written prosimetrum, since the stanzas are quoted in exactly the same order as that in which they appear in the Codex Regius manuscript of the *Poetic Edda* collection. If these stanzas were to be drawn from oral tradition for their insertion into the *þátr*, it would be more likely that there would be some differences in stanza order and quotation method than can be observed in the *þátr*; for example, in the two versions of *Völuspá*, the same stanzas appear in a different order, and the differences between the contents of the stanzas from the two versions when they are compared seem indicative of differences caused by oral transmission.¹²¹⁸ The differences that are found between the stanzas as quoted in *Norna-Gests þátr* and the eddic poems extant in the *Codex Regius* suggest that the writer of the *þátr* had access to a manuscript very similar to but not identical with the Codex Regius.

The stanzas in the *þátr* occur in six episodes:

1. Reginn welcomes Sigurðr and his retainers. (2 stanzas)
2. Reginn encourages Sigurðr to kill Fáfnir. (1 stanza)
3. Sigurðr and his retainers encounter a man on a promontory. (3 stanzas)
4. The king receives Hnikkar's advice. (7 stanzas)
5. The death of Lyngvi. (1 stanza)
6. Brynhildr and a gýgr chant at one another. (13 stanzas)

The context of the performance of the stanzas is deeply in the story-telling mode, which, as the narrator of the story, Gestr controls. As he is telling the story, the input

¹²¹⁷ "Hjálmar's Death Song and the Delivery of Eddic Poetry," p. 198.

¹²¹⁸ Else Mundal, "Oral or Scribal Variation in *Völuspá*."

and questions of the audience spur the story on and remind the audience or reader of the *þáttr* that the context of the episodes in the *þáttr* is a story within a story.

In the first episode in the story, Reginn welcomes Sigurðr and his retainers and recites two stanzas, separated by “Ok enn kvað hann” in prose.¹²¹⁹ These stanzas are *Reginsmál* 13 and 14. It is notable that even though these stanzas are drawn from the same poem and are consecutive in that context too, here in the prose context of the *fornaldarsaga* a bridge between the two stanzas must be added. This is typical of stanza quotation in the *fornaldarsögur*.

The second episode in the story quotes *Reginsmál* 15 and is introduced with “og kvað vísu þessa,”¹²²⁰ and is a standard speech stanza. In these stanzas, the saga author has the characters of the *þáttr* quote themselves: they speak stanzas in the saga context that are spoken in a verse context elsewhere.

The third episode of the *þáttr* is notable for an interesting introduction of the first stanza: “Þessi maðr ljóðar á oss ok kvað.”¹²²¹ The content of the stanza is a traditional demand for identification, and the reply is introduced with “Reginn kvað í móti.”¹²²² The prose introductions thus makes the fact that their dialogue is in verse very explicit. In the third stanza, the “heklumaðurinn” identifies himself without being asked: “Hnikar hetom mik”¹²²³ is the first line of the stanza. This exchange differs from those found in other sagas because here there are no threats involved. Often, identification dialogues involve menacing as well as questioning your opponent. These stanzas are also consecutive stanzas from *Reginsmál*, stanza 16-18.

¹²¹⁹ *Norna-Gests þáttr*, *Flateyjarbók*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, vol. 1 (Akraness: Flateyjarútgáfan, 1955) pp. 384-398, at p. 388.

¹²²⁰ *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, p. 388.

¹²²¹ *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, p. 289.

¹²²² *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, p. 390.

¹²²³ *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, p. 390.

The fourth episode of the *þáttr* is that in which Sigurðr asks Hnikarr's advice. The first stanza, beginning "Segðu mer þat Hnikarr,"¹²²⁴ is a very friendly plea for information. The advice is duly dispensed by Hnikarr in six stanzas. No response is recorded in the narrative, the *þáttr* simply moves on. These stanzas are *Reginsmál* 19-25. The fifth episode contains only one stanza and this too receives little response in the narrative. It is the final stanza that is cited from *Reginsmál* (stanza 26 of the poem). It records the death of Lyngvi by bloodeagle, and is used in the *þáttr* as a speech stanza.¹²²⁵

The final episode in the *þáttr* to contain verse is a lengthy piece between Brynhildr and an ogress. Again, the introduction is rather unusual: "Eftir þat ljóðast þær á, Brynhildr ok gýgr."¹²²⁶ The prose points out that they chant at each other, clearly marking the switch between narrative modes. The verses are introduced as simple speech stanzas, but it is notable that it is Brynhildr who receives the most verses; the ogress speaks only three, while Brynhildr speaks ten. Of course, in this the saga author was constricted by the material he found in his source poem, stanzas 1-6 and 8-14 of *Helreið Brynhildar*. This type of exchange between a human and a supernatural creature is not uncommon in the *fornaldarsögur*, but the human is normally male and the supernatural creature female, rather than one female representative from each world against each other.

Norna-Gests þáttur and Eddic Prosimetrum

The *þáttr* contains a unique type of dialogue poem for the *fornaldarsögur* of two females against each other, one human, one supernatural. This comes from the heroic poetry so is not native to the *fornaldarsögur* genre in the same way as the battles, for example, between Ketil and Forað in *Ketils saga*, but because of the similarity with a

¹²²⁴ *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, p. 390.

¹²²⁵ *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, p. 391.

¹²²⁶ *Norna-Gests þáttr*, ed. Sigurður Nordal, p. 394.

common type of interaction found in *fornaldarsögur*, the dialogue does not sound out of place.

The verses in the þáttr are quotations from characters that are told during a story. This is rather different from how stanzas from *Poetic Edda* eddic poems are used in *Völsunga* saga, in which the material is taken a narrative level deeper and used to form the story itself. It has often been suggested that the story-telling situation in which Gestr tells his tale is a reflection of a realistic scenario for the delivery of a *fornaldarsaga*. It could be noted though that Gestr quotes heroic eddic poetry, not *eddic minora* poetry – the potential difference between these has already been exemplified above with the example of the dialogue between Brynhildr and the *gýgr*.

Family Sagas

Ketils saga hængs

There are two sustained studies of the manuscript and early edition history of *Ketils saga hængs*. Jean Rankine and Sarah M. Anderson have studied the manuscript tradition of the saga (along with that of *Gríms saga loðinkinna*),¹²²⁷ Sarah M. Anderson's later study presents much of the same information as Rankine in a slightly different format and supplements the discussion of manuscripts with several additional transcriptions. Citations from *Ketils saga* will be from her transcriptions.

There are two vellum manuscripts containing *Ketils saga hængs*. One is AM 343 a 4to and the other is AM 471 4to, both from the fifteenth century.¹²²⁸ These manuscripts of *Ketils saga hængs* are particularly interesting for the study of 15th-century manifestations of the Icelandic romance tradition, since they appear to group the texts in a similar fashion to modern genre designations. AM 343 a 4to groups *fornaldarsögur* and *riddarasögur* together, while AM 471 4to group *Íslendingasögur* together with those *fornaldarsögur* that have been described as leaning towards that subgenre (see above), and one popular *riddarasaga*. AM 343 a 4to has the following contents, in manuscript order:

Þorsteins þátrr bæjarmagns (1r-5v); *Samsons saga fagra* (5v-14r); *Egils saga einhenda og Ásmundar berserkjabana* (14r-21v); *Flóres saga konungs og sona hans* (21v-30v); *Vilhjálmss saga sjóðs* (30v-48v); *Yngvars saga víðfjrla* (48v-54r); *Ketils saga hængs* (54r-57v); *Gríms saga loðinkinna* (57v-59v); *Qrvar-Odds saga* (59v-81v); *Áns saga bogsveigis* (81v-87r); *Sálus saga ok Nikanórs* (87r-98v); *Hálfðanar saga Eysteinsonar* (99r-103v); *Bósa saga* (2 fragments: the first on 103v, the second on 104); *Vilmundar saga víðutan* (105r-108r); *Perus saga meistara* (108r-110r).

Of the sixteen sagas, nine are *fornaldarsögur* and six are *riddarasögur*. AM 471 4to preserves the following sagas:

Þórðar saga hreðu (1r-21v); *Króka-Refs saga* (21v-36r); *Kjalnesinga saga* (36r-49r); *Ketils saga hængs* (49r-56v); *Gríms saga loðinkinna* (57r-60v); *Qrvar-Odds saga* (61r-96v); *Viktors saga ok Blávus* (96v-108v).

¹²²⁷ See Jean M. Rankine, *Critical edition of Ketils saga hængs and Gríms saga loðinkinna*, MA Thesis University College London, 1967; Sarah May Anderson, *The Textual Tradition of Two Fornaldarsögur: "Ketils saga hœings" and "Gríms saga loðinkinna"*, Unpublished PhD Thesis, Cornell University, 1990.

¹²²⁸ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 578 and p. 654.

These are three *Íslendingasögur*, three *fornaldarsögur* and one *riddarasaga*. The arrangements of these manuscripts may reflect that their medieval compilers had a sense similar to our own about the similarity of the material.

There are three principle versions of *Ketils saga hængs*, known as the A, B and *E redactions. The A and B versions are preserved in the two vellum manuscripts that contain the saga (A = AM 343 a 4to and B = AM 471 4to). The E redaction is an abbreviation of the saga and exists only in (stemmatic) theory; the best preserved version of the *E redaction seems to be Gks 1006 fol., and it is the prosimetrum of this redaction that is studied below. All manuscripts of the *E group are paper. My comments about the prosimetric structure of the saga pertain mainly to redaction A.

The stanzas in *Ketils saga hængs* appear in seven episodes:

1. The encounter between Bruni and Ketill (A: 2 stt.)
2. The encounter between Gusi and Ketill (A: 10 stt.)
3. Grímr sees a troll (A: 1 st.)
4. Ketill fights Ali (A: 1 st.)
5. The encounter between Forað and Ketill (A: 10 stt.)
6. The encounter between Boðmóðr and Ketill (A: 6 stt.)
7. The encounter between Framarr and Ketill (A: 8 stt.)

Episode One: The Encounter Between Bruni and Ketill (*AB stt. 1-2*)

The two stanzas spoken in this episode are at its beginning when Bruni and Ketill meet each other. The first stanza, which begins “Heill kom þú Hængr,”¹²²⁹ has no significant differences between the A and B versions of the saga.

<p>A1 Heill kom þu hængz hier <i>skalltu</i> þiggia j allann uetur med oss uera. þier mun ek fafna nema þu fyzir latir dottur mina adr dagr komi.</p>	<p>B1 Heill com þu hængz. hier <i>fkalltu</i> þiggia. og j allann vetur med off vera. þier mun eg fafna nema þu fyrer later dottur mina adz dagur come.</p>
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¹²²⁹ A: Andersson, p. 47, 55v, ll.1-3; B: Andersson, p. 89, 51v, ll.16-17.

In naming Ketill in the first stanza, Bruni demonstrates that he must be skilled in magic in some way, since he knows Ketill's name without being told. The prose gives Bruni the attributes of a Sami (skiis and tending to his animals, A: Andersson p. 47, 55v, l. 1, B: Andersson p. 89, 51v, l.15), which complements this suggestion of magical ability, and Ketill replies to the verse with an acknowledgment of the "Finns" skill in magic. Bruni seems to take to Ketill well; in the prose by his good welcome ("fa tók vel vit honum" Andersson p. 89, 51v, 15-16), and in the stanza, he tells Ketill he is welcome to stay with them during the winters, and seems determined to keep a connection with Ketill as his future father-in-law.

<p>A2 Hier mun ek þiggia hygg eg at valldi Finnz fiolkyngi feikna uedri ok j allann dag einn jof ek uid þzia. hualuz kyꝛdi fea huf mun ek þiggia.</p> <p>(Andersson, p. 47, 55v, ll.3-5)¹²³⁰</p>	<p>B2 Hier mun eg þiggia. hygg eg at valde. finz fiolkyngi. feikna vedri. og j allann dag einn jof eg vid þzia. hualꝛ kyꝛde haf hier mun eg þiggia.</p> <p>(Andersson, p. 89, 51v, ll.18-20)</p>
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The second verse carefully echoes the first, and again, there are no significant differences between the A and B versions. The first line of both alliterates on *h* and both contain the word *þiggia*. Bruni's comment about staying during the winters (because travel is impossible) is echoed by Ketill's relation of his travel problems *allann dag* in the second stanza reflecting the *allann vetur* in the first, and Bruni's foresight in stanza one is acknowledged by Ketill's use of *Finnz fiolkyngi*. Bruni's desire to be linked to Ketill is acknowledged by Ketill saying that Bruni's magic has drawn him to there, although this is expressed in different and perhaps contradictory ways in prose and verse. In the stanza, it seems that Ketill is blaming "Finns" for the storm in which he is caught, and the prose indeeds locates him in Finnmark. However, the prose associates Bruni with the Finns and thus Ketill indirectly seems to blame him for causing the bad weather in the stanza. The verse says that the sea was calmed by a whale, not giving any more details; in the prose, the whale that pushes Ketill's boat against the wind is said to have human eyes (A: Andersson p. 47, 55r, l.

¹²³⁰ AB: Here I will take lodging! I think that Finns skilled in magic caused awful weather and for the whole day alone I baled against three. A whale calmed the sea. Here (A house) I will take lodging.

36, B: Andersson p. 89, 51v, l. 12), and given that Ketill ends up near Bruni's farm because of the whale, it seems to suggest that the whale is Bruni, casting Bruni in the role of a helpful rather than malicious Sami. Here the episodes in the prose and verse largely match although their emphasis is different. The prose says that troll woman was shaking Ketill's boat in the night; this is not mentioned at all in the verse; and the second stanza mentions that Ketill was forced to bale his boat out, which is not mentioned in the prose. The stanza mentions Ketill bails against "three," but does not specify what this is referring to. The most logical reading is that he is bailing against the magic of three Sami, referring to Bruni and the two women in his household, although in the prose, Ketill only finds out that there are two women within after this exchange has taken place.

Episode Two: The encounter between Gusi and Ketill (A stt. 3-12.)

The prosimetric encounter between Ketill and Gusi is formed of ten stanzas in which the two men identify themselves and make threats to each other, and ultimately Gusi is killed. In this section, the A and B versions differ, and there are two stanzas fewer in the B version than in A. Their order and first lines can be summarised thus:

First Line in A	Spoken By	Order in A	Order in B
“Skíð þu af kialka” ¹²³¹	Ketill	1	1
“Gufa kalla <i>mik</i> ” ¹²³²	Gusi	2	2
“Hængz ek heiti” ¹²³³	Ketill	3	3
“huerr er a aundzum” ¹²³⁴	Gusi	4	X
“Hæng kalla <i>mik</i> ” ¹²³⁵	Ketill	5	X
“Buztu nu <i>vid</i> ” ¹²³⁶	Gusi	6	4
“Mun ek af audi” ¹²³⁷	Ketill	7	5
“ <i>Ikalltu eigi</i> gulli” ¹²³⁸	Gusi	8	6
“Munek <i>eigi</i> gulli” ¹²³⁹	Ketill	9	7
“ <i>feigur er nu</i> ” ¹²⁴⁰	Ketill	10	8

¹²³¹ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, l. 18. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 9-10.

¹²³² A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 19-21. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 10-12.

¹²³³ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 21-23. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 13-15.

¹²³⁴ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 24-26. Not in B.

¹²³⁵ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 26-27. Not in B.

¹²³⁶ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 27-29. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 16-18.

¹²³⁷ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 29-30. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 18-20.

¹²³⁸ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 30-32. B: Andersson, p. 92, 52r, ll. 20-21.

¹²³⁹ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 32-33. B: Andersson, p. 92, 52r, ll. 21-23.

¹²⁴⁰ A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 36-37. B: Andersson, p. 92, 52r, l. 26 – 52v, l. 1.

The absence of Gusi's stanza and Ketill's reply in B, stanzas four and five in this episode in A, mean that a question/challenge by Gusi is missing, and a reply by Ketill that almost repeats the third stanza in the section and does not seem a terribly good reply to Gusi.

The first stanza of the episode, the third of the saga in AB, is said by Ketill as he sees Gusi riding after him: "Skzid þu af kialka ky2 þu hzeina feggz fidforull feg huattu heitir."¹²⁴¹

The stanza is contextulised slightly differently in A and B. In A, as Ketill looks towards the forest, he sees Gusi riding towards him in a great blaze of snow ("miallroku mikla")¹²⁴² with ".ij. hzeina ok uagn."¹²⁴³ In B, however, the forest setting and the blaze of snow also appear, but now Gusi is riding "akafliga" ['vehemently'] and the reindeer and the sledge are not mentioned. In A, this has meant that the plural reindeer in the stanza and the "hand-sledge" are mentioned literally in the prose as two reindeer and a *vagn*. In B, Gusi's energetic arrival rationalises his need in the stanza to calm his reindeer. That the two versions of the saga have interpreted the same verse differently means that the stanza is likely to be prior to these versions of the prose, but since the prose is nevertheless similar in each version, the versions are clearly related.

In the second verse of the episode, the fourth in the AB versions of the saga, Gusi's reply, introduced with "fa su(ar)ar," is threatening and echoes Ketill's question:

Gufa kalla mik gaufgir Finnar em eg odduiti allraz þiodar. huat er þat manna er mier j moti ferr ok
fkridz sem uargr af uidi. ædzu fkalltu mæla ef þu undan kemzt .iij. fyrir þzumu þui tel eg þic ofniallan.
¹²⁴⁴

¹²⁴¹ ['You, gliding on a hand-sledge, you calming reindeer, a man out late in the evening, say what you are called.'] A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, l. 18. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 9-10. There are no significant differences between the A and B versions of the stanza.

¹²⁴² Andersson, p. 48, 55v, l. 17.

¹²⁴³ Andersson, p. 48, 55v, l. 17.

¹²⁴⁴ Gusi they call me (or: I call myself), honoured by Finns, I am leader of all that people. Who is that man who goes to meet me and skis like a wolf in a wood? You shall utter words of despair if you escape three times at Þruma, for I consider you unwise (B: You shall utter words of despair three times in Þruma firth; I consider you unwise). ok] ÷ B. ef þu undan kemzt .iij. fyrir þzumu þui tel eg þic ofniallan] þzyfuar j Þrumv fizde. þig tel eg ofniallan B. Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 19-21.

Gusi's immediate identification of himself and his assertion of his high-status means that he is immediately trying to establish superiority over Ketill, and this is reinforced by his threat that Ketill will be uttering words of despair (in B), which in A would be caused if Ketill were to try and escape. The snub to Ketill is ended in both versions by Gusi declaring Ketill *ósnjallr*. At the same time, Gusi echoes Ketill's demand for his opponent to identify himself, indicating that he wishes to open a dialogue between the two, and from the point of view of the construction of the saga, opening the way for a poetic exchange.

In the fifth stanza of the saga, Ketill in turn seeks to echo and thus answer Gusi's stanza:

Hængz ek heiti kominn uz Hrafniftu. hefnir Hallbiaznar. hui skridz þu suo hinn azmi. fridmalum mæla mun eg eigi uid Finn ragann helldz mun ek boga benda þann mier Bzuni gaf.¹²⁴⁵

Ketill gives his byname, his place of origin and his relationship to Hallbjörn, in answer to Gusi's affirmation of his origin and status. In reply to Gusi's less than complimentary remarks about him skiing like a wolf in the wood, indicating that Gusi might think him up to no good, Ketill in turn asks in version A, with a rhetorical question, why Gusi is going about like he is, and to counter Gusi's threat says he does not want to attempt to broker peace but will instead shoot him (this is extended in version B). In A, the beginning of the question "hui skridz þu" harks back to the beginning of the first stanza of the episode, "Skzid þu af kialka," linking the stanzas together and providing continuity of imagery. The final reference to the bow that Bruni gave him also links this episode with the episode in which Ketill encounters Bruni and provides structural integrity for the saga in a manner that suggests these episodes, likely with the poetry included since it records such a large amount of the dialogue, must travel together in the saga narrative world.

¹²⁴⁵ ['Hængz I am called, from Hrafnista, Hallbjörn's avenger. Why do you ski so, wretched one? (Why do you ski so, wretched one?) I do not intend to ask for peace'] B) ['I will not speak words of peace with a cowardly Finn, rather I will bend the bow that Bruni gave to me.'] Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 21-23.

At this point, the same introductory phrase appears in A and B to introduce different stanzas in the different versions: “Gufi þottizt nu uita huerr hængur fia [uar] þuiat hann uar frægð miog” [‘Gusi now thought he knew who this Hængur was, because he was very famous’].¹²⁴⁶ This glimpse into Gusi’s thoughts is placed in order to allow us to judge the impact this recognition might have on Gusi’s words and deeds. In both AB, the stanza that Gusi speaks is threatening. In A, the focus is on asking for Hængur’s exact identity and then stating his direct intention to engage in combat with Ketill: “huerr er a aundzum aunduerdan dag giarn til gunnar j grimmum hug. uit fkulum freifta flein at rioda huor at audrum nema hugr bili.”¹²⁴⁷ Gusi’s thought that he might know who Hængur is rationalises the next stanza’s second request for Ketill to identify himself, indicated by the fact that this stanza and its answer from Ketill that follows are absent from B might, likely excluded on the grounds that they are repetitive. In B, the introductory phrase displaying Gusi’s suspicions about Hængur’s identity is followed by the stanza beginning “Buztu nu vid,”¹²⁴⁸ which I will come to below.

In A, Gusi’s stanza is answered by Ketill in the seventh stanza of the saga with an admission that he has given only half his name: “Hæng kalla mið halfu nafni. mun ek ueita þier uid nám heidan. fkalltu uijft uita adz uit fkilium at búkauzlum bita auzuar.”¹²⁴⁹ Ketill also returns Gusi’s insult that his courage might break by stating that he will surely resist him, and that Gusi will certainly be shot by arrows, whilst also insulting him by calling him a *búkarl* [‘farmer’], when Gusi has earlier claimed to be king of the Finns. It is natural that this stanza is absent in B when the stanza that provokes it is also absent. The existence of these two verses in A and their absence in B, where their introductory sentence is used but for other stanzas, shows that

¹²⁴⁶ nu] ÷ B. A: Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 23-24. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 15-16.

¹²⁴⁷ [‘Who stands on snow-shoes at daybreak, eager for battle, with grim mind? We shall try to redder arrows, each at the other, unless courage gives way.’] Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 24-26.

¹²⁴⁸ B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 16-17.

¹²⁴⁹ [‘Call me Hængur for half a name. I will put up resistance to you henceforth. You shall certainly know before we part that arrows bite farmers.’] Andersson, p. 48, 55v, ll. 26-27.

redactors felt they had a certain amount of flexibility in how they used the stanzas and could leave out those they felt to be irrelevant, or else, the exclusion of these two stanzas was an accident and was then likely caused by eyeskip.

The next stanza continues the tone, with Gusi demanding that Ketill ready himself for battle: “Buztu nu *uid* bitri eggþzumu hafðu hlijf fyrir þier hart mun ek fkiota. þier mun ek bzálla at bana uerda. nema þu af audi aullum látir.”¹²⁵⁰ These formulaic and dry-sounding threats, concluded with a demand for money, are answered by Ketill by equally monotonous promises: “Mun ek af audi eigi láta. ok fyrir einum þier alldri renna. fyrr skal þier hoggin hlijf fyrir bziofti ok fyrir fionum fuart at ganga.”¹²⁵¹ It could be noted that the motif of being hewn in the breast and it going black before the eyes is shared with Hjálmar’s Death Song (in *Hervarar saga* and *Qrvar-Odds saga*), in which Hjálmar as he is dying laments this is what has happened to him; this threat from Ketill could thus be considered as a formulaic one in the context of the *fornaldarsögur*.

Ketill interprets the next stanza, spoken by Gusi (“*skalltu eigi gulli ne gersfimum med heilum hug heima rada. kemur þier bani bratt at hondum ef uit skulum úti oddum leika*”)¹²⁵² as a repeated suggestion that he relinquish his wealth. In the A version: “Munek eigi gulli vid Gusi fkipta. ne fyrr til fridað mæla. mier er bzagð betri miklu. enn mier er hugð ok hiedan kuoma.”¹²⁵³ The middle part of the stanza, “mier er bzagð betri miklu,” does not make very good sense; it is not clear what thing might be ‘the foremost’ or ‘the best’ thing in this context. B records a more comprehensible version

¹²⁵⁰ Note that “bzálla” has the same meaning as “bráðla.” [‘Ready yourself now for a bitter battle. Have your shield in front of you. I will shoot hard. I will quickly cause your death-wound, unless you relinquish all your wealth.’] A: Andersson, 55v, p. 48, ll. 27-29. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, ll. 16-18. Note the beginning of the stanza in B is slightly different: “Buztu nu ef þu villt. bzatt vit egg þrumu” [‘Ready yourself now if you want. Soon will edges rattle!’].

¹²⁵¹ [‘I will not give up wealth and by one such as you never be put to flight. Sooner I shall hew at you, shield before breast, and it will go black before your eyes!’] A: Andersson, 55v, p. 48, l. 29 – p. 49, l. 30. B: Andersson, p. 91, 52r, l. 18 – p. 92, 52r, ll. 19-20.

¹²⁵² [‘You shall enjoy neither gold nor jewels with a happy heart at home. Death comes to you in turn if we should finish point-play.’] A: Andersson, p. 49, 55v, ll. 30-32. B: Andersson, p. 92, 52r, ll. 20-21.

¹²⁵³ [‘I will not exchange gold with Gusi, nor, as before, speak of peace. To me is the foremost greatly better, yet to me it is desirable also to escape from here.’] Andersson, p. 49, 55v, ll. 32-33.

of the stanza: “Muneg eigi gulli vit Gufi skipta. nè helldz fyrre til fridar mæla. mier er bradz bane betri miklu. enn hugleyfe og hedan coma.”¹²⁵⁴ Here again we see the stanzas in B, whilst obviously to the content in A, perhaps present a clearer version of the episode. The naming of Gusi in this stanza not only affirms the stanza’s relationship with the verses in this episode, it also provides a final rounding off of the exchange, since the final verse in the episode is separated from this one with a little more prose than usual.

The final verse in the episode comes during the part of the episode that relates how Ketill kills Gusi and takes his arrows, a particularly important event in the saga cycle of the *Hrafnistumenn*, since the arrows, known as “Gusisnautar,” are referred to elsewhere. The prose itself also immediately relates to what we have heard in the verses, as they both bend their bows to shoot each other, and Ketill has previously stated in stanza five that he will bend the bow that Brúni gave to him and Gusi has promised Ketill that he will shoot at him hard. Otherwise, the prose by stating that they shot arrows at each other is somewhat incongruous with what has come before, as both men have also made it sound like they will have a sword fight, with talk of having shields before their breasts and hewing at each other. Likewise, the mention of the “egg þruma,” a clash of edges, also sounds more like a sword fight than firing arrows. This can probably be accounted for by the desire to include formulaic battle-threats in the stanzas, influenced perhaps by sword-wielding heroes such as Hjálmar and his Death Song, tempered by the obviously strong tradition of Ketill obtaining arrows from Gusi, which, I have argued elsewhere, is likely oral since it figures in the wider traditions of the men of Hrafnista.¹²⁵⁵

The final stanza in the episode is a half-stanza: “feigur er nu Finnur hinn ragi er hann föttredur flein finn ranngan.”¹²⁵⁶ Referring to Gusi as “hinn ragi” links back

¹²⁵⁴ [‘I will not exchange gold with Gusi, nor any more than before speak of peace. To me is a sudden death much better than faintheartedness and escape.’] Andersson, p. 92, 52r, ll. 21-23.

¹²⁵⁵ Helen F. Leslie, “The Matter of Hrafnista,” *Quaestio Insularis* 11 (2010): 169-208.

¹²⁵⁶ [‘Finn the Coward is now fated to die, when (since B) he tramples wrongly on his arrows.’] er] at B. A: Andersson, 55v, p. 49, 55v, ll. 36-37. B: Andersson, p. 92, 52r, l. 26 – 52v, l. 1.

to earlier stanzas, and Ketill likely abuses him like that due to disrespect for Gusi's Sami origins, denoted in the text by reference to him as a "Finnur." Gusi may have been trampling his arrows underfoot once he realised he was fatally wounded in an attempt to prevent Ketill from getting hold of them, since they are a precious and supernatural asset. That Gusi has the arrows back after he had already shot them at Ketill is explained elsewhere in the tradition by them being self-returning. This final stanza reinstates the arrows as the important object in this episode.

In the written versions of the saga, two traditional elements – the generic threat of the sword fight and the tradition of Gusi's arrows – are mixed, which likely shows a desire on the part of the saga composers to have the saga in the generic mode of the *fornaldarsaga* whilst retaining the oral-style prosimetrum of a lengthy versified conversation, a narrative tactic quite particular to the *fornaldarsögur*, and as such verses have gathered around the pivotal event of Ketill obtaining Gusi's arrows, the telling of which also include sword-bearing references. It could also be noted that this episode also contains another use of verse common in *fornaldarsögur*: naming-stanzas, which begin by characters announcing their names and origins, and stanzas that demand such names be announced. In the A version, there are five of these. These eddic dialogues embedded in the saga and its use of traditional elements known elsewhere are probably best attributed to oral origins for the saga.

Episode Three: Grímr sees a troll (A st. 13)

Ketill speaks this stanza when Grímr, his son, runs to him to tell him that he has seen a *troll* whilst out collecting water when they are on a journey: it is tragically obvious to the reader that this troll is probably Grímr's own mother,¹²⁵⁷ who tries to take him but whom he fails to recognise: "Huat er þat byfna er uid berg ftendz ok gapir elldi yfir. búfifiar ockrar hygg ek batna munu littu a lioduega."¹²⁵⁸ The use here of *býsna* (as a

¹²⁵⁷ This indicated most explicitly in the B version, in which "ham [Ketill] kuad þat ecke troll vera" (Andersson, p. 96, 53r, l. 16) ['he (Ketill) said it to be no troll'], whereas in A it simply says that Ketill went to meet with the troll (Andersson, p. 51, 56r, l. 32).

¹²⁵⁸ er uid berg ftendz] er eg á biargi fie B. A: Andersson, p. 51, 56r, ll. 33-34. B: Andersson, p. 96, 53r, ll. 16-18.

neuter noun, meaning ‘portent’ or ‘wonder’) is a complimentary way of referring to the “troll” that Grímr has reported seeing, and at the same time correlates well with the original meaning of “monster” as a portent (cf. Latin *monstrum*, a wonder, portent), and is likely a play on the idea of Hrafnhildr as a portent, wonder and monster. Ketill desire for reconciliation with Hrafnhildr can be construed from the fourth and fifth lines, in which he says their relationships are sure to improve, although after this stanza Hrafnhildr simply disappears (“*traullit huarf*”).¹²⁵⁹ The stanza provides the prose action with a setting (near to the cliff) and is appealing in Ketill’s wish for their closeness, but is also mysterious: the sight of Hrafnhildr gaping over the fire is reminiscent of a *völva* practising her magic divination, and Ketill’s instruction to her to ‘look to the stars’ is an odd one, with no explanation in the prose. This *lausavísa* is occasional and does not seem to play a significant role at this point in the saga.

Episode Four: Ketill fights Ali (A st. 14)

Ketill speaks this stanza to Hjálmur and and Stafnglámur when he is fighting Ali, and Ali wounds him dishonourably:

Hjalmur ok Stafngl(ampur) hlifit yckuz bádir gefit rum gaumlum at ganga frammar hóti. fliuga folknaudzum frækn er Dala kappi. liotur er leikuz suerda lit at er fkegg a kazli. frapa fkinnykztlar skialfa hringfkyztur. hristazt jaznferkir. hzædizt bidill meyiaz.¹²⁶⁰

In the prose, this stanza is said because Ketill has blood pouring down his face, and and first it does not make him sound very brave, since his armour is depicted as shaking (presumably with fear) and he tells Hjálmur and Stafnglámur to protect themselves. However, the last line of the stanza, in the context of the prose, makes it clear that it is Ali who is supposed to be depicted as afraid, since he is the “bidill meyiaz,” as it is his rejection by Ketill’s daughter that causes the fight. Directly after

¹²⁵⁹ A: Andersson, p. 51, 56r, l. 34. B: Andersson, p. 96, 53r, l. 18.

¹²⁶⁰ A: Andersson, p. 52, 56v, ll. 5-8. B: Andersson, p. 97, 53v, ll. 4-7. [‘Hjálmur and Stafnglámur, Both protect yourselves! Give space to the old one that goes forward threatening. Spears are flying! The Dala champion is bold! The sword-play is ugly. Dyed (with blood) is the beard on the man. Skin kirtle clatters, iron shirt quivers,

ring shirt shakes, The wooder of maiden is afraid.‘]

this stanza, Ketill kills Ali. The “ljótur” sword-play is depicted in the prose by Ali attacking Ketill before he has his shield in place, and the comment that “spears are flying” is likely not meant to be taken literally and simply mean a fight is taking place, since in both the prose and stanza it seems to be a one-to-one fight with swords rather than spears.

Episode Five The encounter between Forað and Ketill (A: 10 stt.)

This is the second encounter in which Ketill engages in a versified dialogue with a creature belonging to the supernatural realm, or at least to the Other (the first being with the Sami Gusi). Ketill comes across the troll, who in the prose is newly emerged from the sea and bathing in the sun, and similar to his exchange with Gusi, the first stanza begins “*huat er þat flagda er ek fa a fornu nefi*” [‘what is that ogress who I see on a far ness?’],¹²⁶¹ and this demand for identification indicates that a naming-insulting sequence, such as that with Gusi earlier, will begin. Indeed, the remainder of the stanza sets this up, since Ketill provocatively states he has never seen one so hideous looking (A: “*ek hefek aunga eina leidiligri litit*”).¹²⁶² The reply from Forað (the troll) cements the type of exchange. She begins by confirming her name and her place of origin as Gusi and Ketill both did earlier, throws an insult at Ketill, calling him a “*huimleid bumonnum*” [‘hideous farmer’],¹²⁶³ and her mention of an arrow and attack seems to allude to Ketill’s weapons rather than hers. She continues; in B, this is not separate from her naming stanza, although it is in A, being introduced with “*ok enn k(uad) hun.*”¹²⁶⁴ She announces her previous killings of men (“*Moꝝgum manni hefek til molldar fnuit þeim er til fífkiaz foru*”)¹²⁶⁵ and responds to the request for her identity with a request for his: “*huer er sea hinn kaupurmali er kominn er fkerin*” [‘who is this

¹²⁶¹ A: Andersson, p. 52, 56v, ll. 15-16. B: Andersson, p. 98, 53v, ll. 16-17.

¹²⁶² A: Andersson, p. 52, 56v, l. 16. B: “*hefi eg aunga fyꝝ leidiligri litid,*” Andersson, p. 98, 53r, ll. 16-17.

¹²⁶³ B: Andersson, p. 98, 53v, l. 18. A has “*huimleid leidbumonnum,*” where the repetition of “leid” seems to be an error, Andersson, p. 52, 56v, l. 17.

¹²⁶⁴ Andersson, p. 53, 56v, l. 18.

¹²⁶⁵ A: Andersson, p. 53, 56v, l. 18. B: Andersson, p. 98, 53v, l. 19.

bantering one who has come to the skerry”].¹²⁶⁶ The choice of the word “(hinn) köpurmáll” [‘the bantering one’] to describe the manner of her exchange with Ketill perhaps indicates that this type of exchange is a recognised one and that the stanzas indicate their performance context.

The next part of the exchange is in prose, but could easily have been in verse: in A it says “*hann s(uar)ar. kalla mík hæng sagdi hann. hun s(uar)ar. nær uæri þier at uers heima j Hrafnistu en dratta einum til ut fkeria*” [‘it might be fitter for you to be at home in Hrafnista than to drag the same out to a skerry’].¹²⁶⁷ Given that information and comments like this (a name and a threat) have previously been in verse, it is tempting to suggest that in this instance verse has been converted to prose, either verses original to this episode, or verses from the episode with Gusi.

The exchange in verse continues with a long speech by Ketill, the eighteenth in the saga:

einhlitur eg þottumzt að enn hier kuomum um fleftar allar farir uoza2 huat sem ferlig flaugd um gleipa. laftig dreing d2afinn¹²⁶⁸ drepic¹²⁶⁹ a uit fanga. læt ek hier fyrir uinnazt huat er fo2at mælir. naudir mík huóttu nanum er at biarga. hettig¹²⁷⁰ eigi a hólum til fela ef j eyiu æznir uæri.¹²⁷¹

The stanza is somewhat opaque in meaning, particularly near the end, and some emmendations as indicated in the footnotes seem to be needed. Ketill here seems ready to give up.

The remainder of the episode in stanzas 19-24¹²⁷² can be characterised by their regular dialogue format, and short pieces of prose introduction between them, typically giving

¹²⁶⁶ A: Andersson, p. 53, 56v, ll. 18-19. B: Andersson, p. 98, 53v, ll. 19-20. Note that the ending of the B version reads better, with “er komin er j skerin.”

¹²⁶⁷ A: Andersson, p. 53, 56v, ll. 19-20. B: “*hann f(agdi) hæng kalla mig halfu nafni. hun f(agdi) Hollaza væri þier heima at liggia enn dratta einum vt fkeria til*” [‘he said, I call myself Hængr for half a name. She said, “more salutary might it have been to you to stay at home than to drag the same out to a skerry’] Andersson, p. 98, 53v, ll. 20-21.

¹²⁶⁸ drasinn?

¹²⁶⁹ dreg ek?

¹²⁷⁰ hætta ek?

¹²⁷¹ A: Andersson, p. 53, 56v, ll. 20-23. B: Andersson, p. 98, 53v, ll. 22-25.

an snippet of one of the characters thoughts before introducing the stanza. Redaction B is not different in prosimetric structure or stanza order.

Episode Six: The encounter between Boðmóðr and Ketill (A: 6 stt.)

Ketill and Boðmóðr's encounter is six stanzas long and is good example of a short and tightly structured prosimetric narrative with prose inbetween each stanza that does not detract from the ability of the verse to deliver dialogue and remain primary in the scene. None of the stanzas form consecutive units because of this. There is also no need for an elaborate performance context in the prose before and after the stanzas, since each stanza is a direct response to the one before. Nevertheless, some performance context is given, for example the actions and the thoughts of the characters are variously provided in brief between the stanzas to indicate small movements and the moods of characters. This kind of compact prosimetric dialogue would have been entertaining to listening to in an oral context, since the pace is lively and the fast switching of form is engaging.

Episode Seven: The encounter between Framarr and Ketill (A: 8 stt.)

The prosimetric dialogue between Framarr and Ketill has some contrasting features compared to the one directly before it in the saga (Ketill and Boðmóðr). The dialogue with Framarr is longer. Firstly, it contains more stanzas. Secondly, two of the stanzas spoken by Ketill form a unit on two occasions (stanzas 33-34 and 36-37)¹²⁷³ and they are joined by a prose tag: "*ok enn kuad hann.*"¹²⁷⁴ The two consecutive stanzas that Framarr speaks at the beginning of the exchange are not joined with this tag, because the stanzas contain descriptive prose between them. The pattern of exchange is thus Framarr-Framarr-Ketill-Ketill-Framarr-Ketill-Ketill-Framarr which is not terribly

¹²⁷² A: Andersson, pp. 53-54.

¹²⁷³ A: Andersson, p. 58, 57v, ll. 21-24.

¹²⁷⁴ A: Andersson, p. 58, 57v, ll. 22, 28.

unbalanced. It could also be noted that the episodes with Framarr and Boðmóðr are both dialogues with men as opposed to supernatural creatures, as in the case of Forað.

Ketils saga hængs and Eddic Prosimetrum

Ketils saga hængs is typically structured for a prosimetric *fornaldarsaga*, but it is not so bland in its prosimetrum that it can be considered a riff on an obvious stereotype, as is the case with *Hjálmþés saga*. Five of the seven prosimetric episodes are comprised of more than one stanza, and two episodes contain only one stanza. The prosimetric composition of *Ketils saga* is so nicely balanced and represents a midway point between other extremes of prosimetric structure in the *fornaldarsögur* that it is tempting to suggest that the type of prosimetric profile found in *Ketils saga* is indicative of or reflects perhaps the type of prosimetrum that oral *fornaldarsögur* material may once have taken in its narrative form. This is supported by its relatively modest length. I am not suggesting that the saga as extant was transmitted in oral tradition, but nevertheless that something much like it in structure probably formed the basis of the written saga.

Ketils saga is most notable for its sets of dialogue: two sets of dialogue occur with supernatural characters (the Sami Gúsi and the trollwoman Forað), and two with men, Boðmóðr and Framarr. From Ketill's encounter with Gúsi, we can conclude that dialogues can have the following features: firstly, that information can be repeated, as shown by Ketill naming himself twice (although the B redactor opts to leave out one of these stanzas), and secondly that stating one's name and place of origin in eddic verse seems to have been a traditional use of the metre in a prose context. Thirdly, dialogue stanzas can echo and answer each other; this can be seen in stanzas 1 and 2 (AB) and stanzas 8-9 (A, or 7-8 B). This technique would have prevented the dialogue from breaking up easily under oral transmission and would likely have ensured the pairs of stanzas were always performed together.

The length of the dialogues in the saga may also be indicative of the maximum number of stanzas a dialogue preserved in oral tradition in verse could comfortably hold. The sections run from six to ten stanzas, so around eight stanzas seems average

(four for each character). We might also note that in *Ketils saga*, the exchanges are between two characters only, and I suggest for the shorter type of dialogue that does not extend into a *mannjafnaðr*, this is typical. This maintains the simplicity of the exchange while allowing tension to build between the speakers of the dialogue.

Gríms saga loðinkinna

Gríms saga loðinkinna shares the same redaction history as *Ketils saga hængs* (see above). It is a relatively short saga that is written in the same style of *Ketils saga hængs*, but it has far fewer verses (only seven). The reason for this is that it lacks extended dialogues, apart from the first prosimetric episode in the saga, which is an exchange of five stanzas between Grímr and two troll-women.¹²⁷⁵ The prosimetric is a compact, short, piece with minimal prose between the stanzas, enough to name the characters. This type of dialogue was also found in *Ketils saga hængs*. The prosimetric piece has no real performance context other than a simple exchange of speech in verse. These compact, short dialogue pieces possibly have roots in oral tradition, where they would preserve the essence of a scene.

The second and final occurrence of prosimetricum in *Gríms saga* is when Grímr speaks two stanzas that come directly after one another.¹²⁷⁶ These two stanzas are joined by the tag “*ok enn k(uad) hann,*”¹²⁷⁷ a standard manner with which to join the first stanza to subsequent verses in the legendary sagas.

Gríms saga loðinkinna and Eddic Prosimetrum

Although the prosimetricum might not be plentiful in the saga, it nevertheless does display the typical features of a dialogue with a supernatural creature, and conjoined stanzas. It is hard to say why this saga has so few stanzas in comparison to *Ketils saga*. The answer could simply lie in the fact that the traditions surrounding Grímr that made their way into his saga were in prose.

¹²⁷⁵ A: Andersson, pp. 60-61.

¹²⁷⁶ A: Andersson, p. 66, 59v, ll. 5-8.

¹²⁷⁷ A: Andersson, p. 66, 59v, l. 7.

Qrvar-Odds saga

Qrvar-Odds saga contains 146 verses, by far the most of any of the *fornaldarsögur*. The saga is more like the Germanic Heroic Legends (for example *Hervarar saga*) in how the poetic materials are employed in the saga narrative, although it is, according to Torfi H. Tulinius, on the cusp between the “earlier” and “later” *fornaldarsögur*, and as such may mark a turning point in the genre’s development, and the saga should probably best be understood as one that is between oral and written composition.¹²⁷⁸

Qrvar-Odds saga has a complex textual history and exists in six individual redactions.¹²⁷⁹ It has been edited thoroughly by R. C. Boer. In addition, it contains a very large number of verses and is the one of the longest, oldest and most popular of the *fornaldarsögur*. For these reasons, my treatment of the saga here is rather more extensive than that of the other *fornaldarsögur* containing verse. I first outline the manuscript preservation of the saga and look at the saga’s *lausavisur* in depth. I examine the prosimetric structure of Qrvar-Oddr’s drinking contest, and finally, I consider Qrvar-Oddr’s death song, a long poem at the end of some redactions of the saga.

My discussion is based on R. C. Boer’s edition of 1888, and my comments below on the manuscript transmission/stemma of *Qrvar-Odds saga* are mostly limited to the information and deductions published in his introduction to the edition.¹²⁸⁰

¹²⁷⁸ Cf. Oscar Bandle, “Die Fornaldarsaga zwischen Mündlichkeit und Schriftlichkeit: Zur Entstehung und Entwicklung der Örvar-Odds saga,” *Zwischen Festtag und Alltag. Zehn Beiträge zum Thema ‘Mündlichkeit und Schriftlichkeit,’* ed. Wolfgang Raible, ScriptaOralia 6 (Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag, 1988) pp. 191-213.

¹²⁷⁹ Overviews of the manuscript tradition can be found in Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, pp. 27-28; Martin Arnold, “Við þik settumsk ek aldri. Qrvar-Odds saga and the Meanings of Qgmundr Eyþjófsbani,” *Making History: Essays on the fornaldarsögur*, ed. Alison Finlay and Martin Arnold (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 2010) pp. 85-104, at pp. 85-86.

¹²⁸⁰ Of the manuscripts known to Boer, several paper manuscripts were inaccessible to him. These were GKS 1006 in Copenhagen, and from the British Library’s collections (then the British Museum) manuscripts 17 and 357 from Finn Magnússon’s collection and manuscript 6 from Baring Gould’s collection. These are subsequently not considered in his discussion. He also notes, but does not discuss, 89 fol. and 98 fol. of the Royal Library in Stockholm, which are Latin and Swedish translation respectively, and NKS 1205 fol. in Copenhagen, which is a copy of Rudbeck’s edition, *Qrvar-Odds saga*, ed. R. C. Boer (Leiden: Brill, 1888) vii. References to this edition will be made with the abbreviation: *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*.

Qrvar-Odds saga is preserved in 68 manuscripts.¹²⁸¹ The following manuscripts preserving *Qrvar-Odds saga* have been identified by R. C. Boer as being of independent value:¹²⁸²

- Holm Perg. 4to nr 7, Kungliga biblioteket, Stockholm (S)
- AM 344 a 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (M)
- AM 343 a 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (A)
- AM 471 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (B)
- AM 567 IV 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (C)
- AM 173 fol., Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (E)

Holm Perg. 4to nr 7, Kungliga biblioteket, Stockholm (S). This vellum manuscript was written in Iceland at the beginning of the 14th century.¹²⁸³ As it is the oldest manuscript, it has been considered by Boer to preserve the best text of the saga.¹²⁸⁴ *Qrvar-Odds saga* is to be found on fols. 43v²-57r¹⁹. Seven lines on 51v have been scratched off (ll.13-19; cf. *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 95), that would have contained the fight on Sámsey and Hjálmar's body being brought to Sweden. The rubric at the end of line 10 of the same page, "haugsgjord eftir hjalmar" ['cairn-making for Hjálmar'], is, according to Boer, evidence that the episode was once present in S's exemplar and has been lost simply by chance; likely a page was missing in S's exemplar, and when the scribe of S has realised this, he has tried to make a connection.¹²⁸⁵ He has done this by making the two sentences similar on either side of the scratched out lines. Before these lines we find "ok dveljaz þeir nú þar hau..." ['now they stayed there...'] (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 95.11) and after "Nú dvelz Oddr nokkura hríð" ['Now Oddr stayed for

¹²⁸¹ According to "Örvar-Odds saga: Manuscripts," *Stories for All Time: The Icelandic Fornaldarsögur* <<http://am-dk.net/fasnl/bibl/bibl.php?sid=816>>.

¹²⁸² *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*.

¹²⁸³ Dated thus by *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* i.

¹²⁸⁴ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* i.

¹²⁸⁵ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* i.

a while'] (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 109.1). Two paper manuscripts of *Qrvar-Odds saga* descended from S are used by Boer to patch S in those places where it is not readable or is lacking: the fragment Holm papp. 17 fol. (sigla: s) and Holm papp. 103 fol. (sigla: t).

AM 344 a 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (M). This short, vellum manuscript of 24 pages was written in the late 14th century.¹²⁸⁶ It only contains *Örvar-Odds saga*. The saga is divided into three *þættir*, the headings of which are only partially readable, and into chapters, which begin with red, green and yellow initials, and is written by two hands.¹²⁸⁷ One paper manuscript of *Qrvar-Odds saga*, NKS 1793 4to, in the Royal Library in Copenhagen, is descended from M.

AM 343 a 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (A). This vellum manuscript of the 15th century¹²⁸⁸ is one of the principle manuscripts of the *fornaldarsögur* and other romances. These fifteen legendary and romantic sagas cover 110 pages, and *Qrvar-Odds saga* can be found on 59^v-81^v. Although preserved pretty much complete, here and there the manuscript is unreadable; in the case of *Qrvar-Odds saga*, some places in the beginning of the saga cannot be read.¹²⁸⁹ A number of paper manuscripts of *Qrvar-Odds saga* descend from A: AM 344 b 4to (17th century, the saga is on 1-35^f),¹²⁹⁰ AM 340 4to (written by Jón Gissursson, 17th century, the saga is on 19-79^v),¹²⁹¹ AM 591 i 4to (second half of the 17th century, only contains a fragment of *Qrvar-Odds saga*),¹²⁹² AM 109 a 8vo (17th century, the saga, which has

¹²⁸⁶ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, p. ii dates the manuscript to the second half of the 14th century; Kålund dates it to c. 1400, in *KAH* vol. 1, p. 579.

¹²⁸⁷ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* p. ii. Further commentary on the scribes and the orthography of the manuscript can be found in *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* ii-v.

¹²⁸⁸ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 578.

¹²⁸⁹ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* v. See also Kålund, vol. 1, 578-579; also here for commentary on the manuscript's make up.

¹²⁹⁰ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 580.

¹²⁹¹ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 576.

¹²⁹² *KAH* vol. 1, p. 759.

Gríms saga loðinkinna as an introduction, is found on 77^r-142), NKS 1707 4to, 1709 4to, 1715 4to (a compilation of Rudbeck's edition and AM 109 a 8vo).¹²⁹³

AM 471 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (B). AM 471 4to is a vellum manuscript written in Iceland in the 15th century¹²⁹⁴ and is closely related to A.¹²⁹⁵ *Qrvar-Odds saga* is on 61-96^v and is somewhat fragmentary: the beginning is defective since a page is missing (the saga in B thus begins at the equivalent of *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 4.7). The manuscript also lacks a page after fol. 85, producing a gap in the text equivalent to *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 138.18-142.18.¹²⁹⁶ Some of the verses, including Hjálmar's death song and Qrvar-Oddr's death song, are copied into AM 738 4to, a manuscript from 1680¹²⁹⁷ that contains many eddic poems, eddic verses and poems of other kinds, on 7^r-12, although the copies of both poems contain many errors.¹²⁹⁸

AM 567 IV 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (C).

AM 567 IV 4to consists of three leaves from the 15th century, of which leaves 2 and 3 (2r-3v) contain fragments of *Qrvar-Odds saga*; 1r-v contain a fragment of *Gríms saga loðinkinna*. the first of which corresponds to *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 66.19-82.18, and the second of which begins at *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 124.29. The last readable word is on 129.25 ("hjó").¹²⁹⁹ NKS 1689 4to is a copy of C, but is, according to Boer, of no use for establishing the text of C, since every line of the copy contains serious errors.¹³⁰⁰

¹²⁹³ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* v-vi.

¹²⁹⁴ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 654.

¹²⁹⁵ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi.

¹²⁹⁶ See *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi and Kålund, *KAH* vol. 1, 655-656.

¹²⁹⁷ *KAH* vol. 2, p. 167.

¹²⁹⁸ See *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi and Kålund, *KAH* vol. 2, 167-168, although Boer has the manuscript described as "fol. (cod. oblongus)," whereas it is listed as 4to by Kålund, whom I have followed.

¹²⁹⁹ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi.

¹³⁰⁰ R *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi.

AM 173 I fol., Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (E). AM 173 I fol.,¹³⁰¹ written by Ásgeir Jónsson, is from c. 1700¹³⁰² and *Qrvar-Odds saga* is to be found on 17r-65v. The contents of the manuscript are as follows:

Ketils saga hængs-Gríms saga loðinkinna (1r-16r)
Qrvar-Odds saga (17r-65v)
Áns saga bogsveigis (66r-79v)
Friðþjófs saga (80r-95r)

This manuscript is the best representative of a group of paper manuscripts that have a common exemplar that was close to that of the common exemplar of AB, but that was not identical to it.¹³⁰³ All the manuscripts of this group are rather close in content, as far as the text of *Qrvar-Odds saga* is concerned, and for this reason Boer uses only the text of AM 173 I fol. in his edition, sigla E.¹³⁰⁴ Other manuscripts in this group are: AM 172 b fol. (c. 1700, also written by Ásgeir Jónsson),¹³⁰⁵ and AM 342 I-II 4to (17th century).¹³⁰⁶ Copies of AM 342 4to are: NKS 1791 4to and NKS 1792 4to, and later AM 552 q 4to (18th century).¹³⁰⁷

A portion of this group to which E belongs is found in Stockholm, but they preserve no particularly important textual differences. At the end of the 17th century, one manuscript of this group ended up in Stockholm and was copied; this was probably manuscript Papp. 4to nr 32 of the Royal Library, written in 1676.¹³⁰⁸ The first leaf is missing, but is preserved as Papp. 4to nr 1, also in Stockholm's Royal Library.¹³⁰⁹ From 32 4to come the following: Papp. fol. nr 102 (1687, with readings

¹³⁰¹ AM 173 fol. is made up of two manuscripts; *Qrvar-Odds saga* is in the first part, denoted I. The second part, AM 173 II fol., contains only *Sturlaugs saga Starfsama*, 1r-18v. Boer does not make this distinction in his edition.

¹³⁰² *KAH* vol. 1, p. 142.

¹³⁰³ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi.

¹³⁰⁴ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*.

¹³⁰⁵ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 142.

¹³⁰⁶ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 577.

¹³⁰⁷ So according to Boer; Kälund has 17th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 697.

¹³⁰⁸ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi.

¹³⁰⁹ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi.

from S), Papp. fol. nr 73. (1738, with the readings from S recorded in the text), Papp. 4to nr 56 (1786, with Swedish translation), all in Kungliga biblioteket, Stockholm.¹³¹⁰

Boer shows M to be in some ways to be in between S and ABE, as it often agrees with ABE and then deviates on important points to agree with S.¹³¹¹ Boer's readings demonstrate that MABE form a group against S,¹³¹² and that MABE have a common original that they cannot share with S.¹³¹³

Boer concludes that ABE have interpolations in three places. These correspond to pp. 118-137, 150-152, 186-190 of his 1888 edition.¹³¹⁴ Only the first of these interpolations will be considered here, since the other two do not contain any stanzas.

The first interpolation is at pp. 118.30-137.28 of *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* and contains four stanzas in ABE.¹³¹⁵ This is the section in which Oddr is snatched by a vulture and ends up with giants (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 121.33-34). Then Oddr and his men encounter Qgmundr Eyþjófsbani, who speaks three stanzas (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 135.9-12; 136.5-10). Boer concludes that this whole narrative is "ebenso abgeschmackt wie langweilig" ['just as absurd as it is boring'].¹³¹⁶ This, in addition to his view that this section is more akin to 14th century novels¹³¹⁷ and clashes horribly with the first and previous part of the saga that is rooted in the Viking way of life, and that the way that the interpolation is linked into the saga is clumsy, gives us grounds, Boer concludes, to view this as an addition of a scribe in the second half of the 14th

¹³¹⁰ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vi-vii.

¹³¹¹ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vii.

¹³¹² See *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* vii-xii.

¹³¹³ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* xii.

¹³¹⁴ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* xii.

¹³¹⁵ In fact the beginning of E is a bit different: it is more concise, although Boer does not give the variants to this section in his edition. He suggests that the exemplar of E (or a manuscript further up the manuscript family tree) may have had a leaf missing and scribe in E has added this material from memory. See *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* xiii, fn. 2; xiv, fn. 1.

¹³¹⁶ R. C. Boer, ed., *Qrvar-Odds saga* (Leiden: Brill, 1888) xiii.

¹³¹⁷ Boer sadly does not explain what he means by "den romanen des 14. jahrhunderts."

century.¹³¹⁸ Boer is not very persuasive; his reasons to designate this section an interpolation are very subjective: absurdity can be entertaining, the Viking way of life only supposed, and sagas are frequently stilted in the way that they move between scenes.

Heiðr Makes her Prophecy (SM stt. 1-2, ABE stt. 1-3)

Ingjaldr, Oddr's foster father, invites the *völva* Heiðr to his farm to tell people's destinies. Oddr does not want to be involved, but eventually she spots him lying under a cloak. He tells her that he is not interested in hearing her prophecies, and threatens to bat her on the nose if she starts telling prophecies about him (this frames the episode, as he does hit her when she finishes her prophecy). The threat provokes Heiðr to speak some stanzas: in SM this is two stanzas in a block, in ABE this is three, with an extra stanza before the two appearing in SM. After the stanzas, Heiðr elaborates on her versified prophecy in prose.

	S (not present)	M (not present)
A 1. Ægðu eigi mér, Oddr á Jaðri! eldi skíðu, þótt ýmist geipum; saga mun sannaz sú er segir völvu, Öll veit [hon] manna ørlög fyrir. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 15)	B 1. Ægðu eigi mér, Oddr á Jaðri! eldi skíðu, þótt ýmist geipum; saga mun sannaz sú er segir völvu, Öll veit [hon] ýta ørlög fyrir. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 15)	E 1. Ægðu eigi mér, Oddr á Jaðri! elda skíðu, þótt ýmist geipum; saga mun sannaz sú er segir völvu, Öll veit [hon] manna ørlög fyrir. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 15)

The *völva* shows her powers of sight by knowing Oddr's name and where he is from, although this stanza is more an introduction than a prophecy itself. This may be an important point to note about curse stanzas in eddic verse, since in *Bósa saga*, the curses are in eddic metre but contain the threat of the curses rather than the actual spell. She admits that she talks nonsense sometimes (*þótt ýmist geipum*, v. 4), when accused in the prose above by Oddr. He uses the word *fleiprir* ['you prattle'] to describe her (e.g. *S ok fleiprir ekki um mitt ráð* ['and don't prattle on about my lot'],

¹³¹⁸ R. C. Boer, ed., *Qrvar-Odds saga* (Leiden: Brill, 1888) xiii.

Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 12.21-14.1), except in M, where he uses *geipir*, which is closer to the word used in the verses in ABE, *geipum*, although the verse is not in M. The prose in M continues: *ok geipir eigi neitt um mín forlög*; again in M the prose word *forlög* is closer to the word used in verse 8, *ørlög*. M has likely converted this stanza into prose, shown by the use of the vocabulary of the stanza appearing in prose. This might be because it is not really a part of the prophecy and was felt to be unnecessary or even that it detracted from the force of the prophecy itself.

In the second half of the stanza, the *völva* speaks of herself in the third person. In the prose just before the stanza, she speaks of herself in similar terms to verse 6, *sú er segir vólva* [‘that one that the *völva* says’], when she says *ek skal þat ok segja þér* (MABE)/þar má ek ok frá segja (S); this introduction emphasises the present action of her saying her prophecy in the next two verses.

	S 1. Ferr eige þú svá fjörþo breiða, né líþr yfer *lápa* vága, þó skalt[u] brenna á Berorjóþre. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)	M 1. Ferr þú ei svá fjörþo breiða, né líþr yfer langa vága, þót sær um þik sægjom drífi, Berorjóþre skalt[u] brenna á. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)
A 2. Ferr eige þú svá fjörþo breiða, eða líþr yfer laga vága, þót sær yfir þik sægjom gange, hér skalt[u] brenna á Berorjóþre. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)	B 2. Ferr eige þú svá fjörþo breiða, eða líþr yfer langa vága, þót sær um þik sægjom gange, þó skalt[u] brenna á Berorjóþre. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)	E 2. Ferr eige þú svá fjörþo breiða, eða líþr yfer laga vága, þót sær yfir þik skrikkjum gange, þó skalt[u] brenna á Berorjóþre. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)

The prophecy here is that Oddr will burn (ie. die) in Berurjóðr, where their encounter is taking place, no matter what he does to leave – the implication being that were he to escape successfully, he would avoid death. The image painted of him wandering to avoid Berurjóðr in the stanza is a maritime one. In the prose of all the manuscripts this is interpreted as him going from *land af landi* (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 14.9), and makes concrete the implication of him fruitlessly travelling widely to avoid Berurjóðr: “en aldri ferr þú svá víða, þá skaltu hér deyja á Berurjóðri” (M) (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 14.11-12). In S, despite the *völva* having been elaborating her prophecy to Oddr and referring to him in the second person singular so far, here she suddenly

switches in one instance to the third person: *en aldri ferr hann svá víða, þá skaltu hér deyja á Berurjóðri* (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 15.15-16). This is to introduce a taunting and performative aspect to the prose: speaking of him in the third person means that she is addressing those others present at the prophecy, and by extension, us. Suddenly returning to the second person makes the actual prophecy of Oddr's death more threatening to him, and reflects the final line of the stanza.

	S 2. Naþr mon þik höggva neþan á fõte fránn or fornom Faxe hause. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)	M 2. Naþra mon þik höggva neþan á fõte fránn or fornom Faxe hause. þá ertu fullgamall fylkir orðinn. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)
A 3. Skal þér ormr granda eitr blandinn. fránn or fornom Faxe hause. Naþr mon þik höggva neþan á fõte þá ertu fullgamall fylkir orðinn. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)	B 3. Skal þér ormr tapa eitr blandinn. fránn or fornom Faxe hause. Naþr mon þik höggva neþan á fõte þá ertu fullgamall fylkir orðinn. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)	E 3. Skal þér ormr tapa eitr blandinn. Naþr mon þik höggva á fõte fránn or fornom Faxe hausa. þá þú ert fullgamall fylkir orðinn. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 15)

Here the presence and order of lines can be rather different between the manuscripts .

The two lines of S become three in M, with the addition of a last line shared with ABE. ABE have the two lines in both SM reversed, and the last line common with M added after them. These three lines are preceded in ABE with a first line not found in S or M. This means ABE each have four long lines.

Consequentially, the content of the stanza in E is in reverse. First he must reach his allotted age, then something sharp will come out of Faxi's skull, strike him on the sole of the foot, and turn out to a poisonous snake. The same is true of the stanza in SM, though in E, the beginning of the stanza *skal þér ormr tapa eitr blandinn* narrates the consequences backwards, to make the listener wait for the initial cause. In AB, the reordering of the lines tells the prophecy differently. First an event is described: a snake will come out Faxi's skull. Then, the information that it will strike his foot is given temporal context when it is said it will happen when he has reached the allotted age.

The fact that the snake will come out Faxi's skull is not explained in the prose, nor the fact that it will strike Oddr on the sole of his foot. Therefore the only information in the stanzas in S that is repeated in the prose is that he will die at Berurjóðr after ineffectual travelling (S st. 1). Here the stanzas explain the prose. The additional first line about the snake being poisonous in ABE is also not explained in the prose. The poetic statement in the last line of the stanza in MABE that he will die once he has reached his allotted years is expanded in content in the prose to naming exactly how many these allotted years are: 300 years in MABE and 100 years in S, which does not mention Oddr dying at an allotted age in the stanza. This interpretation in the prose also accommodates travelling far and wide, which takes time, especially by boat. An addition in the prose is that he will be the greatest of men and famous; this is an extrapolation and not in the stanzas.

The stanzas are introduced with similar phrases, represented here by MAB: "Þá varð völlumni ljóð á munni" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 14.6). This is a typical phrase with which to introduce prophetic stanzas spoken by a *völva*.¹³¹⁹ After the quotation of the stanzas, their content is then explained in prose by Heiðr. She begins this explanation in all the versions with "Þat er þér at segja, Oddr!" ["That is to say to you, Oddr"], making it clear she is going to explain.

Oddr Kills Two Giants and Gets His Nickname (SM stt. 3-4, AB stt. 4-5, E st. 4)

These two stanzas (one in E) are at the end of Oddr and his companions' travels to Bjarmaland, Finnmörk and encounters with their inhabitants.¹³²⁰ Driven up the coast of Finnmörk in a great storm, they encounter giants whom Oddr shoots with *Gusisnautar* on several occasions (it is in recounting these fights with giants that Oddr

¹³¹⁹ Judy Quinn, "Ok verðr henni ljóð á munni": Prophetic Verse in the fornaldarsögur', *Alvissmál* 8 (1998): 29-50.

¹³²⁰ Oddr travels with his companion Ásmundr and his kinsmen Guðmundr and Sigurðr. First they go to *Finnmerkr* (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* 24.21-26.9 (M); 25.18-8 (S)) then to Bjarmaland. In Bjarmaland they loot, and sail back to *Finnmerkr* where they harbour in the same place as before (*Qrvar-Odds saga*, ed. Boer, 36.8 (M); 37.11 (S)). A great storm overtakes them and they are forced to toss all the *Finnskrefit* overboard, which all clumps together and shoots off in the sea against the wind (*Qrvar-Odds saga*, ed. Boer, 38.9-13 (M); 39.9-13 (S)).

recites the stanzas), then they sail home to Hrafnista and Grímr loðinkinna (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 40.4-50.10 (M); 41.3-50.8 (S)).

The two stanzas (one in E) go together, but do not form a block in this context. They have a small amount of prose inbetween.

	S 3. Réð ek at ganga með Gusisnauta beggja á mille bjargs ok eiso; laust ek í auga einu flagþe en í brjóst framan bjarga Freyjo. ¹³²¹ (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 49)	M 3. Réð ek at ganga með Gusismíði beggja á mille bjargs ok risu; laust ek í auga einu trølli ok í brjóst framan bjarga Freyjo. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 49)
A 4. Réð ek at ganga með Gusisnauta beggja í millum bjargs ok eiso; laust ek í auga einu flagþe en í brjóst framan bjarga Freyjo. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 49)	B 4. Réð ek at ganga með Gusisnauta beggja á mille bjargs ok esju; laust ek í auga einu flagþe en í brjóst framan bjarga Freyjo. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 49)	E 4. Réð ek at ganga með Gusisnauta beggja á mille bjargs ok eiso; laust ek í auga einu flagþe en í brjóst framan bjarga Freyjo. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i> , 49)

The prompt for the recitation of the first stanza is Guðmundr asking Oddr:

S: “ok fagna þeir Guðmundr þeim vel ok spyrr, hvert þeir hefði farit it lengsta.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 49.6-8)¹³²²

M: “vel fagna þeir Oddi, er fyrir váru. “Hvert vartu it lengsta?” sagði Guðmundr.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 48.6-8)¹³²³

A: “vel fagna þeir bræðr þeim Oddi. “Eða hvert fórtu it lengsta Oddr?” sagði Guðmundr.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 48)¹³²⁴

B: “vel fagna þeir Oddi, er fyrir váru. “Eða hvert fórtu it lengsta Oddr?” sagði Guðmundr.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 48)¹³²⁵

E: “fagna þeir þeim, ok spurði Guðmundr tíðinda, hvat borit hafði til í ferðum þeira” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 48)¹³²⁶

¹³²¹ [‘I did go with Gusi’s arrows (M: Gusi’s work) between both the sea cliff and glowing embers (M: giant); I hit an ogress (M: a troll) in the eye and a rock-lady in the front of the chest.’]

¹³²² [‘and Guðmundr and his men welcome them with good cheer, and [he] asks where was the farthest they had been’]

¹³²³ [‘They greeted Oddr, who was in the lead, with good cheer. “Where was the farthest you went?” said Guðmundr.’]

¹³²⁴ [‘the brothers greeted Oddr with good cheer. “But where was the farthest you went, Oddr?” said Guðmundr.’]

¹³²⁵ [‘they greeted Oddr, who was in the lead, with good cheer. “But where was the farthest you went, Oddr?” said Guðmundr.’]

¹³²⁶ [‘they greet them, and Guðmundr asked the news, what they had to report of their journey’]

The stanza is thus not an direct reply to the question, except in the case of E, in which Guðmundr asks for news of the happenings in their journey, rather than enquiring about distance or similar. Instead of giving a location, it simply tells that they met supernatural creatures, leaving this to imply they went a long way from home.

The stanza in SABE tells that the speaker kills two giantesses between the glowing embers of a fire and a rock or sea cliff. In M, the speaker kills a troll and a giantess between a giant and a rock/sea cliff. This reflects a negotiation between the prose story and the stanza.

In SABE, the third line about shooting a giantess in the eye refers to a giantess sent to break their boats and is narrated thus:

M – shoots a giantess “hon bregðr við lófanum, ok flýgr í gegnum lófann ok í auga henna ok kom út um hnakkann, ... en hann skýtr annarri ǫr, ok bregðr hon upp ǫðrum lófa, ok ferr sem it sama.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 42.15-19)

S – shoots Gneip, a giantess “hon bregðr við hendinni, en orin fló í gegnum lófann ok aprt í augat ok út um hnakkann ok aprt á streng. ... Oddr skýtr nú í annat sinn Gusisnaut, ok ferr á sǫmu leið” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 45.3-6)

A – shoots a giantess “hon bregðr fyrir ǫðrum lófanum, ok flýgr í gegnum hann ok í auga henna ok út um hnakkann, ... en hann skýtr þriðju ǫr, ok bregðr hon við ǫðrum lófa ok hrækti í hann áðr, ok sú jafnt ok hin fyrri at í augat kom ok út um hnakkann.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 42.15-19)

B – shoots a giantess “hon bregðr við ǫðrum lófanum, ok flýgr í gegnum hann ok í auga henna ok út um hnakkann, ... en hann skýtr þriðju ǫr, ok bregðr hon við ǫðrum lófa, ok ferr sú jafnt ok hin fyrri.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 42.15-19)

E – shoots a giantess “hon bregðr við ǫðrum lófanum, ok flýgr í gegnum lófann ok í auga henna ok út um hnakkann, ... en hann skýtr þriðju ǫr, ok bregðr hon við ǫðrum lófa, ok ferr sú jafnt ok sem hin fyrri.” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 42.15-19)

Line 2 in the stanza from M says that Gusi’s arrows go between a sea cliff and a giant, rather than a sea cliff and glowing embers in SABE. In the prose of M the arrow does not obviously go between a giant and a rock face, unless it is referring to the arrow missing him as he throws himself up against the rock to get out of the way: “þá bregðr hann við ok tekr sik upp á bjargit” (48.1-2), but the arrow instead hits a woman, as referred to in line four of the stanza. In the stanza from E, a female is hit in the chest with an arrow, but in the prose of E it is the male giant that is hit. In all the manuscripts, the prose interpretation of the stanza thus refers to events that are somewhat distant to each other in time and place; the stanza itself might more imply that both the female troll women were shot on the same occasion, especially given that

the second line about embers of a fire being present seems to refer to both the killings. This stanza is also in *Qrvar-Odds ævidrápa* as stanza 21.

In the body of the saga, the stanza is linked to the second by a request for more news (48.9-11 (M); 49.13-14 (S), although it is mostly illegible in the manuscript). This has nothing to do with the narrative content of the verses and is probably the same age as the rest of the saga prose rather than being part of an ‘original’ versiprose complex with the stanzas. A more typical way to have linked the verses would have been a formula such as “and yet he said,” which is widely found over the corpus.

	S 4. Þá fekk ek heite þatz [ek] vilda, es mik ór fjöllum flogþ kolloþo; kvóþosk Odde Qrvar vilja byr bráþlega í braut gefa. ¹³²⁷ (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 49)	M 4. Þá fekk ek heite þat er [ek] vilda, es mik í björgum flogþ kolloþo; kvóþosk Qrvar-Oddi vilja byr gefa mjök bráðliga í braut heðan. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 49)
A 5. Þar fekk ek heite þat hafa vildak, es mik ór fjöllum flogþ kolloþo; kvóþosk Odde Qrvar skyldu byr bráþlega í braut gefa. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 49)	B 5. Þar fekk ek heite þat [ek] vilda, es mik ór fjöllum flogþ kolloþo; kvóþosk Qrvar-Oddi vilja byr bráþlega í braut gefa. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 49)	E (not present)

The incident that this stanza reports happens in the prose in amongst the events in the prose that the stanza before mentions. Between shooting the giantess in the eye and another in the breast, the chief of the giants’ sees Oddr and his arrows with his second sight:

M: “Þat sé ek ok, at Oddr hefir qrvar þrjár, þær kalla þeir Gúsisnauta, ok mun ek gefa honum nafn ok kalla hann Qrvar-Odd.” (46.20-22).

S: “en fyrir þat er Oddr hefir skotit Gneip, dóttur mina, með Gúsisnautum, þá mun ek honum nafn gefa ok kalla hann Qrvar-Odd.” (47.24-26)

ABE: “Þat sé ek ok, at Oddr hefir qrvar þær er kallaðar eru Gúsisnauta, ok (+ því AE) mun ek gefa honum nafn ok kalla hann Qrvar-Odd.” (46).

¹³²⁷ [‘Then I got a name, that which I wanted, which giantesses called me out of a mountain. They said of themselves to want to get a sudden fair wind for Qrvar-Oddr.’]

In the stanzas however, it is *flagð*, female giantesses that give him his name. The *Lexicon Poeticum* states this is the only place where the word is used of a male monster,¹³²⁸ but there is no need to accept that the name giver in the stanza must be male when every other recorded instance of the *flagð* refers to a female. The name giving is connected (most closely in S) with Oddr shooting giantesses, so it is not unreasonable to think that at one point giantesses from their cave were thought of as giving him his name.

Oddr being given a fair wind to sail away is recounted three times:

- 1) Prose: Said by the chief of the giants, who would like to kill Oddr but who knows he is fated to live a long time, and so wants to give him a fair wind to get rid of him.
- 2) Verse: Said by giantesses in speech reported by Oddr, probably to get rid of him so that he will stop shooting them.
- 3) Prose: Said by Oddr, expanding on the stanza.

The stanza (2) blends in with (3) since both are spoken by Oddr, in a complex blending of direct and indirect speech. That the fair wind recounted in (2) is missing in E is unproblematic for the story, since it is still said by the giant previously in the prose and so we know when Oddr says that they are promised a fair wind who has promised it.

The prose following the second stanza puts the events of the second stanza into the immediate present, and contextualises the occurrences of the second stanza so that they could not have happened very far back in narrative time – the stanza says they have been promised a wind, and the prose makes it clear this will happen immediately. The sequence of events in the prose in comparison to the stanzas is thus muddled.

The order of events in the two stanzas is thus:

- Oddr shoots *Gusisnautar* between the rock (presumably in a cave) and embers.

¹³²⁸ “Flagð,” *Lexicon poeticum antiquae linguae septentrionalis*, ed. Sveinbjörn Egilsson and Finnur Jónsson, 2nd ed. (København: Lyng & søn, 1931).

- He shoots a giantess in the eye.
- He shoots a giantess in the chest.
- He gets his name, from giantesses out of a mountain (cave).
- They promise him a fair wind.

The order of events in the prose is thus:

- He shoots a giantess in the eye.
- He gets his name, from a giant in a cave.
- He gives him a fair wind.
- Oddr shoots an arrow and the giant throws himself up against a rock.
- He shoots a giantesses in the chest.

The stanzas provide a more female-centred story than the prose, and they have events happening closer together in time. This stanza is also the 22nd stanza of the *ævidrápa*.

The introduction to stanza three is fairly unremarkable; the stanza is simply introduced as a speech stanza, for example: “Þá kvað Oddr” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 48.8; 49.8) The introduction to stanza four however is more unusual. In M, the prose simply says “Nafn var mér gefit” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 48.11) and then the stanza follows. This complete lack of introduction to a stanza is rather rare in the *fornaldarsaga* corpus. In S, this is avoided with the addition of “ok þá kvað hann” to the line in M (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 49.14), and in AB, the prose is explicit that he will recite a verse: “Nafn var mér gefit” sagði Oddr ok kvað vísu” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 48).

The Death of Ásmundr (SME st. 5, AB st. 6, C st. 1)

Oddr and Ásmundr go to Ireland harrying. A lone arrow kills Ásmundr and he dies immediately. The stanza is spoken as he recounts what happened to Hjálmar.

<p>C. 1 Rann ek aa víþre vagnslod gøtu, áþr strengvølum stríþom møttak; munda ek Ásmund auþe mínom aptr ódáenn øllom kaupaa. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 77.10-13)</p>	<p>S. 5 Fann ek at víþre vagns sløþgøtu, áþr ek strengvølum stríþom møttak; munda ek Ásmund auþe mínom aptr ódáenn øllom kaupaa.¹³²⁹ (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 77.10-13)</p>	<p>M. 5 Rann ek at víþre vegnslods gøtu, unz ek stronghvelum stríþom møttak; munda ek Ásmund auþe mínom aptr ódáenn øllom kaupaa. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 77.10-13)</p>
<p>A. 6 Rann ek at víþre vagnslod gøtu, áþr en strengvølum stríþom møttak; munda ek Ásmund auþe mínom aptr ódáenn øllom kaupaa. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 77.10-13)</p>	<p>B. 6 Rann ek at víþre vagnslod gøtu, áþr strengvølum stríþom møttak; munda ek Ásmund auþe mínom aptr ódáenn øllom kaupaa. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 77.10-13)</p>	<p>E. 5 Fann ek at víþre vagnstod gøtu, áþr strengvølum stríþom møttak munda ek Ásmund auþe mínom aptr ódáenn øllom kaupaa.¹³³⁰ (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 77.10-13)</p>

This stanza is spoken by Oddr in response to Hjálmarrr's question:

S: "Hjálmarrr spyrr nú, hversu at bæriz um líflát Ásmundar, eða hvárt Oddr hefði nøkkut hefnt hans. Oddr kvað þá" (77. 7-9)¹³³¹
 ABCEM: "“Hefir þú nøkkut hefnt Ásmundar?” segir Hjálmarrr.” (76.10-11)¹³³²

In his stanza in reply to this question, Oddr implies that he has not avenged Ásmundr, and was forced to flee in the face of a volley of arrows. This is not so in the prose, where just a single arrow flies out of the forest and kills Ásmundr (70.14-16; 71.15-18). Incensed, Oddr then finds people in a large clearing and kills four men. The stanza and the prose thus do not correlate. The prose after the stanza frames the question with Hjálmarrr's assumption that Oddr will want to harry, burn everything and kill everyone in revenge, but he does not (76.12-14; 77.14-15). Instead, the situation in the prose provides the explanation that after having killed four men in a rage, he goes underground into a *jarðhús* and tries to take away the most beautiful of the women (of

¹³²⁹ [“I ran along (SE I found) the wide wagon-path way, before I met adversity before arrows; I would buy Ásmundr back alive with all my wealth.”]

¹³³⁰ Boer on p. 77 of *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* states in the apparatus for this stanza that *strengvølum* – *Ásmund* is omitted in E; it is not. He also has E as beginning with *Rann ek*, when it starts with *fann ek* (although in the *avídrápa* in E, the stanza does indeed begin with *rann ek*).

¹³³¹ [“Hjálmarrr asks now, how the loss of Ásmundr's life happened, or whether Oddr had avenged him at all.”]

¹³³² [““Have you avenged him at all?” says Hjálmarrr.”]

which there are seven in S, three in M and four in ABCE!). After insulting her by calling her a *tröll* (in MABCE, in S he does not), she bargains her way out of being taken by force by Oddr by promising a shirt with extraordinary qualities; although the realisation of this promise comes after the verse announcing the death of Ásmundr. This means that the saga author had a clear plan for this section of the saga that expanded the content of the verses, because the stanzas surrounding the delivery of the shirt give extra information about it. Nevertheless, the stanzas reporting Oddr's conversation with Qlvor about the shirt seem to belong to a different theme than the death of Ásmundr, and they have been brought together into the same episode by the saga author. This stanza is also stanza 38 of the *avidrápa*.

In MABCE the stanza is introduced with “Þá verðr Oddi ljóð á munni” but in S there is simply “Oddr kvað þá” (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, 77), perhaps in avoidance of using a tag traditionally associated with female magic on a male character.

The Encounter with Qlvor (SM E st. 6-7, AB st. 7-8, C st. 2-3)

The stanza spoken by Qlvor (SME 6, AB 7, C 2) is in response to Oddr's question as to whether she has made the shirt herself, and Oddr's stanza (SME 7, AB 8, C 3), spoken directly after hers, seems to be the source of some of the properties Qlvor had earlier promised.

The peoples who have contributed to making shirt seem to have a supernatural or practical air to them:

<p>C. Serk fra ék ór silfri í sjau stöðum gørvan: ermr á Íralande, qnnor norþr meþ Finnom, slógo Saxa meyjar, en supreyskar spunno, vófo Valskar dróser, varp Óþjóþans móþer.¹³³³ (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, p. 81)</p>	<p>S. Serk of fra ék ór silke í sjau stöðum gørvan: ermr var á Íralande, qnnor norþr meþ Finnom, slógo Saxa meyjar, en supreyskar spunno, vófo Valskar dróser, varp Óþjóþans móþer. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, p. 81)</p>	<p>M. Serk hefi ek hér ór silfri ok í sex stöðum gørvan: ermr var á Íralande, qnnor norþr meþ Finnom, slógo Saxa meyjar, en supreyskar spunno, vófo Valskar dróser, varp Óþjóþans móþer. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, p. 81)</p>
<p>A. Serkinn fra ék í Sogni ok í sjau stöðum gørvan: ermr á Íralande, qnnor norþr meþ Finnom, slógo Saxa meyjar, en supreyskar spunno, vófo Valskar brúðir, varp Óþjóþans móþer. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, p. 81)</p>	<p>B. Serkinn fra ék ór silfri ok í sjau stöðum gørvan: ermr var á Íralande, qnnor norþr meþ Finnom, slógo Saxa meyjar, en supreyskar spunno, vófo Valskar brúðir, varp óþjóþins móþer. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, p. 81)</p>	<p>E. Serkinn fra ék ór silfri í Sogni ok sjau hlutum gørvan: ermr var á Íralande, qnnor norþr meþ Finnom, slógo Saxa meyjar, en supreyskar spunno, vófo Valskar dróser, varp Óþjóþans móþer. (Qrvar-Odds saga 1888, p. 81)</p>

The differences between the stanzas likely stem from different author's desires to make the stanza internally consistent. In CS we find the shirt to be made out in seven different places, presumably Ireland, amongst the Finns, the Saxons, the Hebrideans, the Welsh and we could add by Qlvor herself – meaning one place is lacking, although this could be where the *Óþjóþans móþer* is located in the last line. In M, it says only six places, as listed and presumably counting Qlvor. In A, it says seven places and Sogn is present in the first line to make up seven places, six actually mentioned in the stanza and counting Qlvor. B too has seven places of manufacture of the shirt, but perhaps lists another place, where the *óþjóð* of the last line dwell. In E, although it is mentioned that the shirt is made in Sogn, the number of places does not appear and instead we find it is made out of seven things, which, including the silver mentioned in the first line, adds up.

¹³³³ [‘I learnt (M I have) a shirt (AB the shirt) out of silver (S silk; A in Sogn) / in seven (M six) places was made: / an arm in Ireland (SMBE one arm was in Ireland) / another north with the Finns, / Saxon maids struck it up / but Hebrideans spun [it], / Welsh maids (AB brides) wove [it] / [on] Óþjóðan’s mother’s (B on the mother of the evil people’s) warp.’] Note the first two lines in E are: [‘I learnt the shirt out of silver and seven things in Sogn to be made.’]

It seems this stanza was the source of physical description the shirt when Ólvor promises it to Oddr, and MS have in the prose the shirt was made out of silk and sewn with gold, while ABCE have that the shirt was made out of silver and sewed with gold (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 74.11, 75.5).

Despite M saying the shirt was made out of silk in the prose, the verse still has that the shirt was made out of silver (likely because of its protective qualities Ólvor mentions, see p.74.14-17 and p. 75.7-10), and this stanza does not mention the shirt was golden stitched – this information is from the next stanza, spoken by Oddr:

<p>C. Varat sem brynja eða bláer hringar ísköld um mik áþan felle, þá er um síþor silkeskyrta golle saumoþ gekk fast ofan. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 81)</p>	<p>S. Vasa sem brynja eða bláer hringar ísköld um mik áþan felle, þá er of síþor silkeskyrta golle saumoþ gekk fast ofan. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 81.23-26)</p>	<p>M. Vasa sem brynja eða bláer hringar verðr köld um mik áþan felle, þá er um síþor silkeskyrta golle saumoþ gekk fast ofan. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 81)</p>
<p>A. Varat sem brynja eða bláer hringar ísköld um mik ofan felle, þá er um síþor silkeskyrta golle saumoþ gekk fast ofin. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 81)</p>	<p>B. Varat sem brynja eða bláer hringar ísköld um mik áþan felle, þá er um síþor silkeskyrta golle saumoþ gekk fast ofan. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 81)</p>	<p>E. Var sem brynja eða bláer hringar ísköld um mik allan felle, þó er ei síþor silkeskyrta golle saumoþ grimdar fast ofin. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 81)</p>

Here the stanzas are consistent in statement that the shirt was of silk and embroidered with gold. SMABC agree, but E has a rather different interpretation of the qualities of the shirt as it sits on Oddr's body. SMABC emphasise how the shirt is not cold like wearing a byrnie or mail-coat, since we can imagine the silk is soft on Oddr's skin. However, in E, the stanza fits literally with Ólvor's statement that the shirt is made out of silver, and in Oddr's stanza, since the shirt is as cold as wearing armour (since it is made of silver, we can presume), but the difference is that the shirt does not chafe as armour might. In E we thus find a scribe concerned with making the story consistent, since it also agrees with prose statement in E about the shirt being made out of silver. Again the stanza is introduced with "þa varð Oddi ok ljóð á munni" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 81.23). The stanza is stanza 41 of the *ævidrápa*.

Angantýr and His Brothers (ME stt. 8-15, AB stt. 9-16)

These stanzas are in MABE (the fragment C does not extend as far as this stanza and this episode falls in a gap in S). This episode is the introduction to the death of Hjálmar, and it describes the arrival of the berserker group of brothers, headed by Angantýr. This saga episode seems built around the verses.

M. Hervaþr ok Hjorvarþr, Hrane ok Angantýr, Bildr ok Bofi, Barr ok Taki, Tindr ok Tyrfingr, tveir Haddingjar, þeir er í Bolm austr fœddir vóro, Arngríms syner ok Eyfuro. (Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888, 97)	A. Hervaþr ok Hjorvarþr, Hrane, Angantýr, Bildr ok Bagi, Barre ok Tóke, Tindr ok Tyrfingr, tveir Haddingjar, þeir í Bolm austr borner vóro, Arngríms syner ok Eyfuro. (Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888, 97)
B. Hervaþr ok Hjorvarþr, Hrane ok Angantýr, Bildr ok Bagi, Berri ok Tóke, Tindr ok Tyrfingr, tveir Haddingjar, þeir í Bolm austr borner vóro, Arngríms syner ok Eyfuro. (Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888, 97)	E. Hervaþr ok Hjorvarþr, Hrane, Angantýr, Bildr ok Bragi, Bolverkr ok Tóke, Tindr ok Tyrfingr, tveir Haddingjar, þeir eru í Bar austr borner vestir, Arngríms syner ok Eyfuro. (Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888, 97)

The divergences in the manuscripts likely indicate the names of Angantýr's brothers were somewhat fluid and there seems no need to posit a name that is not present in any of the manuscripts. This stanza fits with the prose in naming twelve brothers, as asserted by both the narrator (*Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 96.7-8), Angantýr (*Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 97.12-13) before the stanza and the brothers after the stanzas (*Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 100.2-3), and that they are the children of Arngrímr and Eufura, claimed by the brothers after the stanzas (*Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 100.3). In the stanza they are said to have been raised in to the east in Bólm, and in the prose after the stanzas the brother say themselves to be from *Flæmingjaland* (*Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 100.3-4). The two *Haddingjar* are also mentioned in the prose story both by Angantýr (*Ǫrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 100.18) and the narrator (p.101.11), but none of the other brothers are mentioned again.

The second verse spoken by Hjálmar runs straight on from the above:

<p>M. Þá frá ek manna meinúþgasta, ógjarnasta got at vinna; þeir berserker þols of fylder tvau skip hruþo tryggra manna.¹³³⁴ (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 98.1-4)</p>	<p>A. Þá frá ek manna meinúþgasta, ok ugjarnasta got at vinna; þeir eru berserks þols of fylder tvau skip hruþo tryggra manna.</p>
<p>B. Þá frá ek manna meinúþgasta, ógjarnasta got at vinna; þeir eru berserks þols of fylder tvau skip hruþo tryggra manna.</p>	<p>E. Þá frá ek manna meinúþgasta, ok ugjarnasta got at vinna; þeir eru berserks þole of uppfylDIR tvau skip hruþo tryggra manna.</p>

From this verse it seems that Hjálmar and Oddr have a vantage over the ships and can see what has happened to their men, since it says at the beginning of the episode in the prose that Oddr and Hjálmar have two ships that the berserkers storm and kill everyone onboard (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 94.22, 96.9-10). As Hjálmar uses this stanza to explain to Oddr why he feels strange and can hear odd noises (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 97.9-12), we can imagine that this is the point when Hjálmar sees what is happening at the coast (this makes Oddr's later question, "Hafi þér nokkut komit til skipa várra?" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 100.8), somewhat disingenuous, and it was probably added for comic effect). The evil nature of the berserks emphasised in the stanza is born out by their killing of everyone on the ships and their eagerness to fight Oddr and Hjálmar, but the assertion that they are dishonest at fighting is not borne out in the prose; indeed it is Angantýr who suggest that all should be buried honourably with their weapons (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 101.5-9) and when he is killed by Hjálmar there is no suggestion of a dishonest fight. These two verses are introduced by "Þá varð Hjálmarljóð á munni" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 97.13-14).

¹³³⁴ These I learnt of, most malignant of men, / (AE and) most unwilling to win honestly / those (ABE are) berserkers, fulfillers of misfortune (E misfortune fulfillers) / they disabled two ships of trusty men.

Oddr replies to Hjálmar's stanzas and it says in the prose before it that he could now see the berserkers approaching (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 98.5):

<p>M. Menn sé ek ganga frá Munarvógom gunnar gjarna í gróm serkjom; þeir hafa reiþer rómo háþa, ero okkor skip auþ á ströndo.¹³³⁵ (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 98.7-10)</p>	<p>A. Menn sé ek ganga frá Munarvógom gunnar gjarna í gróm serkjom; þeir hafa reiþer rómo háþa, ero okkor skip auþ á ströndo. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 98.7-10)</p>
<p>B. Menn sé ek ganga frá Munarvógom gunnar gjarna í gróm serkjom; þeir hafa reiþer rómo háþa, ero okkor skip auþ á ströndo. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 98.7-10)</p>	<p>E. Menn sé ek ganga frá minni vágum gunnar gjarna í gróm serkjom; þeir hafa reiþer rómo háþa, ero okkor skip á ströndo niðri. (<i>Qrvar-Odds saga 1888</i>, 98.7-10)</p>

The sense in E is more dramatic than in the other three versions, since the author leaves the audience to infer that all the crew will have been killed, rather than stating it directly in the last line of MAB. The prose introducing the stanza is not needed, since it is then stated twice that Oddr can see the attackers approaching; the stanza matches with the prose earlier in the episode when it says that the berserkers have killed everyone onboard the two ships. The vicious nature of the attackers is alluded to again in the third line of the stanza; the prose interprets the brothers being vicious as them being berserkers (p.98.5, for example), because it is never stated that the brothers are berserks in the verse. Again the stanza is introduced with "...ok varð honum ljóð á munni" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 98.5-6).

The fourth stanza in the sequence is also spoken by Oddr and is introduced with (M): "ok þá kvað hann stuku þessa" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 98.13), which is a little more unusual. There is little intervening prose between stanzas to compare the contents of the stanzas with. The fifth stanza is spoken by Hjálmar in ABE but by Oddr in M (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 99). Although in this particular context this makes little sense, when you look at the verse that comes next in the exchange, the sixth stanza, it is introduced with "Þá segir Oddr enn svá" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 99.5). Such a tag is only ever used in other *fornaldarsögur* when the same character speaks more than one

¹³³⁵ I see men walking from Munarvágur (E the bay-mouth) / most eager for battle in grey shirts (ie. corslets); / they have angrily fought a battle / our ships are empty on [the] beach (E our ships are on [the] beach below).

verse. This line is placed after the first stanza and before the remainder of the speech. It seems that in M then Oddr really was the intended speaker, and that “Þá segir Oddr enn svá” is a little out of place in the other redactions. The seventh stanza has rather unusual introduction: “Angantýr, svá sem hann kemur, verður honum þegar ljóð á munni, ok hefir heyrtr hann ok þótti kenna æðru nokkut” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 9.11-13) In this case, the narrator reflects upon the content of the verse before it has been spoken, demonstrating his omniscience. The exchange before they fight ends with a speech stanza by Oddr.

There is little prose between the stanzas, and what there is simply introduces the name of the speaker; this might indeed be unclear, especially to differentiate what is meant to be spoken by Oddr and what is meant to be spoken by Hjálmar. This section was likely once a poem in its own right, this is confirmed by the presence of some of the verses in manuscript R of *Hervarar saga* which also includes a version of this episode.

Hjálmar's Death Song

I have analysed the prosimetric structure of Hjálmar's death song in my discussion of *Hervarar saga*. Here I intend to focus on the differences between the versions in the two sagas. The two sagas have different stanzas and in different orders.

One of Oddr's companions during his long life, the hero Hjálmar, dies from battle wounds, and during his slow death also composes a death song of around 10 stanzas. In their contexts within the prose of the legendary sagas, these autobiographical poems provide an opportunity for personalised review in the first person, whereas the prose surrounding them provides a third person reconstruction of prehistory.¹³³⁶ The

¹³³⁶ Margaret Clunies Ross, “Poetry and *Fornaldarsögur*,” *The Fantastic in Old Norse/Icelandic Literature. Sagas and the British Isles. Preprint Papers of The Thirteenth International Saga Conference Durham and York 6th-12th August, 2006*, ed. John McKinnell, David Ashurst and Donata Kick (Durham: The Centre for Medieval and Renaissance Studies, Durham University, 1996), pp. 180-187 at p. 182. Cf. Lars Lönnroth: “...the Norsemen pushed the separation between factual narration and dramatic exhortation a step further by letting the saga prose take care of the former while reserving poetry for the latter,” “Hjálmar's Death-Song and the Delivery of Eddic Poetry,” *Speculum*, 46 (1971), 1-20 (p. 8).

prose also provides us with narrative justification for including poems with such a shift of perspective, from third person narration to versified speech in first person, although it could be noted that the circumstances for recording the two death songs differ in their emphasis.

Hjálmar's death song is in many ways atypical, since major concerns of the poem are instructions for the present and remarks about the future after his death, in which he cannot share.¹³³⁷ The several proclamations of his own heroism are unsurprising, but distinctive in that he wishes to preserve his reputation in order that the women at home will not laugh at him, rather than any pressing need to preserve his heroic reputation more perpetually. This is somewhat surprising, since a good reputation, and its maintenance after long death, is often considered to be one of the pillars of the heroic mentality, as exemplified by *Hávamál*:

76. Deyr fé,
deyja frændr,
deyr sjálfr it sama;
en orðstírr
deyr aldregi
hveim er sér góðan getr.

77. Deyr fé
deyja frændr,
deyr sjálfr it sama;
ek veit einn
at aldri deyr:
dómr um dauðan hvern.¹³³⁸

[76. Cattle die, kinsmen die,
oneself dies just the same.
But words of glory never die
for the one who gets a good name.

77. Cattle die, kinsmen die,
oneself dies just the same.
I know one thing that never dies:
the judgment on each one dead.]¹³³⁹

¹³³⁷ For an approach that isolates the main components of the general Germanic death song tradition, see Joseph Harris, "Beowulf's Last Words," *Speculum*, 67 (1992), 1-32. He identifies eight or nine shared motifs that are common to the death song tradition as a whole; my approach differs in that I am concerned with the consequences of the varying emphases placed on some of these motifs.

¹³³⁸ *Hávamál*, ed. D. H. Evans, Text Series, 7 (London: Viking Society for Northern Research, 1986) p. 54.

As such, those who exemplify the heroic life are those remembered, but this also indicates that memories of less valouress deeds would also remain.¹³⁴⁰ During his death in *Qrvar-Odds saga*, Hjalmar actually has three bouts of autobiographical poetry:¹³⁴¹

¹³³⁹ The English translation is taken from *The Elder Edda: A Book of Viking Lore*, trans. Andy Orchard (London: Penguin, 2011), p. 25.

¹³⁴⁰ "If death songs have little purchase on the future, they nevertheless instil in audiences a remembrance of those who, at least in Germanic literature, had exemplified the heroic life." Eugene Green, *Anglo-Saxon Audiences*, Berkeley Insights in Linguistics and Semiotics, 44 (New York: Peter Lang, 2001) p. 118.

¹³⁴¹ Cf. *Saga Heiðreks Konungs in Vitra. The Saga of King Heidrek the Wise*, ed. Tolkien, p. 74.

The Prose-Verse Complex of Hjálmar's Death Scene in *Örvar-Odds saga*

1	Prose	Hjálmar sinks down on a knoll, and Oddr goes over.
2	Stanza 1	Oddr says Hjálmar is dying.
3	Prose	Oddr says Hjálmar should not have fought against Angantýr.
4	Prose	Hjálmar says that everyone must die.
5	Stanza 2	Hjálmar tells that he is grievously wounded.
6	Prose	Oddr says that losing Hjálmar is a great loss and would not have happened had Oddr had his own way.
7	Prose	Hjálmar tells Oddr to sit down and Hjálmar will compose a poem to send home to Sweden.
8	Stanzas 3 to 10	Hjálmar's death song.
9	Prose	Hjálmar wants greetings carried to all of his bench-fellows.
10	Stanzas 11 to 15	Hjálmar names all his bench-fellows.
11	Prose	- Hjálmar asks not to be buried with the berserkers, and Oddr agrees. - Hjálmar tells Oddr to pull off his armring to give to Ingibjörg and to tell her he sent it on his dying day.
12	Stanzas 16 and 17	Hjálmar says that men drink with the king and are weakened by ale, but his wounds weaken him; a raven and an eagle are flying in, and he will provide flesh for the eagle.

In terms of verse, we find one stanza from Hjálmarrr informing the saga's main protagonist Oddr that his wounds are serious; then Hjálmarrr's death song proper, followed by a metrical list of more or less anyone he's ever had a drink with, then two additional stanzas also referring to his current mutilated state in which he compares his situation as he lies weak and helpless with his friends becoming weak from beer in a hall elsewhere:

“Drekr með jöfre jarla mēge
 ǫl glaþlega at Uppsolum;
 MAþer marga mungát fira,
 en mik eggja spor í eyjo þjá.”¹³⁴²

[‘A multitude of jarls drink ale cheerfully with the king at Uppsala. Many a man weakens at ale, but traces from [a sharp] edge torment me on an island.]

This stanza is typical of the introductory and concluding stanzas outside of the death song, which all deal with his wounds rather with than autobiography as such, but still this peripheral poetry is integrated into the delivery of his death song proper by drawing out the same themes of beer drinking and chatter in the king's hall. Although not part of the death song proper, it functions to frame his personalised retrospective with present concerns and also works to integrate the prose utterances and the verse more closely, since the prose, aside from Oddr's self-righteous comments, also reasserts more clearly that Hjálmarrr is in the process of dying.¹³⁴³

Hjálmarrr's death song itself focuses mainly on his relationship with his sweetheart Ingibjörg, whom he will never see again, and the possible gossip about him at home:

The Matter of Hjálmarrr's Death Song in *Örvar-Odds saga*

Stanza one: The women will have no reason to think him a coward.
 Stanza two: I went off in a warband with Soti, away from the beautiful songs of women.
 Stanza three: The king's daughter led me to Agnafit and prophesised I would not return.
 Stanza four: I disappeared from Ingibjörg; she will be upset that we will not see each other again.

¹³⁴² *Örvar-Odds saga*, ed. R. C. Boer, Altnordische Saga-Bibliothek, 2 (Niemeyer, 1892) p. 59.

¹³⁴³ Harris has also expressed caution about taking the “contiguous material” with Beowulf's death song as part of the death song proper, “Beowulf's Last Words,” p. 10.

Stanza five: Carry my mailcoat and helmet to the king's hall; the king's daughter will be moved when she sees it.

Stanza six: I owned five farms but was not content; now I lie powerless and wounded on Sámsey.

Stanza seven: Pull off my arming and give it to Ingibjörg; she will be upset that we will not see each other again.

Stanza eight: I can see where the ladies sit in Sigtúna; I'll never drink ale in the hall again.

Hjálmar's death song is also told in *Hervarar saga*, which exists in three main redactions: R (Gks 2845 4to, Royal Library Copenhagen, late 14th to early 15th c.), U (R:715, University Library of Uppsala, mid 17th c.) and H (Hauksbók, AM 544 4to, early 14th c.).¹³⁴⁴ In terms of Hjálmar's death song, the chief differences between the redactions R and U lies in stanza order,¹³⁴⁵ and in manuscript H the saga text does not contain the story, and simply makes reference to *Qrvar-Odds saga: sva sem greinir i Orvarodz sogv*¹³⁴⁶ ['as recorded in *Qrvar-Odds saga*'], although it is not clear that the H version does make any reference to their being a poem involved in Hjálmar's death; it simply narrates that *Hialmarr drap Aganty ok do þar síðan af sarvm*¹³⁴⁷ ['Hjálmar killed Angantýr and died there afterwards of wounds']. As Lönnroth and Alaric Hall have both noted, the changes the poem displays between *Qrvar-Odds saga* and *Hervarar saga* the two sagas must be the result of the poems' independent recording from oral tradition.¹³⁴⁸ *Qrvar-Odds saga* has four extra stanzas in comparison to the poem preserved in *Hervarar saga*, and their comparative reordering from above is as follows:

The Matter of Hjálmar's Death Song in *Hervarar saga*

1. [External stanza in *Qrvar-Odds saga* where Hjálmar says he is grievously wounded.]
2. Stanza six: I owned five farms but was not content; now I lie powerless and wounded on Sámsey.

¹³⁴⁴ For a fuller description of the manuscripts, their relationships to one another and variant patterns, see *Saga Heiðreks konungs*, pp. ix-x and xxix-xxxi and Alaric Hall, "Changing Style and Changing Meaning: Icelandic Historiography and the Medieval Redactions of *Heiðreks saga*," *Scandinavian Studies*, 77 (2005), 1-30 for the most recent attempt at a stemma. See particularly p. 19 for a discussion of the verse tradition of redactions R, H and U.

¹³⁴⁵ See *Saga Heiðreks konungs*, pp. 7-9 for textual variants between R and U.

¹³⁴⁶ *Hauksbók* (København: Thieles, 1892-96) p. 353. I have silently expanded the abbreviations that are marked in the edition.

¹³⁴⁷ *Hauksbók*, p. 353.

¹³⁴⁸ Lönnroth, "Hjálmar's Death-Song," p. 10; Alaric Hall, "Changing Style and Changing Meaning," p. 6.

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3. [External stanza in *Örvar-Odds saga* where Hjálmar says that men drink in his father's hall, and that men are weakened by ale but his wounds weaken him.]
 4. Stanza three: The king's daughter led me to Agnafit and prophesied I would not return.
 5. Stanza seven: Pull off my armring and give it to Ingibjörg; she will be upset that we will not see each other again.
 6. Stanza two: I went off in a warband with Soti, away from the beautiful songs of women.¹³⁴⁹
 7. [External stanza in *Örvar-Odds saga* where he says a raven and eagle are flying in and he provides flesh for the eagle.]¹³⁵⁰

In *Hervarar saga*, Hjálmar's first peripheral stanza in *Örvar-Odds saga* describing his wounds is brought into the death song proper, although between that verse and those which form the death song of *Örvar-Odds saga* there is found in *Hervarar saga* a prose interruption of *Ok enn kvað hann*¹³⁵¹ ['and he said yet']. In *Hervarar saga* it seems like additional prose comments might be needed, and as things stand, Hjálmar's recitation is given no solid context – he simply launches into it after Oddr addresses him when he is wounded.¹³⁵² Having said that, the sequence of ideas in the *Hervarar saga* version cannot be said to be wrong, just different.

In terms of narrative construction, this poem is rather surplus to requirements. It does not play an evidential role, such as proving what the narrator claims, nor does it offer a proper retrospective of the hero's life, focusing as it does on comments about his betrothed (Ingibjörg), instructions as to how he is to be commemorated and the fact that his friends are drinking beer while he is dying. These themes, along with a lack of firm autobiographical details in the poem in *Örvar-Odds saga*, mean that the stories included in the saga about Hjálmar, by which I mean his other deeds recorded in the saga prose previous to the death song section, are not recorded in the saga on the basis of his autobiographical poem.

¹³⁴⁹ In manuscript U of *Hervarar saga*, this stanza follows that marked (4) in this list, about the king's daughter leading him to Agnafit. Tolkien regards this alternative order as more correct; see *Saga Heiðreks konungs*, p. 9, fn. 2.

¹³⁵⁰ Cf. *Saga Heiðreks konungs*, p. 74.

¹³⁵¹ *Saga Heiðreks konungs*, p. 8.

¹³⁵² Cf. Lars Lönnroth, "Hjálmar's Death-Song," p. 18: "...the Norse *Death-Song* must have been accompanied by prose already existing in oral tradition. This can be concluded from the fact that it would otherwise be very difficult to understand many of the references to specific persons and places in the poem. The prose that surrounds the verses in *Hervarar saga* and *Örvar-Odds saga* is also roughly identical in content..."

Oddr in Akvitanian and en route to Jórsalaland (S stt. 8-9)

These two stanzas only occur in S, and are stanzas 53 and 52 from Oddr's death song in ABE (which is not present in S), quoted in the saga prose as evidence stanzas.

The first stanza is about a raid in Akvitanian and is cited as an authenticating stanza that is relevant for only a small part of the saga prose in S. The saga prose is: "Þar kom hann fremst, er heitir Akvitanaland; þar réðu fyrir fjórir höfðingar, ok þar átti Oddr orrostu mikla ok feldi þar alla þessa höfðingja ok mikit fólk annat ok fekk þar øróf fjár. Þar um kvað hann þessa vísu." The second stanza also appears in the death song in ABE. In the saga prose, Oddr is sailing to Jórsalaland but gets lost in a great storm; the stanza seems to be a rare example of symbolism in the *fornaldarsögur*: Oddr talks about going a different way because he is literally lost, but it is interpreted as him being lost because he forgot the Christian faith he has recently converted to, and the other way can be read as leading to hel. Once Oddr turns, he and his men avoid Hell and get to Jórsaland (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 117).

Stanzas in ABE A Couplet from the Giant's Daughter in AB

There are several stanzas that appear only in ABE. One couplet is only present in AB and is spoken by Hildigunnr, a giant's daughter whom Oddr succeeds in later getting pregnant: it is introduced with "þá snøri hon honum fyrir sér ok mælti" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 121.32). Two further stanzas are in ABE and are spoken when Oddr encounters Qgmundr. Both are spoken by Qgmundr as he unheroically runs away from Oddr and Sírnir; one is a plea for assistance from his wife and father-in-law (both giants), and the other describes how he is forced to throw off his fancy cloak that was slowing him down in fleeing (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 135-136).

Oddr and King Knútr

In S, one stanza is quoted in the saga prose from the *ævidrápa* (st. 64) concerning a battle Oddr took part in between King Knútr and King Vilhjálmr. Unlike other stanzas from the *ævidrápa* that also appear in the body of the saga, this stanza is explicitly used as an evidence stanza, introduced by: "Hér um kvað Oddr þessa vísu" (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 135.5, 137.1).

Oddr's Drinking Contest with Sjólfir and Sigurðr (the drinking contest)

The long exchange between Oddr, Sjólfir and Sigurðr is in SMAB. The stanza order varies in each, and below, following Boer (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 159), the stanzas are discussed in the order that they appear in S. There are 25 stanzas, the final sixteen are spoken by Oddr alone as he emerges victorious from the drinking contest. In the first part though, Sjólfir and Sigurðr have one stanza each and Oddr has two – this is perhaps meant to suggest his superiority in versifying as well as in his ability to hold drink. As Oddr speaks so many of the verses in the latter part of the poem, the poem transforms from a contest into an autobiographical revelation. The final line of the final stanza however concludes Oddr's stanzas appropriately for such a contest: “lótom Sæolf mæla” (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 167).

Qrvar-Oddr's Ævidrápa

At the end of *Qrvar-Odds saga*, in ABE we find a long poem that Oddr recounts his life at the point of death. In S, the first two stanzas are quoted.¹³⁵³ In M, the narrative says he composes the poem, but no examples of the verse are given. The saga is explicit how the poem is preserved, and this is presumably to lend extra authority to the poem preserved at the end of some of the sagas. How the poem was preserved depends on the redaction of the saga. In MABE, the poem is memorised, while in S, it is carved in runes on tablets (*Qrvar-Odds saga 1888*, 194, 195). From the point of view of the prosimetrum, the long poem in ABE is surrounded by prose at both ends. Behind the beginning of the poem stands the saga, and afterwards comes a description of Oddr's descendants. The content of the ævidrápa can largely be found in the saga; it probably provided the source for many of the prose episodes.

¹³⁵³ See Judy Quinn, “Ok er þetta upphaf: First Stanza Quotation in Old Norse Prosimetrum,” *Alvíssmál* 7 (1997), 61-80.

Qrvar-Odds saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

It could be said of the saga as whole that the stanzas are generally employed in very specific contexts rather than as stanzas simply dotted here and there as speech (*lausavísur*). This is perhaps to be expected if the long poem in its oral form was the source of many of the prose episodes. The prophetic chant spoken by the *völva* at the beginning of the saga conforms to prophecies or curses being in eddic metre (for example also in *Bósa saga*). The chant is introduced by the phrase “Þá varð henna ljóð á munni” [‘then a chant came to her lips’], and the phrase “þá varð Oddi ljóð á munni” [‘then a chant came to Oddr’s lips’] also occurs. The formula is usually found elsewhere in the *fornaldarsögur* corpus in situations where females speak some kind of prophetic verse and has been analysed in detail by Judy Quinn. She suggests that the author included this occurrence and similar instances where the stanza that follows is spoken by a man “as a cliché to imbue the narrative with the atmosphere of staged, formal utterance set in the legendary past,”¹³⁵⁴ although it is not clear why the saga author would want to have this air to Oddr’s speech.

An exchange in verse form between Hjálmar, Oddr and Ángantýr in *Qrvar-Odds saga* echoes in tone the exchange between Hervör and a shepherd in *Hervarar saga*. In both *Qrvar-Odds saga* and *Hervarar saga*, these exchanges are followed by groups of stanzas that seem to form standalone poems, poems that could be considered formal units and building blocks of the sagas. In *Qrvar-Odds saga* it is followed by a section known as Hjálmar’s death song, metrical last words that the hero Hjálmar recites as he dies and in *Hervarar saga* the scene with a poetic exchange between Hervör and a shepherd is followed by a poem known as *Hervararkviða* [‘a poem about Hervör’], in which Hervör raises her dead father Ángantýr from his gravemound.

Also of note is the section known as Qrvar-Oddr’s drinking contest (following the title of Lars Lönnroth’s essay), a *mannjafnaðr* [‘comparison of men’] that

¹³⁵⁴ “Ok verðr henni ljóð á munni”: Prophetic Verse in the *fornaldarsögur*, *Alvissmál* 8 (1998), 29-50, at 46-47.

Lönnroth proposes as a candidate for the traditional nucleus from which at least part of the saga could have developed.¹³⁵⁵ This is because it summarises much of Oddr's life, but the same is true of *Qrvar-Oddr's* death song, a lengthy poem recited by Oddr as he dies summarising all the escapades and friends of his long life.

As in *Ketils saga hængs* and *Gríms saga loðinkinna*, *Qrvar-Odds saga* also has an exchange between the protagonist and a supernatural creature, this time a pagan priestess who can shoot arrows out of all her fingers. This is in the format of a regular poetical exchange: “þá kvað Oddr” [‘then Oddr said’] followed by a stanza, then “þá kvað hun” [‘then she said’] followed by a stanza, and so on, the exchange brought to an end by her half stanza plea to the pagan gods to save her and her death at the hands of Oddr.

The saga closes with *Qrvar-Oddr's* death song, mentioned above, which is conceived of as a poem in itself by the saga prose: “ok er lokit var kvæðinu...” [‘and when the poem was finished...’]. The poem itself also has stanzas that frame the recounting of Oddr's life that anchors the poem in the present context:

“Þér skuluð skynda
til skips ofan
 heilir allir;
hér munum skiljast;
 berið Silkisif
ok sonum okkrom
 kveðju mína,
kemk eigi þar” (*Qrvar-Odds saga* 1943: ch. 32, 398)

“You should speed yourself down to the ships, farewell all; here must we part; carry my greetings to Silkisif and our sons - I did not arrive [back] there.”

This stanza is also echoed by Oddr's very final words in the prose: “Nú skuluð þér bera kveðju mína heim Silkisif ok sonum okkrum ok vinum.” [‘Now you should carry my greetings home to Silkisif and our sons and friends’], the adverb giving a sense of immediacy to the scene, directly after which Oddr dies. With him ends the poetry in the saga, which is concluded by a brief summary of his sons and descendants.

¹³⁵⁵ Lars Lönnroth, “The Double Scene of Arrow-Odds Drinking Contest,” *The Academy of Odin: Select Papers on Old Norse Literature*, The Viking Collection 19 (Odense: University Press of Southern Denmark, 2011) pp. 243-259, at p. 255.

Boer has labelled great parts of the *ævidrápa* as interpolations or inauthentic, and has attempted (in his later edition of *Qrvar-Odds saga*) to reconstruct the original form of the *ævidrápa*.¹³⁵⁶ Boer argues that the sources of the saga were oral, and considers that the stanzas of the *ævidrápa* that appear in the body of the saga in S were from oral tradition.¹³⁵⁷ I will not rehearse his arguments here, since my study is concerned with the *ævidrápa* as it stands now in extant prosimetra. Nevertheless, I do not agree with Boer when he states that since the *Ævidrápa* is lacking in SM, it can be considered as an interpolation in the other versions.¹³⁵⁸ There are several reasons that Boer does not consider that might explain why SM lack the *Ævidrápa*:¹³⁵⁹

- A saga author did not cite the *Ævidrápa* because they did not know it.
- A saga author did not cite the *Ævidrápa* but they knew it.
 - And they did not cite because it was:
 - generally known
 - generally unknown
- A saga author cited part of the *Ævidrápa* because:
 - they only knew part of it
 - they expected it to be unknown so just gave an example
 - they expected it to be known

The long poem at the end of the saga may be an oral feature of marking the end of a saga.

¹³⁵⁶ See *Qrvar-Odds saga*, ed. R. C. Boer, Altnordische Saga-Bibliothek 2 (Halle a. s.: Niemeyer, 1892) pp. 97-100.

¹³⁵⁷ *Qrvar-Odds saga*, ed. Boer (1982) xi.

¹³⁵⁸ *Qrvar-Odds saga 1888* xiv-xv.

¹³⁵⁹ Cf. Judy Quinn, “Ok er þetta upphaf.”

Áns saga bogsveigis

Áns saga bogsveigis continues the family line as the final saga in the cycle of the *Hrafnistamannasögur* [‘sagas of the men of Hrafnista’], as he is descended from the daughter of Ketill hængur, and is in the generation after Orvar-Oddr.¹³⁶⁰ Although references to the men of Hrafnista can seem somewhat superficial in the saga,¹³⁶¹ there is enough evidence surviving externally in the genealogical tradition, likely to have been preserved orally, to demonstrate that Án really was considered to be part of the clan at the time the *fornaldarsögur* were written down and probably also previously in the oral life of the material.¹³⁶²

The prosimetric structure of the saga is however somewhat different to those sagas commemorating his forbearers. The saga contains only five stanzas. The first stanza is a *dans* stanza, the lyrical first stanza of a *rímur*, and it is used in the saga prose as a situational stanza, introduced with “Án kvað þá vísu” [‘Án spoke a verse’].¹³⁶³ While the first stanza has the metre of *rímur*, the rest of the stanzas are metrically mixed: the second stanza is in *ljóðaháttur*,¹³⁶⁴ the third is skaldic,¹³⁶⁵ and the fourth and fifth in *fornyrðislag*.¹³⁶⁶ All of the remaining stanzas in the saga are *lausavísur*, and introduced very similarly as situational verses. Although this group of *Hrafnistamannasögur* [‘sagas of the men of Hrafnista’] all come from the same pool of oral tradition,¹³⁶⁷ they have quite varied prosimetric profiles, indicating that one pool

¹³⁶⁰ Án is the younger son of Björn and Þorgerðr, who is the daughter of Böðmóðr Framarsson and Hrafnhildr, the daughter of Ketill hængur, see *Áns saga bogsveigis, Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsson, vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Bókauktgáfan Forni, 1943) pp. 403-432, at ch. 1, p. 404, ch. 1.

¹³⁶¹ This is interesting particularly given Elizabeth Ashman Rowe’s work on *Áns saga* as a hybrid between a *fornaldarsaga* and an *Íslendingasaga* in “Generic Hybrids: Norwegian “Family” Sagas and Icelandic “Mythic-Heroic” Sagas,” *Scandinavian Studies* 65 (1993): 539-554. In this article the emphasis is on *Áns saga* as an *Íslendingasaga*.

¹³⁶² See Helen F. Leslie, “The Matter of Hrafnista,” *Quaestio Insularis* 11 (2010): 169-208.

¹³⁶³ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ch. 4, p. 410.

¹³⁶⁴ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ch. 4, p. 412.

¹³⁶⁵ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ch. 4, p. 413.

¹³⁶⁶ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ch. 4, p. 416; ch. 5, pp. 417-418.

¹³⁶⁷ Leslie, “The Matter of Hrafnista.”

of oral tradition can produce sagas with dissimilar structures (perhaps for diachronic reasons).

The main manuscript followed here is AM 343 a 4to, as per Rafn's edition (in which it is indicated by siglum A).¹³⁶⁸ This is a 15th century manuscript containing *fornaldarsögur* and *riddarasögur*,¹³⁶⁹ and which is further discussed in the sections about *Qrvar-Odds saga* and *Ketils saga hængs*. Other secondary manuscripts used in Rafn's edition are AM 340 4to, Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar (manuscript D), and AM 173 I fol., Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum (manuscript E). AM 340 4to is a 17th century *fornaldarsögur* manuscript,¹³⁷⁰ and *Áns saga* is found on 79v-96v. AM 173 I fol. is from c. 1700,¹³⁷¹ and *Áns saga* is to be found on 66r-79v (for more on this manuscript see the section on *Qrvar-Odds saga* below).

Björn and Án Wrestle (1 stanza)

The first stanza of the saga is a dialogue stanza that Án recounts on the occasion of just having bested his opponent Björn in a form of fighting that involves throwing the other man into a fire. Having won, Án's stanza summarizes what has just happened:

Skeldi mér, sem skyldi,
skelkinn maðr við belki;
við máttu ek þá vætkki
vinna, svei þeim æ manni;
varð í fáng at fallast,
felldum eldsmat nökkut;
honum synjaðak heiðri;
svei þeim sè æ manni.¹³⁷²

¹³⁶⁸ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, *Fornaldar Sögur Norðrlanda, eptir gömlum handritum*, ed. C. C. Rafn, vol. 2 (Copenhagen: n.p., 1829) pp. 323-362.

¹³⁶⁹ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 578.

¹³⁷⁰ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 576.

¹³⁷¹ *KAH* vol. 1, p. 142.

¹³⁷² *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 334.

AM 343 a 4to 18r13, the first line of the stanza, reads, as Rafn as edited, “skyldi,” but Guðni Jónsson has “skyldit.”¹³⁷³ It seems as though “skyldi” in the first line ought rather to read “skyldit,” since it would seem to make more sense that Án would think that Björn should not have thrown in the fire, rather than he should have. In the stanza, Án speaks in the first person and the person he says has attacked him is not named. The stanza records the crucial elements of the episode: that a man has thrown him “við belki” [‘against a partition wall’] that there was nothing he could do about it and that some “eldsmat” was added (ie. he threw someone into the fire). The refrain is “svei þeim æ manni” [‘damned ever be that man’]. The stanza is a little odd in the context, since it tells about a situation that has only just occurred in a retrospective manner. After the stanza, the saga moves on.

Episode two: Án addresses a tree (1 stanza)

The second stanza is in *ljóðaháttr*, a simple stanza although poetically beautiful:

Vel þèr selja!
 stendr þú sjó nær
 laufguð harla vel;
 maðr skekkr af þèr
 morgun döggar,
 en ek at þengi
 þrey nátt sem dag.¹³⁷⁴

Good for you, Willow!
 You stand near the sea,
 leafed rather well;
 a man shakes from you
 morning dew.
 And for a thane
 yearn night as day.

In the prose context, the tree must be standing on the shore and Án can see it from the boat; otherwise the stanza gives no context for the expression nor indicates who might be speaking it. The speaker “þrey” [‘desires, longs after’] a thane day and night,

¹³⁷³ *Áns saga bogsveigis, Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsson, vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Bókaútgáfan Forni, 1943) pp. 403-432, at p. 410.

¹³⁷⁴ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 336.

a sentiment that might be more readily associated with a female than male speaker. In the prose, the performance context given for this stanza makes it clear that it is said within earshot of others on the boat. Án's brother offers him the sword Þegn in an attempt to make sense of what Án might want ("eigi skaltu þess þurfa, því ek mun gefa þér sverðit Þegn"),¹³⁷⁵ but the other men ridicule him greatly for the homosexual implications of his stanza: "ek ætla, at þú þreyir at karlmanni nökkrum, [ok villtu serða hann + E], ok gjörðu þeir at þessu gys mikit ok dáraskap".¹³⁷⁶ It is noticeable here that the stanza and the prose that follows it both use the verb "þreyja" in a way that consolidates the linked meanings of the prose and stanza; here the content and wording of the stanza is thus important to its immediate performance context.

Episode three: Án takes a draught before battle (1 stanza)

The third stanza in *Áns saga* (beginning "því betr mér þikir")¹³⁷⁷ is spoken by Án as he receives a horn to drink and anticipates its contents will spur him on in battle. It is introduced as a speech stanza ("hann kvað vísu").¹³⁷⁸ The reply by the king to the stanza, "þetta er vel ort,"¹³⁷⁹ and the performance context in the prose is such that it truly is presented as a stanza composed for that occasion, and the comment by the king shows that the saga prose considered this stanza to be for public consumption, unlike Án's previous stanza, which seemed to be a private reflection overheard.

¹³⁷⁵ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 336.

¹³⁷⁶ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 337.

¹³⁷⁷ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 337.

¹³⁷⁸ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 337.

¹³⁷⁹ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 337.

Episode four: *Án* rebukes Ketill (1 stanza)

The fourth stanza beginning “Þat muntu finna,”¹³⁸⁰ is which *Án* severely rebukes Ketill, is a speech stanza introduced with “kvað vísu.”¹³⁸¹ The stanza relies on a play on *Án*’s nickname, *bogsveigis* [‘bow-bender’], listing other, less complementary things, that Ketill might bend instead: “þú ert brauðsveigir, / heldr enn bogsveigir, / ostaveigir, / en eigi álmsveigir” [‘you are bread-bender, rather than bow-bender, cheese-bender, but not elm-bender’].¹³⁸² The stanza is thus anchored in *Án*’s own identity as “*bogsveigir*” and the speaker names himself in the fourth line as “*Án bogsveigir*.” The recipient of the verse is only ever addressed as “þú” and not named. The earlier poetry *Án* says in the saga causes him problems; now he using poetry as his own weapon.

Episode five: *Án* answers maids back (1 stanza)

This stanza seems to be out of kilter with the surrounding prose. The stanza seems to be recounting the scene from the perspective of some time having passed, but in the stanza it is placed as an occasional stanza that *Án* is supposed to recite in the midst of the event taking place. The context of the stanza is young women, including his host’s daughter *Drífa*, mocking *Án* for his ungainly dress; the farmer (his host) then tells them to stop, at which point

Án kvað þá vísu:
 Meyjar spurðu,
 er mik fundu,
 hvíthaddaðar:
 hvaðan komtu, fersaldr?
 En ek svaraða
 silkigunni
 heldr hæðinni:

¹³⁸⁰ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 341.

¹³⁸¹ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 341.

¹³⁸² *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 341.

hvaðan er logu úti?¹³⁸³

The stanza is rather unusual in that it records a conversation purported to have taken place, and as such recounts everything in the past tense apart from the direct speech. In the prose, the stanza is placed just after this event has taken place, and while everyone is still present. The first three lines of the stanza describe the situation and the beauty of the females, which is perhaps reflected in the prose as Drífa having “hærð kvenna bezt.”¹³⁸⁴ They ask him in the stanza: “hvaðan komtu, ferfaldr?” presented in the prose as “hvaðan gekktu at nú, ferfaldr?” and previously to this, the prose has been at pains to explain that Án wore four layers of clothing, and this is presumably to be taken as the explanation for the name “ferfaldr.” The speaker of the stanza refers to himself in the first person as “ek” and says he answered Silkigunnr (a kenning for a woman) that he has come “hvaðan er logu úti” but presents it “heldr hæðinni” as a question. The stanza seems oddly placed in the prose. If it existed before the prose, then it has not been used well in the construction of the saga.

¹³⁸³ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 343.

¹³⁸⁴ *Áns saga bogsveigis*, ed. Rafn, p. 343.

Áns saga bogsveigis and Prosimetrum

The prosimetrum of *Áns saga* appears to have been constructed from unrelated stanzas that were all nevertheless connected to the figure of Án and that were collected by the prose writer to be used in his narrative. This can be seen from the fact that several of the stanzas in particular are retrospective accounts of an event that are used as speech stanzas. In constructing this saga, the prose author seems to have tried to include speech stanzas as typical of the *fornaldarsögur*, but then found himself in the unfortunate position of their being rather unsuitable. However, as discussed above, the prosimetric context of eddic poetry is rather flexible as to whether a stanza is used as a speech stanza or an evidence stanza, and so the saga author has been undeterred from including the stanzas he knew. Although the prosimetrum in this saga is not typical, it does show again the flexibility of the prose context of poetry in the *fornaldarsögur*, which can accommodate stanzas in a variety of styles, even skaldic ones. In the case of *Áns saga* however, it would appear the author is trying to mould the form of the saga into a *fornaldarsaga* when it may have more naturally not conformed to what is typical for the genre in its prosimetric format.

Romances¹³⁸⁵

Friðþjófs saga ins frækna

There are two versions of *Friðþjófs saga*, one older and shorter thought to be from the end of the 13th century, and one longer version, perhaps from the 15th century.¹³⁸⁶

The older version itself has two versions, the first in AM 510 4to from the end of the 15th century, and the second existing now in several fragments found in three small parchment sheets from the end of the 16th century, and in the paper manuscript AM 568 4to, which was copied from the Stockholm version when it was complete.¹³⁸⁷ The longer, younger version is closer to the second variant of the shorter saga.¹³⁸⁸ The author of the longer version added around nine stanzas to his source, which was not dissimilar to the short version, and it seems knew and used the *rímur*, since the verses he added he made from the kind of language used in the *rímur*.¹³⁸⁹ The short version is thus usually talked of as the ‘original version,’ and it has 29 stanzas, most eddic *lausavísur* with the odd skaldic stanza, all spoken by Friðþjóðr in a “dramatic” context.¹³⁹⁰ Heusler and Ranisch thought highly of the quality of the stanzas.¹³⁹¹

Joseph Harris has suggested that the origins of the saga are somewhat simpler than the Heroic sagas such as *Völsunga saga*, and that the saga is not based on older verse (it “may be based more on invention than real tradition”), but that it is unlikely all the stanzas were composed by the saga author, since they “are not of a piece.” Continuing, Harris believes that the original form of the saga (by which he presumably means oral form) must have been a prosimetrum, and that the verses were more stable than the

¹³⁸⁵ Note that from this section I have excluded *Sturlaugs saga starfsama* and *Göngu Hrólfss saga*, because they only have one stanza each. I include *Bósa saga* because of its interesting use of verse for cursing.

¹³⁸⁶ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, pp. xviii-xix; Joseph Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives,” p. 146.

¹³⁸⁷ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Ludvig Larsson, *Altnordische Saga-Bibliothek* 9 (Halle a. S.: Niemeyer, 1901) pp. vi-vii.

¹³⁸⁸ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. vii.

¹³⁸⁹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, pp. xiii-xviii; Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga” 147.

¹³⁹⁰ Harris, “The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga” 147.

¹³⁹¹ *Eddica minora*, lxxxv-lxxxvii.

prose in the transmission process.¹³⁹² Other scholars have suggested that the source of the saga may have been a unified poem, and that the strophes in the older version of the present saga are survivals from this.¹³⁹³ Harris dismisses this on the basis that no similar such poem exists,¹³⁹⁴ but in fact the long poem at the end of *Qrvar-Odds saga*, Qrvar-Oddr's death song, may be a suitable parallel. A few of the stanzas that appear at the end of the saga are spoken by Oddr during the saga itself, suggestive of a layering process in the development of the saga that may have also happened in *Friðþjófs saga*, only in this case the longer poem has not survived.¹³⁹⁵ Harris's own further analysis supports this, when he links the saga told by Ingimundr at the wedding in Reykjahólar, *Orms saga*, with *Friðþjófs saga* as a late reflex, and suggests that the "good *flokkr*" at the end of his saga may have been an eddic death song rather than a skaldic poem,¹³⁹⁶ which would mirror the situation in *Qrvar-Odds saga*.

It is the longer redaction that Ludvig Larsson edited, since the shorter, older redaction is badly preserved,¹³⁹⁷ and it is to this edition that my comments pertain.

The first stanza of the saga, beginning "Þat mun 'k segja,"¹³⁹⁸ is an occasional stanza spoken by Friðþjófr. The stanza itself is in the present tense and fits well with the saga prose. The prose explains the stanza by Friðþjófr telling the king's daughter to cover the temple with light coloured sheets to signal the return of the kings wishing to

¹³⁹² Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga" 148.

¹³⁹³ Ursula Brown, "The Saga of Hrómund Gripsson and Þorgilssaga." *Saga-Book of the Viking Society* 13 (1947-48): 51-77, at 62-63; Gustaf Wenz, ed., *Die Friðþjófs saga in Ihrer Überlieferung untersucht und der ältesten Fassung kritisch herausgegeben* (Halle a. S.: Niemeyer, 1914) cx-cxi; Ida L. Gordon, "The Origins of Gíslasaga." *Saga-Book of the Viking Society* 13 (1949-50): 183-205, at 201-205; Heather O'Donoghue, *The Genesis of a Saga Narrative: Verse and Prose in 'Kormaks saga'* (Oxford: Clarendon, 1991) 29.

¹³⁹⁴ Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 148.

¹³⁹⁵ For more on Qrvar-Oddr's death song, see below. In fact the death song is not in its entirety in all of the versions of the saga, so its preservation too may have been an accident of survival.

¹³⁹⁶ Harris, "The Prosimetrum of Icelandic Saga and Some Relatives," p. 156.

¹³⁹⁷ For an overview of his decision to edit the saga thus, see *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. xxiii.

¹³⁹⁸ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 12, ch. 2.3, ll. 14-21.

marry Ingibjörg. The stanza is introduced with “Ok næsta morgun eptir gekk hann út snemma ok sagði svá, er hann kom inn, ok kvað vísu” [‘and the next morning after, he went out, early, and spoke thus, when he came in, and said a verse’],¹³⁹⁹ giving not only the stanza but also the following prose a definite setting in the narrative. In the second half of the stanza Friðþjófr remarks that the “blæjur / á blik komnar” [‘sheet are out to bleach’],¹⁴⁰⁰ and the narrator consolidates the point in the prose: “Gengu þeir þá út ok sá, at allr dísarsalrinn var þaktar bleitum léreptum” [‘then they went out and saw, that all of the roofs of the dísir-halls were decked with bleached linen’].¹⁴⁰¹ In the prose however, it is a character called Björn rather than Friðþjófr who interprets this as the herald of the return of the kings,¹⁴⁰² and the prose thus repeats the entire contents of the stanza using both the narrator and another character.

The performance context of the second stanza in the saga, beginning “Snyðja lét ’k ór Sogni,”¹⁴⁰³ is refreshingly comical. Friðþjófr and his men are caught in a great storm when sailing out of Sogn, and in the midst of this, Friðþjófr recites a stanza that records that he launched his ship out of Sogn, and left the maidens drinking mead by Baldr’s field, “þær er oss vilja unna” [‘those who will love us’].¹⁴⁰⁴ Such a stanza provokes Björn into saying: “Þat væri vel, þóttú ættir annat at vinna en ljóða um þær Baldrshagameyjar” [‘It might be as well if you got yourself something else to do than make verse about those Baldr’s-field maids’].¹⁴⁰⁵ The prose employs the stanza with great effect as a situational stanza in which Friðþjófr annoys Björn with his choice of content.

¹³⁹⁹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 12, 2.3, ll. 12-13.

¹⁴⁰⁰ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 12, 2.3, ll. 20-21.

¹⁴⁰¹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 12, 2.4, ll. 22-23.

¹⁴⁰² *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 12, 2.4, l. 23 – p. 13, 2.4, ll. 1-2.

¹⁴⁰³ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 15, 6.1, ll. 5-12.

¹⁴⁰⁴ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 15, 6.1, l. 11.

¹⁴⁰⁵ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 15, 6.2, ll. 13-14.

The third stanza of the saga, which appears in the same episode, continues Friðþjófr's versifying about the storm. The prose recounts that storm drives the ship northwards into the straits near the Solundar islands. In the stanza, which begins "Mjök tekr sjór at svella,"¹⁴⁰⁶ Friðþjófr blames magic for the swelling of the waves and determines to take shelter in the Solundar islands, and in the prose following the stanza, they do this; the stanza is thus used in such a way as to suggest an idea that is carried out, the stanza thus being very much part of the story and having direct influence on what happens therein.

The fourth stanza of the saga also comments on the present sailing conditions. The first four (half)lines look back to another event: "Þat var fyrri / á Framnesi, / at rera 'k á vit / við Ingibjörgu" ['It was off Framness, that I rowed to visit Ingibjörg'],¹⁴⁰⁷ while the second half of the stanza focuses on the present good sailing. The saga prose continues with descriptions of the sailing until the sea turns rough and Friðþjófr recites another stanza, beginning "Eigi sér til alda,"¹⁴⁰⁸ which in addition to commenting on the rough weather, gives more concrete information on their actions: there are eighteen men onboard, and they are all exerting themselves, and the Solundar islands have disappeared. They also name the ship, the *Elliði*. The stanza thus mentions concrete facts about the episode. The sixth stanza in the saga however, beginning "Helgi veldr, at hrannir,"¹⁴⁰⁹ reverts back to mention of women, the topic that provoked Björn after Friðþjófr recited his second stanza, the first half of the stanza again commenting on the sailing conditions, the second half lamenting that he will never get Ingibjörg. Present conditions are also compared to their time spent with women: "Er ei, sem bjarta brúði / í Baldrs haga kyssim" ['It is not as when we kissed bright maidens in Baldr's enclosures'].¹⁴¹⁰ As the episode continues, Friðþjófr

¹⁴⁰⁶ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 15, 6.2, ll. 4-11.

¹⁴⁰⁷ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 16, 6.3, ll. 18-10 – p. 17, ll. 1-2.

¹⁴⁰⁸ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 17, 6.4, ll. 11-18.

¹⁴⁰⁹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 18, 6.5, ll. 3-10.

¹⁴¹⁰ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 18, 6.5, ll. 5-6.

continues to compose on the frightening sailing (stanza seven, beginning “Eigi sér til alda”)¹⁴¹¹ and about the potential reaction of Ingibjörg when he drowns in the rough conditions (in stanza eight, beginning “Mjök drekkur á mik”)¹⁴¹² in an expression of imagination of women’s activities back in the hall that are reminiscent of the Hjálmar’s lamentations as he dies of his friends and the maidens having fun in the hall while he succumbs to his wounds. In the ninth stanza, which starts “Erat, sem ekkja,”¹⁴¹³ Björn responds to Friðbjófr’s declaration in the stanza before that the women will be drinking to him by responding that their present experience is quite unlike the times when women “biði nær fara” [‘bid you to get closer’],¹⁴¹⁴ and the stanza ends with a lament on how the storm is affecting his body. The prose narration continues with lack of sympathy from a man of lesser ranking, to which Friðbjófr replies “Eða hví kveðr þú ekki, Ásmundr?” [‘But why don’t you recite something, Ásmundr?’].¹⁴¹⁵ This response by Friðbjófr shows that from the point of view of the prose narrative, the stanzas are occasional verses that are part of a semi-formal versified exchange, in which those who expect to take part must speak in verse. Ásmundar too in his stanza, which begins “Hér varp snæfrt um siglu,”¹⁴¹⁶ comments mainly on the sailing conditions and the work he must do on the ship in such inclement weather, but also ties his stanza thematically to those that have gone before by stating that he would rather be working inside waiting the tables, something that is picked up in the prose by Friðbjófr as something that shows Ásmundr is “í þrælaættina,”¹⁴¹⁷ that he would be the one serving. The stanzas thus also seem important to establish and consolidate one’s social standing before the others present.

¹⁴¹¹ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 19, 6.6, ll. 1-8.

¹⁴¹² *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 20, 6.7, ll. 3-10.

¹⁴¹³ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 21, 6.8, ll. 1-8.

¹⁴¹⁴ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 21, 6.8, ll. 4-5.

¹⁴¹⁵ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 21, 6.9, l. 12.

¹⁴¹⁶ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 21, 6.9, ll. 14-17 – p. 22, 9, ll. 1-4.

¹⁴¹⁷ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 22, 6.9, l. 6.

As the storm gains a new vigour, Friðbjófr returns to reciting verses. The eleventh stanza in the saga, beginning “Sat ek á bólstri,”¹⁴¹⁸ again begins by looking back to former pleasures with the king’s daughter, and commenting on the present likelihood that he will end up on the ocean’s bed, a sentiment that Björn in the prose comments is “illa um svá góðan dreng” [‘a bad thing in a brave fellow’].¹⁴¹⁹ Friðbjófr’s reply explicitly acknowledges both of these strands of the poems: about the voyages for pleasures they have made, and the fact they are likely to die.¹⁴²⁰ That the stanzas recited to an extent rely on replying to what others have said is also acknowledged by Friðbjófr in his reply to Björn, which unusually is introduced by Friðbjófr himself rather than by the narrator: “Ok skal enn svara þér nokkru” [‘And I shall yet answer you somewhat’], to which the narrator adds “ok kvað” [‘and said’].¹⁴²¹ At this point, Friðbjófr recites a rather provocative stanza (beginning “Þess hefi ’k gangs of goldit”)¹⁴²² in which he reminds Björn that Ingibjörg’s maid were lusting after him and not Björn, although Björn’s magnanimous reply is drowned out, literally, by a huge wave crashing over the ship, snapping the mast and drowning four men. Immediately below the prose description, Friðbjófr versifies the event (stanza thirteen, a half-stanza, beginning “Brustu báðir hálsar”),¹⁴²³ in which he comments on both the damage to the ship and the deaths of the four men. It is slightly surprising that this stanza is so short, and it could be that there was once a full stanza and it has been corrupted. This is more likely to be the case if this section of the saga prose is thought to be based on the stanzas that it contains.

Stanza fourteen of the saga comes amidst a curious section in which Friðbjófr, semi-convinced they are all about to die because of the storm: “Nú þykki mér ván,’

¹⁴¹⁸ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 22, 6.10, ll. 12-15 – p. 23, ll. 1-4.

¹⁴¹⁹ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 23, 6.11, l. 6.

¹⁴²⁰ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 23, 6.11 ll. 7-10.

¹⁴²¹ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 23, 6.11 ll. 10-11.

¹⁴²² *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 23, 6.11, ll. 12-15 – p. 24, ll. 1-4.

¹⁴²³ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 24, 6.12, ll. 10-13.

segir Friðþjófr, ‘at nokkurir várir men muni til Ránar fara’ [“Now it seems to be expected,’ Friðþjófr says, ‘that some of our men will go to Rán’],¹⁴²⁴ and duly cuts up a gold bracelet and distributes the pieces among the men. The stanza he then speaks describes the cutting up of the gold bracelet “er Hálfðanar átti” [‘which Hálfðan owned’],¹⁴²⁵ in order that the men might use it to procure lodging with Rán when they are drowned. This may be looked upon as a reflex of, for example, men taking their swords with them into the burial chamber when they die, or people taking goods with them into the afterlife.

The witchcraft Friðþjófr verbally blames for the storm in the continuation of the narrative about the voyage in the storm has been hinted at in previous stanzas. Now, however, rather than it simply being used as a trope to explain bad weather, in the prose Friðþjófr claims to be able to see two women stood on the back of a whale encircling the ship working “seið ok gøldrum” [‘seiðr and magic’],¹⁴²⁶ sent by King Helgi and preventing them from nearing land. The fifteenth stanza in the saga (begins “Sé ek trollkonur”)¹⁴²⁷ notes the detail that the two “trollkonur” [‘troll women’] have been sent by Helgi and that the ship Elliði will destroy them. What happens next is rationalised in the prose by stating that the ship understands human speech, which is necessary for the ship to follow the command of Friðþjófr in the sixteenth stanza, which he begins by addressing the ship directly with “Heill Elliði!” [‘Elliði, hale!’],¹⁴²⁸ and commanding it to crush the two women, and in the prose it is related that between the efforts of Friðþjófr and the ship, the two women are killed.¹⁴²⁹ In his excitement at achieving this and in assuring Björn they certainly ought to pump to

¹⁴²⁴ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 24, 6.13, ll. 14-15.

¹⁴²⁵ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 25, 6.13, l. 4.

¹⁴²⁶ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 26, ll. 5-6.

¹⁴²⁷ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 26, ll. 9-16.

¹⁴²⁸ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 27, l. 1. The stanza is ll. 1-8.

¹⁴²⁹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 27, 6.16 ll. 9-10.

prevent the ship from sinking, “Friðbjófr kvað vísu” [‘Friðbjófr said a verse’],¹⁴³⁰ the seventeenth in the saga, in which he encourages his men to work and also remarks that it seems that he may in fact get to marry Ingibjörg (the stanza begins “Þurfið ei, drengir!”).¹⁴³¹ Having finally made the shore, the crew are exhausted, according to the prose, and Friðbjófr, as it says in both the prose and stanza eighteen (which begins “Ek bar átta”),¹⁴³² carries eight men ashore (the prose informs the reader that Björn also carried two and Ásmundr one). At this point, the saga episode (and chapter) changes and the episode of Friðbjófr at sea ends.

The stanzas in the episode of Friðbjófr and his men at sea contain all the pertinent information to construct the saga scene. While it is not provable, it seems that this poetic exchange may have preserved the scene orally, which is perhaps signalled by the somewhat repetitive structure of the stanzas. Almost all of them spoken by Friðbjófr have some comment on his relationship with Ingibjörg as well as a comment on the present situation at sea. The prose has then been used to fill out the narrative, for example while Friðbjófr carries eight men in the stanza, the prose also adds that Björn and Ásmundr carries a man each, and to rationalise events in the stanzas, for example stating that their ship understands them in order to explain why Friðbjófr addresses it directly in a stanza. That Björn and Ásmundr engage with Friðbjófr in stanzaic section that is mainly spoken by him shows that the poetic exchange was felt to have a definite performance context in which those listening could contribute. This is comparable to *Innsteinskviða* in *Hálfs saga*, which is mainly spoken by Innsteinn but other characters do speak several verses in the preliminary stages of the episode in *Hálfs saga*.

¹⁴³⁰ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 27, 6.17, ll. 17.

¹⁴³¹ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 27, 6.17, ll. 18-21 – p. 28, 6.17, ll. 1-4.

¹⁴³² *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 28, 6.18, ll. 12-19.

The seventh chapter of the saga begins from when Friðþjófr and his men make land. The first stanza is spoken by Hallverðr, when he “sá ferð þeirra Friðþjófrs” [‘when he saw the journey of Friðþjófr and his men’].¹⁴³³ Hallverðr’s report in verse, beginning “men sé ’k ausa,”¹⁴³⁴ that he sees six men baling out on the Elliði, seven rowing and the one at the bow looking like Friðþjófr not only relates the information to those listening to Hallverðr, as it is a situational stanza, but also contributes to the narrative veracity, since his account matches that found in the earlier stanzas spoken by Friðþjófr and the prose account of the narrator. The twentieth stanza is also spoken by Hallvarðr (beginning “taktu af gólfi”),¹⁴³⁵ instructing a serving woman to give him more drink, and is heard by Angantýr Jarl, who as a result of it “spurði tíðinda” [‘asked for the news’].¹⁴³⁶ Here, the performance context of the stanza is such that it can be heard by other people, although it seems that this is only applicable to the second stanza that Hallvarðr speaks, since if the Jarl had heard his first stanza, he would know what the news was. This section of the narrative must then be thought of as using the device of a character speaking aside, so as not to be heard.

The berserkr Atli and his men threaten Friðþjófr and his men as they arrive, but Friðþjófr “sneri á móti þeim ok kvað vísu” [‘turned to towards them and said a verse’].¹⁴³⁷ The stanza he speaks, the twenty-first in the saga and beginning “Þér munuð eigi,”¹⁴³⁸ insults his would-be opponents and accepts the challenge to fight them, but is spared by friendly invitation from the Jarl, who “spurði opt at ferðum þeirra.”¹⁴³⁹ His questions prompt a five short-line response from Björn, who succinctly replies that they endured the storm for eighteen days in a stanza beginning

¹⁴³³ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 29, 7.1, ll. 6-7.

¹⁴³⁴ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 29, 7.1, ll. 8-15.

¹⁴³⁵ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 30, 7.1, ll. 1-8.

¹⁴³⁶ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 30, 7.3, l. 9.

¹⁴³⁷ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 31, 7.5, ll. 4-5.

¹⁴³⁸ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 31, 7.5, ll. 6-13.

¹⁴³⁹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 32, 7.8, ll. 1-2.

“Jusu vér, meðan.”¹⁴⁴⁰ The jarl’s reply with his thoughts on the subject betray his knowledge of the wider story however, since he speaks badly of King Helgi, while Björn’s stanza did not mention Helgi. However, given that the narrative states that the king asked often, and the stanza by Björn is not introduced as having taken place in a specific context, it seems that Björn’s stanza is not part of a recorded discourse between the men as such, only a record that, at some point during his time with Angantýr, Björn said this verse. It is thus a situational stanza with a weak performance context, which, as the episode of Friðbjófr’s composing in the storm demonstrates, is quite unusual for this saga.

The next episode in the saga to contain verse, in which Friðbjófr arrives home to find his farmstead burnt down, contains several *lausavísur* that do not appear to belong to a sustained prosimetric narrative, unlike the episode about the storm, which was densely punctuated with stanzas. Here we find the twenty-third stanza spoken by Friðbjófr lamenting the burning of his farm and also recalling the old days in which he had feasted there with his father.¹⁴⁴¹ The prose gives the stanza a performance context in which others can hear, but no one responds, although in the prose Friðbjófr does (unsuccessfully) attempt to engage his men in the decision making process about how to proceed. The second stanza in the episode, the twenty-fourth of the saga, beginning “Einn mun ’k ganga,”¹⁴⁴² is spoken directly to Björn and does provoke a response from him. The first stanza can thus be distinguished from the second as simply a comment on the proceedings, whereas the second is a direct address to Björn that logically ought to have a reply.

¹⁴⁴⁰ *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 32, 7.8, ll. 3-7.

¹⁴⁴¹ The stanza begins “Drukum forðum,” *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 34, 9.2, ll. 1-8.

¹⁴⁴² *Friðbjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 34, 9.5, ll. 21-24 – p. 35, ll. 1-4.

The episode continues with stanzas that relate Friðþjófr's activities when inside Helgi's hall to take revenge for the burning of his farm and to deliver the tribute that he collected from Angantýr. In the first stanza, the twenty-fifth of the saga, the stanza is spoken by Friðþjófr and addressed directly to the king with "Taktu við skatti" ["Take the tribute"],¹⁴⁴³ and both the stanza and prose make it clear that Friðþjófr has hurled the silver at the king's front teeth, and in the stanza this silver is identified as that which he and Björn have collected.¹⁴⁴⁴ This is the first time that the name of the character Björn has been recorded in a stanza, and this stanza seems to help consolidate the connection between Björn and Friðþjófr in as far as the stanzas go. Then, in the prose, Friðþjófr causes chaos, and emerges unscathed with a bracelet, prompting Björn to ask him what happened in the hall. Friðþjófr then recounts in verse what has happened in the prose. In this stanza, the twenty-sixth of the saga beginning "Helgi varð fyr höggi,"¹⁴⁴⁵ it is recounted yet again by Friðþjófr that he threw a purse into his face, the icon of Baldr fell into the fire and burnt and that he escaped with the bracelet. A lot of information is presented in this stanza, which is full of narrative details. Here, the narrator becomes explicitly concerned with narrative veracity: "Þat segja menn, at Friðþjófr hafi undit eldskíðu í næfrarnar, svá at salrinn logaði allr, ok kvað vísu" ['Men say that Friðþjófr had swung a burning stick at the rafters, so the temple was all on fire, and said a verse'].¹⁴⁴⁶ The twenty-seventh verse, beginning "Stundum nú til strandar,"¹⁴⁴⁷ is thus cited as evidence that what "men say" may have actually happened, purely by the fact that there is a dialogue stanza associated with this snippet of information. In this case, unlike many of Friðþjófr's other stanzas, the stanza does not replicate the information in the prose, merely saying that they (presumably he and Björn) ought to hasten to the beach since Baldrshaga is ablaze throughout. This lack of correlation between the stanza and the prose

¹⁴⁴³ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 35, 9.7, l. 15. The stanza is ll. 15-22.

¹⁴⁴⁴ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 35, 9.7, l. 21.

¹⁴⁴⁵ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 36, 9.9, ll. 13-20.

¹⁴⁴⁶ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 37, 9.9, ll. 1-2.

¹⁴⁴⁷ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 37, 9.9, ll. 3-6.

information may have led the saga compiler to insert this comment to acknowledge that there is a discrepancy. On the other hand, the saga compiler may be envisaging this twenty-seventh stanza and accompanying prose as an alternative to the prose and stanza he has offered concerning Friðþjófr's exit from the hall/temple, and thus be acknowledging a different tradition. In either case, it seems that the proffering of a section introduced with "þat segja men" demonstrates that here this particular piece of prose was thought to go with the stanza, as if the saga compiler were to have constructed the prose on the basis of this stanza, the prose would likely reflect more accurately the content of the verse.

In fleeing from the wounded and furious Helgi, Friðþjófr snaps his oars, recorded in stanza twenty-eight, beginning "Kysta 'k unga,"¹⁴⁴⁸ and the prose that they snapped like Helgi's bow, which in the prose above the stanza broke because in his anger he pulled too hard on it.¹⁴⁴⁹ Having sailed away, Friðþjófr recites another stanza beginning with "Sigldum vér ór Sogni,"¹⁴⁵⁰ a situational stanza in which he compares their journey out of Sogn watching Baldr's temple burn with their previous journey away, after which their own farm was burnt, and Friðþjófr also says that he will be called a "vargr" ['outlaw'] from now on for burning down the temple.¹⁴⁵¹ It is difficult to know whether Björn's question to Friðþjófr directly after his stanza, about what they should do now, is a result of Friðþjófr's verse or not.

The thirtieth stanza in the saga is a naming stanza, beginning "Þá hét ek Friðþjófr."¹⁴⁵² Such stanzas, identifying name and provianance, are relatively common in the

¹⁴⁴⁸ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 38, 10.3, ll. 7-14.

¹⁴⁴⁹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 38, 10.3, ll. 3-4.

¹⁴⁵⁰ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 39, 10.4, ll. 1-8.

¹⁴⁵¹ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 39, 10.4, l. 7.

¹⁴⁵² *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 43, 11.1, ll. 4-21.

fornaldarsögur. However, this stanza not only is rather long, it also does not give the place the speaker comes from and lists a long list of variants of the speaker's name, and the activities he undertook when he was called such a name. Friðþjófr arrivals, hooded, disguised and as a guest who reveals many names is distinctly Óðinnic. In the final lines of the stanza, however, the speaker reveals he is in need, appealing no doubt to the king's sense of hospitality. The long naming stanza is likely supposed to echo those spoken by Óðinn in other eddic poems, although it is unusual in that it gives Friðþjófr's usual name in the first line. This might suggest it is in fact a parody of the Óðinn verses.

The final episode containing stanzas takes place when Friðþjófr, having arrived at the court of King Hringr and given the list of his names as discussed above, declares he must leave. Hringr is married to Ingibjörg, the lady whom Friðþjófr has been much enamoured and mentioned frequently in the stanzas towards the beginning of the saga recounting his and Björn's voyage in a storm. The performance context of stanza thirty-one is thus rather detailed: after announcing his arrival and reciting his verse, "Kastaði hann þá hringnum góða til Ingibjargar ok kvað hana eiga. Konungr brosti at vísu þessarri..." ['he threw a fine bracelet to Ingibjörg and told her to have it. The king smiled at this verse...']. The king is thus directly aware of the stanza and its contents. Friðþjófr later follows up with the thirty-second stanza, beginning "Bú þú, Hringr konungr!",¹⁴⁵³ in which he wishes the king all good health and compliments him, while mentioning at the end of the stanza that he and Ingibjörg will never meet again. This causes the king to reply with a stanza begging Friðþjófr not to leave, "Far þu ei svá,"¹⁴⁵⁴ and he continues in the thirty-fifth stanza, linked to the thirty-fourth with the standard phrase "ok enn kvað hann" ['and yet he said'],¹⁴⁵⁵ with the remarkable offer to

¹⁴⁵³ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 49, 12.8, ll. 15-22.

¹⁴⁵⁴ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 49, 12.9, ll. 24-27 – p. 50, ll. 1-4.

¹⁴⁵⁵ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 50, 12.9, l. 5.

give Friðþjófr his wife and everything he owns.¹⁴⁵⁶ Friðþjófr declines this in the thirty-fifth verse, beginning “Þær mun ’k ekki,”¹⁴⁵⁷ leaving the king to explain in the prose that he believes he is about to die and he would like Friðþjófr to have his wife and reign his kingdom until his sons come of age. This exchange is a rather simple one, in which stanzas are emotional stanzas are exchanged and replied to in such a manner that their content is not repeated by the prose. These are then true dialogue stanzas.

Friðþjófs saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

Bjarni Einarrson suggested that speech or ‘story’ stanzas were intrinsic to the narrative and could not be skipped without damaging comprehension of the narrative. In this saga, the stanzas function as evidence stanzas in the narrative even as they are used as situational stanzas in dialogue. In the first prosimetric episode of the stanza, for example, the first stanza is a speech stanza and fits well into the prose. Nevertheless, the content of the speech stanza is repeated in the prose narrative. The fact that the characters recite stanzas with the same details in as the prose aids in authenticating the narrative. If this were not the case, the dialogue stanzas would not be so consistently repetitive of what has been said already in the prose. This indicates that story stanzas in fact need not add to the story and can sometimes thus be skipped without any ill effect to the understanding of the prose narrative, although their aesthetic effect is lost.

The second episode to contain verse in the saga is a lengthy episode in which Friðþjófr and his men when sailing get caught in a storm. It contains a lot of stanzas in the form of a dialogue exchange, which is between two men rather than a man and a supernatural creature. The content of the stanzas is partly retrospectively heroic in tone, partly laments their present situation of being endangered by the storm and partly reflects on Friðþjófr’s love for Ingibjörg. The similarity in context to Hjálmar’s death song, for example, might suggest that Friðþjófr’s verses are a variation in a

¹⁴⁵⁶ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 50, 12.9, ll. 6-9.

¹⁴⁵⁷ *Friðþjófs saga ins frækna*, ed. Larsson, p. 50, 12.10, ll. 11-14.

different context of this genre of poetry, which could be why its flippant recital in a storm annoys Friðbjófr's companion Björn at the beginning of the episode. Friðbjófr does not seriously appear to consider his own life to be in danger, and so it is not likely that he is serious in his death-song like verse. The stanzas are blended into a dialogue with Björn in which the character Ásmundr also recites a verse. This too suggests that Friðbjófr is not truly trying to construct a monologic death song. The prosimetric form may have been responsible for the transmission of the scene, although it could be noted that at sixteen stanzas, the episode is rather long to have been preserved orally.

The saga does contain some *lausavísur* that are obviously not part of a sustained dialogue in verse. The episode in which Friðbjófr finds his farm burnt down is quite different in prosimetric structure to the storm episode. This suggests that in the larger saga structure, prosimetric episodes with substantially different constructions can be united into one narrative.

Hálfs saga ok Hálfs rekka

Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka exists in just one vellum manuscript, GKS 2845 4to, from which all other 55 paper manuscripts are descended.¹⁴⁵⁸ GKS 2845 4to, from around 1450,¹⁴⁵⁹ is made up of 73 vellum pages (84), and contains the following sagas:¹⁴⁶⁰

Bandmanna saga (1r-13r)
Norna-Gests þáttr (13r-19v)
Orms þáttr Stórolfssonar (19v-26r)
Rauðúlfs þáttr (26r-32r)
Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka (32r-39v)
Göngu-Hrólfs saga (39v-54v, fragmentary)
Yngvars saga víðfjrla (55r-59r, fragmentary)
Eiríks saga víðfjrla (59v-61v, fragmentary)
Heiðreks saga (61v-73v, fragmentary)

Out of these nine sagas, six are *fornaldarsögur*, four of which are fragmentary. The saga may have appeared in the 14th century and is perhaps based on a lost saga, called **Hróks saga svarta* by the compiler of *Sturlunga saga*;¹⁴⁶¹ this may or may not be similar to the saga as we have it now, but at least seems to have been composed between 1220 and 1280.¹⁴⁶²

Most stanzas are in *fornyrðislag* and are connected to particular episodes in the saga. These are:

1. Alrekr predicts Geirhildr's son will hang (1 stanza)
2. A voice from a mound (disembodied) (1 stanza)
3. Water monsters episode (10 stanzas)
4. About a woman (disembodied) (1 stanza)

¹⁴⁵⁸ Strophes edited in *Eddica minora. Dichtungen eddischer Art aus den Fornaldarsögur und anderen Prosawerken*, ed. Andreas Heusler and Wilhelm Ranisch (Dortmund: Ruhfus, 1903) 33-37, 44-48, 71-73, 89-92, 93. For a stemma of paper manuscripts see *Hálfs saga ok Hálfsrekka*, ed. Hubert Seelow, *Stofnun Árna Magnússonar á Íslandi, Rit 20* (Reykjavík: Stofnun Árna Magnússonar, 1981) pp. 82-83.

¹⁴⁵⁹ According to *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow p. 106. This dating is half a century later than the dating that Jón Helgason seems to accept in *Heiðreks saga: Hervarar saga ok Heiðreks konungs*, ed. Jón Helgason, SUGNL 48 (Copenhagen: Samfund til udgivelse af gammel nordisk litteratur: 1924) i.

¹⁴⁶⁰ See *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow p.83.

¹⁴⁶¹ *Geirmundar þáttr Heljarskinns, Sturlunga saga*, ed. Jón Jóhannesson et al., vol. 1 (Reykjavík: Sturlunguútgáfan, 1946) pp. 5-11, at p. 7.

¹⁴⁶² *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow p. 165.

5. *Innsteinskviða* (Insteinn and the king, the hall burns, versiprose) (24 stanzas)
6. *Utsteinskviða* (14 stanzas)
7. *Hrókskviða* (27 stanzas)
8. About Hámundr and Geirmundr heljarskin (1 stanza)

Several of the situations in which stanzas appear in *Hálfs saga* have immediate parallels in other sagas. As in *Hervarar saga*, in which the dead Angantýr speaks stanzas from the mouth of his grave mound, poetry is spoken from a grave: “hann heyrði uisu þessa kuedna i haugín” [‘he heard this verse spoken in the mound’],¹⁴⁶³ and as in *Ketils saga hængs*, stanzas are also spoken by supernatural creatures. The king Hjörleifr has a short poetic exchange with a *þurs* [‘giant’ by definition, but this creature seems to be a kind of generic *tröll*],¹⁴⁶⁴ and their speeches are specifically noted by the prose to have been in verse, since although Hjörleifr’s stanza is simply introduced with “kong[r] quad” [‘the king said’],¹⁴⁶⁵ the creature’s stanza in reply is introduced with “þá kuad þuss af biargi annat hlíod” [‘then the giant said another verse from the cliff’].¹⁴⁶⁶ A stanza heard by king Hreiðarr¹⁴⁶⁷ is unusual because it is heard out of nowhere: “er Híorleifr kongr kom heyrði Reidar kongr q(uedit)” [‘when king Hjörleifr came, king Hreiðarr heard pronounced’].¹⁴⁶⁸ Found in this saga too is a long exchange of dialogue similar to that in *Ketils saga hængs* between Ketill and the troll woman; here though is found a rather long exchange of fifteen stanzas between the character Innsteinn and king Hálfr (although the penultimate stanza is by Útsteinn),¹⁴⁶⁹ followed by a related five stanza speech by Innsteinn about the situation

¹⁴⁶³ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 2, ll. 8-9.

¹⁴⁶⁴ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 172, ch. 2, ll. 52-70.

¹⁴⁶⁵ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 172, ch. 2, ll. 52-53.

¹⁴⁶⁶ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 172, ch. 2, ll. 62-63. Other stanzas spoken by supernatural creatures in the saga are introduced with the standard “hann kvað” [‘he said’] or similar (for example: 1 stanza in p. 173, ch. 2, ll. 85-92 by a man-shaped cliff coming out the sea; seven stanzas by a sea-goblin on pp. 174-175, ch. 3).

¹⁴⁶⁷ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 176, ch. 3, ll. 83-90.

¹⁴⁶⁸ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 176, ch. 3, ll. 81-82.

¹⁴⁶⁹ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, pp. 179-183.

in which they find themselves, as they are trapped in a burning hall¹⁴⁷⁰ – the stanzas he spoke with Hálfir had predicted this. Such a long commentary about an immediate situation (rather than a retrospective at the time of death), is rather unusual, and it continues with several short prose interludes for four stanzas.¹⁴⁷¹ Suddenly, however, it becomes clear to the audience that Innsteinn is indeed about to meet his death. The last four stanzas build up by recording the deaths of Hálfir and Hrókr; the penultimate stanza switches tone to a concise retrospective mode:

“Eg hefi utti
atían sumur
fylgt full huga
fleín at ríoda
skal eg ecki annan
eíga drottín
gunnar giarnan
ne gamall uerda”¹⁴⁷²

“I have been raiding eighteen summers, followed a dauntless hero to redden an arrow. I shall not have another lord eager for battle, nor become old.”

The retrospective mode continues with Útsteinn’s stanzas, which continue to record the death of Hálfir while commenting on it in hindsight in a *mannjafnaðr*.¹⁴⁷³ The autobiographical poetry in the saga then immediately continues with a long *ævidrápa* from Hrókr inn svartí.¹⁴⁷⁴ It seems here that this section of the saga, recording the death of king Hálfir, is built around the poetry, similar to many sections containing inset autobiographical poetry in the *fornaldarsögur*. Autobiographical poetry is a condensed way to preserve the life stories of heroes and was likely an oral genre; the most extreme of these is Orvar-Oddr’s death song, which preserves events that run through the entire saga.

¹⁴⁷⁰ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, pp. 183-184.

¹⁴⁷¹ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, pp. 184-185.

¹⁴⁷² *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 85, ch. 8, ll. 23-30.

¹⁴⁷³ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, pp. 186-189, ch. 9

¹⁴⁷⁴ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, pp. 190-197, ch. 10.

Episode one: Alrekr predicts Geirhildr's son will hang, st. 1.

The first stanza of the saga, which is a speech stanza beginning “Geirhilft getta / got er aul þetta,”¹⁴⁷⁵ is spoken in the prose by Alrekr (“þa quad Alrekr”).¹⁴⁷⁶ The stanza records to whom it is spoken, since the first line is in the vocative, “Geirhildr getta,” and then the speaker refers to themselves in the first person (“eg se hanga / æ hafum galga / son þin kona”),¹⁴⁷⁷ but does not otherwise reveal their identity. The second half of the stanza is thus a prophecy (one that is played out in *Gautreks saga*). In the saga prose, after the stanza comes “æ þeim misserum uar fæddr Uikar son Alreks ok Geirhildr,”¹⁴⁷⁸ identifying Alrekr as the father of Geirhildr's son. Otherwise, the content of the stanza relates to the surrounding prose only in the second line “gott er aul þetta”,¹⁴⁷⁹ the overall context being a brewing competition in which Óðinn demands, in return for Geirhildr's victory, what is between her and the pot. After the one line after the stanza, the prose turns its attention elsewhere.

Episodes two: a disembodied stanza, st. 2

The second stanza in the saga, beginning “Þat uar fyrer laungu / er leid helldu,”¹⁴⁸⁰ is a disembodied stanza coming from a burial mound, curiously as a reply to a question Finnur enn auðgi asks: “Finnur en auðg[e] af Akra nes í landnama madr la uid Odualldz nes ok buin til Íslanz ok spurdi huersu fyrer laungu Ogualldr kongr fell. hann heyrði uisu þessa kuedna i haugín.”¹⁴⁸¹ The stanza is also stanza 38 in *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*.

¹⁴⁷⁵ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 1, ll. 17-18.

¹⁴⁷⁶ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 1, l. 16.

¹⁴⁷⁷ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 1, ll. 21-23.

¹⁴⁷⁸ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 1, l. 25.

¹⁴⁷⁹ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 1, l. 18.

¹⁴⁸⁰ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 2, ll. 10-11.

¹⁴⁸¹ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 2, ll. 6-9.

The speaker from the mound answers the question by making reference to the viking Hæklingr and his men roaming a long time ago (“fyrer laungu”) and presumably killing Oǧvaldr. Although this is not explicitly stated in the stanza, this is how it appears to be understood in the prose, which tells the brief story of King Oǧvaldr from the beginning of the chapter. After the stanza, the saga moves on to tell about the foster parents of one of King Oǧvaldr’s children, Jǫsurr. This continuation makes the reader realise that the *landnámsmaðr* who heard the verse did so very much further forward in time. The stanza is thus part of a section of prolepsis in which a dead man speaks, rather than as part of the saga’s immediate narrative. It is not clear whether this episode was built on the basis of the verse, but clearly the fact that the man in the stanza recounts retrospective happenings causes the narrative to insert a section based in the narrative future (one which also has an authenticating function), although the future-episode is not contemporaneous with the saga writer’s audience.

Episode three: About the Water Monsters, stt. 3-12.

The third stanza, beginning “Geck þu fra brunni / gletta líttu uid mig,”¹⁴⁸² is said by King Hjørleifr as he sends off a supernatural creature. The stanza is introduced with “kong[r] quad”¹⁴⁸³ and the first line makes it clear that the stanza is addressed directly to someone, while in the fifth line the speaker refers to himself in the first person, although no names are mentioned that identify either the recipient or the speaker in the stanza. The immediate context of the prose matches the stanza in most respects. The prosimetric structure of the rest of the section is somewhat different because the remaining stanzas in the episode are all spoken by supernatural creatures.

The fourth stanza in the saga is spoken by a creature on a cliff, introduced with “kuad þuss af biargí annat hlíod”¹⁴⁸⁴ [‘the giant (supernatural creature) on the cliff said

¹⁴⁸² *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 172, ch. 2, ll. 54-55.

¹⁴⁸³ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 172, ch. 2, ll. 52-53.

¹⁴⁸⁴ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 172, ch. 2, l. 63.

another verse’], with the prose thus explicitly acknowledging that stanza that had come before. The utterances of the supernatural creatures from that point onwards are nevertheless all set within their own prose pieces, and as such are rather individual in nature. There is no attempt to connect the appearance of each supernatural creature with a prosimetric framework.

The fifth stanza is spoken by a “mikit fíall ok jafnt uaxit sem mann. þat quad.”¹⁴⁸⁵ The characters do not react to that stanza that it speaks. The seven stanzas spoken by the *marmendill* men drag out of the sea, however, are placed rather more firmly in a performance context, and as its verses are prophecies and ones that are given immediately and apparently with spite, they are listened to intently by its audience. The stanzas the creature speaks are introduced three times, and on each occasion the location of the creature is given in the prose. The first two stanzas come as a unit, stanza six beginning “Eg se lysa,”¹⁴⁸⁶ and in neither this unit of stanzas nor the next do prose insertions between the stanzas occur; in the next unit of stanzas he speaks four, after a minimal prose piece between to the two units that declares a change of location. Likewise, the prose between the second unit and the final stanza of the saga is very minimal, although it does report that a man asks the creature a question; this means that the final stanza (number 12, beginning “kallt uatn augum”)¹⁴⁸⁷ is introduced as an answer. All the stanzas in this episode are speech stanzas, although here there are no versified dialogues. The final stanza in the episode is a disembodied stanza that comes out of nowhere: “þann en sama aptan er Híorleifr kongr kom heyrðí Reidar kongr q(uedit)”¹⁴⁸⁸ [‘the same evening that king Hjórlleifr came, King Reiðarr heard recited’]. Nevertheless, there is no reaction to the stanza in the saga, and its moves on.

¹⁴⁸⁵ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 173, ch. 2, ll. 83-84.

¹⁴⁸⁶ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 174, ch. 3, l. 12.

¹⁴⁸⁷ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 175, ch. 3, ll. 55-62.

¹⁴⁸⁸ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 176, ch. 4, ll. 81-82.

Episode five: *Innsteinskviða*, stt. 14-37.

The prosimetric piece of *Innsteinskviða* is lengthy and likely formed an important building block for the construction of the saga itself. The dialogue found in the poem, framed by short pieces of prose, as well as prose speaker markings and prose connections for parts of the poem that take place at different points in time, are reminiscent of the eddic heroic poems. The framing that the poem undergoes, its short prose shifts, and the transmission of a good part of the dialogue of the scene in verse perhaps speaks to the oral nature of the poem. The first fifteen stanzas of the episode are an alternating dialogue between Innsteinn and the king (although Útsteinn does join in towards the end of the exchange).¹⁴⁸⁹ The content of the poem is advice and prophecy offered by Innsteinn to the king, who rejects it. But, the fact that this information about Innsteinn's prophetic dreams is offered in verse is perhaps a signal to the audience that his prophecy and advice is likely to be true.

Before stanza 29 and the unit of verses that follow it, there is a prose insertion that describes the men of King Hálfir waking up, realising the hall they are in is burning, and then going back to sleep, presumably to demonstrate their great heroism. Eventually Hálfir awakes, and stirs them to action. After this, the monologue of Innsteinn is introduced with “þa kuad Inst(einn).”¹⁴⁹⁰ It seems clear from the content of this monologue that Innsteinn's monologue properly belongs to a moment in time before King Hálfir wakes up. The comment in the heading prose about wax now dripping from swords seems to have been pulled from the first stanza, and in the second stanza Innsteinn speaks, it seems evident that the king is not yet awake. The proper role for the monologue thus seems to be as evidence stanzas rather than speech stanzas, nevertheless, the verbal spurrings that Innsteinn gives the men in stanzas 32-33 have probably prevented the monologue from being used as such.

¹⁴⁸⁹ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, pp. 179-183, ch. 6.

¹⁴⁹⁰ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 182, ch. 7, l. 10.

The next prose piece after the monologue describes how the men ran out the burning hall and were killed before an overwhelming force; the next stanza to be spoken is by Innsteinn as the king is killed: “Jnst(einn) q(uad) er kongr uar fallin” and a speech stanza is thus spoken. The introduction of the verse gives the stanza a reported quality rather than implying should be thought of as immediately part of the narrative context.

Following this single speech stanza comes a monologue of three stanzas from Innsteinn that again are speech stanzas but seem like they ought to be evidence stanzas. The prose reports that it was night “adr Jnst(einn) fell”¹⁴⁹¹ [‘before Innsteinn fell’], effectively reporting his death – and then the saga introduces verses he speaks and the saga moves on. The prosimetric structure here seems caught between one in which the speeches of men are offered as a kind of retrospective (common when heroes die, for example), and one in the style of the Starkaðr episode of *Gautreks saga* in which the voice of the hero comes through strongly, as it would seem the voice of Innsteinn does in this section of *Hálfs saga*, but nevertheless the stanzas are used for validation rather speech.

Episode six: *Utsteinnskviða*, stt. 38-52.

The beginning of *Utsteinnskviða* is curious: it is the report of Utsteinn in the first stanza of the episode (stanza 38, beginning “Hitt hlæger mig”)¹⁴⁹² that appears to gode Úlfur into a *mannjafnaðr* with Utsteinn. Úlfur’s sons cause Utsteinn misery, but “hítt uar fyr at Utst(einn) sagdí fra falli Alfs kongs, hann q(uad) þa”¹⁴⁹³ [‘that was before Utsteinn had told about the fall of King Hálfr, he said then:’]. This stanza is thus a report of what Utsteinn said to Úlfur. The prose uses this stanza as a reason for Úlfur

¹⁴⁹¹ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 185, ch. 8, l. 13.

¹⁴⁹² *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 186, ch. 9, ll. 6-13.

¹⁴⁹³ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 186, ch. 9, ll.

to taunt him more, and a piece of prose is inserted to explain this and to give the background to the exchange that is about to come: “Vtst(einn) q(uad) er Úlfur jafnadí ser uid hann ok eggiadi hann”¹⁴⁹⁴ [‘Usteinn said when Úlfur provoked him and egged him on’].

The initial exchange between Utsteinn and Úlfur lasts eight stanzas (stanzas 39-46),¹⁴⁹⁵ and the men trade insults until, for the final four stanzas, Utsteinn speaks in monologue. Unlike Insteinn’s stanzas, Utsteinn’s monologue verses are immediately relevant to the situation. Prose is introduced into the narrative to explain that Utsteinn then fights and slays all of Úlfur’s eight sons, something that is also included in the next verse (stanza 47), which the prose introduces as being spoken in front of King Eysteinn. The reply by King Eysteinn and the subsequent two stanza reply by Utsteinn are marked as normal speech stanzas. After the end of the Usteinn’s stanzas, the saga moves on.

Episode seven: *Hrókskviða*, stt. 53-80.

Hrókskviða is a lengthy monologue by Hrókr the Black, in which he reviews his life and laments his present condition. Although the content of the poetry itself is complex, the prosimetric structure of the episode is not, since it is simply a long monologue. The poem is nevertheless given a strong performance context: he does not simply the stanza, but rather is overheard: “hun heyrði at hann kvad”¹⁴⁹⁶ [‘she heard that he spoke’]. After the end of the poem, she reports this to her father who has Hrókr the Black recognised as a hero; thus the poem helps to affect a change in Hrókr’s reality.

¹⁴⁹⁴ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 186, ch. 6, l. 14.

¹⁴⁹⁵ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, pp. 187-188.

¹⁴⁹⁶ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 190, ch. 10, l. 9.

The content of the stanzas vary but a great deal of them reflect what has already been told in the prose of the saga. Another theme is respect for King Hálf, revenge, sadness at the way his situation has turned out and finally his love for Brynhildr, the woman who overhears the monologue. It is difficult to gauge whether the stanzas are secondary to the prose narrative in terms of the content it includes, or vice versa. The third option is that they were perhaps always part of the same narrative tradition, the retrospective poem by Hrókr the Black a form of autobiographical narrative validation as well as a speech in the saga, and has perhaps always existed as such in a prosimetric form. There is other evidence for the existence of long poems in saga narrative, most notably in oral form in the report of the wedding at Reykjahólar, as discussed, and as extant, for example, at the end of *Qrvar-Odds saga*. It is noteworthy that the monologue by Hrókr the Black contains no prose insertions whatsoever, and is completely in verse.

Episode eight: about Hámundr and Geirmundr heljarskin, st. 81.

The final chapter of the saga contains a stanza in which the parentage of Hámundr and Geirmundr is revealed; although not particularly interesting for its role in the saga as a speech stanza, the stanza gains a lot of weight through its speaker, the skald Bragi. It was perhaps the intention that through the connection with this skald that the stanza could be presumed to be true.

Hálfs saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

In *Hálfs saga*, the poetry is thus used in very specific contexts rather than as general standalone dialogue stanzas. *Lausavísur* unconnected to other stanzas are at a minimum: there are only two, one in which Alrekr foresees a Geirhildr's child being given to Óðinn,¹⁴⁹⁷ and the very last stanza in the saga,¹⁴⁹⁸ a *lausavísa* by the skaldic

¹⁴⁹⁷ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 170, ch. 1, ll. 17-24.

¹⁴⁹⁸ *Hálfs saga*, ed. Seelow, p. 198, ch. 11, 28-35.

poet Bragi inn gamli Boddason, who is envisaged in the saga as having been present, since he partakes in the action and speaks his verse as a situational stanza, which is nevertheless in an eddic metre. Eddic poetry is thus vital to the construction of *Hálfs saga*, and in its construction it is closer to sagas such as *Qrvar-Odds saga* and *Hervarar saga* than it is to other sagas in the romance category that are not formed by verses. *Gautreks saga*, though a romance and prosimetric, is built up rather differently.

Hálfs saga is rich in stanzas and contains several longer inset autobiographical poems. Episodes five, six and seven contain three long poems: *Innsteinskviða*, *Utsteinskviða*, and *Hrókskviða*. All three of these are life stories and form the nucleus around which the rest of the saga is built. These observations support the possibility that the poems:

may be older than the saga but are no earlier than the late twelfth or early thirteenth century, and which may – although this cannot be proven – have been created for an older version of the saga that did not contain the inconsistencies of detail to be observed between the verses and the prose text of the existing version.¹⁴⁹⁹

Certainly the existence in the saga of several long poems, especially the lengthy *Hrókskviða*, and the possibility of the lost **Hróks saga svartá*, are interesting. Certainly it is possible that the poems may have been composed for an older version of the saga, but the poems may have also been composed independently as stand alone pieces attached to certain heroic figures. This is most likely in the case of *Hrókskviða*, as it does not appear to be as dependant on the prose of the saga. Individual poems could also of course carry their own prose contexts in oral tradition, and it is possible that all three poems about Hálfr's heroes were once independent and were brought into the same orbit by a saga author in one narrative.

From *Hálfs saga* we can also suggest that eddic prosimetra of similar types could tend to cluster in the same saga. We can see this clearly in *Hálfs saga*, with three long retrospective poems. *Ketils saga hængs* contains a number of dialogues similar in style. *Hervarar saga* contains four long poems, and *Qrvar-Odds saga* contains two

¹⁴⁹⁹ Torfi H. Tulinius, *The Matter of the North*, p. 24.

death songs. If these sagas as a long narrative form have a background in the oral tradition, it might be that similar prosimetric episodes were recited together with a loose prose context to join them. These longer pieces could then be supplemented with *lausavísur*.

Gautreks saga

Gautreks saga is extant in two versions, a long and a short. The long *Gautreks saga* is made up of three *þættir*: *Gauta þáttr*, containing five stanzas, *Víkars þáttr*, a story about Starkaðr, containing most of the stanzas in the saga, and *Gjafa-Refs þáttr*, containing two stanzas. The shorter form does not contain *Víkars þáttr* and subsequently has far fewer stanzas. It is generally held that the shorter version, without much poetry, is older than the longer version that includes *Víkars þáttr*,¹⁵⁰⁰ and as such the longer is a reworking of the shorter version.¹⁵⁰¹ Massimiliano Bampi contends that “the saga writer has probably decided to insert *Víkars þáttr* into *Gautreks saga* because the story of Starkaðr was suitable to represent a further example of the themes the saga dealt with. In particular, the analogies between *Gjafa-Refs þáttr* and *Víkars þáttr* are rather interesting in that they represent stories of gift exchange with different outcomes.”¹⁵⁰² Marianne Kalinke and Michael Chestnutt have contended that it is the inclusion of *Víkars þáttr* that has led to the inclusion of *Gautreks saga* as whole in the *fornaldarsaga* subgenre; without the middle *þáttr* the saga is a *Märchen*, and thus the classification of the saga is dependant on which version is under consideration.¹⁵⁰³ *Víkarsbálkr* is thought to be amongst the oldest Old Norse poetry, dated by Heusler & Ranisch to the 11th century,¹⁵⁰⁴ and is another example of a form of death song in the *fornaldarsögur* or *ævidrápa* [‘poem about a life’]. The fact that the stanzas about Starkaðr are corroborative verses may be an indication of their age, since this is the

¹⁵⁰⁰ Wilhelm Ranisch, ed., *Die Gautrekssaga in zwei Fassungen*, Palaestra 11 (Berlin: Mayer & Müller, 1900) xxxv.

¹⁵⁰¹ Massimiliano Bampi, “Between Tradition and Innovation: the Story of Starkaðr in *Gautreks saga*,” *The Fantastic in Old Norse/Icelandic Literature. Sagas and the British Isles. Preprint Papers of the Thirteenth International Saga Conference. Durham and York 6th-12th August, 2006*, ed. John McKinnell, David Ashurt & Donata Kick, vol. 1 (Durham: Durham University, 2006) pp. 88-96, at 91.

¹⁵⁰² Bampi, “Between Tradition and Innovation: the Story of Starkaðr in *Gautreks saga*,” p. 91. For a comprehensive overview of the differences between the two versions, see *Die Gautrekssaga in zwei Fassungen*, ed. Wilhelm Ranisch, Palaestra 11 (Berlin: Mayer & Müller, 1900) xviii-xl.

¹⁵⁰³ Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” *Viking and Medieval Studies* 2 (2007): 275-296, at 276; Michael Chestnutt, “The Content and Meaning of *Gjafa-Refs saga*,” *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighed. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Agneta Ney, Ármann Jakobsson and Annette Lassen (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 93-106, at p. 95; Marianne Kalinke, “Endogamy as the Crux of the ‘Dalafífla þáttr’,” *Fornaldarsagaerne: Myter og virkelighed. Studier i de oldislandske fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Agneta Ney, Ármann Jakobsson and Annette Lassen (Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanums Forlag, 2009) pp. 107-121, at 109.

¹⁵⁰⁴ *Eddica minora*, xxxiii.

predominant use of stanzas in the *konungasögur*, a saga subgenre that was written down before the *fornaldarsögur*. This section of the saga was almost certainly composed around the stanzas. The stanzas in *Gauta þáttr* are used as speech stanzas, whereas of the two stanzas in *Gjafa-Refs þáttr*, one is a skaldic stanza spoken by Jarl Neri about a shield, introduced as a situational stanza (“Hann kvað þá vísu” [‘he spoke a verse’]),¹⁵⁰⁵ and the other is an eddic stanza spoken by an anonymous speaker, introduced simply with “þá var þetta kveðit” [‘then this was composed’].¹⁵⁰⁶

The edition followed here is Wilhelm Ranisch’s edition from 1900, in which he edits both versions.¹⁵⁰⁷ The long version of the saga is edited from the following manuscripts:¹⁵⁰⁸

- A = AM 590 b-c 4to, Copenhagen, Den Arnamagnæanske Samling (paper, 17th century)¹⁵⁰⁹
- b = Holm. 11, 8vo, Stockholm, Kungliga bibliotekt (paper, c. 1640)
- C = AM 152 I fol. (parchment, 15th century)¹⁵¹⁰

Ranisch concludes that these manuscripts go back to a common original, since they share a number of errors in common.¹⁵¹¹ As for the individual manuscripts, A (AM 590 b-c 4to) contains *Gautreks saga* (1r-10r) and its codicological companion *Hrólfs saga Gautrekssonar* (10r-44r). Ranisch considers A the best of the three manuscripts of the long version, since it has the fullest text, while b and C cut the text in several places.¹⁵¹² It seems likely that A is closely related to a copy of C, although to a

¹⁵⁰⁵ *Gautreks saga, Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsson, vol. 3 (Reykjavík: Bókaútgáfan Forni, 1944) pp. 3-41, at ch. 9, p. 32.

¹⁵⁰⁶ *Gautreks saga, Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsson, vol. 3 (Reykjavík: Bókaútgáfan Forni, 1944) pp. 3-41, at ch. 11, p. 38.

¹⁵⁰⁷ *Die Gautrekssaga in zwei Fassungen*, ed. Wilhelm Ranisch, Palaestra 11 (Berlin: Mayer & Müller, 1900).

¹⁵⁰⁸ *Gautrekssaga*, ed. Ranisch, p. i.

¹⁵⁰⁹ Kälund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 757.

¹⁵¹⁰ Kälund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 105.

¹⁵¹¹ *Gautrekssaga*, ed. Ranisch p. i-ii.

¹⁵¹² *Gautrekssaga*, ed. Ranisch p. ii.

parchment manuscript with a fuller text than that extant in C. There are no known copies of A nor manuscripts descended from it.¹⁵¹³

Manuscript b (Holm. 11, 8vo) is close to A considering the prose of the saga, but it lacks 28 of the 39 stanzas in the saga. That the stanzas are omitted rather than any other cause for their disappearance (e.g. a different version of the saga) is shown by the fact that the introductory formula for the stanzas, *Svó segir Starkaðr*, is in most cases retained.¹⁵¹⁴ There are four secondary manuscripts associated with b and used by Ranisch.¹⁵¹⁵

Manuscript C, AM 152 I fol., contains *Gautreks saga* on 196v-201v, and is the oldest extant record of the long version of the saga. Whilst the scribe of C handles the prose part of the saga more freely than Ab, Ranisch points out he is more conservative than the scribe of b with the stanzas: he omits 14, all of which are also omitted in b.¹⁵¹⁶

As for the short version, Ranisch deduces four manuscripts of interest:¹⁵¹⁷

- L = AM 194 c fol. (paper) (17th century)¹⁵¹⁸
- M = Holm. 1 fol. (paper) (1640-50)
- E = AM 567 XIV γ 4to (fragment, parchment) (c. 1400)¹⁵¹⁹
- K = AM 164 h fol. (paper) (pre-1655)¹⁵²⁰

¹⁵¹³ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p ii.

¹⁵¹⁴ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p ii.

¹⁵¹⁵ That they are related to B can be seen because they share the same prose, omit the same verses and have the same differences in the story. These manuscripts are Holm. 17 4to (paper) (sigla β), AM 194 a fol. (paper) (sigla B), Holm. 6 4to (paper), and ÍB 76 4to (paper). Holm. 17 4to is a true copy of b, and maintains even the redundant introductory phrases for the excluded stanzas. See *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p iii-vi.

¹⁵¹⁶ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p vii. For the manuscripts related to C, see vii-viii.

¹⁵¹⁷ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p xiii-xv.

¹⁵¹⁸ Kålund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 161.

¹⁵¹⁹ Kålund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 725.

¹⁵²⁰ Kålund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 134 has first part of the 17th century.

L and M are descended from the same exemplar, and of this pair L is used as the primary manuscript with M as a corrective. L is the only complete manuscript of the group. As discussed above, *Gauta þáttr*, and *Gjafa-Refs þáttr* are present, while *Vikars þáttr* is absent.¹⁵²¹ It is a 17th century manuscript, and the saga is found on 1r-7r. E is a parchment manuscript of 5 leaves, dated to 1390-1410, that is sometimes quite difficult to read.¹⁵²² Fragmentary, it begins at the nighttime conversation between Gauti and the farmer's daughter, and then contains the end of *Gauta þáttr* and the beginning of *Gjafa-Refs þáttr*.¹⁵²³ K is a paper manuscript from 1600-1650, and *Gautreks saga* in the shorter version is found on 1r-3r.

The first section of the saga to contain verse is in the story of the king Gauti, who visits a parsimonious family, whose members throw themselves from a cliff when they think they have wasted money or committed some other transgression. There are five stanzas quoted, all cited as speech stanzas. The first stanza is lacking in L (a manuscript of the short version), and begins “Skúa tvó,”¹⁵²⁴ after being introduced with “þá kvað konungr.” Interestingly, this stanza is not addressed to anyone, and is simply a comment by the king on the treatment he has received. After the stanza is spoken, it is not reacted to and the saga simply moves on. Such a use of a stanza is more typical in skaldic stanzas used as evidence verses as the end of saga scenes.

The second stanza however is placed in a strong performance context. The stanza, which begins “Heimsliga,”¹⁵²⁵ is introduced with “Gillingr kvað” (in b, a long version, “vísu” is added), and is said by him in response to his family's decision that he has transgressed their rule. It seems to be addressed to them, and they respond

¹⁵²¹ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p xv.

¹⁵²² *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p xvi.

¹⁵²³ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p xvi.

¹⁵²⁴ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 6, ll. 16-21.

¹⁵²⁵ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 8, ll. 18-21 – p. 9, ll. 1-2.

appropriately in the prose following the stanza, telling him not to worry about his deed, the content of which he had expressed in the verse.¹⁵²⁶

The third stanza is also a speech stanza, but it lacks in L (short version), and lines 3-6 lack in EK (short version).¹⁵²⁷ It begins “Stuttir sniglar,”¹⁵²⁸ and is an additional thought in verse to what the narrator has already talked about in reported speech, so here we can see the verse used as direct speech to round off the scene. The fourth stanza, beginning “þat var spell,”¹⁵²⁹ is also a speech stanza, but is a comment on an event that the speaker has observed. Stanza five is spoken in a similar context. It begins “Ungr sveinn” and is introduced with “þá kvað hann,”¹⁵³⁰ but is continued in the prose with more direct speech which is introduced again with “Hann mælti” even though it is the same speaker.¹⁵³¹

The prosimetric construction of the section in which Starkaðr’s lifestory is recounted is an interesting one. On the one hand the prose tells a story independently, on the other, much of the richness and texture of the narrative is contributed by the stanzas that are reported as having been spoken by Starkaðr. The first stanza, beginning “þá var ek ungr,”¹⁵³² is introduced with “svó segir Starkaðr frá” [‘Starkaðr speaks thusly about it’].¹⁵³³ Typically, of evidence stanzas, it ends the scene within which it is placed. The stanza itself repeats what has been told in the narrative, as with most of the stanzas quoted as being spoken by Starkaðr, and it seems plain that the prose narrative

¹⁵²⁶ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 9, ll. 3-4.

¹⁵²⁷ In K there is, however, an alternate strophe given; see *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 9 in the notes.

¹⁵²⁸ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 9, ll. 19-20 – p. 10, ll. 1-4.

¹⁵²⁹ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 10, ll. 11-16.

¹⁵³⁰ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 10, ll. 21-24 – p. 11, ll. 1-3.

¹⁵³¹ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 11, l. 4.

¹⁵³² *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 13, ll. 11-22 – p. 14, ll. 1-2.

¹⁵³³ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 13, ll. 9-10.

lifts its information directly from these stanzas. Nevertheless, the evidential role of the stanzas adds interest to the story, and, as the stanzas are said to be spoken by Starkaðr and the story is about him, this adds an extra level of veracity to the narrative, since it functions as an autobiographical validation of the narrative.

A notable point about the prosimetrum that cites Starkaðr is that even though his voice is used in the verses, there is no direct dialogue in the narrative and minimal reported speech, and we never otherwise hear Starkaðr's voice apart from in the verse. The evidence stanzas thus seem to almost function as speech stanzas, their potential as speech heightened by the lack of dialogue in the prose narrative.

The second and third stanzas of the episode are introduced in the same manner as the first, as evidence stanzas.¹⁵³⁴ The third stanza is actually the top of a unit of three stanzas, none of which have prose insertions between them. It is also remarkable that after the end of the third stanza of the unit (the eleventh of the saga, beginning “Hann mældi mik”)¹⁵³⁵ the narrative reflects on what the verse, the words of Starkaðr, tell us: “Hér segir Starkaðr frá því, at hann hafði þá skegg er hann var tólf vetra” [‘Here Starkaðr tells about how he had a beard when he was twelve winters old’].¹⁵³⁶ Here the prose narrative seems to make it obvious that it takes information from the verse. The prose related to the stanza that comes after the verse does not describe an event but rather another salient point in the stanzas that the saga author wishes to highlight. The event that the verse describes comes before it, as usual.

Stanzas four to twelve of the episode (stanzas 12-20 of the saga) and stanzas fourteen to twenty (stanzas 22-28 of the saga) are all introduced with “svó segir Starkaðr,”¹⁵³⁷ and stanzas 12-13, 17-18 and 22-23 are units, with no prose insertions. The 21st stanza of the saga has a slightly different introductory formula: “Þess getr

¹⁵³⁴ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 14, ll. 15-26 – p. 15, ll. 1-4; p. 15, ll. 20-27.

¹⁵³⁵ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 16, ll. 9-16.

¹⁵³⁶ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 16, ll. 17-18.

¹⁵³⁷ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, pp. 16-21.

Starkaðr, at sú var hin þriðja orrosta Víkars konungs, er hann hafði unnit á Upplöndum” [‘Starkaðr mentions this, that that was the third battle of King Víkars that he had won in Uppland’].¹⁵³⁸ Here the prose draws attention to what the reader should notice in the stanza. This is unusual in this saga, and indicates that the stanza does not function fully as an evidence verse.

The stanzas feature at rather regular intervals in this part of the saga, which is to be expected if the prose narrative explains them then uses them as evidence. There is however, one stanza several pages of the edition further on, and this stanza too is introduced as “sem hann segir,”¹⁵³⁹ and the stanza finishes the scene in which it is placed.

The next episode in which poetry occurs is related but structured differently to the section before it. In this section, what poetry is recited is a deliberately composed poem: “Ok er Alrekr spurði Starkað, hvat hann kunni tíðinda at segja frá frændum sínum eða sjálfum sér, þá orti Starkaðr kvæði, þat er heitir Víkarsbálkr; þar segir svó frá drápi Víkars konungs” [‘When Alrekr asked Starkaðr what he could tell about his kinsmen or about himself, then Starkaðr composed a poem, that which is called Víkarsbálkr; here tells about the killing of King Víkarr’].¹⁵⁴⁰ The stanzas are quoted as an example of the poem Starkaðr has composed. Starkaðr presumably chose to express himself in poetry to assign himself, his family and acquaintances a higher than normal status. The five stanzas quoted at this point are not in the saga said to come out of Starkaðr’s mouth as such, but rather are a quotation about his sorrowful reaction to the killing of King Víkarr, which he did himself.¹⁵⁴¹ The prose after the stanzas comments on them: “Þat má finna á Starkaði, at honum þikir þetta eitthvert verk sitt

¹⁵³⁸ *Gautrekssaga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 22, ll. 9-11.

¹⁵³⁹ *Gautrekssaga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 27, l. 24; the stanza is p. 28, ll. 1-8.

¹⁵⁴⁰ *Gautrekssaga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 31, ll. 2-5.

¹⁵⁴¹ The stanzas can be found *Gautrekssaga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 31, ll. 6-25 – p. 32, ll. 1-18.

vest ok óskapligast orðit hafa, er hann drap Víkar konung, ok ekki hǫfum vér frásagnir heyrðar, at hann hafi ílendr orðit í Nóregi síðan” [‘It must be concluded from [what] Starkaðr [said], at to him it seemed his worst deed and the most evil thing to have done, when he killed King Víkarr, and we have not heard any stories that he settled in Norway afterwards’].¹⁵⁴² The prose acknowledges the poem’s ability to express strong emotion, and it also demonstrates that conclusions were made about events on the basis of stanzas.

The final three stanzas in the section of *Gautreks saga* about Starkaðr are evidence verses introduced with “svó sem hér segir” as his earlier verses were during the narrator’s account of his lifestory.¹⁵⁴³ This section seems akin to these earlier verses, and is used as evidence to corroborate the prose description of the misery that Starkaðr endured at the hands of mean berserkers. These three stanzas are only in A (long version). The saga moves on after the stanzas, as is typical of the prosimetric use of evidence stanzas. It seems in the sections of the saga structured in this manner, the narrator gives several deliberate displays of his ability to interpret poetry and to build a narrative around verses.

There are two stanzas in the section of *Gautreks saga* that comes after the exit of Starkaðr from the story, and both are connected with the theme of gifts and wealth, much like the stanzas in the initial *þáttr* of the saga. The first stanza is stanza 38 of the saga and begins “Skein enn skrautligi raunar.”¹⁵⁴⁴ As a speech stanza that is part of the story, the jarl reacts to his own utterance in the saga, by turning his highseat away from the gap on the wall left by a given-away shield he lamented in the stanza. The final stanza in the saga is unusual in that it is a speech stanza without a speaker given:

¹⁵⁴² *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 32, ll. 19-22.

¹⁵⁴³ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 33, l. 2.

¹⁵⁴⁴ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 38, ll. 11-18.

“Þá var þetta kveðit.”¹⁵⁴⁵ Nevertheless, it provokes a favourable reaction in prose, and so was clearly said to be heard.

The prosimetric structure of *Gautreks saga* is clearly strongest in the section on Starkaðr. Without this middle section, the short version of the saga is really lacking in stanzas, and the ones that do occur are on the whole unremarkable as speech stanzas.¹⁵⁴⁶

Gautreks saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

From the shorter version of *Gautreks saga*, we can perhaps suggest again that stanzas used similarly may cluster together in saga narrative – that is, stanzas with similar roles may be nearby each other. This trend was also visible in *Fagrskinna*, where stanzas used in a similar fashion could sometimes be seen to occur in the same part of the saga. To form the longer version of *Gautreks saga*, the *lausavísur* were supplemented by a long prosimetric episode. We can see from this that such an eddic prosimetric scene as Starkaðr’s episode could exist independently and later be added to a saga. A separate origin to the rest of the saga could also be posited for poems such as *Hlǫðskviða* and Hjálmar’s death song.

If Starkaðr’s episode is genuinely an old prosimetric piece, it might also suggest that eddic stanzas that are both quasi-evidential and quasi-speech stanzas in a prose context are an old form and could have a background in oral tradition. It might be suggested that here we can even see a stage in the development from the evidence based role of verse in the *konungasögur* be replaced by the story-stanza that is more common in the *fornaldarsögur*.

¹⁵⁴⁵ *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, p. 45, l. 12.

¹⁵⁴⁶ This short version can be found edited *Gautreks saga*, ed. Ranisch, pp. 50-73.

Hjálmþes saga ok Ölvis

*Hjálmþes saga ok Ölvis*¹⁵⁴⁷ is heavily prosimetric, containing forty seven stanzas, but this saga is rather late, found in 17th to 19th century manuscripts.¹⁵⁴⁸ It is dated earlier on the basis of *Hjálmþérsrímur*, a 15th century analogue, but the development of the saga itself and its form is obscure.¹⁵⁴⁹ The most notable thing about the prosimetrum of *Hjálmþérs saga* is that it is unremarkable. The introductions are standard and there is very little performance context for the stanzas other than they are all used as dialogue. The most notable thing about the saga is in fact its lengthy dialogues, but there is nothing special about them other than this. This entirely regular use of the prosimetric structure may be as a result of this version of saga being late, when the conventions of prosimetra in the *fornaldarsögur* were well-established and old enough to be stereotyped.

The first episode with verse in the saga has two speech stanzas, which are a demand for identification and a reply. In the first stanza, beginning “Huorier eru skälker,”¹⁵⁵⁰ a man standing on a dragon ship demands the names of the leaders of Hjálmpér’s group and declares he will kill them, only for Hjálmpér to retort with his name, to demand the first man’s identity and then to declare that he will kill him. The saga does not comment on the stanzas afterwards, and their verbal duel continues in prose.

¹⁵⁴⁷ *Hjálmþes saga ok Ölvis, Fornaldarsögur Norðurlanda*, ed. Guðni Jónsson & Bjarni Vilhjálmsón, vol. 3 (Reykjavík: Bókaútgáfan Forni, 1944) pp.231-282.

¹⁵⁴⁸ A full overview of the manuscripts of the saga and a suggestion for their stemma is given in Richard Lynn Harris, *Hjálmþérs saga: A Scientific Edition*, Ph.D thesis, The University of Iowa, 1970. Quotations of the saga will be taken from this edition, and translations into English.

¹⁵⁴⁹ Ralph O’Connor, ““Stepmother sagas,” An Irish Analogue for *Hjálmþérs saga ok Ölvérs*,” *Scandinavian Studies* 72 (2000): 1-48, at 1-2.

¹⁵⁵⁰ *Hjálmþérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 11, ll. 9-11.

The second prosimetric episode is also a dialogue in stanzas 3-10 of the saga, and this a typical *fornaldarsaga* dialogue in which a human exchanges words with a supernatural creature. As Hjálmpér is somewhat dumbstruck upon the appearance of the female creature, the first stanza is introduced thus: “hann hugsar nu med sier, ad eckj skule honum ordfall verda og quad vijsu” [‘He thinks to himself so that he shall not be struck dumb and spoke a verse’].¹⁵⁵¹ The prose thus makes clear that there is a thought process behind even exemptorised verses. In addition, Hjálmpér is shown to deliberately start a poetic exchange with the supernatural woman, “eitt finngälkn miked.”¹⁵⁵² The first stanza is a demand for her to identify herself, and she answers in a regular speech stanza introduced with “hun quad,”¹⁵⁵³ his reply to this introduced with a similarly conventional “hann quad.”¹⁵⁵⁴ The sixth stanza, in which the hag demands a kiss from Hjálmpér, is introduced with the formula “henne vard þä liöd ä munne” [‘then a song came to her lips’],¹⁵⁵⁵ a formula often used to introduce prophecies spoken by females and perhaps used ironically here. Stanza seven is again introduced conventionally with “quad vijsu.”¹⁵⁵⁶ Stanzas eight and nine are two stanzas that come together, stanza eight beginning “Sel eg þier Snarvendil,”¹⁵⁵⁷ although the two stanzas are separated by a prose insertion of “og enn quad hun.”¹⁵⁵⁸ The episode then continues in prose, employing a tenth stanza in order to close the scene; again the formula “vard henne nu liöd ä munne” [‘then a song came to her lips’]¹⁵⁵⁹ is used, and after the stanza the characters do not exchange any more words and the episode ends.

¹⁵⁵¹ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 24, ll. 19-20; p. 138.

¹⁵⁵² *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 24, l. 14.

¹⁵⁵³ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 24, l. 24.

¹⁵⁵⁴ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 25, l. 1.

¹⁵⁵⁵ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 25, ll. 12-13; 139.

¹⁵⁵⁶ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 25, l. 21.

¹⁵⁵⁷ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 26, ll. 5-13.

¹⁵⁵⁸ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 26, ll. 8-9.

¹⁵⁵⁹ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 27, ll. 5-6.

This use of a stanza to conclude an episode is typical of sagas that employ many evidence stanzas, but more unusual when the stanza is speech.

The third episode, stanzas 11 to 21, is a long one also involving prosimetric dialogue between Hjálmpér and a number of large troll women. The eleventh stanza, which initiates the dialogue, is a standard type of stanza spoken by Hjálmpér demanding identification of the huge troll woman he has seen and insulting her; the stanza is introduced with “H(iälmþer) quad vjisu”¹⁵⁶⁰ and her reply is said to be spoken in anger, but is introduced with a standard “og kuad,”¹⁵⁶¹ and Hjálmpér’s answer her to is introduced identically. Thus far the dialogue has been a standard exchange, although now the narration switches temporarily to prose, in which the troll asks Hjálmpér for sex, and he hacks off her hand in reply. In the prose piece is one stanza (number 14, beginning “Vjst gledur mig eitt”)¹⁵⁶² in which she points out to Hjálmpér that her hideous sisters will kill all his men. The stanza is introduced with “þä quad hun,” and is followed by the prose realisation of her promise, as her trollish sisters emerge, and Hjálmpér makes a swift exit from the mountain he is on when he encounters the troll woman.

Hergunnur, one of the troll women, speaks the fifteenth stanza, which is introduced as standard with “þä quad Hergunnur vjisu,”¹⁵⁶³ and marks the return of the section back to prosimetrum. This is continued in a series of stanzas in which Hjálmpér, Ölver and several of the troll women exchange insults and threats in a section of six stanzas which is purely standard dialogue¹⁵⁶⁴ with minimal prose inbetween the stanzas. The final stanza in the scene is one in which one troll woman

¹⁵⁶⁰ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 30, l. 11.

¹⁵⁶¹ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 30, l. 15.

¹⁵⁶² *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 31, ll. 13-16.

¹⁵⁶³ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 32, l. 11.

¹⁵⁶⁴ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, pp. 32, ll. 11-25 – p. 33, ll. 1-14.

pleads for assistance from another (beginning “Huar ertu Margerdur”),¹⁵⁶⁵ a high point in the other wise prose ending of the episode.

The fourth episode in the saga is highly prosimetric, although the dialogue is very unremarkable. This section encompasses stanzas 22- 40, and the majority of introduced through very standard formulae with little reaction in the text. There is only one feature of note in the first exchange of four stanzas between Hjálmpér and Hervor, a maiden he is trying to woo,¹⁵⁶⁶ and that is that when she speaks two stanzas in a row, the second is introduced with “og enn quad hun,”¹⁵⁶⁷ which is a typical linking phrase between stanzas. Their encounter concludes with two more stanzas spoken by Hervor, which are notable because between them comes direct speech in prose, continuing the advice she gives to Hjálmpér in the stanzas before and after it (stanzas 26 and 27).¹⁵⁶⁸ Although the stanzas are explicitly introduced as verse, it could be supposed that the prose piece inbetween them was perhaps also once metrical.

The episode continues with Hjálmpér’s exchange with her father, the king. This exchange in verse is one of the lengthiest in the legendary sagas, stretching from stanza 28 to stanza 40.¹⁵⁶⁹ In this section, slightly more performance context is given for the stanzas. Stanza 28, which begins “Heill sit þu Hunding,”¹⁵⁷⁰ is said to be spoken in greeting as Hjálmpér walks into the hall, and it is noted that this is well-received and is replied to in turn with a stanza. In the prose surrounding stanza 39, the displeasure of its speaker is made apparent as he is made to move from his seat for the

¹⁵⁶⁵ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 33, l. 25.

¹⁵⁶⁶ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 38.

¹⁵⁶⁷ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 38, l. 12.

¹⁵⁶⁸ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 39, ll. 14-25.

¹⁵⁶⁹ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 156 – p. 159.

¹⁵⁷⁰ *Hjálmpérs saga*, ed. Harris, p. 40, ll. 5-8.

new arrival, which serves to anger the king who replies with the fortieth stanza.¹⁵⁷¹ Otherwise, as a prosimetric dialogue the piece in this saga is entirely unremarkable except in its unusual length.

The fifth episode to contain verse is unusual in this particular saga because it contains only one stanza. The forty-first stanza, beginning “Berum ä bake ockru,”¹⁵⁷² is a speech stanza spoken by Hjálmpér in which he swears that he will give the man Hǫrður a dignified burial and that they will carry him as necessary. This is at a moment of extreme emotion in the saga, so much so that blood spurts from underneath Hjálmpér’s nails and from his nose, and this appears to be the reason why he suddenly speaks in verse, although his speech continues directly after the stanza in prose.

The final prosimetric episode is a recognition scene in which the magical maidens are revealed to have aided the heroes at various points and the king of the outstanding hall Hjálmpér and Ölver enter turns out to be the live Hǫrður. This covers stanzas 42-47.¹⁵⁷³ Again, the dialogue of the prosimetricum is unremarkable. Stanza is responded to with stanza. There is one unusual introduction spoken before stanza 42b: he “quad hálfa vjjsuna,”¹⁵⁷⁴ when speaking only half a stanza does not usually prompt acknowledgement in the prose.

Hjálmpés saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

As I suggested above, the structure of *Hjálmpés saga* is probably a result of the stereotyping of the eddic prosimetric tradition by the 17th century. With the exaggeration of the traditional features of the prosimetric *fornaldarsaga*, nuance and

¹⁵⁷¹ *Hjálmpés saga*, ed. Harris, p. 42, ll. 8-17.

¹⁵⁷² *Hjálmpés saga*, ed. Harris, p. 57, ll. 11-14.

¹⁵⁷³ *Hjálmpés saga*, ed. Harris, p. 59 – 60.

¹⁵⁷⁴ *Hjálmpés saga*, ed. Harris, p. 59, l. 19.

texture in the narrative has been lost, even though stanzas have been included. This is largely down to the very standard and unexciting ways in which they are used. For the length of the saga, there are almost too many stanzas. It is, however, interesting to note which features this late saga author thought typical of the *fornaldarsaga* subgenre and sought to employ to such an extreme degree. The most obvious is the prosimetric dialogue, both with a supernatural creature and then with a woman he is trying to woo and her father. There are no other examples of an eddic dialogue in which a man tries to woo a woman. Another typical role of verse in *fornaldarsögur* which the saga picks up on is shown right at the beginning of the saga, when verse is used to demand the name of a man, and threats follow. These two uses of eddic prosimetrum seem to have become very entrenched in the tradition of the *fornaldarsaga*.

Bósa saga ok Herraud̄s

Bósa saga is thought to have been composed around 1350 and exists in two quite different recensions. The older recension is found in 15th century vellum manuscripts, while the later recension is found in paper manuscripts from the 17th and 18th centuries. The saga has a complicated textual history and was very popular until recent times.¹⁵⁷⁵

The discussion here follows the edition of the two versions of the saga edited by Otto Luitpold Jiriczek.¹⁵⁷⁶ Jiriczek uses six manuscripts for his edition of the older version,¹⁵⁷⁷ as follows (with the sigla he assigns):¹⁵⁷⁸

A = AM 586 4to, 12v-19r (parchment), 1450-1499.¹⁵⁷⁹

B = AM 343 a 4to, 103v-104v (two fragments) (parchment), 1450-1475.¹⁵⁸⁰

C = AM 510 4to, 8v-21r (parchment), 1540-1560.¹⁵⁸¹

D = AM 577 4to, 50r-63r (parchment), 1450-1499.¹⁵⁸²

¹⁵⁷⁵ The textual tradition for the saga is outlined by *Die Bósa-saga in zwei Fassungen nebst proben aus den Bósa-Rímur*, ed. Otto Luitpold Jiriczek (Strassburg: Karl J. Trübner, 1893), for the older recension see pp. ix-xxxvii, and for the younger recension see pp. xxxviii-viii. For a summary, see Hans Peter Naumann, "Bósa saga (Herraud̄s saga ok Bósa)," *Medieval Scandinavia: An Encyclopedia*, ed. Philip Pulsiano et al., Garland Encyclopedias of the Middle Ages 1, Garland Reference Library of the Humanities 934 (New York: Garland, 1993) p. 54.

¹⁵⁷⁶ *Die Bósa-saga in zwei Fassungen nebst proben aus den Bósa-Rímur*, ed. Otto Luitpold Jiriczek (Strassburg: Karl J. Trübner, 1893).

¹⁵⁷⁷ He also lists the "wertlose" paper manuscripts and those containing translations, excerpts and those that were inaccessible to him; *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek pp. ix-xi.

¹⁵⁷⁸ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. ix.

¹⁵⁷⁹ Thus dated on *Handrit.is*, <<http://handrit.is/en/manuscript/view/is/AM04-0586>>. Kålund has 15th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 747.

¹⁵⁸⁰ Thus dated on *Handrit.is*, <<http://handrit.is/en/manuscript/view/is/AM04-0343>>. Kålund has 15th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 578.

¹⁵⁸¹ Thus dated on *Handrit.is*, <<http://handrit.is/en/manuscript/view/is/AM04-0510>>. Kålund has the close of 15th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 670.

¹⁵⁸² Thus dated on *Handrit.is*, <<http://handrit.is/en/manuscript/view/is/AM04-0577>>. Kålund has the close of 15th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 739.

b = AM 340 4to, 131v-147v (paper), 1600-1700.¹⁵⁸³

d = AM 361 II 4to, 1r-5v (fragment) (paper), 1600-1700.¹⁵⁸⁴

The younger version is edited from the following manuscripts:¹⁵⁸⁵

α = AM 360 b 4to (paper), 1663.

β = AM 360 a 4to (paper), beginning of the 18th century.¹⁵⁸⁶

γ = AM 345 4to (paper), 1695.

δ = AM 362 4to (paper), c. 1700.¹⁵⁸⁷

NKS 1701 and 1767 4to, copied at the end of the 18th century from γ and δ .

ÍB 295 4to (fragment) (paper), 1804.

ÍB 297 4to (fragment) (paper), mid-18th century.

Papp. 4to nr 1, Kungliga biblioteket, Stockholm (fragment) (paper), 17th century.

Both recensions of the saga contain stanzas in the same distribution, although the stanzas themselves have remarkable differences between them.¹⁵⁸⁸ In the older version of the saga the nine stanzas are said to be from two different poems, eight

¹⁵⁸³ Thus dated on *Handrit.is*, <<http://handrit.is/en/manuscript/view/is/AM04-0340>>. Kálund has 17th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 576. Kálund has 17th century, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 586.

¹⁵⁸⁴ Thus dated on *Handrit.is*, <<http://handrit.is/en/manuscript/view/is/AM04-0361>>.

¹⁵⁸⁵ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. xviii.

¹⁵⁸⁶ Thus dated by Kálund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 586.

¹⁵⁸⁷ Thus dated by Kálund, *KAH* vol. 1, p. 587.

¹⁵⁸⁸ At the end of his edition, Jiriczek also includes two apocryphal 19th century versions of *Buslubæn* (pp. 141-144) that are not considered here.

stanzas of *Buslubæn* [‘Busla’s prayer’] and one stanza of *Syrpuvers* (regarded by Johnni Langer, however, as merely the final and ninth strophe of *Buslubæn*).¹⁵⁸⁹ The stanzas are different in the younger version, and neither they nor the character called Busla in the older version are named (she is simply referred to as the “kelling” in the younger version).

In the older version, the stanzas appear in a section in which King Hringr has imprisoned his son Herrauðr and his friend Bósi. He offers to spare Herrauðr, but Herrauðr will not accept this unless Bósi is also spared, which angers his father greatly.¹⁵⁹⁰ It is related earlier in the saga that Bósi’s father, Þvari, has a concubine called Busla, an old woman who fosters his sons Bósi and Smiðr:

Busla hét kelling, hún hafði verit frilla Þvara [÷ b] kallz; hún fóstraði sonu hans [kallz, þvíat D]; hún kunnni margt í töfrum. Smiðr var henni miklu eptirlátari ok nam han margt af henni [í töfrum D]. Hún bauð Bósa [÷ b] at kenna honum [Bósa b] galdra, en Bósi [hann b] sagðizt eigi vilja, at þat væri skrifat í sögu hans [sinni D], at hann ynni nökkurn hlut með sleitum, þann sem honum skyldi með kallmennzku telja.¹⁵⁹¹

Since Þvari refuses to do anything about Bósi’s imprisonment and impending execution by King Hringr, Busla takes matters into her own hands and, as the *bæn* shows, employs her magic in *fornyrðislag*.¹⁵⁹²

In the older version, the body of the *bæn* (which is more of a curse) is introduced thus:

Þetta kveld hit sama kom Busla í þat [sama b] herbergi, sem Hringr [÷ Hringr D] konungr sváf í, ok hóf upp bæn þá, er síðan er kölluð Buslubæn, ok hefir hún víðfræg orðit síðan, ok eru þar í mörg orð ok ill [ok ill ÷ bCD], þau sem kristnum mönnum er þarfleysa í munni at hafa; en þó er þetta upphaf á henni...¹⁵⁹³

¹⁵⁸⁹ Johnni Langer, “*Galdr e Feitiçaria nas Sagas Islandesas: Uma Análise do Poema Buslubæn*,” *Braithair* 9 (2009): 66-90, at 74. <<http://ppg.revistas.uema.br/index.php/brathair/article/view/483/400>>.

¹⁵⁹⁰ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. 14, ll. 15 – p. 15, ll. 1-7.

¹⁵⁹¹ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. 6, ll. 16-21 – p. 7, ll. 1-2.

¹⁵⁹² *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. 15, ll. 7-16.

¹⁵⁹³ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. 15, ll. 16-22.

The prose is not necessarily assigning authorship of the *bæn* to Busla, just that afterwards it was called after her. The prose also makes it clear that this is only beginning of the poem, as quoted above. The manuscripts differ somewhat on the formulation of the introduction. Instead of “en þó er þetta upphaf á henni,” D has a similar “ok þetta er upphaf á,” whereas in b is found “ok þetta er bænin, svó mikít sem skrifuð er ok hér eptir fylgir,” and in C: “en hér stendr hún skrifuð.”¹⁵⁹⁴ Manuscripts bC have different emphases on the preservation and amount of the *bæn* recorded. The introduction in manuscript b acknowledges that the saga only records as much of the prayer as is written down (which is self-evident); however, this could also be understood as meaning as much as was written down even in relation to the time at which Busla recited it. The saga author will not commit to writing that which has not been written before, perhaps the more powerful part of the prayer/curse was thought dangerous to have written down. C introduces the stanzas it quotes as the whole of the *bæn*, and does not imply that it might not be complete.

The first lot of poetry is a run of seven stanzas. The first stanza of *Buslubæn* refers to the context in which she is standing as she recites the *bæn* and to the reason she is there:

Hér liggur Hringur konungur, hilmir Gauta,
einráðaztr allra manna;
ætla þú son þinn sjálfur at myrða;
þau munu fádæmi fréttast víða.¹⁵⁹⁵

The king is said to be lying in the stanza because in the prose, as the introduction to the stanza says, she is in his bedroom and so we can assume that the king is in bed. Busla alludes to the fact that, as things stand, the king's own son as well as her foster son Bósi will die at the king's command, and that news of this deed will travel widely. This links to the second stanza, in which Busla states her prayer “at [÷ b] heyrast skal um heim allan” [‘will be heard throughout the whole world’],¹⁵⁹⁶ the spread of her

¹⁵⁹⁴ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. 15.

¹⁵⁹⁵ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek p. 16, st. 1, ll. 1-4.

¹⁵⁹⁶ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 16, st. 2, l. 7.

magic equalling the spread of the gossip about the king; this emphasises both her might and the consequences this might have for the king in terms of his reputation. The second part of the second stanza is more threatening: “ok óþörf öllum þeim sem á heyra, / en þeim þó fjandliguzt, sem ek vil fortala.”¹⁵⁹⁷ All those who will hear will be, as she has said, the whole world, and “sem ek vil fortala” announces that she must continue her speech. The poem itself thus provides the context for the curses it contains, and locates its audience. This awareness in the narrative of its purpose continues throughout stanzas three to six, since they combine a threat with a reminder to the king that to avoid this, he ought to let both his son and Bósi free. Stanzas three to six all have similar sounding formulas to express Busla’s condition the men ought to left in peace, which adds a forceful cadence to the curse. At the end of the seventh stanza, the repetition of the demand the men be freed is not repeated; instead she asks, “villzt þú þá [villtz þú þá A; villstu þá b; villzt þú þá C; villr ert þú D] vegarins [+ ok far í rassinn C]; eða viltu þulu lengri?”¹⁵⁹⁸ In the saga there is then prose between these stanzas of *Buslubæn* and the next. Since the king will not give into her demands, more powerful magic must be used:

Busla lét þá frammi annan þriðjung bænarinnar, ok mun ek láta þat [÷ bCD] [um líða at skrifa hann [hjá líða hann at skrifa b], [því þat er öllum þarfleysa at hafa hann eptir, en þó má svó sízt eptir hafa hann, at hann sé eigi skrifaðr [÷ bCD]; en þó er þetta þar [÷ D] upphaf á...¹⁵⁹⁹

Again only the first part of the sequence is presented as being recorded, the rest being too dangerous. In the stanza that follows, stanza eight of the saga, the threats are more concentrated, and the second half of the last line, “nema þú vilja minn gjörir,”¹⁶⁰⁰ refers back to the demands in the previous stanzas. This stanza must thus be read as a unit with those that come before it. The prose refers to the stanza as a “þula.”¹⁶⁰¹ The king’s partial agreement to her demands spurs Busla on:

¹⁵⁹⁷ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 16, st. 2, ll. 8-10.

¹⁵⁹⁸ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 18, st. 7, l. 5.

¹⁵⁹⁹ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 18, ll. 12-16.

¹⁶⁰⁰ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 18, st. 8, l. 21.

¹⁶⁰¹ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 19, l. 1.

Þá skal taka þér framm betr, segir Busla; hóf hún þá upp þat vers, er Syrpvers er kallat, ok mestr galdr er í fólgin, ok eigi er lofat at kveða eptir dagsetr, ok er þetta þar í nærri endanum...¹⁶⁰²

The prose emphasis is on ever-increasingly powerful magic from Busla to gain her ends, but the stanza she speaks, *Syrpuvers*, has a rather different emphasis from the others. In the stanza recorded, instead of being directly concerned with freeing Bósi and Herraudr, rather it is presented as a challenge or riddle to the king himself. The way for the king to escape the curse is not to free the men, but rather to answer the riddle she poses: “Komi hér seggir sex, seg þú mér nöfn þeirra / öll óbundin.”¹⁶⁰³ The one stanza given in the prose is said to be from near the end, and the prose seems to make clear that she actually speaks more stanzas that are unrecorded; after the stanza, the prose talks of a point when Busla has finished speaking: “En er Busla hafði úti bænina [÷ D; En er þat var úti b],”¹⁶⁰⁴ which again emphasises the verses’(perhaps ironic status) as a prayer and also implies that there was more to *Syrpuvers* than one stanza.

The stanza from *Syrpuvers* is related to a string of runes in a few manuscripts of the older recension: in three vellum manuscripts from the 15th and 16th centuries (AM 510 4to, 11v; AM 577 4to, 54r; AM 586 4to, 14v) and one paper manuscript Lbs 423 fol., 338v–339r from the 18th century (which Jiriczek does not use in his edition).¹⁶⁰⁵ The curse is connected to a string of runes that mimic or employ an old formula in an unconventional way,¹⁶⁰⁶ but which have been demonstrated to be

¹⁶⁰² *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 19, ll. 4-8.

¹⁶⁰³ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 19, st. 9, ll. 8-9.

¹⁶⁰⁴ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 19, ll. 17-18.

¹⁶⁰⁵ “Lbs 423 fol.,” *Handrit.is*, <<http://handrit.is/en/manuscript/view/is/Lbs02-0423>>, accessed 2nd May 2012; John McKinnell & Rudolf Simek with Klaus Düwel, *Runes, Magic and Religion: A Sourcebook*, *Studia Mediaevalia Septentrionalia* 10 (Fassbaender: Wien, 2004) 139.

¹⁶⁰⁶ I explore the relation of *Buslubæn* to the Old Norse verbal charming tradition in the light of Old and New Philological methods in “Younger Icelandic Manuscripts and Old Norse Studies,” *Approaching Methodology*, ed. Frog and Pauliina Latvala, *RMN Newsletter* (special issue) 5 (2012): 148-161, at 156-157, and much of the material presented here on the rune sequence in the saga is drawn from there. See also Lorenzo Lolli Gallo, “Persistent Motifs of Cursing in Old Norse Literature in *Buslubæn*,” *Linguistica e Filologia* 18 (2004): 119-146; Langer, “*Galdr* e Feitiçaria nas Sagas Islandesas”; Bernt Øyvind Thorvaldsen, “The Poetic Curse and Its Relatives,” *Along the Oral-Written Continuum: Types of Texts, Relations and Their Implications*, ed. Slavica Ranković with Leidulf Melve & Else Mundal, *Utrecht Studies in Medieval Literacy* 20 (Turnhout: Brepols, 2010) pp. 253-267.

unrelated to the old tradition by Claiborne W. Thompson.¹⁶⁰⁷ The runes, transliterated below as “**r.o.þ.k.m.u iiii sssss ttttt iiii llll**,” appear to be the solution to a riddle posed at the end of the curse:

Komi hér seggir sex,
 seg þú mér nöfn þeira
 öll óbundin,
 ek mun þér sýna:
 getr þú eigi ráðit,
 svá at mér rétt þykki,
 þá skulu þik hundar
 í hel gnaga,
 en sál þín
 sökkvi í víti
r.o.þ.k.m.u iiii sssss ttttt iiii llll

Let six men come here
 (if you) tell me their names
 all clearly (or ‘unencrypted?’),
 I will reveal to you:
 if you cannot interpret
 so that they seem right to me
 than shall dogs
 gnaw you to death
 and your soul
 sink in torment.
*Ristill, æstill, þistill, kistill, mistill, vistill.*¹⁶⁰⁸

The runes are an indigenous Old Norse formula found in other places,¹⁶⁰⁹ and the formula seems to have been intended as a locking formula (for example on a chest or grave) and to ward off evil.¹⁶¹⁰ In *Bósa saga*, the runes are integrated into the literary context of the curse and riddle and thus are likely contemporaneous.¹⁶¹¹ As a comparison of the transliterated runes and their rearrangement in the translation shows, the runes are bound and must be rearranged from the way they are written to

¹⁶⁰⁷ Claiborne W. Thompson, “The Runes in *Bósa Saga ok Herrauds*,” *Scandinavian Studies* (1978) 50: 50–56. Cf. Langer, “*Galdr e Feitiçaria nas Sagas Islandesas*,” who argues that *Buslubæn* is indeed indicative of continuity with medieval practical magic.

¹⁶⁰⁸ McKinnell et al., *Runes, Magic and Religion* p. 139.

¹⁶⁰⁹ Collected by Thompson, “The Runes in *Bósa Saga ok Herrauds*,” pp. 51-53 and McKinnell et al., *Runes, Magic and Religion* pp. 134-140.

¹⁶¹⁰ McKinnell et al., *Runes, Magic and Religion* p. 134.

¹⁶¹¹ Thompson, “The Runes in *Bósa Saga ok Herrauds*,” p. 55.

form words; such a cryptographic rearrangement of the runes was normal when this particular charm was written down.¹⁶¹²

Thompson has demonstrated that indeed the curse sequence and its closing riddle-rune section are totally literary, since it depends on the written runes in order to be able to solve the riddle. It thus seems unlikely that the curse and riddle sequence can be linked convincingly to (oral) Old Norse magical practices. Busla is supposed to chant the curse in the saga, but she could not chant the runic formula in its bound form – the runes need to be rearranged first. As such, the sequence is an “optical puzzle” and should be dated to around the 14th century, at the same time as the first written version of the saga was likely to have been written.¹⁶¹³ This seems to make it a late, parodic version of the charm, the older examples of which occur in other, quite different contexts. In addition, its use in the saga as a rounding-off device in the curse sequence is quite meaningless and apparently leads the curse nowhere.

Although in the stanza itself the solving of the riddle is not linked to the freeing of the men, which is Busla’s stated aim in her other stanzas, in the prose following the final stanza of the saga the context is given that the king must solve the riddle to escape the torments she promises him, “nema þú gerir minn vilja” [‘unless you do my will’],¹⁶¹⁴ and the king, at a loss, is forced to enquire “hverr er nú þinn vili?” [‘what is now your will?’].¹⁶¹⁵ Once he has promised to honour his promise to her that Bósi and Herraudr are to be sent away on a mission, “en þá skyldi Buslubæn ekki á honum hrína.”¹⁶¹⁶ The stanzas and prose are thus mixed as to what Busla’s stated demands are.

¹⁶¹² McKinnell et al., *Runes, Magic and Religion* p. 134.

¹⁶¹³ Thompson, “The Runes in *Bósa Saga ok Herrauds*,” p. 55.

¹⁶¹⁴ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 19, ll. 16-17.

¹⁶¹⁵ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 20, ll. 1-2.

¹⁶¹⁶ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 20, ll. 7-8.

In the younger version, the narrative context of Bósi and Herrauðr being in trouble is the same, but the narrative including the verses is introduced differently and is worth quoting at length:

Þetta sama kvöld, sem kóngsson og Bósi voru fangaðir, kom Busla fostra hans að máli við jallinn Brynþvara og mælti: Þú far nú og hjálpa Bósa, syni þínum, sem nú er í fangelsi og fjötrum haldinn með Herrauð kóngssyni. Brynþvara mælti: Til lítils kemur þjer kuklaradómur þinn, forneskja og tungukraptur, ef þú kannt ei að hjálpa honum úr hættu þessari. Busla mælti: Aldri má mjer ver fara heldur en þjer, þar þú liggur nú heima sem hugblauð hormegða¹⁶¹⁷ bikkja ok bannsett þý. Var kelling mjög málóð og gekk burt síðan. Nú skal frá því segja, að Hrólfur kóngur vaknar um nóttina, þar hann liggur í sinni sæng, að hann heyrir, kona gengur inn í húsið; þykkir honum af henni eldur sindra og að öllu ill ásyndar; þessi mælti til hans: Hjer liggur þú, Hrólfur, Gauta kóngur, þig veit eg vera hrak allra manna á jörðunni af þinni allri breytni, af því þú vilt myrða og af dögum ráða þinn eiginn son, og munu allir segja þig hinn vesta níðing og fordæðufól, falsara fordæmdan og fúlasta gauð, leiðan lygara, sem löstrum er bundinn, væri rjettast þjer kólnaði í kjapti [+ en hitnaði í helvízkri boru γδ (last two words in runes in δ)], fyr en þinn flærðarsaman vilja hefðir í þessu, og eg syngi þjer Syrpuvers mitt gamla, og að gjörðri bæn þessari skaltu gásbjúgur gana víða. Sem kóngur heyrði orð þessi, reiddist hann og hugði að standa á fætur og lemja kellingu; sem hann hugði nú þetta að gjöra, var hann fastur í sænginni, so öngvan sinn lim mátti hann hræra. Síðan mælti hún [- ð β]: Nema þú gefir Bósa líf og neitir ei bæn Herrauðar, sonar þíns, skal það allt á þjer hrína, sem og mun fram segja. Kallaði kóngur nú á sinna riddara, er sváfu í forstofunni og bað, þeir kæmi þangað, en það var sem ógjört, því enginn kunni að vakna. Síðan mælti hún: allt það hið illa, sem eg kann að mæla, bið eg á þjer hríni...¹⁶¹⁸

It is notable that here the contents of the first two stanzas in the older version are in prose in the younger version: the fact that the king (called Hringr in the older version, Hrólfur in the younger version) is king of the Gautar,¹⁶¹⁹ that he is going to “myrða” [‘murder’] his own son (the word is used in verse in the older version and in prose in the younger version),¹⁶²⁰ and that everyone in the world will hear about it.¹⁶²¹ The introduction to the stanzas is much longer in the younger than the longer version and the way the scene is built up is more cinematic. The manner in which the information about the scene is distributed in the prose around the stanzas is also different. In the younger version, that the king cannot stand up from his bed and that his men cannot be awakened comes before the stanzas; in the older version, this comes after the first set of stanzas.

¹⁶¹⁷ Cf. modern Icelandic *horaður* ‘emaciated,’ and *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. viii, where he suggests this reading.

¹⁶¹⁸ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 99, ll. 19-28 – p. 100.

¹⁶¹⁹ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 16, st. 1, l. 1; p. 100, l. 7.

¹⁶²⁰ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 16, st. 1, l. 3; p. 100, l. 9.

¹⁶²¹ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 16, st. 1, l. 4; p. 16, st. 2, ll. 7-9; p. 100, ll. 7-9.

In the younger version, the stanzas are also in three groups with prose in between. Unlike in the older version, in the younger version the king is not given a chance to respond. The whole prose and verse complex is a monologue by Busla, and rather than the king in the older version acting defiantly in the prose and telling her to go away, in the younger version he is said to be terrified; and does not speak “en kóngur þagði og bystist” [‘the king was silent and became angry’]¹⁶²² Eventually, when he is given the opportunity to speak, the “kóngur þagði ok tók til að skjálfa” [‘the king was silent and started to shake’],¹⁶²³ and the final challenge found accompanied by runes in some manuscripts of the older version is not present in the younger version. The stanzas too are different between the versions:¹⁶²⁴ the younger version focuses on threats rather than outlining and repeating Busla’s demands in the main body of the prayer. In the younger version, the stanzas are in blocks of four, three and then one and a half, making there more strophes in this version than in the old. In the older version, the prose-verse complex is a lively exchange with well-articulated demands by both parties, whereas in the younger version we find a stream of vitriol from Busla. It is noteworthy that in the younger version the stanzas are referred to only as *Syrpuvers* and not as *Buslubæn*.

In the older version, the stanzas do not carry the content of the saga, only versified threats and demands that are provisional to the prose context of the saga. It thus seems that the stanzas are not older than the prose, but rather have been composed to emphasize Busla’s skills in sorcery, and metre must have been important for giving a magical edge to her words. That the rest of the saga contains no verse also perhaps demonstrates that as such stanzas are not important for reasons of content or

¹⁶²² *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 102, l. 4.

¹⁶²³ *Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 103, ll. 1-2.

¹⁶²⁴ Although there are some similarities, the only stanzas that seem to be related for certain are the eighth stanza in the older version and the fifth stanza in the younger, as can be seen by a comparison of their first few lines:

Old version: “Tröll ok álfar ok töfrnornir, / búar, bergrisar brenni þínar hallir, / hati þik hrímþussar, hestar streði þik” (*Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 18, ll. 17-19).

New version: “Tröll taki þig og töfranornir, / álfar og riser efli þjer mæðu, / hamra hetjur og hellirs gýgjur” (*Bósa-saga*, ed. Jiriczek, p. 102, ll. 6-8).

narrative authenticity in this particular saga; they are included in the Busla episode for aesthetic reasons. The same could be said for the younger version. In this, the content of the two introductory stanzas to the older version seem to be in the prose introduction to the episode. The stanzas in the younger version are more dramatic than in the older version and help sustain a monologue rather than a dialogue. However, they carry even less information related to the prose plot of the saga than the older version and thus are likely contemporary.

In conclusion, it seems that *Bósa saga* is more likely playing on cursing traditions known to the author(s) rather than, for example, preserving a curse from oral tradition. The saga itself with its carefully repetitive telling of Bósi's sexual exploits is not a heroic one, although it is very amusing. The stanzas play a crucial role in the narrative in terms of moving the story on since they are threats that provoke action, but they do not contain material related to the plot of the saga. It is worth noting that the enumeration of threats rather than the actual spell itself in *Bósa saga* is in keeping with similar episodes in Old Norse poetry. Nine stanzas of *Grógaldr*,¹⁶²⁵ fourteen stanzas of *Sigrdrífumál*,¹⁶²⁶ and eighteen stanzas of *Hávamál*¹⁶²⁷ all contain episodes in which lists of *galdrar* are given, but not the spells themselves, and Tom DuBois has pointed out that this, although usually understood as being a “sign of the artificiality of such poetry,” is paralleled in Finnish oral tradition.¹⁶²⁸ Stanzas do not play an important role in structuring the saga either, used only on one occasion by one character as dialogue. The verse is thus likely contemporaneous to the saga prose.

¹⁶²⁵ See Bugge pp. 339-341, stt. 6-14.

¹⁶²⁶ See Bugge pp. 227-236, at pp. 229-231, stt. 6-19.

¹⁶²⁷ See Bugge pp. 43-64, at pp. 62-64, stt. 146-163.

¹⁶²⁸ Tom DuBois, “Dynamics and Continuities of Tradition: What a Finnish Epic Song Can Teach Us About Two Old Norse Poems,” *Dynamics of Tradition: Perspectives on Oral Poetry and Folk Belief. Essays in Honour of Anna-Leena Siikala on her 60th Birthday 1st January 2003*, ed. Lotte Tarkka, Studia Fennica, Folkloristica 13 (Helsinki: Finnish Literature Society, 2003) pp. 233-247, at pp. 235, 237-238.

Bósa Saga and Eddic Prosimetrum

From *Bósa saga*, we can learn that eddic verse in a prose context could have magical connotations, and threats about placing curses on people were perhaps thought more menacing by virtue of the fact they were delivered in verse. This is perhaps highlighted in the saga by the fact that this is the only verse that occurs in the narrative, so it clearly has a special role to play, and eddic verse may in fact have been thought to be the only suitable form for such content.

The Non-Prosimetric *Fornaldarsögur*

Although this thesis is chiefly concerned with the extant prosimetric *fornaldarsögur*, many of the sagas contain no verse. Margeret Clunies Ross has suggested that the sagas without prose represent a moving away from their “traditional poetic base” in the sense of the non-prosimetric form being a development.¹⁶²⁹ On the whole, this is likely because of the similarity and affinity of the *fornaldarsögur* with the *riddarasögur*. These sagas without verse tend to be in the Romance category, as discussed above. The sagas in the Rowe’s Romance category seem to have been influenced by the contact of the vernacular oral genre of the *fornaldarsögur* with the *riddarasögur* texts, and have likely found their non-prosimetric form through this stimulus. Indeed, it is possible that the 13th century translation of the *riddarasögur* into Old Norwegian inspired the writing down of oral *fornaldarsögur* in the first place. While much material in the *fornaldarsögur* genre is older, at the time of the entry of the *riddarasögur* into Old Norse literature the *fornaldarsögur* genre was still a productive one in terms of saga composition, and the *fornaldarsögur* without verses, particularly those in the Romance category that tend to be the youngest, are likely the product of this influence.¹⁶³⁰ The *riddarasögur* were initially translations from continental sources in Norway (translated *riddarasögur*), but indigenous sagas of the type quickly followed (indigenous *riddarasögur*, sometimes referred to as *lygisögur*,

¹⁶²⁹ Judy Quinn et al., “Interrogating Genre in the *Fornaldarsögur*,” p. 277.

¹⁶³⁰ There is not space here to go in to the complex question of why verse romances were translated into prose in Norse, but see Paul Bibre, “From Riddarasaga to Lygisaga: The Norse Response to Romance,” *Les sagas de chevaliers (Riddarasögur)*, ed. Régis Boyer, *Civilisations* 10 (Toulon: Juillet, 1982) pp. 55-74 at 59-61, whose two arguments can be summarised by firstly saying that prose was the preferred target form because unsuitable metres existed in Old Norse, and secondly because the prose saga was the dominant literary art form. Both are interesting suggestions but neither are convincing: as for the first suggestion, Bibre dismisses outright the possibility of translation into skaldic verse (which I agree with, because it was used for completely different purposes), and discounts using eddic verse because it “may not have been culturally acceptable because of the specific associations of these metres with the native heroic myth and poetry” (p. 59); as I commented on above, however, there is a large amount of skaldic-type material in eddic metre, so there must have been a great deal of flexibility in the use of the eddic metres. His second reason, that the *riddarasögur* were translated into prose because it was the dominant art form does not explain why they contain *no* verse at all: translations moulded specifically to fit the dominant art form would have been prosimetric, nor does Bibre’s explanation that the Icelandic saga “developed more or less simultaneously with the European romance during the second half of the twelfth century” (p. 61) help this; this is likely the time of the transition of the saga to the written form, but the native saga form must have existed in oral tradition for a long time before this, prosimetric sagas included.

although the terminology here is fluid).¹⁶³¹ The source material of the translations were long narrative poems, but the translations are in prose. The indigenous sagas, modelled on these translations,¹⁶³² have been well summarised by Paul Bibre as having “abandoned inherited narratives in favour of morphology and motif composition” and do not seem to have developed under the influence of other native saga genres.¹⁶³³ Neither the translated nor indigenous *riddarasögur* contained verses,¹⁶³⁴ and once the native *riddarasögur* was established it likely influenced the *fornaldarsögur* genre. The absence of verses in the *riddarasögur* is thus probably the reason for the absence of the verses in the Romances included in the *fornaldarsögur* genre.¹⁶³⁵

Another reason for the absence of verses in some of the Norse romances, including the *fornaldarsögur*, should likely be sought in the changing fashions in France. The translation of the *riddarasögur* sources into Norse is thought to have taken off in the Norwegian court of King Hákon Hákonarson (reigned 1217-1263) as part of his programme of drawing the Norwegian court closer in culture to its European counterparts: “the general view is that transmission of the new chivalric ideology, as deliberately targeted by Hákon, could be achieved especially effectively through the medium of literature” as part of the “civilising and feudalizing efforts” the king undertook during his reign.¹⁶³⁶ This court programme looked to France, and a

¹⁶³¹ For overviews and references to the most important literature, see the following overview chapters: Jürg Glauser, “Romance (Translated *riddarasögur*),” *A Companion to Old Norse-Icelandic Literature and Culture*, ed. Rory McTurk, Blackwell Companions to Literature and Culture 31 (Malden, MA: Blackwell, 2007) pp. 372-387; Matthew James Driscoll, “Late Prose Fiction (*lygisögur*),” *A Companion to Old Norse-Icelandic Literature and Culture*, ed. Rory McTurk, Blackwell Companions to Literature and Culture 31 (Malden, MA: Blackwell, 2007) pp. 190-204; Marianne E. Kalinke, “Norse Romance (*Riddarasögur*),” *Old Norse-Icelandic Literature: A Critical Guide*, ed. Carol J. Clover & John Lindow, *Islandica* 65 (Ithaca, NY: Cornell UP, 1985) pp. 316-363.

¹⁶³² Marianne Kalinke proposes the model for the development of the *riddarasögur* from a translated to an indigenous genre thus: “(1) Norwegian translation; (2) Norwegian/Icelandic copy; (3) Norwegian/Icelandic revision; (4) Icelandic adaptation; (5) Icelandic recreation.” See Marianne E. Kalinke, “Norse Romance (*Riddarasögur*),” p. 345.

¹⁶³³ Paul Bibre, “From Riddarasaga to Lygisaga: The Norse Response to Romance,” p. 62.

¹⁶³⁴ With a couple of exceptions: the translation of *Equitan* in the *Strengleikar* collection contains two Latin distichs. Of the indigenous sagas, a version of *Mágus saga* has three stanzas.

¹⁶³⁵ Bibre also discusses the possibility that the *fornaldarsögur* genre may have influenced the *riddarasögur* genre, although in the main concludes that such influence seems “consciously to have been avoided,” in “From Riddarasaga to Lygisaga: The Norse Response to Romance,” pp. 55-74, at 73.

¹⁶³⁶ Jürg Glauser, “Romance (Translated *riddarasögur*),” p. 375.

great deal of the source material for the translations was drawn from Old French *chansons de geste* (French heroic poetry), courtly romances (*roman courtois* and *lais*) and *fabliaux*.¹⁶³⁷ The literary fashions in France were changing, however, at the same time as Hákon was trying to align his literary milieu with the type of texts in favour. Prior to the thirteenth century in France, prose in the vernacular was only used for, Gabrielle M. Spiegel lists, “juridical texts, charters, translations of the Bible, and homiletic works.”¹⁶³⁸ However, the course of the 13th century, the use of prose spread to almost every written genre, and this necessitated “the recasting of many earlier romance works into the newly prestigious medium,” and prose was dominant by 1270.¹⁶³⁹ This change could not have gone unnoticed in Norway, and even French poetic material was likely translated in Norse prose under its influence.

Scholars have sought rather to emphasise the difficulty in drawing sharp lines between the various sagas genres belonging to the romance tradition; this is too large a topic to be gone into here, but is well summarised by Marianne E. Kalinke,¹⁶⁴⁰ who points to the danger that grouping sagas too definitely into either the *riddarasögur* category or *fornaldarsögur* category precludes the study of interrelationship between the two groups.¹⁶⁴¹

¹⁶³⁷ For a brief overview of some of the translations stemming from French material, see Glauser, “Romance” p. 373.

¹⁶³⁸ Gabrielle M. Spiegel, *Romancing the Past: The Rise of Vernacular Historiography in Thirteenth-Century France*, *The New Historicism* 23 (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1993) 56.

¹⁶³⁹ Spiegel, *Romancing the Past* p. 56. See further the second chapter of the same book, “*Psuedo-Turpin* and the Problem of Prose.” See also Renate Blumenfeld-Kosinski, “The Earliest Developments of the French Novel: The *Roman de Thèbes* in Verse and Prose,” *The French Novel: Theory and Practice*, ed. Michel Butor, French Literature Series 11 (Columbia, S.C.: The University of South Carolina, 1984) pp. 1-10, at p. 6 ff.

¹⁶⁴⁰ Marianne E. Kalinke, “Riddarasögur, Fornaldarsögur and the Problem of Genre,” *Les sagas de chevaliers (Riddarasögur)*, ed. Régis Boyer, *Civilisations* 10 (Toulon: Juillet, 1982) pp. 77-87.

¹⁶⁴¹ Marianne E. Kalinke, “Riddarasögur, Fornaldarsögur and the Problem of Genre,” p. 77.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this thesis was to explore the role of eddic verse in prose contexts, particularly in the *fornaldarsögur*, with comparative material drawn from pre-Edda texts *Sverris saga*, *Fagrskinna*, *Íslendingabók*, and *The First Grammatical Treatise*. I used these to explore the various roles of verse, particularly in *Fagrskinna*, where I argued that the accretive use of verse was an important feature of the text. In my analysis of *Gylfaginning*, I suggested that it may have been written first of all the sections in *Snorra Edda*. I also argued that its eddic prosimetric structure shows influences from the Latin textbook as well as the vernacular tradition, that its quotational pattern of stanzas is quite deliberate in places, particularly with regard to *Grímnismál*, and that it is a notable feature of *Gylfaginning* as well as of *Fagrskinna* that evidence verses tend to end the episode in which they occur.

I used the concept of episode to look at the structure of the prosimetric profile of the *fornaldarsögur*, extracting each episode from the sagas that contain verse and looking at them individually. That these episodes or sequences in the *fornaldarsögur* constitute specific sense units is supported by the fact that, after the end of a sequence (or indeed frequently simply the quotation of a single stanza), the narrative moves directly on to another topic, without pausing to comment on the stanza thus included. I argued that the *fornaldarsögur* in some form existed in oral tradition, and that it was possible this was in the form of a relatively long prose narrative. The use of verse sense units to mark the end of a saga may also be noted: it is said in the account of the wedding at Reykjahólar that the saga had a good *flokkur* at the end. This may have been one oral method of marking the end of saga; examples can be found in *Qrvar-Odds saga*, *Ásmundar saga kappabana*; *Friðþjóðs saga* (as a prayer) and *Ragnars saga loðbrókar*.

I argue that it is unlikely that the *fornaldarsögur* originated directly from prosimetric material of the same type as found in the *Poetic Edda*. The sagas do not have the air of the type of poetry contained in the heroic section of the *Poetic Edda*, because many of the prominent examples are structurally different. *Fornaldarsögur* such as *Hervarar Saga*, *Qrvar-Odds saga* and *Hálfs saga* have been constructed by pulling together

longer poems, with the poetry as distinct units. The longer poems themselves are not heavily prosimetric like the poems found in the *Poetic Edda*, and rely on the prose framework of the saga to unify the narrative. Otherwise, the *fornaldarsögur* are predominantly constructed by assembling dialogue pieces that were likely prosimetric in the oral period, or are imitative of such an oral dialogue. The *fornaldarsögur* likely developed from “many stanzas,” probably similar to the long units which are extant in the written sagas.

From the structural analysis of *Gylfaginning* and the *fornaldarsögur*, it seems that the oral *fornaldarsögur* could have perhaps promoted the idea of using eddic rather than skaldic verse in a narrative style where skaldic verse was more usual in early written texts (as evidence stanzas). This may have been particularly true of *Völsunga saga*, which may have provided an early model for the extensive use of eddic verse quotation in prose narrative. *Gylfaginning* perhaps helped to prompt the writing down of the *fornaldarsögur*, and may have also prompted eddic poetry to be assembled in a large collection. The extensive use of evidence verses in a *fornaldarsaga* may point towards an older age for that prosimetric section of the saga, and this may be due to influence from the *konungasögur*. They may have contributed the idea that in order for a narrative to be credible, it must include evidence stanzas, particularly in written tradition. However, *fornaldarsögur* usually include predominantly speech stanzas, and this was also likely the case in the oral tradition. The influence of the *konungasögur* may have given rise to the verses identified in sagas like *Gautreks saga* where stanzas are both quasi-evidence and quasi-speech stanzas.

Verse is used in the *fornaldarsögur* for several reasons: in moments of high emotion and perhaps also to assert the superiority of the speaker. This is perhaps visible in situations, for example, where a man encounters a supernatural creature and addresses them in verse. The use of verse in order to demand the identity of an opponent and to provide one’s own identity and place of origin also seems traditional.

The prosimetric structure of accretive verse in *Fagrskinna*, *Gylfaginning* and the *fornaldarsögur* is the same, with all the texts frequently employing the tag “and yet he

said” between the first stanza quoted and subsequent verses in situations where a number of verses appear consecutively.

An important difference between the eddic and skaldic prosimetric tradition illustrated in my analysis of the pre-*Edda* texts and the eddic tradition captured in the *fornaldarsögur* is the tradition of dialogues in verse. Often in the *fornaldarsögur*, the stanzas encountered are spoken by characters within the narrative as dialogue. Often these seem to be either singular stanzas or a unit of dialogue stanzas that go together. It is not clear whether these dialogue stanzas that seem to travel together can be conceived of as a poem in their own right. Of the skaldic tradition, John Lindow comments: “The men who etched the great prose narratives in Old Norse used skaldic stanzas to illustrate their points; at least in their role as narrators they were not interested in entire skaldic poems.”¹⁶⁴² In the eddic tradition found in the prosimetra of the *fornaldarsögur*, it does not seem that the *lausavísa* drawn from complete poems played as substantial a part in furnishing stanzas to be included in the prose narrative. There are two kinds of exceptions to this. The first is when saga characters speak or quote stanzas from the *Poetic Edda*, as in *Völsunga saga* or *Norna-Gests þáttur*. Another exception to this is in *Órvar-Odds saga*, in which stanzas from the long poem found at the end of the saga are also quoted within the prose narrative in a manner that I have argued is a device to add verisimilitude to the saga. This use of evidence verse may also be under the influence of the *konungasögur*, as the saga is rather old. The eddic and skaldic tradition in a prosimetric context thus might share the disinterest in whole poems, but the eddic tradition may not have even had the lengthier skaldic poems (reconstructed by the likes of Finnur Jónsson and Russell Poole) to extract singular stanzas from.¹⁶⁴³

¹⁶⁴² John Lindow, “Narrative and the Nature of Skaldic Poetry,” *Arkiv för nordisk filologi* 97 (1982): 94-121, at 99.

¹⁶⁴³ Cf. Whaley on the skaldic tradition: “The two kinds of use [of verses] in the prose sagas correspond largely with the presumed original status of the verses. Authenticating verses tend to come from long compositions, normally royal panegyrics, while situational verses tend to be singletons, *lausavísur*, often referred to in English as occasional verses. The equation of authenticating verses with excerpts from long poems and situational ones with *lausavísur* does not, however, always hold.” Whaley, “Skalds and Situational Verses in Heimskringla,” p. 253.

The *fornaldarsögur* seem to include dialogues in poetry particularly when they take place between a human and a supernatural creature. The first reason this might be is to display heightened emotion in the narrative: the surprise of encountering such a beast might be thought sufficient by the saga author to include a section that is highlighted from the surrounding prose by including verse. This seems plausible, since it tends to be a human who starts a verse exchange with a supernatural creature. The second reason could be that speaking in verse contributes to the air of mystery about the being from the other world. The third reason, in contradiction to reason number two, could be that speaking in verse in reply to a human places the supernatural creature on an equal narrative footing with the human speaker of stanzas. Equality in the dialogue makes for a more spirited and balanced exchange, helping the aesthetic of the dialogue in the narrative. A fourth reason might be that the dialogue was always in verse in the tradition of a particular saga, and was transmitted right the way into written tradition in a prosimetric format. It could also be that some of these verse dialogues were composed by a saga author to make their saga sound like a *fornaldarsaga*; this is likely the case with *Hjálmþés saga*, in which the prosimetric dialogues are highly stereotypical and imitative.

The *fornaldarsögur* have relatively lengthy sections of speech in dialogue. This has no apparent parallel in the skaldic tradition, and likely comes from oral eddic tradition. The extremely long prosimetric dialogue scenes in *Hjálmþés saga* is probably playing on *fornaldarsaga*-stereotypes rather than suggesting that such long scenes could exist orally. Very long speech scenes do exist, but they are monologues rather than dialogues (for example *Hrókskviða* in *Hálfs saga*).

It seems more important in the prose context of eddic poetry in the *fornaldarsögur* to provide a strong performance context for the stanza in the narrative than it does for the pre-*Edda* material, although the notion of *Begleitprosa* suggests an interest in a performance context in the oral period for both *fornaldarsögur* and *konungasögur*, since such a context is partly what the accompanying prose might provide.

Prosimetric scenes form the building blocks of many of the *fornaldarsögur*, and *lausavísur* may also form the nucleus of episodes. The placement of poems and prosimetric episodes in the sagas may have been a conscious decision on the part of the saga author, to add variety to his narrative, to provide interest at the opening and close of the saga, or to conform to tradition (for example by having a long poem at the end of the saga).

Written prosimetra as found in the *fornaldarsögur* should be understood as the result of the codification of prosimetric oral narratives; the various roles of verse found within them replicates oral narrative strategies of telling, of transmission and of authentication. The situations in which verse is used in the *fornaldarsögur* likely represent similar situations in which verse was used in oral narrative. Evidence based verse may be prominent only in the written tradition of the *fornaldarsögur*, or if the authenticating element was heavily used in the oral tradition of the material, it was lost in the majority of cases in the transmission from the oral to the written. In the *fornaldarsögur*, authentication of the narrative seems to have worked on a different dynamic, for example through autobiographical validation of prehistory (Clunies Ross).

Some differences between prosimetrum in the oral and written traditions can be suggested. In oral tradition, likely the emphasis would have been on the stanza rather than the prose. Oral prosimetra are suggested by cases where the verse is obviously older than the prose, by length pieces of dialogue in eddic verse and by longer poems contained in clusters. Evidence based stanzas are likely part of the written tradition. They introduce an element of repetition, and tolerance of this likely reflects the fact that the culture was familiar with continued oral traditions. By using evidence stanzas at the end of episodes, units in the saga are created similar to those found in oral narratives (Quinn). The oral culture was thus a necessary precondition for some aspects of the written tradition. Quotation of eddic stanzas in the manner of *Gylfaginning* and perhaps *Völsunga saga* is a phenomenon of the written tradition of eddic prosimetrum.

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Abbreviations

Bugge = *Norræn fornkvæði: Islandsk samling af folkelige oldtidsdigte om nordens guder og heroer, almindelig kaldet Sæmundar Edda hins fróða*. Ed. Sophus Bugge. Universitetsforlaget, 1965 [1867].

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